

LANDMARC

D2.6: CASE STUDY SCALING SCENARIO FINAL REPORT

**INPUT FOR SIMULATION MODELLING OF SCALING LAND-BASED MITIGATION
SOLUTIONS IN THE LANDMARC CASE STUDY COUNTRIES**

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LANDMARC

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Dissemination and uptake	<i>This deliverable provides an overview of qualitative information per country on the realistic scaling potential of one or more land-based mitigation solutions (LMT portfolios) in a series of LANDMARC case study countries (including Germany, The Netherlands, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine, Burkina Faso, Kenya, South Africa, Indonesia, Nepal, Vietnam, Canada, and Venezuela). This qualitative information serves as input for simulation modelling done with the following models: DayCent (time series biogeochemical model), ALCES (web-based land use change simulation model), LandSHIFT (global / regional land use change simulation model), E3ME (macro-econometric model)</i>
Short Summary of results	
<p>This document provides an overview of qualitative information that has been collected for the assessment of the scaling potential of national LMT portfolios in the respective case study countries. The qualitative information has been collected via literature review and a range of stakeholder engagement activities (e.g., interviews, workshops). The qualitative information has been synthesised or codified in more structured tables as a first step to translate or codify the qualitative information into inputs relevant for the scenario modelling within the LANDMARC project. These results feed into two upcoming deliverables (October 2023).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - D5.3 Model run outputs from model set (e.g., DayCent, ALCES, LandSHIFT, and FaBIO) - D5.5 E3ME model simulations 	
Evidence of accomplishment	
This report.	

Preface

Negative emission solutions are expected to play a pivotal role in future climate actions and net zero emissions policy scenarios. To date most climate actions have focussed on phasing out fossil fuels and reducing greenhouse gas emissions in, for example, industry, electricity, and transport. While zero emission trajectories in these sectors will remain a priority for decades to come, it is expected that residual GHG emissions will remain. To be able to fulfil the Paris Agreement and meet the world’s climate goals research, policy and markets are increasingly looking at negative emission solutions.

This is why the nineteen LANDMARC consortium partners work together to:

- Estimate the climate impact of land-based negative emission solutions, in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors,
- Assess the potential for regional and global upscaling of negative emission solutions,
- Map their potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs,

LANDMARC is an interdisciplinary consortium with expertise from ecology, engineering, climate sciences, global carbon cycle, soil sciences, satellite earth observation sciences, agronomy, economics, social sciences, and business. There is a balanced representation of partners from academia, SMEs, and NGOs from the EU, Africa, Asia, and the Americas, which ensures a wide coverage of LMTs operating in different contexts (e.g., climates, land-use practices, socio-economic etc.) and spatial scales.

The LANDMARC project consortium:

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Purpose of this document

This document provides an overview of qualitative information (literature review and stakeholder engagement) that has been collected by the LANDMARC country case study partners for the assessment of the realistic scaling potential of national portfolios of land-based mitigation solutions (LMTs). This qualitative information is presented in the form of *narratives* or *storylines* (see Annex II), as well as a series of tables in which an effort has been made to translate or codify the qualitative information into inputs to be used in simulation modelling (see **Annex III**).

Chapter 1 introduces the methodological approach the LANDMARC research team has taken to co-design and/or co-create scaling scenarios for both individual land-based mitigation solutions (LMTs), and LMT portfolios within the respective (#14) countries. Chapter 1 also provides an overview of the simulation model suite applied within LANDMARC, as well provides a rationale for co-creation of scaling scenarios with local (national) level stakeholders.

Chapter 2 provides an overview table of the availability of qualitative narratives / storylines per country, and the application of simulation models to the respective LMT or LMTs per country. The descriptive section in Chapter 2 provides a condensed overview of the main development trajectories or scenarios to be used for simulation modelling derived from **Annex III**.

Chapter 3 provides a more cross-cutting or thematic synthesis of all national LMT narratives / storylines for all 14 LANDMARC case study countries where simulation modelling will be applied (see **Annex II**).

1. Introduction

In this Chapter we briefly discuss some of the concepts (Sections 1.1 and 1.2), simulation modelling tools (Section 1.3) and the methodological approach (Section 1.4) the LANDMARC research team has taken to co-create scenarios scaling up the implementation of individual land-based mitigation solutions (LMTs) as well as LMT portfolios (Section 1.5) within (#14) LANDMARC case study countries.

1.1 Narratives, storylines, or scenarios?

Within this interdisciplinary research project (LANDMARC), researchers from different cultural and scientific backgrounds (e.g., simulation modelling, social, and natural sciences) are collaborating to create new knowledge and insights. With respect to advancing our common understanding of the impacts of scaling portfolios of land-based mitigation technologies and practices (LMTs)¹ there has been ample debate and sometimes confusion with respect to the proper use of terminology for simulation modelling. Are we talking about development scenarios, narratives, or storylines?

Within LANDMARC we follow the logic of a *'storyline approach'*, such as stressed by (Shepherd, T.G., Boyd, E., Calel, R.A. et al., 2018). They propose an alternative approach to represent uncertainty in the physical aspects of climate change simulation modelling. Within the 'storyline' approach there is more *"emphasis on qualitative understanding rather than quantitative precision."* This more qualitative approach highlights the existing limitations of probabilistic approaches used in climate change simulation modelling. While some authors (Shepherd, T.G., Boyd, E., Calel, R.A. et al., 2018) mainly refer to climate change scenarios based on simulation modelling, the logic for a storyline approach also applies to other types of simulation modelling, where increasing complexity such as portfolio-option based approaches can be developed.

1.2 Stakeholder engagement & co-creation

A more qualitative approach to the elicitation and creation of possible future scenarios also has merit in other fields of simulation modelling, aside from earth systems modelling (ESM). In the field of transition scenario studies, economic and land-use modelling - which study the impacts on and from human or socio-economic systems on the environment - the codified, technocratic, and/or stylized (i.e., quantitative) approaches to scenario design often can hamper effective and meaningful engagement/participation, and co-creation of plausible futures, particularly with non-expert stakeholders.

For example, (Faehn, T. and Stoknes, PE, 2023) suggest that: *"involving a relatively broad transdisciplinary stakeholder group [... can] be extremely rewarding in the first, explorative phase of the [scenario design process]"*, while in the second phase i.e., the translation of the qualitative

¹ e.g., afforestation, agroforestry, peatland rewetting, no tillage, crop-/grassland management, biochar, BECCS

narratives into quantitatively modelled scenarios (or pathways), stakeholders with more “*specialised technical skills, training within economic and technological numerical modelling and insight*” would be needed.

This report is the product of a series of stakeholder engagement activities carried out in 14 LANDMARC case study countries², complemented with literature review to advance our qualitative understanding of the key factors (drivers, and constraints) and dynamics of implementing a range (portfolios) of LMTs nationwide (i.e., scaling) within each country. This work has been conducted by the LANDMARC country case study partners, with great support from many local and indigenous stakeholders (e.g., local communities, farmers, land/forest owners or managers, investors, AFOLU sector advisors, companies, local, and national policy makers, researchers) who have shared their views and perspectives via interviews, follow-up information exchanges, focus groups, and workshops. Thus, while the storylines (or narratives) are written and edited by the respective LANDMARC country case study leaders, they are an attempt to reflect the combined, and shared knowledge and information gathered throughout the research process and (at the time of writing) still ongoing stakeholder engagement activities.³

1.3 Simulation modelling

Within the LANDMARC project simulation modelling is pursued with the following five models:

1. **DayCent:** DayCent is a daily time series biogeochemical model used in agroecosystems to simulate fluxes of carbon and nitrogen between the atmosphere, vegetation, and soil. Model inputs include daily maximum/minimum air temperature and precipitation, surface soil texture class, and land cover/use data. Model outputs include daily fluxes of various N-gas species (e.g., N₂O, NO_x, N₂); daily CO₂ flux from heterotrophic soil respiration; soil organic C and N; net primary productivity; daily water and nitrate (NO₃) leaching, and other ecosystem parameters. DayCent has been tested with data from various native and managed systems.

² Germany, The Netherlands, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine, Burkina Faso, Kenya, Indonesia, Nepal, Vietnam, Canada, Venezuela.

³ Special effort has been put on ensuring that the stakeholder engagement process within the LANDMARC project was sufficiently inclusive, and that all relevant perspectives (e.g., minorities, gender and indigenous) are represented. However, despite these efforts, we acknowledge that specific (inter)national events (e.g., political instability, recession, COVID-19), as well as our own limitations (time and resources) unintentionally may have resulted in an imperfect engagement / participatory process and representation.

We strongly encourage those (research) projects, policy makers, companies and communities that seek to make use of the results of the LANDMARC project to build upon and strive for a more inclusive and representative engagement process.

It is our shared belief that a (global, national, local) transition without adequate participation and representation will not be effective (i.e., resulting in low acceptance and low speed of implementation). This transition process already starts in the exploratory stages of research into plausible / feasible futures.

2. **LandSHIFT:** LandSHIFT (Land Simulation to Harmonize and Integrate Freshwater Availability and the Terrestrial Environment) is a land use change model for global and regional scale simulation experiments. its principal objective is to simulate the interactions of socio-economic drivers and the biophysical environment determining land use and land use changes and to assess the impacts of these changes on human society and the environment. The model design aims at delivering a tool that can play a central role in scenario analysis projects.
3. **E3ME:** The E3ME model is a macro-econometric model with global coverage designed to address major economic and economy-environment policy challenges. E3ME features integrated treatment of the world's economies, energy systems, emissions, and material demand. This enables it to capture two-way linkages and feedbacks between these components. The model is characterized by a high level of disaggregation, enabling detailed analysis of sectoral and country-level effects in global analysis.
4. **ALCES:** The ALCES software creates cumulative effect models that simulates changes in landscape composition and related indicators in response to LMTs and other drivers, such as natural disturbances and climate change. ALCES will be communicating scenario outcomes via web-based dashboards made of dynamics maps and graphs. This tool also has the capacity for comprehensive simulation of co-benefits as is required for trade-off analysis across case-studies.
5. **FaBIO:** FABio (Forestry and Agriculture Biomass Model) is a simulation model created using the method of system dynamics and agent-based modelling of biomass production and use in agriculture and forestry and describes their impact on certain environmental indicators.

1.4 Translating storylines into model inputs

Throughout the co-design process LANDMARC's country case study leaders have gone through the four following basic steps:

1. Literature review eliciting a long-list of land-based mitigation technologies and practices that can be scaled in the respective country,
2. Stakeholder elicitation (often interview) based shortlisting of LMTs that are deemed most relevant or promising by stakeholders,
3. Creation of qualitative storylines (narratives) of LMT portfolios gathering complementary information from different sources (literature, stakeholders),
4. Generating national LMT scaling scenarios portfolios (based on storylines) to serve as input for simulation modelling.

Both step one [1] and two [2] focussed on narrowing down the scope of the research activities, to a) limit it to manageable levels, and b) ensure a high level of relevance. With respect to identifying the most 'relevant' or 'promising' LMTs for a given country we did not developed a prescribed set of selection technocratic or quantifiable criteria, such as e.g., technical scaling potential, or lowest cost option, lowest land claim and/or most favourable public acceptance. We intentionally left the shortlisting of LMTs up to the specific LANDMARC researcher who was informed by stakeholders and ongoing (public and political) debates and other developments within the respective country. While

this may have created in a certain bias for some LMTs, we believe that LMT prioritization of the specific focus of low-carbon transition research should build more on stakeholder (society, or community) driven or participatory decision-making approaches (i.e., is not only the privilege of researchers). Moreover, the creation and prescription of a set of measurable criteria by researchers for selection may just as easily have created certain biases.

The drafting of the qualitative storylines [3] has gone through several iterations or revisions. The country reports (see **Annex II**) are the final product of these iterations.⁴

The final step in this process [4] was to make a first effort to translate these qualitative storylines into more quantified scenarios that could be used in simulation modelling. One of the main challenges here was to generate or extract key values, numbers and/or parameters from the storylines that would be fitting or matching with key model input parameters and assumptions.

Continued dialogue and information exchange between the modelling experts and country case study leaders in the project has shown that it is challenging to standardize and harmonize this process. For instance, to make it fully transparent and objective given the different characteristics of the selected LMTs and LMT portfolios, as well as specific country context (e.g., differing socio-economic drivers/constraints and dynamics). To address this inter- and transdisciplinary challenge, the iterative dialogue between modelling experts and country case study leaders, as well as engaged external national stakeholders has resulted in the development of a guide to enable the codification of storylines into input for scenario simulation modelling (see. **Annex I** ‘A stepwise approach to generate LMT scenarios including input for LANDMARC model simulations’). This guide was developed by J. Onigkeit, M. Laub and J. Lieu.

1.5 Modelling LMT portfolios

Simulation models traditionally, have been used to explore the magnitude of specific socio-economic and/or environmental impacts associated with introducing a new technology or practice into an existing system (e.g., ecosystem, economic system, social system). For example, energy transition studies have benefited from using simulation models to explore for example the (integrated) impacts, co-benefits, trade-offs of scaling e.g., solar PV systems, bioenergy systems and/or phasing out nuclear or coal fired power generation systems. Also, in the area of land-based mitigation technologies and

⁴ Initial, and draft versions of these storylines were developed within the context of the LANDMARC project and have been part of the following project specific outputs:

- Milestone 6: Initial draft report with national scaling scenarios
- Deliverable 2.1: Case study scaling scenario advanced DRAFT report

These two outputs have not been circulated publicly, to prevent spreading and using of different versions of a similar document. The two previous versions in combination with this new ‘final’ version reflect the changes of ongoing co-creation and subsequent improvements in the storylines. Follow-up co-creation actions, and dynamic developments could build upon these storylines and further refine and develop them as the collective knowledge and perspectives evolve.

practices there has been an accumulation of studies focussing on assessing the impacts of scaling specific LMT practices such as agroforestry, afforestation, BECCS deployment, or a regional roll-out of biochar plants and application.

While it is scientifically appealing to perform ‘*ceteris paribus*’ simulation modelling for a single technology or practice, real-world transitions (e.g., energy, bioeconomy, circular economy, mobility, industry) are increasingly facing the (un)expected consequences of the aggregated impacts of different actions, measures or events that are implemented in parallel or occur at the same time. To reach net zero by 2050 rapid deployment and scale up of a wide portfolio of mitigation (reduction) and carbon dioxide removal measures will be required in roughly the next three decades.

With respect to the assessing the impacts of implementation of land-based mitigation technologies (LMTs), negative emission technologies (NETs) or carbon dioxide removal (CDRs) solutions, there is a need for more integrated or holistic simulation modelling approaches that capture the dynamics of implementing a suite or ‘portfolio’ of mitigating measures. For example, realistic future scaling scenarios for afforestation, are only viable if proper account has been given for the future scaling of BECCS and/or biochar. Similarly, with respect to the usage of land and biomass, BECCS and biochar – in principle – are two competing (or alternative) solutions for producing renewable energy and delivering permanent carbon dioxide removals.

Portfolio-based simulation modelling approaches are expected to increase in importance, in areas of land-use, economic, and climate modelling (e.g., IAMs, ESMs). The inability to adequately represent (i.e., to model) may increasingly become a limitation for providing robust and actionable evidence-based support for policy makers, decision makers and communities in relation to the transition towards a more sustainable, net-zero economy and society. We need to improve models to consider:

- a) specific mitigation and/or removal solutions (e.g., LMTs, NETs, and/or CDRs) or full options-portfolios,⁵
- b) the dynamics of interlinkages (i.e., synergetic vs. conflicting or symbiotic vs. parasitic), between different options within a portfolio,
- c) or deliver more regionally and spatially explicit assessment results useful for decision makers at the local or regional scale/level⁶

⁵ Within LANDMARC regional/global simulation modelling efforts for LMT scaling are pursued. The combinations of simulation models used (i.e., LandSHIFT-G, and EC-Earth3-GCM) do not (yet) allow for inclusion of specific LMT solutions. For this reason, the focus is put on a more limited portfolio with 5 LMTs, including: afforestation, no/reduced tillage, agroforestry, enhanced irrigation and BECCS.

⁶ Ongoing EU-funded research projects such as the RESCUE project ([link](#)) focus on integrated assessment and earth systems (IAM/ESM) modelling of expanded CDR portfolios. Current IAM/ESM simulation modelling efforts typically include a relatively limited set of CDRs (e.g., mainly BECCS, DACCS, biochar, forest management and afforestation) and/or do not (yet) provide regionally/spatially disaggregated simulation results.

The coupled model systems that are currently used make a probabilistic approach informed by stakeholders (e.g., local knowledge and experience) less and less practical. The sheer (technical) complexity of such systems and the specific parameters and values required as modelling input may eventually alienate and frustrate many non-expert stakeholder groups. Here, qualitative and storyline-based approaches can capture more than one specific option and include a broader portfolio of options. This inclusion of a wider portfolio may help to keep relevant stakeholders actively engaged in the co-creation process. By putting more emphasis on co-creating a more qualitative, holistic/integrated understanding of scaling different LMT portfolios, the fundamental drivers, and constraints will become more apparent to broader stakeholder groups. Such a participatory co-creation processes (provided it is sufficiently inclusive and representative) may eventually foster the creating of a shared vision and belief upon which to act.

2. Overview of results from translating storylines into model inputs

As indicated in Section 1.4 the LANDMARC country case study leaders were requested to synthesise or translate the information from their national LMT portfolio narratives (see **Annex II**) in a specific table format (see **Annex I**). The results of this ‘translation’ per country are presented in **Annex III**. In this section we provide an aggregated overview (Section 2.1) and brief discussion (Section 2.2) on key development and scaling trajectories for LMTs for each country.

2.1 Overview

Table 1 provides an overview of the application of different LANDMARC simulation models (see Section 1.3) per country and per LMT. Some of the LANDMARC case study countries have provided a storyline for a larger LMT portfolio (e.g., The Netherlands, Spain), while others have focussed on a more limited set of LMTs (e.g., Germany Venezuela).

In most cases the DayCent simulation modelling is linked to one (or two) specific LMTs and is not used to derive results for a full LMT portfolio. FaBIO simulation modelling is only applied to one specific LMT in the German country case study.⁷ The LandSHIFT simulation model is also applied in a more limited set of case study countries, but in most cases targets the full national LMT portfolio (i.e., Switzerland, Burkina Faso, Indonesia, and possibly Ukraine⁸). Both the E3ME and ALCES simulation models generally aim to capture the economic or land use change dynamics / impacts of full national LMT portfolios, but more limited coverage of LMTs may also be possible.

Table 1 provides an overview of the (planned, executed) application of all LANDMARC simulation models and their linkage to a respective case study country and LMTs/LMT portfolio. **Annex II** and **Annex III** provide resp. the qualitative input to serve as a starting point for simulation modelling, as well as full descriptions of the national LMT portfolio narratives.

Table 1 also shows which country-LMTs are not yet included in simulation modelling. The respective qualitative information on these LMTs provided in **Annex II** and **Annex III** can also be used by third parties (e.g., other research projects, simulation modelling teams):

- to build on and further develop their own storylines for LMT scaling in a respective country and/or
- to perform their own LMT portfolio model simulations

⁷ The FaBIO simulation model is not part of the original model set in LANDMARC but was applied as a result of stakeholder collaborations and synergies for the German case study.

⁸ The decision to deploy LandSHIFT and ALCES simulation modelling in Ukraine is still pending and will depend on the availability of (external) funding.

Country	LMT portfolios	DayCent	E3ME	LandSHIFT	ALCES	FABio
Germany	Forest management		X			X
	Afforestation					
	Soil carbon – mineral soils					
	Soil carbon – organic soils					
Netherlands	Afforestation		X		X	
	Agroforestry	X	X		X	
	Peatland rewetting		X		X	
	BECCS (manure AD-based CCS)		X			
Portugal	Cropland management					
	Pastures (Montados)	(X)				
	Agroforestry (Montados)	(X)				
	Forest management					
Spain	Forest management				X	
	Afforestation / reforestation	X			X	
	Agrosilvopastoral land (Dehesas)				X	
	Grassland management				X	
Sweden	Forest management					
	Afforestation / reforestation					
	BECCS		X			
	Biochar		X			
Switzerland	Agroforestry		X	X	X	
	Organic agriculture	X	X	(X)	X	
	Reduced / no tillage	X	X	X	X	
	BECCS					
	Biochar					
Ukraine	Agroforestry (shelterbelts)			X	X	
	Organic farming	X		(X)	X	
	Reduced / no tillage	X		X	X	
	Bioenergy			(X)		
Burkina Faso	Agroforestry	(X)		X	X	
	Cropland management			(X)	(X)	
	Forest management	X		(X)	(X)	
	Afforestation / reforestation			X	X	
Kenya	Afforestation					
	Agroforestry					
	Integrated soil fertility	X				
South Africa ⁹	N.A.					
Indonesia	Reforestation			X	X	
	Peatland management			(X)	X	
	Agroforestry			X	X	
	Soil carbon (biogas & compost)		X			
	Cropland management			(X)	X	
Nepal	Forest management				(X)	
	Afforestation / reforestation				X	
	Agroforestry				X	
	Organic farming				X	
	Improved rice management				X	
Vietnam	Agroforestry				X	
	Biochar (coffee husks)					
	Afforestation / reforestation				X	
Canada	Afforestation		X		(X)	

	Wetland restoration		X		(X)	
Venezuela	Forest management (integrated)	(X)			X	

Table 1: Overview of LMT portfolios and (intended) application of simulation models per country.

X = more detailed application of the simulation model indicates higher quality, reliability of the data information used, and more robust co-design approach applied for respective LMT.

(X) = less detailed application of the simulation model indicates lower quality, reliability of the data information used, and less robust co-design approach applied for respective LMT.

- The DayCent simulation modelling partner within LANDMARC is ETH Zürich (ETHZ)¹⁰
- The E3ME simulation modelling partner within LANDMARC is Cambridge Econometrics (CE)
- The LandSHIFT simulation modelling partner within LANDMARC is University of Kassel (UNIK)
- The ALCES simulation modelling partners within LANDMARC are TU Delft (TUD) and ALCES

2.2 Description

2.2.1 Germany

The German LMT portfolio with developed (qualitative) storylines includes four LMTs, including i) forest management, ii) afforestation, iii) soil carbon enhancement in mineral soils, and iv) soil carbon enhancement in organic soils (peat/wetlands). Simulation modelling with the FaBIO and E3ME model will be applied to forest management.

The key storyline trajectories developed by the country case study leader (Oeko Institute) covers three alternative development or deployment scenarios for all LMTs. The *reference scenario* is geared towards supporting regenerative and restoration practices, while at the same time few additional restrictions are put on continuation of existing economic activities, such as agriculture on organic soils or the continued use of existing managed forests for wood supply. The second and third scenario are resp. labelled as ‘*achieve existing targets*’ and ‘*green supreme*’. Both scenarios combine the reference scenario with additional (policy) limitations by taking forest area and agricultural soils out of production and reduce livestock (dairy/meat) production to free up land for alternative uses. The key difference is that that the second scenario seeks for compliance with existing climate and environmental targets, while the third scenario works with more ambitious targets.

By limiting the scope of existing economic activities in the AFOLU sectors in Germany, complementary support schemes, revenue streams and business models for farmers and forest owners will need to be in place to support a more radical transition.

⁹ The South African case study is solely serving LANDMARC research on improving the earth observation practices for better monitoring of the carbon cycle. Hence, this EO-specific case study is not included in any (qualitative) storyline development or simulation modelling with ALCES, E3ME, LandSHIFT and/or DayCent. More information on this case study can be found here ([link](#)) or here ([link](#)).

¹⁰ Additional DayCent modelling runs will be performed for non-LANDMARC case study sites, in France, and Australia.

2.2.2 The Netherlands

The Dutch LMT portfolio with developed (qualitative) storylines includes four LMTs, including i) afforestation, ii) agroforestry, iii) peatland rewetting, and iv) CO₂ capture applied to biogas production facilities based on anaerobic digestion of liquid animal manure. Simulation modelling with both the E3ME and ALCEs model will be applied to the full LMT portfolio.

The key storyline trajectories developed by the country case study leaders (JIN Climate & Sustainability and Bioclear Earth) covers three alternative development scenarios for all LMTs, which are closely linked to the future scale/size of the Dutch livestock sector (mainly dairy cattle and pig farming).

The *base case* assumes a business-as-usual scenario where the existing (intensive) livestock farming practices, with associated land use, economic benefits and socio-environmental costs remains roughly at current levels. Although this scenario, is incompatible with a range of environmental and climate policy targets the political process and public debate appears to be at an impasse. Two alternative transition scenarios are considered. The first one considers a significant forced reduction of the size of the livestock sector thereby freeing up land for scaling of the more nature based LMTs, such as agroforestry, peatland rewetting and afforestation. The second alternative scenario envisages a more moderate (forced) reduction or buy-out of a share of the livestock farmers, which is combined with the upscaling of biogas production based on anaerobic digestion of (remaining) liquid animal manure. The biogas production facilities can enable the replacement of fossil energy as well as deliver organic fertilizers (to replace chemical fertilizers) and capture biogenic CO₂ (from biogas treatment) which can be stored underground or used in other applications (e.g., food industry).

By limiting existing livestock farming activities in agriculture in The Netherlands, complementary support schemes, revenue streams and new business models for farmers will be needed to be in place to support a more radical transition. Currently, the economic outlook for farmers for the nature based as well as the engineered transition scenario is uncertain / risky. There may be a case for a hybrid transition scenario, where both the nature-based and the engineered LMT scenario co-exist, but are tailored to fit local (e.g., soil, climatic, environmental, and socio-economic) conditions.

2.2.3 Portugal

The Portuguese LMT portfolio with developed (qualitative) storylines includes four nature based LMTs, including i) forest management, ii) agroforestry (Montados), iii) pastures (Montados) and iv) cropland management. Simulation modelling with DayCent will be applied the montados system (combination of agroforestry and grassland pastures).

The key storyline trajectories developed by the country case study leader (AgroInsider) for forest management and agroforestry covers two alternative development scenarios. The *reference scenario* is aiming to maintain the current situation which is assuming it will lead to further degradation of natural capital i.e., ongoing losses in biodiversity and soil/forest degradation and lower resilience and vitality of ecosystems. The alternative development scenario assumes an upgrading of the valuation of natural capital and ecosystems. For this to manifest significant additional amounts of external public

and or private finance (e.g., via the voluntary carbon markets) would be required to make the overall ecosystems and local communities more resilient. For cropland and grassland management only one future development trajectory is indicated. For cropland management sustainable agricultural practices through precision farming to conserve soil health and water are ‘prescribed’. Similarly, biodiverse pastures rich in legumes and grasses are ‘prescribed’ as the single future development trajectory. Both development trajectories appear to suggest that regenerative and biodiversity promoting grass- and cropland management can almost be seen as a minimum condition (‘conditionality’) to be able to sustain some form of productive plant and livestock farming in Portugal under expected future climate conditions.

2.2.4 Spain

The Spanish LMT portfolio with developed (qualitative) storylines includes four nature based LMTs, including i) agrosilvopastoral land management (Dehesas), ii) grassland management, iii) forest management, and iv) afforestation / reforestation of degraded agricultural areas. Simulation modelling with the DayCent will only be applied to afforestation/reforestation, while ALCES simulation model will be applied to the full LMT portfolio.

The key storyline trajectories developed by the country case study leader (Ambienta) covers three alternative development or deployment scenarios for all LMTs. The *reference scenario* is geared towards maintaining some sort of status quo or conservation with respect of the management and use of agricultural, semi-natural, natural and forest land. The two alternative development trajectories present both a positive and negative development scenario. The negative development scenarios for all four LMTs are closely linked to the ongoing depopulation of Spanish rural areas. Linked to that decline is a relatively poor economic outlook and development for rural populations, that will leave more and more land unmanaged, which may give rise to increasing desertification and wildfires. The alternative (positive) development scenario aims to create more favourable socio-economic conditions for rural populations, which can help mitigate the negative effects of climate change on the landscapes, improve ecosystem services driven by better economic outlook for rural populations.

By promoting additional (economic and eco-system service) activities in the rural areas, the landscape management systems can be improved, providing a range of potential co-benefits. This, however, will require a fundamental shift in rural and economic development policies.

2.2.5 Sweden

The Swedish LMT portfolio with developed (qualitative) storylines includes two engineered LMTs, including i) BECCS, and ii) biochar as well as afforestation and forest management. Simulation modelling with the E3ME simulation model will be applied to BECCS and biochar.

The key storyline trajectories developed by the country case study leader (SEI) covers a ‘low cost’ and a ‘high cost’ development scenario for both engineered LMTs. The low-cost scenario will result in a higher deployment rate of BECCS and biochar, which is based on assumption of relatively low biomass,

and energy prices as well as low costs for CO₂ transport and underground CO₂ storage. The high-cost scenario reflects the reverse, where overall system costs are higher than anticipated.

To fund, or incentivise these LMTs, a mixture of private and public schemes (e.g., voluntary carbon market) is considered, where the low-cost scenario considers ambitious carbon pricing and other complementary policies.

2.2.6 *Switzerland*

The Swiss LMT portfolio with developed (qualitative) storylines includes three nature based LMTs, including i) organic agriculture (soil carbon), ii) reduced / no tillage, and iii) agroforestry. Simulation modelling with DayCent will be applied to both soil carbon enhancement oriented LMTs (organic agriculture and reduced / no tillage). In addition, both (ALCES and LandSHIFT) as well as the E3ME simulation model will be applied to the full Swiss LMT portfolio.

The key storyline trajectories developed by the country case study leader (ETH Zürich) covers three development trajectories for all LMTs, where the reference scenarios assume a continuation of current practices (or status quo) in terms of land use and agricultural practices. The two alternative development trajectories for the LMT portfolio consider a moderate scaling as well as an ambitious scaling trajectory.

To understand the potential magnitude or impact of scaling these LMTs nationwide, for example by 2050 almost no conventional tillage practices would remain, and about 50% of the permanent grasslands would be under silvopastoral management (agroforestry). For such ambitious development (or scaling trajectories) robust incentive schemes and policies would need to be in place.

2.2.7 *Ukraine*

The Ukrainian LMT portfolio with consists out of three nature based LMTs, including i) organic farming, ii) reduced / no tillage, and iii) agroforestry. In addition, one engineered LMT, bioenergy (biogas from agricultural feedstocks) is considered. More detailed qualitative storylines/narratives for Ukraine are not available as Ukraine was added as a country case study at a later stage during the LANDMARC research process. Simulation modelling with DayCent will target organic farming and reduced / no tillage, whereas both ALCES and LandSHIFT simulation is intended to be applied to all three nature based LMTs.¹¹

The key storyline trajectory developed by the country case study leaders (TUD / ISSAR) covers a 'balanced mix' approach where implementation of all four LMTs at a certain scale is deemed most desirable. However, depending on the specific LMT this scenario the specific ambitions differ and for each LMT a high, mid, and low deployment scenario is made. No/reduced tillage practices would have

¹¹ The implementation of simulation modelling with ALCES and LandSHIFT is dependent on complementary (external) funding.

to be scaled nationwide to reach 13-50% of arable land by 2050, as well as substantial agricultural area would have to be under organic farming management and about 5-15% of arable land needs to be converted into shelterbelts (agroforestry). Also, for biogas developments the ambitions are significant (1,5 – 3,5 bcm m³ of biomethane) and should be feasible given the much larger technical potential for scaling.¹²

2.2.8 *Burkina Faso*

The Burkinese LMT portfolio with developed (qualitative) storylines includes four nature based LMTs, including i) agroforestry, ii) cropland management (soil carbon), iii) forest management, and iv) afforestation / reforestation. Simulation modelling with DayCent will be applied to forest management and agroforestry, while efforts will be made to apply ALCES and LandSHIFT modelling to the full LMT portfolio¹³.

The key storyline trajectories developed by the country case study leader (eLEAF) covers three development trajectories for all LMTs, where the reference scenarios assume a business-as-usual (or stay as current) development in terms of land use (forest and agricultural practices). The two alternative development trajectories for the LMT portfolio consider a moderate scaling (slow growth) as well as an ambitious (max growth) scaling trajectory.

To understand the potential magnitude or impact of scaling these LMTs nationwide, for example by 2050 almost all farms would have to deploy organic cropland management practices and all forest areas are protected and sustainably managed. In addition, a resp. 70% (2030) and 150% (2050) growth of land under agroforestry management is applied, and a 5% (2030) and 15% (2050) increase of forest cover would have been achieved. For such ambitious development (or scaling trajectories) robust incentive schemes, capacity building, policies, and (inter)national support would need to be in place.

2.2.9 *Kenya*

The Kenyan LMT portfolio with developed (qualitative) storylines includes three nature based LMTs, including i) afforestation, ii) agroforestry, and iii) integrated soil fertility management (ISFM). Simulation modelling with DayCent will be applied to ISFM.

For Kenya, a range of ISFM scenarios for DayCent simulations have been co-developed with stakeholders compared to the baseline (no/little input) during a workshop. These scenarios are the use

¹² Outside the scope of the LANDMARC project, a small research project has been set up between Ukrainian (Institute for Soil Science and Agrochemistry Research, and Adverio Engineering UA) and Dutch (JIN Climate & Sustainability and Adverio Engineering NL) partners to assess different development scenarios for biogas development and deployment in Ukraine, post-war. The small project, titled: **“Post-war recovery and energy independence strategy through biogas deployment in Ukrainian agriculture”** is funded via a small grant from the TPM (Technology, Policy, and Management) faculty, Energy Transitions Lab from TU Delft.

¹³ Cropland management (organic farming) and forest management may be incorporated in the LandSHIFT modelling with less detail due to data and resource limitations.

of organic inputs (farmyard or green manure) at medium or high (1 or 2 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) or the use of mineral N only (at 30, 60 or 90 kg N ha⁻¹) and the combined use, i.e., real “integrated” soil fertility management at medium and high rates. The simulations will thus effectively cover an option space for farmers at different levels of resource availability.

Annex II provides the qualitative storylines for the Kenyan LMT portfolio. Since, only DayCent simulation modelling will be applied in Kenya no specific input table for simulation modelling (see **Annex III**) for Kenya has been made.

2.2.10 Indonesia

The Indonesian LMT portfolio with developed (qualitative) storylines includes four nature based LMTs, including i) afforestation, ii) agroforestry, iii) peatland management, and iv) cropland management and one engineered LMT targeting soil carbon enhancement, namely the deployment of small-scale anaerobic digesters for biogas production and compost/organic fertilizer production. Simulation modelling with ALCEs, LandSHIFT will focus on all four nature based LMTs, while E3ME simulation modelling will be applied to biogas and compost systems to enhance soil carbon.

The key storyline trajectories developed by the country case study leader (Su-re.Co) covers two development trajectories for all LMTs. Both a ‘High’ and ‘Low’ ambition scenario is considered for all LMTs, where the low ambition scenario generally aims for compliance with existing targets or current efforts, predominantly relying on domestic regulations, internal enforcement and monitoring and funding sources. A key generic conditional for the high ambition scenarios for all LMTs is that more external sources of international funding, capacity building and support are assumed to be needed.

2.2.11 Nepal

The Nepalese LMT portfolio with developed (qualitative) storylines includes five nature based LMTs, including i) forest management, ii) afforestation, iii) agroforestry, iv) organic farming, and v) improved rice management. Simulation modelling with ALCEs will be applied to the full LMT portfolio.

The key storyline trajectories developed by the country case study leader (SPRU) covers three development trajectories for all LMTs. The reference scenario assumes limited or partial growth of more sustainable land management practices (all five LMTs). The two alternative development trajectories present resp. a moderate and ambitious scale up of these LMT practices.

Simulation modelling with ALCEs, may reveal any potential conflicts in terms of land use. On top of that the proposed development trajectories may have certain co-benefits in terms of reduced usage (and imports) of chemical fertilizers, revitalization of degraded lands, biodiversity, and climate resilience gains. Potential trade-offs could entail a lower level and productivity of domestic food supplies. Proposed development trajectories suggest a strong reliance on national subsidies and regulations. However, some international funding support may be required to support the transition and dampen possible increases in domestic food prices.

2.2.12 Vietnam

The Vietnamese LMT portfolio with developed (qualitative) storylines includes three LMTs, including i) agroforestry, ii) biochar (from coffee husks), and iii) afforestation/reforestation. Simulation modelling with ALCES will be applied to the upscaling of agroforestry practices and afforestation / reforestation.

The key storyline trajectories developed by the country case study leader (CIAT) covers two development trajectories for agroforestry and two for biochar. Agroforestry scaling is assumed to result either in a conversion of 50% or nearly all current monocropping systems. For biochar scaling either half or all the coffee wastes are converted into biochar. However, for the second scenario two varieties are designed, where the end use market differs (i.e., biochar for export market as activated carbon or biochar for domestic use for soil application).

Simulation modelling with ALCES, may reveal any potential conflicts in terms of land use. The proposed development trajectories suggest a strong reliance on national subsidies and regulations.

2.2.13 Canada

The Canadian LMT portfolio with developed (qualitative) storylines includes two nature based LMTs, including i) afforestation, and ii) wetland restoration. Simulation modelling with ALCES and E3ME will be applied to the full LMT portfolio.

The key storyline trajectories developed by the country case study leaders (TUD & Innolab) covers three development trajectories for all LMTs. The reference scenario assumes limited (minimal compliance) efforts made by logging and oil and gas industries with respect to land reclamation practices in relation to cutlines and wetlands. This scenario would allow continuation of such economic practices with minimal compliance land reclamation practices. The second development trajectory would entail the protection / conservation of most remaining natural landscapes and aim for a moderate or limited restoration of affected landscapes. The third development trajectory is the most ambitious with almost all wetland under conservation/restoration practices and all cutlines fully restored.

Simulation modelling with ALCES, may reveal any potential conflicts in terms of land use in areas where afforestation / reforestation and/or rewetting may occur (or could be combined). E3ME simulation modelling could provide insights in the overall economic impact on the oil and gas and timber industries.

2.2.14 Venezuela

The Venezuelan LMT portfolio with developed (qualitative) storylines includes one main nature based LMTs, namely Integrated fire management (IFM). This LMT builds strongly upon indigenous knowledge and populations with respect to forest fire management. Simulation modelling with DayCent is considered and modelling with ALCES will be applied.

The key storyline trajectories developed by the country case study leaders (COBRA) covers three development trajectories IFM. The reference scenario assumes that traditional/indigenous fire management practices remain prohibited, while modern fire management strategies do not prevent the periodic megafires (fuel accumulation). The other two development trajectories consider resp. a limited and high level of acceptance and scaling of indigenous IFM. The limited scaling of IFM is a result of a weak policy framework and low enforcement, whereas the high level of IFM scaling considers a more robust, nationwide policy, enforcement, and funding framework for forest conservation and IFM.

Simulation modelling with ALCES, may reveal any differences in impacts on landscapes and effectiveness of forest fire management under (currently banned) indigenous practices versus conventional or regulated forest fire management.

3. Synthesis of national LMT portfolio storylines / narratives

This chapter synthesises all 14 national LMT portfolio storylines by elaborating on some common cross-cutting themes. This will allow the reader to achieve a contextualized understanding of the main topics addressed in the Case Study Country LMT portfolio storyline documents presented in **Annex II**.

3.1 Land use

Land use plays a critical role in developing scaling up trajectories, as most (nature based) LMTs involve some form of change in land use. While local ecosystems have the potential to accommodate some LMTs, their implementation must comply with regional land use constraints, such as high population density, food (or other resources) security, or limited usable land due to alpine or desert/degraded landscapes. When there is intense competition for land, techniques that are less land-intensive or can be combined (e.g., agroforestry) are given priority.

For instance, in Switzerland, where most land is either urbanized, dedicated to intensive farming, protected forests (with already high carbon stocks), or alpine, BECCS and biochar are the preferred LMTs since they can be applied without significant domestic land use competition (biomass can be imported). However, these two techniques compete for biomass, and it must be considered that their combined mitigation potential is not the sum of their individual potential. These LMTs can be combined by applying BECCS to the production of biochar, increasing the mitigation potential without significantly increasing land competition. However, if BECCS must be applied through the production of domestic biomass not derived from residues, it could lead to increased land competition.

From a land use perspective, agroforestry can be understood a form of combined land use which could alleviate land use competition, as observed in Kenya and Switzerland scenarios. However, agroforestry still needs to comply with food and income security as its implementation can result in significant yield decreases.

Land use changes are expected to face more competition in most countries due to population growth and the further implementation of often land-intensive renewable energy, with some countries facing more specific challenges in food and energy security, as expressed by Germany. Sanctions on Russia following the war in Ukraine have increased the demand for locally produced food and energy, further intensifying land competition by the widespread implementation of renewable energy generation.

In terms of land-use, sustainable agriculture offers interesting potential for scaling up by increasing carbon stocks without substantially changing land use or competing for land, as demonstrated by case studies in Switzerland, Indonesia, Kenya, and Burkina Faso. Sustainable agriculture encompasses a wide range of practices, such as mulching, reduced tillage or specific local practices. Due to the variety of practices sustainable agriculture encompasses, the mitigation potential and carbon permanence of some techniques are not yet well understood. An added advantage of sustainable agriculture is that it

is not significantly susceptible to further climate risks than conventional agriculture, as these techniques introduce some changes to the already used methods rather than replacing them by completely different practices. Moreover, it can provide added market value, although this depends on local public awareness or access to internationally recognized certifications, which are not always easily obtainable for smallholders. Additionally, increasing land competition in countries with significant forest covers could result in deforestation.

3.2 Alignment with national priorities

When assessing the potential of LMTs to scale up, it is important to carefully consider their mitigation potential as well as other co-benefits, as sometimes the latter can outweigh the former. This is particularly relevant for developing countries that have historically low contributions to climate change and where priorities align more with climate adaptation, poverty alleviation, and food security rather than with mitigation. In such scenarios, BECCS often does not play a major role, as it does not provide significant ecological co-benefits beyond mitigation. Moreover, in many developing countries, competition for biomass is high, as crop and forest residues constitute a large share of household energy sources or are fed to livestock.

For instance, Burkina Faso's LMT portfolio has been defined based on the NDC plan, which prioritizes actions that increase soil health and harvest security over mitigation. Locally adapted sustainable agriculture actions provide advantages over mainstream industrial agriculture by increasing water and nutrient retention, mitigating erosion (an increasingly important threat, particularly in the north of the country), and rising food security while contributing to increasing soil carbon without compromising land competition. This is also the case in Kenya or Nepal, where rice is key to food and income security, and dry seeded rice features both security and climate change mitigation advantages.

Aligned with the countries' NDC and/or national plans to increase the forest area by 2030, the scenarios of Kenya, Vietnam, Sweden, Nepal, and the Netherlands include forest actions within their portfolios. In addition, agrosilvopastoral techniques such as *dehesas* and *montados* are included in the Spanish and Portuguese scenarios. Both countries are prioritizing the further development of these traditional low-intensity (i.e., extensive) farming techniques as a way to make climate change mitigation and sustainable livestock production compatible.

On the other hand, for industrialized countries with high energy consumption and less domestic competition for biomass, BECCS is often the technique with the highest mitigation potential. For example, Sweden has identified BECCS as the key technique for achieving net-zero emissions by 2045. The combination of BECCS and Biochar is interesting, as biochar complements BECCS by bringing in the environmental co-benefits that BECCS lacks, although biochar often plays a complementary role in terms of mitigation, as identified in the Swedish scenario.

In specific contexts, biochar has been identified as a very advantageous option. For example, Vietnam is a country with a very intensive agriculture system that produces a lot of agricultural residues. Using them to produce biochar is a traditional technique that allows improving the soil's quality. However, it

must be considered that these circumstances only apply in cases where the competition for biomass is low, such as Vietnam, but this could change if BECCS is implemented at a larger (regional or global) scale.

One of the main challenges of aligning the LMT portfolio to national priorities is to ensure that they are also sustainable. For instance, Portugal's eucalyptus trees sequester three times more carbon than local species while needing less maintenance, but they degrade the land. A similar case applies to Vietnam and Nepal, where afforestation with rapidly growing or high-timber-value tree species is often prioritized because of higher revenues in terms of carbon credits or wood, but they are detrimental in the long term as they constitute monocultures that decrease diversity and provide few(er) ecosystem services.

When co-benefits are the priority and funding is scarce, land regeneration (e.g., accelerating vegetation growth in an existing forest) yields better results both for adaptation and mitigation than implementing techniques that imply land-use change, while also being less exposed to climate-change related disturbances. This is exemplified by the narratives of Burkina Faso and Kenya.

Fire management can provide significant co-benefits for soil fertility and biodiversity, especially in ecosystems that are adapted to naturally occurring fires. Controlled fires can temporarily reduce carbon stocks, but they can also prevent larger and more destructive fires. These co-benefits have been considered in the Venezuelan scenario.

3.3 Future perspectives

Global warming is expected to have a widespread impact on various systems and to alter the application and effectiveness of low emission mitigation techniques (LMTs). Developing countries, which are heavily reliant on primary sectors, are likely to experience more pronounced effects compared to industrialized nations. As a result, implementing LMTs that enhance climate resilience is particularly important for developing countries. While some effects of global warming may lead to increased carbon stocks, such as the rise of the tree line to higher altitudes in alpine areas, such as expressed by the Swiss scenario, or the expansion of forest areas in boreal regions, it is generally detrimental to climate change mitigation.

The rise in pests is an ongoing trend that is expected to intensify in the coming years, as noted by the Spanish and Dutch narratives. To ensure the success of LMTs, it is essential to design and implement strategies that avoid monocultures and incorporate suitable plant species to minimize the exposure to parasites. Climate change is also expected to increase the risk of forest fires, and current fire suppression policies may need to be re-evaluated to incorporate controlled fires that prevent destructive mega fires.

Climate change is expected to largely increase forest fire-prone conditions. Most governments apply a zero-fire policy, meaning that every forest fire should be avoided, and forest fire management actions are almost exclusively directed to forest fire suppression. With a higher incidence of megafires, fire

management policies will need to change to allow for small scale, controlled forest – where possible in combination with using livestock grazing to manage undergrowth - fires that mitigate the risk for more destructive big fires.

Finally, as detailed in Deliverable 4.1: Climate Risk Assessment and Initial Risk Management Plan (Picon & Spijker, 2022), climate change is (bringing and) expected to bring more climate extreme event, potentially creating disturbances in the techniques, and affecting their effectiveness, as mentioned in all scenarios. LMTs possess variable degrees of exposure to climate disturbances, with engineered solutions being often regarded as the least vulnerable. However, disturbances in temperatures and rain patterns could heavily affect afforestation efforts, especially in the early phases, growth patterns of grasses and legumes, or yields of more sensitive crops such as coffee. This could compromise carbon stocks provided by the techniques and the general success of the techniques.

3.4 Institutional, social and policy contexts

Some of the challenges the implementation of LMTs face is the lack of information and data regarding carbon stocks and soil composition. This makes it difficult to assess the effectiveness of the implemented action or to set a baseline that would allow for the participation in carbon markets. This is particularly relevant for developing countries, where capacity to perform widespread soil studies is scarce, especially in vast and sparsely populated areas, as was expressed by the scenarios of Kenya and Burkina Faso.

Political stability and security also play a role in the successfully implementing these techniques, as policy frameworks and funding schemes must remain stable for land users to trust and use them. Low political stability disincentivizes investments and actions that bring benefits in the long term and prioritizes short-term results and the continuation of known practices, a consequence of the so-called 'poverty trap'. This was explicitly expressed by the scenario of Burkina Faso.

LMTs also face bureaucratic challenges regarding their definition, as expressed by the Dutch, Spanish and Portuguese narratives. A necessary condition to create policies around a technique is to be able to define it, but certain LMTs, such as agroforestry, are difficult to define (how many trees per hectare and with which distribution constitute an agroforestry system? Do agricultural or livestock farming incentives apply to dehesas and montados?). Policymakers will need to address these topics to allow for the creation of supportive regulatory frameworks.

Demographic changes are also expected to challenge the implementation of LMTs; a worldwide trend towards rural emigration to urban areas will translate into a decreased availability of labour (i.e., depopulation) in rural areas and an increase in labour costs. This has two implications; the first is that LMTs that decrease costs and labour requirements will have a greater upscaling potential, such as dry seeded rice in Nepal. Second, LMTs that foster the active involvement of local communities will help slowing down or reversing this trend, such as Dehesas and Montados in Spain and Portugal or forest management in Nepal. Linked to this fact is the potential decrease in regulatory support for activities

in rural areas as higher rates of the population concentrate in urban areas, further removing the attention and priorities from the countryside and hindering the development of these techniques.

References

Faehn, T. and Stoknes, PE. (2023). Involving stakeholders in scenario-building: Lessons from a case study of the global context of Norway's climate policies. *Frontiers in Environmental Science: DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2023.1048525>*.

Picon , C., & Spijker, E. (2022). *CLIMATE RISK ASSESSMENT AND INITIAL RISK MANAGEMENT PLAN*.

Shepherd, T.G., Boyd, E., Calel, R.A. et al. (2018). Storylines: an alternative approach to representing uncertainty in physical aspects of climate change. *Climatic Change*, 555-571.

Annex I

A stepwise approach to generate LMT scenarios including input for LANDMARC model simulations.

This guide was developed by J. Onigkeit (University of Kassel), with support from M. Laub (ETH Zürich), and J. Lieu (TU Delft) and provided to the LANDMARC case study leaders.

Summary of procedure

Context: Co-develop qualitative storylines of LMT development and potential with stakeholders:

This has been developed via the development of qualitative narratives for the LMT portfolio in the country (2 years). Now we need to translate the narratives/storylines into a usable scenario storyline. These are the steps to translate the narratives. This process is estimated to take around 6 months:

- **Consider realistic potential:** Define the type of scenario you would like to develop for each LMT in the portfolio and give a name to it (E.g., a scenario for a plausible maximum of LMT implementation until 2050 in contrast to a scenario with medium LMT implementation). **By Case Study leads**
- **Scenario-storyline development for each LMT (see Table 2):** Based on the interview results - summarized in LANDMARC deliverables D4.1 (*Climate risk assessment*) and D5.2 (*Results from risk, co-benefit and trade-off assessments*) and associated workshops and other stakeholder engagement activities - translate the opportunities and risks for each LMT implementation that are relevant for a country into a scenario-specific set of measures and actions (e.g., policies, education/training on technologies and practices, funding etc.). These actions together could, for example, either delay and/or hinder or promote the implementation of a particular LMT. This scenario-specific set of actions would need to be defined for each LMT option (e.g., agroforestry, paludiculture, etc.) and each scenario period (2020-2030 and 2030-2050). **By Case Study leads**
- **Quantifying pace of implementation for each LMT (see Table 3):** These qualitative trends must be quantified in a meaningful, realistic, and transparent way. What will be the percent change of LMT area relative to the current situation or in hectare LMT realized? To make this quantification realistic, information on historic trends, existing national policy targets or targets under discussion from the country narratives (D2.6) or other sources should be used. It is important to give as much evidence as possible to the quantified storylines. The outcome of this final step can then be used by the simulation models to quantify LMT scenarios under the given qualitative scenario storylines. **By Case Study leads and modeller**
- **Running LMT portfolio simulations:** Implement quantified scenario assumptions and perform model simulations. **By modellers**
- **Present initial results** (scenario storylines and simulations) **to stakeholders.** Modify scenarios including model input if necessary. **By Case Study leads, modellers, and stakeholders**
 - **Documentation:** make transparent and assessable how the assumptions were made inspired by stakeholder statements
- Final model simulations. **By modellers**

- **Present & report case study findings:** in LANDMARC deliverables D5.3 (Model run outputs from model set) and D5.5 (E3ME model simulations), publications, presentation to stakeholders and others. *By modellers and Case Study leads*

Translating SH preferences to qualitative storylines

Aim of scenario development: including stakeholder’s knowledge into LMT portfolios. This reference table will be used for inputs for ALCES, LandSHIFT and E3ME and provide indirect guidance for DayCent scenario development. This is an initial table that will be updated throughout the next months to document the development of story lines in case studies.

Step 1

- Draft qualitative storylines by identifying measures and actions from interviews (including D5.2) for each LMT scenario.

Table 2: Qualitative Storylines of implementation for each of the LMT options

Country X LMT 1:

	1. What are the wishes of the future for the LMT: include timing	2. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How much does it cost? • Who pays for the cost? • Who implements? 	3. Target/Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • policies, strategies, projects
Scenario 1: “ ” Stakeholder representations:			
Scenario 2: “ ” Stakeholder representations:			
Scenario 3: “ ”			

Country X LMT 2:

	4. What are the wishes of the future for the LMT: include timing	5. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How much does it cost? • Who pays for the cost? • Who implements? 	6. Target/Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • policies, strategies, projects
Scenario 1: “ ” Stakeholder representations:			

Scenario 2: " "			
Stakeholder representations:			
Scenario 3: " "			

Step 2

Quantitative storylines: pace of implementation for each LMT.

- Please fill the following table with expected qualitative trends on speed of change resulting from the storyline drafts from previous step.
- Provide sources from literature and interviews (include reference section).

Table 3: Quantitative trends/pace of implementation of LMT options

Year	Current situation (baseline)	SCEN-“ ” SH perspective:		SCEN-“ ” SH perspective:		SCEN-“ ” SH perspective	
		2030 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2050 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2030 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2050 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2030 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2050 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)
LMT 1:							
LMT 2:							
LMT 3:							

ANNEX II

REPOSITORY OF STORYLINES/NARRATIVES FOR SCALING OF NATIONAL
LMT PORTFOLIOS

LANDMARC

**SCALING LAND-BASED MITIGATION SO-
LUTIONS IN GERMANY**
LMT NARRATIVE AND SCENARIOS

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1. Introduction

This document presents the potential of LMTs in Germany identified within the LANDMARC project. It explores the scope for national level simulation modelling, delivers the co-design of LMT narratives and taps into current political measures that will influence the performance of LMTs in Germany. The LMT portfolio and estimates of their potential to remove CO₂ or reduce GHG emissions are based on a thorough literature review and a stakeholder validation. The analysis builds on existing work in ongoing (BioSink¹ and DIFENS²) and completed projects (dena 2021).

For the narratives, information collected and provided in the dena-study (dena 2021) was mainly used as this study addresses the main aspects of potential, risks and benefits of LMTs. To estimate risks and opportunities (T.4.1) a questionnaire was distributed to collect expert opinions on each of the LMTs. The results complement the findings from the dena-study.

The identification of stakeholders followed recommendations given in the stakeholder mapping tool. For the case study, a national stakeholder network was established, including stakeholders from forest authorities, private forests, and science were identified. Regarding the continental stakeholder network, actors from governance, NGOs, and science were identified. Interactions with stakeholders were performed in different formats, such as workshops, phone calls, working sessions, work meetings but also on more official occasions such as dialogues organized by ministries.

2. Overview of potential of LMTs in Germany

2.1 Introduction

In 2021 the German government agreed in its Federal Climate Protection Act on the national target of considerably reducing GHG emissions until 2030 and reaching GHG neutrality by 2045. GHG neutrality is planned to be achieved by compensating remaining emissions in 2045 through CO₂ removals by natural sinks. Therefore, the government has also set up net sink targets to be achieved by the sector of Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF).

In 2018, the land use sector in Germany represented a net sink of approximately -30 Mt CO₂e. Significant amounts of CO₂ were captured from the atmosphere by forests (-67 Mt CO₂e) and stored by wood

¹ <https://www.ifeu.de/projekt/biosink/>

² <https://www.difens.de>

products (-3 Mt CO₂e). Above- and below-ground biomass played a major role in CO₂ sequestration (-50 Mt CO₂e) in the forest. In addition, considerable amounts of carbon were sequestered in the mineral forest soil (-16 Mt CO₂e). In contrast, emissions occurred on land under arable land (16 Mt CO₂e), grassland (15 Mt CO₂e), settlements (6 Mt CO₂e) and wetlands (4 Mt CO₂e) (UBA 2020).

Prognos et al. (2020) published pathways for achieving GHG neutrality in Germany until 2045 and 2050. The estimates provide potentials for emission reductions and for LMTs to compensate residual emissions mainly from the agricultural sector. The technological potential for land-based negative emissions is particularly high in the industrial and energy sector by applying BECCS. The scenario also assumes measures to ensure that the LULUCF sector remains a net sink for CO₂. The study assumes that forests in Germany could remove about the same amount of CO₂ as BECCS.

Table 1 gives an overview of German LMTs and their potential for emission reductions and removals. In the following sections, we will discuss options of LMTs in Germany within the context of the LANDMARC project scope (long-list of options). We then discuss which LMTs seem most promising for supporting Germany's target of climate neutrality in 2045. This set of LMTs is referred to as 'short list' (see Table 1).

Table 1: Overview of LMT potential in Germany

LMT	Source	Area (1.000 ha)		Specific potential* (t CO ₂ e/ha)		Total potential** (Mt CO ₂ e)		Additional costs EUR/t CO ₂ e	Bio-mass PJ/Mt
		2030	2050	2030	2050	2030	2050		
BECCS (industry sector)	[1]					15	37		
BECCS (energy sector)	[1]						3		
Re-wetting of organic soils	[2]	-	300-900	-	20-40	-	7,0-15,2	2-380	
	[1]	278	650	25,2	27,7	7	18		
Abandoning peat extraction	[1]	18	18	122	122	2,2	2,2	28	
Avoided conversion of grassland	[2]	34,1	34,1	73 -91		2,5 - 3,1		15 – 60	
Afforestation	[2]	400	850	4,7	4,7	18	120	159	
Managing forests incl. HWP	[4]	10.900	10.900	2,8	2,9	31	32		
	[5]	10.400	10.400	3,8	6,5	40	68		

Increasing SOC on agricultural land	[3]	3.100				0,3 – 0,4			
Total negative emissions		25.130,1	23.152,1 – 23.752,1	231,5 – 249,5	183,8 – 203,8	116 – 116,7	287,2 – 295,4	204 - 627	
Total required biomass									
CO ₂ -transport per 250 km at 10 Mt/y									
CO ₂ -storage under sea									

*Specific potential= potential per unit area **Total potential= potential on total area

[1] Prognos et al. (2020)

[2] BMEL (2016b)

[3] Wiesmeier et al. (2017)

[4] Rüter et al. (2017)

[5] (Böttcher et al. 2018b)

2.1.1 Technologies dependent on biomass / photosynthesis

BECCS within the industrial and energy sector

There is technical potential for negative emissions in Germany that is related to the use of biomass and subsequent utilization or geological storage of biogenic carbon (BECCS). In the scenario presented by Prognos et al. (2020) it is assumed that negative emissions of -34 Mt CO₂-eq will be reached within the industrial sector and further -3 Mt CO₂-eq from the energy sector by 2050. The post-CO₂ combustion will largely be applied within the industrial sector while in the energy sector the oxyfuel-technology is applied. Both processes are estimated to reach a removal rate of CO₂ of at least 90 %.

Biomass, most suitable is solid biomass due to transportation reasons, needs to be available in necessary quantities. In 2030, the demand amounts 221 TWh, increasing to 284 TWh in 2050. The biomass feedstock will derive from existing streams of agriculture and forestry primary and secondary residues and waste. It is assumed that the increasing demand is covered by agroforestry systems, hedges and short rotation plantations growing on former cultivation areas of maize used as biogas substrates. This leads to benefits as this implies a reduction in the use of fertilizer, an additional accumulation of humus, and a better adaptability towards climate change.

2.1.2 Land management practices

Managing forests and HWP

German forests currently provide considerable negative emissions causing the LULUCF sector to be a net sink (Prognos et al. (2020)). In 2018 forests took up 67 Mt CO₂e (Prognos et al. (2020)). In addition, net storage through harvested wood products (HWP) was 3 Mt CO₂e. HWP cannot sequester carbon themselves and are therefore not considered as carbon sinks. But their carbon pool is closely connected to the forest pool of living forest biomass because harvested biomass reduces the living biomass pool but also transfers carbon partly to the HWP pool. The amount of carbon stored in HWPs depends on the allocation pattern of the harvested wood to wood product types and their lifetimes. This net sink could be increased considerably according to the WEHAM-Nature protection preference scenario (WEHAM-NPS) (Oehmichen et al. 2018). The WEHAM-NPS assumes an increasing consideration of nature protection in forests. Compared to current forest management, which is modelled in the WEHAM-Basis scenario (WEHAM-BS) (Oehmichen et al. 2018), harvesting and thinning activities mainly promote more old trees with larger diameters and tree species of the actual forest habitat type. WEHAM-NPS does not assume an increase in protected areas (4,2%) compared to WEHAM-BS but a reduced intensity of harvest, especially for broadleaved trees. Additionally, deadwood occurrence is increased from 20 m³/ha to 40 m³/ha on average. Another scenario of forest development is the “Forest vision” (Böttcher et al. 2018a) that assumes high standards of close-to-nature forestry. Under this scenario the forest sink could be substantially increased to -68 Mt CO₂ in 2050. The forest area without timber harvest is higher (16.6 %) compared to WEHAM-NPS. The harvest intensity is also lowered and results in an increase of the average wood stock from 356 m³/ha in 2012 to 501 m³/ha in 2052.

Implementing the WEHAM-NPS would lead to net removals of 35 Mt CO₂ in 2050, which is about twice as much compared to the WEHAM-BS (Rüter et al. 2017). HWP do not store carbon but cause net emissions of 2 Mt CO₂ in 2030 and 3 Mt CO₂ in 2050 because less wood is harvested and HWP stocks therefore slightly decreasing. Assumptions for wood assortment are based on current technological requirements but future innovations of wood use, especially for wood from broadleaved trees that are currently to a large degree used for fire wood, might increase carbon storage potentials in harvested products.

There are significant risks for maintaining or even increasing the sink in forests due to natural disturbances (see section "Land use change dynamics").

Rewetting of Organic Soils

In 2018 the LULUCF sector reported emissions of about 43 Mt CO₂e caused by agricultural activities on organic soils in Germany (1.8 Mha), including peat extraction (18,000 ha). Rewetting and abandoning peat extraction on these soils can reduce emissions substantially and therefore increase the net sink in LULUCF. Following the scenario by Prognos et al. (2020) emission reduction of 7 Mt CO₂e (25.2 t CO₂e/ha) can be achieved by abandoning peat extraction and rewetting 20 % (278,000 ha) of cropland and

grassland on former peatlands until 2030. Until 2050, an emission reduction of 18 Mt CO₂e (27.7 t CO₂e/ha) can be achieved after rewetting 50 % (650,000 ha) of cropland and grassland on organic soils.

Prognos et al. (2020) describes that the total agricultural area will decrease by 7 % in 2050 due to rewetting of organic soils and the expansion of infrastructural areas and settlement. The latter implies that due to less agriculturally used land, less fertilizers are applied. Partially, the rewetted soils will stay in agricultural use (e.g., paludiculture): 0.2 Mha in 2030 and 0.7 Mha in 2050.

In the scenario by Prognos et al. (2020), the management of the rewetted soils in 2030 is mainly extensive pasture and mowing (40 %). Also, paludicultures can be introduced and 30 % of the rewetted organic soils is left without agricultural management for nature restoration. In 2050, paludiculture use could increase to 50 % on the rewetted area while 50 % is left for nature restoration.

Abandoning peat extraction

The scenario by Prognos et al. (2020) assumes that until 2030 peat extraction will be abandoned and that the areas used for peat extraction will be rewetted.

Another study “Pathways into a resource-saving greenhouse gas neutrality (RESCUE)” carried out by the federal environmental agency (UBA) in 2019 assumes that peat extraction could be stopped by 2040 cutting current emissions from this activity of over 4 Mt CO₂e to zero.

Afforestation / Reforestation

Afforestation potentials is very difficult to assess in a densely populated country like Germany with high land use competition. Estimates by BMEL (2016b) assume an afforestation potential of 5 % of the agricultural area, which corresponds to 850,000 ha (7.7 % of forest area in 2012) until 2050. In 2018 a total of 17,730 ha of mainly grassland was converted into forests according to the latest National Inventory Report (UBA 2020b). However, this option is limited by the availability of land that can be converted to forests. Land area converted to forest land from 1998 to 2018³ was reported as a net sink of -4.7 Mt CO₂.

Emission reductions by afforestation measures might be counteracted by deforestation emissions. About 5,000 ha of forest area were lost each on average between 1990 and 2012. In 2018 forest area loss amounted to 6,890 ha causing emissions of 1.7 Mt CO₂. Deforestation occurs only in relation to rather big infrastructural projects which are of social relevance and further those deforested areas must be compensated through replanting elsewhere (WBW 2016).

Increasing SOC on agricultural land

Wiesmeier et al. (2017) estimated the C_{org}-storage potential for agricultural soils in the state of Bavaria. His results show that the soils had an average saturation of only 50 % and providing a theoretical

³ Afforestation is reported as land converted to forest land over a 20-year period.

potential of storage of 108 Mt C_{org} (respectively 395 Mt CO_2 eq). On average 128.3 t CO_2 per hectare could potentially be stored. The authors discuss, however, that this value exceeds by far the C-accumulation rate of different measures increasing soil organic carbon (e.g., extending intercropping, improved cropping sequence, introduction of agroforestry system etc.). Furthermore, the assumptions are that before reaching the maximum C storage potential a new equilibrium will be reached. The estimated overall potential of C_{org} storage is 1.35 Mt CO_2 .

Avoided grassland conversion

During the development of this report, the LMT avoided grassland conversion first had been included in the short-listed LMTs but later had been excluded as the potential is very limited. The protection of grassland is already legally binding due to the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) of the EU in 2013. A mechanism of the “Greening”-measure regulates the conservation of grassland for farmers that receive direct funding through the CAP. Some Federal states in Germany have issued their own regulations and there it is generally prohibited to convert grassland; exemptions must be authorized⁴.

⁴ <https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/daten/land-forstwirtschaft/gruenlandumbruch#okologische-bedeutung-des-grunlands>

2.2 Determining the scope for national level LMT portfolio

In this section a short-list of LMTs for Germany is formed. Table 2 summarises identified LMTs and presents the short-list of the LMT portfolio. The criteria for including LMTs in the list are:

- focus on natural sinks,
- availability of data,
- capabilities of tools to assess potentials,
- degree of realism that measures can be implemented, and
- relevance of the option in the policy context.

The application of the criteria resulted in the following short-list of LMTs: peat soil management, including rewetting, reverse drainage, paludiculture of grasslands and croplands, forest management and afforestation and reforestation.

Table 2: Long-list of relevant land based LMTs in Germany

LMTs	Specification	Included in national LAND-MARC LMT portfolio
BECCS	BECCS based on domestic biomass (Anaerobic digestion (AD) with CCS based on domestic biomass etc.)	N
	BECCS based on imported biomass	N
Biochar	-	N
Wetlands	Peat soil management, including rewetting, reverse drainage, paludiculture	Y
Cropland	Reduced tillage	N
	Harvest residues, crop rotation	N
	Application of organic fertilizers and anaerobic digestates	N
	Peat soil management	Y
	Agroforestry	N
	Landscape elements (hedgerows etc.)	N
Grassland	Avoided grassland conversion	N
	Peat soil management	Y
	Agroforestry	N
	Landscape elements (hedgerows etc.)	N
Forest land	Avoided deforestation	N
	Afforestation / reforestation	Y
	Forest management (incl. HWP)	Y
	Agroforestry	N
	Landscape elements (hedgerows etc.)	N
Settlements	Reducing net conversion to built-up land	N

BECCS could be a promising technical land-based solution, however, the case study focuses on natural sink solutions. SOC enhancement technologies are not included because the data on this LMT in Germany is very limited.

2.3 Discussion on short-listed LMTs

2.3.1 Land use change dynamics

Almost all selected LMTs imply considerable changes in land use in the future, with LMTs related to forest management and harvested wood products being an exception. In a densely populated country like Germany, land availability is a major challenge. Especially, agricultural land (cropland and grassland) which amounts to 19.7 Mio ha in Germany will be under pressure to be converted or managed differently. For example, organic soils under agricultural land that make up 1.3 Mio ha will have to be rewetted (see section 1.2.3) to reduce emissions from peat decomposition. This might cause land use conflicts because soil rewetting will often make conventional farming impossible. Currently, cattle farming and the production of meat and dairy products are an important income source for the national agricultural sector. Less available grassland for fodder crop cultivation could lead to leakage effects because more animal feed would have to be imported from abroad. Additionally, afforestation will have to be mainly applied on agricultural land (see section 1.2.3), which further reduces the area for crop production, also with possible leakage effects. There are also potential conflicts with nature conservation interests regarding highly diverse grasslands or sparsely vegetated heathland. Usually, these kinds of habitats derive from animal herding practices in the past. They are actively kept clear of trees to protect the established habitat and biodiversity.

2.3.2 Land management dynamics

Some of the potential land use change conflicts due to rewetting of organic soils as mentioned above can be avoided when a change of land management is applied which still can generate economic income. For example the introduction of paludicultures like reed, cattail, reed canary grass, alder, peat moss is preserving the existing peat body and therefore an effective climate mitigation measure (Wichtmann et al. 2016). However, implementation of paludiculture will require agricultural policies to set monetary incentives for farmers to rewet drained agricultural organic soils and maintain them as wetlands (O'Brolchain 2020). Also, paludiculture products like insulating material and peat substitute material will have to be mainstreamed. Additionally, rewetting measures will need to change the hydrology of the site and block drainage systems, which can cause conflicts with neighboring cropland or infrastructure.

In the future, it is very likely that there will be even more agricultural management options that compete with the implementation of the LMTs. For example there will be a high demand for bioenergy crops like maize and wood from short rotation plantations (UBA 2021).

Current forest land management can differ substantially in Germany, especially in-between ownership classes. About 50 % of the forests are privately owned with mainly small forest areas (less than 20 ha). The states own 29 % and the Federal government 4 % of the forests. Communities own about 19 % forests (BMEL 2016a). The intensity of forest management is mainly determined by the economic interest of the forest owner and the market demands which are in favor for coniferous wood of low diameter. To promote higher carbon stocks in the forests (living biomass, deadwood, SOC, litter), incentives for less intensive forest management will be needed in the future. Also, the net effects on the sequestration potential depend on the future tree species composition of forests, the ability of species to adapt (Seidl et al. 2014). Therefore, forest adaptation to climate change will have to be considered in future management regimes to ensure continuous rates of carbon sequestration and to protect forest carbon stocks. These adaptation measures can have synergies with the extensification measures already mentioned. For example, promoting mixed forest stands with deciduous tree species to minimize the devastating effects of natural disturbances like storms or insect pests. Additionally, promoting all tree age classes in the forest stand can reduce the risks against pests and other calamities. Extensification of forest management can also positively affect biodiversity and ecosystem services like elevated water retention by deciduous trees (IPCC 2019; Griscom et al. 2017).

Harvesting wood from forests transfers carbon stored in living biomass into different pools of HWP. From these wood products the stored carbon is released as these products get out of use and are being incinerated or dumped (however, there is a landfill ban for HWP in EU). Given that these products have different lifetimes and there are recycling flows between them, the estimation of total carbon stored in these products can be complex. In case the wood is being used for energy or left in the forest, the stored carbon counts as an emission. Wood products hold back these emissions and can contribute to mitigation, especially when products are long-lasting and recycling rates are high. Wood products can also help reducing emissions in other sectors, like the building industry through substitution of fossil-based products. Changes in forest management will affect wood production potentials in different ways depending on the side conditions and existing trees species composition. Currently wood from broad-leaved trees is to a large extent directly used for energy. Coniferous trees instead are mostly used for construction wood. Extensification of wood harvest can reduce domestic wood supply and thus lead to increased imports.

2.3.3 Projection of land management dynamics

The German Government's most recent projection report on the development of greenhouse gas emissions in Germany covers the period until 2040 (UBA 2021). In the LULUCF-sector four LMTs already addressed by policy measures are considered in the projection (Table 3). Peat soil management on different land types reveal a GHG mitigation of 5.2 Mt CO₂e in 2030. The reduction of the use of peat that is associated with the rewetting of peat extraction areas mitigates another 1.2 Mt CO₂e. The reduction of net conversion to built-up land from 80 ha to 30 ha in 2030 leads to a GHG-mitigation of 2.0 Mt CO₂e. Finally, maintaining grassland areas reduces GHG emissions by 1.3 Mt CO₂e. However, the latter mitigation is derived from a scenario assuming the absence of this grassland measure. As

maintaining grassland areas is now part of the good agricultural practice this GHG mitigation should not be considered. In total, the LMTs amount up to about 8.5 Mt CO₂e excluding and 9.7 Mt CO₂ including maintaining grassland area.

Table 3: Land based mitigation technologies (LMT) covered in the Germany GHG projection report

LMT	Description	GHG mitigation in 2030 (MT CO ₂ e)
Reducing net conversion to built-up land	In 2015 to 2020 about 80 ha/day are converted to settlements. This value is reduced to less than 30 ha/day in 2030.	2.0
Maintaining grassland areas	Within the framework of the Common Agricultural Policy, the net conservation of permanent grassland has been successfully addressed in Germany since 2015. It is assumed that the grassland conversion ban will result in the existing grassland area remaining constant compared to mean losses from 2000 to 2010. ⁵	1.3
Peat soil management in cropland, grassland, peat extraction areas and wetland areas	Until 2030: - 12,700 ha of arable land are converted to grassland - 224,000 ha of grassland are moderately and 80,000 ha are fully rewetted - 1,200 ha of peat extraction areas are rewetted - about 73,000 ha of drained wetland areas are rewetting and their water management is optimised.	5.2
Reduction of peat use in cultivation substrates	Compared to 2018, peat extraction and peat use will be reduced to half by 2030.	1.2
Sum		9.7 (8.5 without maintaining grassland areas)

Source: (UBA 2021)

UBA (2021) also shows projections of emissions and removals from forests. However, the used forest scenario is based on data from 2012, assuming rather high rates of timber extraction. Moreover, the projection does not reflect strong draughts and beetle calamities from 2018 to 2020 (compare Hennenberg et al. (2021), UBA 2021). Hennenberg et al. (2021) showed that the forest sink in Germany strongly depends on the level of natural disturbances. Assuming a timber harvest of 70 Mio m³ and a low level of natural disturbances (as in the period 2008 to 2017) results in a sink of living biomass of

⁵ This contrafact analysis is critical as maintaining grassland is now well established and can be considered as good agricultural practice.

about -46 Mt CO₂. Under strong natural disturbances (as in the period 2002 to 2007) the sink of living trees drops to about -18 Mt CO₂. Assuming higher natural disturbances may result in sink values of -9 Mt CO₂ (very strong disturbances) and 0 Mt CO₂ (extreme disturbances). Thus, the magnitude of uncertainties due to natural disturbances is about 28 Mt CO₂ or even more. Assuming a decrease of timber harvest from 70 to 65 Mm³ implies a change of the sink from -46 to -50 Mt CO₂, and an increased timber harvest of 80 Mm³ reveals a sink of about -40 Mt CO₂.

This shows that the reduction of timber harvest is an important leverage for increasing CO₂ fixation in the LMT forest management. However, the sink benefits targeted by the reduced timber harvest can be reversed by natural disturbances, especially if the increase of growing stock in forests is targeted to forest stands that are not well adapted to climate change risks..

Other scenario studies on the development of GHG emissions in Germany also estimate potentials for LMTs mentioned in Table 3 but with varying intensities. Also additional LMTs are covered, namely increasing harvested wood products (Repenning et al. in press) and establishment of agroforestry systems including short rotation coppices (dena (2021), (Repenning et al. in press).

2.3.4 Policy context for LMT implementation in Germany

The political situation in Germany has changed recently towards a new coalition consisting of the green, socialist, and liberal party. The coalition contract addresses numerous initiatives relevant for LMT implementation in Germany. Additionally, the military conflict between Russia and Ukraine has severe impacts on the energy supply of Germany. In the aftermath of the beginning of the armed conflict big changes took and are still taking place regarding the origin and amount of imported fossil energy. At the same time the demand for alternative energy supply (including wood) increased enormously. Moreover, the conflict resulted in food security becoming an important consideration in national politics. This led to a discussion on the area available for agricultural production and reducing or postponing ambitions regarding the establishment of ecological priority areas.

The coalition contract includes⁶ a variety of measures addressing conservation and protection of ecosystems that potentially lead to a reduction of GHG emissions or enhancement of carbon removals.

- Contract nature conservation (Vertragsnaturschutz⁷) is to be strengthened and will be provided with better financial opportunities and more flexibilities in its implementation on a regional scale. The concept of contract nature conservation delivers a scope that for a fixed period (several years) a contracted party commits themselves to a certain management method

⁶

<https://www.bundesregierung.de/re-source/blob/974430/1990812/04221173eef9a6720059cc353d759a2b/2021-12-10-koav2021-data.pdf?download=1>

⁷ <https://www.bmu.de/themen/naturschutz-artenvielfalt/naturschutz-biologische-vielfalt/waelder/nationale-waldschutzpolitik>

oriented towards nature conservations goals, e. g. a forest owner selects trees to be designated as biotope trees.

- The Natural Climate Protection Action Program (Aktionsprogramm natürlicher Klimaschutz⁸) is designed to encompass all necessary means to protect and strengthen ecosystems. This includes the capture of the status of an ecosystem and finding the causes, the development of appropriate counter measures, and to build up necessary competences, as well as the permanent implementation of measures and their monitoring. The concrete measures are divided into 10 areas of action, such as implementation of the national peatland protection strategy, restoration of the water balance, promotion of sound forest ecosystems, sea and coastal areas, wilderness areas, etc. The Action Program is strongly connected to a wide range of other governmental programs and strategies to create and use synergies. The draft of the Action Program is currently being discussed in an online dialogue where stakeholders, the interested public, administration etc. can share their ideas and suggestions. It is expected that the cabinet resolution will be in early 2023.
- The development of a long-term approach that monetizes climate protection and biodiversity services that go further than existing certification systems. Thus, it enables forest owners to restructure their forests to increase climate change resilience and to afforest and reforest, if necessary.
- Old growth beech forests owned by the state will no longer be subject to wood extraction and all other publicly owed forests must be managed at least according to FSC- or Naturland⁹-Standards in the medium term.
- In September 2022 the ministries of economy, agriculture, and environment published key points on the National Strategy on Biomass (Nationale Biomassestrategie¹⁰). The strategies' goal is to provide Germany with a framework that allows in a long run a sustainable use of resources and to protect climate and biodiversity. Principles of the sustainable production and usage of biomass will be developed to set more incentives and targets for sustainable biomass use. The most important guiding principle will be a consequent cascading and multiple usage of biomass. Material use in which C can be stored long-term should always have priority before energetic usage. This strategy serves also to address the increasing pressure on land use by balancing between nature protection and food production..
- The National Peatland Protection Strategy (Moorschutzstrategie¹¹) aims to reduce annual greenhouse gas emissions from peatland soils by at least 5 Mio. t of CO₂e by 2030. To achieve

⁸ <https://www.bmuv.de/download/aktionsprogramm-natuerlicher-klimaschutz>

⁹ <https://www.naturland.de/en/producers/service-and-expertise/standards.html>

¹⁰ https://www.bmwk.de/Redaktion/DE/Publikationen/Wirtschaft/nabis-eckpunktepapier-nationale-biomassestrategie.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=18

¹¹ <https://www.bmuv.de/themen/naturschutz-artenvielfalt/naturschutz-biologische-vielfalt/moorschutz#c61293>

this, the strategy relies on financial incentives for voluntary rewetting measures of peatlands used for agriculture and forestry as well as for the improvement and restoration of natural peatlands. The strategy also pursues the goal of ending the use of peat in horticulture due to its negative impact on the climate and replacing it with sustainable substitutes. The peat reduction strategy of the Ministry of Agriculture and Food of July 2022 picks up on this goal and sets milestones and measures for phasing out peat use.

- The National Strategy on Bioeconomy (Bioökonomiestrategie¹²) has been adopted in March 2020. Bioeconomy has the goal to sustainably combine economy and ecology. The strategy lays the foundation to develop principles and goals for the implementation of the strategy. Two overarching principles shape the objectives and activities of the strategy. First, available biological knowledge and technologies as the basis towards a sustainable and climate-neutral economic system. And second, resources, which are the base of the economy, need to be directed into sustainable production systems and integrated into a circular economy.

In September 2022, the Bioeconomy Council published a statement¹³ on the consequences and global disruptions in food, energy and raw materials supply caused by the armed conflict between Russia and Ukraine. A sustainable bioeconomy can provide solutions and explicitly mentioned are short-, medium-, and long-term strategies to mitigate the effects worldwide and in Germany. Short-term measures comprise, among others, the focus on food security. Agricultural products that can be used as food should no longer be integrated in process for energy production. The number of livestock should be decreased and eventually feed grain could also be used as food grain. The consumption of meat should be reduced by financial incentives set in the plant-based food sector and new innovations regarding meat substitutes. Further, the possibilities of the Common Agricultural Policy¹⁴ of the EU should be better used to increase the agricultural production in Germany sustainably.

A new instrument to push for more climate adapted forest management and a more extensified wood use has been introduced by the ministry of agriculture (BMEL) in July 2022¹⁵. This instrument rewards forest owners for providing ecosystem services of forests and efforts for additional climate and biodiversity protection¹⁶. In a long-term this approach addresses concrete measures that go beyond existing legal requirements and certification systems for additional climate and biodiversity services. The goals are:

- to maintain and develop resilient, adaptable, and productive forest,

¹² <https://www.bmel.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/DE/Broschueren/nationale-bioekonomiestrategie-langfassung.html>

¹³ https://www.bioekonomierat.de/media/pdf/stellungnahmen/Stellungnahme_des_BOER_zur_Ernaehrungs_Energiekrise.pdf?m=1662392320&

¹⁴ https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/common-agricultural-policy_en

¹⁵ <https://www.bmel.de/SharedDocs/Pressemitteilungen/DE/2022/93-wald-foerderprogramm.html>

¹⁶ https://www.gstb-rlp.de/gstbrp/Schwerpunkte/Wald_im_Klimastress/Konzept_Finanzierung_Klima+Biodiversität_Wald_für_HH-Ausschuss.pdf and it

- stabilization and enhancement of biodiversity also as a basic prerequisite for resilience and vitality of forests and the provision of ecosystem/climate protection services,
- and contributing to the conservation of natural C reservoirs and additional greenhouse gas mitigation, which is aligned with the requirements of the Federal Climate Protection Act, which sets mitigation targets for the LULUCF sector for the years 2030 and 2045.

The step towards the payments of ecosystem services has already been described as a necessary measure to maintain and improve the provision of ecosystem services by an expert opinion of the Scientific Advisory Board for Forest Policy to the BMEL in 2021. It is essential that our forests will have the abilities to buffer negative consequences of increasing temperatures, changes in the precipitation regime but most to comply with extreme events such as storms, insect infestations and fires. The experts advocate a system, which provides forest owners with predictable revenues from the provision of ecosystem services. A pragmatic approach would be to reward the adaptability of forests towards climate change as a basis for all future provisions of all ecosystem services. It is recommended to orientate the payments along the state of a forest.

Implications on the LMT forest management may also have the latest revision of the renewable energy directive (RED III¹⁷) that is currently in the trilogue negotiations between the EU Council, Commission, and Parliament. The directive sets a target that by 2030 45 % for renewable energy in the EU's energy consumption. Highly debated is the consumption of energy wood, which might no longer be considered as renewable and primary woody biomass thus might not be eligible for funding. Further, it will be mandatory for wood to be used in cascade use and there will be requirements for forest management.

All the above-mentioned initiatives, action plans, and suggestions of expert groups tend all to protect, stabilize, enhance, or re-establish ecosystems that with regard to LMTs, have the potential to increase storage and uptake of CO₂. However, it very much depends on the concrete implementation and interactions among differently targeted policies what exactly impact on emissions and removals from land use will be.

¹⁷ https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/renewable-energy/renewable-energy-directive-targets-and-rules/renewable-energy-directive_en

3. LMT narratives

This section elaborates further on the LMTs identified in the short-list. Information on the potential for emission reductions and increased removals, the durability or reversibility, synergies, and conflicts with other societal goals are provided. The content provided in the sub-chapters on climate related risks and impacts and effects on the local environment derive from expert opinions.

3.1 Afforestation

In 2018, about 17,000 ha of net new forest area was added, mainly from grassland (UBA 2020a). The expansion of forest area allows CO₂ from the atmosphere to be sequestered and stored over a long period of time in growing above-ground and below-ground biomass of forest stands and in the forest soil. In this process, C stocks usually increase continuously compared to previous land use. During the conversion of grassland to forest, temporary emissions from the soil may occur under certain circumstances, e.g., when the soil is tilled for the establishment of the tree stand. In the course of the growing forest stand, possible losses of C stocks due to young growth and thinning measures must then be taken into account. There are hardly any studies available so far for the potential to increase forest area in Germany, but there are estimates from the climate protection report in agriculture and forestry (BMEL 2016b).

The expansion of forest area is countered by land conversions from forest to other land uses. These occur primarily in the course of infrastructure expansions. By law, these losses of forest land must be compensated. Nevertheless, significant emissions are initially generated due to the high losses of carbon stored in biomass. In 2018, approximately 6,890 ha of forest land in Germany was converted into settlement areas, resulting in emissions of approximately 1.7 Mt CO₂e (UBA 2020b).

3.1.1 Potential of the option for climate protection

In the climate protection report of the scientific advisory boards of the German Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture (BMEL 2016b), a total afforestation area potential of 5% (850,000 ha) of agricultural land was assumed, starting from the year 2012 until 2050. For the year 2030, just under half of the land potential can already be achieved. The average tree species distribution of the first age class (1 to 20 years) from the last federal forest inventory in 2012 was used as a basis for calculating the reduction potential. This showed a proportion of 58% deciduous trees and 42% conifers. Thus, the study indicates a reduction potential of 4.7 t CO₂e per ha, or 18 Mt CO₂e by 2030. As forest cover grows, the accumulation of carbon in biomass increases quasi-exponentially and can reach a mitigation potential of approximately 120 Mt CO₂e. for Germany by 2050.

3.1.2 Durability or reversibility of the option

The forest area in Germany is legally protected from larger clearcuts (> 1 ha) as well as forest conversion to other land uses. Therefore, a large-scale reduction of the forest area is not to be expected. Nevertheless, forest areas will continue to be converted primarily to settlement areas in the future. By

2050, BMEL (BMEL 2016b) assumes about 5,000 ha per year. In contrast, natural disturbances such as dry periods, storms, insect pests (e.g. bark beetles), and fire can cause considerable damage even in young forest stands. Dry periods, in particular, can be especially damaging to young trees whose root systems are not yet well developed and can even lead to plant death. As climate change progresses, the frequency and magnitude of natural disturbances such as drought and storms can be expected to increase (Seidl et al. 2014). For this reason, the resilience of future forest stands is crucial to their durability and climate change mitigation performance in afforestation measures. The choice of tree species is therefore of particular importance, as is the method of afforestation, whether from plantations, seeding or natural regeneration.

3.1.3 Synergies and conflicts with other societal goals

In addition to carbon sequestration and the long-term provision of raw material for wood products, forest areas have a positive influence on water infiltration into the soil and thus also on groundwater recharge. Compared to cropland, the rate of groundwater recharge decreases over time as evapotranspiration and interception of growing trees increase. However, by avoiding fertilization and pesticide use, it can be assumed that the quality of the leachate is significantly better (BMUB/UBA 2016). Afforestation areas can also make a positive contribution to the protection of biodiversity due to their succession stages to forest stand. Compared to arable land with few structures, species communities typical of forests can form here. However, conflicts for species protection arise where species-rich grassland is converted into forest. This should therefore be avoided, also with a view to possible losses of soil carbon.

Further conflicts may arise with an increasing demand for agricultural land. This competition for land could be exacerbated by further measures for climate protection, such as the rewetting of organic soils and the extensification of arable land. In addition, negative relocation processes may occur abroad if some agricultural goods, such as meat and dairy products, can no longer be produced in Germany. This could further exacerbate environmental problems such as deforestation and drainage of organic soils for the production of agricultural goods abroad. The extent of these displacement effects from measures such as the expansion of forest area is thus very closely linked to the development of consumption of agricultural goods, especially meat and dairy products, and land for infrastructure. The discussion on how to use land received a new spin as in February 2022 Russia started to invade Ukraine as the questions of food and energy security moved into the focus.

3.1.4 Climate related risks / impacts and effects on the local environment

As a result of the expert interview, the most relevant climate-related extreme events are according to the interviewee heat waves, droughts, fires, strong winds and biotic disturbance events such as insect infestation.

Heat waves lead to the shedding of leaves/needles and tissue damage impairing the capabilities of photosynthesis and growth, which is especially relevant for A/R. Beech and spruce trees are more

affected than pine and oak. Within Germany the East, West and Centre are more affected than the North or South.

Droughts occurred in 2003, 2018, 2019 and 2022. Again, beech and spruce trees are more affected than pine and oak. The failure of xylem causes irreversible damage to water conducting tissues, a lack of C leads to reduced photosynthesis activities, and drought-stressed trees are more vulnerable regarding insect attacks. An adaptation needs to consider a higher species diversity.

Natural forest fires hardly occur, largest risk through human causes and land history (e.g. old military areas with old ammunition). Stand structure influences fire behaviour (lot of undergrowth creates fire-ladders for fire to reach canopies) only high forest less susceptible than coppice

The risks regarding damage due to strong storms must be differentiated between species, stand structure, management, and neighbouring effects. Effects of other climatic conditions, such as soil moisture and season (foliated trees) play a role. Stronger effects occur due to reduced tree vitality and re-enforcing effects in combination with other disturbances, e.g., damage to the fine roots, where no visible damage is detected.

Biotic disturbance events (insects) strongly relate to drought and management. The interviewee expects that biotic disturbances will gain further importance and they are directly affected by climate change (warmer winters, more populations of beetles) and indirectly through changes in forest growth and resilience (e.g., reduced vitality after drought). This category deserves more granularity.

The most important parameters regarding the effects of AR on the local environment are C sequestration, nutrients retention in the soil, water balance, and soil protection.

A/R contribute highly to the parameter of C sequestration mostly in a positive way (increased C sequestration due to growth). The impacts on the nutritious soil level and soil protection depend very much on how A/R is carried out. If it is a plantation or the establishment is industrialized, it might harm the soil and its nutrients but if degraded lands is restored this leads to an improvement regarding nutrient retention and soil protection. Regarding impacts on the hydrologic balance, it also depends very much on the type of A/R and its management, e.g., plantations are water demanding. Coniferous species can decrease soil water status, also in winter as they lose water due to interception.

3.2 Forest Management

Forest management can contribute to the continuous uptake of CO₂ from the atmosphere by trees and to the increase of carbon stocks in the living and dead biomass as well as in the soil through targeted measures. Forest carbon dynamics are very complex and biomass growth and natural mortality are influenced by site factors (climate and soil). For example, beech growth may be lower on average in regions with less precipitation, such as Brandenburg and Saxony-Anhalt, than in low mountain regions with more precipitation (e.g. Hesse and Thuringia) (BMEL 2012). Emissions in forests are predominantly caused by the death and subsequent decomposition of trees, with deadwood also representing

a carbon pool. The decomposition of deadwood, and thus the release of emissions, varies by tree species and site conditions.

Harvest intensity has a significant influence on forest carbon capture and storage (e.g. Pilli et al. 2016). If annual biomass removal through timber harvesting remains below the annual net-to-increase (increment minus natural mortality) of wood biomass in the forest, then carbon storage in the forest continuously increases. According to the latest carbon inventory from 2017, wood utilization in Germany has decreased significantly since 2012 (-19%). On average, 74 Mm³ of wood were harvested annually between 2002 and 2012, compared to about 62 Mm³ between 2012 and 2017.

Thus, on average, 76% of the increment was siphoned off. As a result, the average wood stock increased by 6 % to 358 m³/ha from 2012 to 2017, as in the previous ten years (2002 to 2012). A major part of this increase in stock occurred in spruce tree species (+ 54 Mm³) (Hennig et al. 2019). In the future, the carbon sink in the forest is expected to decline, as the stock built up especially in spruce and pine stands of the same age is likely to be reduced by the upcoming timber harvest (UBA 2021). Although actual harvest volumes tended to be lower compared to expected skimming through 2017, a significant increase is expected with the recent forest damage (see below). The effects on the sink capacity of the forest have not yet been estimated.

The carbon stock in wood biomass is directly related to the carbon storage of wood products. When wood is harvested, the wood product store fills up while the carbon store in the forest decreases. From the forest's point of view, timber harvesting represents an emission. By using the wood in products, this emission is delayed. The calculation of carbon dissipated in wood products is complex because the use time of wood products is very different and there are different recycling processes that also must be considered. Finally, if the wood is used for energy, emissions are produced. In Germany, approximately 30 % (23 Mm³)¹⁸ of the total harvested wood was used for energy in 2019. This applies predominantly to hardwood, as around 67 % of the harvested hardwood is used for energy and therefore does not contribute to the wood product store. Long-lived wood products in particular retain emissions. Due to the advantageous product properties and easy processing of softwood, it is preferably used, for example, in timber construction (WBGU 2020). Alone 66 % (37 Mm³)¹⁹ of the harvested softwood in 2019 will be processed as sawnwood. In addition, wood products can contribute to reduce emissions in other sectors by substituting products with a worse climate balance, e.g. concrete in the construction sector. Substitution effects of wood products in the future are very much dependent on the development of renewable energy supply, which can again significantly improve the carbon footprint of non-wood products. In the LULUCF sector, the substitution effects from wood use are not accounted for, but in the respective sectors where they are used.

¹⁸ [Thünen-Institut für Internationale Waldwirtschaft und Forstökonomie, Thünen-Einschlagsrückrechnung, BWI3, Amtliche Statistik](#)

¹⁹ <https://www.wri.org/blog/2020/06/global-tree-cover-loss-data-2019>

3.2.1 *Potential of the option for climate protection*

Based on data from the 2012 Federal Forest Inventory, the WEHAM-Nature Conservation Preference Scenario (WEHAM-NPS) was developed in a project of the Forest Climate Fund (Oehmichen et al. 2018). This traces the development of the forest starting from 2012 to 2050 and aims at silviculture with a focus on promoting native forest biodiversity. In the WEHAM-NPS, forest conversion towards deciduous and mixed deciduous forests is targeted, with conifers that are ready for cutting being rapidly harvested and replaced with predominantly deciduous species of the natural forest community. Where conifers occur naturally, however, they were also encouraged. Thus, the proportion of coniferous wood was reduced by 19% and the proportion of deciduous trees increased by 15%. In addition, deciduous trees were harvested less and remained longer in the forest to increase their stock. Overall, the average wood stock increased from 345 m³/ha in 2012 to 374 m³/ha in 2052. Deadwood stock was also increased from approximately 20 m³/ha to 40 m³/ha to promote biodiversity tied to these structures. In addition, the forest area with use restrictions or without wood use was slightly increased, which also contributed to the build-up of wood biomass. Thus, a total of about 31 million tCO₂ by 2030 and 35 Mt CO₂ by 2050 annual sink performance was achieved in the forest. This is about 20 Mt CO₂ more in sink performance in 2050 compared to the WEHAM baseline scenario, which continues the existing forest management from 2012 (Rüter et al. 2017). In the WEHAM-NPS, between 70 and 80 million m³ of wood was harvested over the simulation period, yet the wood product reservoir is transformed into an emission source of up to about 4 Mt CO₂ (Rüter et al. 2017). This is mainly due to the fact that the assumptions for material and energetic wood use remain the same over time. Thus, the hardwood generated in WEHAM-NPS was predominantly used for energy rather than materials, directly releasing emissions.

The historical sink performance of the forest can likely only be maintained through 2050 via greater extensification. In the "Waldvision" study by Böttcher et al. (2018b), which is also based on data from the 2012 Federal Forest Inventory, timber extraction is reduced by 25% compared to a baseline scenario. Compared to the WEHAM-NPS, the forest vision shows an even lower logging intensity, especially in hardwoods. This is partly a consequence of the assumption that areas without forestry use are increased to 16.6%. This increases the average wood stock to 501 m³/ha in 2052, resulting in an average annual carbon sink of -48 Mt CO₂ in the living forest biomass (-14 Mt CO₂ in the baseline scenario). However, non-utilization is accompanied by reduced carbon sequestration in wood products, which is why approximately 14 Mt CO₂ emissions are recorded annually from these by 2052.

3.2.2 *Durability or reversibility of the option*

Beech-dominated deciduous and mixed forests are the actual climax society (hypothetical end-state of vegetation development) in Germany (Fischer 2003). Under expected climate changes, this is unlikely to change significantly for many regions, although productivity losses of beech in dry regions are to be expected (Dulamsuren et al. 2017). In addition, the dominance of beech in tree species composition could shift in favor of other broadleaf species, such as sessile oak and field maple (Mette et al. 2013; Walentowski et al. 2017). Therefore, investing in forest carbon stocks as a climate mitigation

measure is a good option. The sink potential of forests can decrease in quite short time periods, due to natural disturbances and human interventions. As climate change impacts on forests are likely to increase in the future (Seidl et al. 2017), current and future management decisions are of particular importance to promote and maintain forest resilience and thus forest sink permanence in the long term (Mausolf et al. 2018). Currently, forests in Germany are not in a natural state when the tree species composition is considered, as it is predominantly dominated by spruce and pine (BMEL 2016a). In addition, the distribution of age classes, breast height diameters, and deadwood quantities and dimensions do not correspond to the optimal ecological state on average (Reise et al. 2017b). This can have a direct negative impact on forest resilience to climatic change and other disturbances (Norris et al. 2011; O'Hara und Ramage 2013). The past few years, 2018 to 2020, have demonstrated this very clearly. They were characterized by storm events, prolonged dry periods, and subsequent bark beetle infestations on spruce trees. In combination, these ultimately led to a damaged wood accumulation of 171 Mm³ on approx. 277,000 ha of forest area, as estimated by the BMEL²⁰, with spruce being predominantly affected. In contrast, deciduous tree species contributed only about 9 % to the emerging damaged wood²¹. Nevertheless, deciduous trees such as beech have also been affected by the drought and have lost vitality. In addition, their mortality has increased, but it is still significantly lower than that of other broadleaf and conifer species (BMEL 2020a). Currently, no estimates are available on the loss of the carbon sink in the forest. Nevertheless, it is clear that tree species selection and the associated resilience of forests are directly related to the success of the climate change mitigation measure of building carbon stocks in forests. For this reason, forest conversion towards deciduous and mixed forests is a key measure. In addition, it makes sense to promote natural structures such as old and strongly dimensioned trees as well as a higher amount of deadwood in order to support natural biodiversity and increase resilience to natural disturbances.

The conversion to mixed forests and their resilience to climate change are also essential factors in ensuring the continued production of wood products in Germany. In addition, due to an ever-increasing demand for bioenergy, there continues to be competition with energy use, which, however, in the case of direct energy use, usually has no positive effects on climate protection (Hennenberg et al. 2019). The energetic use of wood should be at the end of the utilization cascade in order to increase the retention time of carbon in the wood product store. Therefore, innovations in hardwood utilization are also needed to promote its material use.

²⁰ BMEL release (31.12.2020): <https://www.bmel.de/DE/themen/wald/wald-in-deutschland/wald-trockenheit-klimawandel.html#doc14830bodyText3>

²¹ <https://www.bmel.de/SharedDocs/Pressemitteilungen/DE/2020/040-waldschaeden.html>

3.2.3 Synergies and conflicts with other societal goals

The measures to promote carbon sinks in the forest can be implemented on the existing forest area, which means that, compared to other land-based climate protection measures, there is no direct competition for land.

In addition, synergies for the protection of biodiversity can result if native deciduous tree species are promoted in the future and, above all, a higher proportion of older deciduous trees is left in the forest. In addition, a higher proportion of deadwood and a higher diversity of deadwood structures (lying, standing, different dimensions) also contribute (Reise et al. 2017a; Reise et al. 2019). In addition, promoting more deciduous trees in the forest can lead to higher groundwater percolation rates, compared to conifer stands (Müller 2019).

A key conflict of the option to increase carbon stocks in the forest is with economic interests in timber harvesting, especially for conifers. Currently, timber production is the main source of income for forest owners. New models of financing are needed and as described in section 7 are already being discussed. Politics already promised that there will be payments for ecosystem services.

Increased use of durable wood products and recycled wood can make an important contribution to climate protection, especially in the building sector (WBGU 2020). However, the sustainability of wood use is highly dependent on overall consumption. Should the demand for wood products increase to such an extent that domestic forests and those abroad have to be managed intensively, then disadvantages for the protection of biodiversity may occur and the forest sink would decrease (Verkerk et al. 2014).

3.2.4 Climate related risks / impacts and effects on the local environment

The most relevant climate-related extreme events are according to the interviewee heat waves, droughts, fires, strong winds and biotic disturbance events such as insect infestation.

Heat waves lead to the shedding of leaves/needles and tissue damage impairing the capabilities of photosynthesis and growth. Beech and spruce trees are more affected than pine and oak. Within Germany the East, West and Center are more affected than the North or South.

Droughts occurred in 2003, 2018, 2019 and 2022. Again, beech and spruce trees are more affected than pine and oak. The failure of xylem causes irreversible damage to water conducting tissues, a lack of C leads to reduced photosynthesis activities (carbon starvation), and drought-stressed trees are more vulnerable regarding insect attacks. An adaptation needs to consider a higher species diversity.

Natural forest fires hardly occur, largest risk through human causes and land history (e.g., old military areas with old ammunition). Stand structure influences fire behavior (lot of undergrowth creates fire-ladders for fire to reach canopies) only high forest less susceptible than coppice

The risks regarding damage due to strong storms must be differentiated between species, stand structure, management, and neighboring effects. Effects of other climatic conditions, such as soil moisture and season (foliated trees) play a role. Stronger effects occur due to reduced tree vitality and re-enforcing effects in combination with other disturbances, e.g., damage to the fine roots, where no visible damage is detected.

Biotic disturbance events (insects), strongly relate to drought and management has an effect of this event. The interviewee thinks that biotic disturbances will gain further importance and they are directly affected by climate change (warmer winters, more populations of beetles) and indirectly through changes in forest growth and resilience (e.g. reduced vitality after drought). This category deserves more granularity.

The most important parameters, seen by the expert, regarding the effects of FM on the local environment are C sequestration, nutrients retention in the soil, water balance, and soil protection.

Forest Management contributes highly to the parameter of C sequestration in a positive and negative way. The impacts on the nutritious soil level and soil protection depend very much on the harvest regime. A higher harvesting frequency is probably more damaging to the nutrient soil status in comparison to a careful management that brings in nutrients from harvesting residues. The type of management strongly influences the hydrologic balance, especially in water scarce situations.

3.3 Conservation and improvement of carbon content in agricultural mineral soils

Organic carbon (C_{org}) is stored in soils in the form of dead soil organic matter (humus), e.g. consisting of plant residues or animal excreta and their microbially transformed components. Humus consists of approximately 58% carbon and is formed on agriculturally used soils mainly from crop residues and organic fertilizers (e.g. manure and compost) (Thünen Institut für Agrarklimaschutz 2018). Due to the microbial degradation of the C_{org} , CO_2 is released and only a smaller fraction remains in the soil and is stored there in the long term. The humus content of soils is determined in principle by the amount and type of organic matter input and its decomposition. The main factors influencing this, and thus the C_{org} storage potential, are climate and soil properties (Kolbe 2012). Soil management also influences humus content through factors such as tillage, crop rotation, and fertilization. A good example of this are the mineral soils of permanent grassland, which have up to one-third higher C_{org} stocks compared to soils under average cropland use. This is mainly due to the year-round vegetation cover and intensive rooting as well as the lack of soil tillage (Poeplau et al. 2011). Therefore, maintaining permanent grassland on mineral soils is an important measure to avoid emissions from mineral soils and to store C_{org} . Furthermore, the conversion of arable land to grassland can have a positive impact on climate protection.

To maintain a positive climate impact by storing C_{org} in the soil, more carbon must be sequestered from the atmosphere via humus build-up and the existing C_{org} must be protected (Chen et al. 2019). However, the build-up of soil C_{org} is limited in time and quantity as a new equilibrium is established between

carbon input and C_{org} removal. To maintain the level of C_{org} storage, the constant input of carbon into the soil is necessary. If the humus enrichment measure is abandoned, then a rapid degradation of C_{org} stocks occurs again (Thünen Institut für Agrarklimaschutz 2018).

According to the German BBodSchG §17, it is part of good professional practice to ensure the long-term preservation of the site-typical humus content, whereby two measures are essentially emphasised: One is the sufficient supply of organic matter and the reduction of tillage intensity. Extensive tillage reduces the mineralisation of the C_{org} by microbes and the associated CO_2 emissions. A sufficient supply of organic matter can be achieved primarily through efficient and low-loss recycling of nutrients in the arable soil, e.g. through the following measures (Sykes et al. 2020; Thünen Institut für Agrarklimaschutz 2018):

- intercrop cultivation and undersown crops for revegetation,
- cultivation with perennial crops such as clover grass,
- leaving crop residues on the field,
- organic fertilization,
- planting hedges and trees (agroforestry).

3.3.1 Potential of the option for climate protection

There are no studies that present the overall potential of mitigation measures from arable soils and the accumulation of humus as carbon storage in soils for Germany as a whole. In a study by Wiesmeier et al. (2017), the C_{org} storage potential for agricultural soils in Bavaria was determined. In the results, it is clear that these have a high storage potential, as they are only about 50% saturated with carbon. In determining the total potential, the measures implemented were expansion of intercropping and organic farming, improved crop rotation, introduction of agroforestry systems, and conversion of arable land to grassland for humus enrichment. Thus, Wiesmeier et al. (2017) assume a total annual potential for C_{org} storage in Bavaria of 0.37 Mt C (1.3 Mt CO_2).

A long-term cultivation of catch crops on arable land could increase C_{org} stocks in the soil by an average of 8 t C/ha (29 t CO_2 /ha) in the topsoil within 20 years (Poeplau und Don 2015).

The positive effect for humus build-up in organic farming is probably related to the use of organic fertilizer and the increased cultivation of clover grass and alfalfa. This can result in an increase in soil carbon stocks of 3 to 4 t C/ha (11 to 15 t CO_2 /ha), compared to conventionally managed cropland (Gattinger et al. 2012). However, it should be noted that humus build-up through organic fertilizer does not result in net CO_2 uptake from the atmosphere, but rather in nutrient recycling and thus the transfer of fertilizer carbon to the soil (Rumpel et al. 2020).

Despite individual studies and model results on possible developments of the C_{org} soil stock in agriculturally used soils, the question of potential cannot be answered with certainty at present. Overall, however, the potentials of C_{org} accumulation in arable soil through targeted measures seem to be very uncertain (BMEL 2016b; Rumpel et al. 2020) and are probably subject to quite high regional variability.

Further research is needed to obtain better, regionalised asbestos estimates for humus build-up potentials in Germany and to develop measures to protect existing stocks (Thünen Institut für Agrarklimaschutz 2018).

3.3.2 Permanence or reversibility of the option

Soil C_{org} stocks generated by humus-enhancing measures are depleted very quickly if the measures are discontinued or substantially changed. Therefore, comprehensive humus management concepts for farms are necessary, but would require long-term compliance with the measures (Thünen Institut für Agrarklimaschutz 2018). This could possibly be a barrier for farmers.

3.3.3 Synergies and conflicts with other societal goals

Building up C_{org} stocks in arable soil has many positive effects for soil properties, which may even outweigh climate change mitigation effects (Rumpel et al. 2020). Overall, soil structure and fertility can be improved, as well as water absorption and storage capacity. This, in turn, can contribute to the resilience of arable soils to the impacts of climate change. In addition, high soil carbon levels protect against soil erosion. In sum, the improvement of soil properties can also contribute positively to agricultural productivity and thus further guarantee the food supply (Frank et al. 2017).

Conflicts can arise, above all, from an excess of organic fertiliser, as this can upset the nutrient balance of the soil and lead to N_2O emissions. In addition, nitrogen can enter the groundwater, but also heavy metals, hormones and microplastics, if compost or biogas waste is used for fertilisation in addition to manure. The positive effect of biochar to build up humus on nutrient-rich soils of the temperate climate zone is also questionable, as this has so far only been proven in nutrient-poor, tropical soils (Jeffery et al. 2011). Further, there are many open questions regarding the suitable pollutant-free initial substrate, the profitability, and the overall ecological assessment.

3.4 Conservation of carbon in organic soils and restoration of wetlands

In contrast to mineral soils, organic soils contain a high proportion of organic matter (> 12%, IPCC 2014). Organic soils are formed in peatlands by the formation of a peat layer of at least 30 cm and 30% organic matter over thousands of years. These peats consist of plant biomass (e.g., peat mosses) that does not decompose under the water-saturated conditions and associated lack of oxygen. As a result, peatlands can store carbon for thousands of years (Michel et al. 2011). Because of their high water content, peatlands are considered as wetlands. Due to agricultural use and the construction of settlement structures, the drainage of peatlands in Germany began many centuries ago. As a result, the water table in the organic soil decreases and the stored carbon escapes into the atmosphere via oxidation. A large part of the drained organic soils is located in the northwest of Lower Saxony, Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania and Brandenburg but also in the foothills of the Alps in Bavaria (BMEL 2016b). If the water table is ≥ -0.1 m, then the soils are considered undrained, which applies to only 8% (150,000 ha) of organic soils in Germany. These are located on unused land but also in forests and

grassland (Tiemeyer et al. 2020). The average water table in grassland is -0.5 m and in cropland -0.6 m. While undrained organic soils produce hardly any CO₂ emissions, when drained to -0.9 m, emissions of up to 40 t CO₂/ha/a can occur (Tiemeyer et al. 2020).

Therefore, avoiding emissions from drained organic soils in grassland, cropland, and wetlands is of high importance to maintain the net sink in the land use sector in Germany. If the water table is raised again to the point where peatlands regenerate, then they can additionally contribute to the capture and storage of carbon from the atmosphere.

In addition, emissions arise from the extraction of peat. In Germany, about 4 million m³ of peat was extracted in 2018, mainly in Lower Saxony, and about the same amount was imported, mainly from the Baltic States²². Since 1980, peat extraction has largely been carried out on drained and fallow agricultural land, which is subsequently rewetted if there is still a layer of peat about 50 cm thick. Peat is used as an important basic substrate, especially in private and commercial horticulture (BMEL 2020c). The German Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture (BMEL) will develop a peat reduction strategy with the aim of discontinuing peat use in the private sector and significantly reducing it in commercial horticulture. In the long term, the aim is to reduce peat use in Germany (BMEL 2020b). The use of peat moss from paludiculture cultivation (see below) is being researched as a possible substitute substrate (Krebs et al. 2015).

After raising the water table on managed organic soils, emissions can be effectively avoided (Tiemeyer et al. 2020). However, intensive use as pasture and fodder cropland or the cultivation of common crops is no longer possible. In contrast, grassland management as extensive pasture can be an alternative use even with higher water levels. In addition, extensively used wet grasslands are a species-rich ecosystem that contributes to the protection of a variety of species (Isselstein 2018). Another alternative form of management can be the cultivation of paludicultures such as cattails (*Typha*), reeds (*Phragmites*) and peat mosses (*Sphagnum*). They are cultivated under rewetted conditions, which protects the still existing peat body and thus emissions from peat decomposition can be avoided (Wichtmann et al. 2016).

3.4.1 Potential of the option for climate protection

In a study by Prognos et al. (2020), measures to avoid emissions from cultivated organic soils are implemented, which by 2030 could reduce emissions by 7 Mt CO₂e (25.2 t CO₂e/ha) can be achieved. To achieve this, peat cutting was stopped in this scenario and 20% (278,000 ha) of arable land and grassland was rewetted by 2030. Of this land, 40 % is used for extensive grazing or mowing and 30% is used for paludiculture. The remaining 30 % of rewetted land will be permanently removed from use. By 2050, the rewetted area will be increased to nearly 50% (650,000 ha) and half of it will be used for

²² [Bundesinformationszentrum Landwirtschaft](#)

paludiculture, while the remaining rewetted areas will no longer be cultivated. As a result, 18 million t CO₂e (27.7 t CO₂e/ha) of emission reduction can be achieved.

In the climate protection report of the scientific advisory board at the BMEL (BMEL 2016b), three measure scenarios for achieving emission reductions on organic soils are presented.

In these scenarios, rewetting and extensification of the use of organic soils are implemented on different proportions of land, with total emission reductions approximately 20 years after implementation of the measure, ranging from 7 to 15.2 Mt CO₂e per year (BMEL 2016b). For the calculations of these mitigation potentials, it was assumed that rewetting, depending on the depth of the water level, has between 20 and 40 t CO₂e/ha of potential savings (see Table 4). In the potential effect of extensification measures, water levels are also crucial, as well as the type of change in land use. For example, raising the water level and changing the use from cropland or intensive grassland to extensive grassland can result in a reduction of up to 20 t CO₂e/ha (BMEL 2016b).

Table 4: Scenarios illustrating mitigation potentials for rewetting and extensification of organic soils (BMEL 2016b).

Scenarios for reducing emissions from organic soils	Agricultural area for rewetting in Mha	Assumption of reduction potential in t CO ₂ e/ha for rewetting	Area for extensification in million ha	Assumption of reduction potential in t CO ₂ e/ha for extensification	Total reduction potential in Mt CO ₂ e/year
Scenario a)	0.1	40	0.2	15	7
Scenario b)	0.2	30	0.4	10	12
Scenario c)	0.3	20	0.6	6	15.2

In a publication by Tanneberger et al. (2021), two scenarios are considered to achieve emission reductions on organic soils under cropland and grassland. With a complete conversion of cropland on organic soils to grassland and an abandonment of peat cutting by 2030. In addition, water levels in grassland are raised to an annual average of -30 cm (wet) to 15 % completely rewetted by 2030. This will result in emission reductions of up to 17 Mt of CO₂ by 2030. Finally, all organic soils in grassland (including cropland) will be rewetted by 2050. This will save a total of 35.8 Mt CO₂ emissions compared to 2020 (Tanneberger et al. 2021).

3.4.2 Durability or reversibility of the option

In principle, the measure is reversible, as emissions can be released again through renewed direct or even indirect drainage (e.g. interventions in the water catchment area of the peatland). Therefore, the permanent change in the use of organic soils is a necessary prerequisite to ensure the long-term nature of the climate protection effect (BMEL 2016b). Due to ongoing climate change and the resulting lower precipitation in some regions, there could be a seasonal lowering of the water table on rewetted areas. This effect may be exacerbated if the hydrology of peatlands is compromised by human impacts (e.g.

high water use in settlements). Therefore, it is important to restore the natural water balance in the catchment area of rewetted peatlands, if possible (Swindles et al. 2019).

Emission reduction potential can be reduced due to methane emissions that may occur after rewetting. These emissions are caused by methanogenic bacteria in the uppermost soil layer (Hendriks et al. 2007). Therefore, removal of the top soil layer prior to rewetting can reduce up to 99 % of methane emissions (Harpenslager et al. 2015).

3.4.3 Synergies and conflicts with other societal goals

Many synergies arise for the water balance and especially for nature conservation (BMEL 2016b). The rewetting of organic soils with subsequent extensive use as wet grassland, creates valuable habitats that can be used by many meadow bird species that have become rare (e.g. lapwing) (Oppermann et al. 2020). For reasons of meadow bird protection, sufficiently extensively managed grassland areas should therefore be preserved and not completely rewetted. Complete rewetting with renaturation and subsequent protection of peatlands also makes an important contribution to achieving national and European biodiversity goals (BMU 2007; European Commission 2020). However, the implementation of these measures may lead to competition for arable land, especially for animal feed, field crops and intensive pasture. This can cause economic disadvantages for some rural regions, e.g. in the north-west of Lower Saxony (BMEL 2016b). In addition, if a substantial part of organic soils under agricultural use is rewetted, cultivation on mineral arable land and grassland could intensify, which may be detrimental to environmentally sound production (Tanneberger et al. 2021). In addition, this may lead to further relocation of agricultural production abroad, which could possibly lead to additional emissions, such as deforestation and peatland drainage. Therefore, measures to reduce emissions from organic soils should be implemented together with accompanying measures to reduce the consumption of all meat and dairy products (WBGU 2020). The cessation of peat extraction and subsequent rewetting of land has a positive impact on nature conservation goals (see above). However, as long as no cost-effective and high-quality substrate alternatives for horticulture are available, peat imports may still occur in the medium term, which also lead to emissions (BMEL 2016b).

3.4.4 Climate related risks / impacts and effects on the local environment

The most approved relevant climate-related extreme events are according to the interviewee droughts and fires. Other extremes, such as heat and cold waves, frosts, very mild winters, and landslides are likely to have an impact but still lack the scientific experience.

Droughts have an impact on the water supply and on productivity and **fire** is occurring on peatland. **Heat waves** effect the water supply as well and have an impact on the productivity of grassland if on organic soil.

The expert concludes that the most important parameters regarding the effects of Rewetting on the local environment are water balance, soil protection, bird diversity, climate resilience and fire risk reduction.

Rewetting contributes highly to the **water balance**. Vegetation that is adapted to wet conditions show higher evatranspiration than grassland on drained soils. It might be necessary to store “winter water” onsite to have a full inundation (aboveground water levels of >50cm) during the winter time to avoid too low water tables in summer. The impacts on **soil protection** depend very much on the intensity of rewetting measures. The nearer the water tables get to the soil surface, the higher the emission reductions on GHG will be. The effects on the birdlife of rewetted areas will be important for aquatic bird species (and ornithologists) but also managed rewetted areas are a prerequisite for the re-introduction of rare bird species such as the aquatic warbler (*Acrocephalus paludicola*). Regarding **climate resilience**, when an area is fully rewetted, N₂O emission will immediately stop, CO₂ emissions are reduced with every increase in water levels up to 5 cm below the soil surface. If water tables rise above this threshold, CH₄ emission occur. Rewetting has a negative effect on the occurrence of peat **fires**.

3.4.5 *Socio-economic risks and uncertainties*

The expert sees the main constraints regarding the implementation of rewetting are the acceptance of land users and landowners, the lack of sufficient incentives, the missing of political willingness and a missing market for products from paludiculture. The most promising opportunity seems to be the potential to reduce GHG emission and mitigate climate change. The expert currently sees problems as there is still an underestimation by the population of drainage-based management of peatlands and thus there is not enough support for rewetting and the implementation of paludiculture.

4. Conclusions

4.1 Contribution of LMTs in Germany to climate protection

The land-based mitigation technologies reported in the land use change and forestry (LULUCF) sector in Germany still form a net sink and can thus contribute to Germany's path to climate neutrality. The most important LMT in Germany is the forest. The sink capacity of the forest is projected to decline. In order to achieve a sufficient net sink capacity in the future, emissions from land use from arable land and grassland, among other things, must be more than halved from the current level of over 40 million tonnes of CO₂e. In addition, the sink capacity of forests would have to be restored to approximately the current level.

Ambitious protection of organic soils, e.g. through rewetting, can avoid emissions from land use and at the same time create valuable habitats for various wetland species. In addition, carbon can be sequestered in wood in the long term through more extensive management in already resilient mixed and deciduous forests, through afforestation and via the establishment of woody structures on agricultural land. These LMTs can also contribute to the protection of biodiversity in forest stands of relatively high density and create new valuable habitats.

4.2 Limitations to the LMT potential

The potential of LMTs in Germany is limited. All mitigation measures will require significant changes in management to some extent, and they conflict directly or indirectly with each other or with other land uses such as settlement expansion in relation to land demand. Where mitigation measures affect agricultural or forestry production, displacement effects need to be taken into account, e.g. through accompanying measures such as livestock reduction and changing consumption patterns.

The need for financial investments for e.g. compensation payments will depend on many different factors. In general, mitigation measures in the land use sector can trigger opportunities for development in rural areas and be of social benefit. They are often not quantifiable but are likely to have a positive impact.

Climate change will affect all investigated LMTs in the medium to long-term perspective. Impacts on plant growth may be positively influenced by higher average temperatures, whereas acceleration of decomposition, especially in wetlands, may lead to net emissions over time. Increasing natural disturbances are also expected to have a negative impact on the carbon stored in trees.

5. References

BMEL (2012): Ergebnisdatenbank der Bundeswaldinventur. Bundesministerium für Ernährung und Landwirtschaft. Online verfügbar unter <https://bwi.info/>, zuletzt geprüft am 31.08.2017.

BMEL (2016a): Der Wald in Deutschland. Ausgewählte Ergebnisse der dritten Bundeswaldinventur. Bundesministerium für Ernährung und Landwirtschaft.

BMEL (2016b): Klimaschutz in der Land- und Forstwirtschaft sowie den nachgelagerten Bereichen Ernährung und Holzverwendung. Bundesministerium für Ernährung und Landwirtschaft, zuletzt geprüft am 03.04.2017.

BMEL (2020a): Ergebnisse der Waldzustandserhebung 2019, zuletzt geprüft am 20.05.2020.

BMEL (2020b): Gärtnern ohne Torf - Schützt das Klima! Online verfügbar unter https://www.torffrei.info/fileadmin/torfminderung/dateien/Torf_Flyer_DIN_Lang.pdf, zuletzt geprüft am 08.06.2021.

BMEL (2020c): Torf und alternative Substratausgangsstoffe. Bonn. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.ble-medien-service.de/0129/torf-und-alternative-substratausgangsstoffe>, zuletzt geprüft am 07.06.2021.

BMU (2007): Nationale Strategie zur biologischen Vielfalt. Vom Bundeskabinett am 7. 11. 2007 beschlossen. Berlin.

BMUB/UBA (2016): Die Wasserrahmenrichtlinie – Deutschlands Gewässer 2015. Bonn, Dessau.

Böttcher, Hannes; Hennenberg, Klaus Josef; Winger, Christian (2018a): FABio-Waldmodell - Modellbeschreibung Version 0.54. Öko-Institut e.V. Berlin. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.oeko.de/fileadmin/oekodoc/FABio-Wald-Modellbeschreibung.pdf>.

Böttcher, Hannes; Hennenberg, Klaus Josef; Winger, Christian (2018b): Waldvision Deutschland - Beschreibung von Methoden, Annahmen und Ergebnissen. Öko-Institut e.V. Berlin. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.oeko.de/fileadmin/oekodoc/Waldvision-Methoden-und-Ergebnisse.pdf>.

Chen, Songchao; Arrouays, Dominique; Angers, Denis A.; Martin, Manuel P.; Walter, Christian (2019): Soil carbon stocks under different land uses and the applicability of the soil carbon saturation concept. In: *Soil and Tillage Research* 188, S. 53–58. DOI: 10.1016/j.still.2018.11.001.

dena (2021): dena-Leitstudie Aufbruch Klimaneutralität. Eine gesamtgesellschaftliche Aufgabe. Hg. v. Deutsche Energie-Agentur GmbH.

Dulamsuren, C.; Hauck, M.; Kopp, G.; Ruff, M.; Leuschner, C. (2017): European beech responds to climate change with growth decline at lower, and growth increase at higher elevations in the center of its distribution range (SW Germany). In: *Trees* 31 (2), S. 673–686. DOI: 10.1007/s00468-016-1499-x.

European Commission (2020): Stepping up Europe’s 2030 climate ambition. Investing in a climate-neutral future for the benefit of our people. Impact Assessment accompanying the document

Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, Commission Staff Working Document (SWD(2020) 176 final Part 1/2).

Fischer, A. (2003): Forstliche Vegetationskunde. Eine Einführung in die Geobotanik. 3. Aufl. Stuttgart: Eugen Ulmer.

Frank, S.; Havlík, P.; SOUSSANA, J.-F.; Wollenberg, E.; Obersteiner, M. (2017): The potential of soil organic carbon sequestration for climate change mitigation and food security (CCAFS Info Note).

Gattinger, Andreas; Muller, Adrian; Haeni, Matthias; Skinner, Colin; Fließbach, Andreas; Buchmann, Nina et al. (2012): Enhanced top soil carbon stocks under organic farming. In: *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* 109 (44), S. 18226–18231. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1209429109.

Griscom, Bronson W.; Adams, Justin; Ellis, Peter W.; Houghton, Richard a.; Lomax, Guy; Miteva, Daniela A. et al. (2017): Natural climate solutions. In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 114 (44), S. 11645–11650. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1710465114.

Harpenslager, S. F.; van den Elzen, E.; Kox, M.A.R.; Smolders, A.J.P.; Ettwig, K.; Lamers, L.P.M. (2015): Rewetting former agricultural peatlands: Topsoil removal as a prerequisite to avoid strong nutrient and greenhouse gas emissions. In: *Ecological Engineering* (84), S. 159–168.

Hendriks, D. M. D.; van Huissteden, J.; Dolman, A. J.; and van der Molen, M. K. (2007): The full greenhouse gas balance of an abandoned peat meadow, Biogeosciences. In: *Biogeosciences* (4), S. 411–424.

Hennenberg, K.; Böttcher, H.; Reise, J.; Herold, A.; Bohn, F.; Gutsch, M.; Reyer, C. (2021): Interpretation des Klimaschutzgesetzes für die Waldbewirtschaftung verlangt adäquate Datenbasis – Reaktion auf die Stellungnahme des Wissenschaftlichen Beirats für Waldpolitik beim BMEL (vom 22.06.2021). Hg. v. Öko-Institut e.V. (Öko-Institut Working Paper 3/2021). Online verfügbar unter <https://www.oeko.de/fileadmin/oeкодoc/03-WP-Klimaschutzgesetz-Waldbewirtschaftung.pdf>.

Hennenberg, Klaus; Böttcher, Hannes; Wiegmann, Kirsten; Reise, Judith; Fehrenbach, Horst (2019): Kohlenstoffspeicherung in Wald und Holzprodukten. In: *AFZ-DerWald* (17), S. 36–39.

Hennig, P.; Schnell, S.; Riedel, T. (2019): Rohstoffquelle Wald - Holzvorrat auf neuem Rekord. In: *AFZ-DerWald* 74 (14), S. 24–27.

IPCC (2014): 2013 Supplement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories: Wetlands. Hiraishi, T., Krug, T., Tanabe, K., Srivastava, N., Baasansuren, J., Fukuda, M. and Troxler, T.G. (eds). Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. Switzerland.

IPCC (2019): Summary for Policymakers. In: *Climate Change and Land: an IPCC special report on climate change, desertification, land degradation, sustainable land management, food security, and greenhouse gas fluxes in terrestrial ecosystems*. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.ipcc.ch/srccl/>.

- Isselstein, J. (2018): Protecting biodiversity in grasslands. In: Athole Marshall und Rosemary Collins (Hg.): Improving grassland and pasture management in temperate agriculture. Cambridge: Burleigh Dodds Science Publishing (Burleigh Dodds Series in Agricultural Science, Number 51), S. 381–396.
- Jeffery, S.; Verheijen, F.G.A.; van der Velde, M.; Bastos, A. C. (2011): A quantitative review of the effects of biochar application to soils on crop productivity using meta-analysis. In: *Agr. Ecosyst. Environ.* 144 (1), S. 175–187. DOI: 10.1016/j.agee.2011.08.015.
- Kolbe, H. (2012): Zusammenführende Untersuchungen zur Genauigkeit und Anwendung von Methoden der Humusbilanzierung im konventionellen und ökologischen Landbau. In: Bilanzierungsmethoden und Versorgungsniveau für Humus. Hg. v. Schriftenreihe des Sächsischen Landesamtes für Umwelt, Landwirtschaft und Geologie. Dresden.
- Körschens, M.; Breitschuh, G.; Eckert, H. (2018): Agrarfakten-Humus als CO₂-Senke-eine fatale Illusion. Online verfügbar unter http://files.agrarfakten.de/200000233-3eaf83faaa/AF%20Senke%2036%202018_07_24.pdf, zuletzt geprüft am 26.03.2021.
- Krebs, M.; Gaudig, G.; Wichmann, S.; Joosten, H. (2015): Torfmooskultivierung: Moorschutz durch Moornutzung. In: *TELMA - Berichte der Deutschen Gesellschaft für Moor- und Torfkunde* Beiheft 5, S. 59–70. DOI: 10.23689/fidgeo-2927.
- Mausolf, K.; Härdtle, W.; Jansen, K.; Benjamin M. Delory; Dietrich Hertel; Christoph Leuschner et al. (2018): Legacy effects of land-use modulate tree growth responses to climate extremes. In: *Oecologia* 187 (3), S. 825–837. DOI: 10.1007/s00442-018-4156-9.
- Mette, T.; Dolos, K.; Meinardus, K.; Achim Bräuning; Björn Reineking; Markus Blaschke et al. (2013): Climatic turning point for beech and oak under climate change in Central Europe. In: *Ecosphere* 4 (12), S. 1–19. DOI: 10.1890/ES13-00115.1.
- Michel, B.; Plättner, O.; Gründel, F. (2011): Klima-Hotspot Moorböden (Forschungs Report, 2). Online verfügbar unter https://www.thuenen.de/media/institute/ak/Projekte/moor/Klima-Hotspot_Moorboeden.pdf, zuletzt geprüft am 04.06.2021.
- Müller, J. (2019): Die forsthydrologische Forschung im Nordostdeutschen Tiefland. Veranlassung, Methoden, Ergebnisse und Perspektiven. (Habilitationsschrift). Hg. v. Agrar- und Umweltwissenschaftliche Fakultät Universität Rostock. Rostock (SchrR Umweltingenieurwesen 91).
- Norris, Catherine; Hobson, Peter; Ibisch, Pierre L. (2011): Microclimate and vegetation function as indicators of forest thermodynamic efficiency. In: *Journal of Applied Ecology* 102, no-no. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-2664.2011.02084.x.
- O'Brolchain, N. (2020): CAP Policy Brief Peatlands in the new European Union Version 4.8. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.eurosite.org/wp-content/uploads/CAP-Policy-Brief-Peatlands-in-the-new-European-Union-Version-4.8.pdf>.
- Oehmichen, K.; Klatt, S.; Gerber, K.; Polley, H.; Röhling, S.; Dunger, K. (2018): Die alternativen WEHAM-Szenarien: Holzpräferenz, Naturschutzpräferenz und Trendfortschreibung. Szenarienentwicklung,

Ergebnisse und Analyse. Johann Heinrich von Thünen-Institut. Braunschweig (Thünen report 59). Online verfügbar unter https://www.thuenen.de/media/publikationen/thuenen-report/Thuenen-Report_59.pdf.

O'Hara, K. L.; Ramage, B. S. (2013): Silviculture in an uncertain world: utilizing multi-aged management systems to integrate disturbance. In: *Forestry (Lond)* 86 (4), S. 401–410. DOI: 10.1093/forestry/cpt012.

Oppermann, R.; Pfister, S. C.; Eirich, A. (2020): Sicherung der Biodiversität in der Agrarlandschaft - Quantifizierung des Maßnahmenbedarfs und Empfehlungen zur Umsetzung. Institut für Agrarökologie und Biodiversität (IFAB). Mannheim.

Pilli, R.; Grassi, G.; Kurz, W., A.; Jose V. Moris; Raúl Abad Viñas (2016): Modelling forest carbon stock changes as affected by harvest and natural disturbances. II. EU-level analysis. In: *Carbon Balance Man- age* 11 (1), S. 1–19. DOI: 10.1186/s13021-016-0059-4.

Poeplau, Christopher; Don, Axel (2015): Carbon sequestration in agricultural soils via cultivation of cover crops – A meta-analysis. In: *Agr. Ecosyst. Environ.* 200, S. 33–41. DOI: 10.1016/j.agee.2014.10.024.

Poeplau, Christopher; Don, Axel; Vesterdal, Lars; Leifeld, Jens; van Wesemael, Bas; Schumacher, Jens; Gensior, Andreas (2011): Temporal dynamics of soil organic carbon after land-use change in the temperate zone - carbon response functions as a model approach. In: *Glob. Change Biol.* 17 (7), S. 2415–2427. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-2486.2011.02408.x.

Prognos; Öko-Institut; Wuppertal-Institut (2020): Klimaneutrales Deutschland. Studie im Auftrag von Agora Energiewende, Agora Verkehrswende und Stiftung Klimaneutralität. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.agora-energiewende.de/veroeffentlichungen/klimaneutrales-deutschland>.

Reise, J.; Wenz E; Kukulka F; Linde A; Winter S (2017a): Bewertung der Waldbiodiversität der WEHAM-Szenarien. Hg. v. Allgemeine Forstzeitschrift (13).

Reise, Judith; Hennenberg, Klaus; Winter, Susanne; Winger, Christian; Höltermann, Anke (2017b): Analyse und Diskussion naturschutzfachlich bedeutsamer Ergebnisse der dritten Bundeswaldinventur. BfN-Skript 427. Bundesamt für Naturschutz.

Reise, Judith; Kukulka, Florian; Flade, Martin; Winter, Susanne (2019): Characterising the richness and diversity of forest bird species using National Forest Inventory data in Germany. In: *Forest Ecology and Management* 432, S. 799–811. DOI: 10.1016/j.foreco.2018.10.012.

Repenning, J.; Harthan, R.; Blanck, R.; Böttcher, H.; Braungarth, S. Bürger, V.; Cook, V. Emele, L. et al. (in press): Klimaschutzinstrumente-Szenario 2030 (KIS-2030) zur Erreichung der Klimaschutzziele 2030. Teilbericht.

Rumpel, Cornelia; Amiraslani, Farshad; Chenu, Claire; Garcia Cardenas, Magaly; Kaonga, Martin; Koutika, Lydie-Stella et al. (2020): The 4p1000 initiative: Opportunities, limitations and challenges for implementing soil organic carbon sequestration as a sustainable development strategy. In: *Ambio* 49 (1), S. 350–360. DOI: 10.1007/s13280-019-01165-2.

Rüter, Sebastian; Stümer, Wolfgang; Dunger, Karsten (2017): Treibhausgasbilanzen der WEHAM-Szenarien. In: *AFZ-DerWald* (13), S. 30–31. Online verfügbar unter https://www.weham-szenarien.de/fileadmin/weham/Ergebnisse/AFZ_13_17_7_Treibhausgasbilanzen_der_WEHAM-Szenarien.pdf, zuletzt geprüft am 27.10.2017.

Seidl, Rupert; Schelhaas, Mart-Jan; Rammer, Werner; Verkerk, Pieter Johannes (2014): Increasing forest disturbances in Europe and their impact on carbon storage. In: *nature climate change* 4 (9), S. 806–810. DOI: 10.1038/nclimate2318.

Seidl, Rupert; Thom, Dominik; Kautz, Markus; Martin-Benito, Dario; Peltoniemi, Mikko; Vacchiano, Giorgio et al. (2017): Forest disturbances under climate change. In: *nature climate change* 7, S. 395–402. DOI: 10.1038/nclimate3303.

Swindles, G. T.; Morris, P. J.; Donal J. Mullan; Richard J. Payne; Thomas P. Roland; Matthew J. Amesbury et al. (2019): Widespread drying of European peatlands in recent centuries. In: *Nat. Geosci.* 12 (11), S. 922–928. DOI: 10.1038/s41561-019-0462-z.

Sykes, Alasdair J.; Macleod, Michael; Eory, Vera; Rees, Robert M.; Payen, Florian; Myrgeiotis, Vasilis et al. (2020): Characterising the biophysical, economic and social impacts of soil carbon sequestration as a greenhouse gas removal technology. In: *Glob. Change Biol.* 26 (3), S. 1085–1108. DOI: 10.1111/gcb.14844.

Tanneberger, Franziska; Abel, Susanne; Couwenberg, John; Dahms, Tobias; Gaudig, Greta; Günther, Anke et al. (2021): Towards net zero CO₂ in 2050: An emission reduction pathway for organic soils in Germany. In: *Mires and Peat* 27, S. 1–17. DOI: 10.19189/MaP.2020.SNPG.StA.1951.

Thünen Institut für Agrarklimaschutz (2018): Humus in landwirtschaftlich genutzten Böden Deutschlands. Ausgewählte Ergebnisse der Bodenzustandserhebung. Hg. v. BMEL. Bonn. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.bmel.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/DE/Broschueren/Bodenzustandserhebung.html>, zuletzt geprüft am 09.06.2021.

Tiemeyer, Bärbel; Freibauer, Annette; Borraz, Elisa Albiac; Augustin, Jürgen; Bechtold, Michel; Beetz, Sascha et al. (2020): A new methodology for organic soils in national greenhouse gas inventories. Data synthesis, derivation and application. In: *Ecological Indicators* 109, S. 105838. DOI: 10.1016/j.ecolind.2019.105838.

UBA (2020a): Berichterstattung unter der Klimarahmenkonvention der Vereinten Nationen und dem Kyoto-Protokoll 2020. Nationaler Inventarbericht zum Deutschen Treibhausgasinventar 1990 – 2018. CLIMATE CHANGE 22/2020. Hg. v. Umweltbundesamt (UBA). Dessau-Roßlau, Germany.

UBA (2020b): National Inventory Report for the German Greenhouse Gas Inventory 1990 -2018. Submission under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change and the Kyoto Protocol 2020.

UBA (2021): Projektionsbericht 2021 für Deutschland. Gemäß Artikel 18 der Verordnung (EU) 2018/1999 des Europäischen Parlaments und des Rates vom 11. Dezember 2018 über das Governance-System für die Energieunion und für den Klimaschutz, zur Änderung der Verordnungen (EG) Nr. 663/2009 und (EG) Nr. 715/2009 des Europäischen Parlaments und des Rates sowie §10 (2) des Bundes-Klimaschutzgesetzes. Hg. v. Umweltbundesamt (UBA). Online verfügbar unter https://www.bmu.de/fileadmin/Daten_BMU/Download_PDF/Klimaschutz/projektionsbericht_2021_bf.pdf.

Verkerk, P. J.; Mavsar, R.; Giergiczny, M.; Lindner, M.; Edwards, D.; Schelhaas, M. J. (2014): Assessing impacts of intensified biomass production and biodiversity protection on ecosystem services provided by European forests. In: *Ecosystem Services* 9, S. 155–165. DOI: 10.1016/j.ecoser.2014.06.004.

Walentowski, H.; Falk, W.; Mette, T.; Jörg Kunz; Achim Bräuning; Cathrin Meinardus et al. (2017): Assessing future suitability of tree species under climate change by multiple methods: a case study in southern Germany. In: *Annals of Forest Research* 60 (1), S. 101–126. DOI: 10.15287/afr.2016.789.

WBGU (2020): Landwende im Anthropozän: Von der Konkurrenz zur Integration. Berlin. Online verfügbar unter https://www.wbgu.de/fileadmin/user_upload/wbgu/publikationen/hauptgutachten/hg2020/pdf/WBGU_HG2020_ZF.pdf, zuletzt geprüft am 02.06.2021.

Wichtmann, W.; Schröder, C.; Joosten, H. (2016): Paludiculture - productive use of wet peatlands. Climate protection - biodiversity - regional economic benefits.

Wiesmeier, M.; Burmeister, J.; Treisch, M. und Brandhuber, R. (2017): Klimaschutz durch Humusaufbau – Umsetzungsmöglichkeiten der 4 Promille-Initiative in Bayern. Online verfügbar unter https://www.researchgate.net/publication/321141231_Klimaschutz_durch_Humusaufbau_-_Umsetzungsmoeglichkeiten_der_4_Promille-Initiative_in_Bayern, zuletzt geprüft am 26.03.2021.

Annex I Validation of Germany's LMT shortlist through stakeholders

The validation of the LMTs was done by stakeholders with whom contact was already established due to other projects. Several meetings were held and discussions took place in the context of those other projects and thus were also used for extracting the information needed regarding the validation of LMTs.

LMT	Meeting / Event	Stakeholders	Discussion	Conclusion
BECCS	6	4,5	Not in favor of a technical solution on bio energy; OI has no own capacities to follow up	Not to be considered further in LandMarc CS
Rewetting of organic soils	4, 5	3, 4, 6	Advanced on the political side, but lacks implementation mechanisms	Important LMT to be considered
Abandoning peat extraction	7	4	This is a measure that should be implemented faster	Important LMT to be considered
Avoided conversion of grassland			GL protection already legally binding, therefore no additional potential, however continuation needed for containing C stock still emissions from GL conversion due to net area approach	Relevant LMT to be considered, need for further exchange/ discussion
Afforestation			Currently not high on political agenda due to anticipated agricultural land demand	Important LMT to be considered, need for further exchange/ discussion
Managing forests incl. HWP	1, 2, 3	1,2,3,7,8	LMT with high potential but intensively debated between stakeholders High potential through large area Trade-offs with wood supply, therefore forest and HWP carbon storage need to be assessed in combination	Important LMT to be considered
Increasing carbon in soil and vegetation on agricultural land		4	Ongoing discussion with BMU	Relevant LMT to be considered

Meeting / Event

1. Workshop, FSC, Sozialkammer-Treffen, 21.01. 2021
2. Conference, Charta für Holz 2.0, Statustagung, 28.04.2021
3. Panel discussion, Familienbetriebe Land und Forst, Rewarding the climate protection performance of the forest, 06.11.2020
4. Bilateral exchange with the BMEL, 04.05. 2021
5. Bilateral exchange with Thünen-Institute and BMU, 07.05.2021
6. Bilateral exchange with BMU and UBA, various meetings in 2020
7. Bilateral exchange with BMU, project meetings in 2021 and e-mail exchange

Stakeholders

1. Certifiers of wood and forests, Forest Stewardship Council (FSC)
2. German Forest Associations (BDF, DFWR)
3. Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture (BMEL)
4. Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety (BMU)
5. German Environment Agency (UBA)
6. Thünen Institute, Institute of Forest Ecosystems
7. Timber and wood associations (German Timber Industry Council (DHWR), Main Association of the German Wood Industry (HDH), Association of the German Wood-Based Panel Industry e.V. (VHI), German sawmill and timber industry (DeSH)), Association of forest owners
8. Representatives of political parties in Germany

LANDMARC

SCALING LAND-BASED MITIGATION SOLUTIONS IN THE NETHERLANDS

LAND-BASED MITIGATION NARRATIVES

JIN & BIOCLEAR
STATUS: CONFIDENTIAL

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1. Co-design of LMT scenarios

1.1 Introduction

This report includes a description of a generic nation-wide transition scenario for the implementation of land-based mitigation technologies and practices for the AFOLU sector (agriculture, forestry, and other land use sectors) in The Netherlands.

To co-develop these scenarios a broad range of information/literature sources, and stakeholder consultations have been conducted. Land-based mitigation technologies (LMTs) includes a broad range of carbon farming options and/or nature-based solutions for emission reduction and carbon removal, such as peatland rewetting, BECCS, biochar, agroforestry, and afforestation. It is the intention of this report to serve as input for economic and land use simulation modelling to estimate (quantify) the impacts of nation-wide scaling up of a series of LMT solutions.

The combination of LMT solutions ('National LMT portfolio') described in this report has been selected (short-listed), after consultation with several stakeholders. Key selection criteria included policy relevance, technological feasibility, and scalability.

The Dutch climate agreement states that the Dutch AFOLU sectors will have to be climate neutral by 2050. This implies that deep cuts in GHG emissions are needed, and to compensate for any residual/remaining emissions a certain amount of carbon removals will also be needed.

A portfolio of land-based mitigation solutions for agriculture and land use sectors

We consider a mixture of the following key reduction and removal solutions:

1. Peatland management (rewetting and paludiculture)
2. Agroforestry (grasslands trees outside forests)
3. Afforestation (land converted into forest land)
4. Bio-energy carbon capture and storage (BECCS) and recycling of nutrients and organic carbon

Peatland management

CO₂ emissions due to the drainage of peat(y) soils within The Netherlands are responsible for about 3-4% of the national GHG emissions. On top of that the oxidation of peat causes significant soil subsidence in large areas of the country. There are already many pilot initiatives that experiment with different technologies for rewetting peat(y) soils in an effort to limit soil subsidence and retain the soil carbon. These pilot initiatives mostly are executed in relation to dairy cattle farming, where grass is cultivated in peat meadows and used as animal feed. In addition, a more limited set of pilot projects are experiments with different crops and vegetation that thrive better in wet conditions (paludiculture). To date, the total acreage of pilot rewetting projects has been rather limited. While the pilot projects show promising results, nationwide scale-up of rewetting comes with a series of challenges. For example, the business model for rewetting for the dairy cattle farmer is still too weak (in most cases the dairy cattle farmer will have to accept or switch to another form of land-use). On top of that the national water management systems (run by regional water boards) that serves

different land use functions (farming, housing, industry) will become much more decentralised/localised and difficult to manage to guarantee water safety, quality, and quantity.

Afforestation and agroforestry

While the total area of forest cover (about 10% of total land surface area) in The Netherlands is limited, the forest sector is a significant carbon sink. While forest cover in The Netherlands gradually increased since the 1970s, but after 2013 rapidly declined again to 1990 levels. The trend in deforestation has nearly come to a halt in the past few years. A key cause for deforestation were a range of nature restoration initiatives that resulted in forest land being converted back into other (more open) forms of nature landscapes. There are increasing ambitions to expand the forest area outside the already existing nature areas. This can be done either by means of afforestation, or by planting more trees outside forest, such as through agroforestry (e.g., food forests or reintroducing landscape elements such as hedgerows). In most cases the expansion of the forest / agroforestry area will come at the expense of land used for agricultural purposes.

Bio-energy carbon capture and storage/utilization and recycling or organic carbon

Bio-energy carbon capture and storage/utilization (or BECCS/U) is considered one of the key options for carbon removal internationally. Also, within The Netherlands, BECCS/U is considered a serious climate change mitigation option, with significant potential. However, most BECCS studies and scenarios for The Netherlands assume that large amounts of biomass will be imported from abroad, where after combustion the biogenic CO₂ will be captured and stored in underground geological formations. Within this scenario study we analyse BECCS/U, where the bioenergy stems from the anaerobic digestion (AD) of (liquid) animal manure, and where the excess biogenic CO₂ from the biogas is captured and stored/used.

The main advantage of animal manure is that it is available domestically in large quantities. Currently, only about 5-10% of the total annual domestic production of animal manure is processed or treated. The biogas production potential is significant (reduction)¹, as well as the potential for reducing methane emissions from manure management (reduction) and associated ammonia emissions (NH₃) from stable systems. The captured CO₂ can be either stored underground (removal) or used in several industries as feedstock (reduction). On top of that the AD of manure results in a digestate, that can be further processed and converted into an organic fertilizer. Organic fertilizers have the potential to replace chemical fertilizers (reduction) as well as aid in the accumulation of soil carbon (removal).

The impact of scaling up the LMT portfolio

¹ Biogas can be used directly for co-firing, or be upgraded to be injected into the gas grid or upgraded to transport fuel (bio-CNG or bio-LNG).

Scaling up of these different LMTs to the national level will be highly challenging for a small, and densely populated country like The Netherlands. The transition in the AFOLU sector, will likely have a broad range of spatial, socio-economic, and environmental impacts that are difficult to predict.

To be able to co-design more realistic scaling up scenarios for the selected LMT portfolio to be able to meet the set climate sectoral 2050 net-zero climate target, we also must consider a range of other relevant (policy) developments and targets that have an (in)direct impact on the GHG emissions within this sector.

Figure 1-1: Land use in The Netherlands (2017 data)

Source: CBS, 2021

Within the agricultural sector, livestock farming in The Netherlands has a large claim on the use of scarce land. In 2022, about 2,2 mln. ha of land (or 54% of total land use) was used for agricultural purposes. A sizeable part of this arable land 1,16 mln. ha (54%) was used as grassland and cultivation of other feed crops for cattle (e.g., fodder maize). Both the cattle sector and pig sector are key contributors to national NH₃ and CH₄ emissions. This livestock farming practice is no longer considered to be sustainable in the long-run due to several environmental (e.g., biodiversity, soil subsidence, GHG/NH₃ emissions) and social (e.g., animal/human health, housing shortage, land scarcity and flood risks) issues).

As a result, a transition strategy is needed for (dairy) cattle and pig farmers to make better, more sustainable end/or alternative use of their land, livestock, and biomass resources to reduce their negative impacts on the environment, while at the same time contributing to a range of social, economic, and environmental goals.

We propose three transition storylines or scenarios:

1. **Base case:** dairy cattle and pig farming remain at the same level of productivity and do not switch away from traditional (intensive) livestock farming practices. This will entail a continuation of existing livestock management practices with associated negative environmental and social impacts (e.g., emissions and future costs of soil subsidence and further environmental decline).
2. **New 1 - scaling nature-based solutions:** Planting additional trees outside forests (as agroforestry or as afforestation) and rewetting organic soils will be implemented. The subsequent land claim for scaling these nature-based solutions could be synergetic with the envisioned deliberate (planned/forced) reduction of the livestock sector. Such reduction of livestock herds will automatically reduce the related NH₃/CH₄ emissions. Both rewetting and tree planting will reduce the land available for feed (grass / maize) production or will lower the overall yields per hectare, requiring more extensive livestock management practices for cattle (or additional feed imports).
Business case: the business case for rewetting is uncertain as nationwide rewetting maybe implemented without clear plans for farm compensation. Also, the business case for agroforestry and afforestation is still marginal and risky, particularly in the start-up phase of around 5 years, and because new supply chains and market demand for new bio-based products are not well established. Also, the valorisation strategy (which incentives to pick and combine) is unclear. Rewetting practices are most suitable in the lower lying Northern and Western parts of The Netherlands with higher shares of organic/peat(y) soils, while tree planting (for agroforestry or afforestation) is more suitable in the Southern and Eastern parts of the country with higher shares of sandy and clay type soils.
3. **New 2 - scaling engineered solutions:** Anaerobic digestion of animal manure and post-treatment of digestate is used to reduce CH₄, NH₃ emissions from livestock, to produce renewable energy (biogas), liquid CO₂ and organic fertilizers to replace fossil equivalents. The scale of deployment (manure availability) will largely depend on the expected size of the dairy and pig herds. The current political debate considers planned reductions (even with possible forced buyouts) of the livestock sector ranging from 10-50%.
Business case: Currently, the business case for biogas-CCUS is highly uncertain within the political landscape which intends to proactively reduce the size of the livestock sector, and fragmented policy regime for valorisation. In this situation the expected decline in domestic food production may be dampened.

We anticipate that a most plausible scenario will entail a combination of the above three scenarios, where certain highly productive regions, where soil subsidence is less of an issue, and no Natura2000 zones are nearby will retain intensified cattle/pig farming (**Base case**). Other regions could retain a certain level a semi-intensive (dairy) cattle farming, which can be combined with anaerobic digestion of animal manure (**New 2 – scaling engineered solutions**). This would also free up land to build additional houses and infrastructure but may limit land available for expansion of natural areas (e.g., afforestation). Other areas may switch to a more extensive type of livestock farming system to limit environmental issues, expand land available for rewetting and tree planting (**New 1 – scaling nature based solutions**).

Within the Chapter 2 we discuss a diverse range trends and (policy) developments and targets that have a significant (in)direct impact on the scaling up of the presented LMT portfolio.

2. Policy developments

There are several ongoing policy processes that are relevant for the AFOLU sector, and for driving the implementation and scale up LMTs.

2.1 Climate and renewable energy policies / strategies

Given the inherent exposure to naturally occurring processes, such as oxidation, photosynthesis, and mineralisation, the agricultural sector is unlikely to be able to reduce their sectoral GHG emissions to zero by 2050. Some ‘hard-to-abate’ residual emissions (e.g., N₂O, CH₄) in agriculture are likely to remain (IPCC, 2023). As a result, this sector will have to rely on the use of a certain amount of carbon removals to be able to achieve net zero emissions by 2050. For most sectors specific GHG emission reduction targets are set. However, national level or sector level carbon removal targets are not (yet) determined. The extent to which carbon removal measures have to be implemented largely depends on the success and efforts made on reducing emissions.

In the interim period towards 2030, there are several energy, land use and climate policy initiatives relevant for the LMTs included in our portfolio (summarised in). These policy processes run in parallel. The main ones include:

- The regional energy strategies (RES)
- The peat meadow strategy (VWS)
- The forest strategy (BS)
- Blending obligation for green gases (BV)

Regional energy strategies

The regional energy strategies aim to decarbonise the electricity and heating system in the different regions. There are 30 so-called ‘RES-regions’ which formulate their own strategies and implementation plans for reducing energy related CO₂ emissions. The combined efforts (and pledges) of the RES-regions will have to add up to meeting the set national climate and energy targets for 2030. The primary focus of this nationwide participatory policy process up until now has been on ensuring that by 2030 an additional total of 35 TWh of renewable electricity is produced. This would require a land claim of about 5.000 ha (estimated range between 4.500 and 6.700 ha) to meet the target.

An evaluation of the RES 1.0-strategies by (PBL, 2021) shows that the regions have pledged to produce 55 TWh of renewable electricity. However, (PBL, 2021) estimates that based on several implementation challenges (e.g., grid capacity shortages, grid congestion, environmental permitting) that a realisation of 35 to 46 TWh (with middle value of 41 TWh) is realistic. This increase in capacity for renewable electricity production will mainly comprise onshore wind, and solar pv (rooftop and/or field). This expansion will have significant spatial implications due the additional land use claim. This will interact with the scale up of the different LMTs in our portfolio. With agroforestry/afforestation, the expansion of onshore wind/pv can compete for the same land. Also given the announced reduction

of the Dutch livestock sector, the economics of an LMT versus, for example, an onshore solar park will become a relevant factor in determining future land use.

Peat meadow strategy

In the Dutch Climate Agreement (Government D. , 2019) it is anticipated that measures for managing peat meadow areas (i.e., increasing the groundwater level) will deliver 1 MtCO₂-eq. of emission reductions by 2030. This is roughly a 20% reduction relative to the 2019 peat meadow emissions reported in the Dutch National GHG inventory report (RIVM, 2021). The measures to achieve this target are elaborated in the so-called Peat Plan phase 1 (Dutch: “Veenplan 1e fase”) for the period 2020-2022 (LNV, 2020). The Phase 1, is considered a start-up phase, where the plan mainly focusses on learning experimental pilots, improving GHG monitoring, and preparing for the scale up of rewetting peat(y) soils up to 2030 and beyond.

Of the about 436.000 ha of organic soils, 274.000 ha are so-called peat(y) soils. Most of this land (207.000 ha) is used for agriculture. The other 162.000 ha (of which 130.000 ha is used in agriculture) generally have thinner peat layers (5-40 cm of peat in the top 80cm of soil). The areas where rewetting will likely be conducted, are those areas where soil subsidence is most significant. Soil subsidence due to decades of peat soil drainage is a major driver for current and future damages to houses and infrastructure for the coming decades.

Forest strategy

The National Forest Strategy (LNV, 2020) builds upon the agreements made in the National Climate Agreement (Government D. , 2019). It also aims to implement biodiversity policy in the scope of the EU Habitat and Birds Directives. the National Forest Strategy focusses on 1) increasing the national forest area by 10% from 370,000 ha in 2020 to 407,000 ha in 2030 (of which 18.000 ha in existing nature areas, and 19.000 outside nature areas), 2) the revitalization of forests, and 3) increase the number of trees outside forests (TOF). Especially, the expansion of the forest area and TOF outside of the already existing nature areas will most likely come at the expense of the land used for agricultural purposes.

Blending obligation green gas

The blending obligation for green gases aims to scale up the production of green gases (biogas, hydrogen) up to at least 1,6 bln. m³ (current production around 220 mln. m³) by 2030 (EZK, 2022). This in turn is expected to result in a 2,9 Mton CO₂ emission reduction (1,8 – 4,9 Mton CO₂/y range estimate) by 2030. These estimated CO₂ savings exclude any potential emission reductions or carbon removal associated with the production and utilization of organic fertilizers (derived from AD digestate), as well as any CO₂ capture and reuse/storage at the biogas plants. As such the net CO₂-savings from AD of animal manure, combined with CCS/U and production of organic fertilizers could be significantly higher.

In a report (CE-Delft, 2022) commissioned by the Ministry of Economic Affairs exploring the impact of a blending obligation green gas, assumes a high reliance on AD of animal manure for meeting the set

target. It is estimated that around 57% of the biogas will have to originate from animal manure (with 43% originating from other feedstocks). The report also assumes that the green gas production target (for animal manure derived biogas) can be achieved, assuming an assumed 20% (min) or 30% (max) reduction in the livestock population. This target will not likely be achieved by reducing the livestock population >30%. The discussion about the size of the Dutch livestock sector is very relevant, since within the current public/political debate regarding NO_x and NH₃ emissions there are several political parties advocating reducing the livestock sector by about 50%.

Table 2-1: Overview of policy programs relevant for LMT portfolio

Policy	Blending obligation green gases	Regional Energy Strategies	Peat meadow strategy	Forest strategy
Target	1,6 bcm of green gas production in 2030, to be mainly supplied in to built environment	35 TWh of additional renewable electricity production by 2030 (pledge by RES-regions is 55 TWh)	-1 Mt CO ₂ emissions from peat soils in 2030 (is about 20% of national reported peat soil emissions in 2019)	A 10% increase in forest area, of which 18,000 ha to be realized in the NNN areas, 19,000 ha outside NNN network.
Expected climate target impact	-2,9 Mton CO ₂ emissions by 2030	A near zero-emission electricity sector by 2030	-1 Mton CO ₂ emissions from peat soils by 2030	0,4 Mton CO ₂ removed (ambition to go to 0,8 Mton CO ₂ removed), of which about 0,1 Mton CO ₂ for agroforestry
Challenge	To go from 220 mln. m ³ renewable gases (in 2021) to 2.000 mln. m ³ in 2030	To go from approximately 39 TWh net renewable electricity production in 2021 (+35 TWh) to 74 TWh in 2030	To reduce LULUCF peat soil emissions from 5,5 Mton CO ₂ in 2019 to 4,5 Mton CO ₂ in 2030.	To go from about 370.000 ha of forest to 407.000 ha of forests.
	About 900% increase in 9 years time.	About 200% increase in 9 years time.	About 20% decrease in 10 years time.	About 10% increase in 9 years time.
Link to / relevance for AFOLU sector	Increase in domestic green gas production potential is highly reliant (57%) on AD of animal manure digestion (already discounted for a 20% reduction of the livestock sector).	Land claim for onshore wind and solar parks (4500-6700 ha), likely taken from agriculture. Agricultural sector also is a key source for rooftop pv (on stables), and investor in renewable electricity production.	Rewetting of peat soils will mostly affect current of peat meadows used for cattle farming and nature areas	Additional land claim will most likely come at the expense of agricultural (grass/feed) land.
	Link 1 Link 2	Link 1 Link 2 Link 3	Link 1 Link 2 Link 3	Link 1 Link 2 Link 3

2.2 Other relevant policies / strategies / incentives

Aside from the energy and climate policies, there are a wide range of other policy processes running in parallel. The key ones affecting the implementation of the LMTs in our portfolio will be briefly discussed below.

- National Program Rural Area
- Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) reform
- Nitrate Directive – derogation
- Voluntary carbon market
- Meadow bird action plan
- National housing agenda
- Spatial planning – soil and water

National Program rural area

The National Program Rural Area (Rijksoverheid, 2022) acts as an umbrella policy program to integrate the different policy targets regarding nature, nitrogen (NH₃) emissions², agriculture, water, soil, and climate. Within this program there is a transition fund of around €24,3 bln. available up to 2035 to ensure that The Netherlands will become compliant with the national targets for nitrogen emissions, climate, and water. The targets set for nitrogen (N-related) emission reduction are the primary policy driver. For the rural area ambitious targets have been set to substantially reduce NH₃ emissions with 39 kton NH₃ by 2030. This is on top of an already projected base scenario reduction (based upon existing policies) of 10 kton of NH₃ emissions relative to the chosen reference year 2018.

In 2018, agriculture was by far the largest emitter of NH₃ emissions with 109 kton NH₃ emissions (or 87% of the national NH₃ emissions). Assuming a proportionate sectoral share for reducing NH₃ emissions, the agricultural sector at minimum would have to reduce 34 kton of NH₃ emissions (or about 31% of agricultural NH₃ emissions). The main reason for reducing NH₃ emissions is to reduce the nitrogen deposition in the environment, particularly in and around the more vulnerable, and protected habitats. The program is set up, so that each subregion can develop its own regional implementation strategy.

Common agricultural policy (CAP) reform

Eco-schemes are part of the new CAP 2023-27 ([link](#)). Eco-schemes provide an incentive (premium) for the agricultural sector when implementing certain eligible eco-activities. For 2023, eligible eco-activities in The Netherlands ([link](#)) include e.g., cover cropping, paludiculture, landscape elements, etc, thereby providing a possible financial incentive for two of our LMTs, agroforestry and peatland rewetting.

Nitrate directive – derogation

² NOx emissions will be addressed through national level generic policy frameworks.

Under the EU's nitrate directive, The Netherlands is set to gradually phase out its derogation to the application of N from animal origin on soils. This derogation allowed the usage of higher levels of N from animal origin on soils. As per 2026 Dutch farmers can only submit a maximum of 170 N-manure to soils ([link](#)). The current debate is now, on whether this phase-out will result in a number of undesirable trade-offs ([link](#)), including:

- Increased manure surplus could lead to increased production costs for livestock farmers,
- Potential increased conversion of grasslands into cropland to ensure protein supplies for livestock, potentially leading to higher levels of N-leaching and worsening conditions for meadow birds.
- Potentially lower N-surplus (NH₃ emissions) at farm level, which may result in some gains for biodiversity,
- Increased use of chemical fertilizers (and thus natural gas) to meet the needs of the highly productive cropping/farming systems in the country.

A relevant ongoing debate within The Netherlands and Europe relates to the possible production and application of recovered nitrogen from manure (RENURE). RENURE ([link](#)) could play a significant role in reducing the agricultural sectors' dependence of chemical fertilizers and promote more circular agricultural system ([link](#)). For the feasibility and scaling of our BECCS/U LMT (biogas-production systems) acceptance of RENURE fertilizers could provide an additional economic incentive. However, in light of the current phase out of the derogation it remains to be seen if RENURE will be seen and perceived as i) a circular and more sustainable way to replace chemical fertilizers and reduce natural gas use, ii) or a 'backdoor' to reinstate the lost derogation for applying animal manure on Dutch soils. Advanced manure treatment systems, that produce biogas, captured CO₂, as well as organic fertilizers can outperform chemical fertilizers in terms of overall climate impacts and sustainability. Moreover, such systems are also more likely to outperform the management usage and application of untreated liquid animal manure. A possible compromise to allow for extended derogation could be to ban, phase out or limit the usage of untreated liquid animal manure on soils and promote (or mandate) more advanced manure management and treatment systems, combined with biogas production. Continued uncertainty regarding derogation and RENURE will most likely negatively affect the feasibility of rolling out biogas production systems in The Netherlands.

Voluntary carbon market

Since 2019, a voluntary domestic carbon market (Stichting Nationale Koolstofmarkt; [SNK](#)) is operational within The Netherlands. SNK provides an incentive for a range of accepted project types relevant for AFOLU sectors ([link](#)). Approved methodologies exist for peatland rewetting, CH₄ reduction by applying feed additives, conversion of liquid fraction of digestate into replacement of chemical N-fertilizers, planting of trees outside forests, climate smart forest management, ash forest revitalisation, permanent grasslands on mineral soils, as well as hemp cultivation for long duration sequestration in materials. It has to be noted that SNK only provides a potential additional (or complementary) incentive for all four LMTs in our portfolio (*policy additionality*). This means that the voluntary carbon

market should be considered as a last resort instrument in case existing and/or planned policies and incentives fail to deliver.

Meadow bird action plan

To preserve and support biodiversity in the country, and in particular meadow birds like the black-tailed godwit), there is a nationwide ([link](#)) meadow bird strategy. One of the measures promoted is to rewet bird breeding grounds and meadows during breeding season to provide a more suitable habitat for these birds. The strategy has a budget reservation of about EUR 70 mln. budget, which also aims to provide a premium for participating farmers to compensate for any economic damages / losses related to rewetting and/or other bird-friendly practices. However, due to an ongoing disagreement between the national government and provincial governments this fund remains mostly unused to date ([link](#)). As a result of this rewetting practices are slowing down and there is uncertainty added to novel more nature-inclusive and sustainable farming business models.

National housing & building agenda, and the circular building strategy

The Dutch national housing and building agenda ([link](#)) illustrates that by 2030 an estimated 900.000 new houses will have to be built to meet housing demand. From these 900.000 about 13% will replace outdated (to be demolished) houses, while 87% entails a net expansion of the housing stock. This net expansion will put an additional claim on the use of land, which in most cases will likely be agricultural land close to existing urban or rural settlements. Finding suitable locations for building new houses will be a challenge in a densely populated country, with already intensive forms of land use. Also making sure that new houses are built in locations that are sufficiently climate resilient (e.g., flooding areas, soil subsidence areas near coastal and river zones) requires a planned approach ([link](#)).

While the foreseen housing expansion may put additional claims on land, the net effect on land use competition with existing agricultural practices is likely to remain relatively modest. Alternatively, the Netherlands government has significant ambitions to promote the use of bio-based materials and circular building designs. The Policy agenda ‘standardizing and stimulating circular construction’ ([link](#)) aims for example to:

- Enhance and widen the scope for the minimum environmental performance of (new) buildings,
- Introducing minimum performance standards for CO₂-emissions for material usage in buildings,
- Promote and incentivise the application of bio-based materials in buildings,

These policy ambitions could provide an alternative incentive for forest owners/managers and farmers to start cultivating or supplying biomass for the production and use of building materials. Such complementary business models or market opportunities could be synergetic with afforestation and agroforestry via construction or engineered wood products, rewetting of organic soils (e.g., cattail, miscanthus, hemp, straw based) insulation or plate materials ([link](#)), as well as anaerobic digestion and post-treatment or animal manure (manure digestate based building blocks - [link](#)).

Spatial planning – soil and water

A recent (November 2022) letter from Dutch the Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management ([link](#)) on the role of water and soil/land in spatial planning is aiming to structurally increase ground water levels in areas with significant acreages of peat(y) / organic soils. Increasing or managing ground water levels is delegated to the regional water authorities throughout the country. As a result this (planned) policy could directly affect the viability ongoing (mainly cattle) livestock farming (higher costs of production, lower yields), peatland management / rewetting initiatives (e.g., meadow bird strategy, or voluntary carbon market projects). Without proper compensation or development perspective for potentially affected farming communities, uncertainty regarding the public acceptance of rewetting practices remains.

2.3 Greenhouse gas emissions, and emission reduction targets

The Dutch Climate Agreement (Government, 2019) states that the Dutch economy will have reduced its national GHG emissions by 49% in 2030, and at least 90% (95%) in 2050 relative to 1990 emissions. The known residual GHG emissions for 2030 and 2050, as well as the emission reduction efforts relative to 2020 GHG emissions per sector are indicated in Table 2-2 below.

Table 2-2: Residual emissions, 2020 emissions and reduction efforts per sector for 2030, 2050 (in Mton CO₂-eq.)

Sector	Residual emissions		Emissions	Reduction effort	
	2030	2050	2020	2030	2050
Electricity	12,4	?	32,6	20,2	?
Industry	35,7	?	53,4	17,7	?
Built environment	15,3	?	21,8	6,5	?
Transport	25	?	30,6	5,6	?
Agriculture and land use	28	0	27,1	-0,9	27,1
Total	116,4	11-23	165,5		

Sources:

- <https://www.emissieregistratie.nl/data/overzichtstabellen-lucht/broeikasgassen>
- <https://www.klimaatakkoord.nl/klimaatakkoord/vraag-en-antwoord/wat-is-het-doel-van-het-klimaatakkoord>
- <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/onderwerpen/klimaatverandering/klimaatakkoord/maatregelen-klimaatakkoord-per-sector>

For agriculture and land use sectors we can see that the 2020 recorded GHG emissions (27,1 Mton CO₂-eq.) are already slightly below to the projected residual 2030 emissions (28 Mton CO₂-eq). This would imply that up to 2030 no further GHG emission reduction efforts would be needed. However, only for this sector a 2050 target appears to be set. By 2050 climate neutrality will have to be reached, indicating that this sector will have to get to a net zero emissions level.³ This suggest that within the 2020-2050 period the agriculture and land use sectors would have to reduce and/or remove an equivalent of 27,1 Mton CO₂-eq. relative to 2020 GHG emission levels. Key options within this sector to reduce emissions or remove CO₂ from the atmosphere from our LMT portfolio include a broad range of technological measures and nature-based solutions (see Table 2-3).

Table 2-3: Potential reduction and removal impacts from Dutch LMT portfolio

Reduction	Removal
Reduction of methane emissions from livestock (e.g. reduction of livestock, manure management)	Afforestation
Peatland rewetting	Agroforestry (planting trees outside forest)
Land management (No tillage, permanent grasslands)	Paludiculture (wet agriculture for building materials)
Efficient or reduced use of nitrogen fertilizers	Harvested wood products

³ “Om te zorgen dat de landbouw en het landgebruik in 2050 klimaatneutraal zijn, moet er veel gebeuren. Een deel van de uitstoot van broeikasgas is namelijk niet te vermijden. Zo stoten koeien methaan uit. En veengebieden veroorzaken CO₂-uitstoot als de grondwaterstand laag is. Daar staat tegenover dat planten CO₂ opslaan. Bomen en gras doen dat bijvoorbeeld heel goed. Dit is gunstig om de CO₂-uitstoot te verminderen.”

Avoided deforestation, reforestation	CO2 capture, and storage/re-use
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To know which emission reduction or removal measures to implement in this sector to meet its 2030/50 climate targets will be good to know the origins of the agricultural and land use sector emissions.

2.4 Agricultural and land use sector (AFOLU) emissions

In 2020 the GHG emissions in these sectors represent 16,4% of total national CO₂-eq. emissions (see Figure 2-1). This mainly comprises the non-CO₂ GHGs, CH₄ and N₂O representing respectively 76,3% and 73,9% of total national CH₄ and N₂O emissions. CO₂-emissions from these sectors comprise only about 5,4% of total national CO₂ emissions.

Figure 2-1: GHG emissions in AFOLU sector in NL (1990-2020) in MtCO₂-eq.

If we take a closer look at the specific GHG emission and removal data from both the agriculture and land use, land use change (LULUCF) sectors we can see that the LULUCF sector not only includes emission sources, but also a few carbon sinks (removals). Within the National Inventory GHG reporting The Netherlands reports agriculture and land use, land use change and forestry (LULUCF) sector emissions and removals. In (RIVM, 2021) Chapters 5 (Agriculture) and 6 (LULUCF), more disaggregated GHG emission data is published.

Agriculture sector emissions

GHG emissions in agriculture mainly comprise CH₄ and N₂O emissions (see Table 2-4). The CH₄ emissions almost exclusively originating from the livestock subsector (enteric fermentation and manure management), while the N₂O emissions are mainly stemming from the application of inorganic and organic nitrogen (N-)fertilizers.

Table 2-4: GHG emissions in agriculture in The Netherlands

Year	Gas	1990	2018	2019
Total	All	24,6	18	17,7
	CO ₂	0,2	0,1	0,1
	CH ₄	14,7	12,1	12
	N ₂ O	9,7	5,8	5,6
Enteric fermentation	CH₄	9,2	8,3	8,1
Manure management	All	6,3	4,6	4,6
	CH ₄	5,4	3,8	3,8
	N ₂ O	0,9	0,8	0,8
Agriculture soils	N₂O	8,7	5	4,8
Liming	CO₂	0,2	0,03	0,03
Urea application	N₂O	0	0,1	0,05

Source: (RIVM, 2021)

For both CH₄ and N₂O emissions sources the total aggregate GHG emissions are largely dependent on the total size of the livestock sector. More/less animals (mainly cattle and pig) imply higher/lower enteric emissions (cattle) and manure management emissions (cattle and pig manure). At the same time more/less animals also increases/decreases the availability of organic fertilizers (animal manure), which to a certain extent could decrease/increase the application of inorganic N-fertilizers on agricultural soils.

LULUCF sector emissions

GHG emissions in the LULUCF sector mainly comprise CO₂ emissions stemming from the different land uses and land use changes. The LULUCF sector is one of the few sectors that includes both emission sources and carbon sinks (see Table 2-5).

Table 2-5: GHG emissions in LULUCF in The Netherlands

Year	Gas	1990	2018	2019
Total	All	6,1	4,5	4,4
	CO ₂	6	4,6	4,4
	CH ₄	0	0	0
	N ₂ O	0,1	0,1	0,1
Forest land (total)	CO₂	-2	-1,9	-1,9
Forest land remaining forest land	CO ₂	-1,5	-1,4	-1,4
Land converted to forest land	CO ₂	-0,5	-0,5	-0,5
Cropland (total)	CO₂	2,6	1,6	1,6
Cropland remaining cropland	CO ₂	1,2	0,5	0,4
Land converted to cropland	CO ₂	1,4	1,1	1,2
Grassland (total)	CO₂	4,7	3,1	2,9
Grassland remaining grassland	CO ₂	5	3,3	3,2
Land converted to grassland	CO ₂	-0,3	-0,2	-0,3
Wetlands (total)	CO₂	0,1	0	0
Wetlands remaining wetlands	CO ₂	0	0	0

Land converted to wetlands	CO ₂	0,1	0	0
Settlements (total)	CO₂	0,8	1,5	1,5
Settlements remaining settlements	CO ₂	0,4	0,4	0,4
Land converted to settlements	CO ₂	0,4	1,1	1,1
Other land (total)	CO₂	0	0,2	0,2
Other land remaining other land	CO ₂	0	0	0
Land converted to other land	CO ₂	0	0,2	0,2
Harvested wood products (total)	CO₂	-0,2	0,1	0,1

Source: (RIVM, 2021)

The primary CO₂ emission source for the LULUCF sector in The Netherlands is drainage of peat/peaty soils. In 2019 this contributed to 5,5 Mton CO₂-eq. emissions for mainly the grassland, cropland, and settlement land use subcategories. A large portion of the Dutch open land is being used to cultivate grass and fodder (maize) for the livestock sector. To sustain the agricultural use of land for agricultural purposes, and particularly the peat/peaty soils the groundwater levels are being controlled. Under the current water management regime this mainly results in active drainage of large peat(y) areas of land in the country resulting in oxidation of soil organic carbon. Within a changing climate proper management of ground- and surface water levels is increasingly challenging given the less predictable and more erratic/extreme precipitation patterns.

The main carbon sink in The Netherlands is forest land. In addition, grasslands also comprise a potential yet limited carbon sink. Within the grassland category, also the carbon removal from trees outside forest concepts (e.g., agroforestry, landscape elements with trees) are accounted. The relevance of sinks (removals) will be relevant for both the agriculture and land use sectors combined in their effort to reach the climate neutrality (or net zero) target by 2050. In this respect the accounting and allocation of carbon removals related to all kinds of raw (biogenic) materials for the bio-based economy, will become relevant. Within the current GHG accounting there is only a key focus on harvested wood products (HWP), but the agriculture and land use sectors could also provide raw materials for a broad range of bio-based products and materials (e.g., bio-plastics, biochemicals, bio-based insulation materials, hemp- or grass-based materials, organic fertilizers) with subsequent short- and long-lived applications. For 2019 HWP comprise a net emission source for the LULUCF sector of 0,1 Mton CO₂-eq. However, during the 1990-2019 period this fluctuated between -0,158 (removal) and 0,165 (emission) Mton CO₂-eq. This implies that downstream uses of biomass in other economic sectors originating from agriculture and land use sectors, any emissions, or removals (claims) will be accounted within these two sectors.

3. LMT Portfolio

The scope of the Dutch LMT portfolio focuses on the shortlisted LMTs that have been narrowed down by literature review and a few interviews with relevant experts. These four shortlisted LMTs are considered for further analysis including their potential to store carbon and reduce GHG emissions (with the help of model simulations). Before such an assessment can be done a narrative or storyline for each of the selected LMTs needs to be developed. The following sections provide the qualitative narratives of the four LMTs for the Netherlands.

- Peatland management (see section 3.1)
- Forestry (see section 3.2)
- Agroforestry (see section 3.3)
- CCS applied to AD based on animal manure & soil carbon enhancement with AD based digestate (see section 3.4)

3.1 Peatland management

3.1.1 Introduction

Peatlands in the Netherlands have already been faced with soil subsidence for a long time, mainly due to a systematic draining of the land to make it suitable for agricultural use. During the last 100 years, the process of soil subsidence has been increased due to improved pumping techniques that have been applied to meet the increasing requirements of agriculture. The draining of the peatland results in the peat drying out and oxidising – or ‘burning’ – under the influence of oxygen, which causes subsidence. Due to this subsidence, the groundwater level becomes closer to the ground level, which may hamper agricultural management. Hence the water authorities lower the water level even further so that agriculture can continue. This process ends up in a negative spiral. Apart from costs for adapting drainage to continue using the land for its current purposes, other problems arise as well, such as damage from subsidence of infrastructure and buildings; CO₂ emissions from peat oxidation, and the drying out of nature conservation areas (RLI, 2020). These problems are also cumulative and build up over time. This cumulative process can be stopped by reversing the adaption of the groundwater level from lowering into increasing it. However, there are some limitations of increasing the groundwater level as N₂O and CH₄ emissions arise when groundwater levels become too close to the ground level. Evidence from Germany and the UK shows that with groundwater levels over 20 cm below the ground level there are hardly any N₂O and CH₄ emissions (RLI, 2020).

3.1.2 Policy context

Climate Agreement and Peat Plan

Estimates of current annual carbon emissions of peatlands in the Netherlands vary from 4 to 7 MtCO₂-eq. (RLI, 2020). As total carbon emissions in the Netherlands have to be reduced to 11 MtCO₂-eq. by 2050, it goes without saying that peatlands have to contribute to the reduction effort. In the Dutch

Climate Agreement (Government D. , 2019) it is anticipated that measures for managing peat meadow areas (i.e. increasing the groundwater level) will deliver 1 MtCO₂-eq. of emission reductions by 2030. These measures are elaborated in the so-called Peat Plan phase 1 (Dutch: “Veenplan 1e fase”) for the period 2020-2022 (LNV, 2020). During this phase, the focus is on gaining more insight into the effectiveness of emission reduction measures and how these can be rolled out by setting up pilots, a National Research Programme on Emissions in Peat Meadow Areas (NOBV) and communities of practices. As emission reduction in peatlands cannot be considered in isolation from other activities, regional actors are asked to develop an integrated territorial peat meadow area strategy for their region by the end of 2020. In those strategies, regions have to indicate how they will achieve emission reductions while simultaneously taking account of the economic perspectives of farmers, nitrogen disposition, water management and biodiversity. For stimulating piloting with territorial measures aimed at increasing the groundwater level, a budget of €100 mln is available for peat meadow areas in five provinces. Within the scope of the research programme NOBV, a national network for measuring emission reductions of measures will be developed, that can be used for monitoring. It is expected that by 2022 the second phase of the Peat Plan can be started, aimed at scaling up and rolling out effective measures.

Numerous initiatives on peat soil subsidence

Apart from these activities aimed at implementing the emission reduction target for the peat meadow areas of the Climate Agreement, during the last decade, numerous initiatives have been set up for exploring solutions for problems arising from peat soil subsidence. These refer amongst others to five peat areas financed by the Intergovernmental Programme (IBP) on a Viable Countryside, a project on climate-smart agriculture on peat soils in Utrecht, so-called Region Deals for nature including agriculture and peat meadow areas in the Green Heart, farmers’ collectives on nature and landscape management, and a Green Deal on value for peat (Dutch: “VvV”) (Verhagen, Westerhof, & de Weerd, 2020). The experiences of actors participating in these initiatives may act as a useful knowledge source for LANDMARC in scaling up climate mitigation technologies and practices. However, the (RLI, 2020) observes a lack of upscaling of initiatives as pilots tend to stay in an experimenting phase and local actors are repeatedly trying to invent the wheel without pushing the process any further.

Combining public and private funds

Although there are public funds specifically labelled for emission reduction measures available from the Climate Agreement and the national government, additional funds are needed. These have to be derived from provinces, other policy fields and private actors. By doing so, it is hoped that public-private partnerships will manage to achieve various objectives by combining a mix of public and private funds. Other policy fields are amongst others the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), fiscal policy, economic policy, environmental policy, nature policy and regional policy.

3.1.3 Current land use and potential land-use competition

In the Netherlands, organic soils amount to 436,000 ha, which is about 10% of the total area (Table 3-1). Depending on the depth of the peat layer, these soils are divided into peat soils (274,000 ha) and peaty soils (Dutch: “moerige gronden”) (162,000 ha) (LNV, 2020). Over three-quarters of these organic soils are used by agriculture (resp. 76% of the peat soils and 80% of the peaty soils), mainly as grassland (279,000 ha) and to a lesser extent as cropland (67,000 ha). Grassland on organic soils is usually referred to as peat meadow area. Its typical Dutch landscape value is in general highly appreciated, nationally as well as internationally. The area of organic soils tends to decline because of oxidation, particularly in drained agricultural areas. In the years 1990-2017, this decrease amounted to over 60,000 ha.

Table 3-1: Land use on organic and mineral soils in the Netherlands, 1990-2017

Land use		1990	2004	2009	2013	2017
Forest land	Organic soils area (ha)	20,482	21,990	21,885	21,453	20,396
	mineral soils area (ha)	341,619	348,052	351,595	354,291	345,183
	% organic soils	6	6	6	6	6
Cropland	Organic soils area (ha)	108,979	85,117	80,816	75,967	66,842
	mineral soils area (ha)	910,373	854,500	844,046	868,373	803,468
	% organic soils	11	9	9	8	8
Grassland (non-TOF)⁴	Organic soils area (ha)	322,053	292,709	282,252	276,031	278,616
	mineral soils area (ha)	1,185,62	111,535	1,109,23	1,069,67	1,128,42
	% organic soils	9	6	6	8	5
TOF	Organic soils area (ha)	2,216	2,237	2,221	2,132	2,120
	mineral soils area (ha)	18,590	19,970	19,872	19,443	19,120
	% organic soils	11	10	10	10	10
Other land uses	Organic soils area (ha)	45,142	61,999	64,440	66,082	68,718
	mineral soils area (ha)	1,196,41	1,349,57	1,375,13	1,398,05	1,418,61
	% organic soils	6	1	6	0	3
Total	Organic soils area (ha)	498,873	464,051	451,615	441,666	436,691
	mineral soils area (ha)	3,652,62	3,687,44	3,699,88	3,709,83	3,714,80
	% organic soils	7	9	5	4	9
	% organic soils	12	11	11	11	11

Source: <https://edepot.wur.nl/314315>.

⁴ Trees outside forest (TOF)

As the Climate Agreement and the Peat Plan focus on peat meadow areas, for the time being, we only consider organic soils used for grassland in the narrative. At a later stage, we can eventually extend the narrative to peaty soils. In the Netherlands, three clusters of peat meadow areas can be considered (RLI, 2020):

1. The western peat meadow areas in the provinces of South Holland and Utrecht;
2. The peat meadow areas in the province of North Holland;
3. The peat meadow areas in the provinces of Friesland and Overijssel.

These clusters greatly differ from each other due to, amongst others, the thickness of the peat layer, the extraction history, the drainage level, and the plot pattern. There are also differences when it comes to the relationship with other land uses in the area, such as housing, infrastructure, energy production, nature, and recreation.

Current land use competed by societal demands

Land use competition issues in the Dutch agricultural sector usually originates from land claims by other functions, in particular for settlement and infrastructure use, land use to accommodate the energy transition and land for nature and recreation. In the case of the peat meadow areas, however, current agricultural land use is competed by societal demands for increasing the groundwater level to reduce soil subsidence. Higher groundwater levels imply that current agricultural management practices have to be adapted to alternatives like less intensive management, nature including agriculture and wet cultivation.

Within LANDMARC the focus is on climate change mitigation technologies and practices. As such, rewetting peat meadows could be referred to as a practice to reduce GHG emissions. However, demands for increasing groundwater levels in the peat meadow areas in the Netherlands are not only related to achieving climate goals but to several other societal concerns as well (RLI, 2020):

- Due to soil subsidence, buildings and infrastructure subside as well and infrastructure cables in the soil can be blotted,
- Lower soils need water management adaptations like bigger pumps and higher quays and flood defences,
- The water quality deteriorates due to leakages from nitrates, sulphates, and phosphates from peat oxidation and salination from seepage water, which in turn has consequences for biodiversity,
- Adjacent nature areas are in danger of drying out as the water from these higher-lying areas drains to the lower-lying peat meadow areas.

Addressing these issues imply high societal costs, which can be prevented by stopping soil subsidence. Within this context, it can be argued that a transition to higher groundwater levels in peat meadow areas is rather a societally driven urgency than a voluntary choice by farmers.

3.1.4 Climate risks & sensitivities

Risks

For avoiding any further oxidation of peat and peaty soils, and thereby reducing GHG emissions, hydrological interventions, i.e., reverse drainage and re-wetting the area, are needed. A key condition for such water-based strategies is the continued and structural availability of sufficient water. However, climate-related disturbances, like increasing levels of annual rainfall and prolonged periods of (extreme) drought endanger sound water management due to fluctuations in water availability. Although in the last decade progress has been made to deal with extreme rainfall through temporary ‘flooding areas’ which allow for an overflow of excess water, prolonged drought periods seem more difficult to address. Droughts might result in drops in groundwater levels, which hamper proper drainage of the soil and thereby contributing to continued oxidation.

Sensitivities

Climate sensitivities of soil subsidence are related to the sea-level rise, which increases the danger of flooding the steady subsiding peat meadow areas. Technical solutions to protect the land from flooding cannot be realized without drastic measures and high costs. Hence this sensitivity can be considered as a plea for rewetting peat areas.

3.1.5 Economic implications

The consequences of increasing the groundwater level for agricultural management practices depend on the groundwater level before the increase and that after the increase (Daatselaar & Prins, 2020). Estimations of the costs of increasing the groundwater level in the peat meadow areas in the Green Heart show that an increase in the groundwater level from 100 cm below ground level to 80 cm below this level has hardly any effects on current practices. However, further increases closer to the ground level result in lower feed production and require adaptations in agricultural management like a lower livestock density per ha, feed purchases, less outdoor grazing, and lighter machines due to less load-bearing capacity of the soil. These adaptations result in higher costs per ha (Table 3-2). In the peat meadow areas outside the Green Heart costs will differ due to different plot sizes and permeability of the peat.

Table 3-2: Effect on CO₂ emissions and estimated additional costs with increasing groundwater levels in peat meadow areas in the Green Heart under various baseline situations.

	100→ 80 cm	80→ 60 cm	60→ 40 cm	40→ 20 cm	30→ 10 cm	Average
CO ₂ reduction (ton per ha)	8	8	8	8.1	8.2	8.1
Costs for farmer (euro per ha)	0	87	312	470	489	332
Costs per ton CO ₂ reduction (euro)	0	11	39	58	60	41

Source: (Daatselaar & Prins, 2020)

As current business models in peat meadow areas do not comply with increasing groundwater levels, farmers have to look for alternative business models, like:

- Less intensive dairy production,
- Wet cultivation (like cattail (*Typha*), reed (*Phragmites*), sphagnum moss (*Sphagnum*), wild rice (*Zizania*) duckweed fern (*Azolla*) (Smolders, et al., 2019);
- Energy/biomass production,
- Other activities on the farm, like milk processing, care and recreation,
- Nature including agriculture aimed at providing ecosystem services (landscape and nature management, CO₂ reduction, less soil subsidence etc.).

In particular, a business model derived from ecosystem services could be promising if the long term and sufficient payments for these services could be guaranteed. Such payments could originate from subsidies and private payments by, for example, firms buying certificates of CO₂ emission reductions. From Table 3-2 it can be derived that in the calculations for farmers in the Green Heart the price of a certificate for one ton CO₂ reduction has to amount to at least 41 euro to compensate for farmers' costs.

- Region Alblasserwaard-vijfheerenlanden: 15,000 ha out of which 4,000 ha are economic to apply pressure drainage (rewetting). This results in less soils subsidence and less CO₂ emissions (both reduced by 50-75%) (Paulin et al., 2022)
- "Greatest uncertainties in the calculations are the price for CO₂ that will be calculated in the future and the costs of installing and managing the pressure drainage system." (Paulin et al., 2022)
- Pressure drainage: "The average net present value per hectare for these locations is approximately €7,800/ha over a 30-year period. The analysis shows that the costs for the construction of pressure drainage mainly end up with the farmers (investment & maintenance costs of pressure drainage and loss of yield), the benefits of CO₂ reduction are shared by society." (Paulin et al., 2022)

3.1.6 *Co-benefits and trade-offs*

The main issue with stopping soil subsidence in peat meadow areas is the question of who has to pay for it: society or farmers? In the current situation of continuing soil subsidence, farmers benefit and society suffers. When groundwater levels are increased to stop soil subsidence, the opposite applies: farmers suffer and society benefits. Given the severe impacts of soils subsidence on costs for subsidence of buildings and infrastructure, costs for water management and climate change, the question is not whether groundwater levels in the peat meadow areas will be increased, but when and at which pace. Avoided societal costs can be considered as a financial benefit of increasing the groundwater level. Whether farming will continue in peat meadow areas with increased groundwater levels depends on the extent farmers manage to set up viable business models. Public/private payments for ecosystem services likely play the main role in such models.

Changes in agricultural production

On the whole, increasing groundwater levels imply less feed production per ha in peat meadow areas. This can result in less dairy production if the feed is not purchased from elsewhere. If farmers decide to change to less intensive dairy production or other types of production, like wet crops, a drop in dairy production occurs as well. This implies that the total Dutch supply of dairy products may decrease and that of wet crops increase. The extent of these shifts are yet unclear but could be explored in the LANDMARC model simulations.

Landscape changes

In a situation of increased groundwater levels in the peat meadow areas, farmers have broadly three options: to adapt their management practices, to stop their farming activities or to move their business to another area. Changing agricultural practices will result in changes in the landscape of peat meadow areas: it turns into a mix of wet grasslands and areas with wet cultivation, nature and water.

Biodiversity

Biodiversity may benefit from less intensively farming practices. Nowadays the peat meadow areas are an important habitat for meadow birds, that feed on wet soils. However, if areas become swampy due to groundwater levels close to the ground level, these areas are no longer suitable for meadow birds (RLI, 2020). Biodiversity in adjacent nature areas also benefits from increased groundwater levels in peat meadow areas as it lessens dehydration due to drainage of water

- Pressure drainage: “makes the area more attractive for farmland birds such as black-tailed godwits, lapwings and oystercatchers. Pressure drainage also offers other advantages, such as lower costs for water purification and water management. One disadvantage of the higher groundwater level is that less grass can be produced.”(Paulin et al., 2022)

Nitrogen emissions

The achievement of the national nitrogen aim of reducing nitrogen depositions near nature areas can both positively or negatively be affected by increased groundwater levels in peat meadow areas. If farmers adapt their agricultural management practices by decreasing the number of livestock per ha, this results in fewer nitrogen emissions from ammonia. However, if farmers adapt by less outdoor grazing and feed purchases, nitrogen emissions increase as these are higher in stables than outdoor (Hoving et al., 2015).

Water quality

Peat oxidation is a substantial source of nutrients and dredging production that pollutes surface water (Smolders, et al., 2019). Moreover, the eruption of low-lying peat soils and seepage results in salination. These problems decrease at rising groundwater levels with positive effects on the water quality.

3.1.7 Risks associated with scaling up

The amount of land where groundwater levels can be increased to prevent soil subsidence is limited to the peat meadow areas. These areas equal about 15% of total Dutch agricultural land. The main risk refers to whether farmers manage to implement viable business models. The development of such models needs knowledge, time, and financial support. If farmers do not manage this transition, the main risk would be a drop in agricultural production and an increase in land abandonment.

3.2 Forestry

3.2.1 Introduction

Forests in the Netherlands cover about 340,000 ha, which is just over 8% of the total area (Table 3-3). About 55% of the forest (larger than 5 hectares) is owned by public organizations; the remaining is private forest property. This concerns both private individuals such as estate owners and organizations such as 'Nature Monuments' (Dutch: "Natuurmonumenten") (Rijksoverheid, 2014). A recent survey among forest owners revealed that almost 80% of them indicated that their forests were faced with increasingly natural and climate-related disturbances over the last decade (Sikkema, 2020). These disturbances were related to drought, storm damage, extreme temperatures and intense rainfall. On top of that, they experience increased insect damage (bark beetles, oak processionary caterpillar) and fungal diseases (ash dieback). Other disruptions refer to soil damage caused by wild pressure and acid nitrogen deposition. In particular, species like Norway spruce, native oak, ash, larch, Scots pine, beech and Douglas are affected by these disturbances.

3.2.2 Policy context

The National Forest Strategy (LNV, 2020) builds upon the agreements made in the National Climate Agreement (Government D. , 2019) and also aims to implement biodiversity policy in the scope of the EU Habitat and Birds Directives. As such, the emphasis is on the sequestration of CO₂ and reinforcing biodiversity. Broadly, the National Forest Strategy focusses on three areas:

- a) increase in the forest area by 10% (from 370,000 ha in 2020 to 407,000 ha in 2030)

This increase has partly (18,000 ha) to be realized in the so-called Nature Network the Netherlands (NNN), which includes all Dutch Natura 2000 sites, and partly (19,000 ha) outside this network in forests that are private property. Afforestation outside the NNN could be realized using transition zones bordering the NNN, in and around towns and villages to enhance life quality and to decrease recreation pressure in other forests, along brooks and rivers, and by combining forests with other uses such as agriculture, house construction and wind energy.

- b) revitalization of forests

Revitalization is intended to adapt forests to climate changes. First, it focuses on surrounding factors, such as reducing nitrogen deposition in forests, water retention in sandy soils, rejuvenation of forests, and improvement of corridors between forests. Second, revitalization intends to give forests a quality boost by aiming at self-regulating natural forests due to adaptations in structure, composition, and hydrology of forests. Third, revitalization must be realized by adjustment of forest management, an increase of natural forests, which are fully directed at reinforcing biodiversity and more attention for recreation forests.

- c) increase in trees outside forests

Trees in the countryside and towns and villages contribute to carbon sequestration, biodiversity, and quality of life. Increasing the number of trees outside the forests must be realized by an enhancement of the so-called 'blue-green veining' of the countryside through planting more woody landscape elements, by extension of agroforestry, by an increase of trees in each Dutch municipality by 1% p.a., and by support for planting trees by primary school children on the national tree day.

The National Forest Strategy is a cooperation of the national government and the 11 provinces in the Netherlands, as forest policy is part of nature policy, which is due to decentralization a common responsibility of the national government and the provinces. Other actors involved in forestry development are public/private forest organizations and forest owners.

The National Forest Strategy covers the period 2020-2030. There is a limited budget available from the so-called Nature Pact for the increase in trees within the NNN. For other actions, the budget must come from the general budget for nature policy, other policy fields, such as the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and from private partners. It is yet insecure whether these funds will be sufficient for realizing the ambitions of the National Forest Strategy.

3.2.3 Current land use and potential land-use competition

The Netherlands is a highly densely populated country. The pressure on land for new houses and transport infrastructure is high. Moreover, due to the high intensity of agricultural production, productivity per ha is high, which results in high land prices. So, it is doubtful whether sufficient land can be acquired for a substantial extension of forest area. Therefore, the National Forest Strategy focuses particularly on the extension of forests within the NNN and on smart combinations with other policies and ambitions. The NNN is public property, which consists mainly of nature area. A part of this area has a relatively low natural value and could therefore without much biodiversity harm be converted into a forest area. Combinations with other policies or ambitions refer amongst others to the reduction of the nitrogen deposition in nature areas, water retention, the Climate Agreement ambition of an increase in trees in and around villages and towns, the planting of hedgerows for increasing the green-blue vein of the countryside and agroforestry in the scope of the CAP.

Table 3-3: Area in the Netherlands, 2015

Sector	Size in % of total
Traffic area	2.8
Built area	8.7
Semi-built area	1.2
Recreation area	2.5
Agricultural area	53.8
Forests	8.2
Nature	3.8
Water area (internal and external)	18.9
Total area (million ha)	4.2

Source: CBS.

Prospects for combinations of forests/trees with other land use depend on its economic or intrinsic benefits. Planting and maintaining hedgerows on agricultural land is eligible for CAP support. Whether farmers decide to plant hedgerows depends on the extent these can be integrated into farm management and the ratio of income forgone and revenues of hedgerows. Support for agroforestry has for decades been included in the CAP, as a rather marginal measure. With the increasing attention for the circular economy nowadays, also the interest in circular agriculture increased in the Netherlands. This is often related to the concept of nature inclusive agriculture, which opts for sustainable agricultural production based on an integration of agriculture and the natural environment. Within this context, interest in agroforestry increased, either production forests or food forests. Planting trees on agricultural land contributes to CO₂ sequestration and enhancement of biodiversity. However, severe doubts can be raised on the business model of agroforestry. That is why the National Forest Strategy put in the years up to 2025 efforts in knowledge development, design of financial and fiscal instruments and support for pilot projects and agroforestry initiatives.

3.2.4 Climate risks & sensitivities

Existing forests – but newly planted forests as well - are threatened by climate-related disturbances such as drought, storm damage, extreme temperatures, and intense rainfall, which ask for climate adaptation measures. Within the National Forest Strategy, some revitalization measures to better cope with these disasters are foreseen.

3.2.5 Economic implications

In the Netherlands, the economic benefits of forest per ha land are relatively low compared with benefits from other land uses. So, it is unlikely that the market mechanism will bring about a considerable land-use change in the direction of an extension of forest area. Only if non-economic benefits like carbon sequestration, enhancing biodiversity and increasing quality of life, could be

monetized by for example payments for carbon credits or ecosystem services, opportunities for forestry become more promising.

3.2.6 Co-benefits and trade-offs

Forests contribute to carbon sequestration, offer room for biodiversity, produce wood, and provide recreation opportunities. Often, the neighbourhood of trees or other 'green elements' increase real estate prices.

Trade-offs arise as land used for forestry excludes its use for other functions. Putting it simply: if the land is used for forestry, this land cannot be used for building houses or producing cereals. If the supply of houses or potatoes exceeds demand, this is not necessarily problematic. However, the opposite applies in cases of shortage. Smart combinations such as planting several trees in the garden of houses could be used to limit such trade-offs.

3.2.7 Risks associated with scaling up

It is likely that scaling up of forestation of the intended 10% in the National Forest Strategy to, for example, 50% or 100% will be mainly realized on agricultural land. Doubling the forest area would imply that forest area increases from over 8% of the total area to more than 16%. The Netherlands is the second agricultural exporter in the world. As such, a decrease in agricultural production due to less agricultural land would have consequences for the global food supply.

3.3 Agroforestry

3.3.1 Introduction

Agroforestry is a rather new concept in the Netherlands representing an interesting climate mitigation option. In a former publication about the current state of agroforestry in Europe, agroforestry is defined as “*the deliberate integration of trees with agricultural crops and/or livestock either simultaneously or sequentially on the same unit of land*” (Mosquera-Losada et al., 2009, p. 3). Agroforestry, therefore, aims at integrating woody structures with agriculture and livestock farming (Figure 3-1).

Figure 3-1: The agroforestry triangle shows the different agroforestry types which are combinations of crops, livestock and trees and shrubs (source: adapted from (Luske et al., 2020, p. 10))

The most prominent agroforestry types in the Netherlands are listed in the Dutch Agroforestry Masterplan (Luske et al., 2020):

- *Silvopastoral systems*: combinations of productive grassland and livestock with trees or shrubs (this also includes old cultural landscapes such as the Northern Frisian Woods and the Maasheggen area).
- *Silvoarable systems*: combinations of arable land, open field vegetable/fruit cultivation, and trees or shrubs.
- *Windbreaks* (NL: ‘Windhagen’): combinations of grassland or arable farming with hedges to break the wind.

- *Food forests*⁵: cultivation systems consisting of multiple layers of vegetation to produce a range of fruit, nuts, seeds, vegetables, and herbs.

Similar to forestry, agroforestry supports the **sequestration of carbon** in the biosphere but also contributes to important **ecosystem services** such as improvements in biodiversity, pest control and reduced soil erosion (Kay et al., 2019) as well as economic benefits of a more diverse product range.

3.3.2 Policy context

In the Netherlands, using land for agroforestry aligns with objectives of multiple policies, such as the National Forest Strategy (Interprovinciaal Overleg & Ministerie van Landbouw, Natuur en Voedselkwaliteit, 2020) and the transition to a more circular and nature-inclusive agriculture (Ministerie van Landbouw, Natuur en Voedselkwaliteit, 2018).

Figure 3-2: Agroforestry can be seen as a link between forestry and agriculture (source: (Interprovinciaal Overleg & Ministerie van Landbouw, Natuur en Voedselkwaliteit, 2020, p. 37))

To facilitate agroforestry in the Netherlands, the Dutch key stakeholders in research, private and government sector, paved the way for specific policy and regulation in recent years. The integration of agroforestry in the Dutch Climate Agreement goals, even though with few specifications, can be seen as an important starting point (Ministerie van Economische Zaken en Klimaat, 2019). Further steps followed with the aforementioned Masterplan Agroforestry as well as the subsequently published official Dutch Forest Strategy (Interprovinciaal Overleg & Ministerie van Landbouw, Natuur en

⁵ According to (Interprovinciaal Overleg & Ministerie van Landbouw, Natuur en Voedselkwaliteit, 2020, p. 37), food forests are defined as follows:

“A productive ecosystem designed by humans after the example of a natural forest, with a high diversity of perennial and/or woody species, parts of which (fruits, seeds, leaves, stems, etc.) serve as food for humans. With presence from:

- a canopy of taller trees.
- at least three of the other niches or vegetation layers of resp. lower trees, shrubs, herbs, ground covers, underground crops and climbing plants.
- a rich forest floor life.

A food forest has a robust size, i.e. an area of at least 0.5 hectares in an ecologically rich environment; in a severely impoverished environment a minimum area of up to 20 hectares is required.”

Voedselkwaliteit, 2020) providing more insights and concrete steps toward an expansion of agroforestry in the Dutch context.

As outlined in the Dutch Forest Strategy, the total climate impact of agroforestry is quantified as part of the sector goal “trees, forest and nature” **with 0.4 Mton CO₂ and 0.8 Mton CO₂ (‘ambitious goal’) in 2030**. However, it is not clear yet how much of the aimed GHG emissions are assigned to non-agroforestry in this sector such as landscape elements. According to (Lesschen et al., 2021), agroforestry could contribute to 0.1 Mton CO₂, however, assuming a more ambitious target of 25,000 ha in 2030 compared to 7,000 ha mentioned in the Dutch Forest Strategy (see section 3.3.3).

The current phase of Dutch policy development (2020-2024) focuses on a general evaluation of agroforestry including the development of knowledge, financial incentives and the elimination of implementation barriers (Interprovinciaal Overleg & Ministerie van Landbouw, Natuur en Voedselkwaliteit, 2020). In a first step, a task force consisting of provincial governments, water boards, municipalities and agricultural stakeholders has been established to identify policy barriers in 2021. The focus for the following period is planned to be on the application and upscaling of agroforestry.

In terms of **available funding**, the forest strategy mentions potential funding either via pillar I and/or II of the Common Agriculture Policy (CAP) of the EU, or funding from the Dutch Climate Agreement. The latter specifies the available funding with 51 MEUR (‘climate funds’) for, among others, the restoration of landscape elements/agroforestry, and a subsidy scheme for farmers planting forests on their land. How much exactly shall be accounted for in agroforestry has not been specified.

The former option of funding via the CAP so far limited the integration of tree structures in agriculture since so-called landscape planting is deducted from eligible agricultural for the calculation. As a result, planting trees on the agricultural ground would lead to a reduction of EU subsidies. However, the new CAP (2021-2027) is expected to provide more degrees of freedom for national governments to design subsidy schemes that could reward e.g., farmers for ecosystem services such as biodiversity. Still, in this context advisors to the respective Dutch ministry concluded that the **CAP alone is not sufficient for a solid agroforestry business case but needs to be complemented by national subsidies (Strootman et al., 2020)**.

Strootman et al (2020) mention three examples for national funding: (1) the Transition Fund which still needs to be set up and would include a total funding budget of some 175 MEUR, (2) the ‘nitrogen letter’ from the Minister of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality which offers financial opportunities to support companies in the reduction of nitrogen (which is a co-benefit of agroforestry), and (3) the subsidy scheme for Nature and Landscape Quality Impulse (SKNL) which supports the conversion of agricultural land to forestry by compensation of loss of economic value of the ground.

To conclude, there are multiple opportunities to incentivise the implementation of agroforestry. It requires more in-depth research to evaluate if/how these can be combined and if this is sufficient to stimulate agroforestry development.

3.3.3 *Current land use and potential land-use competition*

What is particular to the Dutch situation is that in policy documents specific goals are mentioned for so-called food forests (NL: 'voedselbossen') as one integral element of agroforestry.

This is an important distinction since there is a specific sub-target mentioned for food forests in both, the national forest strategy as well as the masterplan agroforestry. However, the speed of agroforestry deployment differs in the two documents. Whereas the masterplan agroforestry strives for **25,000 ha agroforestry in 2030, including 1,000 ha food forest** (Luske et al., 2020), the national forest strategy takes a more conservative approach by setting the contribution of agroforestry to the general forestry expansion to **7,000 ha in 2030, but supporting the goal of 25,000 ha for the long-term**.

Agriculture being with its over 50% land coverage the largest land user in the Netherlands will be most probably impacted by the described expansion plans for agroforestry, e.g. by requiring agricultural lands to partly integrate tree structures and/or by the land-use change to grasslands.

Concrete agroforestry cases in the history of the Netherlands are limited. One of the main reasons for the limited use of agroforestry lies in the high **land-use competition** with intensive agriculture. According to (Oosterbaan & Kuiters, 2009) many farmers due to high labour costs and land prices switched towards large-scale agricultural production to achieve as much production as possible, including intensive fertiliser and chemical use. An analysis of the European land use and land cover data by (den Herder et al., 2017) has shown that in 2015, livestock agroforestry was the largest form of agroforestry (27,800 ha), next to 3,700 ha grazed fruit, olive and nut tree area (belonging to the high-value tree agroforestry category) and no sizeable (>100 ha) arable agroforestry.

Next to the larger established parts, there are also plenty of **small-scale agroforestry projects** and experiments. (Oosterbaan & Kuiters, 2009) show a variety of 17 small-scale agroforestry experiments across several Dutch provinces (1-10 ha per experiment) to search for alternative ways of producing different crops (e.g. beet and maize) and growing trees (e.g. poplar and walnuts).

More recent experiences, experiments and projects at a small scale (<100 ha per test location) are published on various Dutch websites.⁶ Most of the small tests are currently executed in the province of North Brabant (see Annex I: Additional information for the national narratives).

⁶ References: <https://www.agro-forestry.nl/projecten/>
<https://www.landbouwenvoedselbrabant.nl/landbouw+en+natuur/agroforestry+brabant/initiatievenkaart+agroforestry/default.aspx>
<https://www.landbouwmetsnatuur.nl/initiatieven-agroforestry/>

3.3.4 *Climate risks & sensitivities*

In general, climate risks and sensitivities for the agroforestry sector closely align with the forestry sector. The National Forest Strategy (Interprovinciaal Overleg & Ministerie van Landbouw, Natuur en Voedselkwaliteit, 2020) specifies **salinisation in the low-lying parts of the Netherlands** as one specific risk that makes some places unsuitable for tree structures. This can be caused by rising sea levels, subsidence and more extreme periods of drought and their effect of freshwater displacement by brackish or saltwater.

Drought can also cause forests to become more prone to nitrous oxide, precipitation, diseases, and plagues.

Another limitation is **very wet and poorly drained soils** with increasing groundwater levels. Many species do not grow well under those conditions such as nut and fruit trees.

3.3.5 *Economic implications*

In general, it can be assumed that agroforestry is not economically viable based on regular income alone (Strootman et al., 2020). On the positive side, Strootman et al. mention the possibility of increased crop yield thanks to agroforestry, e.g., by protecting from wind leading to increases of 5-30% in the arable crop. Though, one has to note the provided additional economic value is usually not realised in the short-term in contrast to annual crops since trees and shrubs take some years to grow which poses a serious challenge to agroforestry. Also, a general barrier that many ecologically valuable options face is that the provided services to the ecosystem such as erosion control, reduced nutrient loss, and carbon storage cannot be monetized (Kay et al., 2019). The same research paper generally concludes that when societal values of ecosystem services and dis-services are priced, the profitability of agroforestry is higher than for non-agroforestry cases.⁷ **Realised carbon prices of some 30 EUR/ton CO₂** favoured agroforestry in comparison to non-agroforestry cases.

In this regard, the Dutch National CO₂ market, which is a voluntary emission trading market, currently works on methodologies for providing certificates e.g. the plantation of new forests and different forest management.

Additional ways of financial support are also discussed in the National Forestry Strategy:

- Supporting advantageous tax schemes and available funding from the Circular Agriculture Conversion fund (NL: Omschakelfonds Kringlooplandbouw)
- Supporting research to monetize ecosystem services, possibly based on critical pressure indicators described in the national plan for recreating biodiversity

⁷ The research paper's scope comprises of agroforestry and non-agroforestry profitability assessment of case studies in Atlantic and continental regions of Europe.

3.3.6 *Co-benefits and trade-offs*

Next to the positive effect of carbon sequestration in the biosphere, the implementation of agroforestry introduces various co-benefits but also some negative impacts on agriculture.

The more diverse product range of agroforestry is an advantage since it can help farmers to lower the risk of total income losses in the events of natural disturbances affecting their only product (e.g., silvoarable systems: flood damages conventional crops such as wheat but high stem fruit trees may be less affected). Other examples of co-benefits are provided in literature (Dollinger & Jose, 2018; Interprovinciaal Overleg & Ministerie van Landbouw, Natuur en Voedselkwaliteit, 2020; Kay et al., 2019; Lesschen et al., 2021; Luske et al., 2020; Strootman et al., 2020):

- **Ecosystem services** such as reduced nutrient and soil losses, enhanced soil organic matter (which affects soil biodiversity and associated soil biological functions), pest control in agricultural areas, water retention, pollination, biodiversity, and animal welfare (e.g., natural sun protection for cattle and poultry by trees).
- **Social benefits** such as savings on healthcare costs and positive effects on business climate and real estate value

What can generally be observed is the trade-off between these ecosystem and social co-benefits on the one hand and negative impacts on agricultural production on the other hand. The agricultural sector is negatively impacted by among others: (1) the incompatibility of trees with agricultural practices since trees can result in potentially lower harvesting efficiencies due to the heterogeneous composition compared to monocropping and thus an increase of labour costs, and (2) the reduction of available area for crops. Especially the latter can also result in increasing emissions somewhere else (Lesschen et al., 2021) e.g., due to land use conversion in a different country to agricultural land.

3.3.7 *Risks associated with scaling up*

Many risks for agroforestry in the Netherlands originate from the fact that it is a new concept that has not been accounted for in much of the Dutch agriculture and nature **policy**. The National Forest Strategy mentions the example of unclarity on how agroforestry parcels need to be registered in terms of land categories, crop codes etc.

Another risk for upscaling is that with fragmented or even without **financial** support for carbon sequestration and ecosystem services, the profitability of agroforestry is less in comparison to traditional agriculture. On top of that, parts of the incomes may be generated in the longer term which can be a disadvantage compared to the short-term income of annual crops.

A lack of knowledge is another risk for upscaling agroforestry. The combination of different sectors in agriculture and forestry comes with scattered knowledge over those sectors which can pose a barrier for agroforestry implementation.

3.3.8 Research gaps

Due to the just recent appearance of agroforestry in the national policy context, knowledge about agroforestry is limited and therefore needs to be developed and deepened to provide reliable qualitative and quantitative information.

Not just on a national level, but also on the EU level, there is a knowledge gap on effective measures to account for ecological and social benefits in the economic evaluation of projects (Kay et al., 2019).

3.4 CCS applied to AD based on animal manure and soil carbon enhancement with AD based digestate

3.4.1 Introduction

The historical developments, ongoing research activities and market initiatives in the field of CO₂ capture and geological storage within the Netherlands over the past two decades or so do not show a promising picture. Several CCS market initiatives and projects have been proposed and cancelled, and to date, no commercial-scale CCS projects have been developed. While great advancements have been made in post-combustion CO₂-capture technologies, and techno-economic assessments for CO₂-transport and geological storage infrastructure have been developed, CCS in The Netherlands is far from market implementation and meaningful scales. However, this picture is not unique to The Netherlands, similar delays in CCS market application can be observed in many other countries around the globe. This is despite the notion that most 1.5 and 2.0°C compatible climate scenarios rely considerably on CCS deployment at scale. However, the basic geophysical and industry conditions for developing a viable CCS sector in The Netherlands are available. As a former top-3 exporter of natural gas in the EU (whose domestic gas production is now in considerable decline) there will be increasing opportunities to (re)use existing gas sector knowledge/expertise, and natural gas infrastructure for CO₂-transport and geological storage.

(Strengers B., 2018) provide a first estimate of the **technical potential** for **post-combustion CO₂-capture of 46-55 Mt CO₂ per annum** for the Netherlands for several different BECCS supply chain configurations. The resulting estimated **realistic potential** is considerably smaller with resp. **4.6 and 17 Mt CO₂ per year**. This is mainly due to a range of risks and uncertainties relating to the core technology, CCS: Among others, social resistance to onshore CCS projects, uncertainty about viable business cases and doubts about sufficiently available subsidies have so far blocked several CCS projects and still hamper the introduction of large CCS applications in the Netherlands (Akerboom et al., 2021).

Next to the concerns of CCS, the bioenergy component of BECCS raises another major question, namely if the Netherlands can secure the required volumes of biomass sustainably.

Side-effects of more irrigated biomass plantations are e.g., extra water stress in an already water-stressed world (Stenzel, Greve, Lucht, Tramberend, & Wada, 2021). Furthermore, all the BECCS supply

chain configurations considered by (Strengers B., 2018) rely heavily on imported biomass.⁸ While there are ample scenario studies about the international availability and future trade of biomass considering major global developments such as the energy transition, the circular economy, the bio-based economy, general population growth and food security, securing (future) supplies of imported and domestically available biomass will remain a continuous risk and challenge. (SER, 2020) recommend a phase-out of lower value biomass to energy applications, such as for electricity production, low-temperature heating systems and as fuel for light vehicles and to use biomass for (higher value) bioenergy applications - such as heavy road transport, shipping, and air transport – only as a temporary, or bridging option.

Figure 3-3: Outline of a possible AD BECCS + soil carbon enhancement supply chain in The Netherlands

Concerning this stress on biomass supply for bioenergy and CCS applications, animal manure is one of the few remaining and underutilized domestic sources of biomass within the Netherlands (Strengers B., 2018). The sizeable Dutch livestock sector (mainly dairy cattle and pig farming) produces a steady

⁸ Post-combustion CO₂-capture configurations include: CCS applied to coal fired power plants using biomass as feedstock, CCS applied to the about 30 larger and smaller gas-fired power plants in the country that could be fuelled with biogas, CCS applied to the Hlsarna process in the steel sector, CCS applied to solid biomass combustion in high temperature heat applications, CCS applied to waste incineration plants (biogenic fraction of waste).

annual supply of mainly liquid manure⁹ that can be used to produce biogas, as well as organic fertilizers.

Biogas from animal manure results in avoidance (reduction) of CH₄ emissions (from manure storage) and CO₂ emissions (substitute fossil fuels), as well as in negative emissions (removals) through CO₂ capture and geological storage (from biogas treatment and CO₂-separation), and soil carbon enhancement by using manure derived digestate / organic fertilizers (see Figure 3-3). Other aspects to consider in the overall GHG balance include e.g., N₂O emissions from soils, CH₄ leakages, CH₄ emissions from enteric fermentation, manure management, potential CO₂ emission savings from reduced use of fossil fertilizers.

While there undoubtedly is a technical domestic potential for negative emissions concerning treatment and usage of animal manure, robust scenario studies on the realistic scaling potential of these negative emission solutions are scarce. (Strengers B., 2018) have excluded CO₂-capture at anaerobic digestion plants from their assessment, mainly due to the considerable infrastructure requirements for CO₂ transport but argue that in a possible future where large-scale centralised (manure)digesters will be built (>1000 m³ per hour) then this BECCS option could become interesting. Marginal costs are estimated at EUR 70-80 per ton of CO₂ (including CO₂-transport costs). However, further risks and impact assessments, techno-economic analysis and scenario studies would be needed to determine the realistic potential.

In this study, we try to determine whether such a scenario for nationwide scaling-up of manure digestion with CCS and digestate reuse for soil carbon enhancement can be compatible with the net-zero emission ambitions for agriculture in 2050.

3.4.2 Policy context

The BECCS value chain finds itself in a complex situation of different policies and measures affecting both components (bioenergy and CCS) either separately or simultaneously. In this chapter, we briefly address CCS and bioenergy related policy items and go into more depth about the biomass supply which is crucial for BECCS to be implemented at scale.

CCS

For considering CCS alone, the **EU CCS directive (2009/31/EC)** is of importance that aims at the safeguarding of safety and health conditions for CCS applications, as well as minimum requirements for storage permits, liability and roles and tasks of CCS actors (Akerboom et al., 2021). The CCS directive finds its national implementation in **chapter 3 of the Dutch Mining Act**.

⁹ In 2020 the annual production of liquid manure in the Netherlands was 71,642 mln. kg and 2704 mln. kg solid manure. Source: (Statline, 2021)

To support the **economic viability** of CCS, there are basically three policy measures on EU and national level impacting the CCS business case: (1) Avoided costs of the EU Emission Trading Scheme where e.g., actors that fall under this scheme can apply CCS to reduce emissions which otherwise may result in costs for additional allowances, (2) avoided costs by the Dutch carbon tax for industrial emissions, and (3) financial support by the Dutch SDE++ subsidy in form of a premium bridging the gap between installation costs and financial business case. More information about each option can be found in (Akerboom et al., 2021).

Bioenergy

On the matter of bioenergy, important points are mentioned in the Dutch Climate Agreement (Ministerie van Economische Zaken en Klimaat, 2019): (1) The green gas sector aims to realise some 3.6 Mt carbon dioxide reduction and a cost level of 100-150 EUR per avoided tonne of CO₂ by 2030, (2) there is a reduction aim of 1-2 Mt by 2030 through **CCS and CCU in the green gas sector**, and (3) a **cascade of biomass use** primarily for soil fertilisation, human and animal feed, feedstock for materials and chemicals, and just lastly for energy production.

In this framework BECCS would apply to the second category, thus contributing to the green gas reduction aim of 1-2 Mt carbon dioxide by 2030. As to the question of where the required biomass for the generation of bioenergy and subsequent CCS can be sourced, this narrative focuses on manure from the domestic livestock sector.

(Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy, 2022):

- At least 2 bcm green gas in Netherlands annually from 2030 onwards
- The current green gas production capacity is approximately 220 million m³ per year, built up over a period of more than 10 years
- The current coalition has expressed itself through the Coalition Agreement in favour of an admixture obligation of 20%, or an expected 1.6 bcm, in the built environment by 2030 *equivalent to 2.9 Mton CO₂ reduction per 2030*
- Scaling-up primarily in built environment
- The blending obligation will be fulfilled with administrative certificates, whereby the green gas is fed into the natural gas network. These can only be obtained, with the consent of the European Commission, on the basis of: green gas produced in the Netherlands. The Dutch Emissions Authority (the NEa) is the supervisory and enforcement authority for this certificate system.
- Blending obligation starting in 2025 with 150 mln. m³
- Efforts to increase availability of unused biomass potential such as micro algae, seaweed and digestate.

Dutch legislation regarding the livestock sector

Next to the indirect contribution of livestock to the reduction aims of the green gas sector, it also directly contributes to climate change mitigation via more sustainable farming, e.g., by reducing methane and ammonia emissions (see table 3-4).

Table 3-4: Overview of AFOLU sector measures stated in the Dutch Climate Agreement

Theme	Measure	Foreseen emission reduction in 2030 (Mton CO ₂ -eq.)	Finance / funding 2020-2030 (mln. EUR)
Livestock farming	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Precision fertilization dairy cattle farming - Low emission dairy cattle and pig stable systems - Extend productive life and genetic selection of dairy cattle - Integrated approach for reducing methane and ammonia emissions - Research on nitrification inhibitors - Sustainable stable systems in pig farming - Buy-out scheme for pig farming - Substitution of fossil fertilizers - Research & Development 	1.2 – 2.7*	252
Livestock farming in / close by Natura2000 areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Measures to reinforce the ecological value in Natura2000 areas - Specific measures for the livestock sector 	-	100
Peat(y) soils	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increasing water level 	1.0	276
Agricultural soils and open soil cultivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pilots, vocational training and information 	0.4 – 0.6	28
Trees, forest, and nature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National Forest Strategy 	0.4 – 0.8	51
Horticulture (glass)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Production and use of renewable energy 	1.8 – 2.9	250
Food waste, residual flows, and biomass	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training and information on circular agriculture - Activities towards preventing food waste 	0	13

*of which at least 1 Mton CO₂-eq of methane emission reduction (in line with coalition agreement).

Source: (Ministerie van Economische Zaken en Klimaat, 2019).

Concerning relevant policies, there is a complex subset of negative impacts associated with the current livestock sector that triggers the public debate and drive policy action to improve the sustainability of the agriculture/livestock sector. This includes a range of impacts on soil (land use, soil quality, soil health, use of fertilizers, pesticides), water (eutrophication), air (ammonia/nitrogen emissions), climate (CO₂, CH₄, N₂O emissions), flora (monoculture grasslands) and fauna (soil biodiversity, animal welfare, human health), etc. To govern/regulate all these impacts a comprehensive framework and complex web of generic policies and specific measures apply. Generic policies include the EU's

common agricultural policy, the laws on environmental management (Dutch: “Wet milieubeheer”), best available technology guidelines, etc. Specific policies include among others:

- Law on ammonia (NH₃) emissions and animal husbandry (Dutch: “Wet ammoniak en veehouderij”)
- Law on odour nuisance and animal husbandry (Dutch: “Wet geurhinder en veehouderij”)
- Decree low emission animal housing (Dutch: “Besluit emissiearme huisvesting”)
- Production rights pig & poultry (Dutch: “Productierechten varkens / pluimvee”)
- Specific laws on phosphate rights and phosphate production dairy cattle (Dutch: “Fosfaatrechten / fosfaatproductie melkvee”)
- Regulations for manure storage, - transport, and - processing
- Regulations for housing and caretaking of animals, and use of antibiotics
- Regulations on the use of (manure, organic, fossil) fertilizers on soils
- Subsidies and fiscal support schemes e.g. manure processing, low-emission stable systems, biogas production, air filtration systems, etc.

The current governance regime puts most emphasis on regulating and stimulating the sustainability of farm-level activities while the rest of the supply chain such as the agro-food processing industries, and supermarkets face a different governance regime (e.g. EU ETS, Energy Efficiency regulations, and other health, safety and environment (HSE) regulations and support schemes). Specific rules and regulations for consumers/end users tend to focus more on voluntary actions or nudging and less on price regulations. While sugar- and meat taxes are part of the political and public debate, to date they have not been implemented. For consumers, softer measures like promotional campaigns for more sustainable or vegetarian/vegan food dominate.

One of the key political challenges is linked to nitrogen/ammonia emissions. The existing policy regime, the so-called programmatic approach nitrogen (Dutch: “Programmatische Aanpak Stikstof”), that serves as a governance framework and basis for the government for permitting economic activities¹⁰ was declared inadequate by the Dutch Council of State.¹¹ This ruling has caused the ‘nitrogen crisis’ as it is currently blocking a wide range of economic activities. Agriculture is one of the major contributors to nitrogen (NO_x) and ammonia (NH₃) emissions with resp. 16% and 85% of national emissions (livestock is the main source of NH₃ emissions in the country at about 87% of total NH₃ emissions in agriculture).

Any climate change mitigation/negative emission scenario within this sector will likely face heavy (political and public) scrutiny for its positive or negative impact on mitigating the nitrogen crisis. In

¹⁰ Such as the expansion of livestock stables, building construction activities, and infrastructure works on roads, etc.

¹¹ **Invalid source specified. and Invalid source specified.**

addition to this other sustainable development objectives (e.g., biodiversity impact, land use, animal welfare, etc.) will also be included in such transition pathway evaluations.

The biogas-hub scenario, which includes manure digestion, adjustments of stable (floor) systems, has the potential to significantly contribute to reductions in NH₃ emissions. However, a more in-depth qualitative risk and impact assessment and quantitative assessment are needed to evaluate the real scaling potential of this scenario and the associated co-benefits and trade-offs.

Stakeholders and actors involved

The biogas hub CCS scenario adds a new economic activity to a market system with its structure (see Figure 3-4) and dynamics. Livestock farmers produce dairy and meat as their core activity and supply this to meat/dairy processing factories. The biogas hub and the efforts to enhance soil carbon also make the farmers renewable energy producers, and ‘carbon farmers’. The biogas based energy can be supplied via an intermediary (energy trader) or directly to different end-use sectors (transport, industry, heating). CO₂ transport and geological CO₂-storage services will most likely be provided by independent legal entities as well.

Figure 3-4: Simplified market system for a biogas hub BECCS scenario

3.4.3 Current land use and potential land-use competition

Grassland and land use for feed/fodder production comprise about 65% of total land use in agriculture (see Table 13). While domestic agricultural land is mainly used for roughage and fodder for the

livestock sector, the sector also has significant indirect land use resulting from the import of animal feed (e.g. soy, mixed feeds, etc.).

Table 3-5: Agricultural land use in the Netherlands in 2010 and 2019 (in 1000 ha)

Land use category	2010	2019
Agricultural area, total	1,872	1,816
Arable land	542	532
Horticulture in the open	87	93
Horticulture under glass	10	10
Grassland and feed crops	1,232	1,182

Source: (Statline, 2020)

Any significant land-use change resulting from the biogas-hub & soil carbon enhancement scenario is not expected as this LMT depends on manure as input. In case the livestock sector would shrink for political reasons or competing land claims from other sectors, this may have consequences for the supply of manure. Competing land claims on land used to feed the livestock sector may arise from the rewetting of peat(y) soils, afforestation, an extension of built areas, and expansion of wind and solar electricity generation on the land. Apart from competing for land use claims outside the livestock sector, some land-use change is expected for additional biogas, gas, and CO₂ pipeline infrastructure, but it is plausible that such infrastructure will largely follow existing infrastructure corridors.

3.4.4 Climate risks & sensitivities

In this section, we focus on climate risks and sensitivities related to the biomass supply which we expect to be more impacted by a higher degree than the technologies for bioenergy generation and CCS. A report by the Dutch Ministry of Agriculture, Nature, and Food Quality addresses climate risks for the agriculture sector (Dutch Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality, 2020). Among others, the livestock sector is impacted by more frequent **extreme temperatures** and exposure to UV radiation. This puts additional stress on animal welfare – something that needs to be prevented by farmers e.g., by ventilation and misting in stables and taking precautions when transporting animals.

Droughts can cause lower feed/fodder yields and affect the nutritional value of feed/fodder. Finally, livestock farming can also be confronted with **new animal diseases and zoonoses**, including those transmitted by insects.

3.4.5 Economic implications

A general estimate on BECCS CO₂ avoidance costs is provided by (Geden & Schenuit, 2020) which mention a range of 100-200 USD₂₀₁₁ / tonne CO₂ removed in 2050. However, this is highly dependent on the type of biomass used, transportation distances (e.g., imported biomass) and digester sizes (economics of scale). During our study, we will analyse in more depth the GHG emission mitigation and negative emission potential in the Netherlands.

Manure availability for anaerobic digestion

Detailed figures about the production of the starting product, dairy manure, can be found via the statistics office of the Netherlands (Statline, 2021).

Figure 3-5: Manure production in the Netherlands in the period of 1995-2020

1st scenario: Required integrated manure management to reach national emission reduction target

- Net zero by 2050: “However, even by 2050, greenhouse gas emissions from this sector will be inevitable. This is because greenhouse gases are inherent to natural products, such as methane and nitrous oxide from animal husbandry and fertilisation (even from "green fertilisers"⁷²). At the same time, the sector will increasingly be capturing carbon in soils, forests and materials, produce biomass and generate renewable energy. The sector’s aim is to achieve an equilibrium between the unavoidable emissions of greenhouse gases, on the one hand, and the capture of greenhouse gases and production of renewable energy and biomass, on the other hand, by 2050.” (Ministerie van Economische Zaken en Klimaat, 2019)
- Link to 1.2 – 2.7 Mt emission reduction target by 2030 of the livestock farming sector, of which at least 1 Mt CO₂-eq in methane emission reduction (in accordance with the Coalition Agreement). e.g. by digestate replacing conventional fertilisers,
- “the Coalition Agreement sets out that “technical measures (e.g. manure processing, mixed feed and energy-producing greenhouses) will **take preference over measures aimed at curbing volumes.**” → constant livestock volumes?

- *“measures for “Manure storage and Fertiliser”: changes to livestock facilities, whether or not in conjunction with outdoor storage of methane oxidation, manure mono-fermentation and replacement of part of the grass with clover to reduce the amount of artificial fertiliser used;”*
- *Update own comment: Reduction inevitable due to lifted derogation for Netherlands conventional farmers with largely grassland will be allowed to use around ~30 % (170 compared to 230/250 kg/ha) less manure from next year. That will certainly have an impact on the number of cows. But I also understood that it will not have an impact for everyone. Organic farmers such as Jan already use a maximum of 170 kg/ha, (is that correct?) It will be interesting to see how we will link this development to the scenarios (e.g. 30% fewer cows, excluding organic farmers).*

2nd scenario concerning manure availability: Livestock reduction

- Reduction of livestock in accordance with Greenpeace (Tirado, 2018) suggesting that by 2050 the global production and consumption of meat and dairy should be halved.
- 50% livestock reduction for which farmers are compensated according to the previous subsidy scheme about cessation of dairy farming (Dutch State Secretary for Economic Affairs, 2017)
 - o Buy-out price per full grown (dairy) cow: 1,200 EUR
 - o Calves (23% of 1200 EUR)
 - o Young cattle (53% of 1,200 EUR)

The livestock manure is used to produce biogas and digestate in an anaerobic digestion process, which is described further in the next section.

- Interview summary René Cornelissen:
 - o The production of biogas from manure is closely linked to intensive livestock farming. The more livestock is allowed to graze outdoors, the less the ratio of manure that can be retrieved to be used for this purpose, so it could somehow conflict with a future trend in improving animal wellbeing. The ratio of manure that gets to biodigesters from intensive livestock farming is around 90%.

Anaerobic digestion

During the fermentation process of manure, part of the organic matter is converted into methane and carbon dioxide. There are different types of digestors out of which monodigestion (only digestion of one product such as manure) and co-digestion (at least 50% manure and the remainder composing of plant-based biomass) are the most applied in the Netherlands (Netherlands Enterprise Agency, 2021).

“Mono-manure digesters are small digesters in which only manure is processed. These installations are usually located at livestock farms. In a co-digester, manure is fermented in combination with an energy-rich co-substrate such as silage maize. An all-purpose digester is a large-scale digester that can process both mono-substrate (for example WWTP sludge) and co-substrates (different feedstocks). Fermenters do not differ substantially in process technology.”(van der Veen et al., 2020, p. 11)

Manure that is actually available for biogas production = 14%

Tabel 4 - Aandeel vrij beschikbare biomassa voor energietoepassingen en huidige inzet van biomassa, op basis van DNV GL (2017)

Biomassa-stromen	Huidig aandeel vrij beschikbaar ¹	Huidige inzet (alle toepassingen)					
		Veevoer	Bio-brandstoffen	Grondverbeteraar	Elektriciteit en warmte	Biogas en groengas	Anders
VGI	40%						
RWZI-slib	88%						
Natte gewasresten	17%						
Stro	0%						
Mest	14%						
GFT en ONF	61%						
Rest- en afvalhout	53%						
Papierresiduen	93%						
Productiebossen	18%						
Hout van fruit- en boomteelt	29% ²						
Hout uit landschap	50%						
Natuur- en bermgras	20% ²						

¹: 'Vrij beschikbaar' betekent beschikbaar voor energietoepassingen (elektriciteit, warmte, brandstoffen en groengas). De vrij beschikbare biomassa is gelijk aan de technisch beschikbare biomassa min de huidige inzet voor niet-energietoepassingen (DNV GL, 2017). Het percentage in de tabel is ten opzichte van de technisch beschikbare biomassa.

²: Hout van fruit- en boomteelt en natuur- en bermgras staan op 0% in DNV GL (2017), terwijl er wel aandelen naar verbranding en vergisting gaan. Daarom zijn hier de door DNV GL gegeven percentages voor 2030 genomen.

(van der Veen et al., 2020, p. 20)

Tabel 6 - Aandelen economisch beschikbare biomassa per stroom en per scenario

Biomassastromen	Aandeel economisch beschikbaar voor groengas in Scenario's A en B	Aandeel economisch beschikbaar voor groengas in Scenario's C en D
VGI	13%	8%
GFT en ONF	34%	21%
Gras uit recreatie	15%	10%
Afvalhout (huishoudens)	40%	25%
RWZI-slib	75%	25%
Slootmaaisel en bermgras	15%	10%
Mest	75%	25%
Akkerbouw: granen	38%	0%
Akkerbouw: groenten en overig	17%	10%
Akkerbouw: gras	15%	10%
Tuinbouw: fruit open grond	22%	14%
Tuinbouw: boomkwekerijen open grond	22%	14%
Overige tuinbouw en glastuinbouw	17%	10%
Bos	13%	8%

*: In Scenario's A en B is er een sterk ondersteunend beleid voor groengas en in Scenario's C en D een matig ondersteunend beleid voor groengas.

(van der Veen et al., 2020, p. 26)

Figuur 6 - Verhouding van de productiecapaciteit van biomaccategorieën en superkritische vergassing in de 'startlijst'

SKV = superkritische vergassing.

(van der Veen et al., 2020, p. 31)

(Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy, 2022)

“Currently, only a very small part of the manure in the Netherlands is fermented (<5%). Even within a reduction of the livestock, there is therefore still room for manure fermentation.”

Existing manure digesters (monomest, co-digestion, ? Mestvergisting (HEW)&(HG):

Figure 3-6: Commissioned Manure Digesters in the Netherlands (author’s figure based on (RVO, 2022))

Important factor for high biogas production is that the manure is fed into a digester system as soon as possible. A respective study shows that e.g., pig manure stored for one month could already result in a biogas potential decrease about 30 percent from 47.6 m³/ton manure (three days storage in sewerage) to 33.7 m³/ton manure (32 days storage in sewerage) (de Buissonjé & Verheijen, 2014).

Focus on monomanure since this is specifically pointed out as a measure in the Dutch climate Agreement (Ministerie van Economische Zaken en Klimaat, 2019, p. 136)

Green gas production from manure can contribute to the reduction of methane and nitrogen emissions. In the CE Delft report, if an emission reduction in the built environment of 2.5 Mton CO₂ is achieved, an additional methane emission reduction of 1 Mton CO₂-eq. estimated.(Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy, 2022)

Interview summary René Cornelissen 24 May 2022:

- The most usual configuration for this technique consists in small biodigesters (or co-digesters) that farmers have in their farms (private individual ownership). The biogas produced in these biodigesters is usually sold to large biogas consumers.
- Among the main environmental advantages of this technique, the interviewee cited a strong decrease in methane emissions in these farms that use this technique, and the easy collection of

the CO₂ derived from this process. This is particularly interesting when applied to the small scale, but the economic feasibility of these type of set-ups is at the moment very dependent on external subsidies.

The bottleneck for realizing negative emissions from gasification and anaerobic digestion is in the investment costs of a manure digester and the processing costs of biogas. Generally, if the cost price of bioenergy exceeds fossil energy cost prices, it will be difficult to exploit manure-based anaerobic digestion and gasification at a profitable scale (Strengers, Eerens, Smeets, van den Born, & Ros, 2018). Besides, the export costs of surplus manure at the farm play a role. As these costs increase, farmers get an incentive to look for alternative solutions for surplus manure, for example, as input for digestion. Incentives for manure digesting can be generated by legal obligations.

- *Efficiency*

- “Relatively little biogas is produced from this manure. For cattle manure, this is around 25-30 m³ of biogas per tonne of manure in the case of **co-fermentation**. For pig manure, this may be slightly higher.”(Netherlands Enterprise Agency, 2021)

Figure 3. Energy Yield Estimation Chart

Material	Biogas Yield per wet tonne of material (m ³ /t)	Electrical Yield per wet tonne of material * (kWh/t)	Heat Yield per wet tonne of material * (kWh/t)
Dairy Manure	23	48	62
Corn Silage	180	335	425
Bakery Waste (average)	265	490	630

Source: Böhni Energie & Umwelt, Systemoptimierungen Wirtschaftlichkeitsuntersuchungen Umsetzung

m³/t = cubic metre per tonne

kWh/t = kilowatt hour per tonne

* Assumes 35 per cent conversion of biogas energy to electricity, 45 per cent conversion of biogas energy to heat. Some of this heat will be required to heat the digester. Electrical efficiency can vary from 25 to 42 per cent.

- (Ontario Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Rural Affairs, 2021)

Table 7
Renewable energy production from anaerobic digestion of animal manure in 2030*.

	Pig	Cattle
Manure availability in mln. ton (wet basis)	11.65	39.66
Biogas yield per ton of liquid pig manure (in m ³ /ton manure)	25	30
Methane content (% CH ₄ /Nm ³ biogas)	56	56
1 m ³ CH ₄ = MJ	35.9	35.9
Energy balance (correction factor for own energy use)	≈ 0.5	≈ 0.6
Total estimated net renewable energy output (in PJ)	2.93	9.57

- * Energy yields from manure digestion only attribute to the IMM pathway.

(Spijker et al., 2020)

Biogas

- The methane content of biogas typically ranges from 45% to 75% by volume, with most of the remainder being CO₂. This variation means that the energy content of biogas can vary; the lower heating value (LHV) is between 16 megajoules per cubic metre (MJ/m³) and 28 MJ/m³. Biogas can be used directly to produce electricity and heat or as an energy source for cooking. (IEA, 2020)

Costs

Notes: HH = household; "HH Basic" includes biodigesters constructed in place using traditional construction materials such as sand, gravel and cement; "HH Advanced" includes pre-manufactured biodigesters made of more expensive composite material. Maintenance and operating costs include ordinary and extraordinary maintenance, labour costs, and energy required to operate the system. Capital costs have been levelised for the production lifetime of each technology: 25 years for landfill gas recovery and advanced household biodigesters; 20 years for centralised biodigesters (small, medium and large) and wastewater digesters; 15 years for basic household biodigesters. 1 MBtu = 0.29 MWh. Sources: IEA analysis based on different sources (Dennehy et al., 2017; ETSAP, 2013; and others).

(IEA, 2020, p. 28)

- biogas upgrading today is around USD 19/MBtu (IEA, 2020, p. 37)
- Investments required to transform biogas into electricity or heat, and this can be considerable in some cases; for example, adding a co-generation unit and including power grid connection and heat recovery distribution can add an additional 70% to the costs of an integrated project. (IEA, 2020, p. 31)
- Investment and operational costs for monomanure digesters for either green gas production, CHP, or heat generation are available (Lensink & Schoots (red.), 2021)

Tabel 2 - Productiekosten en conversierendement⁴

Categorie	SDE 2018 basisbedrag		SDE 2030 basisbedrag		Conversierendement
	Productie-kosten (€/Nm ³)	Waarvan onrendabele top	Productie-kosten (€/Nm ³)	Waarvan onrendabele top	
Allesvergisting	0,54	0,31	0,49	0,25	60%
Mest/co-vergisting	0,64	0,41	0,59	0,35	60%
Monomest-vergisting	0,76	0,53	0,64	0,40	60%
Vergassing	0,90	0,67	0,59	0,35	70% (reguliere vergassing) 95-99% (in geval van superkritische watervergassing)

De kosten voor productie van groengas kunnen omlaag van de huidige € 0,54-0,90/m³ naar € 0,25-0,40/m³ door onder meer ontwikkeling van superkritische watervergassers met hoog omzettingsrendement, en door verwaarding van overige outputstromen zoals hoge druk biogene CO₂ dat kan worden ingezet voor de realisatie van negatieve CO₂-emissies.

(Leguijt et al., 2018, p. 8)

Digestate

Digestate is the biomass that remains in in the digester after the digestion process. In conventional co-digestors, digestate accounts for about 90% of the starting products' mass (Hoeksma, 2013). To be able to use digestate however, additional washing steps could be required to be able to apply it as a fertilizer (spreading over fields), as a substitute for peat, and/ or potting soil.

- "The N/P ratio in digestate can differ significantly from that in animal manure because co-products often contain much less P than animal manure." (Hoeksma, 2013) "The properties of digestate are globally comparable to those of animal manure."
- *Nutrients:*

Tabel 1: Nutriëntengehalten in rundveedrijfmest en vergiste rundveedrijfmest en in de dikke en dunne fracties na scheiding met een vijzelpers (Verloop et al, 2009)

Mest(fractie)	Stikstofgehalte (N) g/kg	Fosfaatgehalte (P ₂ O ₅) g/kg	Kaligehalte (K ₂ O) g/kg
A drijfmest	3,4	1,0	5,7
A dikke fractie	4,0	1,9	4,8
A dunne fractie	3,2	0,8	5,6
B vergiste drijfmest	3,5	1,0	6,0
B dikke fractie	4,5	3,6	5,2
B dunne fractie	3,1	0,7	5,6

(Hoeksma, 2013, p. 9)

Tabel 3: Samenstelling (in g/kg) van de fracties uit **vergiste varkensdrijfmest** voor en na scheiding met een centrifuge en een vijzelpers (De Buissonjé en Smolders, 2002)

	Dr. stof	Org. stof	N-totaal	N-NH ₃	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O
Centrifuge						
Ingaande vergiste drijfmest	41	23	5,2	3,6	1,5	4,8
Dikke fractie	270	190	9,2	5,1	17,2	4,8
Dunne fractie	26	13	4,7	3,5	0,4	4,7
Vijzelpers						
Ingaande vergiste drijfmest	38	23	5,2	3,7	1,3	4,9
Dikke fractie	240	210	7,8	4,1	4,8	5,1
Dunne fractie	34	18	5,0	3,7	1,2	4,9

(Hoeksma, 2013, p. 11)

As a by-product of animal manure digestion, digestate can substitute conventional mineral fertilisers. The emission footprint of digestate depends on the total attribution of GHG emissions that are released during the complete life cycle of the anaerobic digestion process. (Timonen, Sinkko, Luostarinen, Tampio, & Joensuu, 2019) conducted a respective LCA considering the life cycle of AD including feedstock procurement, digestion, storage of feedstocks and digestate, energy use (in CHP) and digestate fertiliser use. They conclude that life cycle emissions of the digestate by-product are less compared to the emissions of mineral fertilisers (8.2-10.6 kg CO₂ eq/kg N and 11.7 kg CO₂ eq/kg N respectively). Costs associated to avoid GHG emissions can be zero if digestate is a by-product and all costs are attributed to the production of biogas. Otherwise, a wholistic analysis of the AD process is required to attribute costs to digestate and biogas, respectively.

- *“The sale of digestate is a significant cost item (up to 40% of the production costs of biogas) which weighs heavily on the economic efficiency of many co-digestion installations.”* (Hoeksma, 2013)

Carbon Capture and storage

CCS

Carbon capture and storage (CCS) is a mature technology that can nowadays be applied at an industrial scale. The stored carbon in the biogas stream can be captured at different stages of the value chain, dependent on the final intended use of the produced biogas and technology choice:

- 1) Pre-combustion capture: To be able to feed biogas in the natural gas grid, it needs to be upgraded to a respective quality. As part of this process, CO₂ needs to be removed and can be stored subsequently. It, therefore, qualifies as pre-combustion carbon capture.
- 2) Post-combustion capture: For power and heat generation in CHPs, it is not mandatory to upgrade biogas to biomethane, but biogas can be combusted directly. After biogas is combusted, the emitted CO₂ can be captured from the exhaust gas.

- 3) Oxy-fuel combustion capture: In this process, biogas is burnt in a nitrogen-free environment using pure oxygen. The CO₂ can be simply captured by separating water from the exhaust gas (CO₂+H₂O) via condensation of water (moisture).

Strengers et al. (2018) mention costs of 70-80 EUR/ tonne CO₂ captured including onshore transport. This is an estimate for large (manure) digesters of more than 1,000 m³ / h. The same source also states costs for transport and storage at sea with 7.5-13.5 €/ton CO₂.

So far, there are no CCS applications for biogas production. However, there are possibilities to capture CO₂ during the upgrading process of biogas, and to capture CO₂ from flue gases of biogas combustion. The economic feasibility depends on the value of avoided CO₂ emissions, and/ or the value of further CO₂ utilization. For instance, greenhouses are a large consumer of CO₂. Currently, the greenhouse gas operators combust natural gas to generate CO₂ for internal use as a stimulus for plant growth. With increasing gas and CO₂ prices, one may consider compressing CO₂ from biogas/biomethane instead and transporting it in bottles to the greenhouses as an alternative to natural gas.

3.4.6 Co-benefits and trade-offs

Negative impacts

To be profitable, manure digesters on farms should be installed at larger farms with livestock permanently stabled. Larger farms and fewer cattle in meadows harm the landscape (van der Schans, Rougoor, & van der Weijden, 2020).

Some studies suggest that the **emission of nitrogen by digestate is less** compared to untreated manure, so that nearby nature areas suffer less from nitrogen deposition **and biodiversity is increased** (Bertora et al., 2008; van der Schans et al., 2020). On the other hand, Lesschen et al. (2021) find that the risk of N₂O emissions is comparable to slurry. Also, if manure digesters are linked with permanently stabled cows practice less **meadow manure** is produced. This meadow manure acts as a microhabitat for insects that are feed for (meadow) birds (van der Schans et al., 2020).

If the digestate is applied early in the year (February) on the land, nitrogen leaching towards ground and surface water may occur, with deteriorating effects on the water quality (Praktijkonderzoek Plant & Omgeving B.V. - Wageningen Universiteit en Researchcentrum, 2008).

Co-benefits

The application of manure in digesters contributes to solving the longstanding problem of surplus manure in the Netherlands. Also, the digestate by-product can substitute mineral fertilisers which have a higher CO₂ footprint (Timonen, Sinkko, Luostarinen, Tampio, & Joensuu, 2019).

Trade-offs

The main trade-off is related to the solution of the problem of surplus manure and the costs of manure digestion. In the end, large scale manure digesting, linked to regulations on the use of digestate, could

prevent a reduction of the livestock population if such a large-scale manure processing could be realized at relatively low costs.

3.4.7 Risks associated with scaling-up

The LMT can easily be applied in the whole country, as farms at which manure digesters can be installed are in all parts of the country. As mentioned previously, the main risk of scaling up CCS based on bioenergy is the supply of large-scale sustainable biomass. For manure based BECCS, policies towards scaling down fattening farms impact the supply of manure for digesters.¹²

3.4.8 Research gaps

Research gaps refer to a lack of knowledge of enabling factors for farmers to apply manure digestion and a lack of insight into the costs of manure digestion.

¹² <https://nos.nl/artikel/2372685-einde-lijkt-in-zicht-voor-huidige-kalvermesterij-in-nederland.html>

4. Bibliography

- CE-Delft. (2022). *Bijmengverplichting groen gas; Ontwerptopties en effectenanalyse*. Delft: CE Delft.
- Daatselaar, C., & Prins, H. (2020). *Vernatting Groene Hart: kostprijs melk en CO2-prijs*. Wageningen: Wageningen Economic Research.
- Dutch Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality. (2020). *Actieprogramma klimaatadaptatie landbouw*. The Hague: Het ministerie van Landbouw, Natuur en Voedselkwaliteit.
- European Commission. (2018). *A Clean Planet for all - A European strategic long-term vision for a prosperous, modern, competitive and climate neutral economy*. Brussels: European Commission: COM(2018) 773 final.
- European Commission. (2020). *Stepping up Europe's 2030 climate ambition - Investing in a climate-neutral future for the benefit of our people*. Brussels: European Commission.
- EZK. (2022). *Blending obligation green gas (Bijmengverplichting groen gas)*. The Hague: Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate.
- Geden, O., & Schenuit, F. (2020). *Unconventional Mitigation - Carbon Dioxide Removal as a New Approach in EU Climate Policy*. Berlin, Germany: German Institute for International and Security Affairs SWP.
- Government. (2019). *Klimaatakkoord*. The Hague: Dutch Government.
- Government, D. (2019). *Klimaatakkoord*. The Hague: Rijksoverheid.
- Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). (2018). *Special Report 1.5-Global Warming of 1.5°C*. Geneva: IPCC.
- International Energy Agency. (2020). *Outlook for biogas and biomethane - Prospects for organic growth*. IEA.
- IPCC. (2023). *AR6 Synthesis Report; Climate Change 2023*. IPCC.
- Jepma, C., van Leeuwen, C., & Hulshof, D. (2017). *Store&Go D8.1 Exploring the future for green gases*.
- Julema, G., Ramaekers, P., & Berkhout, P. (2020). *De Nederlandse agrarische sector in internationaal verband*. Wageningen Economic Research - Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek.
- Karel, E. G. (2015). The history of the peat manufacturing industry in The Netherlands: peat moss litter and active carbon. *Mires and Peat*, 1-9.
- LNV. (2020). *Bos voor de toekomst: Uitwerking ambities en doelen landelijke Bossenstrategie en beleidsagenda 2030*. Ministry of Agriculture and Interprovinciaal Overleg.

LNV. (2020). *Veenplan 1e fase - Kamerbrief aan de Voorzitter van de Tweede Kamer der Staten-Generaal*. The Hague: Dutch Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality.

PBL. (2021). *Monitor RES 1.0. Een analyse van de Regionale Energie Strategieën 1.0*. Den Haag: Planbureau voor de Leefomgeving.

Praktijkonderzoek Plant & Omgeving B.V. - Wageningen Universiteit en Researchcentrum. (2008). *Digestaat - Voor u en het milieu het beste resultaat*. Lelystad: Praktijkonderzoek Plant & Omgeving B.V. - Wageningen Universiteit en Researchcentrum.

Rijksoverheid. (2014, July 23). *Compendium voor de Leefomgeving*. Retrieved from Eigendom van bossen, 1975-2012: <https://www.clo.nl/indicatoren/nl1262-eigendom-van-bossen#:~:text=Circa%2055%25%20van%20het%20bos,circa%2045%25%20is%20privaatrechtelijk%20bosbezit.>

Rijksoverheid. (2022). *Startnotitie Nationaal Programma Landelijk Gebied (NPLG)*.

RIVM. (2021). *Greenhouse gas emissions in the Netherlands 1990 - 2019; National Inventory Report 2021*. RIVM.

RLI. (2020). *Stop bodemdaling in de veenweidegebieden. Het Groene Hart als voorbeeld*. The Hague: Raad voor de leefomgeving en de infrastructuur (RLI).

Schouten, C. (2020). *Kamerbrief - Veenplan 1e fase*. The Hague: Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality.

Schouten, C. (2020). *Veenplan 1e fase*. Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food quality.

SER. (2020). *Biomassa in balans: Een duurzaamheidskader voor hoogwaardige inzet van biograndstoffen*. Sociaal-Economische Raad.

SER. (2020). *Biomassa in balans: Een duurzaamheidskader voor hoogwaardige inzet van biograndstoffen*.

Sikkema, R. (2020). Nederlandse bosegenaar ervaart gevolgen klimaatverandering en pleit voor steun. *Vakblad Natuur Bos Landschap*, 17(169), 18-23.

Smolders, A., van de Riet, B., van Diggelen, J., van Dijk, G., Geurts, J., & Lamers, L. (2019). De toekomst van ons veenweidelandschap - Over vernatten, optoppen en veenmosteelt. *Landschap*, 36(3), 133-141.

Statline, C. (2020). *Landbouw; gewassen, dieren en grondgebruik naar regio*. CBS.

Stenzel, F., Greve, P., Lucht, W., Tramberend, S., & Wada, Y. (2021). Irrigation of biomass plantations may globally increase water stress more than climate change. *Nature Communications*.

Strengers B., H. E. (2018). *NEGATIEVE EMISSIES. Technisch potentieel, realistisch potentieel en kosten voor Nederland*. Den Haag: PBL.

Strengers, & Elzenga. (2020). *Availability and applications of sustainable biomass*. PBL.

Strengers, B., Eerens, H., Smeets, W., van den Born, G. J., & Ros, J. (2018). *Negatieve emissies- Technisch potentieel, realistisch potentieel en kosten voor Nederland*. Planbureau voor de Leefomgeving (PBL) .

Timonen, K., Sinkko, T., Luostarinen, S., Tampio, E., & Joensuu, K. (2019). LCA of anaerobic digestion: Emission allocation for energy and digestate. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 235, 1567-1579.

Tol-Leenders et. al. (2019). *Koolstofvoorraad in de bodem van Nederland (1998-2018)*. Wageningen Environmental Research & Eurofins.

van der Schans, F., Rougoor, C., & van der Weijden, W. (2020). *Duurzaamheidseffecten van stikstof- en klimaatmaatregelen voor de landbouw; De scores van 18 stikstof- en klimaatmaatregelen voor de landbouw op 15 duurzaamheidscriteria bepaald en in beeld gebracht*. Culemborg: CLM, publication nr. 1038.

Verhagen, F., Westerhof, R., & de Weerd, M. (2020). *Betaalbaarheid van maatregelen in het veengebied*. Amersfoort: HaskoningDHV Nederland B.V.

Wiebes, E. (2020). *Kamerbrief - Routekaart Groen Gas*. Den Haag: Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate.

Akerboom, S., Waldmann, S., Mukherjee, A., Agaton, C., Sanders, M., & Kramer, G. J. (2021). Different This Time? The Prospects of CCS in the Netherlands in the 2020s. *Frontiers in Energy Research*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenrg.2021.644796>

Bertora, C., Alluvione, F., Zavattaro, L., van Groenigen, J. W., Velthof, G., & Grignani, C. (2008). Pig slurry treatment modifies slurry composition, N₂O, and CO₂ emissions after soil incorporation. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 40(8), 1999–2006. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2008.03.021>

de Buissonjé, F., & Verheijen, R. (2014). Drijfmest verliest snel zijn waarde voor biogas. *V-focus, April 2014*, 20–21.

den Herder, M., Moreno, G., Mosquera-Losada, M. R., Palma, J., Sidiropoulou, A., Santiago-Freijanes, J., Crous-Duran, J., Paulo, J., Tomé, M., Pantera, A., Papanastasis, V., Mantzanas, K., Pachana, P., Papadopoulos, A., Plieninger, T., & Burgess, P. (2017). Current extent and stratification of agroforestry in the European Union. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 241, 121–132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2017.03.005>

Dollinger, J., & Jose, S. (2018). Agroforestry for soil health. *Agroforestry Systems*, 92(2), 213–219. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-018-0223-9>

Dutch State Secretary for Economic Affairs. (2017). *Regulation of the State Secretary for Economic Affairs of 8 February 2017, no. WJZ/16191070, containing a subsidy scheme to support dairy farmers who terminate their business (Subsidy Scheme cessation of dairy farming)*. Government of the Netherlands. <https://zoek.officielebekendmakingen.nl/stcrt-2017-7933.html>

Hammingh, P., Daniels, B., Koutstaal, P., Schure, K., Hekkenberg, M., & Menkveld, M. (2020). *Netherlands Climate and Energy Outlook 2020—Summary* (No. 4299; p. 18). PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency. <https://www.pbl.nl/sites/default/files/downloads/pbl-2020-netherlands-climate-and-energy-outlook-2020-summary-4299.pdf>

Hoeksma, P. (2013). *Verwerking van digestaat uit co-vergisting* (PPO-564; p. 28). ACRRES - Wageningen UR. <https://edepot.wur.nl/273735>

Hoving, I. E., Holshof, G. J., Evers, A. G., & de Haan, M. H. A. (2015). *Ammoniakemissie en weidegang melkvee* (Livestock Research Rapport 856; p. 49). Wageningen UR Livestock Research.

IEA. (2020). *Outlook for biogas and biomethane: Prospects for organic growth*. IEA. <https://www.iea.org/reports/outlook-for-biogas-and-biomethane-prospects-for-organic-growth>

Interprovinciaal Overleg, & Ministerie van Landbouw, Natuur en Voedselkwaliteit. (2020). *Bos voor de toekomst—Uitwerking ambities en doelen landelijke Bossenstrategie en beleidsagenda 2030*. Ministerie van Landbouw, Natuur en Voedselkwaliteit; Publicatie-nr. 1120-001. <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/documenten/kamerstukken/2020/11/18/uitwerking-ambities-en-doelen-landelijke-bossenstrategie-en-beleidsagenda-2030>

Kay, S., Graves, A., Palma, J. H. N., Moreno, G., Roces-Díaz, J. V., Aviron, S., Chouvardas, D., Crous-Duran, J., Ferreiro-Domínguez, N., García de Jalón, S., Măcicășan, V., Mosquera-Losada, M. R., Pantera, A., Santiago-Freijanes, J. J., Szerencsits, E., Torralba, M., Burgess, P. J., & Herzog, F. (2019). Agroforestry is paying off – Economic evaluation of ecosystem services in European landscapes with and without agroforestry systems. *Ecosystem Services*, 36, 100896. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2019.100896>

Leguijt, C., Kruit, K., & Rooijers, F. (2018). *Contouren en instrumenten voor een Routekaart Groengas 2020-2050* (Publicatienummer: 18.5T20.147). CE Delft. https://groengas.nl/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/CE_Delft_5T20_Contouren_instrumenten_Routekaart_Groengas_2020-2050_Def.pdf

Lensink, K., & Schoots (red.), K. (2021). *Eindadvies basisbedragen SDE++ 2021* (PBL-publicatienummer: 4032). PBL. https://www.pbl.nl/sites/default/files/downloads/pbl-2021-eindadvies-basisbedragen-sde-plus-plus-2021_4032.pdf

Lesschen, J. P., Hendriks, C., Slier, T., Porre, R., Velthof, G., & Rietra, R. (2021). *De potentie voor koolstofvastlegging in de Nederlandse landbouw*. Wageningen Environmental Research. <https://doi.org/10.18174/557330>

Luske, B., Bestman, M., van Veluw, K., Prins, E., & Rombouts, P. (2020). *Masterplan Agroforestry* (No. 2020-017 LbD; p. 42). Louis Bolk Instituut.

Ministerie van Economische Zaken en Klimaat. (2019). *National Climate Agreement—The Netherlands—Publicatie—Klimaatakkoord*. Ministerie van Economische Zaken en Klimaat. <https://www.klimaatakkoord.nl/documenten/publicaties/2019/06/28/national-climate-agreement-the-netherlands>

Ministerie van Landbouw, Natuur en Voedselkwaliteit. (2018). *Landbouw, natuur en voedsel: Waardevol en verbonden - Nederland als koploper in kringlooplandbouw* - [Richtlijn]. Ministerie van Algemene Zaken. <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/documenten/richtlijnen/2018/09/01/landbouw-natuur-en-voedsel-waardevol-en-verbonden-nederland-als-koploper-in-kringlooplandbouw>

Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy. (2022). *Kamerbrief over bijmengverplichting groen gas* [Kamerstuk]. Ministerie van Algemene Zaken. <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/documenten/kamerstukken/2022/07/01/bijmengverplichting-groen-gas>

Mosquera-Losada, M. R., McAdam, J. H., Romero-Franco, R., Santiago-Freijanes, J. J., & Rigueiro-Rodríguez, A. (2009). Definitions and Components of Agroforestry Practices in Europe. In A. Rigueiro-Rodríguez, J. McAdam, & M. R. Mosquera-Losada (Eds.), *Agroforestry in Europe: Current Status and Future Prospects* (pp. 3–19). Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-8272-6_1

Netherlands Enterprise Agency. (2021, July 27). *Technieken vergisting*. Vergisting en vergassing. <https://www.rvo.nl/onderwerpen/bio-energie/vergisting-en-vergassing/technieken#downloads>

Ontario Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Rural Affairs. (2021, February 13). *Energy Yields from a Farm-Based Anaerobic Digestion System*. <http://www.omafra.gov.on.ca/english/engineer/facts/enyields.htm>

Oosterbaan, A., & Kuiters, A. T. (2009). Agroforestry in the Netherlands. In *Agroforestry in Europe: Current Status and Future Prospects* (pp. 331–342). Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-8272-6_1

Paulin, M. J., Koopman, K. R., Melman, R. R., Kok, S., De Knecht, B., Lof, M. E., & de Nijs, T. (2022). *Ruimtelijke MKBA Alblasserwaard-Vijfheerenlanden Waar is toepassing van drukdrainage maatschappelijk gezien rendabel?* (RIVM-rapport 2022-0090). Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu. <https://www.rivm.nl/publicaties/ruimtelijke-mkba-alblasserwaard-vijfheerenlanden-waar-is-toepassing-van-drukdrainage>

RVO. (2022, April 6). *SDE(+)(+) Projecten in beheer april 2022 (Excel document)*. Feiten En Cijfers SDE(+)(+). <https://www.rvo.nl/sites/default/files/2022-04/SDE-plus-projecten-in-beheer-april-3-2022.xlsx>

Spijker, E., Anger-Kraavi, A., Pollitt, H., & van de Ven, D.-J. (2020). Evaluating integrated impacts of low-emission transitions in the livestock sector. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 35, 482–492. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2019.11.003>

Statline. (2021, December 13). *StatLine—Agriculture—Manure production*. Regionale kerncijfers Nederland.

<https://opendata.cbs.nl/#/CBS/nl/dataset/70072ned/table?searchKeywords=mestproductie>

Strootman, B., Groot, R., & van den Wittenboer, S. (2020). *Landschap versterken met bomen en bos—Advies voor het ontwikkelen van een Bossenstrategie*. College van Rijksadviseurs.

<https://www.collegevanrijksadviseurs.nl/actueel/nieuws/2020/08/27/bossenstrategie>

van der Schans, F., Rougoor, C., & van der Weijden, W. (2020). *Duurzaamheidseffecten van stikstof- en klimaatmaatregelen voor de landbouw; De scores van 18 stikstof- en klimaatmaatregelen voor de landbouw op 15 duurzaamheidscriteria bepaald en in beeld gebracht* (Publication nr. 1038.). CLM.

https://www.clm.nl/uploads/pdf/1038-CLMrapport-Matrix_stikstof_klimaat_maatregelen.pdf

van der Veen, R., Naber, N., & Leguijt, C. (2020). *Potentieel van lokale biomassa en invoedlocaties van groengas—Een verkenning voor 2030* (20.190281.008). CE Delft.

https://www.netbeheernederland.nl/_upload/Files/Verkenning_biomassa-reststromen_potentieel_voor_2030_164.pdf

5. Annex I: Additional information for the national narratives

Table 5-1: Overview of recent agroforestry projects and experiments in the Netherlands

Agroforestry project/ practitioner	Location	Type of agroforestry				Covered area [ha]
		Silvopastoral	Silvoarable	Mix	n.a.	
Farm P. Hermus	North Brabant		X			53
Manders-Selten V.O.F.					X	2.5
Hillekens Hoeve				X		1
Expertisecentrum Agroforestry		X				1
de Kort-van der Hamsvoord V.O.F.					X	2
Janmiekeshoeve					X	35
Lex Verbeek		X				7
De Ruurhoeve					X	2
Bioboerderij het Schop					X	2
Hoeve de Mertel		X				8
Maatschap Keijzers				X		4
Ecologische Tuinderij De Weitens				X		5
BoerInNatuur					X	23
van Haperen C&T				X		2
Gertjan Tijssen		X				2
Sprankenhof				X		3
Hanne Hoeve		X				4
Farmlife ¹³				X	31.8	
Proeftuin Lettele	Overijssel	X				1
Notengaard Bisschop			X			5.5
Boerendiekhuus		X				1
Weerwoud/Utopia	Flevoland				X	1.4
Pluktuin van Geesje	North- Holland				X	2
De Fruittuin van West	North- Holland				X	4.5
de Dennenhoeve	Drenthe	X				2
Oosterbierum	Friesland		X			3
Total	27 locations	8 (26 ha)	8 (74.5 ha)	9 (103.7 ha)	1 (2.5 ha)	208.8

¹³ Based on internal information on the sites in Drimmelen, St Oetenrode and Alphen

In the general context of the historic and projected Dutch greenhouse gas emissions, the agricultural and land-use sectors contribute to the total GHG emissions by about 17% or 31 Mton CO₂-eq in 2019 (Hammingh et al., 2020). According to current policies, these emissions are expected to decrease by about 0.8-4.5 Mton CO₂-eq in 2030, 0.4-0.6 Mton CO₂ reduction per year are attributed to agricultural soils (Lesschen et al., 2021). In comparison, the bear share of the emission reductions yet to come by 2030 is planned in the area of power generation with a reduction of 17-31.2 Mt CO₂eq. Projections also show that the self-set goals (-49% in 2030) will not be met (projected -34% in 2030) with the current measures being in place. Efforts will need to be increased in all sectors including the agricultural and land-use sectors.

LANDMARC

**SCALING LAND-BASED MITIGATION
SOLUTIONS IN PORTUGAL
LAND-BASED MITIGATION NARRATIVE CO-DESIGN**

PATRÍCIA LOURENÇO AND JOSÉ RAFAEL MARQUES DA SILVA
STATUS: PUBLIC

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2. Introduction

This report includes a description of a generic nation-wide transition scenario for the implementation of land-based mitigation technologies and practices for the AFOLU sector (agriculture, forestry, and other land use sectors) in Portugal. The report shows the outcomes of a series of research steps that have been conducted in this country since the start of the project in June 2020 until the end of 2022.

First, we performed an initial scoping of key LMTs in the case study country. The scoping assessment resulted in a long list of broad portfolios of different LMTs that could be viable within the various case study countries.

Second, following this long list, we developed a short-list LMT portfolio containing key LMTs that would be the most relevant for a given country context. All case study country partners were asked to propose and validate their LMT portfolio through complementary (policy) literature review and with the help of stakeholder interviews (i.e., external validation by relevant country experts and stakeholders). AgroInsider held online meetings and interviews (due to the COVID-19 pandemic) and participated in international conferences and academic circles to engage and understand stakeholders views regarding the LMT portfolio. The list of stakeholders includes Portuguese and Spanish pastures associations, small and large national private actors from pastures, agriculture (e.g., wine production), agroforestry (e.g., Montado and Dehesa) and forestry (e.g., eucalyptus production for paper pulp) systems. Ex-ante no specific guidance of criteria for LMT portfolio short-listing was provided to allow for a free and open co-design process with stakeholders. The scoping process and results are presented in section **Error! Reference source not found.** of this report (step 1 & 2).

Third, after the short-listed LMT portfolios were validated, the LANDMARC case study country partners were asked to develop national scaling narratives or storylines for each LMT included in their portfolio. The assessments focus on climate risks, vulnerabilities as well as socio-economic co-benefits and trade-offs associated with upscaling LMTs in the case study countries. The analysis is based on a broad range of information/literature sources, and stakeholder consultations conducted. This process is supported through a risk and impact assessment (i.e., an online survey and workshops/seminar/webinars) conducted through the LANDMARC tasks 4.1, 4.2 and 5.2. The results of this analysis are a set of LMT narratives which are presented in section **Error! Reference source not found.** of this report.

The research steps are designed to enable both an **analysis of the risks and (climate) impacts of scaling up land-based mitigation and negative emission solutions**. As such this report mainly contributes to objectives 2, 3 and 4 of the six LANDMARC key objectives (see **Error! Reference source not found.**).

Table 1: LANDMARC project objectives.

	Project key objectives
1	Determine the potential and effectiveness of LMTs in GHGs mitigation using Earth Observation (EO)
2	Improve climate resilience of LMT solutions at the local level for large-scale implementation
3	Assess the risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs of scaling up local LMTs nationally

4	Scaling up LMT solutions to the continental and global level to assess effectiveness
5	Improve current methodologies to estimate emissions and removals for LMTs
6	LMT capacity building and develop new tools and services for decision making

While the results shown in this report represent a mostly qualitative storyline describing the context and impact of scaling up LMTs in a country context, they also enable project partners to proceed with the translation of the outcomes in a manner so that they can serve as direct model input.

Furthermore, these national level assessments provide a testing ground and empirical basis for the continental, and global assessment of the realistic scaling potential of land-based mitigation and negative emission solutions implemented in Work Packages 6 and 7 of the LANDMARC project (**Objective 4**).

3. Scoping of land-based mitigation solutions in Portugal

3.1 Overview of potential of LMTs in Portugal

3.1.1 Introduction

Portugal is a country with a proven track record of climate policy, being one of the 14 countries in the European Union (EU) with the best performance in effective emissions of Greenhouse Gases (GHG) that have met the objectives defined in the targets of the Kyoto Protocol, as well as the 2020 targets for reducing emissions, energy efficiency and promoting renewable energy sources.

According to the World Bank in the period 1990-2019, total Portuguese GHG emissions in kt of CO₂ equivalent are composed of CO₂ totals excluding short-cycle biomass burning (such as agricultural waste burning and Savannah burning) but including other biomass burning (such as forest fires, post-burn decay, peat fires and decay of drained peatlands), all anthropogenic CH₄ sources, N₂O sources and F-gases (HFCs, PFCs and SF₆) were estimated at about 61.4 MtCO₂eq in 2019, representing an increase of 9.20% compared to 1990 levels and a decrease of 7.60% compared to 2018 (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Evolution of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in Portugal between 1990 and 2019 (ktCO₂eq). Source: <https://www.macrotrends.net/countries/PRT/portugal/ghg-greenhouse-gas-emissions>. Retrieved 2022-10-26.

During the 1990s, there was a steady increase in Portuguese emissions associated with the increase in energy demand and mobility, followed by a period of stagnation in the early 2000s and recession between 2011 and 2013, and recovery since then (Figure 1). The emission stabilisation/reduction trends started before the crisis (2005) as a result of technological improvements in pollution control systems and energy efficiency; of the introduction of less polluting fuels, with emphasis on natural gas from the late 1990s onwards; of the significant growth of energy produced from renewable sources (with special emphasis on wind); of the implementation of waste management measures, aimed at the

increase of selective deposition; of reuse and recycling; and of the energy recovery of biogas generated in the waste management systems (Figure 2). In 2017, the strong growth is related to the forest fires that occurred in the tragic year of 2017, a situation associated with a particularly dry year, with high temperatures occurring outside the summer period (June and October), and with unusually strong winds, such as the Hurricane Ophelia that swept the coast of the Iberian Peninsula in October 2017. In 2018, the Forest resumed its role as a natural GHG sink with a sequestration of 6,287 kt of CO_{2eq} (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) in Portugal between 1990 and 2018. LULUCF: Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry. UNFCCC: United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change.

Figure 3. Greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) by emission sector in Portugal between 1990 and 2018. LULUCF: Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry. UNFCCC: United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change.

In order to guarantee the neutrality of its emissions until the end of 2050, the Portuguese government elaborated a Carbon Neutrality Roadmap (RNC2050, 2019) to reduce emissions from -45% to -55% by 2030, -55% to -65% in 2040 and -85% to -90% by 2050, compared to the 2005, assuming a carbon sink

value of between -9 and -13 MtCO₂ (Figure 4). To achieve these objectives, all sectors will have to contribute, either by reducing their emissions or by increasing their carbon sink capacity.

Figure 4. Emissions reduction trajectory from 85% to 90% by 2050 compared to 2005. The emissions trajectory includes net emissions from agriculture and agricultural lands, considering their carbon sink role. The value of the carbon sink does not include this component for pastures and other agricultural lands. Source: RNC2050, 2019.

3.1.2 Technologies dependent on biomass / photosynthesis

BECCS and Biochar

In Portugal, Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS) and biochar are not commonly used techniques for negative carbon emissions. Most of the Portuguese forests are for commercial forestry purposes (e.g., pulp, timber, fruit extraction). However, biomass is emerging as one of the decarbonization vectors whose consumption will grow until 2030/35, subsequently dropping to lower levels than the current ones, with the emergence or increase of other more competitive energy vectors. It is in the industrial sector that the consumption of biomass is most evident, replacing, among other sources, petroleum coke.

Instead, Portuguese policy for negative carbon emissions has focused on alternative resources, such as, solar (centralized and decentralized), wind (onshore and offshore) and hydroelectric (with and without pumping) energies. Photovoltaic solar technology will be most clearly established by increasing its importance and reaching 13 GW centralized and 13 GW decentralized by 2050. Onshore wind energy is also increasing its share significantly (almost 2.5x). These two technologies have a cost-effective potential to jointly supply 50% of the electricity generated in 2030 and 70% in 2050. Hydroelectric production using pumped water will also continue to play an important role in regulating the power system which will have a pumped hydroelectric capacity of 3.4 GW in 2030.

3.1.3 Land management practices

The evolution of emissions associated with agriculture and forests in Portugal is highly dependent on the introduction of structural changes and the types of management used for example, the evolution of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) (Table 2 and Figure 5). Since 1990, forests have remained stabilized, having operated as a liquid sink with annual values ranging between -6.1 MtCO₂eq and -15.4 MtCO₂eq. Land-use changes have been occurring in the Portuguese forests between different forest types, i.e., conversion of one type of forest into another (e.g., changes from *Pinus pinaster* to *Eucalyptus* sp.) or changes in dominant species in mixed forests. Other land uses, including forests, can significantly increase current sequestration levels to around 11-13 million tons of CO₂, and for this to happen, it is essential to control areas set on fire annually and to achieve productivity increases across forestry species in general (RNC2050, 2019).

Table 2. Evolution of emissions/sequestrations of the agriculture, forests and other land uses sector in Portugal. Source: RNC2050, 2019.

AGRICULTURE, FORESTS AND OTHER LAND USES	2005	2015	2020	2030	2040	2050	Δ 2050/2005
TOTAL AFOLU	8.25	-1.69	3.01	-2.84 -4.55	-4.21 -7.02	-5.73 -9.44	-169% -214%
Agriculture	6.77	6.79	6.79	6.42 6.3	6.33 5.52	6.19 4.74	-9% -30%
Enteric Fermentation	3.6	3.57	3.57	3.39 3.32	3.41 2.99	3.43 2.69	-5% -25%
Livestock Effluent Management	0.92	0.91	0.91	0.89 0.88	0.83 0.77	0.77 0.66	-17% -29%
Rice Production	0.15	0.14	0.14	0.13	0.13	0.12 0.13	-19% -12%
Agricultural Lands	2.02	2.07	2.07	1.89 1.85	1.84 1.52	1.75 1.12	-13% -44%
Burning of Agricultural Waste	0.05	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.07 0.06	0.06	21%
Liming	0.03	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.06	0.07	136%
Land Uses	1.48	-8.48	-3.78	-9.25 -10.85	-10.54 -12.54	-11.92 -14.18	-903% -1055%
Forested Land	-2.22	-11.4	-8.67	-12.7 -13.51	-14.03 -15.01	-15.4 -16.45	592% 640%
Agricultural Land	1.36	0.63	0.8	0.63 0.62	0.62 0.59	0.61 0.56	-55% -59%
Pastures	1.7	0.13	0.13	-0.75 -0.89	-0.73 -1.11	-0.69 -1.32	-141% -178%
Wetlands	0.43	0.43	0.37	0.38	0.39	0.39	-8%
Urban land	1.95	2.64	2.18	2.30	2.36 2.34	2.4 2.37	23% 21%
Scrubland and other land uses	-1.73	-0.9	1.41	0.88 0.26	0.85 0.27	0.77 0.28	-144% -116%
Agriculture, agricultural land and pasture	9.83	7.55	7.72	6.3 6.02	6.22 4.99	6.11 3.98	-38% -60%
Forest and other land uses	-1.58	-9.24	-4.71	-9.14 -10.57	-10.43 -12.01	-11.84 -13.42	651% 751%

Unit: Mt CO₂e

Figure 5. Evolution of emissions of the agricultural, forest and other land uses sector in Portugal between 2005 and 2050. Source: RNC2050, 2019.

In Portugal, carbon sinks are the result of some land uses, notably in agriculture, pastures, forests and scrubland, which between 2007 and 2017 absorbed from the atmosphere about -8.5 MtCO₂ (from -13 to +7 MtCO₂), or about -12% of the emissions from the other sectors. However, the size of the national carbon sink varies greatly between years, mainly due to the influence of the rural fires each year.

Afforestation

In mainland Portugal, about 35% of the total area is forest composed of four predominant forests: i) planted forests, with the objective of producing wood, in particular maritime pine (*Pinus pinaster*); ii) Montados, of native species such as cork oak (*Quercus suber*), holm oak (*Quercus ilex*) and stone pine (*Pinus pinea*), where agroforestry is inserted; iii) forests of natural regeneration, a relatively recent phase and started with the abandonment of agricultural areas; iv) intensive forestry, with exploration in a short rotation coppice system, where the eucalyptus allotone is the main species.

Over the past 60 years, reforestation with native holm oak, cork oak and stone pine species has taken place in Portugal due to the important role played by native trees, in contrast to the clear negative impacts of planted species. However, it is necessary to know the land use before reforestation since the carbon stocks associated with each land use can be very different (Table 3). For example, cork oak forestation is a much better carbon uptake mitigation option when previous land use was agriculture or pasture, and a relatively poor option in replacing other types of forest.

Table 3. Emissions associated with afforestation with cork oak, depending on previous land-use in Portugal.

Land Use before afforestation with cork oak	Emission associated with afforestation tCO ₂ /ha	Years before new cork oak forest offsets initial emission
<i>Pinus pinaster</i>	110	47
<i>Eucalyptus</i> spp.	81	35

<i>Quercus rotundifolia</i>	49	21
<i>Quercus</i> spp.	75	32
Other broadleaves	162	69
<i>Pinus pinea</i>	74	32
Other conifers	60	26
Non-irrigated annual crops	2	1
Irrigated annual crops	2	1
Rice paddies	2	1
Vineyards	23	10
Olive groves	33	114
Other permanent crops	36	16
Grassland	5	2
Shrubland	50	22

In addition, afforestation in Portugal has been occurring mainly through eucalyptus plantation, an exotic, highly invasive, fast-growing subtropical tree that can be harvested and sold, whether for bioenergy, pulp, and wood pellet industry. Portugal leads Europe statistic of being the EU country with more land planted with eucalyptus (10% of Portugal's area). Eucalyptus represents an important source of national wealth which removes large amounts of carbon from the atmosphere, with a reduction prospecting of 180 000 tons of CO₂ per year. Eucalyptus has the capacity to assimilate up to almost 9 tonCO₂/ha/year, three times as much as that verified in the cork oak and holm oak. The renewal of the forest is done in cycles of 12 years (from planting to harvesting the tree) leading to a replacement of part of this carbon, the eucalyptus forest allows a significant increase in stocks carbon in the forest and in the soil, in the form of long-term organic matter. However, such tree plantations bring serious environmental and social impacts. Despite concerns over the impacts of eucalyptus plantations in Portugal, some communities physically uprooted eucalyptus plantations almost three decades ago, citing concerns about fires and the drying up of springs. Furthermore, the strength of the pulp and paper lobby and the large-scale migration away from rural areas have left the slopes abandoned, with landowners turning to eucalyptus as an easy way to make a small profit from land that would otherwise go unused.

Furthermore, Portuguese forests have a major problem with fires and average annual burned area due to poor management and planning, and to the extreme weather events that are occurring more frequently. To fight against this problem, greater investment is needed in the management of plots for the prevention and fighting of fires, including new afforestation and reforestation with production species (cork oak, pine and eucalyptus) or with protection and conservation species (native hardwoods). In addition, investment support policies should take ecosystem services into account, maintain forest biodiversity and, consequently, increase the carbon sink.

Soil fertility management

Agricultural land and pastures have the potential for reducing emissions rises from 40% to 60% by stop being a source of emissions and become sources of sequestration, through conservation agriculture,

replacing mineral fertilizers with organic fertilizers and sowing improved and biodiverse pastures. To reduce emissions and increase sequestration, the agricultural sector must focus on a green scheme in which there are more equitable payments to farmers when they consider the environment, climate change and the country in their practices. In addition, the expansion of organic and conservation agriculture, and precision agriculture (PA) will allow a reduction in emissions associated with animal effluents and the use of fertilizers. Therefore, the emissions reduction in agriculture is occurring at a slower rate than in other sectors, inherent to the characteristics of the associated biophysical systems, which means that its weight in national emissions will be between 29% and 34% by 2050, depending on whether one considers or not the contribution of land uses.

Moreover, it is necessary to increase the capacity for carbon sequestration by increasing the organic matter content in pastures, particularly in areas with sown, improved, permanent and biodiverse pastures. The use of biodiverse pastures has a very important contribution to the net sequestration associated with the use of agricultural land in 2050. Hence, it is essential that there is an increase in biodiversity pastures of about 400% compared to 2005 (from 50 000 ha to 250 000 ha), thus resulting in a net sequestration of 0.76 Mt in 2050.

3.2 Determining the LMT scope for national level simulation modelling

In Portugal, there is a main set of LMT that comprise several LMTs including the short list of the LMT portfolio (Table 4). The LMTs included in the LMT are described below. Within the scope of the guidelines of the European Commission, the agro-environmental measure for results integrated in the Strategic Plan of the Confederation of Portuguese Farmers (CAP) for Portugal that can be applied to LMTs, include four objectives: i) Improvement of the natural regeneration of the trees and thus increase of the forest sprout; ii) Improvement of soil conditions and regeneration of its productive capacity; iii) Improvement of the composition of pastures with Mediterranean biodiverse characteristics; iv) Diversification and qualification of unique elements of the landscape, such as riparian galleries, groves of Quercineas and/or Pinus, patches of brush, Mediterranean temporary ponds and permanent ponds.

Table 4. Long-listing of relevant land-based LMTs in Portugal.

LMT	Specification	Included in national LANDMARC LMT portfolio
BECCS	Biomass play an important role in heat generation.	No
Cropland	Soil fertility management (use of organic fertilizers, use of harvest residues, cover crops, crop rotation, precision agriculture).	Yes
Grassland	Fertilized natural pastures, sown biodiverse permanent pastures rich in legumes, soil correction (e.g., in Montado/Dehesa)	Yes

Forests and other land uses	Forest management (incl. reduction of burned area and improved forest productivity).	Yes
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Cropland

Sustainable practices in agriculture, such as organic and conservation agriculture, and PA reduce GHG emissions from different sources over time, such as, reduction in the use of synthetic fertilizers and substitution by organic compost. Also, these practices enhance carbon sequestration resulting from increases in soil organic matter content, namely through the promotion of biodiverse pastures. This type of agriculture will have consequences in terms of improving the efficiency of water use, allowing for productivity gains and water savings, which is a scarce and essential good to preserve. It will also be needed to study new forms of animal diet to obtain improvements in the digestibility of animal feed with a consequent positive impact on reducing emissions. Nevertheless, it is also important to highlight and replicate the good examples of marketing in agri-food short circuits, which reduce energy consumption and pollutant emissions due to the lower requirements for packaging, transport and refrigeration of the products.

In addition, the opening of agricultural markets to countries outside the EU has boosted these practices with consequences to produce crops for which the country has more competitive advantages, such as vegetables, dried and fresh fruits and olives. However, on the 13th of September 2022, the European Parliament said that it wants to tighten the rules on importing products, in the context of the fight against climate change and loss of biodiversity, forcing companies to ensure that goods sold in the EU do not contribute to deforestation. The proposal put forward by the European Commission covers livestock, cocoa, coffee, palm oil, soya and wood, including products that contain, have been fed with or made from these goods, such as leather, chocolate and furniture. The assembly also wants to include pork, sheep and goat, poultry, maize and rubber, as well as charcoal and printed paper products.

Agroforestry

The Agroforestry system Montado, in Portugal, and Dehesa, in Spain, is a High Nature Value system characterized by a high complexity because of the interactions between climate, soil, pasture (natural pastures, fertilized natural pastures, and sown biodiverse permanent pastures rich in legumes), trees (e.g., pure or mix stands of cork oak, holm oak, stone pine), and animals (e.g., sheep, pigs, cows, goats). Montado/Dehesa is one of the most prominent and best preserved low-intensity farming systems in Europe. The integration of traditional land-use and biodiversity conservation that is characteristic of this system is an exemplar for the wise management of the countryside. As well as the Montado regeneration is the last frontier to the desertification process. Moreover, with a good management plan, these systems can be strong carbon sinks with low GEE emissions.

Pastures

Montado/Dehesa pastures are generally established in low fertility and high spatial variability soils. However, pasture biomass production can increase three times more and organic matter can rapidly grow in the soil with small and cheap changes such as low soil inputs correction. Moreover, improving the balance between legumes and grasses in the pasture will reduce nitrogen fertilization and promote floristic biodiversity to pollinators. Thus, fertilization and soil correction should be applied to improve soil fertility and, consequently, productivity/quality of pastures. In this context, monitoring the pasture quality is a key element in the decision-making process of a farm manager since these pastures are the main source of animal feed in extensive animal production systems in Portugal and Spain.

Forests

The forest area present in Portugal, about 1/3 of the national territory, presents problems of degradation of the forests and particularly of the soil due to the poor management of the forest stands, of incorrect agricultural practices and of the intensive exploitation of the eucalyptus. The tragic fires of 2017 exposed the problems of forest management. Since then, the government has been developing a forest defense plan that places emphasis on active forest management aimed at planning and prevention, as well as reforming the firefighting system. This plan includes improvements in forest management and production, consequent reduction of the burnt area, and reinforcement of the commitment to ecosystem services that allow and contribute to the fight against desertification and to the valorisation of the territory, being one of the foundations of territorial cohesion. To contribute to the sink potential of the forest area will have to be reinforced, assuming its management in the articulation of territorial planning aspects, investing in management practices and models that enhance the role of sinking forests and increase their resilience in the face of climate change, which has the potential for worsening conditions for forest fires and soil degradation.

Excluded options from the short list of LMTs

BECCS

In Portugal, there is no national strategy to increase the forest area for the use of biomass as an energy source. Although the consumption of industrial biomass may grow until 2035, this source will eventually be replaced by a more competitive energy source. Currently, only 5.61% of the total electricity production in mainland Portugal is generated by biomass.

However, renewable sources consumption are very important LMTs in Portugal having already surpassed the non-renewable energy by 42.3% with the remaining 6.7% of energy consumption to be imported (which may or may not be renewable) in 2019. In 2021, renewable energy production supplied 59% of electricity consumption in Portugal, with emphasis on wind energy, which represented 26%, while non-renewable production supplied 31%. According to the National Energy Networks (REN), of the 59% of electricity consumption supplied by energy production from renewable sources last year, 26% correspond to wind energy, 27% to hydroelectric power, 7% to biomass and 3.5% the photovoltaic. Of the 31% of electricity consumption supplied by non-renewable energy production in

2021, 29% is coal, with the last plant closed at the end of November (Pego, in Abrantes) representing less than 2%. The remaining 10% correspond to importation. Between January and September 2022, 31,225 GWh of electricity were generated in mainland Portugal, of which 54.5% came from renewable sources.

Portugal has been positioned as one of the countries in the world that uses more renewable energy, such as solar, wind and hydroelectric. Despite the renewable energy being very important energy source in Portugal, they were excluded from the short list of LMTs for not being part of the scope of the LANDMARC project focus which is focus on LMTs in agriculture, agroforestry and other land uses changes.

3.3 Discussion on short-listing LMTs

3.3.1 Land use change dynamics

According to the short list of LMTs and based on the estimated data for 2050 in Table 5, the Portuguese forest area will remain relatively constant. An increase in the rate of new afforestation is expected to 8,000 ha/year (expansion of the forest area to other land uses) and a decrease in the rate of expansion of other land uses, particularly in urbanized areas, flooded dams and scrubland. The afforestation trend will be focused on planting trees of low- growing species and protection against fire, as is the case of cork oak and stone pine, reducing in this way fast-growing and fire-susceptible tree species, such as eucalyptus, maritime pine and other resinous trees. The Portuguese Forest policies measures will push the low growing species because of their better resistance to climate change and for allowing exploitation in multifunctional systems, with annual or periodic/regular revenues and with characteristics that can make a very relevant contribution to economic valorization, job creation, fire risk reduction, etc., complementing or replacing woody productions. Thus, Portuguese forestry will be diversified to be more resilient and less vulnerable in the event of drought or cold or heat wave and consequently mitigate the fires prevention.

The trend of agricultural area is to decrease with the abandonment of some marginal lands which, from the point of view of agricultural competitiveness, are not very high. These marginal agricultural areas will change to areas of pasture or scrubland. The pasture area will increase due to the abandonment of agricultural land and marginal land because of the competitiveness of agriculture. Moreover, the Montado/dehesa pastures will become better preserved.

Table 5. Evolution of the area of different land uses in Portugal (RNC2050, 2019).

LAND USE	2015	2020	2030	2040	2050	Δ 2050/2005
NATIONAL TOTAL	9.24	9.24	9.24	9.24	9.24	0%
Forested Land	4.36	4.19	4.19 4.23	4.18 4.27	4.17 4.31	-4% -1%
Maritime pine	1.18	1.10	1.08 1.05	1.07 1.01	1.06 0.97	-10% -18%
Cork Oak	0.93	0.94	0.95 0.98	0.96 1.02	0.97 1.06	4% 14%
Eucalyptus	0.85	0.78	0.8 0.74	0.81 0.71	0.83 0.67	-3% -21%
Holm Oak	0.60	0.60	0.59 0.61	0.59 0.63	0.59 0.65	-2% 9%
Oaks	0.21	0.21	0.2 0.23	0.2 0.25	0.2 0.27	-6% 28%
Other leafy trees	0.35	0.36	0.34 0.38	0.33 0.4	0.31 0.42	-10% 21%
Stone pine	0.21	0.21	0.21 0.21	0.21 0.22	0.21 0.23	2% 10%
Other resinous trees	0.03	0.01	0.01 0.02	0 0.03	0 0.03	-90% 21%
Agricultural land	2.39	2.39	2.25	2.17 2.11	2.16 1.99	-10% -17%
Pastures	0.66	0.60	0.66 0.66	0.8 0.57	0.96 0.49	46% -26%
Wetlands	0.20	0.20	0.21	0.21	0.21	8%
Urban land	0.50	0.52	0.55	0.56 0.56	0.57 0.56	15% 13%
Scrubland and other land uses	1.14	1.33	1.39 1.34	1.31 1.53	1.17 1.68	3% 48%

[1,000,000 ha]

3.3.2 Land management dynamics

Portugal intends to promote the annual increment of carbon sequestered forests and pastures land management dynamics to accomplish the GHG emissions targets set by 2050 (Table 6). Once Portugal is part of the Mediterranean region, fire is an integral and structuring part of ecosystems which should not ended but ensure that it has low intensity, resulting in smaller impacts.

Thus, the main management dynamic implemented in forests will be: i) making greater use of fire prevention techniques, including reforestation with suitable tree species (e.g., cork oak and cork holm); ii) tree understory deforestation; iii) increasing the organic matter in the soil; iv) promote permanent pastures; v) increasing the use of small ruminants to reduce the combustible material; and vi) using renewable energies and local fertilizers. In this way, it is estimated that there will be a large reduction in the burned areas from an average of about 164,000 ha/year between 1998 and 2017 to 70,000 ha/year by 2050 (i.e., a 60% reduction).

Table 6. Carbon sequestration in Portugal by 2050 (Alvarenga et al., 2017).

	2014	Maximum area available	Annual increment		Total carbon Sequestered
	(ha)	(ha)	(ha)	%	(t CO ₂)
Biodiversity pastures	137 000	963 000	12 000	8.8	7 919 520
Native forest	180 000	725 000	21 585	12.0	11 493 519
Total	317 000	1 688 000	33 585	20.8	19 413 039

Cropland changes will consist in the replacement of mineral fertilization by organic fertilization, the reduction of the total quantities of fertilizers used and an increase in the organic matter content of agricultural land using for example cover crops. Replacing mineral fertilisers with organic fertilisers will increase the use of compost from livestock waste and/or organic waste from other sources (e.g.,

agribusiness). Replacement with organic fertilisers, especially composting, is expected to reach 180,000 ha by 2050. On the other hand, it is also estimated that the total amount of fertiliser used per unit area will be reduced through the expansion and development of PA techniques, totalling 300,000 ha in 2050, which will lead to a 58% reduction in the use of synthetic nitrogen compared to 2005. These changes will contribute to the objectives and targets of the Farm to Fork Strategy and The European Green Deal by reducing the use of fertilizers by at least 20% by 2030 due to nutrient losses by 50%, and by reducing chemical and hazardous pesticides by 50% by 2030. Consequently, agricultural land will be undergone an increase in organic matter content following an increase in carbon sequestration capacity by increasing the area under conservation (or regenerative) agriculture, reaching 180,000 ha by 2050 and increasing the area under biological cultivation and/or replacement of mineral fertilization by organic fertilization. All these measures will lead to total reductions of -177 ktCO₂eq in 2030, -331 ktCO₂eq in 2040 and -639 ktCO₂eq in 2050.

Agroforestry ecosystems with a high environmental value, i.e., Montado/Dehesa, are adopting collective management and exploitation models to protect biodiversity and enhance the natural capital of territories and the services provided by ecosystems. With low soil inputs correction and the correct balance between grasses and legumes, biomass production can be tripled, and soil organic matter can rapidly grow in the soil. Thus, a shift from natural pastures to biodiversity seeded pastures can lead to an estimated a carbon sequestration factor of 6.48 tCO₂/ha/year over a period of 10 years (Teixeira et al., 2011). In addition, it is estimated that the Mediterranean forests retain up to 14 million tonnes of CO₂ every year, a notable contribution to the reduction of GHG, the main source of climate change. In the case of Portugal alone, the retention of CO₂ associated with cork oak forests is around five million tons/year (5% of total CO₂ emissions in the country). A stripped cork oak fixes, on average, five times more CO₂ during the natural regeneration process than a non-stripped cork oak.

4. Co-design of LMT narratives

4.1 Introduction

The literature review allowed to select from the long list of LMTs, a short list of LMTs representative of the Portuguese systems. The three selected LMTs will later be considered to analyze the techniques used to scale up at local, regional, national and global level through models in order to meet the objectives of the LANDMARC project. To do so, it is necessary to proceed with a description or narrative of the short list of selected LMTs. To accomplish this objective the following sections, provide the quality narrative for the three LMTs for Portugal: Section 3.2) Cropland; Section 3.3) Grassland; and Section 3.4) Forests and other land uses.

4.2 Precision agriculture

4.2.1 Introduction

PA is more innovative, more sophisticated, more productive and more market oriented with the adoption and investment in new technologies, namely technologies for inputs optimization (e.g., soil, water, plants, fertilization, pesticides...) and environment impact reduction. Some PA front runners in Portugal implemented sustainable practices and exploitation of resources considering the European Policies (e.g., Green Deal and Farm to Fork) and consumer sustainable concerns, in line with modern concepts of environmental protection, mitigation of climate change and combating desertification. These practices translate effectively in the reduction of GHG emissions from different sources over time, such as, reduction in the use of synthetic fertilizers and substitution by organic compost, the use of cover crops in between crops, the use of inputs differential distribution, etc. These changes in the sector have allowed an increase in productivity and a more efficient use of resources, improving the competitiveness of farms who putted in practice PA activities, and increase carbon sinks with low GHG emissions. Moreover, technological advances have also made it possible to respond to the demands of the market and productivity, with research being a key point in its development. The progress of the Portuguese agriculture is, in turn, a factor in the development of industrial activity, namely the agri-food industry, the manufacture of agricultural equipment and plant protection products.

4.2.2 Policy context

Considering the ambitions demonstrated by the European institutions in terms of relaunching the economy, protecting the environment and increasing biodiversity, namely through the recently approved European Recovery Plan and the European Ecological Pact - “Green Deal” – the CAP is promoting activities related to agriculture in a context of sustainable exploitation of resources, in line with modern concepts of environmental protection, mitigation of climate change and combating desertification.

In Portugal, there are highly qualified farmers (“front runners”) who use PA techniques (state-of-the-art technology), conservation farming, biological farming and the use of composting, which will allow

a reduction in emissions from synthetic fertilizers and their replacement with organic fertilizers, a reduction in emissions from livestock systems by increasing the quality of the diet and installing biodiverse pastures. Farmers and many producer associations improved their products and processes, such as fruits and vegetables, as well as olive oil, wine or cork, thus enabling them to compete with the best producers in the world. In the agricultural sector, there is professional training that is mandatory, by national or community imposition, in which CAP develops a considerable activity, and training to develop specific technical skills. However, there are still a significant number of companies that do not have specific training. Moreover, in recent years, there has been a growing market interest in organic products that will force greater promotion of national production and exports, a better organization of production and marketing and a reduction in the external food deficit.

The overall amount of additional investments in some of the technologies identified, which can lead to reductions in fertiliser emissions and increases in carbon sequestration on agricultural land, pastures and forests, amounts to around EUR 570 million over the period 2021-2050, equivalent to an annual amount of around 19 million euros.

4.2.3 Current land use and potential land-use competition

The importance of GHG agriculture emissions to total national emissions (excluding LULUCF and international bunkers) has decreased from 12.1% in 1990 to 9.8 % in 2017. Emissions from agriculture have been increasing since 2013, mainly because of the increase in livestock numbers, particularly non-dairy cattle. In 2015, GHG emissions from agriculture represent about 10% of national emissions, totalling 6.8 MtCO₂eq, and mainly involve methane (CH₄), corresponding to 40% of national emissions of this gas, and nitrous oxide (N₂O) which in this case represents 73% of the total national emissions of this gas. The most important emission sources originate from the animal sector, and represent 83% of agricultural emissions (e.g., enteric fermentation, livestock effluent management, direct manure spreading on pastures and application of livestock effluents on agricultural lands). The remaining 17% refer to the use of mineral fertilisers, lime correctors and crop residues not removed from agricultural lands. The component associated with agricultural and pasture uses in 2015 represented about 0.7 MtCO₂eq of emissions, resulting from the kinds of practices used and the conversions between the different use categories to these categories over the last 20 years. Considering this component, thus associating all activities and impacts on the land of this sector, agricultural emissions in 2015 represented 11% of total emissions.

The management of the agricultural sector aims to a more effective climate action and better protection of the environment and biodiversity. To reduce emissions and increase sequestration, the agricultural sector must focus on a green scheme in which there are more equitable payments to farmers when they consider the environment, climate change and the country in their practices. In the case of the livestock sector, emission reductions can occur through improvements in food digestibility and in livestock effluent management systems. The use of biodiverse pastures has a very important contribution to the net sequestration associated with the use of agricultural land in 2050 (e.g.,

biodiverse pastures covering the soil in between lines of oliveyards and vineyards, sequestering carbon, reducing nutrients leaching and soil erosion).

In addition, the expansion of organic and conservation agriculture, and PA will allow a reduction in emissions associated with animal effluents and the use of fertilizers. Therefore, the emissions reduction in agriculture is occurring at a slower rate than in other sectors, inherent to the characteristics of the associated biophysical systems, which means that its weight in national emissions will be between 29% and 34% by 2050, depending on whether one considers or not the contribution of land uses (please see Table 1 from 1.4.3 Land management practices).

The evolution of the Portuguese economy and society in the last 50 years, although positive, has not stopped the population exodus to large urban centers and the progressive aging of the rural population, leading to the abandonment of territories and traditional activities in agriculture. Consequently, it gave rise to the progressive extension of forest use, often spontaneous and not managed with great concentration of fuel loads and strong exposure to rural fire hazard, which had the tragic consequences of the summer of 2017 with loss of human lives and countless losses in equipment and goods, which are added to the destruction of the forest and the goods and services it produces, further promoting the abandonment of these territories.

However, at this stage and considering cropland optimization the only way to go is to consider the usage of sustainable agriculture practices, namely PA techniques and others that for sure will start to exist in the fields to solve the labor deficit in agriculture (e.g., robotics).

4.2.4 Climate risks & sensitivities

The agricultural sector faces a major challenge in terms of adapting to climate change and mitigating its effects. It should be noted that agriculture, while being part of the problem, is also part of the solution as it plays an important role in carbon sequestration. Indeed, agriculture depends on natural resources and climate to provide a suitable environment for growing crops and climate change threatens to cause great damage to agriculture in the future. There are several mitigation and adaptation opportunities in agriculture. Many agricultural practices that are beneficial for mitigation also make positive contributions to water, soil and biodiversity protection, as well as to adaptation. For example, including grasses in crop rotations decreases emissions while providing year-round ground cover, thus reducing soil erosion and increasing soil water retention. Many of these actions can reduce the sector's impact on climate change, maintaining productivity levels to meet food demand.

In a climate change scenario, the rise in the average sea level can make the agricultural use of certain soils in coastal areas unfeasible as a result of either the rise in the water table, the total flooding of the plots, or even the increase in salinity.

Although agricultural systems are extremely climate dependent, so far, there is little documented evidence of ongoing climate change impacts. This fact is probably due to the great influence of aspects not related to the climate, such as irrigation, the management of crops and technological innovations, as well as markets and subsidy policies. Globally, agricultural productivity shows a growing trend over

the last 40 years, as a result of technological improvements in breeding, pest and disease control, fertilization and mechanization. Thus, it is difficult to identify effects of recent climate change on agricultural productivity.

It is however possible to find evidence of impacts on other aspects related to agricultural activity. Crop phenology is one of the processes that highlights some effects of current climate change, particularly in perennial crops such as fruit trees, vines and olive groves. In fact, in annual crops, the sowing date can be chosen, which allows an adjustment depending on the thermal regime of each year.

In Portugal, this type of LMT considers inputs and systems optimization and because of that the mitigation strategies should be different from the North of the country (growing biomass potential when there exist a rising in average temperature) when compared to the South of the country (decreasing of biomass potential when there exist a rising in average temperature). However, the last one is only true for rainfed crops but not true for irrigated crops.

4.2.5 *Economic implications*

In 2030, the European Union wants 25% of the agricultural area to be under organic farming, which corresponds to 39.2 million hectares, that is, an increase of 26.7 million hectares compared to 2019. With 27 Member States, the agricultural area of the European Union is 156.7 million hectares. In 2019, around 8% of this area was occupied by biological agriculture, that is, around 12.5 million hectares. In Portugal, the organic farming area represents 6% of the agricultural area. The distribution of organic farming in the EU-27 and Portugal in 2019 is as follows (Portuguese Environmental Agency, 2019):

	Arable crops	Permanent pastures	Permanent crops
EU 27	45 %	45 %	10 %
Portugal	20%	60 %	20 %

In the specific case of Portugal, agricultural production will result in a significant increase in imports, consequently in maritime and road transport, and, consequently, in the carbon footprint of food. However, the situation in Portugal is quite sensitive, since the national agro-industry has a weight of raw materials imported from third countries and intra-community transactions much higher than the average of the European Union.

In order to achieve greater environmental sustainability in the context of Portuguese agriculture, it will be necessary to create the institutional political conditions capable of promoting an expansion throughout the national territory of production systems and the occupation and use of agricultural and forestry soils based on crops, technologies and practices that, being economically viable, contribute to: i) fighting climate change; ii) a sustainable management of natural resources; iii) the preservation of biodiversity and rural landscape. To achieve these three different contributions to greater environmental sustainability, three types of interventions are needed: 1) the good agricultural and environmental conditions provided for under the new conditions that all farmers will have to comply with in order to benefit from different future public support; 2) the eco-regime payments that will integrate the 1st Pillar of the CAP post-2020, replacing the “greening” payments in force; 3) payments

for environmental, climate and other management commitments, which are expected to form part of the 2nd Pillar of the CAP and which will essentially correspond to an adaptation of the system of agri-environmental measures (MAA) currently in force.

In Portugal, income support to producers subject to conditions of an environmental nature, usually called “greening” payments, correspond to a total value of 166 million euros. Support for producers’ dependent on the choice of agricultural practices beneficial from the point of view of the climate and the environment, known as eco-regime payments, corresponds to an annual value of 126 million euros.

4.2.6 *Co-benefits and trade-offs*

Weather conditions drastically affect agricultural productivity. The geographic distribution of crops and pastures is a function of climate and photoperiod. The total amount of precipitation, as well as its pattern of variation, are important aspects for agrarian systems. Crops have climatic limits that affect their growth, development and productivity. There are also climatic factors limiting productivity that are only effective for a few days, as in the case of cereals and fruit trees. These include temperature values associated with specific phenological phases and that condition the formation of reproductive organs, such as grains and fruits. Thus, it is easy to predict that climate change will have a strong impact on agricultural activity. The main effects, however, are the impacts of global warming on phenology and the increase of CO₂ on the photosynthetic efficiency of crops.

Those two effects can have antagonistic consequences. On the one hand, warming reduces crop cycle times and therefore productivity. On the other hand, increasing CO₂ increases the photosynthetic rate and therefore productivity. What will be at stake will be to verify if the reduction in the cycle duration is compensated by the increase in the photosynthetic rate. Depending on the balance between the two components, the result can be different, from a drop in productivity to an increase. It is logical that in that balance there are many other determining variables, the main one being water availability. Without these, crops will not be able to take advantage of the increase in CO₂. Other key variables in the balance between cycle length and photosynthetic rate are the impacts of changes in pests, diseases and weeds.

In permanent crops, there will be an anticipation of the beginning of the vegetative cycle. In annual crops, it will be possible to sow earlier and, in some cases, the possibility of carrying out two sowings each year. The areas of crop aptitude will tend to expand to North, making it possible to introduce new crops with greater thermal needs (and/or lesser water requirements) and make others unfeasible. The occurrence of extreme weather events, such as, heat waves, hailstorms or dry spells can compromise part or all the production of a campaign. In a climate change scenario, the probability of occurrence of these events is greater, so it is possible to predict greater production losses.

Considering PA techniques, which is defined as “techniques that monitor and optimize production processes ... thereby conceivably increasing yields and outputs and improving the efficiency and effectiveness of inputs” (Fraser, 2019), co-benefits and trade-offs will vary from crop to crop. Irrigated crops will benefit more from these types of techniques and technologies in terms of getting more

production, reduce nitrogen emissions and benefit water quality impacts (Sishodia et al., 2020). On the other hand, these same techniques highlight the relevance of integrating specific ecological principles and biodiversity management procedures into agroscape management, while optimizing inputs to maximize yields (Loures et al., 2020). PA techniques, when applied correctly, provide important ecosystem benefits, such as mitigating agricultural pollution and reducing water consumption (i.e., avoid excessive chemical inputs in soil, reduce carbon footprint in field operations, reduce herbicide and pesticide use, and monitor plant health) while reducing input costs, maximizing yields, reducing dependence on external inputs and sustain or enhance ecosystem services (Loures et al., 2020; Schrijver et al., 2016).

4.2.7 Risks associated with scaling up

Despite of being a small country, Portugal has a very marked thermal gradient and geographic characteristics between North and South regions which has different implications for the techniques to be used in agriculture. The North and Centre regions are characterized by small crops areas (< 20 ha) due to the relief. However, the crops of these regions are not so affected by the lack of water but by the pattern of rainfall and temperature variation. The South regions (Alentejo) corresponds to about 1/3 of the territory of mainland Portugal. It is a region with low population density, but with a high agricultural potential. The lack of water in this region has been one of the main constraints on its development, preventing the modernization of agriculture and sustainability in public supply. Located in the Alentejo (South region), the Alqueva Multipurpose Development (EFMA) has about 120 thousand irrigated hectares, which makes this project a structuring instrument, mobilizing a diversified set of activities, supported by an integrated development process. Taking advantage of available water resources, alternatives that are economically, socially and environmentally sustainable must be sought and supported. At EFMA, there has been a tendency to change the crop occupation towards an increase in the weight of permanent crops, as a result of the growing importance of olive and almond groves. In fact, permanent crops had a stronger growth than annual crops. Thus, permanent crops started from an initial position of 64% to the current 83%. This increase is all the more relevant when permanent cropping systems have been replaced by other. On the other hand, from the analysis of the origin of the investment, it appears that the annual crops are almost exclusively Portuguese and the permanent crops, with a very significant weight, are from foreign investors.

In terms of PA techniques, scalability is possible mainly when using remote sensing tools. This scalability is possible in the south of the country (Alentejo) but not in other types of regions, such as the small property typical of the northern regions of the country.

4.2.8 Research gaps

No research gaps have been identified.

4.3 Grassland

4.3.1 Introduction

Grasslands have the availability of capturing carbon and also emit GHG. Grasslands are generally expected to have high biomass turnover, productivity and nutrient cycle, and only moderate capacity for carbon sequestration in biomass when compared to woody communities. Therefore, not all area available for sown biodiverse grassland is available for sequestering carbon and neutralize emissions.

A particular activity, taking place in grazed lands is reported and accounted for under “grassland remaining grassland”: Sown Biodiverse Permanent Pastures Rich in Legumes (SBPPRL) sown biodiverse permanent grassland rich in legumes. Sown biodiverse grasslands are based on a diverse mixture of about twenty different species, many of which (approximately 30-50%) are legumes. These grasslands are more productive than the baseline land use system – spontaneous natural grasslands. Productivity is accompanied by an increase in soil organic matter (SOM) and correspondent carbon sequestration. Teixeira et al. (2011) analyzed the effect from a shift from natural to sown biodiverse grasslands, and calculations based on this work estimated a carbon sequestration factor of $6.48 \text{ tCO}_2\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}\cdot\text{yr}^{-1}$ for a period of 10 years. Most of the time, these grasslands are grazed directly by cattle, sheep or goats and result from the seeding with improved and selected seeds. Thus, grazing intensity and opportunity can influence pasture growth and thus affect soil carbon storage. Both undergrazing and overgrazing can decrease soil carbon build-up. In addition, pastures that favor the intercropping of different species should be used. It increases grassland productivity by increasing soil carbon sequestration.

A grassland study showed that the composition of the species community is sensitive to CO_2 increase, which has implications for its stability and resilience. For example, in an annual Mediterranean grassland after three years of trials, species diversity decreased with increasing CO_2 , increased with increasing precipitation and showed no effect with increasing temperature. In sown grassland, the increase in CO_2 favored legumes.

The increase in climate variability, with more frequent occurrence of extreme events will also have a negative effect on agricultural activity as it will increase the uncertainty associated with different agricultural systems. On the other hand, the increase in extreme events can lower crop productivity more than the effect of increasing average values. This results from the fact that the impact of extreme events largely depends on the phenological state of the crop at that time. The more frequent occurrence of more intense rainfall will have a negative impact on productivity as it increases the occurrence of periods of saturated soil and, consequently, of stress for crops. Those events will also have impacts at the level of soil erosion.

4.3.2 Policy context

According to the trajectories for carbon neutrality of the Portuguese economy by 2050, it is necessary to ensure the capacity for carbon sequestration by increasing the organic matter content in grasslands, especially in areas with sown, improved, permanent and biodiverse grasslands. The use of biodiverse

grassland has a very important contribution to the net sequestration associated with the use of agricultural land in 2050.

In a similar way to croplands, the expansion of biological and conservation farming and PA, as well as permanent grasslands, will reduce emissions associated with fertilizer use and animal effluents, and increase carbon sequestration resulting from increases in organic matter content in the soil. These approaches are highly being used by highly qualified farmers who use state-of-the-art technology, including sowing biodiverse grasslands which induce other environmental benefits, such as the preservation of natural and ecological resources, promotion of biodiversity and/or improvements in animal welfare.

4.3.3 Current land use and potential land-use competition

Contrary to cropland, the areas of grassland have seen an increase since 1990, with most of the area coming from cropland (rain-fed annual crops). The conversion from agriculture to grasslands usually results in an increased sequestration, while the conversions from forest land and other land result in increased emissions. The net-balance has favoured emissions, although these have been heavily reduced since 1990. More recently the introduction of incentives for biodiverse grasslands has allowed an increase in sequestration rates due to an increase in the areas of grasslands and extensive livestock, the greater use of more sustainable practices in environmental terms (e.g., organic production, integrated production, direct sowing and minimal mobilization) and the reduction in the use of fertilizers.

Furthermore, permanent grasslands will increase the capacity of carbon sequestration by sowing improved and biodiverse grasslands which consequently will increase the organic matter content in the soil. With low soil inputs correction, biomass production can be tripled, and soil organic matter can rapidly grow in the soil. For instance, improving the balance between legumes and grasses in the grassland, the technology will reduce nitrogen fertilization and promote floristic biodiversity to pollinators. Fertilization and soil correction should be applied to improve soil fertility and, consequently, productivity/quality of grasslands. Therefore, not all area available for sown biodiverse grasslands is available for sequestering carbon to neutralize emissions.

Moreover, it is necessary to ensure an increase in the organic matter content of the land area used for grassland, focusing in particular on areas with sown, improved, permanent and biodiverse grasslands in order to increase their sequestration capacity. This requires an increase in biodiversity grasslands of about 400% compared to 2005 (from 50 000 ha to 250 000 ha), thus resulting in a net sequestration of 0.76 Mt in 2050.

4.3.4 Climate risks & sensitivities

Climatic conditions drastically affect grassland productivity in the same way affect the productivity of crops. The geographic distribution of grasslands is a function of climate and photoperiod, total amount of precipitation and effect of temperature on phenological development. The occurrence of extreme

weather events, such as, heat waves, hailstorms or dry spells can compromise part or all the production of a campaign. In a climate change scenario, the probability of occurrence of these events is greater, so it is possible to predict greater production losses in this way.

4.3.5 Economic implications

In Portugal, and according to INE (2020), the area of permanent grasslands grew 14% compared to the last agricultural census carried out – Agricultural Census 2009 (RA09), which means that this important agrarian system occupies about 60% of the Useful Agricultural Area (SAU) in Portugal. There is a great diversity of permanent grasslands (e.g., natural and sown, on clean land and under cover of Montado) and, therefore, several management strategies. In some of these grasslands, it is justified to define and apply strategies for their recovery or improvement, to be able to increase their productivity by reducing their production irregularity, to improve the quality and also to increase the different ecosystem benefits produced, that is, to obtain a grassland with a sustainable management method.

Currently in Portugal, sustainable biodiverse grassland is being implemented where, through the increase of leguminous species in the mixtures to be used, instead of the traditional permanent ryegrass grasslands. It is intended to reduce the use of nitrogen fertilizers and its environmental impact, increase the production of biomass and soil fertility and contribute to an increase in the volume and quality of dairy production. At the same time, it is expected to reduce production costs and consumption of concentrated feed and raw materials needed for its manufacture. The production of GHG resulting from the processes of manufacturing and transporting compound feed and fertilizers from the continent is also reduced. Thus, framing a logic of Circular Economy, with the corresponding positive impact on climate change.

4.3.6 Co-benefits and trade-offs

The contribution of grasslands and forages to Portuguese agriculture has not been properly recognized or taken advantage of. It is 2/3 of the agricultural area that is occupied by these crops that support animal production (especially ruminants) which are cheaper and of better quality. There is a lack of definition of national strategies to encourage the use of more productive, more resilient and persistent species and mixtures, and improvement in the management of installed pastures (e.g., sowing, fertilization, mineral correction, animal management, etc.) is lacking.

Direct aids (i.e., integrated production, organic production, greening, etc.) are neither sufficient nor adequate to promote the improvement of production and the impact of forage and grass crops. More research and experimentation are needed, on species, varieties, mixtures, cultural techniques and the management of grasslands and animals to increase the efficiency of the use of these foods, their quality, reduce costs, improve animal performance and, above all, increase the effective animal/animal load to better value natural meadows and grasslands.

4.3.7 Risks associated with scaling up

Meadows and permanent grasslands on clean land predominate (55% of the total) over those under cover of woods and forests (41%) and over those under cover of permanent crops (3%) or those that

are non-productive under a regime single payment scheme (1%). Alentejo is the region with the largest area of permanent meadows and grasslands, with about 66% of the national total (1.27 million ha) and the Azores are the region with the highest occupation of the agricultural area used by meadows and permanent grasslands (80% of the agricultural area used).

Across the country, except for the Azores, poor grasslands predominate – i.e., natural/spontaneous grasslands not fertilized or sown – representing, on average, 73% of the total surface of meadows and permanent grasslands. In the Azores, the weight of poor grasslands does not reach 10%, the remaining 90% corresponding to sown meadows or improved natural grasslands (by fertilization or introduction of improved/selected species). Alentejo is the region with the largest area of temporary meadows (56% of the national total) and forage crops (37% of the total). It is followed in importance by the region of Entre Douro e Minho, with 10% of temporary meadows and 19% of forage crops.

Adding the area of meadows and permanent pastures with that of temporary grasslands and forage crops, we obtain a value of 2 451 329 hectares (67% of agricultural area used) dedicated to animal feed, that is, 2/3 of the Portuguese territory is occupied by these agricultural crops. Despite the current importance and the increase in area recorded in recent decades, because of the change in agricultural policies that led to a decrease in arable crop areas, in particular of cereals, and to an increase in the number of livestock in grasslands, namely in the number of cattle in extensive regime, the expected positive impact on the increase in livestock production did not occur, for several reasons.

On the one hand, because the area that increased from permanent grasslands was mainly poor grasslands, whose productive potential is incomparably smaller than that of a sown/improved meadow (400 Forage Units/ha against 2000 Forage Units/ha, on average), and on the other hand, because the meadow mixtures used in the meadows (permanent and temporary) or the forage mixtures used were not the best ones due to lack of information or experimentation.

4.3.8 Research gaps

In the near future, the Portuguese Society of Pastures and Forages will continue to strive for recognition of the important role that grasslands and forages can play in national animal production and the need to articulate efforts to produce and spread more knowledge about meadows and forage production as a guarantee of cheaper, higher quality and more sustainable animal productions.

In addition, research and experimentation work is needed to determine the best varieties and mixtures for each edaphoclimatic combination. There is also a lack of studies on the response to production factors (e.g., fertilization, irrigation, etc.) and on management, to be able to advise livestock producers and prepare manuals on good practices, which can serve as guides for the good use of these productions by the animals.

4.4 Forests and other land uses

4.4.1 Introduction

Portugal is covered, in about 35% of its territory, by forest. In addition to its economic, environmental and social value, it supports important economic sectors downstream, such as, the wood and cork industry, or the uniqueness of biomaterials for the green economy, forests are providers of goods and services to society, such as carbon sequestration, landscape creation, regulation of the hydrological cycle, combating desertification or preserving biodiversity.

There is a consensus on the need to create a forest for the future that is more orderly, biodiverse and resilient, combined with an agricultural, agroforestry and silvopastoral mosaic, capable of providing various environmental services and sustaining the economic activities associated with them, in addition to significantly reducing the severity of the burned area. In order to consolidate the process of fighting fires, it is necessary to reinforce the forest policy, which is a crucial asset to ensure the sustainability of the territory and for the future.

In the forests, a reduction in the annual average burned area should be given prominence, through improvements in land management and planning and greater investment in the management of stands, in fire prevention and fighting. New afforestation and reforestation are mostly implemented with production species (e.g., cork oak, pine and eucalyptus) or with protection and conservation species (e.g., native hardwoods), depending on the scenario considered. Also, in the context of the definition and implementation of investment support policies, it is recommended to reinforce the distribution of support for ecosystem services and the maintenance of forest biodiversity.

4.4.2 Policy context

The Portuguese forest is biodiverse, no species have dominance, all occupy less than 1/3 of the forest area, which is 72% covered by autochthonous plants. Forest policy must be oriented towards conservation and environmental sustainability, bearing in mind that the forest is also a source of economic wealth, with its forestry-industrial ranges, in particular pine, cork oak and eucalyptus. The essence of forestry policy in Portugal must be based on a symbiosis between the conservation forest and the production forest, with the priority being conservation, environmental sustainability and the minimization of fire risks. For this to happen, it is necessary to reduce unmanaged and abandoned territories, with scrubland and uncultivated land representing about 16% of the territory.

Forests and other land uses will experience improvements in forest management and consequent increases in average productivity, the rate of new afforestation (e.g., expansion of the forest area from other land uses) and the expansion rate from other land uses, with more productive and better adapted varieties and increasing the density of production or protection of species. On one hand, there will be a large reduction in the burned areas from an average of about 164,000 ha/year between 1998 and 2017 to 70,000 ha/year by 2050 (i.e., a 60% reduction). There will also be a better management of the use given to these areas after the fire, ensuring smaller total areas affected by fires, considering the suitability of the species used in reforestation, reducing deforestation caused by fires (forests

converted to scrub) and making greater use of fire prevention techniques, including increasing the use of small ruminants to reduce the combustible material. On the other hand, there will be an increase in the rate of new afforestation to 8 000 ha/year (expansion of the forest area for other land uses) and a decrease in the rate of expansion of other land uses, particularly in urbanized areas, flooded dams and scrubland.

98% of the national forest is private. In order to improve forest governance and reformulate the equation of owners' income, it is necessary to incorporate remuneration for ecosystem services through appropriate forest policy instruments. The remuneration of the multiple goods and services provided by the forests will not only promote their protection, but may also constitute a complementary form of income for the forest owners, allowing the return on their investment.

4.4.3 Current land use and potential land-use competition

The component of land uses associated with forest occupation are normally large carbon sinks. This is how, in 2015, forest lands obtained a net sequestration of 11 MtCO_{2eq}. However, in the Portuguese case, this carbon sink potential is greatly affected by the impact of rural fires, which reveals itself directly in net GHG emissions when they are large fires, and indirectly in decisions to maintain or change the land use, by the farmers. The main factors for this change were changes in land use patterns over time and the introduction of policies to increase reforestation, improve the system for preventing and fighting forest fires (introduced after the great fire seasons of 2003 and 2005) and the introduction of incentives for carbon sequestration in agricultural and pasture soils. The fire had a high inter-annual variability due to changes in weather patterns from year to year, with a record high value of 546 kha of burnt area in 2017 (5.9% of the country). The Forest and other land uses sector changed from a net emitter in 1990 (1.2 MtCO_{2eq}) to a carbon sink in 1992. This situation was again reversed in the 2003 and 2005 due to the severe forest fires in recent years. In 2017, this sector returned to being a net emitter, with a total of 7.2 MtCO_{2eq}, representing 9% of the total country's emissions of for the reasons previously mentioned. Excluding that year, the average over the last decade would be -10 MtCO_{2eq}.

The net total of emissions and carbon sinks is therefore currently 60 MtCO_{2eq}, and this is the order of magnitude that will have to be reduced by 2050 to achieve carbon neutrality. Therefore, it will be necessary to ensure a large reduction in burned areas, from an average of about 164,000 ha/year between 1998 and 2017 to 70,000 ha/year by 2050 (i.e., a 60% reduction), to be careful about the use given to these areas after the fire, ensuring smaller total areas affected by fires, considering the suitability of the species used in reforestation, reducing the deforestation caused by fires (forests converted into scrubland) and making greater use of fire prevention techniques, including increased use of small ruminants to reduce combustible material. On the other hand, there is a series of actions that will allow improvement of forest management and achieve consequent increases in average productivity, such as improving management and increasing fire prevention, using more productive and better adapted varieties and increasing density, of either production or protection species.

4.4.4 *Climate risks & sensitivities*

Forests, in addition to being considered one of the greatest natural heritages, are considered the great precursors in the mitigation of climate change. On the other hand, one of the most notorious consequences of climate change is the occurrence of extreme temperatures, which, if very high, increase the probability and intensity of fire occurrence. Fires are one of the worst scourges facing the national forest, and consequently, in addition to the impacts on populations, the economy and biodiversity, the carbon sequestration service is also heavily penalized. Thus, if climate change penalizes the provision of carbon sequestration services by forests via combustion, there is a vicious cycle between climate change and carbon sequestration, as it is one of the main solutions in combating change climate.

The effects of climate change with extreme events characterized by very hot and very dry climates and with deviations in relation to precipitation have culminated in large forest fires in Portugal. The impacts of climate change should be taken into account in mitigation options, notably as regards future water availability, heating and cooling needs and the risk of rural fires. In this regard, it is also particularly important to note that the determining factor in forest carbon sink capacity - a decrease in the annual average burned area - will be hampered in a scenario of worsening of the effects of climate change. In order to reduce the climate change effects in the Portuguese forests, the management and planning of the territory must be improved to reduce the average annual burned area. In addition, there must be a greater investment in the management of plots, especially in the prevention and fighting of fires. Active forest management is crucial to defend the environment, protect biodiversity, fight fires and minimize the advance of desertification, which is one of the great problems facing the country.

4.4.5 *Economic implications*

The challenge for the forestry sector in Portugal lies in the ownership structure, which is extremely fragmented, and the attractiveness and income of owners, only possible with investment in the conversion of diversified landscapes capable of promoting the well-being of local populations and communities, in addition to making territories more resilient to fire risk. Portugal is one of the European countries potentially most affected by climate change and therefore it is necessary to create a more adapted territory.

4.4.6 *Co-benefits and trade-offs*

In the forest sector, the increase in active afforestation, the promotion of more efficient forestry practices in the use of resources and risk management, and the valorisation of ecosystem services, leverage and sustain a growing role for the bioeconomy, with an impact on carbon retention and on the net balance of emissions. Future productivity gains may arise from better forest management practices and less fire losses, as forest area expansion is expected to be limited by 2050, which means a reduction in forest area relative to 2015.

The forest sector is a value chain that already has a high degree of circularity, and forests play an inevitable role in achieving carbon neutrality. Thus, it can be seen that investment in forests to

increase biological carbon sequestration could lead to gains of over 40% by 2050 (compared to a non-circular scenario).

4.4.7 Risks associated with scaling up

The tendency of the forest area is to remain relatively constant until 2050. However, it is expected an increase in the rate of new afforestation, i.e., expansion of the forest area to other land uses of 8.000 ha/year due to the inevitable rural depopulation.

4.4.8 Research gaps

Not applied.

5. Conclusions

In the last decade, Portugal presents a decreasing trend of GHG emissions, and it has the objective to reach neutrality emission until the end of 2050 with an emission reduction trajectory from 85% to 90% by 2050 compared to 2005.

The GHG emissions are mainly due to biomass burning, where rural fires play an important role in GHG emission values due to poor management and planning, and to the extreme weather events that are occurring more frequently. Hence, Portugal is investing in afforestation and reforestation with low-growing species and protection against fire (cork oak and stone pine), reducing fast-growing and fire-susceptible tree species (e.g., eucalyptus, maritime pine and other resinous trees) as they are more resistant and less vulnerable in case of drought or cold or heat wave and consequently mitigate fire prevention.

In croplands, the mineral fertilization will be replaced by organic fertilization to reduce the total quantities of fertilizers used and to increase the organic matter content cover crops will be used. All these measures will lead to total reductions of -177 ktCO₂eq in 2030, -331 ktCO₂eq in 2040 and -639 ktCO₂eq in 2050.

Agroforestry systems, such as, the Montado which is a very high nature value system, and a hotspot of biodiversity has a CO₂ retention associated with cork oak forests around five million tons/year (5% of total CO₂ emissions in the country). In these systems there has been management towards the protection and natural regeneration and the planting of cork oaks and holm oaks to preserve and increase the retention of CO₂. Montado soil is poor and therefore farmers are putting low soil inputs correction and planting biodiverse pastures with the correct balance between grasses and legumes, to increase the soil organic matter and the CO₂ retention. These grasslands uptake more carbon than spontaneous natural grasslands with an estimated carbon sequestration factor of 6.48 tCO₂.ha-1.yr-1 for a period of 10 years.

The highly qualified Portuguese farmers (“front runners”) use of precision agriculture (PA) to implement sustainable practices and exploitation of resources considering the European Policies (e.g., Green Deal and Farm to Fork) and consumer sustainable concerns, translate effectively in the reduction of GHG emissions through practices of environmental protection, mitigation of climate change and combating desertification. With the national projections of CO₂ emissions from agriculture of 29%-34% by 2050, PA thus emerge as a solution to reduce agriculture total emissions and increase carbon sequestration by eco-regime payments, that will integrate the 1st and 2nd Pillars of the CAP post-2020, to farmers when they consider the environment, climate change and the country in their practices.

Climate changes (i.e., temperature and precipitation) is affecting crop growth, development and productivity, in the same way that affect the grassland productivity. Global warming, as well as pests, diseases and weeds, are affecting the phenology and the increase of CO₂ on the photosynthetic

efficiency of cereals and fruit trees. However, climate change will affect differently Portugal due to the very marked thermal gradient and geographic characteristics of the North and South regions.

6. References

- Alvarenga, A., Marta-Pedroso, C., Santos, J., Felício, L., Serra, L. A., do Rosário Palha, I. M., Palha, M. do R., Sarmento, N., Vieira, R., Santos, S., Oliveira, T., Sousa, T., & Domingos, T. (2017). Towards a carbon neutral economy how is Portugal going to create employment and grow? *MEET2030, Business, Climate Change and Economic Growth*, 109.
- Fraser, A. (2019). Land grab/data grab: Precision agriculture and its new horizons. *The Journal of Peasant Studies*, 46(5), 893–912.
- Loures, L., Chamizo, A., Ferreira, P., Loures, A., Castanho, R., & Panagopoulos, T. (2020). Assessing the effectiveness of precision agriculture management systems in mediterranean small farms. *Sustainability*, 12(9), 3765.
- Portuguese Environmental Agency. (2019). *PORTUGUESE NATIONAL INVENTORY REPORT ON GREENHOUSE GASES, 1990—2017*.
- RNC2050. (2019). *Roadmap for carbon neutrality 2050 (RNC2050). Long-term strategy for carbon neutrality of the Portuguese economy by 2050*.
- Schrijver, R., Poppe, K., Daheim, C. (2016). Precision agriculture and the future of farming in Europe. In: Scientific Foresight Study. European Parliamentary Research Service, Brussels, Belgium.
- Sishodia, R. P., Ray, R. L., & Singh, S. K. (2020). Applications of Remote Sensing in Precision Agriculture: A Review. *Remote Sensing*, 12(19), Art. 19.
- Teixeira, R., Domingos, T., Costa, A., Oliveira, R., Farropas, L., Calouro, F., Barradas, A. M., & Carneiro, J. (2011). Soil organic matter dynamics in Portuguese natural and sown rainfed grasslands. *Ecological Modelling*, 222(4), 993–1001.

LANDMARC

SCALING LAND-BASED MITIGATION SOLUTIONS IN SPAIN

LAND-BASED MITIGATION NARRATIVES

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2. Introduction

This report includes a description of a generic nation-wide transition scenario for the implementation of land-based mitigation technologies and practices for the AFOLU sector (agriculture, forestry, and other land use sectors) in Spain. The report shows the outcomes of a series of research steps that have been conducted in this country since the start of the project in June 2020 until the end of 2022:

First, we performed an initial scoping of key LMTs in the case study country. The scoping assessment resulted in a long list of broad portfolios of different LMTs that could be viable within the various case study countries.

Second, following this long list, we developed a short-list LMT portfolio containing key LMTs that would be the most relevant for a given country context. All case study country partners were asked to propose and validate their LMT portfolio through complementary (policy) literature review and with the help of stakeholder interviews (i.e. external validation by relevant country experts and stakeholders). Ex-ante no specific guidance of criteria for LMT portfolio short-listing was provided to allow for a free and open co-design process with stakeholders. The scoping process and results are presented in section 3 of this report (step 1 & 2).

For the case study of Spain, the methodologies of specialised literature review and interviews with experts in the fields of science, public administration, and the professional agricultural and forestry sectors were mainly used.

Third, after the short-listed LMT portfolios were validated, the LANDMARC case study country partners were asked to develop national scaling narratives or storylines for each LMT included in their portfolio. The assessments focusses on climate risks, vulnerabilities as well as socio-economic co-benefits and trade-offs associated with upscaling LMTs in the case study countries. The analysis is based on a broad range of information/literature sources, and stakeholder consultations conducted. This process is supported through a risk and impact assessment (i.e. an online survey and workshops/seminar/webinars) conducted through the LANDMARC tasks 4.1, 4.2 and 5.2. The results of this analysis are a set of LMT narratives which are presented in section 4 of this report.

The stakeholder interviews were conducted in a structured way, so that the responses could be used in the final report in an easily recognisable place in terms of policy aspects, economic performance, or impacts on climate risks.

The research steps are designed to enable both an **analysis of the risks and (climate) impacts of scaling up land-based mitigation and negative emission solutions**. As such this report mainly contributes to objectives 2, 3 and 4 of the six LANDMARC key objectives (see Table 1).

Table 1: LANDMARC project objectives.

	Project key objectives
1	Determine the potential and effectiveness of LMTs in GHGs mitigation using Earth Observation (EO)
2	Improve climate resilience of LMT solutions at the local level for large-scale implementation
3	Assess the risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs of scaling up local LMTs nationally
4	Scaling up LMT solutions to the continental and global level to assess effectiveness
5	Improve current methodologies to estimate emissions and removals for LMTs
6	LMT capacity building and develop new tools and services for decision making

While the results shown in this report represent a mostly qualitative storyline describing the context and impact of scaling up LMTs in a country context, they also enables project partners to proceed with the translation of the outcomes in a manner so that they can serve as direct model input.

Furthermore, these national level assessments provide a testing ground and empirical basis for the continental, and global assessment of the realistic scaling potential of land-based mitigation and negative emission solutions implemented in Work Packages 6 and 7 of the LANDMARC project (**Objective 4**). This report has been produced as part of the LANDMARC project.

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3. Scoping of land-based mitigation and negative emission solutions in Spain

LANDMARC focusses on a particular set of NETPs: carbon capture and geological storage, linked to bioenergy production (BECCS), biochar, and land management practices in the Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use (AFOLU) sector. These are marked by a red line in Fig.1. Sometimes land users employ technologies like biochar in their land management practices. The more industrial negative emission solutions, like direct air capture (DAC) or different carbon capture and utilization options are thereby excluded for further assessment. NEGEM and OCEANNETs are related EU projects that also research the potential of NETPs, where the latter focuses on ocean based NETPs.¹

Figure 1: Scope of the LANDMARC project

3.1 Overview of potential of LMTs in Spain

3.1.1 Introduction

Spain, due to its geographical location and socio-economic characteristics, faces significant risks derived from climate change. Key sectors of the Spanish economy, such as agriculture, forestry, tourism, and transport; closely depend on the climate. Other essential factors for human well-being such as health, biodiversity, or housing also depend on climate.

Climate change is a reality in Spain, and numerous effects have been observed, including an average increase in temperatures of approximately 1.7 °C since pre-industrial times (fig. 2), longer summer

season, more extremely warm nights, longer heatwave events, a decrease in rainfall, disappearance of glaciers, a decrease in average river flows, an expansion of semi-arid climate, warming sea waters, sea-level rise, and acidification of marine waters. The existing models forecast an intensification of these trends in the future. Also, these models project an increase in extreme temperatures, an increase in evapotranspiration, a decrease in aquifer recharge, an increase in drought events, and an increase in torrential rains and floods (Government of Spain, 2020a).

Figure 2. Annual average temperatures for Spain for the period 1901-2018. The gradation from blue to red indicates the increase in temperature. Figure extracted from the Spanish National Plan for Climate Change Adaptation 2021-2030 (Government of Spain, 2020a).

Adaptation and mitigation are two complementary strategies against climate change. The PNACC (Spanish National Plan for Climate Change Adaptation 2021-2030) (Government of Spain, 2020a) aims to coordinate action towards avoiding and lessening the impacts of climate change. This plan emphasizes adaptation to climate change without giving up on climate mitigation, as it can reduce the need and cost of adaptation. **It defines 18 areas of work and specifies objectives and action plans for each. These areas are climate, human health, water, biodiversity, forestry, farming, coasts, urbanism, cultural heritage, energy, transport, industry, tourism, financial system, disaster risk management, research and innovation, education, and security.** The most relevant of these areas for **LANDMARC** are **water, biodiversity, forestry, and farming**. These are reviewed and analyzed in the following sections to assess current and potential LMT use.

3.1.2 Land management practices for wetlands

The PNACC establishes that climate change should be specifically considered in the management of water and water resources. Particularly, the plan aims to lessen the impacts and reduce the risk of extreme events such as droughts and floods. This will be achieved by maintaining a ‘good state’ of the water bodies and their associated ecosystems according to the Water Framework Directive through sustainable practices. In this sense, management plans are expected to be designed with a holistic and integrative perspective, including climate change adaptation, flow management, and pollution control.

From all the planned actions, the most relevant for LANDMARC are those aimed at the recovery of the morphology and dynamics of the water channels. These intend to help regulating the hydrological regime through restoration of meanders, reconnection of flood plains, naturalization of channels, preservation of wetlands, improvement of fluvial continuity, and recovery of floodplain forests. These actions offer multiple co-benefits aside from water regulation that are directly relevant to land mitigation, including biodiversity enhancement, wetland ecosystem restoration, erosion reduction and soil structure improvement. Thus, although not specifically considered in the PNACC, the projected land management practices for water management have the potential of acting as negative emission practices too, as wetlands generally act as carbon sinks (Taillardat et al., 2020). Also, naturalized forests, in this case floodplain forests, can capture carbon continuously for decades (Lewis et al., 2019).

Finally, it is important to highlight that the management of hydrological resources cannot be separated from the management of forest resources. Soil, forests, and water form a triangle of integral management in the territory, which means that hydrology can be considered as a LMT in the strict sense of the term.

3.1.3 Land management practices for forest and biodiversity

Forestry, desertification, hunting, and inland fishing are considered jointly in the PNACC. Forest management is particularly relevant in Spain due to its high forest diversity and its increasing vulnerability to risks enhanced by climate change. These risks include extreme climatic events, drought, desertification, fires, and climatic stress on tree species. The PNACC report acknowledges that climate change should be considered in forest planning and management to guarantee the provision of ecosystem services. There is an emphasis on land degradation and forest fire prevention using adaptive and nature-based solutions, all of which contribute directly or indirectly to land mitigation.

Desertification and land degradation control measures can generate co-benefits for climate change mitigation, biodiversity conservation, and food security. Specific measures to address desertification and land degradation include nature-based solutions for erosion control and restoration of degraded and abandoned areas such as quarries, mining areas, landfills, abandoned agricultural plots, etc. These include afforestation and reforestation projects in degraded areas using native species and general recovery of the native vegetation cover.

The planning instruments for forests and the Spanish forest sector such as the Spanish Forest Strategy, the Spanish Forest Plan, the Forest Resources Management Plans, or the Spanish Strategy for the Conservation and Sustainable Use of Forest Resources, among others, coordinate the forest policies and allow synergies with other sectors that influence forest management while creating conditions for the multifunctional potential of Spanish forests to be sustainably managed. Climate considerations must be incorporated into the available forest policy instruments to ensure efficient and sustainable management.

The available climatic projections for Spain indicate an increase in extreme climatic events, especially during summer, leading to extended heat waves dominated by high temperatures and low relative humidity. These conditions generate a greater tendency for the forest fuel to burn, increasing the risk of large forest fires. Thus, it is important to consider climate change in forest fire prevention and extinction plans, and in restoration projects for burnt areas. The knowledge of forest ecology allows us to address the expected impact of climate change and manage landscapes to increase their resilience to fires. The integration of regional policies and the involvement of different stakeholders, together with the promotion of agroforestry systems and traditional uses such as pastoralism, are a good mechanism to implement adaptive measures in the face of the increase in the danger of fires. This is highly relevant for LANDMARC, as a successful forest fire prevention can be considered a land management mitigation practice. As mentioned earlier, naturalized forests capture and store carbon

over decades (Lewis et al., 2019). Hence, forest fires lead to large carbon release events. These events can make up to 50% of the global emissions of CO₂ and NO_x (Galanter et al., 2000). In certain forest ecosystems, the contribution by forest fires to carbon release is similar to that of deforestation (Aragão et al., 2018). Post-fire carbon dynamics and fluxes are not completely understood and depend on the specific forest ecosystem. While some forest ecosystems tend to keep releasing carbon over several years after a fire event, others immediately compensate for the release of carbon thanks to natural regeneration (Goetz et al., 2012; Houghton et al., 2012).

In addition to forest, the PNACC expects natural heritage, biodiversity, and protected areas to be affected by climate change and aims to improve ecosystem resilience. Issues such as increasing ecosystem disturbance, habitat fragmentation and the presence of invasive species are worsened by climate change. Consequently, climate change must be factored in for future conservation schemes and protected area management plans.

Some of the actions projected to enhance climate change adaptation for natural heritage, biodiversity, and protected areas can potentially act as negative emission land management practices and be directly relevant for LANDMARC. These include the creation of green corridors to increase habitat connectivity, interventions to increase the permeability of the territory to species movement, interventions aimed at improving the provision of regulating ecosystem services, changes in practices to reduce the pressure on ecosystems, and ecological restoration projects. Interestingly, the PNACC also states that areas that are highly relevant to mitigate the impacts of climate change will be identified, restored, and protected. The report does not provide more detail on this topic, but this hints that, even though the primary focus of the PNACC is climate change adaptation, mitigation is also considered in this national plan.

3.1.4 Land management practices and negative emission technologies for croplands and grasslands

Agriculture, livestock, fishing, aquaculture, and food are considered under the same title in the PNACC document. The plan aims to adapt these sectors to the climate change projections to ensure food security through increased ecosystem resiliency and promotion of sustainability in the food system. Agriculture, livestock, fishing, and aquaculture are strategic sectors in Spain, with great economic, social, territorial, and environmental importance. The food sector is also one of the most important in the Spanish economy and the food industry is the leading industrial sector. The area devoted to agricultural and livestock activities in Spain, farmland, and area of main use for pastures, is around 25 million hectares, which is half of the total area of the country. Also, the agricultural sector can act as a net emitter or net carbon sink depending on the agricultural practices applied. Carbon emissions by the agricultural sector are derived from the use of fossil fuels, the use of fertilizers, the burning of agricultural residues, livestock, rice fields, liming of soils and the use of urea. Almost half of the emissions from this sector are generated by the use of fertilizers and soil management, while the other half is caused by livestock (enteric fermentation and manure management).

As in previous sections, management actions to increase resilience also help in climate change mitigation. Essential pillars of the strategy include preservation of soil and water resources and biodiversity conservation. Organic farming, conservation agriculture, reduced tillage, precision agriculture, extensive livestock (low density), appropriate manure and slurry management, cattle diet modifications, use of renewable energy sources, and use of anaerobic biodigesters are favoured practices. Other proposed adaptive measures are floodplain forest restoration to protect soils in agricultural areas, crop rotations, crop diversification, avoidance of bare soil, incorporation of pruning waste to the soil. These are resource-saving measures that can potentially be climate change mitigating as well, and thus directly relevant to LANDMARC. Particularly, grassland management for livestock can be a very effective and resilient land mitigation practice (Dass et al., 2018). Increasing pasture species diversity and applying compost soil amendments can constitute carbon sinks (DeLonge et al., 2013; Hewins et al., 2018; Hungate et al., 2017).

3.2 Determining the LMT scope for Spanish national level simulation modelling

In this section, we discuss which set of LMTs we will study in detail in Spain. From the perspective of the National Plan for Adaptation to Climate Change 2021-2030 (Government of Spain, 2020a), forest and agricultural uses represent the LMTs with the greatest impact. Table 1 summarises the main LMTs and indicates which ones are included in the short-list of the LANDMARC LMT portfolio. The main rationales for including the various LMTs in the national level scaling simulation assessment are presented below.

Table 1. Long-listing of relevant land based LMTs in Spain.

LMTs	Specification	Included in national LANDMARC LMT portfolio
Grasslands	Dehesas (Spain) and montados (Portugal) management (agroforestry)	YES
	Grasslands for soil regeneration and carbon sequestration	YES
Agriculture	Reduced tillage	NO
	Harvest residues, crop rotation	NO
	AD residue based on organic fertilizers/digestates	NO
	Soil conservation and regeneration	NO
	Landscape management in agricultural lands (hedgerows etc.)	NO
Forest land	Forest planning and management	YES
	Afforestation/reforestation of degraded lands	YES
	Forest fire prevention	NO
	Watershed and forest management	NO
Wetlands	Wetland conservation	NO
	Floodplain forest recovery	NO

Forests

Land use and forest planning in the medium- and long-term faces, in the climate change scenario, important challenges in Spain. Monitoring and inventory of forest resources need to reflect the continuous change in environmental variables spatially and over time. It must also consider the ecological and economic value of the mitigation potential of the forest and make this value compatible with other traditional uses.

The CO₂ capture and emission processes in a forest constitute a complex system with four groups of carbon storage agents: aboveground biomass, root biomass, decomposing organic matter and forest products stored outside the forest (that is, wood, paper, etc.). Each of these reservoirs has different average lifetimes, after which they end up being incorporated back into the atmosphere. Therefore, it

can be affirmed that forests act as sinks since they store large amounts of carbon for long periods (wood) and by increasing their biomass annually due to growth. On the other hand, they are also sources of emission due to natural mortality, fires, deforestation, and decomposition of forest products, plants and plant organs (Montero et al., 2005).

Despite these sources of emission, managing forests for carbon sequestration is a cost-effective way of mitigating climate change. This can be achieved by regulating tree density, rotation periods, and thinning regimes to achieve mitigation, without increasing forest management cost and increasing carbon capture by Spanish forests from 35 to 42 MtCO₂e (Albiac et al., 2017).

One of the main initiatives of the Government in Spain is to convert plots from various land uses to forest land and promote sustainable forest management (Government of Spain, 2020b). Specifically, converting unproductive and degraded agricultural lands to grasslands or forests can increase soil carbon sequestration, although more studies are needed on this topic (Rodríguez Martín et al., 2016). In Spain, the Agricultural Land Afforestation Program started more than 25 years ago thanks to the Common Agricultural Policy (Vadell et al., 2019). This program has successfully improved ecosystem service provision including soil conservation, regulation of the hydrological regime, biodiversity indicators, carbon sequestration in vegetation and soil through trees.

Afforestation/reforestation of degraded lands

One of the main initiatives of the Government in Spain is to convert plots from various land uses to forest land and promote sustainable forest management (Government of Spain, 2020b). Specifically, converting unproductive and degraded agricultural lands to grasslands or forests can increase soil carbon sequestration, although more studies are needed on this topic (Rodríguez Martín et al., 2016). In Spain, the Agricultural Land Afforestation Program started more than 25 years ago thanks to the Common Agricultural Policy (Vadell et al., 2019). This program has successfully improved ecosystem service provision including soil conservation, regulation of the hydrological regime, biodiversity indicators, carbon sequestration in vegetation and soil through trees.

Agroforestry (dehesas)

A great proportion of the extensive livestock management (low-density cattle) takes place within dehesas. These agroforestry systems derive from the Mediterranean oak (holm oaks, cork oaks and oaks) forest by continuous human intervention over centuries. The result is a low tree density forest that is adapted to the productive needs of the nearby human populations.

The Agroforestry system Montado, in Portugal, and Dehesa, in Spain, is a High Nature Value system characterized by a high complexity as a result of the interactions between climate, soil, pasture (natural pastures, fertilized natural pastures, and sown biodiverse permanent pastures rich in legumes), trees (e.g., pure or mix stands of cork oak, holm oak, stone pine), and animals (e.g., sheep, pigs, cows, goats). Montado/Dehesa is one of the most prominent and best preserved low-intensity farming systems in Europe. The integration of traditional land-use and biodiversity conservation that is characteristic of this system is an exemplar for the wise management of the countryside. As well as the Montado

regeneration is the last frontier to the desertification process. Moreover, with a good management plan, these systems can be strong carbon sinks with low GEE emissions.

The aforementioned different structural layers of dehesas (tree, shrub, and pasture) can be managed separately as intrinsically sustainable managed forest or grassland systems, as both benefit from the ecological interactions among the different biotic elements of the dehesa. Besides, one of the main objectives of the Government of Spain to increase carbon sequestration is to promote agroforestry systems such as dehesas for livestock production (Government of Spain, 2020b).

Grasslands (grassland management in dehesas agro-ecosystem)

Grassland management in Spain and Portugal is closely linked to the multifunctional agroforestry systems known as dehesas or montados. There is grassland and sometimes also a shrub layer under the tree canopy. In the dehesas, acorns, pasture and twigs are used for free-range livestock feeding. This livestock use is compatibilized with other uses such as agriculture, forestry, hunting, or recreation in this multifunctional landscape. These agroforestry systems are exclusive of the Mediterranean region and have great cultural relevance, especially in rural areas. Besides, their inherent landscape complexity and biodiversity enhance overall landscape connectivity, strengthen biodiversity indicators, and have great potential for climate change mitigation. There are several examples of successful and sustainable dehesa management, which have enormous potential for scaling up and can be an example to follow for territories facing sustainability challenges.

Also, there are 1,420,000 hectares of dehesa grasslands in the Extremadura region, equivalent to 57% of the useful agricultural area. This is why in this assessment of negative emission land management practices in Spain, agroforestry management and grassland management are considered described jointly in this section.

Currently, the potential value of the dehesa systems and grasslands as carbon fixers is not fully known, and the relationship between biodiversity and carbon sequestration in these pastures is understudied. Dehesas are highly resilient and multifunctional systems that can ensure food security and biodiversity conservation in a climate change scenario, and contribute consistently to mitigation (Pateiro et al., 2020). A study in central-western Spain found that an increase in forest cover in dehesas could benefit long term carbon capture in the soil (Howlett et al., 2011). Also, particularly for the grassland portion of dehesa systems, managing for livestock, increasing pasture species diversity, and applying compost soil amendments can act as resilient net carbon sinks (Dass et al., 2018; DeLonge et al., 2013; Hewins et al., 2018; Hungate et al., 2017). In the case of dehesas, these compost amendments can come from waste generated during pruning and clearing of the tree and shrub layers of the system, decreasing the need for external inputs.

3.3 Discussion on short-listing LMTs

3.3.1 Land management dynamics in Spanish agriculture

In general, agriculture plays a double role in the face of climate change, placing itself, on the one hand, as a victim of disturbances derived from meteorological phenomena, and on the other, acting as a source of greenhouse gases that causes climate change itself. The agricultural area shows a decreasing trend (figure 4). This evolution of agricultural land area results in the estimated greenhouse gas emissions shown in table 3.

Figure 4. Evolution and projections of the agriculture land area, in hectares, between 1990 and 2020 (ha) (Government of Spain, 2015).

Table 3. Projection of net CO₂ emissions in agricultural lands in 2015 and 2020 (Gg CO₂-eq) (Government of Spain, 2015).

	2015	2020
Agriculture land use	- 2421	- 2726

3.3.2 Land use change dynamics. Grasslands.

The grasslands land use in Spain shows a decreasing trend, as shown in figure 3. This is likely a result of increasing stabling and feed use in livestock production. This intensive livestock production contributes to climate change, while the agroforestry system described in earlier sections (grasslands within dehesa systems) are likely a carbon sink. As a result of the evolution of grasslands area, the estimated CO₂ absorptions are presented in table 2.

Figure 3. Evolution and projections of grasslands area, in hectares, between 1990 and 2020 (Government of Spain, 2015).

Table 2. Projection of net CO2 emissions in grasslands in 2015 and 2020 (Gg CO2-eq) (Government of Spain, 2015)

	2015	2020
Grasslands land use	1276	1832

3.3.3 Forest management

Forests are the main stable carbon sink and reservoir of biodiversity on the Iberian Peninsula. Its sustainable and profitable management, conservation and restoration are considered priorities and are part of the Spanish strategy for adaptation and mitigation of climate change. Forest area shows a stable trend over the last years, after a surge between 1992 and 2005, when the majority of the afforestation projects from the Agricultural Land Afforestation Program took place (Vadell et al., 2019) (figure 5). This evolution of forest land area results in the estimated greenhouse gas emissions shown in table 4.

Figure 5. Evolution and projections of the forest land area, in hectares, between 1990 and 2020. (Government of Spain, 2015).

Table 4. Projection of net CO₂ emissions in forest lands in 2015 and 2020 (Gg CO₂-eq) (Government of Spain, 2015)

	2015	2020
Forestry land use	- 34119	- 34157

4. Co-design of LMT narratives

4.1 Introduction

The list of LMTs has been narrowed down to four for further analysis within the LANDMARC project. These include:

- dehesas (Spain) and montados (Portugal) management (agroforestry),
- grasslands for soil regeneration and carbon sequestration,
- forest planning and management, and
- afforestation/reforestation of degraded lands.

These LMTs are expected to have high carbon sequestration potential in Spain and could provide an additional source of income for farmers in a hypothetical carbon market. The qualitative narratives of the four LMTs for Spain are presented in the following sections.

4.2 Dehesas (Spain) and montados (Portugal) management (agroforestry)

4.2.1 Introduction

Agroforestry systems such as dehesas and montados could be key to achieve climate targets (Kay et al., 2019b). Dehesas and montados are heterogeneous “savannah” agroforestry ecosystems that include a grass layer, a tree layer and sometimes also a shrub layer. All these elements contribute to carbon sequestration within the system. This traditional multifunctional landscape and land use holds great potential for carbon sequestration, as resources are used very efficiently (VVAA, 2013). Carbon sequestration in dehesas could be achieved through a combination of pasture, tree and shrub growth.

Figure 5. Dehesa agroecosystem in Montehermoso (Extremadura, Spain). C16.

4.2.2 Policy context

Agroforestry systems are recognized in the EU Strategy of Adaptation to Climate Change, the European Forestry Strategy and the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change as relevant adaptation and mitigation mechanisms (in+dehesa, 2020).

The Long Term Decarbonization Strategy 2050 for the Spanish economy aims to reach climate neutrality by 2050. This strategy identifies the promotion of agroforestry systems such as dehesas and montados and their regeneration as one of its main lines of work (Government of Spain, 2020c). The traditional management of dehesas is inherently sustainable, as it is a multifunctional use of the land that takes advantage of the ecological interactions between the different elements of the ecosystem (trees, pastures, shrubs, livestock).

Which national policies exist that address the LMT?

Considering the ambitions demonstrated by the European institutions in terms of relaunching the economy, protecting the environment and increasing biodiversity, namely through the recently approved European Recovery Plan and the European Ecological Pact - “Green Deal” – the Confederation of Portuguese Farmers (CAP) is promoting activities related to agriculture in a context of sustainable exploitation of resources, in line with modern concepts of environmental protection, mitigation of climate change and combating desertification.

However, as far as political aspects are concerned, the lack of support from the institutions for the countryside should be highlighted, as the importance of the countryside in society and the economy is not really valued.

In addition, there is a very long and heavy bureaucracy, which makes it difficult for landowners to improve their farms. The policies are geared towards extreme ecological conservation, not allowing the owner to carry out the uses that have traditionally been made on the farm for decades and that have given rise to what we see today. Everything is seen from a regulatory point of view and not from the reality of the countryside.

Which actors are currently applying the LMT (e.g. land users, forest owners farmers)?

In Spain and Portugal, there are highly qualified farmers (“front runners”) who use PA techniques (state-of-the-art technology), conservation farming, biological farming and the use of composting, which will allow a reduction in emissions from synthetic fertilizers and their replacement with organic fertilizers, a reduction in emissions from livestock systems by increasing the quality of the diet and installing biodiverse pastures. Farmers and many producer associations improved their products and processes, such as fruits and vegetables, as well as olive oil, wine or cork, thus enabling them to compete with the best producers in the world. In the agricultural sector, there is professional training that is mandatory, by national or community imposition, in which CAP develops a considerable activity, and training to develop specific technical skills. However, there are still a significant number of companies that do not have specific training. Moreover, in recent years, there has been a growing

market interest in organic products that will force greater promotion of national production and exports, a better organization of production and marketing and a reduction in the external food deficit.

It should be highlighted that the Spanish dehesas provide high quality foodstuffs, among which Iberian pork products, such as Iberian ham, stand out.

Politicians and administrations need to have a better knowledge of the countryside in order to reach agreements that facilitate the sustainable management of the land and at the same time are profitable for the landowners. The amount of exploitation generated by the dehesa and all that surrounds it has been forgotten.

In addition, there is a lack of political support for the regeneration of the dehesas, as well as for cultural work such as pruning, clearing, planting, etc.

Which funds are available for the LMT?

Currently, the economic situation is unfavourable for carrying out improvements in the dehesas due to the high cost of materials and new techniques and technologies, as well as the weather conditions, which make it difficult for improvements related to pastures, trees or livestock to be successful.

With regard to business risks, the dehesas face major challenges such as high initial investment, due to the high cost of the land and the long period necessary for its amortisation.

In terms of social aspects, it is important to say that there is a lack of specialised labour, with knowledge about the proper management of these fields. The new generations are not motivated to work in the fields; they see it as a very demanding and unprofitable job.

As far as environmental aspects are concerned, we have already mentioned that there are many benefits generated by the dehesas related to the soil, plants, animals and birds. For all these reasons, they should not be abandoned when it comes to carrying out actions such as cork harvesting, tree pruning, pest treatment, grazing or tree regeneration.

In general terms, the overall amount of additional investments in some of the technologies identified, which can lead to reductions in fertiliser emissions and increases in carbon sequestration on agricultural land, pastures and forests, amounts to around EUR 570 million over the period 2021-2050, equivalent to an annual amount of around 19 million euros.

4.2.3 Current land use and potential land-use competition

Dehesas are traditional land use systems that have been occurring in the Iberian Peninsula for centuries. In Spain, dehesas cover an approximate area of 3.5 million ha. Most of them are privately owned and dedicated to livestock. Expansion of dehesa management as a LMT would not necessarily mean the geographical expansion of dehesa system themselves. Instead, carbon capture could be

included as one of the objectives of the multifunctional management plan of the dehesa system. Consequently, dehesa management as an LMT would not compete with other land uses.

What is the national (1) historic and (2) current land use of the LMT and how is this projected to develop over the coming decades (2030 & 2050)?

The management of the agricultural sector aims to a more effective climate action and better protection of the environment and biodiversity. To reduce emissions and increase sequestration, the agricultural sector must focus on a green scheme in which there are more equitable payments to farmers when they consider the environment, climate change and the country in their practices. In the case of the livestock sector, emission reductions can occur through improvements in food digestibility and in livestock effluent management systems. The use of biodiverse pastures has a very important contribution to the net sequestration associated with the use of agricultural land in 2050 (e.g., biodiverse pastures covering the soil in between lines of oliveyards and vineyards, sequestering carbon, reducing nutrients leaching and soil erosion).

In addition, the expansion of organic and conservation agriculture, and PA will allow a reduction in emissions associated with animal effluents and the use of fertilizers. Therefore, the emissions reduction in agriculture is occurring at a slower rate than in other sectors, inherent to the characteristics of the associated biophysical systems, which means that its weight in national emissions will be between 29% and 34% by 2050, depending on whether one considers or not the contribution of land uses.

The main effects of dehesas on the local environment are several:

- Dehesas as carbon sinks, through both the woodland and pasture present.
- In terms of soil protection, adequate vegetation cover, through trees and grasses, controls erosion processes and in turn contributes to the balance of the water balance.
- In terms of diversity, the high biodiversity present in a pasture system is evident, both in terms of plant life, macro-fungi, macro-fauna and birds.
- The scenic value of the landscape is important in that it prevents fragmentation of the landscape, due to the diversity of habitats present.
- Nowadays there is a high demand from society for this biodiversity present in the dehesa, which is reflected in ornithological tourism or the increasingly demanded orchid tourism, both of which nowadays move large amounts of money.
- As a cleared Mediterranean ecosystem, the risk of fire is lower in the dehesa than in a forest with closed undergrowth where, in the event of a fire, the area would be completely destroyed.

It is very necessary to include pastureland systems in national policy, because they are suffering a great decline, and in less than 50 years many dehesas will have disappeared as we know them today.

Furthermore, society is unaware of the existence of aid or subsidies related to the regeneration of woodland. The dehesas are very close to society, but they are not valued. In the past, dehesas were used in a more sustainable way, but nowadays there is no respect for the environment (rubbish, excess of vehicles) which contributes to the degradation of the vegetation cover and the biodiversity of the environment. In short, there is a lack of environmental awareness.

The positive impact of the dehesa on the daily life of rural communities due to its diversified uses has been forgotten, as well as the lack of awareness of the benefits it can generate. All this leads to a deterioration of the traditional pasture system and a loss of biodiversity.

With regard to business risks, dehesas face major challenges such as a high initial investment with a long payback period. Currently it is difficult to invest in dehesa, due to climate change, because if it is affecting 70-100 year old holm oaks, which are drying out, the new trees that are put in place for tree regeneration may not survive these episodes of extreme conditions. Therefore, in addition to the high economic costs for investment, there are also climate-related risks.

In terms of environmental aspects, changes in land use have a major negative impact on the dehesa.

The opportunities are many: it provides a great increase in biodiversity in the environment. Water and soil management is essential for the conservation of pastures and to avoid soil degradation.

Are there other land use developments that compete with the expansion of the LMT, and if so, how do those affect the scaling-up of the LMTs?

The evolution of the Spanish economy and society in the last 50 years, although positive, has not stopped the population exodus to large urban centers and the progressive aging of the rural population, leading to the abandonment of territories and traditional activities in agriculture. Consequently, it gave rise to the progressive extension of forest use, often spontaneous and not managed with great concentration of fuel loads and strong exposure to rural fire hazard, which are added to the destruction of the forest and the goods and services it produces, further promoting the abandonment and masculinization of these territories.

However, at this stage and considering cropland optimization the only way to go is to consider the usage of sustainable agriculture practices, namely PA techniques and others that for sure will start to exist in the fields to solve the labor deficit in agriculture (e.g., robotics).

In some areas, species increasingly adapted to extreme conditions such as drought are appearing, for example *Crataegus monogyna* or *Cistus ladanifer*, which appear on degraded land and are capable of adapting to more extreme conditions. In turn, these species of low ecological value contribute to reducing erosion on degraded land and therefore favour the establishment of other less resilient species.

Dehesa is a system heavily affected by pests, which is being aggravated by drought conditions. It may be that in 50 years there will be very few trees left in the dehesas, it should be borne in mind that

these are ancient trees. With the right planning, there would be no major difficulties in the maintenance of dehesas, nor do they involve a high economic cost for the landowner. There are new technologies available on the market that can be applied in pasture systems and whose economic cost is not so high. It is observed that the application of these new technologies in the future will be the main tools for detecting problems in the pastures, such as dry trees or the state of the pastures. Another aspect to be highlighted is the over-exploitation of livestock due to high stocking rates.

In terms of political barriers or opportunities, there is a lack of support for pasture systems, and the necessary measures for tree regeneration are not applied. There is also excessive bureaucracy in the processing of permits for actions and exploitation in pastureland systems, which hinders the maintenance of the ecosystem.

4.2.4 *Climate risks & sensitivities*

Extreme temperatures could trigger mortality events in trees and higher incidence of forest fires. In addition, a shifting pattern of temperatures and rainfall could gradually eliminate trees from dehesas due to stress and vulnerability to diseases. Previous studies have found that forest species composition is changing as a result of climate change (Batllori et al., 2020). This could mean that the current locations of dehesas might not have the ideal environmental conditions for the typical dehesa trees (*Quercus* spp.) to thrive in the future. Climate projections for Spain include the worsening of drought periods. Dehesa ecosystems are resilient to drought disturbances (Martínez-Valderrama et al., 2021).

The main risk factors related to climate and the management and conservation of the dehesas considered in Spain are drought as the main problem, together with heat waves, which are increasingly present and prolonged over time. Forest fires are also increasingly present due to the drought we are currently experiencing in our fields and especially in nearby areas. The most relevant periods of drought in living memory are those of the early 1980s and 1990s. As for heat waves, the last few summers have been more frequent and longer in summer.

Furthermore, the main visible effects of the dehesa on the local environment are several. On the one hand, environmental, affecting both soil structure and water balance and soil protection. When there is rainfall and a good autumn and spring, the vegetation cover is excellent and everything is in balance. In terms of diversity, the high biodiversity present in a dehesa is evident, both in terms of plants, animals and birds. The scenic value of the landscape is important, we all like to see a green and flowery dehesa in autumn and spring. The risk of fire is lower compared to a forest that is more enclosed and with more tree vegetation, but in the event of fire the losses are greater because the trees are centuries old.

It is also important to mention that it is an ecosystem with a high capacity to adapt to extreme conditions such as the current drought, and this may be due to the diversity of products it generates, as well as its agrarian, forestry and grassland use. The progressive increase in temperatures, the absence of rainfall and the distribution of the latter are becoming more and more common. More

concentrated and torrential rainfall combined with higher temperatures affects both fauna and flora in the dehesa as they are not used to it and can lead to alterations in their cycles, such as flowering or acorn production. For example, the torrential rains in November 1997 in Badajoz led to episodes of soil loss that were very significant in comparison with the average values for the area. This soil loss was due both to the torrential rains and to tillage practices, which showed that good agricultural practices are very important in agroforestry systems.

4.2.5 Economic implications

The lack of generational replacement and the age of the managers of agroforestry systems is an obstacle to the implementation of new technologies in the dehesas. In addition to the current difficulty in finding labour to carry out field work and the lack of training of this labour force in specific tasks. The economic situation also hinders the management and application of technologies, due to the high costs, which leads the owner to depend on subsidies for such implementation.

In terms of political risks, despite the fact that the dehesa is highly regarded at national level, there is little support for this agroforestry system. This is often due to a lack of knowledge on the part of the institutions, which is reflected in the inadequacy of aid. For example, the European Union does not fully understand dehesa because it cannot be classified as either a forest or a crop.

In Spain, although much importance is given to the dehesa and it is well considered, only in Andalusia is there a more up-to-date law on the Dehesa. In Extremadura, for example, the legislation regulating this agro-forest-grass system is outdated and out of date.

This political situation means that the European Union often allocates large amounts of money to rural development, and therefore also to the dehesa, and yet it is lost due to a lack of knowledge or inefficiency in the management of the funds earmarked for this agroforestry system. In addition, the lengthy bureaucracy is a major obstacle to the proper management of the agroforestry system. The aids available take a long time to be resolved, the owner has to anticipate a high investment and then assume a great uncertainty for the collection of these aids.

On the social side, the lack of generational replacement, the lack of interest on the part of young people in agricultural work and the lack of training in specific jobs have already been mentioned. Furthermore, there is a certain reluctance to change the mentality that involves the application of new management tools or the inclusion of women in farm work.

Socially, it can be said that the dehesas are very well regarded by society in general, especially by the rural population, due to the fact that most families in rural environments depend on agricultural and livestock activity and in many cases on the dehesa.

The main business risks are reflected in the high costs of agroforestry land, which makes these lands inaccessible to young people, and the fact that most of the land is inherited, which is leading to land division. In addition, high investments are required for machinery and livestock. All this means that in addition to the high investment, there is a high uncertainty of payback.

The existing risks and benefits generated in the dehesa are directly related to the good agricultural practices developed in these systems. It is also worth highlighting the opportunities that exist in terms of R&D related to the dehesa, as many related R&D projects are currently being developed, as well as various calls for proposals in which these agroforestry systems are being considered.

Most dehesas are already actively managed for livestock raising. Adjustments to the multifunctional management could make livestock compatible with mitigation and open a new source of income for farmers under a potential carbon capture market. A life cycle assessment of dehesas under organic management found that carbon sequestration values were extremely high. Up to 89% of the carbon emissions were compensated for meat producing ruminants, and 100% for dairy goats and Iberian pigs fed in montanera (making use of the grass and acorns within the dehesa) (Horrillo et al., 2020). Agroforestry systems such as dehesas tend to have slightly lower revenues than agriculture. However, the inclusion of monetize positive externalities such as carbon capture and storage payments could increase the profitability of agroforestry (Kay et al., 2019a). It is estimated that 0.93 tC/ha/year is sequestered in aerial biomass in dehesas (in+dehesa, 2020). More general estimates for agroforestry systems suggest a range between 0.09 and 7.29 tC/ha/year (Kay et al., 2019b).

4.2.6 *Co-benefits and trade-offs*

Conversion from conventional farming activities to agroforestry approaches could capture between 1.4 and 43.4% of the agricultural carbon emissions in the European Union and Switzerland (Kay et al., 2019b). Also, agroforestry systems such as dehesas and montados optimize the use of resources and have very low pollution externalities from soil and nutrient losses (Kay et al., 2019a). Dehesa systems are traditional landscapes with great aesthetic, historical and ethnographic value, and are frequently visited by eco-tourists. In addition, they are inherently biodiverse, hosting endangered flora and fauna (amphibians, birds) in many cases. Studies have found that agroforestry both increases biodiversity (mean species abundance) and carbon sequestration opportunities (Nunez et al., 2020). The pasture management carried out in dehesa ecosystems for livestock helps preventing erosion and floods (Fuentes Pazos et al., 2018).

The main visible effects of the dehesa on the local environment are several. Well-managed agroforestry systems, i.e., with good agricultural practices for their management, contribute on the one hand to increasing their carbon sequestration capacity and on the other hand to the reduction of emissions into the atmosphere.

In addition, a well-managed agroforestry system contributes to increasing the system's capacity for soil nutrient retention, improved water balance, soil protection and soil macrofauna.

On the other hand, the fact that the dehesa is characterised by a diversity of habitats, areas with more or less density of scrub or woodland, pastures or aquifers, contributes or generates an added value to the landscape. Biodiversity in the dehesa is favoured by the implementation of good practices in agroforestry systems for both flora and fauna.

In terms of resilience, well-managed dehesas through the implementation of good agricultural practices contribute to better adaptation to climatic conditions, as well as being species adapted to the environment. The resilience or capacity of an agroforestry system to adapt to changing conditions is directly related to the climate and the implementation of good agricultural practices.

On the other hand, being an agroforestry system with scattered trees and grazing livestock, the probability of a major forest fire is considerably reduced.

4.2.7 *Risks associated with scaling up*

The main risk to scaling up would be relating to climate change, as dehesa ecosystems could be dramatically altered by shifts in temperature and rainfall patterns. It must be understood that the dehesas are vulnerable to increased periods and intensity of drought, and this in the Iberian Peninsula has effects, among them, a greater risk of advancing desertification. Careful planning is required to ensure that specific dehesa locations will still be environmentally adequate for *Quercus* spp. trees in the future. This is highly relevant, as these trees grow slowly, are hard to replace and are a key element of dehesa and montado systems. In addition, climate change could limit water availability, hindering the productivity of dehesas (in+dehesa, 2020).

4.2.8 *Research gaps*

More information on the carbon sequestration potential of dehesas and montados ecosystems is required. Also, life cycle assessments of meat and dairy products of dehesas and montados are needed for accurate estimations of the dehesa carbon sink.

4.3 Grasslands for soil regeneration and carbon sequestration

4.3.1 *Introduction*

Grasslands and pastures are the most common land cover in the planet, covering about 25% of the Earth. Even though many of these grasslands are degraded, they still store large amounts of carbon and hold great mitigation potential, especially in underground biomass. Grassland and pasture soil amendments for increased organic matter and productivity using compost constitutes a net carbon sink (DeLonge et al., 2013; Hewins et al., 2018). Increasing pasture diversity also captures carbon (Hungate et al., 2017). Moderate livestock loads could also increase the amount of carbon stored in the soil, although this depends on the particular environmental characteristics of the site (Hewins et al., 2018; Rolinski et al., 2018).

Grasslands have the availability of capturing carbon and also emit GHG. Grasslands are generally expected to have high biomass turnover, productivity and nutrient cycle, and only moderate capacity for carbon sequestration in biomass when compared to woody communities. Therefore, not all area available for sown biodiverse grassland is available for sequestering carbon and neutralize emissions.

A particular activity, taking place in grazed lands is reported and accounted for under “grassland remaining grassland”: Sown Biodiverse Permanent Pastures Rich in Legumes (SBPPRL) sown biodiverse permanent grassland rich in legumes. Sown biodiverse grasslands are based on a diverse mixture of about twenty different species, many of which (approximately 30-50%) are legumes. These grasslands are more productive than the baseline land use system – spontaneous natural grasslands. Productivity is accompanied by an increase in soil organic matter (SOM) and correspondent carbon sequestration. Teixeira et al. (2011) analyzed the effect from a shift from natural to sown biodiverse grasslands, and calculations based on this work estimated a carbon sequestration factor of 6.48 tCO₂.ha-1.yr-1 for a period of 10 years. Most of the time, these grasslands are grazed directly by cattle, sheep or goats and result from the seeding with improved and selected seeds. Thus, grazing intensity and opportunity can influence pasture growth and thus affect soil carbon storage. Both undergrazing and overgrazing can decrease soil carbon build-up. In addition, pastures that favor the intercropping of different species should be used. It increases grassland productivity by increasing soil carbon sequestration.

A grassland study showed that the composition of the species community is sensitive to CO₂ increase, which has implications for its stability and resilience. For example, in an annual Mediterranean grassland after three years of trials, species diversity decreased with increasing CO₂, increased with increasing precipitation and showed no effect with increasing temperature. In sown grassland, the increase in CO₂ favored legumes.

The increase in climate variability, with more frequent occurrence of extreme events will also have a negative effect on agricultural activity as it will increase the uncertainty associated with different agricultural systems. On the other hand, the increase in extreme events can lower crop productivity more than the effect of increasing average values. This results from the fact that the impact of extreme events largely depends on the phenological state of the crop at that time. The more frequent occurrence of more intense rainfall will have a negative impact on productivity as it increases the occurrence of periods of saturated soil and, consequently, of stress for crops. Those events will also have impacts at the level of soil erosion.

4.3.2 Policy context

The Spanish Long Term Decarbonization Strategy 2050, which aims to reach climate neutrality by 2050, identifies the increase of carbon content in soils as one of its main lines of work (Government of Spain, 2020c). The Common Agricultural Policy, in its first pillar, promotes *greening*. This implies the application of sustainable practices that would have an indirect positive effect on carbon sequestration (EIP-AGRI, 2018).

Which national policies exist that address the LMT?

According to the trajectories for carbon neutrality of the Spanish economy by 2050, it is necessary to ensure the capacity for carbon sequestration by increasing the organic matter content in grasslands, especially in areas with sown, improved, permanent and biodiverse grasslands. The use of biodiverse

grassland has a very important contribution to the net sequestration associated with the use of agricultural land in 2050.

In terms of environmental risks, a pasture plot, with optimal vegetation cover, considerably reduces soil erosion, as well as reducing emissions compared to bare soil. The opportunities generated by a pasture cover increase biodiversity and improve water and soil management.

There is a lack of political support for grassland, due to lack of awareness and knowledge, which leads to a lack of funding for grassland. Lack of knowledge and awareness of the benefits of grassland such as reduced erosion, increased biodiversity, increased organic matter and therefore increased carbon assimilation and storage capacity.

With regard to the CAP, there is a lack of coordination between the different administrations, which means that the new CAP (2023-2027) in Spain is not updated for the most widespread crops currently grown.

Bureaucracy is also long and tedious in Spain, which hinders the development of new techniques and knowledge in general.

There is a lot of uncertainty in the income regime, there is a popular saying: "Any business that depends on the sky, is not a business", it reflects the reality of the Extremadura countryside.

Which actors are currently applying the LMT (e.g. land users, forest owners farmers)?

In a similar way to croplands, the expansion of biological and conservation farming and PA, as well as permanent grasslands, will reduce emissions associated with fertilizer use and animal effluents, and increase carbon sequestration resulting from increases in organic matter content in the soil. These approaches are highly being used by highly qualified farmers who use state-of-the-art technology, including sowing biodiverse grasslands which induce other environmental benefits, such as the preservation of natural and ecological resources, promotion of biodiversity and/or improvements in animal welfare.

The high costs of the technology right now make it difficult to access and implement. As well as the lack of knowledge and lack of training on the part of farmers and landowners, which makes it necessary to hire specialised labour and therefore increases costs. The failure of the application of new technologies is based on the high costs of both equipment and specialised labour for their application, which is necessary due to the lack of knowledge on the part of landowners about the use of such equipment.

With regard to social risks, there is a lack of generational change, the new generations do not want to work in the countryside. There is also a lack of knowledge about pasture cultivation, as society does not consider pasture as a crop that needs management and agronomy.

Which funds are available for the LMT?

Markets in grassland are regulated by the CAP and the future lies in achieving a circular economy.

From a financial point of view, it currently takes between 300-400 €/ha to establish one hectare of grassland. High capital costs are needed due to very high land prices, as well as a long payback period.

In the new CAP there are three new lines related to pasture: low carbon agriculture, which is achieved with spontaneous or sown biodiverse plant cover, agroecology, favouring the biodiversity of agroecosystems, and crop rotation. Payments in the new CAP for pastures are 60-70€/Ha, i.e. they are very little valued in Spain.

4.3.3 Current land use and potential land-use competition

Permanent pasture area has been reduced over the last decade (National Statistics Institute, 2020). Agricultural areas have decreased as well. This is probably a result of the ongoing rural abandonment taking place in Spain over the last decades. Population is migrating towards large cities looking for jobs. Using grasslands and pastures for carbon sequestration would not encounter any conflict with other land uses, especially in isolated areas of the country. In fact, new uses of the land such as carbon sequestration management could create new job opportunities in rural areas, contributing to their revitalization.

Contrary to cropland, the areas of grassland have seen an increase since 1990, with most of the area coming from cropland (rain-fed annual crops). The conversion from agriculture to grasslands usually results in an increased sequestration, while the conversions from forest land and other land result in increased emissions. The net-balance has favoured emissions, although these have been heavily reduced since 1990. More recently the introduction of incentives for biodiverse grasslands has allowed an increase in sequestration rates due to an increase in the areas of grasslands and extensive livestock, the greater use of more sustainable practices in environmental terms (e.g., organic production, integrated production, direct sowing and minimal mobilization) and the reduction in the use of fertilizers.

The main effect of grasses on the local environment is primarily related to soil, water and air. In particular, they contribute mainly to the water balance, due to their water retention capacity, which is linked to a higher retention of nutrients and therefore to a better soil quality and a reduction of erosion. Currently, due to the lack of water, extensive livestock farms, whose main food is grass, are going through very hard times due to the lack of feed and drinking water.

In terms of their contribution to carbon sequestration, it is the roots that accumulate carbon, so in pasture land under livestock management it is the soil that is the largest store of carbon. Grasses do not store large amounts of carbon, but the roots of these species do, which is stored in the soil.

The diversity of macro-fungi is very important for their nitrogen and phosphorus storage capacity, therefore, soils with good soil quality reduce the amount of external inputs of inorganic fertiliser to the pasture.

Pasture management as a tool for increasing carbon sequestration and vegetation cover of the systems. With these tools we will not be able to avoid climate change, but we will try to mitigate it and adapt to new climatic conditions. For example, a fire in an area of pasture burns the pastures and trees. The following year the grasses return with a little rain, but it will take at least 20 years for the holm oaks to return to their carbon sequestration function. Therefore, in a forest fire situation, grasses adapt better and perform a higher long-term CO₂ storage function than oaks, because during the first 20 years the trees accumulate low amounts of CO₂.

Adaptable plant species need to be genetically improved in order to achieve species that are able to adapt to the new climatic conditions.

4.3.4 *Climate risks & sensitivities*

Extreme temperatures and extended drought periods would have a very detrimental impact on grassland productivity and thus, carbon capture. This is especially relevant in Spain, where aridity is increasing as a result of climate change. A simulation study carried out in France found that less protein content and water drainage, and more interannual and interseasonal variation are likely to happen by the year 2100 (Graux et al., 2013). Community compositions are also expected to shift as a result of a change in climate patterns (Ghahramani et al., 2019).

How sensitive is the LMT to climate related changes regarding:

Climatic conditions drastically affect grassland productivity in the same way affect the productivity of crops. The geographic distribution of grasslands is a function of climate and photoperiod, total amount of precipitation and effect of temperature on phenological development. The occurrence of extreme weather events, such as, heat waves, hailstorms or dry spells can compromise part or all the production of a campaign. In a climate change scenario, the probability of occurrence of these events is greater, so it is possible to predict greater production losses in this way.

The main risk factors related to climate and pasture management in Spain considered are drought as the most important, followed by heat waves, cold waves, frost and erosion. Regarding these, it was commented that pastures develop in optimal temperatures between 25-35°C, anything below 20°C and above 50°C for a long period of time causes lack of growth and senescence.

In the past, it was colder than now, when the minimum temperatures reached -5°C and 5°C, the grasses showed a stop of growth, because with $T^{\circ} < 0^{\circ}C$ the grasses burned. Nowadays, it is not as cold and these temperatures are not as frequent as in the past.

On the other hand, frost stops the growth of grasses and others that are very sensitive to cold burn and die.

There have been several episodes of drought lasting 3-4 years, and since 2019 we are currently in a period of drought. In Extremadura for example $pp < 200mm$ is a disaster, a period of drought in winter is not the same as in spring, because evapotranspiration in spring is higher and if it does not rain it is a

disaster for the emergence of grasses. The false autumn or inadequate distribution of rainfall is a very important situation, because the worst thing is that it rains at the beginning of autumn, for example, but it does not rain again until January, which means that the grasses are born in autumn but due to the lack of rain they die and the seed bank is lost. However, if the rain falls at another time, the seed bank remains in the soil available for another season with better conditions.

In terms of erosion, if a drought occurs, the soil is not covered with vegetation cover and this leads to runoff processes, gullying and loss of nutrients. Therefore, a soil cover <30% total disaster of 30-60% can prevent erosion, above 60% is an optimal cover where no or minimal erosion would occur.

4.3.5 Economic implications

Grazing management in grasslands and pastures would need to be regulated to achieve optimal carbon sequestration (EIP-AGRI, 2018). In many cases, this will mean lowering the livestock loads, which will have an impact on productivity. However, this could be compensated by the income generated for farmers in a potential carbon market. In addition, management practices that promote carbon sequestration are often advantageous for farmers in the long run. Soils with high carbon content have better structure, are more nutritious for plants and can hold water more efficiently, improving their fertility in the long run (EIP-AGRI, 2018). Also, sustainable grazing management will usually lead to higher quality meat products and higher income for farmers (EIP-AGRI, 2018).

As for the barriers to the application of good pasture management, we find that the management of Mediterranean pastures in large areas is complex due to the need to divide the land into fences and to rotate grazing over them, something that in many cases is not done due to the increased costs and limitations that this entails.

However, the investment in improving pastures by sowing improved species pays for itself in the first year, i.e. the benefit of the grassland is immediate and pays for itself in terms of increased quality and biomass production.

In terms of political and institutional aspects, pastures are abandoned, they do not have sufficient support because the benefits they bring are not contemplated. The new CAP will favour pastures, so that the owner is required to carry out certain actions, which he is already doing, but they will be better remunerated. For example, greater administrative control will be required by means of a field notebook in which the different actions carried out, such as sowing, fertilising, grazing, mowing, etc., are recorded.

The high cost of acquiring land for Mediterranean pastures must be emphasised, which means that a very long period is needed to amortise this investment. This disadvantage means that pasture land is being used for the implementation of photovoltaic plants or the planting of woody species in intensive systems.

The social opportunities generated by proper pasture management are directly related to livestock farming, in such a way that good pasture management contributes to an increase in profitability, generating greater economic value, employment and therefore fixing the population in rural areas.

The main constraint to the implementation of the grasslands management could be lack of knowledge about pasture improvement, its correct management. The costs of improvement and therefore the benefits generated. For example, pasture improvement represents 0.1% of the total costs of a farm and this percentage is amortised per year and the benefits can last up to 10 years.

It is necessary that work in the countryside is better remunerated and socially recognised, for which it is necessary to provide products with added value. For example, the dehesa with livestock, in the case of cattle, which in itself provides little labour, if we improve the landscape and its conservation we will provide it with greater added value, which also involves selling the fact that pastures are CO₂ sinks and their importance.

In terms of environmental opportunities, knowledge plays an important role in terms of the choice of species to achieve a balance of species that provides an increase in biodiversity and therefore carbon storage capacity.

4.3.6 Co-benefits and trade-offs

In a context of climate change, with increased frequency and intensity of wildfires, grasslands and pastures could be a more resilient mechanism than forests for climate change mitigation (Dass et al., 2018). Grazed grasslands and pastures are essential for the economic sustainability of many urban communities. In addition, they provide various ecosystem services, including erosion prevention, water regulation and biodiversity support (EIP-AGRI, 2018). Grassland management for carbon would also have a positive impact on biodiversity, as an increase in plant biodiversity leads to an increase in carbon storage (EIP-AGRI, 2018).

The most important effects of grasslands on the local environment are carbon sequestration, water balance directly related to soil protection, as well as biodiversity and fire risk reduction. In terms of carbon sequestration, grasslands are key, if we manage grasslands well, we will have a good vegetation cover that will act as a carbon sink, as well as reducing the amount of emissions, because the dependence on external inputs (animal supplementation) would be lower. So that a well-managed grassland cover contributes to a higher retention of nutrients in the soil and therefore to an improvement of soil quality and a better regulation of the water balance.

In terms of biodiversity, a land with a good grassland vegetation cover, the more balanced it is, the more it affects the scenic landscape value, due to the high biodiversity in terms of plant and bird species, although the contribution of grassland to these factors will depend on the stocking rate of livestock using the land. Grasslands have an important role as carbon sinks as well as buffers for the overall system.

The main risk factor related to climate and pasture management in Spain considered by farmers is drought, both lack of water and inadequate rainfall distribution. Linked to drought are the increasingly frequent and longer heat waves in the summer season. Past droughts of note were those of 1982-1983 and 1993-1994 due to their severity.

Furthermore, the pastures are affected by continuous frosts and strong winds, the latter of which, when they occur, reduce the intensity of the rainfall.

There is a lack of definition of national strategies to encourage the use of more productive, more resilient and persistent species and mixtures, and improvement in the management of installed pastures (e.g., sowing, fertilization, mineral correction, animal management, etc.) is lacking.

Direct aids (i.e., integrated production, organic production, greening, etc.) are neither sufficient nor adequate to promote the improvement of production and the impact of forage and grass crops. More research and experimentation are needed, on species, varieties, mixtures, cultural techniques and the management of grasslands and animals to increase the efficiency of the use of these foods, their quality, reduce costs, improve animal performance and, above all, increase the effective animal load to better value natural meadows and grasslands.

It is clear that proper grassland management and adequate vegetation cover contributes to the regulation of water flows, soil protection and more even and efficient distribution of rainwater.

Grazing management has a direct impact on biodiversity, as the management itself can influence the botanical composition or the phytodiversity of the plot. Continuous grazing encourages the emergence of less productive species and biomass less exposed to consumption by livestock. However, if grazing rotations are carried out, you will see a greater diversity of species and therefore a more resilient pasture that is better adapted to adverse conditions. In Mediterranean pastures, if we don't protect the pasture in early autumn, when the legumes emerge, that fence is going to have worse grass than if we let it rest. Likewise, this happens during the flowering season, logically the grasses that thrive have a smaller size, producing seeds that livestock cannot access and producing an imbalance in the diversity of species.

Pasture management in the Mediterranean context has a direct effect on the probability of fires due to the presence of trees. It is a risk to have these areas without any management, as the probability increases.

4.3.7 Risks associated with scaling up

Livestock farms are highly polluting if managed unsustainably. Scaling up grasslands for carbon sequestration would require a careful assessment of the sequestration potential of an area, and comprehensive management plan including circular economy and elements such as the use of compost for soil amendments.

The parameter that has the greatest impact is drought, but not only in terms of a decrease in the amount of precipitation collected, but also in terms of the irregular distribution of rainfall. An example is: it does not have the same effect if 500 mm/m² falls over a hydrological year if it falls in 4 episodes of rainfall as if this amount is distributed in an irregular way which allows the pastures to have moisture for as long as possible. This reduction in litres or inadequate distribution of rainfall affects both the amount of biomass and the quality or botanical composition of the grassland. Thus, adequate rainfall in the right way favours the production of legumes, whereas when rain falls too early, and then falls too little or too late, it enhances the emergence of grasses.

Other important factors related to grasses are heat waves, frost and ground fires. So heat waves also depend on when they occur, they will affect more or less, so if they occur when the pastures are already dry or parched, the effects are of little importance. However, when they occur during the reproductive period of these species, such as at the end of spring, the impact is much greater, because the natural cycle is altered and natural seed production is affected. This last climatic episode occurred in the spring of 2022 and its effects will be visible this autumn.

As for frosts, they limit the development of species. If they last longer, they can kill many plants, which penalises both the quantity and the quality of the grass. It is also important to consider the grazing that is carried out in cold periods, as this is grazing that greatly penalises the pastures, and the trampling of these plants during the frost period ends up killing them.

In Mediterranean pastures, where there are fences that are not used until the end of the summer, the probability of a forest fire is greater, so it is very important in the management of pastures to take into account the risk of fire, because the pastures resurface the following year but the trees that accompany them take decades to recover.

In terms of policy parameters, there are no policies aimed at sustainable pasture management. Although the new CAP is now promoting greener agriculture and livestock farming, in terms of pasture use, the techniques required of owners are practically the same as in the previous period, with the difference that they must be registered.

The problem is that there are pastures that should be used by livestock, because of the benefits and opportunities they generate. However, there is a lack of political support that values this type of production. It makes no sense to call for the sustainable use of pastureland and, on the other hand, not to value the products generated by such use. At the present time, the politicians are misjudging livestock farmers, they are being persecuted and the current tools for measuring emissions are inadequate because they are generalist, and no distinction is made between the emissions produced, for example, by a stall animal and those produced by an animal grazing in the field.

There is no legislation to support or promote the management of pastures and their use. There is no legislation to protect these ecosystems. The Mediterranean pastures have never received support from the CAP; on the contrary, they have been heavily penalised, for example, by deducting money for the presence of trees.

With regard to social parameters, it should be pointed out that there is a clear lack of labour to carry out tasks in the fields, problems of depopulation, and a lack of knowledge and training to carry out these tasks. The availability of manpower is essential for proper pasture management or valuation. Nowadays, due to this lack, farms are opting to give up good management, livestock graze freely on large areas of land, but they are not managed, there are no rotations, for example. This is due to various causes such as:

- nowadays it is not well seen or valued to work in the countryside,
- young people do not want to work in the countryside, they are not motivated because they see it as a sacrifice and old-fashioned, as well as the amount of aid that people receive from the government, which means that there is no interest in working in the countryside because they prefer to live on subsidies.

4.3.8 *Research gaps*

Accurate monitoring and measuring methods for carbon uptake by grassland species are required. In addition, life cycle assessments for meat and dairy products are essential to calculate the carbon effectively removed from the atmosphere by grassland systems. More information on the appropriate grazing management for specific locations and combination of species is required (EIP-AGRI, 2018).

Research and experimentation work is needed to determine the best varieties and mixtures for each edaphoclimatic combination. There is also a lack of studies on the response to production factors (e.g., fertilization, irrigation, etc.) and on management, to be able to advise livestock producers and prepare manuals on good practices, which can serve as guides for the good use of these productions by the animals.

As far as pasture management technologies are concerned, there are quite a few advances such as different types of fencing, genetic improvement, specific harvesters for pasture species, etc. The obstacle is not the lack of technologies in grassland management, but the lack of knowledge for the application of new techniques or new technologies that have been developed in recent years. The technological blockage comes from a lack of knowledge both of the existence of these technologies and of the people who can access them for their correct application.

There is a lack of promotion of the ecosystemic benefits generated by the exploitation of pastures and extensive livestock farming, as well as a valuation by consumers, and institutional support to promote and value these products. The risk is not high, because to implement sustainable management you do not need to make a large investment, but no matter how small it is, if the income does not increase, managers stop implementing sustainable management because in the end they see it as a reduction in their costs. In terms of environmental aspects, it is clear that proper pasture management generates a number of ecosystem services that would not otherwise be generated. Sustainable management leads to reduced inputs and increased carbon sequestration.

4.4 Forests planning and management

4.4.1 Introduction

Forests capture carbon from the atmosphere as the trees grow, and then store it long-term in their biomass. The carbon emission-capture in forests is a complex system comprising four main carbon pools: aerial biomass, underground biomass, soil organic matter and forest products outside of the forest (wooden furniture, paper, pulp, wooden buildings, etc.). It is estimated that Spanish forests capture up to 19% of the carbon dioxide emitted in the country. Also, these forests store more than 2858 tonnes of carbon dioxide. Consequently, forests play a major role in carbon mitigation in Spain, and carbon sequestration should be explicitly taken into account in sustainable forestry management. Sustainable forestry could improve carbon capture by forests due to the rejuvenation process that wood extraction instigates in the forest mass, and wooden products could have long lives outside the forest (Montero et al., 2005).

Specifically, *carbon silviculture* should speed up natural forest regeneration using an adequate forest cutting plan. It should also make use of biomass waste generated during cuttings or prunings, clear the shrub layer when necessary to increase tree regeneration. Also, the forestry management should optimise the quality of the wood extracted, as higher quality wood is usually turned into long lasting wooden products. Lastly, forest fire prevention should also be a cornerstone of the forestry management, avoiding large carbon release events as a result of forest fires (Montero et al., 2005).

What is the general context of the LMT and how does it address climate change mitigation?

Forests and associated woodlands occupy 54% of Spain's surface area (27 million ha). This area has been increasing at a rate of more than 180,000 ha/year in the last 25 years (the highest rate in the EU) both by action (afforestation, afforestation of agricultural land) and by spontaneous expansion of forests as a result of rural abandonment. (<https://juntosporlosbosques.ingenierosdemontes.org/>)

Spanish forests produce goods, some of which are traded via the market, and environmental services. The former includes timber and firewood with a harvested volume of almost 20 million m³/year (1,000 M € in primary value), cork with 70,000 t/year (cork stoppers alone account for 350 M €/year), natural resin with 12,000 t (14 M €/year), as well as hunting and fishing, chestnuts, asparagus, forest fruits, pastures, pine nuts and mushrooms, etc.

Spanish forestry use less than 40% of the wood from the growth of the forests and 80% of this is generated in 20% of the surface area (Galicia and the Cantabrian coast). Wood is the basis of a complex industrial fabric that includes: wood industry (sawn timber, boards, wood packaging), pulp and paper industry, and furniture industry. Together with the remaining forestry products, it generates 1.7% of GDP, 300,000 direct jobs (1.7% of total employment - INE Input-Output Tables 2015), covering 5% of the primary energy consumed in Spain, with a consumed in Spain, with 40% of total renewable energy as a target (IDAE 2015).

In many of the non-wood products, harvesting is not regulated, producing a free appropriation that does not contribute to defraying the costs of forest management. Nor are the environmental services generated by forests, such as environmental services generated by forests, such as water regulation, improvement of water quality, the effect of water regulation, water quality improvement, atmospheric carbon sink effect, erosion and desertification processes, and preservation of biodiversity, as well as others of a social nature, such as landscape - key in coastal areas for their coast, mountains and islands - due to their relevance for tourism, recreation and leisure.

Spanish forests are crucial in the fight against climate change as they are the only manageable sink. Beyond reducing its own emissions, it is the only sector that can offset the emissions of others. Today, the growth of the forest stock of Spain's total CO₂ emissions, as well as significant additional climatic benefits from temporary storage thanks to the use of long-lasting forest products, especially wood in construction, and by the substitution of non-renewable raw materials and energies.

Wood and cork are the most widely available materials for the transition to bio-economy, capable of replacing non-renewable raw materials in construction, chemical industry or energy for non-renewable raw materials. The use of forest-based biomass is a unique opportunity for fire risk reduction, job creation, mitigation, energy of fires, job creation, climate change mitigation and reduction of external energy dependence.

4.4.2 Policy context

Both the PNACC and the Climate Change and Ecological Transition Bill consider the necessity of incentivising private and public stakeholders to increase carbon sequestration in the available terrestrial and marine carbon sinks. Among these sinks, the agricultural and forestry sector are expected to play a major role (Government of Spain, 2021a, 2020a). Specifically, the Long Term Decarbonization Strategy 2050 for the Spanish economy, which aims to reach climate neutrality by 2050, identifies the promotion of sustainable forest management as one of its main lines of work (Government of Spain, 2020c). Also, the Spanish Forestry Law promotes incentivising positive externalities of forests such as carbon capture, biodiversity conservation, soil preservation and hydrological regime maintenance (Government of Spain, 2003). Since 2014, forest lands can be listed in the voluntary register of forest carbon dioxide removal projects. The aim of this register is to enable carbon compensation for Spanish companies. Since the creation of the register, the number of listed projects has been increasing steadily. Registered mitigation projects may be eligible for funding depending on their local administration (Government of Spain, 2021b).

The Spanish Forest Plan was created to structure the specific actions required by the National Forest Strategy, which aims to manage forest sustainably, increase their multifunctionality, and contribute to social cohesion in rural areas. This plan was designed in 2002 and will remain in effect until 2032. The plan projects various forest restoration projects mainly for hydrological regulation, but considers carbon sequestration as a positive externality of these actions. Also, the plan promotes silvicultural

management of forests, optimising biomass production and increasing carbon sequestration up to 20% (Government of Spain, 2002).

Which national policies exist that address the LMT?

In Spain, forestry management competences are delegated by the Government to the 17 Spanish Autonomous Communities, so that forestry policy is managed in a fragmented manner in each of the 17 Autonomous Communities plus the cities of Ceuta and Melilla.

However, there are general criteria, set by the Spanish Forestry Strategy and the Spanish Forestry Plan, directed by the Spanish Government, which in turn follow the guidelines of the European Commission.

The Spanish Forestry Plan (https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/biodiversidad/temas/politica-forestal/planificacion-forestal/politica-forestal-en-espana/pfe_plan_forestal_esp.aspx), the application in time and space of the Spanish Forestry Strategy, aims to structure the necessary actions for the development of a Spanish forestry policy based on the principles of sustainable development, multifunctionality of forests, contribution to territorial and ecological cohesion and public and social participation in the formulation of policies, strategies and programmes, proposing the co-responsibility of society in the conservation and management of forests. It was approved by the Council of Ministers in July 2002.

The Spanish Forestry Plan is projected for 30 years (2002-2032). During this period, two in-depth revisions of the document are planned, which may affect the diagnosis, structure, development and interpretation of the measures proposed in the Plan. At the same time, and to the extent that the financial scenario may be altered, a second cycle of revisions will be carried out which will exclusively affect the financial programming of the Plan.

Inspiring principles:

- Sustainable development.
- Multifunctionality of forests.
- Contribution to territorial cohesion through rural development, fixing population and employment.
- Contribution to ecological cohesion, integrating the conservation of biological diversity in forest management and preserving the genetic heritage of forests.
- Public and social participation in the formulation of policies, strategies and programmes.

The Spanish Forestry Plan proposes a total of 150 measures, including the following:

- Permanently updated statistics: National Forest Inventory, Spanish Forest Map, National Soil Erosion Inventory, Forest Fires Statistics, European forest damage monitoring networks, as well as other statistics of interest to the forestry sector.
- Hydrological-forest restoration actions framed in a Priority Actions Programme.
- Drawing up Basic Instructions for the Management and Use of Forestry.

- Establishment of Forest Resource Management Plans as forestry planning instruments on a regional scale and promotion of sustainable forest management through forest management.
- Elaboration of a Spanish Plan for Dehesas.
- Support for forest certification.
- Promotion of forestry.
- Support for the monitoring, prevention and extinction of forest fires.
- Updating of regulations for the use and marketing of forest reproductive material.
- Integration of biodiversity conservation in forest management. Guidelines and management models in Natura 2000 Network forest areas.
- Elaboration, by the competent administrations, of a Forest Industry Plan.
- Promotion of forestry associations.
- Establishment of the Forestry Committee in the National Commission for the Protection of Nature.

Which actors are currently applying the LMT (e.g. land users, forest owners farmers)?

Two thirds of Spanish forests are owned by more than 2 million private citizens or groups, while the other third is public, located in mountain areas and mainly owned by municipalities. Although progress has been made in recent decades in the implementation of sustainable forest management in a large number of forests, there are still certain areas with forest land abandoned for various reasons: lack of income to maintain them or collective properties whose owners cannot be identified due to loss of inheritance, as well as a very pronounced smallholding in the northern half, which makes management extremely difficult.

Which funds are available for the LMT?

Beyond the funding received in the forestry sector from the European Commission (ERDF funds, CAP, EAFRD, Horizon2020, EIP AGRI...), the General State Budgets in Spain, or the benefits that the economic activities of the private forestry sector reinvest in the forests themselves, it is necessary to advance in new forms of funding for the maintenance and sustainability of a sector that can effectively be a real and stable carbon sink over time. For that, there are some interesting proposals from Spanish foresters stakeholders (Plataforma Juntos por los Bosques):

- ensure an adequate allocation for the forestry sector in the General State Budget, which, beyond the fires, will enable actions to be undertaken and the objectives of the Spanish Forestry Plan 2002 to be achieved,
- Convene the representatives of the Monitoring Committee of the Socio-Economic Activation Plan for the Forestry Sector.
- Present to the Council of Ministers a proposal for measures in Spanish taxes, to stimulate Sustainable Forest Management and mobilise existing resources.
- Define and reach a consensus with the sector and interested agents on an ambitious forestry political agenda that includes at least the following actions:

- Implement a Programme for the promotion of forest products, to increase their responsible consumption, which will activate forest management in Spain.
- Recover a Hydrological-Forestry Restoration Plan to help alleviate soil loss due to erosion and reduce the risk of desertification. This could be implemented by means of an Agreement with the Autonomous Regions and the Hydrographic Confederations, with sufficient funds to apply the European Water Framework Directive.
- Strengthen forest health, updating and speeding up the registration of phytosanitary products and improving forest damage networks, as a tool for forest planning and pest monitoring.
- Ensure the unity of the internal market for forestry service companies.
- Retake and prioritise the National Forest Inventory and its cartography, the Spanish Forest Map, as key tools for sustainable forest management and included in the National Statistical Plan.
- Promote forestry research, establishing a legal and financial institutional framework to define the sector's research priorities, support its development and guarantee its application, as well as the dissemination of results.
- Address the reporting obligations of the Greenhouse Gas Emissions Inventory, improving methodologies for compliance with both EU regulations, the agreements of the Climate Change Convention (LULUCF) including the recent Paris Agreement in relation to changes in land use, forestry and the sink effect of forest products, as well as incentivising domestic forest sinks.

4.4.3 *Current land use and potential land-use competition*

Forest ecosystems cover more than 27 million ha in Spain. Almost 15 million ha (29% of the country's area) of these are tree forest ecosystems, and almost 12 million ha (23% of the country's area) belong to shrubs or other treeless covers. There has been an increase in tree forest ecosystems and a decrease in treeless areas over the last years (Government of Spain, 2021c). As of 2019, there are 42 projects listed in the register of forest carbon dioxide removal projects, which covered a total area of 530.24 ha, and mitigated 4264 t CO₂ (Government of Spain, 2021b). However, there are probably other forested areas that are acting as carbon sinks and are not registered. Also, the high forest cover and the presence of treeless areas offer great potential for scaling up carbon silvicultural management without competing with other land uses.

Over the last years, trends in land use change in Spain have shown a decrease in agricultural and farming land uses, especially in the most isolated areas of the country. Forest has regenerated in these abandoned agricultural lands, or reforestations have been executed. Both productive (forestry) and unproductive forested areas have increased. Another, more localised land use change trend is the conversion to anthropic land covers as a result of the growth of cities and the rise in second home ownerships. However, these urbanisation processes are highly localised in certain areas of the country (Fernández Nogueira and Corbelle Rico, 2017).

What is the national (1) historic and (2) current land use of the LMT and how is this projected to develop over the coming decades (2030 & 2050)?

The Spanish Platform Together for Forests (juntos por los Bosques) provides a constructive critique of the plans for the forestry sector and the climate challenges framed in the Spanish government's foresight strategy for 2050. The following notes stand out:

- Activate the full potential of forests in the fight against climate change. In order to achieve the carbon neutrality in 2050 that this document and the EU guidelines foresee, forests are strategic in the fight against climate change.
- EU guidelines foresee, forests are strategic as the only manageable sink (mitigation) in all 3 dimensions:
 - increase of the sink in forest either by increased area or biomass/ha density
 - temporary sink for long-lasting forest products, especially in the construction sector
 - substitution of non-renewable raw materials whose processes are highly intensive in terms of energy and therefore CO₂ emissions (cement, iron, aluminium, plastics, glass, synthetic textiles, etc.).
 - The weight of each of these depends on the time and place, with the greatest synergistic effect between the 3 dimensions while integrating adaptation.
- Green taxation. In practice it has not been used in Spain except when required by the EU. The tax on Hydrocarbon tax is merely a tax on revenue with a collateral environmental effect. It is following international recommendations, it is essential to reinforce and give coherence to environmental taxes, leaving aside their revenue-raising dimension and ensuring the neutrality of their effect. Another issue is the legitimate debate on the level of taxation as a whole. In any case, if one opts for the internalisation of environmental externalities it is not permissible to limit oneself only to negative externalities (pollution, waste, etc.), but also to recognise positive environmental services generated by the sustainable management of natural resources must also be recognised (payment for environmental services), which are so widely applied in international cooperation, especially in forests (REDD+), should also be recognised. In particular in relation to the fight against climate change, not transferring part of the taxation associated with reducing CO₂ emissions to forestry, the only sector that acts as a mitigator of these emissions is grossly unfair as well as ineffective, as it misses out on the existing potential that can be activated through incentives is lost.
- Realigning water and forestry policies. Spanish Hydrographic Confederations must overcome their limitation to the Public Water Domain (DPH) and address the basin as a whole, which is where the water resource comes from.
- Recognise forestry and agricultural activity as a livelihood for less populated areas.
- Do not confuse risk with effective desertification. Thanks to the socio-economic changes that have taken place over the past 150 years and the reforestation of the past, the risk of desertification and erosion in Spain has slowed down considerably.

- Avoiding a focus on a single star measure: afforestation. Afforestation is one more instrument of forest management but it should not become an end in itself. It is true that it is more clearly recognised than other climate-positive forestry actions, but this fact, related to the greater simplicity of quantification, must not generate a dysfunctional land use dynamic that has already suffered in the past. In addition, it should be remembered that the carbon sequestration effect of reforestation on more than 90% of soils is very long term, whereas the effect of increased sequestration in the case of existing stagnant stands is short term and also avoids the emission of CO₂ from fires.
- Environmental education that is more aware of the rural world. Environmental education, especially in the education system, needs to be reset in order to recognise primary activities and the rural world as a key asset, as a supplier of healthy and vital food, strategic bio-products and essential environmental services, not as something to be extinguished.

Are there other land use developments that compete with the expansion of the LMT, and if so, how do those affect the scaling-up of the LMTs?

The main effects of forests on the local environment are obvious. Forests clearly contribute to air quality, due to photosynthesis. Similarly, soils, with both tree and shrub cover, contribute to the soil's nutrient retention capacity and water balance. On the other hand, experts indicate that a diversity of ecosystems is better than a continuous mass of the same species in a given area, because biodiversity will be greater the greater the diversity of ecotones we find, and this biodiversity contributes to the ability to adapt to inclemency and recovery, i.e. greater resilience. Similarly, sustainable forest management, with regular and orderly silvicultural treatments, reduces the risk of forest fires.

4.4.4 Climate risks & sensitivities

Forests are highly threatened by climate change and the disturbances it provokes. Shifting temperatures and rainfall patterns are already increasing mortality in certain tree species, triggering a change in forest community composition (Batllori et al., 2020). The specific trajectories of species change are very case dependent and should be taken into account in long term forest planning for carbon sequestration. Climate also influences fire regime, which has changed in Spain (Moreno et al., 2014). Forest fires are the main cause of forest loss in the Mediterranean, and large fire events rates and burned areas are expected to increase under climate change conditions (Molina et al., 2019; Pérez-Sánchez et al., 2019).

The main risk factor related to climate and forest management and development is drought, not only because of the decrease in rainfall but also because of changes in the distribution of rainfall throughout the year. For example, the city of Cáceres has an average rainfall of 400 mm/year, experts speak of a 20% reduction due to climate change. This may seem like a slight variation, but it is also noticeable because these rains are not distributed as evenly as before. Recently, in the first autumn rains, we have

seen how rainfall has been concentrated in a few torrential episodes, as rainfall that was previously distributed throughout the autumn and spring is increasingly concentrated in a shorter period.

Another factor related to drought is the increasingly frequent and prolonged heat waves. It should be noted that the negative effects of these heat waves are not due to the fact that the average maximum temperatures are exceeded at a specific time of the year, but rather the prolonged tendency of these maximum temperatures. An example of this was last 2022 summer, when we had three heat waves, the first at the beginning of June, another at the beginning of July and the last at the end of July/beginning of August. These climatic episodes have been prolonged in days, where the minimum temperature at night was between 22-28 degrees, something that affects both humans and plants.

Related to the above are the forest fires, which, due to the lack of precipitation and the prolonged tendency of high temperatures, make the probability of large fires high. Plants, as they have less humidity, accumulate a higher calorific value, temperatures at night do not decrease sufficiently and therefore make it difficult to extinguish fires.

Another of the most relevant factors is erosion, which is directly related to the factors mentioned above. The decrease in precipitation and the high temperatures lead to a critical situation of prolonged water stress in the soil, which reduces the water absorption capacity of the soil. We have been able to observe this in recent weeks, in which we have seen the formation of streams and soil dragging, due to both the concentration of torrential rains and the decrease in the soil's absorption capacity. In other words, the soil is so dry and compacted that it is not able to absorb water so quickly, as well as due to the speed with which the rain falls.

4.4.5 Economic implications

The rentability of carbon capture forestry as opposed to traditional timber silviculture or is hard to assess due to the long timescales of forest growth (Boylard, 2006), the spatial heterogeneity of forests (Campos et al., 2017), and the various carbon pools within a forest and in timber products (Eriksson et al., 2007). In addition, alternative uses like non timber products or carbon capture require specific studies developing natural growth and yield models for forests, which are uncommon (Campos et al., 2017). For these reasons, specific information adapted to Spanish forests is currently lacking. However, studies in other countries have found that carbon sequestration payment schemes have the potential to influence silvicultural management and increase profitability (Juutinen et al., 2018; Manley and Maclaren, 2012).

Carbon silviculture could be easily included in a multifunctional forestry management regime, which is already common in Mediterranean forests in Spain. However, this multifunctional forestry is not currently accurately quantified in terms of productivity or rentability (Campos et al., 2017). Instead, multifunctional forestry in Mediterranean forests remains a small-scale traditional management regime. Common guidelines for carbon forestry include the extension of rotation length and thinning to improve growth rates (Campos et al., 2017). These recommendations could easily be compatibilized with multifunctional forestry or cork forestry, two common forestry regimes in Spain.

Can the LMT be applied in a competitive way (i.e., returns exceed costs)?

With regard to the barriers to the application of forests as a tool for climate change mitigation, one of the main obstacles is the lack of demand for technologies aimed at the use of nearby natural resources. Thus, the main tool for mitigation and carbon capture in the environment in which we find ourselves in this part of Europe is the consumption of biomass from our forests. For example, there are many buildings belonging to regional administrations, which have heating systems that use fossil fuels. If this were to be replaced by biomass, we would be consuming biomass from our forests, which would contribute to better forest management and at the same time contribute to climate change mitigation, as forests are the main carbon sinks on the planet.

At the level of policies and administrations, the existing interlocking of policies set by the European legislative power, subsequently designed by the European executive power and finally implemented by regional administrations, fails. In other words, at the European level, the policies and objectives set by the European Union for the coming years are very ambitious and climate change is very present in these policies, however, regional administrations do not currently have sufficient capacity to address the proposed changes. This inability on the part of the administration is based on excessive bureaucracy and lack of qualified staff to carry out the measures.

Is there any information on the costs of the LMT implementation? E.g., what are the specific costs of the LMT to reduce GHG emissions (e.g. in EUR costs per ton CO2 equivalent per ha (EUR x ton CO2eq-1 x ha-1))

Another of the elements of this mechanism that we mentioned earlier are the forestry companies. In Spain they are small and medium-sized companies, whose contracts are required and governed by the public administration under the same conditions as those of large companies, which causes a great imbalance that in difficult times leads to the company's suffocation and its disappearance, or in good times the company's growth is not so great because it starts from low profit levels.

As far as social aspects are concerned, there is a notable lack of awareness in society of the need for a change in consumer habits. It is necessary to create a demand for natural resources, biomass in this case, which leads to a consumption of natural resources closer to home and therefore reduces dependence on fossil fuels. At the level of citizens, if we look around us, we see, for example, the increasing proliferation of photovoltaic parks and the ease with which solar panels can be installed in homes, which is the result of policies set by the legislature and implemented by the administration.

Furthermore, there is a way of thinking in which, for example, it is seen as a good thing by society to cut down trees in distant areas of our country for our own supply, but nevertheless in our forests the way of thinking that is being established is that of protection and extreme conservationism, without knowing that these forests need silvicultural treatments for their conservation.

Nature has demonstrated on many occasions its great capacity for resurgence when subjected to extreme conditions, as well as its ability to adapt to adversity.

The greatest opportunity lies in a change of consumption habits in society, so that we realise that we consume more than we need.

4.4.6 *Co-benefits and trade-offs*

The management actions required for carbon forestry, which include measures such as longer rotation periods and the promotion of forest regeneration can indirectly benefit biodiversity, erosion control, and water quality by improving the structural complexity of the forest. Landscape and recreation could also be positively impacted by more presence of large trees. In the unlikely scenario that carbon silviculture became a highly profitable activity, forestry could start competing with other land uses.

As carbon could also be stored in wooden products, the popularisation of carbon silviculture and wooden goods could diminish the demand for other less environmentally friendly materials such as plastics, steel or concrete.

What are the risks (negative side-effects) or co-benefits (positive side-effects) of the LMT?

The main risk factor related to climate and forest management and development is drought, followed by heatwave events. The effects can be seen for example in the reforestations of 10-15 years ago which were doing well, however, in addition to the effects of natural selection their situation has been aggravated by drought and extreme heat conditions, all of which have led to the death of many established stands. In the north there are many pines and strawberry trees that have suddenly dried up, which is unusual here given the climatic conditions.

Forest fires are also one of the factors that is having the greatest impact. This year 2022, together with 2003, we have suffered major fires, which in addition to the occasional loss of all the biodiversity of the area, we must take into account the erosion and loss of soil produced, which affects the resilience of the area, which, although we are used to the frequent occurrence of fires, this resilience or capacity for regeneration is diminishing.

Erosion has been reversed in some areas by forest management, but due to the occurrence of fires, droughts and heat waves this situation has worsened, contributing to the loss of regeneration capacity and soil fertility.

The main effect of forests on the local environment, local being understood as the environment involving human well-being, is mainly on water balance, air quality and soil protection, insofar as the environment and human development are improved.

Biodiversity would be included with habitat diversity as they are directly related and include diversity of plants, fauna, macrofungi, etc.

In terms of resilience, species that adapt to extreme conditions in the environment are fundamental for adaptation to climate change, to the environment or to disturbances that may arise.

Are there any other risks / co-benefits as part of the LMT implementation?

As regards the barriers to the application of good management, there are several obstacles, the main one being rural abandonment, the loss of local development capacity, which affects forests because there has been a devaluation of the products from these rural environments. Therefore, trying to develop sustainable management when there is no valuation of the products is difficult, insofar as we depend on subsidies and investments in the environment that vary greatly over time, depending on the economic situation at the time. We are all aware of the natural benefits of the environment, but we cannot forget that it is the traditional uses that have contributed to the environment's capacity to adapt to intrinsic conditions, so the main obstacle to the development of sustainable forest management that contributes to the mitigation of climate change, is the lack of valuation of the products and benefits produced by this rural or natural environment.

Trade-offs of the LMT

As for the political aspects, they are related to the abandonment of the rural environment. This fundamentally believes that this is not a political issue but rather economic interests, based on outsourcing production to other countries using raw materials other than those that have traditionally been used and that thanks to them the resilience and adaptive capacity of the forests has been maintained. Furthermore, subsidies and overly conservationist policies have contributed to the detriment of forests.

European forest management policy is very positive on paper, but in reality it does not deliver. There is a big contradiction, because the reality is a constant degradation of our forests. By really outsourcing everything, you cannot maintain our development because everything is interrelated, we cannot separate the development of society from the forests and nowadays they are separated because society does not look at forests as a source of profit, they have made us lose that perception. Therefore, we have to re-engage with forests, which is not necessary to do it in the same way as in the old days, 80 or 1000 years ago, because nowadays, there are many technologies and R&D that would make it easier to develop together with forests in a sustainable and self-sufficient way in our environment. It is all very well the, for example: "from farm to fork", the circular green economy, but the reality is that we are still dependent on the outside and they are not carried out because of political and economic interests.

4.4.7 Risks associated with scaling up

A forest with long rotation periods and a complex vertical structure could be prone to large forest fires due to the accumulation of fuels (biomass, which stores carbon) and the fuel continuity in the vertical axis (different vegetation strata). Careful fire prevention management and availability of extinction means are of utmost importance if carbon forestry is to be applied at a large scale. This is especially relevant in Spain, which has a climate characterised by a long, dry and warm summer season.

What are the risks of scaling up specific LMT solutions from the sub-national level to the national level?

In all sectors there is a problem with bureaucracy. However, in other sectors with higher profitability they can cope with these costs, however, in the forestry sector the lack of profitability does not allow to cushion these expenses.

With regard to economic risks, the main risks are market dominance and market regulation related to the above.

In terms of business risks, the investment challenges, the high costs and the lack of diversified income are generated by the aforementioned lack of revaluation of the products that could be obtained from the forest.

On the social side, the lack of knowledge is a determining factor that has led to the separation of society from forests, only looking towards them when there is some kind of ecological disaster such as the fires of last summer. Society does not see what forests contribute in a less tangible way, what they contribute and all that could be obtained, because society believes that management is like plundering, for example, when one sees the felling of trees for thinning, it is seen as plundering and not as a proper management of the stand. Lack of knowledge is a major obstacle to forest management.

4.4.8 *Research gaps*

As mentioned earlier, the main research gap hindering carbon sequestration forest management is the lack of accurate growth and yield models for certain tree species and management regimes different from timber silviculture.

What are the research gaps identified during this exercise?

As an opportunity, the main one today is the ability to be self-sufficient in terms of energy, food if we take into account extensive livestock farming and also the ecotourism benefits of revaluing natural habitats.

The greatest environmental risk is the lack of social and political support for forests, which leads to a neglect of forests and the environmental, cultural and social benefits they generate. They are only appreciated from an ecological and conservationist point of view of the city.

We must take advantage of this situation of economic crisis and absolute dependence on the outside world to look around us in order to take advantage of all the tools available today for forest management and to obtain self-sufficiency and take advantage of all the opportunities they generate.

4.5 Afforestation/reforestation of agriculture degraded areas

4.5.1 *Introduction*

Reforestation and afforestation projects are a cost-effective and simple way of capturing carbon, and are being used world-wide for that purpose (Nunes et al., 2020). In Spain, the Agricultural Lands

Afforestation program started more than 25 years ago as a result of the European Common Agricultural policy. Abandoned or low productivity agricultural lands were afforested, amounting to more than 730 000 ha. Even though it was not the intended primary objective of the program, the potential of this large scale afforestation scheme to help transitioning to a low emissions economy is widely acknowledged (Iglesias Ranz et al., 2021; Vadell et al., 2019).

What is the general context of the LMT and how does it address climate change mitigation?

Afforestation as a land use strategy to absorb carbon. As mentioned above, afforestation is considered a land management practice which can increase SOC stocks. Afforesting former croplands is agreed to be a valid and efficient opportunity to mitigate climate change (Bateni, Ventura et al., 2021; Cunningham, Mac Nally et al., 2015; Quinto et al., 2021). It was acknowledged in the Kyoto protocol (1997) as an effective method to sequester C into the soil (Lal, Negassa et al., 2015; Metz et al., 2001) and thus offset CO₂ emissions (Black, Byrne et al., 2009). A recent publication shows that the practice of afforestation could sequester from 0 to 111 Mt CO₂ yr⁻¹ in the soil at the EU level (Bellassen, Angers et al., 2022).

Despite some divergency in the literature, both in magnitude and direction of change (Hoogmoed, Cunningham et al., 2012; Vesterdal, Rosenqvist et al., 2007), afforestation is generally considered as one of the best practices to increase SOC stock (Arrouays, Balesdent et al., 2002; Kim, Kirschbaum et al., 2016; Lorenz & Lal, 2014, 2018; Minasny, Malone et al., 2017). Indeed, this LUC (from cropland to forest) not only stores C as tree living biomass (both above- and belowground) and dead OM, but it also facilitates the transfer of OM to the soil, thus leading to an increase of the SOC stocks (Black, Byrne et al., 2009; Cardinael, Chevallier et al., 2017; Laganier, Angers et al., 2010; D. Li, Niu et al., 2012; Liu, Yang et al., 2018; S. Shi, Zhang et al., 2013). This increase is mainly dictated by increased litter input above- and/or belowground (Bàrcena, 2013; Rahman, Bàrcena et al., 2017). On the one hand, afforestation boosts primary production, which in turns increases the input of OM to the soil, thus enhancing soil C sequestration (Arrouays, Balesdent et al., 2002; Lorenz & Lal, 2018) (Figure 3). On the other hand trees, having extensive root systems, are able to enrich the soil via root-derived C inputs and thus increase the SOC stocks also in deep soil horizons (Lorenz & Lal, 2018). Trees also promote SOC sequestration by forcing a reduction or cessation of tillage, which leads to smaller decomposition rates of SOM (Lorenz & Lal, 2018). In an afforested landscape there are thus more C inputs to and less C losses from the soil in comparison to annual croplands, which are cyclically fallow.

4.5.2 Policy context

The Common Agricultural Policy reform of the year 1992 included the promotion of environmentally friendly agricultural practices as an objective. This included the afforestation of certain privately owned lands. This would contribute to reforest abandoned or unproductive lands, lessen the deficit in forestry products in Europe, promote sustainable environmental management and fight against the greenhouse effect. These objectives lead to the Agricultural Lands Afforestation program in Spain (Iglesias Ranz et al., 2021). In the early days, the program subsidized the establishment cost of the

afforestation and established a system of payments to maintain the plantation during the first 5 years and compensate for the income lost due to the surrendering of agricultural activity. This last payment system has been reduced over the years (Vadell et al., 2019).

As mentioned earlier, both the PNACC and the Climate Change and Ecological Transition Bill consider the agricultural and forestry sector potential major carbon sinks (Government of Spain, 2021a, 2020a). Specifically, the Long Term Decarbonization Strategy 2050 for the Spanish economy, which aims to reach climate neutrality by 2050, identifies the creation of new forest areas as one of its main lines of work (Government of Spain, 2020c). This would continue the afforestation trend established by the Agricultural Lands Afforestation program.

Which national policies exist that address the LMT?

With regard to the CAP, the owners of reforested land request a change of use in order to be able to declare livestock. Previously they were pasture land and by requesting such a change, the rights increase, both for the land and for the head of livestock grazing on the land.

On the other hand, the implementation of reforestations on unproductive agricultural land represents a job opportunity for local society, as both the implementation and maintenance work requires local labour, as has been proven in recent years.

The environmental opportunities generated by reforestation are multiple, as mentioned in the previous section: carbon sinks, increased biodiversity, increased soil organic matter content and soil quality, and improved water quality.

Q1.2.2. Which actors are currently applying the LMT (e.g. land users, forest owners farmers)?

Most reforestations are implemented on private land, the main objective of which is to obtain profitability in addition to environmental aspects. Reforestations cannot be seen as a business because the income is not obtained directly and the initial investment required is high.

With regard to the economy, it should be noted that the implementation of reforestations represents an investment challenge for the owner, due to the high initial costs, the long period of recovery of the investment and the maintenance work in successive years. However, once the trees have reached adulthood, the sources of income are diversified: acorns, cork, firewood, livestock and improved pastures. With regard to subsidies, it has already been mentioned above that in recent years there have been several calls for proposals for the implementation of reforestations on agricultural land and for densification.

Which funds are available for the LMT?

Most of the reforestations in the last decades have been carried out thanks to the subsidies promoted by the regional administration for this purpose, otherwise many landowners would not have made these investments. The first reforestations with subsidies were carried out in 1993 and the last call for

subsidies was in 2007. Therefore, the regional administration has managed this technique adequately, as it has been quick and in accordance with the needs of the ecosystem and the landowner.

4.5.3 Current land use and potential land use competition

Trends in land use change in Spain have shown a decrease in agricultural and farming uses, especially due to land abandonment in isolated areas. Forest has regenerated in these abandoned agricultural lands, or reforestations have been executed. The Agricultural Lands Afforestation program has been the most relevant program promoting the expansion of forested areas in Spain. Certain areas of the country have more area of forest now than what they have had over the last centuries. The program has contributed to the active use of lands that would otherwise be abandoned agricultural lands (Iglesias Ranz et al., 2021; Vadell et al., 2019). The progressive emptying of rural areas suggests that afforestation of abandoned lands could be an interesting option for carbon sequestration in Spain, as it is unlikely that other land uses would be in competition.

What is the national (1) historic and (2) current land use of the LMT and how is this projected to develop over the coming decades (2030 & 2050)?

In Spain, since 1993, different regulations have been applied to develop Community regulations. Currently, Royal Decree 6/2001, of 12 January, on the promotion of afforestation of agricultural land and Royal Decree 1203/2006, of 20 October, which amends the article relating to the justification of establishment and maintenance costs of RD6/2001, are still in force.

As regards the regulatory framework in the Autonomous Communities, for example in Andalusia, the most recent is the Order of 26 March 2009, which regulates the aid scheme for the promotion of the first afforestation of agricultural land in the framework of the Rural Development Programme of Andalusia 2007-2013 and the Order of 2 February 2010, which amends the Order of 26 March 2009.

At present, although these regulations are in force, there is no line of financing open in this respect in Andalusia. Only maintenance aid and compensatory aid from previous programmes continue. However, the new Andalusian Rural Development Plan is expected to include this type of aid for afforestation once again.

Are there other land use developments that compete with the expansion of the LMT, and if so, how do those affect the scaling-up of the LMTs?

Afforestation or reforestation is understood as the process of establishing a stand of trees on land that has never existed or has been absent for a certain period of time, for example, due to agricultural activities.

In this sense, afforestation of agricultural land offers interesting opportunities to restore forest landscapes in economically unprofitable, abandoned or degraded areas, as a result of the abandonment or rural exodus that has taken place in rural areas during the second half of the 20th century.

In this sense, we are talking about degraded and abandoned agricultural land. At present, the tendency is not to recover this land for agriculture, but there are locations where renewable energy projects can be considered, for example, photovoltaic solar energy plants that occupy these spaces. However, this alternative to the reforestation of degraded agricultural land, due to the amount of existing surface area, is limited in terms of the land it would occupy.

4.5.4 *Climate risks & sensitivities*

Various coniferous and broadleaved native species were used in the afforestation of agricultural lands. Both mixed and monoculture stands were established, with a dominance of broadleaved species such as *Quercus ilex* for the creation of permanent forests or harvesting or high value woods in long rotation periods (Vadell et al., 2019). Landowners chose the species using mainly economic criteria, such as the payment amounts, which varied depending on the species. Nowadays, it is acknowledged that forests are highly threatened by climate change and the disturbances it provokes. The changes in climate patterns are already increasing mortality in certain tree species, initiating a change in forest community composition (Batllori et al., 2020). The specific trajectories of species change are very case dependent and should be taken into account in long term forest planning for carbon sequestration. This shift in environmental conditions was not taken into account in 1992, when the Agricultural Lands Afforestation Program started.

How sensitive is the LMT to climate related changes regarding:

- a) heat waves (extreme temperatures)***
- b) drought and desertification***
- c) forest fires***
- d) heavy rain (extreme precipitation)***
- e) river floods and sea level rise***
- f) storms and tropical cyclones***
- g) increased or generally changed weather variability***
- h) erosion and land slides***
- i) ocean acidification***
- j) loss of biodiversity***

The main risk factor related to climate, forestations and their viability considered is drought. Most reforestations are of indigenous species, *Quercus* sp., which are adapted to the terrain. However, the increasingly frequent and prolonged drought conditions and heat waves in recent years have led to the appearance of a large number of dry stands. Moreover, these are small trees, with few sapwood, which means that if both planting and maintenance work is not carried out in good weather conditions, the plants do not develop properly and die. At present, the climatic conditions are not conducive to the good development or optimal establishment of reforestations and densifications, because the soil is not in a suitable condition for this due to the drought.

Forest fires affect reforestation directly, so in the first few years, until the plants are well developed, the scrub and grasses that appear between the lanes and create a permanent cover must be removed, thereby reducing the possibility of forest fires. As well as this maintenance work, the root system must not be affected, as this could damage it considerably.

On the other hand, the contribution of reforestation to the reduction of erosion processes in the areas where it is carried out is visible. Many of the reforestations carried out in recent decades have been carried out on agricultural land or land with poor soil conditions and therefore quite eroded, which has led to a slowing down of these processes. The establishment of a permanent vegetation cover on degraded soils, with few trees, e.g. less than 10 ft/ha or 20 bushes, slows down erosion considerably.

4.5.5 *Economic implications*

This LMT is highly competitive, as it implicates a change in land use from agricultural lands that are currently unproductive to forest lands that could be managed in various ways depending on the objectives of the land manager.

Can the LMT be applied in a competitive way (i.e., returns exceed costs)?

The implementation of most of the reforestation carried out in recent decades in Extremadura is thanks to the aid for the reforestation of agricultural land that the Regional Government of Extremadura promoted years ago. These calls for aid established the conditions for both implementation (planting framework, species, work, etc.) and for maintenance and grazing periods.

As far as business aspects are concerned, it is necessary to make a high initial investment with a long amortisation period. However, it is an activity that generates jobs, as a company specialised in this type of work was contracted to implement it, as well as to carry out pruning and maintenance work.

Moreover, reforestation is directly linked to livestock farming, as sheep grazing is carried out during two periods a year, which, among other things, provides organic matter to the soil and maintains the vegetation cover.

As far as the administrations are concerned, the bureaucratic procedures for obtaining permits to carry out work such as pruning and weeding are slow, which makes it difficult to carry out such work at the right time of year.

There are many benefits or opportunities generated by the implementation of reforestation in degraded areas, both environmental and economic, for example, many of the reforestations are in a high percentage of *Quercus suber*, which through the use of cork increases the margin of economic benefit compared to those of *Quercus ilex*.

Is there any information on the costs of the LMT implementation? E.g., what are the specific costs of the LMT to reduce GHG emissions (e.g. in EUR costs per ton CO2 equivalent per ha (EUR x ton CO2eq-1 x ha-1))

Afforestation costs range from roughly 1800 €/ha to 4000 €/ha for the initial establishment of the trees. The cost depends on the species chosen (Vadell et al., 2019). Subsequent costs of forest management depend on the strategy. In addition, maintenance costs need to be taken into account for the first 10 to 15 years after the initial planting, which may be soil tillage, scrub clearance, support irrigation or replacement of dead plants.

4.5.6 *Co-benefits and trade-offs*

As mentioned in earlier paragraphs, this LMT is unlikely to compete with agriculture for the most fertile and accessible lands. Instead, it uses abandoned or derelict lands in remote locations within the country, making positive impact on their value and productivity.

Throughout its years of implementation, the Agricultural Lands Afforestation program has also had a positive impact in other areas. First, the technology and techniques to execute the reforestations have advanced greatly. Survival rates of the trees have been maximized, keeping costs and losses to a minimum. They have also contributed to environmental awareness in society. Forestry related companies can thrive thanks to the abundance of forestry works. In addition, new streams of work and research have been developed, such as the ongoing developments in carbon quantification techniques. The revitalization of the country through the afforestation program has had a positive social impact in the rural communities. New forest products such as wood, honey, game, cork, mushrooms or truffles can be extracted. Lastly, the creation of new forested areas has increased biodiversity and diversified the landscape (Iglesias Ranz et al., 2021).

Objectives of the CAP afforestation programme for agricultural land:

- To contribute to the reduction of surplus products through set-aside and less extensive farming.
- To promote farming that is more environmentally friendly and at the same time provides higher quality products.
- To contribute to the rejuvenation of the agricultural workforce.
- To actively promote the education of farmers and the general public on the need to preserve the environment.
- To contribute to the generation of stable jobs, both in direct and indirect activities related to the above objectives.
- To increase in the long term the Community's forestry resources and the management of the natural area in a more appropriate way, seeking an alternative use of agricultural land through afforestation and the development of forestry activities on farms.

What are the risks (negative side-effects) or co-benefits (positive side-effects) of the LMT for:

- a) agricultural production?***
- b) landscape?***
- c) biodiversity?***

d) nitrogen emissions?

e) water quality?

The main effect of reforestations and their associated pastures on the local environment is primarily related to carbon sequestration, reforestations play an important role as carbon sinks. It can be seen how in soils that were previously bared with poor pasture quality, where, after the reforestation was implemented, the maintenance work carried out between subsequent lanes and the absence of grazing in the first 10 years or so, has led to an improvement in pasture, soil quality and water balance.

There has also been an increase in biodiversity, in terms of vertebrates, an increase in small and large game species, an increase in the diversity of birds present and nesting sites. All this is due to the fact that these are quiet areas that are used as a refuge, as well as ecosystems with a very high diversity of fungi as a result of the quality of the soil. Furthermore, some of the reforestations implemented in recent years have been carried out with mycorrhizal plants, although there are no major differences between the reforestations that did not use this type of plant, as these are the fewest.

As far as pollination is concerned, the presence of pollinating agents is evident due to the frequent installation of beehives between the lanes.

On the other hand, pest resistance is reduced, due to the homogeneity of age classes, so that pests have a more direct impact. In particular, the carbonaceous canker disease, *Biscogniauxia mediterranea*, in cork oak trees is notable for its high presence, caused by the disinfection of tools and implements used in maintenance forestry work.

Are there any other risks / co-benefits as part of the LMT implementation?

The effects of the reforestations on the local environment are various. In terms of soil, water and air parameters, it should be noted that the reforestations were carried out on agricultural land that was not very fertile.

Trade-offs of the LMT

After the installation of the reforestation, it can be observed how the soil structure, its water retention capacity and erosion have changed. There is an increase in organic matter in the soil, also due to the fact that pruning residues are shredded and left on the ground, which contributes to improving the soil as a carbon sink.

In terms of biodiversity, there has been a high increase, due to the fact that it was previously cereal land and now forms a compact mass of trees, which has led to the appearance of a greater diversity of plants and animals.

In addition, the *Quercus ilex* and *Quercus suber* are native species, adapted to the environment and climatic conditions of the area, which makes them more resilient.

4.5.7 Risks associated with scaling up

If afforestation projects were to be widely applied, they would need to be accompanied by a comprehensive fire prevention and extinction plan. Under no circumstances should forest plantations be left unmanaged, as even-aged trees constitute a continuous canopy layer that represents a danger of fire. Carbon capture would need to be compatibilized with controlling the accumulation of fuels (biomass), to prevent large forest fires that would release large amounts of carbon into the atmosphere. This is especially relevant in Spain, which has a climate characterised by a long, dry and warm summer season.

What are the risks of scaling up specific LMT solutions from the sub-national level to the national level?

The main climate-related risk factors affecting reforestation are drought, heat waves and heavy rainfall. During the years 1996-1998, for example, there was a period of drought that lasted several years. The effects of the drought were visible in the loss of many trees, which were replaced. This period of drought coincided with the first years of reforestation, in which seedlings of one or two saps were planted.

Over the last 20 years, the climate has been fairly stable in the area, so with the exception of the previous episodes, the weather has not played an important role in the development of reforestation.

It should also be noted that 2012 was a fairly rainy year, which resulted in more grass growing between the rows and the need for more frequent maintenance work.

In any case, the experiences serve as a reference for future interventions and scaling up. Most significantly, a budget should be set aside for the planning and execution of maintenance works for the reforestation of agricultural land for 20-30 years. Without maintenance the grading leads to risks of plant death or overgrowth of undergrowth and thus increased forest fuel, which increases the risks of forest fires.

Efficient planning and correct execution of the planning is essential for successful scaling.

4.5.8 Research gaps

More research is needed to accurately quantify the carbon sequestered by a growing forest. Accurate growth and yield models adapted for carbon capture silvicultural management are required.

What are the research gaps identified during this exercise?

To our knowledge there are very few studies carried out in Spain looking at the combined effect of afforestation on oaks biomass and SOC stocks changes. Studies were either conducted on Dehesas and compared these with tree-less pastures, or they were conducted following afforestation but with other afforested species (Perez-Cruzado, 2012). Also, the outcomes of the afforestation initiatives in Spain are generally poorly documented. A final issue worth mentioning is that, for the few studies which have been done on the effects of afforestation on SOC stocks, there are large inconsistencies regarding

sampling methods, soil analysis techniques and experimental designs, which hinder the drawing of coherent conclusions.

5. Conclusion

The land mitigation technologies assessed in Spain in the framework of the LANDMARC project are land management activities that occupy large areas of land in the Iberian Peninsula. Forestry planning, forest restoration of degraded agricultural land, management of dehesa agroecosystems, or extensive grasslands, are traditional land uses in Spain, with decades and centuries of history, typical of the rural environment in Mediterranean climate environments.

Large areas of land, in rural areas, and in a Mediterranean climate. These three factors are very relevant when considering that these traditional land uses can also be considered as having an added value in terms of negative emissions and carbon sequestration and storage.

By occupying large areas, they can contribute quantitatively to the reduction of greenhouse gases.

The fact that they are traditional rural uses means that they are not immune to the implicit social and economic problems of rural areas in Spain, i.e. depopulation, masculinisation, emigration of young people and women to urban areas, abandonment of the land, increase in economic problems associated with agroforestry management, etc.

The Mediterranean climate also has its own particularities, and in the case of Spain, climate change affects aspects such as drought, desertification, forest fires and the increasingly irregular distribution of rainfall.

Therefore, considering these traditional land uses with new added values, related to ecosystem services, biodiversity, landscape, and the potential for carbon sequestration and storage, offers new perspectives and opportunities for the territories, stakeholders and people affected, in a rural environment that needs innovation, technology, talent and new sources of income, to face social, economic, environmental and climate challenges.

6. References

- Albiac, J., Notivol, E., Kahil, T., Calvo, E., 2017. Agriculture and climate change: Potential for mitigation in Spain. *Sci. Total Environ.* 592, 495–502. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.03.110>
- Aragão, L.E.O.C., Anderson, L.O., Fonseca, M.G., Rosan, T.M., Vedovato, L.B., Wagner, F.H., Silva, C.V.J., Silva Junior, C.H.L., Arai, E., Aguiar, A.P., Barlow, J., Berenguer, E., Deeter, M.N., Domingues, L.G., Gatti, L., Gloor, M., Malhi, Y., Marengo, J.A., Miller, J.B., Phillips, O.L., Saatchi, S., 2018. 21st Century drought-related fires counteract the decline of Amazon deforestation carbon emissions. *Nat. Commun.* 9, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-017-02771-y>
- Batllore, E., Lloret, F., Aakala, T., Anderegg, W.R.L., Aynekulu, E., Bendixsen, D.P., Bentouati, A., Bigler, C., Burk, C.J., Camarero, J.J., Colangelo, M., Coop, J.D., Fensham, R., Floyd, M.L., Galiano, L., Ganey, J.L., Gonzalez, P., Jacobsen, A.L., Kane, J.M., Kitzberger, T., Linares, J.C., Marchetti, S.B., Matusick, G., Michaelian, M., Navarro-Cerrillo, R.M., Pratt, R.B., Redmond, M.D., Rigling, A., Ripullone, F., Sangüesa-Barreda, G., Sasal, Y., Saura-Mas, S., Suarez, M.L., Veblen, T.T., Vilà-Cabrera, A., Vincke, C., Zeeman, B., 2020. Forest and woodland replacement patterns following drought-related mortality. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2002314117>
- Boylard, M., 2006. The economics of using forests to increase carbon storage. *Can. J. For. Res.* <https://doi.org/10.1139/X06-094>
- Campos, P., Caparrós, A., Cerdá, E., Diaz-Balteiro, L., Casimiro Herruzo, A., Huntsinger, L., Martín-Barroso, D., Martínez-Jauregui, M., Ovando, P., Oviedo, J.L., Pasalodos-Tato, M., Romero, C., Soliño, M., Standiford, R.B., 2017. Multifunctional natural forest silviculture economics revised: Challenges in meeting landowners' and society's wants: A review. *For. Syst.* 26. <https://doi.org/10.5424/fs/2017262-10505>
- Dass, P., Houlton, B.Z., Wang, Y., Warlind, D., 2018. Grasslands may be more reliable carbon sinks than forests in California. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 13, 074027. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aacb39>
- DeLonge, M.S., Ryals, R., Silver, W.L., 2013. A Lifecycle Model to Evaluate Carbon Sequestration Potential and Greenhouse Gas Dynamics of Managed Grasslands. *Ecosystems* 16, 962–979. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10021-013-9660-5>
- EIP-AGRI, 2018. Focus Group Grazing for Carbon.
- Eriksson, E., Gillespie, A.R., Gustavsson, L., Langvall, O., Olsson, M., Sathre, R., Stendahl, J., 2007. Integrated carbon analysis of forest management practices and wood substitution. *Can. J. For. Res.* 37, 671–681. <https://doi.org/10.1139/X06-257>
- Fernández Nogueira, D., Corbelle Rico, E., 2017. Cambios en los usos de suelo en la Península Ibérica: un meta-análisis para el período 1985-2015. *Rev. Bibliográfica Geogr. y Ciencias Soc.* 22.
- Fuentes Pazos, M., Zamora Rojas, E., Gallardo Cobos, R., Lara Vélez, P., 2018. Servicios ecosistémicos de la dehesa. Proyecto LIFE BioDehesa.
- Galanter, M., Levy, H., Carmichael, G.R., 2000. Impacts of biomass burning on tropospheric CO, NO_x, and O₃. *J. Geophys. Res. Atmos.* <https://doi.org/10.1029/1999JD901113>

- Ghahramani, A., Howden, S.M., del Prado, A., Thomas, D.T., Moore, A.D., Ji, B., Ates, S., 2019. Climate change impact, adaptation, and mitigation in temperate grazing systems: A review. *Sustain.* <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU11247224>
- Goetz, S.J., Bond-Lamberty, B., Law, B.E., Hicke, J.A., Huang, C., Houghton, R.A., McNulty, S., O'Halloran, T., Harmon, M., Meddens, A.J.H., Pfeifer, E.M., Mildrexler, D., Kasischke, E.S., 2012. Observations and assessment of forest carbon dynamics following disturbance in North America. *J. Geophys. Res. Biogeosciences* 117. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2011JG001733>
- Government of Spain, 2021a. Proyecto de Ley de cambio climático y transición energética. (621/000020). Senate, Madrid, Spain.
- Government of Spain, 2021b. Registro de huella de carbono, compensación y proyectos de absorción de dióxido de carbono [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/cambio-climatico/temas/mitigacion-politicas-y-medidas/registro-huella.aspx> (accessed 5.21.21).
- Government of Spain, 2021c. Bosques españoles y su evolución [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/desarrollo-rural/temas/politica-forestal/inventario-cartografia/inventario-forestal-nacional/index.aspx> (accessed 5.21.21).
- Government of Spain, 2020a. Plan Nacional de Adaptación al Cambio Climático 2021-2030. Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico, Madrid.
- Government of Spain, 2020b. Informe final sobre las acciones del sector del uso de la tierra, del cambio de uso de la tierra y de la silvicultura de España [WWW Document]. URL https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/cambio-climatico/temas/mitigacion-politicas-y-medidas/informeaccioneslulucfart10decision529diciembre2020_tcm30-520352.pdf (accessed 4.8.21).
- Government of Spain, 2020c. Estrategia de descarbonización a largo plazo 2050. Madrid, Spain.
- Government of Spain, 2015. Información sobre acciones en el sector del uso del suelo, cambio de uso del suelo y silvicultura de España.
- Government of Spain, 2003. Ley 43/2003, de 21 de noviembre, de Montes. Madrid, Spain.
- Government of Spain, 2002. Plan Forestal Español. Madrid, Spain.
- Graux, A.I., Bellocchi, G., Lardy, R., Soussana, J.F., 2013. Ensemble modelling of climate change risks and opportunities for managed grasslands in France. *Agric. For. Meteorol.* 170, 114–131. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2012.06.010>
- Hewins, D.B., Lyseng, M.P., Schoderbek, D.F., Alexander, M., Willms, W.D., Carlyle, C.N., Chang, S.X., Bork, E.W., 2018. Grazing and climate effects on soil organic carbon concentration and particle-size association in northern grasslands. *Sci. Rep.* 8, 1336. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-19785-1>
- Horrillo, A., Gaspar, P., Escribano, M., 2020. Organic farming as a strategy to reduce carbon footprint in dehesa agroecosystems: A case study comparing different livestock products. *Animals* 10, 162. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10010162>
- Houghton, R.A., House, J.I., Pongratz, J., Van Der Werf, G.R., Defries, R.S., Hansen, M.C., Le Quéré, C., Ramankutty, N., 2012. Carbon emissions from land use and land-cover change. *Biogeosciences* 9, 5125–5142. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-9-5125-2012>

- Howlett, D.S., Moreno, G., Mosquera Losada, M.R., Nair, P.K.R., Nair, V.D., 2011. Soil carbon storage as influenced by tree cover in the Dehesa cork oak silvopasture of central-western Spain. *J. Environ. Monit.* 13, 1897–1904. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c1em10059a>
- Hungate, B.A., Barbier, E.B., Ando, A.W., Marks, S.P., Reich, P.B., van Gestel, N., Tilman, D., Knops, J.M.H., Hooper, D.U., Butterfield, B.J., Cardinale, B.J., 2017. The economic value of grassland species for carbon storage. *Sci. Adv.* 3, e1601880. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.1601880>
- Iglesias Ranz, Á., Ceballos Aranda, J., Jovellar Lacambra, L.C., Sánchez Martín, Á., 2021. Programa de forestación de tierras agrarias en Castilla y León. *Desarrollo y avance de resultados. Montes* #143 14–22.
- in+dehesa, 2020. Convenio interadministrativo de colaboración entre la Consejería de Medio Ambiente y Rural, Políticas Agrarias y Territorio de la Junta de Extremadura para el desarrollo de acciones de desarrollo sostenible y adaptación al cambio climático de la dehesa.
- Juutinen, A., Ahtikoski, A., Lehtonen, M., Mäkipää, R., Ollikainen, M., 2018. The impact of a short-term carbon payment scheme on forest management. *For. Policy Econ.* 90, 115–127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2018.02.005>
- Kay, S., Graves, A., Palma, J.H.N., Moreno, G., Roces-Díaz, J. V., Aviron, S., Chouvardas, D., Crous-Duran, J., Ferreiro-Domínguez, N., García de Jalón, S., Măcicășan, V., Mosquera-Losada, M.R., Pantera, A., Santiago-Freijanes, J.J., Szerencsits, E., Torralba, M., Burgess, P.J., Herzog, F., 2019a. Agroforestry is paying off – Economic evaluation of ecosystem services in European landscapes with and without agroforestry systems. *Ecosyst. Serv.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2019.100896>
- Kay, S., Rega, C., Moreno, G., den Herder, M., Palma, J.H.N., Borek, R., Crous-Duran, J., Freese, D., Giannitsopoulos, M., Graves, A., Jäger, M., Lamersdorf, N., Memedemin, D., Mosquera-Losada, R., Pantera, A., Paracchini, M.L., Paris, P., Roces-Díaz, J. V., Rolo, V., Rosati, A., Sandor, M., Smith, J., Szerencsits, E., Varga, A., Viaud, V., Wawer, R., Burgess, P.J., Herzog, F., 2019b. Agroforestry creates carbon sinks whilst enhancing the environment in agricultural landscapes in Europe. *Land use policy* 83, 581–593. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2019.02.025>
- Lewis, S.L., Wheeler, C.E., Mitchard, E.T.A., Koch, A., 2019. Restoring natural forests is the best way to remove atmospheric carbon. *Nature* 568, 25–28. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-019-01026-8>
- Manley, B., Maclaren, P., 2012. Potential impact of carbon trading on forest management in New Zealand. *For. Policy Econ.* 24, 35–40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2010.01.001>
- Martínez-Valderrama, J., Ibáñez, J., Ibáñez, M.A., Alcalá, F.J., Sanjuán, M.E., Ruiz, A., del Barrio, G., 2021. Assessing the sensitivity of a Mediterranean commercial rangeland to droughts under climate change scenarios by means of a multidisciplinary integrated model. *Agric. Syst.* 187, 103021. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2020.103021>
- Molina, J.R., González-Cabán, A., y Silva, F.R., 2019. Potential effects of climate change on fire behavior, economic susceptibility and suppression costs in Mediterranean ecosystems: Córdoba Province, Spain. *Forests* 10, 679. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f10080679>
- Montero, G., Ruiz-Peinado, R., Muñoz, M., 2005. Producción de Biomasa y Fijación de CO₂ por los Bosques Españoles. Madrid, Spain.
- Moreno, M.V., Conedera, M., Chuvieco, E., Pezzatti, G.B., 2014. Fire regime changes and major driving forces in Spain from 1968 to 2010. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 37, 11–22.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2013.08.005>

National Statistics Institute, 2020. España en cifras.

Nunes, L.J.R., Meireles, C.I.R., Gomes, C.J.P., Ribeiro, N.M.C.A., 2020. Forest contribution to climate change mitigation: Management oriented to carbon capture and storage. *Climate*.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/cli8020021>

Nunez, S., Verboom, J., Alkemade, R., 2020. Assessing land-based mitigation implications for biodiversity. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 106, 68–76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2020.01.006>

Pateiro, M., Munekata, P.E.S., Domínguez, R., Lorenzo, J.M., 2020. Ganadería extensiva frente al cambio climático en España. *Tec. Econ. Agrar* 116, 444–460.
<https://doi.org/10.12706/itea.2020.024>

Pérez-Sánchez, J., Jimeno-Sáez, P., Senent-Aparicio, J., Díaz-Palmero, J.M., Cabezas-Cerezo, J. de D., 2019. Evolution of burned area in forest fires under climate change conditions in southern Spain using ANN. *Appl. Sci.* 9, 4155. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app9194155>

Rodríguez Martín, J.A., Álvaro-Fuentes, J., Gonzalo, J., Gil, C., Ramos-Miras, J.J., Grau Corbí, J.M., Boluda, R., 2016. Assessment of the soil organic carbon stock in Spain. *Geoderma* 264, 117–125.

Rolinski, S., Müller, C., Heinke, J., Weindl, I., Biewald, A., Leon Bodirsky, B., Bondeau, A., Boons-Prins, E.R., Bouwman, A.F., Leffelaar, P.A., Roller, J.A.T., Schaphoff, S., Thonicke, K., 2018. Modeling vegetation and carbon dynamics of managed grasslands at the global scale with LPJmL 3.6. *Geosci. Model Dev.* 11, 429–451. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-11-429-2018>

Taillardat, P., Thompson, B.S., Garneau, M., Trottier, K., Friess, D.A., 2020. Climate change mitigation potential of wetlands and the cost-effectiveness of their restoration. *Interface Focus* 10.
<https://doi.org/10.1098/rsfs.2019.0129>

Vadell, E., De Miguel, S., Fernández Centeno, G., Robla, E., Lerner, M., Pemán García, J., 2019. La forestación de tierras agrícolas: balance de un instrumento de política forestal para el cambio del uso de la tierra. *Cuad. la Soc. Española Ciencias For.* 45, 1–20.
<https://doi.org/10.31167/csecfv0i45.19497>

VVAA, 2013. Montados and dehesas as High Nature Value Farming Systems: implications for classification and policy support, in: Institute for Mediterranean Agrarian and Environmental Sciences, Universidade de Évora (Eds.), Proceedings of the ICAAM International Conference. Universidade de Évora, Évora, Portugal.

LANDMARC

**SCALING LAND-BASED MITIGATION
SOLUTIONS IN SWEDEN
LAND-BASED MITIGATION NARRATIVE CO-DESIGN**

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LANDMARC

Land-use based Mitigation for Resilient Climate Pathways

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Short Summary of results

This narrative of a Swedish portfolio of selected Land-based Mitigation Technologies (LMTs) presents a possible future of deployment and upscaling in order to contribute to the country's climate policy targets. We base the analysis on a comprehensive literature review of scientific and grey literature, as well as interviews with key stakeholders active in this field. This report discussed general and policy context, land-use competition, climate risks, co-benefits and trade-offs of each LMT. Then economic implications and risks associated with upscaling are evaluated.

The shortlisted LMTs in the Swedish context are **BECCS**, **biochar** and **afforestation**. Among these, however, only biochar can be characterised as a specific land-based measure that can be upscaled in national, regional, and global terms. BECCS is the key negative emission technology (NET) in the portfolio, as it is expected to deliver a large share of the negative emissions needed for Sweden to achieve its 2045 target for net-zero emissions.

BECCS is expected to remove 1.8 Million tonnes CO₂-eq per year by 2030 and between 3 to 10 Million tonnes CO₂-eq per year by 2045. Biochar is considered as part of the increased carbon sink in forests and land category, which, in overall is expected to remove 1.2 Million tonnes CO₂-eq per year by 2030 and a minimum of 2.7 Million tonnes CO₂-eq per year by 2045. The above means that carbon removals between 9.4 and 16.4 would be reasonable to be assumed under this narrative by the year 2045.

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3. Executive summary

Sweden's long-term strategy for reducing greenhouse gas emissions states that the country will have no net emissions of greenhouse gas by 2045 and should thereafter achieve negative emissions. As a result, the Swedish Government appointed in 2018 a commission for investigating how a "climate positive" future can be achieved for the country. The main task of the commission was to investigate three types of measures for negative emissions: (i) land-use, land-use change and forestry sector activities (LULUCF); (ii) Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS); and (iii) verified emission reductions (VER) in other countries.

This narrative of a Swedish portfolio of selected Land-based Mitigation Technologies (LMTs) presents a possible future of deployment and upscaling in order to contribute to the country's climate policy targets. We base the analysis on a comprehensive literature review of scientific and grey literature, as well as interviews with key stakeholders active in this field. This report discussed general and policy context, land-use competition, climate risks, co-benefits and trade-offs of each LMT. Then economic implications and risks associated with upscaling are evaluated.

The shortlisted LMTs in the Swedish context are **BECCS**, **biochar** and **afforestation**. Among these, however, only biochar can be characterised as a specific land-based measure that can be upscaled in national, regional, and global terms. BECCS is the key negative emission technology (NET) in the portfolio, as it is expected to deliver a large share of the negative emissions needed for Sweden to achieve its 2045 target for net-zero emissions. Biochar, although favoured for its diversity of co-benefits and co-products especially in the local context, will have a complementary role. Biochar can be scaled out (i.e., replication in different locations, countries and/or contexts and at varying scales), which is one of the reasons that it has been pursued in Sweden in spite of its somewhat limited applicability as well as the lower potential associated with the northern European climate. The wide applicability of biochar, especially in agriculture in developing countries, is of strategic interest for Sweden because of its international cooperation efforts and its commitment to investments in measures outside of Sweden to as to support pathways to negative emissions internationally as well as domestically.

BECCS is expected to remove 1.8 Million tonnes CO₂-eq per year by 2030 and between 3 to 10 Million tonnes CO₂-eq per year by 2045. Biochar is considered as part of the increased carbon sink in forests and land category, which, in overall is expected to remove 1.2 Million tonnes CO₂-eq per year by 2030 and a minimum of 2.7 Million tonnes CO₂-eq per year by 2045. The above mean that carbon removals between 9.4 and 16.4 would be reasonable to be assumed under this narrative by the year 2045. On average, this can be translated to 12.9 Million tonnes CO₂-eq per year, which is approximately equivalent to 25% of total greenhouse gas emissions in Sweden in 2019 (in CO₂-equivalent terms, excluding LULUCF).

Stakeholders working with these LMTs highlight that in order for the emission removals to be delivered in line with the Swedish net-zero targets, there needs to be stronger incentives that would in turn create viable carbon markets. Sweden has a frontrunner status regarding BECCS implementation, but it is still unclear how investments on transportation and storage of carbon will be supported and by whom. At the same time, climate change is threatening Swedish forest species and might create cascading effects affecting biodiversity and biomass supply for BECCS and biochar upscaling.

4. Introduction

Sweden's long-term strategy for reducing greenhouse gas emissions states that "by 2045 at the latest, Sweden is to have no net emissions of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere and should thereafter achieve negative emissions. This means emissions from activities on Swedish territory are to be at least 85 % lower by 2045 at latest compared with 1990. Supplementary measures may count towards achieving zero net emissions, such as increased uptake of carbon dioxide in forests and land, investments in other countries or bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS). The effect of the supplementary measures shall be calculated in accordance with internationally agreed regulations (Ministry of the Environment 2020).

The Swedish Government appointed in 2018 a commission for investigating how a "climate positive" future can be achieved for the country. The main task of the commission was to investigate three types of measures for negative emissions: (i) land-use, land-use change and forestry sector activities (LULUCF); (ii) BECCS; and (iii) verified emission reductions (VER) in other countries (Ministry of the Environment 2020). The commission's investigation supported the previous claims that BECCS has large potential for helping achieve climate targets of the country.

The shortlisted LMTs in the Swedish context are BECCS, biochar and afforestation. Among these, however, only biochar can be characterised as a specific land-based measure that can be upscaled in national, regional, and global terms. Biochar can also be scaled out (i.e., replication in different locations, countries and/or contexts and at varying scales), which is one of the reasons that it has been pursued in Sweden in spite of its somewhat limited applicability as well as the lower potential associated with the northern European climate. The wide applicability of biochar, especially in agriculture in developing countries, is of strategic interest for Sweden because of its international cooperation efforts and its commitment to investments in measures outside of Sweden to as to support pathways to negative emissions internationally as well as domestically.

BECCS is a key NET in the Swedish context in reaching zero and negative emission targets, but the land use side is less relevant because so much land in Sweden is already managed and optimised for biomass supply and bioenergy. Consequently, the main issues of concern are related to biomass supply from existing production areas and the (non-land) issues associated with carbon dioxide transport and storage. Since CO₂ storage is expected to occur outside of Sweden (e.g., Norway) there are also some implementation issues that remain unresolved, in addition to other uncertainties associated with a new technology.

Afforestation is not a major issue in Sweden in and/of itself, but rather what is important is Forest Resource Management overall, as it will intersect with—and impact the relevance of—biochar, BECCS and other LMTs in various ways, since the forest resource in Sweden is overall by far the most strategic aspect of achieving climate neutrality. Therefore, the discussion below provides this broader context

for Forests and BECCS, while the discussion around biochar follows more closely the notion of an LMT that can be scaled up in national, regional and global terms.

4.1 National policy context

Sweden has a total land area of 410 000 km² of which about 7% correspond to agricultural area and 68% to forest area, as presented in Table 1. Compared to other European countries, Sweden has one of the biggest shares of forest area.

Table 1: Total land area and distribution (SCB 2022).

Sweden land area	410 000 km²
Forest area	68%
Agricultural area	7%
Open land	22%
Built area	3%

Energy in Sweden is supplied by renewable energy sources (e.g., wind, hydro, solar PV and biofuels) and imported nuclear fuels, biofuels and fossil fuels. More than half of the energy consumption in the Swedish industrial sector stems from the pulp and paper industry, which relies in the use of energy sources such as biofuels and electricity. Alternatively, the iron and steel industry, while consuming less energy than pulp and paper industry, makes extensive use of fossil fuels (Energimyndigheten 2022).

Sweden's final energy consumption in 2020 was about 355 TWh, of which about 136 TWh (38%) were consumed by the industrial sector. On the other hand, electricity consumption in 2020 accounted for 135 TWh_{el}, of which 47 TWh_{el} (35%) were consumed by the industrial sector (Table 2).

Table 2: Industry sector energy and electricity use in 2020 (Energimyndigheten 2022).

Energy use	TWh	355
Industrial sector energy use	TWh	136
Electricity use	TWh _{el}	135
Industrial sector electricity use	TWh _{el}	47

4.2 Emission reduction goals and potential

By 2045, Sweden plans to reduce its emissions by 85%, compared to 1990. Thereafter, negative emissions should be achieved. The strategy envisioned by Sweden considers goals for the use of negative emission technologies (NET) and VER in other countries, as presented in Table 3. The baseline of emission reduction is 2030 and the projected emission reductions to 2045 consider two scenarios, one with lower and the other with higher carbon removals. BECCS is expected to remove 1.8 Million tonnes CO₂-eq per year by 2030 and between 3 to 10 Million tonnes CO₂-eq per year by 2045. Biochar is considered as part of the increased carbon sink in forests and land category, which, in overall is

expected to remove 1.2 Million tonnes CO₂-eq per year by 2030 and a minimum of 2.7 Million tonnes CO₂-eq per year by 2045. The higher end of this category is uncertain, and therefore open to higher emission reduction. Verified reductions in other countries are expected to contribute to a reduction of 0.7 Million tonnes CO₂-eq per year by 2030. Further reductions to 2045 under this category are uncertain. Despite no other NET are considered in the national planning, Sweden is open to other NETs that could contribute to enhanced emission reduction.

Table 3: Sweden’s projected emission reduction potential (Karlsson et al. 2020)

	2030	2045	
	Mtonnes CO ₂ -eq per year	Mtonnes CO ₂ -eq per year	
		Low	High
Increased carbon sink in forests and land (biochar included)	1.2	2.7	?
BECCS	1.8	3	10
Verified reductions in other countries	0.7	3.7	?
Other technologies for negative emissions	-	0	?
Total	3.7	9.4 – 16.4	

4.3 Biomass market outlook

Biomass is the main input for the implementation of BECCS and biochar in Sweden. Therefore, this section introduces biomass prices in the Swedish context. The average biomass price in 2020 was about 18.6 EUR/MWh. If a linear increase of price is assumed, then a biomass price around 20.2 EUR/MWh should be expected in 2022. If further projected to 2045, biomass price could be around 29.1 EUR/MWh (Martelius 2022). Given that the prices in 2045 are uncertain, it is relevant to consider a lower and a higher price boundary. Therefore, 14.6 EUR/MWh in the low biomass price scenario and 58.2 EUR/MWh in the high biomass price scenario could be reasonable to assume (Martelius 2022). A summary of the prices is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Biomass price projections to 2045 (Energimyndigheten 2022; Martelius 2022)

Year	Units	Low	High
2020	EUR/MWh	10	31.1
2022	EUR/MWh	20.2	20.2
2045	EUR/MWh	14.6	58.2

4.4 Structure of the report

In the following sections, the narratives for the selected LMTs representing the Swedish portfolio are presented. After a short introduction to the general and policy context of each LMT, land-use competition, climate risks, co-benefits and trade-offs are discussed for each LMT. Then economic implications and risks associated with upscaling are evaluated. Finally, we close the analysis for each LMT with a concluding discussion summarizing outlook and future research. General reflections from the LMT narratives for Sweden are summarized in the final section of this report.

Engagement with stakeholders for the development of this narrative included actors at local and national levels, including public agencies and private actors, and was aimed at identifying some initial perceptions of the enablers and barriers for LMTs and measures in Sweden and the Nordic region. We included stakeholders with general knowledge on climate and/or sectoral issues (e.g. biomass and bioenergy sector stakeholders) but focused more on those with knowledge on the key LMTs that have been identified for our LMT portfolio. The stakeholder views were used as input in the development of the national LMT portfolio and narrative, as well as a commentary on future research directions and knowledge gaps that our project should cover. Stakeholder input has been used to validate modelling and case study assumptions, as well as for increasing our understanding of government strategies to create a well-functioning system for LMTs and NETs. Stakeholder input was gathered through one-to-one semi-structured interviews, a survey, as well as the first regional engagement workshop.

5. BECCS

5.1 Introduction

Bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS) is among the key mitigation technologies in most 1.5–2.0 oC compatible climate change mitigation scenarios. BECCS refers to a group of technologies used for capturing and storing carbon emitted from biomass combustion. Even though widely discussed in literature, actual BECCS implementation projects are few. Previous literature attributes this to the high upfront costs and the lack of strong policy drivers (Fridahl et al. 2020).

BECCS is a technology to achieve negative emissions, by sequestering emissions resulting from biomass burning. As a result, BECCS has multiple benefits; it combines energy production (electricity and heat), with negative emissions. BECCS is a popular choice in integrated assessment models (IAMs) that optimize costs. Previous studies estimate that the median estimation in IAMs for the BECCS deployment for primary energy use production by 2050 is 46 % (Fridahl 2018). Out of 116 scenarios of the IPCC, 101 with a “likely” chance to stay below 2 oC include BECCS. In 67 of these scenarios, BECCS represents 20 % of the global primary energy by 2100 (Fuss et al. 2014).

BECCS is currently strongly pursued in Sweden by Stockholm Exergi, an energy company, which supplies the Stockholm region with electricity, heat, cooling, as well as provides waste management services. Stockholm Exergi is partially owned (50 %) by the municipality of Stockholm. The other owner of Stockholm Exergi is the Finnish energy company Fortum.

Among local authorities, Stockholm’s municipality is one of the actors that discuss the possibility of including BECCS as part of negative emissions portfolios that would help achieve their climate targets. But apart from Stockholm, many other Swedish municipalities are interested in BECCS. For example, the climate policy knowledge network of Climate Municipalities (Klimatkommunerna in Swedish) has published material explaining how BECCS, among other technologies, can contribute to negative emissions .

In December 2019, Stockholm Exergi inaugurated a research facility in order to test BECCS, and in the autumn of 2020, the Swedish Energy Agency, approved a grant that gave the opportunity to Stockholm Exergi to expand the tests to additional technologies and processes. The target according to Stockholm Exergi is to get more robust results from operation of the small-scale demo, before proceeding with investments to a large-scale facility.

5.2 Policy context

Sweden’s carbon neutrality target has been translated in previous scenario studies to a net zero CO₂ emissions target from 2045 to 2050, which in turn would need BECCS to achieve a maximum of 6.5 Mt negative CO₂ emissions (equivalent to 10% of the emissions in 1990), with linear CO₂ reductions between 2030 and 2045 (Millot, Krook-Riekkola, and Maïzi 2020).

The investigation also suggested the direction of complementing measures up to 2030 regarding increasing the impact of carbon sinks in terms of emission reduction. Among them, BECCS measures should aim for a reduction of 1.8 Mton CO₂eq/year. After 2030 and with a comprehensive strategy in place, the potential emissions savings from BECCS up to 2045 could reach between 3 to 10 Mton CO₂eq/year (Karlsson et al. 2020). For this goal to be met, it is projected that between 3 to 5 plants are in operation by 2045 (Karlsson et al. 2020).

One of the main policy instruments to assist implementation of BECCS and help realize Swedish goals on carbon neutrality is the so-called “Industrial Leap” (Industriklivet in Swedish), administered by the Swedish Energy Agency. BECCS is seen as a potential option for the Swedish energy intensive industries, such as the cement sector (Ministry of the environment & Government offices of Sweden, 2020). Previous case studies on the deployment of BECCS in the Swedish base industry recommend a wide set of actions in order to motivate BECCS investments; RD&D funding, governmental risk sharing and state funding to first-of-the-kind projects, support for niche markets through public/private procurement, market making for zero- and negative-CO₂ products, as well as adaptation of infrastructure policies (Rootzén et al. 2018).

The Industrial Leap’s scope was amended in 2020 in order to facilitate supporting measures leading to negative emissions such as BECCS. The budget of the Industrial Leap has also been steadily increasing; from 30 million € in 2018, to 50 million € in 2019, and the government has proposed an increase by 60 million € for the period 2020-2022 (Ministry of the Environment 2020). As mentioned above, Stockholm Exergi received a grant for their industrial test project. A total of 10 million € was allocated to the promotion of negative emission technologies. This was the first economic incentive for test facilities for BECCS .

BECCS has an important role to play from a political perspective in Sweden’s case; developing this technology at full-scale will help Sweden maintain frontrunner status both at the climate policy arena, but also from an international business perspective according to some stakeholders (Christiansen 2020). In the budget proposition for 2021, the government discusses how NETs are important for strengthening businesses export ability and competitiveness at an international level. The Swedish Energy Agency suggests that a national centre for CCS should be developed, focusing among others on introducing an auctioning system for BECCS that would support operation of such plants already from 2022 . It is also recognized that Sweden should influence processes at the EU level in order to introduce policy instruments for BECCS that are cross-national.

However, the Swedish Climate Policy Council recommends that the creation of such incentives, as the ones discussed above, should be clarified in order to implement and scale up CCS in general, and more specifically BECCS, which currently seems to be necessary for certain types of emissions and for being able to reach negative emissions (Klimatpolitiska rådet 2019).

The storage of the captured CO₂ emissions is planned to be underground. As of today, local storage is underexplored. An estimation indicates that the storage capacity in Sweden is about 3,400 Million

tonnes of CO₂, but these are not confirmed. Exploration for local storage is previewed for 2040. The option following would be international storage (Karlsson et al. 2020). Denmark and Norway have geological storage availability (Table 5). However, the current Swedish regulation severely limits the transportation and geological storage of emissions in other countries (Martelius 2022).

Table 5: Underground storage capacity (Karlsson et al. 2020)

	Storage capacity (Million tonnes CO₂)
Sweden	3,400
Denmark	22,000
Norway	94,600

In this sense, the regulation requires to be updated to allow local and international CO₂ transportation and storage. Only if international storage infrastructure is not possible, local storage would be considered by Sweden. This could hinder BECCS development and risk meeting the 2045 goals (Martelius 2022).

5.3 Current land use and potential land-use competition

BECCS is likely to compete with other land-based activities, such as food production. This negative side-effect can be mitigated with agricultural intensification, but this approach could instead lead to biodiversity loss and increased biochemical flows. There are no specific studies quantifying these impacts for Sweden in the case of scaled-up BECCS, a research gap which is necessary to fill (Fajardy et al. 2019).

5.4 Climate risks and sensitivities

Negative emission technologies have been a topic for debate with regards to how their effects are modelled in IAMs. Previous studies express concerns on the feasibility of deploying such technologies large-scale. IAMs assume that large areas of arable land (e.g. double the size of India) will need to be available to provide biomass for BECCS. Area availability of such magnitude is unrealistic and would lead to significant loss of biodiversity and risks for food security (Christiansen 2020). There are yet no studies specific for such effects for the case of a Swedish implementation of BECCS.

However, as discussed by Swedish stakeholders, these risks may cause a big uncertainty, but as long as an offset claim has not been made on the affected land, the problems of that uncertainty can be minimized. There is indeed increased risk of disturbances from a changing climate, e.g. from pests (in Sweden the spruce bark beetle), storms, wildfires, drought etc. which means that storing carbon in forests is an uncertain climate mitigation strategy associated with risk. In that sense, permanent ground storage that biochar and BECCS offer are less sensitive to risks, however permanence is still an

issue that needs to be clarified. Additionally, climate disturbances will affect the biomass availability, which will have indirectly negative impacts on other LMTs' deployment.

5.5 Co-benefits and trade-offs

Some estimations have been proposed for calculating the impact of BECCS in electricity production and energy use. According to national assessment, the capture and compression of 2 Mtonne CO₂ will increase the consumption of biomass by 0.6 TWh, meaning that about 0.3 TWh of additional biomass are needed per Mtonne CO₂ processed (Karlsson et al. 2020). Additionally, electricity consumption is predicted to increase too. It is estimated that an additional 0.2 TWh_{el} per Mtonne CO₂ captured and compressed will be needed (Karlsson et al. 2020).

Emission intensive sectors such as cement and iron and steel, could potentially reduce their emission with Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS). In the case of the cement industry, there are limited alternatives to decrease process CO₂ emissions given that in clinker production emissions are practically unavoidable. In the case of iron and steel, using CCS is an alternative to emission reduction (Karlsson et al. 2020). It has been estimated that a potential reduction of 12 Mton CO₂ could require about 22 TWh of energy. This translates to an energy requirement of about 1.8 MWh per tonne CO₂ to capture the emissions in these sectors (Karlsson et al. 2020).

BECCS may have impact on resource depletion, soil health, and biodiversity, since it can lead to monocultures for increased biomass yields. In fact, these negative side-effects have been identified as major limitations to the deployment of BECCS. Land use as well as water depletion associated with BECCS is according to previous studies a major concern (Fajardy et al. 2019). Nevertheless, implications of BECCS for the food, water, energy, biodiversity, and social systems nexus remain unclear at the regional/local scale.

There are mainly two routes currently discussed for BECCS; one via liquid biofuel production (biodiesel or ethanol) and the other via biomass conversion to heat and power (most often with direct pulverized combustion of biomass). Both routes imply the presence of co-benefits from implementing BECCS, since energy is produced, either as fuel or as electricity and heat. This means that implementation of BECCS could not only deliver negative emissions, but also help decarbonize other sectors, such as transport or heating sector.

However, there are some important risks connected to large-scale BECCS sustainability that can be summarized as follows (Fajardy et al. 2019):

- The industry's potential scale – IAMs estimate large-scale BECCS deployment being two thirds of the size of today's fossil industry by the end of the century,
- The reliance of large-scale BECCS on a significant quantity of sustainable biomass, and additionally water, land and nutrients,
- The possibility that BECCS deployment would encourage delays in mitigation action, and
- Missing the 2100 temperature target if BECCS potential to deliver negative emissions is not realized.

Additionally, stakeholder interviews highlighted the need for common accounting protocols and standards for negative emissions in order to be able to globally trade them in common markets.

On the other hand, the underground storage of the captured CO₂ will require transportation to suitable geological locations. Considering that most of the storage capacity is international (Norway and Denmark), transportation is required to deliver the captured emissions. Two types of transport options considered by Sweden are boat transportation and pipelines.

Boat transportation is judged as a realistic option for the foreseeable future (Karlsson et al. 2020). Sweden could potentially make use of the Mälaren and the Vänern lakes, as well as the Baltic Sea to ship the captured CO₂ to suitable underground storage in Norway or Denmark. One transport scenario considers the use of 4,000 tonne-capacity ships, able to travel about 1500 km in a one-way trip to Norway. Transportation cycle time would be around 200 hours (sailing at 12 knots and considering 70 hours in total for loading and unloading). In this case, one ship could do about 40 transport cycles per year, which represent a total of 160,000 tonnes of CO₂/per year (Karlsson et al. 2020). A second transport scenario considers the use of a bigger ship, powered with LPG, with a capacity of 20,000 tonnes. In this case, about 800,000 Mtonne CO₂/year could be potentially transported to international underground storage (Karlsson et al. 2020).

In contrast, pipeline transportation is considered less feasible, mainly due to the logistic implications of planning, designing and installing pipeline systems that connect the emitters and the potential storage sites, which already implies long distances (Karlsson et al. 2020). Along the same line, Swedish landscape conditions make a project like this unrealistic. First, the pipelines would need to cross hard rock, lakes and nature conservation areas. Secondly, a connection of the ground-level pipelines to the sea bottom would be needed, which represents increased costs. As a result, the emergence of such pipeline infrastructure would be dependent on state investment and would potentially require the creation of a state-owned company to oversee the piping system's operation (Karlsson et al. 2020).

5.6 Economic implications

According to the Swedish Government's investigation, which was recently published, the costs for BECCS should be expected to be within a range of 400 to 600 SEK/ton CO₂ with an additional cost of 150 to 300 SEK/ton CO₂ for the transportation to storage sites (including sites outside of Sweden). The storage itself is expected to cost between 100 and 200 SEK/ton CO₂. As presented in Table 6, the total cost would thus vary between 650 and 1,100 SEK/ton CO₂ (about 65 – 110 €/ton CO₂). The capital costs are expected to decrease by 30 % by 2045, but at the same time there is uncertainty regarding the long-term price trends for biomass supply, which could influence the overall cost of the technology (Karlsson et al. 2020).

Table 6: Forecast prices for BECCS stages (Karlsson et al. 2020).

	Low	High
	SEK/tonne CO ₂	
Capture of CO ₂	400	600
Transportation	150	300
Storage and safety	100	200
Total cost	650	1,100

Furthermore, Stockholm Exergi together with researchers have published their estimations for the costs and benefits of a potential large-scale implementation of BECCS for the case of Stockholm and the KVV8 plant. The calculations included a range on assumptions for potential costs for transport and storage and conclude that costs would range from 55 to 93 €/tonne CO₂, which is somewhat lower, but within the same range with the costs indicated in the government investigation (Levihn et al. 2019).

The study concludes that BECCS is cost-efficient compared to many other abatement options, and abating 850 ktonne CO₂/year (i.e. full scale implementation of BECCS at KVV8) would cost 47 – 79 million €/year for Stockholm Exergi. In order to manage the implementation of BECCS on one plant, Stockholm Exergi would have to increase the income by 10 %, according to the authors' calculations. With a profit at 120 million € (2016 values), this would mean reduced profit by 39 to 66 %. It should be noted that transferring cost to the consumers is not an option considered, because of the deregulated competitive heat market (Levihn et al. 2019).

Nevertheless, the municipality of Stockholm calculated the private and social costs of BECCS in the climate plan of 2017. The CO₂ abatement potential through BECCS was estimated to be more than 2000 ktonne CO₂/year. The private cost (cost for the municipality who owns 50 % of Stockholm Exergi) would then be 50 €/t CO₂ and the social cost (for Sweden) was estimated at 120 €/t CO₂. These numbers refer to a case where Exergi would have to be the sole investor on BECCS for KVV8, while in reality it is likely that State support would be required for realizing such an investment.

The cost competitiveness of the technology in the future is closely linked to carbon pricing as well as the potential to build a market for the negative emissions created. This is confirmed from our interviews with Swedish stakeholders, who discussed the need of a global market for negative emissions, in the same manner as the EU ETS. The carbon tax is not sufficient for doing any difference between fossil and renewable fuels.

5.7 Risks associated with scaling up

Stakeholder interviews show there are technical, political, economic, and other risks that BECCS would have to overcome for scaling-up and becoming commercial. From the technical perspective, building and adapting existing CCS technologies to various industry types is one challenge, for example. From

the political perspective, increasing interest and support for the technology is considered a challenge and from the economic perspective, introducing financial instruments and incentives for public and private investors at a wider scale is one of the main barriers. Finally, alleviating the public's concerns and spreading knowledge about the technology is another important challenge that the technology faces (Jakobsson 2020).

Another interview-based analysis stress that, in Sweden, both material and ideational factors support the role of negative emission technologies (NETs) – especially BECCS – as a way for the country to maintain a status of international frontrunner for battling climate change. However, financing BECCS and other NETs might be a challenge to the widely established “polluter pays” principle; rights and responsibilities for funding and implementing the technologies will shift to the society (Christiansen 2020). In other words, will the public fund private companies deploying BECCS in order to provide negative emissions? This would require strong public support, and, in any case, the potential risks should be discussed.

A remaining question is to what extent existing Swedish and international (UN, EU) climate policy instruments provide incentives for researching, developing, demonstrating and eventually upscaling BECCS in Sweden. It is possible that Swedish climate policy instruments would need to be reformed to deliver the desired effects when it comes to BECCS. It recommended that efforts to remove regulatory barriers continue and are complemented with demand-pull instruments. The existing policy mix needs to be reformed, in order to avoid risking substantial public expenditure on BECCS without succeeding with substantial deployment and diffusion of the technology (Fridahl et al. 2020).

5.8 Conclusion

BECCS is a key NET in the Swedish context, expected to deliver a large share of emission removals in line with the Swedish policy target to be a net-zero welfare country by 2045. This has led to Sweden being among the frontrunners of BECCS demonstration projects around the world, with planning for upscaling being at a relatively more advanced stage than other EU countries. Still, significant investments would be needed not just on the actual carbon capture and removal plants, but also in transportation and permanent storage of the carbon. There are technical, political, economic, and other risks that BECCS would have to overcome for scaling-up and becoming commercial, but there certainly is a technology that Sweden is placing at a central point in its LMT portfolio.

Negative emission accounting methods have been identified as an important knowledge gap according to interviews. Incorporating the time and lifecycle perspectives are two parameters which are also of interest when developing LMT portfolio narratives and modelling potential impacts. There is lack of a system in order to get reimbursed for negative emissions. How would a global market of negative emissions look like? Additionally, it should be further explored how countries should have their own systems/instruments to support biomass technologies. There is a policy gap for the large-scale implementation and storage of BECCS that is necessary to address.

6. Biochar

6.1 Introduction

Biochar is produced when plant matter is heated in a zero or low oxygen environment at relatively low temperatures (300 – 1000 °C) in a process called pyrolysis, when done in a zero oxygen environment (Saifullah et al. 2018; Hertsgaard 2014); or gasification, for low oxygen environments (Woolf et al. 2014). After the transformation, biochar can come in many forms such as sticks, pellets or dust (Hertsgaard 2014).

Biochar has many applications. According to the European Biochar Industry Consortium (EBI), biochar could be used to sequester carbon in soils (although a percentage of the char will decay) or it can be used in building materials (housing, asphalt) (Bier et al. 2020). If mixed into the soil, biochar enhances plant and crop growth and is said to have positive impacts on soil quality (Agegnehu, Srivastava, and Bird 2017; Agegnehu et al. 2016), although the long-term benefits in real world applications might be less than thought and might require further study (Jones et al. 2012). Additionally, biochar could be fed to livestock, thus enhancing soil quality indirectly (Gunnerund 2021). Sequestration potential varies according to assumptions such as availability of biomass and production efficiency, but is said to range between 1 and 3 Gigatons of CO₂ per year globally (Bier et al. 2020), also in a sustainable manner (Woolf et al. 2010).

Biochar is currently produced on small scale in Sweden and is used as a soil amendment in parks and tree plantations. However, these small quantities not accounted for in Swedish climate and emission reporting (Karlsson et al. 2020).

In terms of biochar production, The European Biochar Industry Consortium (2022) reported that about 20,000 tonnes biochar were produced in Europe 2021. Of this, Scandinavia represents 23% of overall production. Sweden participation in the Scandinavian biochar market represents about 75%, which translates in an estimated biochar production of 3,450 tonnes. If an average of 2,9 tonnes CO₂ stored per tonne biochar is assumed, it can be estimated that about 10,000 tonnes of CO₂ were stored in the biochar produced in Sweden (The European Biochar Industry Consortium 2022).

6.2 Policy context

Even though biochar deployment is currently limited, it is expected to play an important role in the Swedish mitigation strategy. For instance, biochar is mentioned in the Swedish National Integrated Energy and Climate plan (a plan to be delivered regularly due to EU regulation EU 2018/1999) and other studies speak of policy support to be expected (Azzi, Karlton, and Sundberg 2021).

On the local level, the city of Stockholm explicitly mentions biochar in its climate action plan of 2020 – 2023 (Stockholms Stad 2020), which lists increased use of biochar produced at local plants as one of the measures for reducing emissions and eventually leading to a climate positive municipality. According to an interview with Stockholm's municipality, the city is involved in several international

initiatives building knowledge on issues related to implementation of negative emission technologies, such as biochar and BECCS, and even though land management is not directly under their sphere of influence, they are interested in the potential of negative emission technologies that can support the realization of their climate targets.

The potential emission savings per year by biochar deployment in Sweden are estimated to be less than 1 Mton CO₂ up to 2045, but according to the recent Swedish Government's investigation the use of biochar as fertilizer is considered to be the technology which has the "[...] largest practical potential to contribute to negative emissions for Sweden by the middle of this century" (Karlsson et al. 2020). The report also recommends that investment support for biochar should continue through various programs.

The city of Stockholm has built a pyrolysis plant to turn park and garden waste into biochar with the funding of the Bloomberg Mayors Challenge fund (Bloomberg Cities Network 2021). There is a pilot plant in Högdalen annually producing 300 tons biochar from 1300 tons of garden waste (Gustafsson 2017). Five more plants are planned, which are expected to produce 7000 tonnes of biochar per year, thus sequestering 25,200 tonnes of CO₂ per year¹. Other cities and municipalities also have several pilot projects such as Länghem where a company works on carbon credit certification for biochar or Hällekis where a farm is producing biochar from waste. In addition, Swedish stakeholders are rather active in the research and development (R&D) sector when it comes to biochar. For instance, the energy and agriculture department of the university of Uppsala has a research programme on biochar as does KTH Royal Institute of Technology.² Some private sector players such as Envigas focus on making the process more efficient.³ However, besides those pilot projects and early innovators, production and use of biochar is still in its early stages (Azzi, Karlton, and Sundberg 2021).

The Klimatkliv fund, administered by the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency, allows entities to compete for grants to implement emission reduction projects. In the past, Klimatkliv has financed biochar projects and the total budget in 2019 stood at SEK 1.5 billion (Ministry of Infrastructure 2020). As mentioned above, the Stockholm plant was financed by the Bloomberg Mayors Challenge fund, so international financing is available as well. Financing biochar deployment is also discussed under agricultural programs.

6.3 Current land use and potential land-use competition

Biochar applications and production facilities are in the beginning phase of its deployment, truly a niche technology (Geels 2010). Therefore, impacts on land use have seldom been investigated and historic data is lacking.

¹ https://nordregio.org/sustainable_cities/stockholm-biochar-project/

² <https://www.biochar.abe.kth.se/>

³ All info from <https://www.nordicbiochar.org/about-us/map/>

Biochar is not considered a main technology to achieve negative emissions, but as a complementary measure that could contribute to Sweden’s achievement of its objectives. Biochar potential is projected to be, in an optimistic scenario, up to 1 Million tonnes of CO₂ stored per year, as long as economic measures and incentives accompany its market expansion. This would require employing at least 5.4 TWh worth of biomass (branches and park and garden waste) for the pyrolysis process, and about 500,000 tonnes of biochar would be produced as a result (Karlsson et al. 2020).

Like many LMTs, biochar might enter in competition with other LMTs for land and resources. To produce biochar, input materials in form of biomass is needed which might enter in competition with land for food growth (Tisserant and Cherubini 2019). However, (Dumortier et al. 2020) observe in their models that land-use change might even decrease, provided that the baseline lands produce higher yields (assumed 1% in their US case study) because of biochar applications (Dumortier et al. 2020).

6.4 Climate risks & sensitivities

Overall, there are not many studies investigating the impacts of climate change on biochar. Biochar production entails an “energy penalty”, meaning that, in addition to the feedstock, between 2.5 to 3 TWh of additional biomass are needed in order to produce about 500,000 ton of biochar per year (Karlsson et al. 2020, 667). Azzi, Karlton, and Sundberg (2021) study Swedish biochar systems and report potential reduced biochar production capacities when heat demand (in combined systems where heat is used to heat homes/farms) varies according to weather patterns, depending on electricity demand and heat demand. This might be interpreted in the way that exceptionally cold or, conversely, mild winters will influence biochar production.

Table 7: Biochar energy production and penalty (additional biomass) for the production of 500,000 ton biochar (Karlsson et al. 2020).

		Low	High
Energy production	TWh	2	4
Additional biomass required	TWh	2.5	3

Jahromi et al. (2020) in a case study in Tennessee, U.S. observe that biochar increases water retention in flooded sandy soil suggesting that biochar might be able to mitigate the impacts of heavy rainfall. Similarly, biochar has been observed to increase the health of soils by mitigating soil erosion, increasing soil porosity, and by improving soil consistency (Blanco-Canqui 2017). When it comes to flooding, biochar was observed to have water filtering qualities when applied in lab setting which potentially makes it appropriate to mitigate influx of metals, nitrates, phosphates and other substances in storm water (Reddy, Xie, and Dastgheibi 2014).

Another also unresearched issue is the impact of biochar on the reflectiveness (albedo) of the surfaces it is applied to which might change the temperature of the soil. However, initial studies suggest a saturation effect (applying more biochar over a certain threshold - going from 30 tonnes per ha to 60

tonnes per ha in the case study - doesn't affect the albedo) and propose to mitigate negative effects of the darkening of the surface by improved land management (Genesio et al. 2012). Other studies, in turn, see a reduction in climate mitigation potential by -30% in high solar irradiation contexts such as the Mediterranean (Bozzi et al. 2015).

6.5 Economic implications

Tisserant and Cherubini (2019) argue that biochar was one of the most affordable negative emission technologies (NET). But given the different biochar production pathways (high temperature, low temperature pyrolysis, gasification etc.) and the different input materials possibly used, cost and benefits vary from location to location and from context to context (Pratt and Moran 2010).

For instance, a study for Western and Northern Europe concluded a negative net present value (costs outweigh the benefits), while a positive net present value was found for sub-Saharan Africa (Dickinson et al. 2015). Nevertheless, Latawiec et al. (2019) found that costs for biochar production and application in Brazil for small farms largely outweigh the benefits. However, a case study in Canada modelled biochar production in combination with energy production and came to the conclusion that, provided that carbon sequestration can be monetised at 60 Canadian dollars per ton sequestered CO₂ (about EUR 42), biochar applications could be profitable for farmers 12 years after investment (Homagain et al. 2016). Interestingly, the study identifies the pyrolysis process as having the biggest impact on overall costs (36%), thus pointing to the fact that efficiency gains in pyrolysis technology might increase the profitability of biochar applications.

Production cost of biochar vary widely depending on the technology used and the study parameters (Meyer, Glaser, and Quicker 2011). Slow pyrolysis in an earthen kiln was found to be the most expensive process (at 3,747 USD/tonne), while slow pyrolysis in a drum kiln was found to be producible at 41USD/tonne (Meyer, Glaser, and Quicker 2011).

In Sweden's national climate plan, Karlsson et al. (2020) refer to international biochar price for two types of biochar. On one hand, high quality biochar was found to be around 500 to 600 € per ton biochar. On the other hand, biochar for construction market price lies around 450 € per ton biochar.

Table 8: Observed market biochar prices (Karlsson et al. 2020).

	Low	High
	EUR/ton biochar	
High-quality biochar with low level of hydrocarbon	500	600
Biochar for construction soil	450	

The interviewed Swedish actors agreed that there are currently no economic incentives for biochar deployment in Sweden. Creating a market for biochar products from different feedstocks is also discussed in the Swedish Government investigation for a climate positive country. The investigation

provides some estimations on potential costs for biochar used as fertilizer (0.9-2.8 SEK/kg CO₂ or 0.1-0.3 €/kg CO₂) (Karlsson et al. 2020).

6.6 Co-benefits and trade-offs

A technical factor that should be considered when accounting for emission storage in biochar is carbon stability, which is directly related to carbon permanence. Permanence refers to the amount of carbon that remains in the biochar sample after some time. It is desired that carbon performance in biochar is at least 100 years or more. The permanence of carbon in biochar obtained through slow pyrolysis at a temperature of around 450 °C, after 100 years, is about 80% (Karlsson et al. 2020).

Table 9 shows the carbon content and yields of biochar depending on the different production methods.

Table 9: Carbon content and yields of biochar depending on the different production methods (Meyer, Glaser, and Quicker 2011)

process type	typical process temperature	typical residence time	typical solid product yield on a dry wood feed-stock basis [in mass %]	typical carbon content of the solid product [in mass %]	typical carbon yield: (mass _{carbon, product} /mass _{carbon, feedstock})	reference
torrefaction	~ 290 °C	10– 60 min	61–84%	51–55%	0.67–0.85	16, 20
slow pyrolysis	~ 400 °C	minutes to days	≈ 30%	95%	≈ 0.58	16, 21
fast pyrolysis	~ 500 °C	~ 1 s	12–26%	74%	0.2–0.26	16, 17, 22, 23
gasification	~ 800 °C	~10 to 20 s	≈ 10%			15, 16
htc	~ 180–250 °C	1–12 h	<66% ^b	<70% ^a	≈ 0.88	12, 24
flash carbonization	~ 300–600 °C	<30 min	37%	≈ 85%	≈ 0.65	25

^aThe carbon content of 70% of the product indicated in Tsukashima²⁴ is related to the dry, ash-free product. ^b Lower solid product yields for htc at both shorter and longer residence times are reported by Libra et al.¹²

Studies on a Swedish farm (using model runs) point to the fact that a combined heat and pyrolysis installation on a farm (50 kW heat capacity) could save around 12 tonnes of CO₂eq per year, or the equivalent of 1.5 average Swedish citizens (Azzi, Karlton, and Sundberg 2021). If half (12,500) of comparable Swedish farms (25,000 in total), were to use the investigated technology, around 125,000 tonnes of biochar could be produced, saving 0.3 million tonnes of CO₂eq annually (Azzi, Karlton, and Sundberg 2021).

Biochar applications to soils do seem to have tangible benefits (see above) and some scholars make the connection between improved soil quality and crops yields (Palansooriya et al. 2019). In a meta review of published studies, (Biederman and Harpole 2013) come to the conclusion, that biochar increased “[...] aboveground productivity, crop yield, soil microbial biomass, rhizobia nodulation, plant K tissue concentration, soil phosphorus (P), soil potassium (K), total soil nitrogen (N), and total soil carbon (C) compared with control conditions.” However, some studies nuance this picture and argue that biochar’s impact on crop yield would depend on things factors like the pH value of the soil (moderate pH soils are already quite nutrient rich, therefore, biochar addition in moderate pH soils in temperate climates would yield less benefits) (Jeffery et al. 2017).

Regarding effects on the landscape, and since biochar is mostly used underground, impacts are expected to be negligible, except with a potential darkening of the soil. Furthermore, impacts on biodiversity have not been studied in depth. Experiments have shown that biochar applications have increased “biological activities” (Gałązka et al. 2019), but other studies came to the conclusion that different land management practices would have a larger impact compared to biochar (Hardy et al. 2019). There is, however, a positive impact on nitrogen emissions. According to a meta-analysis, N₂O emissions could be 38 – 54 % lower if biochar was applied to soils and nitrate leaking might be reduced by 13 % (Borchard et al. 2019; Cayuela et al. 2014). Finally, studies show that application of biochar generally increased the capacity of soil to retain water (Fischer et al. 2019).

A study investigating a biochar pyrolysis unit on a Swedish farm reported several potential side effects based on model results: higher land use and negative impacts on human via a respiratory route (compared to purely electric heating) since combustion of biomass and the pyrolysis process can also generate harmful gases and air pollutants (Azzi, Karlton, and Sundberg 2019). Also, while not detecting any long term negative environmental impacts, (Gruss et al. 2019) observed short-term avoidance of biochar applied in fields for springtails (an insect) in laboratory tests due to a sudden increase in pH, suggesting some potential short term toxicity. Similarly, studies found that depending on the input materials used for the pyrolysis, biochar products might develop toxic properties (Godlewska, Ok, and Oleszczuk 2021).

Nevertheless, the Swedish Government’s investigation on carbon sinks concluded that more studies are needed on the effects of biochar on agriculture, carbon sequestration, and the environment taking into account the Swedish prerequisites (Karlsson et al. 2020).

One recently published Swedish study estimates the environmental impacts from biochar production using soil waste as feedstock. It is in the study that the increased demand for biomass would be met by harvesting residues from Swedish forestry. Even when emissions were included as a result of this direct change in land use (loss of forest ecosystem due to harvest compared to non-harvest), climate change impacts are low compared to other conventional heating fuels. With another set of assumptions about the availability of biomass, lower bioenergy availability for biochar production would lead to higher climate impacts. However, high stability of the biochar and low emission factors for electricity and biomass make the Swedish case unique and show large potential for emissions’ reduction (Enell et al. 2020).

The main trade-off when it comes to biochar production is the competition between on the one hand energy and heat (generated by burning biomass) and on the other hand the different products which are technically feasibly using the pyrolysis or gasification pathways. Figure 1 gives an overview of different pathways.

Figure 1: Biomass to bioproducts pathways. Source: Woolf et al. (2014).

As Woolf et al. (2014) have shown, the choice of heating temperature, input materials, the efficiency of the production site itself and the expected product to come out of the process have considerable impacts on biochar yields, heat generation and yields of other products (bio oils, syngas etc.). For instance, higher temperatures usually yield biochar high in carbon content (i.e. more carbon sequestration) (Zhao, Ta, and Wang 2017), which in turn reduces other fuel yields and increased energy demand as input (Woolf et al. 2014).

6.7 Risks associated with scaling up

One of the main risks of scaling of biochar it's its competition with cropland if biomass is grown especially for the purpose of converting it to energy and biochar, although increasing crop yields due to biochar application might offset this land-use change (Dumortier et al. 2020). Also, using waste biomass to produce biochar might offset the impact on land-use change, but the diverging lignite and moisture content of waste biomass could further complicate the picture of yield identified above (Tripathi, Sahu, and Ganesan 2016). Another risk might lie in the effect of biochar application of soil reflectivity and soil darkening.

There is interest in biochar from the perspective of a developing market, but as demand grows so should the supply grow as well. Ensuring profitable selling of heat and biochar is important not for just upscaling within Sweden but also outscaling to the rest of the world (Söderqvist, Norberg, and Turnstedt 2021). This was also confirmed in interviews, where the co-benefits from producing biochar through pyrolysis include the production of gas which can be used for running peak-power plants and support the grid when high capacity is needed. Ensuring the necessary grid capacity under peak loads

has been a point of major discussions in the past years in Sweden, and according to recent reports the potential of biobased solutions has not been fully exploited.

6.8 Conclusion

Although currently deployed at smaller volumes, biochar will play a role in achieving Swedish climate policy targets, as a complementary measure with several co-benefits, such as soil productivity enhancement, as well as co-products, such as heat and electricity. Swedish municipalities have been active in exploring biochar implementation, but upscaling would require incentives and a stable market creation.

Climate risks and sensitivities are not well covered by the literature when it comes to biochar. Also quite surprisingly, there are few studies which take into consideration land-use change implications if biomass would be grown specifically for charcoal production. Moreover, investigating the issue of soil reflectivity (albedo) more in depth is another research gap. (Jakobsson, 2020). According to interviews, it is also important to connect to the Global Carbon Project in order to gain understanding about how biomass is increasing at the global level and how could this be utilized for biochar production.

7. Afforestation, Reforestation, Forest Management

7.1 Introduction

Sweden has more land under forest than any other country in the EU, with Sweden and Finland together accounting for nearly one-third of EU forests. Management of forests in Sweden has reached a high level of maturity and optimisation in environmental and socio-economic terms as a result of the high priority placed on the contribution to both carbon sinks and fossil fuel substitution. Markets for pulp and paper, wood products, and high-quality bioenergy products (e.g., wood pellets) have evolved continuously ever since WWII. There have also been a variety of major research and development efforts ever since the 1960s related to conversion of woody biomass, including biofuels, gasification, pyrolysis, and other platforms such that will be of strategic relevance for climate stabilisation and resilience. These efforts accelerated after the oil crises of the 1970s, with developments aimed not only at technological and market developments domestically but also to establish best practices within Europe and globally in some cases. Consequently, the forest resource base in Sweden is a pillar of land-based mitigation and negative emissions efforts not only in Sweden and the Nordic region but for the entire EU and to some extent in global terms as well due to international cooperation on technology and resource development.

At the same time, precisely because the use of forest resources is so mature and developed and is already high-performing in climate terms, it is difficult to talk about afforestation or reforestation as a major LMT in the Swedish context for several reasons. First, deforestation was extensive by the end of the 19th century, after which a continuous and comprehensive approach to reforestation and was later combined with an increasingly intensive management style that allowed high productivity for both standing biomass and extraction for wood products and bioenergy.

Second, since management has been oriented towards climate and renewable energy aims for so long, concerns have shifted somewhat to biodiversity and cultural impacts of intensive forest management, and therefore policy changes underway are expected to be more inclusive of wider societal aims even as climate mitigation and zero emission targets will receive high priority.

Third, as biomass and bioenergy markets become tighter and more competitive within the EU but at the same time Sweden and other countries are aiming to maximise domestic use rather than trade, there are greater linkages, synergies, and conflicts with portfolios of LMTs in Sweden and elsewhere in the EU, particularly in light of the new EU Forest Strategy that is under consultation and development (Aggestam and Giurca 2021). Therefore, rather than afforestation or reforestation, this LMT relates to Forest Management more generally, and will be analysed in this context, particularly emphasising the evolving forest policies and strategies. However, it is not possible to comprehensively cover such a broad set of issues for the Swedish case, so the discussion here is somewhat selective and is based on

changes that are occurring at the margin and especially in relation to net zero emission goals that were established in 2016 (Regeringskansliet 2017).

7.2 Policy context

A long period of deforestation and/or neglect of forests into the 1800s eventually led to the Swedish Forestry Act of 1903, which began a century-long process of reforestation and establishing the basis for the modern and productive forest sector that is now the most important in the EU in many respects. The law was updated in 1993 to include ecological considerations and again in 2008 to incorporate social aspects, while the National Forest Programme of 2014 increased public participation in forest policies and strategies (Johansson 2016). The other main policy guidance for forests is found in the Swedish Environmental Code, which aims for sustainable use of forests across the three pillars of economics, ecology, and social elements (Riksdag 1998). The law was updated in 1993 to include ecological considerations and again in 2008 to incorporate social aspects, while the National Forest Programme of 2014 increased public participation in forest policies and strategies (Johansson 2016). The other main policy guidance for forests is found in the Swedish Environmental Code, which aims for sustainable use of forests across the three pillars of economics, ecology, and social elements (Riksdag 1998).

The significant efforts at reforestation have always been combined with an emphasis on commercial competitiveness in terms of high-quality wood and paper products and in recent decades, as bioenergy for heat and power production. Approximately two million of Sweden's 28 million hectares of forest, mainly in national forests and other public areas, are under protection such that any extractive or productive uses are aimed solely at ecological preservation and/or socio-cultural improvements rather than economic value. The Swedish Forest Agency (Skogsstyrelsen) interacts with many other government agencies at national and local level to manage forest resources in line with laws and guidelines. Sustainability certification of forests, covering more than 60% of forest area in Sweden, is provided through the internationally recognised guidelines of the Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) and the Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC). Forest management is an integral element in implementing the measures to achieve negative emissions' targets (Karlsson et al. 2020).

The forest sector in Sweden is dominated by small owners/managers, mainly the 200,000 or some families that own on average 50 hectares of forest. There are also some private and nationally-owned forests, as shown in Figure 2. It is important to note that "ownership" of forests does not allow these actors full control over forested land and forest resources: as in most countries they must follow the environmental regulations and institutional guidelines established by the Forestry Act and the Environmental Code and any additional guidance at local or national level. In terms of recreational use of forests, areas that are not under production or extraction are generally subject to the principle of *Allemansrätt*, under which citizens or residents may walk or visit land and forest anywhere as long as they respect these areas and do not disturb or remove trees, plants, or animals.

The forestry sector is largely self-supporting in Sweden because of the relatively stable commercial value of timber extracted and the associated economic linkages and sectors. There may be some funds available where additional measures in the forest sector are needed to fulfil climate policy aims associated with net zero emission goals. However, there is no general or systematic way to specify these financial support mechanisms without reference to implementation in particular contexts and locations.

Source: Swedish Forest Industries Foundation, Skogsstyrelsen, refers to 2018

Figure 2: Ownership of forests in Sweden.

7.3 Current land use and potential land-use competition

Forests currently occupy around 28 million hectares or 70% of land area in Sweden, of which around 22 million hectares can be considered productive or potentially available for extraction and/or production. The long process of forest restoration that started in the early 1900s has resulted in nearly a doubling of land under forest while the quality and productivity of forest land has also increased several times over. As the management of Swedish forests is somewhat decentralised due to the ownership structure, there are some variations in management approaches but in general the model aims to combine the three pillars of sustainability. It is unlikely that the amount of land under forest will change significantly in the coming decades, but rather the management practices may change and the balance between production and conservation may shift as some additional emphasis is placed on biodiversity and ecosystem services (including cultural ecosystem services).

The most important single contributor to Swedish climate targets is thus essentially the forest resource base, as it provides carbon sequestration and fossil substitution alongside all the other benefits associated with forests. The comparison across the land sectors in Table 10 shows that other land types are net sources of emissions while managed forest land provides a considerable share of Sweden’s overall net positive GHG balance. The key metric in current practices relates to net growth, which continues to be positive, i.e., the growth in Swedish forests continues to outweigh the amounts harvested and/or removed (Ministry of the Environment 2020).

Table 10: Historical and projected net emissions (+) and net removals (-) of GHG from land sectors in Sweden (million tonne CO₂-equivalents). Source: Ministry of the Environment (2020)

	2015	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040
Afforested land	-0.8	-0.9	-0.9	-0.9	-0.9	-0.9
Deforested land	4.0	2.9	2.9	2.8	2.8	2.7
Managed forest land	-42.9	-43.1	-46.5	-44.5	-45.4	-47.4
Managed cropland	4.3	4.7	4.6	4.6	4.5	4.5
Managed grassland	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
Managed wetland	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Total	-34.9	-35.9	-39.3	-37.4	-38.4	-40.4

Land competition is not a major issue in the context of the Swedish forestry sector, but it does affect decisions about the replication or expansion of particular forestry measures, in a few ways. First, forest measures that are expected to result in reduced agricultural land (which is already small by comparison) and/or increased food imports will normally not be prioritised, for reasons of national health and food security or safety but also because imports may have a higher climate impact. Second, commercial development for non-land activities (i.e., housing, commercial sector, etc.) also tends to get lower priority except for remote areas in the north where additional infrastructure and development is needed for quality-of-life improvements. Finally, social, and cultural factors are increasingly being considered in the choice between intensive harvesting practices (e.g., clear-cutting) vs. low-impact solutions to forest management, particularly in the context of indigenous peoples in northern Sweden or areas where cultural values are more strongly incorporated into regional guidelines. This last point connects also to the central debate around greater emphasis on biodiversity, ecology, and nature rather than productivity and climate stabilisation targets.

7.4 Climate risks & sensitivities

According to an existing study of the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency, afforestation of previously abandoned arable lands could have a positive effect for climate due to their contribution to emission absorption and substitution, and also pose negative effects due to intense cultivation with short time for rotation and the risk of monocultures could limit tree species growth (Karlsson et al. 2020). Other potential risks associated to afforestation concern biodiversity impact (Karlsson et al. 2020).

There needs to be a larger awareness of the importance of biological systems to enable a fossil-free future, according to Swedish stakeholders. This includes aspects related to energy and material but is broader than that and includes poverty alleviation, food provision and a broad set of factors related to sustainable development in general. A key general advantage of managed forests, compared to

unmanaged, is a decrease in risks of fire and other damages and that it allows for more adaptation opportunities, i.e., in response to changing climate conditions.

7.5 Economic implications

The forest sector is highly cost-competitive and thus the current issues relate primarily to the trade-offs with other societal aims beyond climate rather than cost-competitiveness of forest measures. In particular, any marginal costs associated with measures in the forest sector have to be analysed for specific implementation and in connection to particular scenarios and pathways.

The costs are generally negative for a variety of measures in the forest sector but the maturity of the sector and the integration of forest management with downstream products and markets means that different changes in management could have varying cost implications and need to be analysed in particular cases and/or locations within future scenarios.

7.6 Co-benefits and trade-offs

The main issue that has emerged in forest resource management in Sweden is that the intensive production systems that have been used have raised some concerns with biodiversity and to some extent cultural issues. A number of approaches have been considered to improve biodiversity, including increasing the area of protected forest, lengthening the harvest cycle, and diversifying the structure of forest plantings (mixed leaf/forest case), as shown in Table 11. Among these options, increased forest protection would increase carbon sequestration capacity the most in the near to medium term, while also supporting biodiversity aims. The loss of production would also reduce the amount of biomass substituting for fossil fuels but the estimate of the resulting change in GHG emissions depends on the timeframe and substitution scenario used and therefore cannot be specified without further disaggregation. Lengthened harvest cycle initially provides greater removal but declines over time by 2045, due to the differing sequestration and growth capacities for younger vs. older forest stands. Increased production methods for forest resources would result in 3.1 million tonnes of additional CO₂ removal by 2045, similar to the low case of increased forest protection and more than the high case of lengthened harvest cycle. It must also be noted that some of these scenarios can change significantly over the entire lifecycle of the trees, which can be up to 100 years, but the results are only shown until 2045 because of the net zero emission target.

Table 11: Measures for changing carbon management in Sweden via forest management practices.
Source: Statens Offentliga Utredningar (2020)

	Area applied (Million hectares)	Net CO2 removal (million tonnes CO2/year)		Change in harvesting (2020-45)		Effect on Biodiversity	Effect on Fossil Substitution
		2030	2045	million m ³	percent	2045	2045
Increased forest protection (high case)	4.5	12	13	-17.0	-23%	+	-
Increased forest protection (low case)	0.5	1.3	3.1	-2.0	-2.5%	+	-
Lengthened harvest cycle (high case)	3.8	4	2.9	-2.0	-3%	+	-
Lengthened harvest cycle (low case)	0.5	0.2	0.1	-0.1	-0.1%	+	-
Mixed leaf/forest	5.5	2.2	4.5	-4.0	0%	+	-
Increased production methods	varies	2.8	3.1	2.0	2%	-	+

7.7 Risks associated with scaling up

Afforestation is already a very upscaled LMT in Sweden and there are not many risks associated with further scaling up. However, when large areas are populated with poorly adapted to the local environment species, negative environmental consequences have been observed (Cao et al. 2010). As previously mentioned, the risk of monocultures limiting tree species growth has been discussed in the Swedish context. Another issue could be that the increase of forest areas and subsequent decrease of open areas, especially pasturelands, can lead to species extinction. Furthermore, reduction in the available grazing land could lead to decreasing numbers of grazing animals and therefore to decreased food production. A final risk of uncontrolled expansion of afforestation as an LMT might lead to loss of high biological or cultural heritage sites in the country (Svensson 2018).

7.8 Conclusion

Sweden has the most forest land among EU countries and has a long history of forest policies. In the Swedish context, the LMT generally referred to as afforestation or reforestation is more related to forest management more generally. The significant efforts at reforestation have always been combined with an emphasis on commercial competitiveness in terms of high-quality wood and paper products and in recent decades, as bioenergy for heat and power production. A key general advantage of managed forests, compared to unmanaged, is a decrease in risks of fire and other damages and that it allows for more adaptation opportunities, i.e., in response to changing climate conditions.

There are relatively few major research gaps in general terms since there has been intense analysis and research on Swedish forest resources and management for several decades. However, in light of the critical role of forest management and/or afforestation/reforestation for climate aims in the EU and globally, there are no doubt a variety of research gaps that could be identified depending on the particular focus in the research programme and the interactions with other LMTs. One research gap is associated simply with the uncertainties associated with future climate change impacts as well as with the effects of changing climate policies in relation to net zero emission goals, i.e., feedbacks and interactions during the next decade or so as efforts are intensified to reach climate neutrality.

8. Final reflections

In this analysis, we focused on BECCS, biochar, and afforestation (or rather forest resource management) as the selected LMTs comprising the Swedish portfolio. BECCS is the key NET in the portfolio, as it is expected to deliver a large share of the negative emissions needed for Sweden to achieve its 2045 target for net-zero emissions. Biochar, although favoured for its diversity of co-benefits and co-products especially in the local context, will have a complementary role.

A recent comprehensive government investigation showed that BECCS is expected to remove 1.8 Million tonnes CO₂-eq per year by 2030 and between 3 to 10 Million tonnes CO₂-eq per year by 2045. Biochar is considered as part of the increased carbon sink in forests and land category, which, in overall is expected to remove 1.2 Million tonnes CO₂-eq per year by 2030 and a minimum of 2.7 Million tonnes CO₂-eq per year by 2045. There are still high uncertainties of course, and the country is open to any other NET that could contribute to enhanced emission reduction.

The above mean that carbon removals between 9.4 and 16.4 would be reasonable to be assumed under this narrative by the year 2045. On average, this can be translated to 12.9 Million tonnes CO₂-eq per year, which is approximately equivalent to 25% of total greenhouse gas emissions in Sweden in 2019 (in CO₂-equivalent terms, excluding LULUCF)⁴.

Stakeholders working with these LMTs highlight that in order for the emission removals to be delivered in line with the Swedish net-zero targets, there needs to be stronger incentives that would in turn create viable carbon markets. Sweden has a frontrunner status regarding BECCS implementation, but it is still unclear how investments on transportation and storage of carbon will be supported and by whom. At the same time, climate change is threatening Swedish forest species and might create cascading effects affecting biodiversity and biomass supply for BECCS and biochar upscaling.

⁴ According to Sweden's 2021 National Inventory Report (p23) submitted to the UNFCCC, Sweden emitted 50.9 MtCO₂e of GHG emissions in 2019.

9. References

- Agegnehu, Getachew, Adrian M. Bass, Paul N. Nelson, and Michael I. Bird. 2016. “Benefits of Biochar, Compost and Biochar–Compost for Soil Quality, Maize Yield and Greenhouse Gas Emissions in a Tropical Agricultural Soil.” *Science of The Total Environment* 543 (February): 295–306. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.11.054>.
- Agegnehu, Getachew, A. K. Srivastava, and Michael I. Bird. 2017. “The Role of Biochar and Biochar-Compost in Improving Soil Quality and Crop Performance: A Review.” *Applied Soil Ecology* 119 (October): 156–70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsoil.2017.06.008>.
- Aggestam, Filip, and Alexandru Giurca. 2021. “The Art of the ‘Green’ Deal: Policy Pathways for the EU Forest Strategy.” *Forest Policy and Economics*. Elsevier B.V. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2021.102456>.
- Azzi, Elias S., Erik Karlton, and Cecilia Sundberg. 2019. “Prospective Life Cycle Assessment of Large-Scale Biochar Production and Use for Negative Emissions in Stockholm.” *Environmental Science & Technology* 53 (14): 8466–76. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.9b01615>.
- . 2021. “Small-Scale Biochar Production on Swedish Farms: A Model for Estimating Potential, Variability, and Environmental Performance.” *Journal of Cleaner Production* 280 (January): 124873. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.124873>.
- Biederman, Lori A., and W. Stanley Harpole. 2013. “Biochar and Its Effects on Plant Productivity and Nutrient Cycling: A Meta-Analysis.” *GCB Bioenergy* 5 (2): 202–14. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcbb.12037>.
- Bier, Harald, Helmut Gerber, Marcel Huber, Hannes Junginger, Daniel Kray, Jörg Lange, Hansjörg Lerchenmüller, and Pal Jahre Nilsen. 2020. “EBI Whitepaper Biochar-Based carbonsink to mitigate climate change.” European Biochar Industry Consortium.
- Blanco-Canqui, Humberto. 2017. “Biochar and Soil Physical Properties.” *Soil Science Society of America Journal* 81 (4): 687–711. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj2017.01.0017>.
- Bloomberg Cities Network. 2021. “Solution Spotlight: Turning Garden Waste into a Carbon Sink in Stockholm | Bloomberg Cities.” 2021. <http://bloombergcities.jhu.edu/news/solution-spotlight-turning-garden-waste-carbon-sink-stockholm>.
- Borchard, Nils, Michael Schirrmann, Maria Luz Cayuela, Claudia Kammann, Nicole Wrage-Mönnig, Jose M. Estavillo, Teresa Fuertes-Mendizábal, et al. 2019. “Biochar, Soil and Land-Use Interactions That Reduce Nitrate Leaching and N₂O Emissions: A Meta-Analysis.” *Science of The Total Environment* 651 (February): 2354–64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.10.060>.
- Bozzi, E., L. Genesio, P. Toscano, M. Pieri, and F. Miglietta. 2015. “Mimicking Biochar-Albedo Feedback in Complex Mediterranean Agricultural Landscapes.” *Environmental Research Letters* 10 (8): 084014. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/10/8/084014>.

Cao, Shixiong, Tao Tian, Li Chen, Xiaobin Dong, Xinxiao Yu, and Guosheng Wang. 2010. "Damage Caused to the Environment by Reforestation Policies in Arid and Semi-Arid Areas of China." *AMBIO* 39 (4): 279–83. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-010-0038-z>.

Cayuela, M. L., L. van Zwieten, B. P. Singh, S. Jeffery, A. Roig, and M. A. Sánchez-Monedero. 2014. "Biochar's Role in Mitigating Soil Nitrous Oxide Emissions: A Review and Meta-Analysis." *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, Environmental Benefits and Risks of Biochar Application to Soil, 191 (June): 5–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2013.10.009>.

Christiansen, Kirstine. 2020. "Governing the Emerging Sociotechnical Imaginary of a Climate-Positive Sweden : An Exploration of the Political Discussion on Negative Emissions Technologies as a Climate Change Solution." MSc. thesis 9012835. Lund: LUCSUS (Lund University Centre for Sustainability Studies).

Dickinson, Dane, Ludovico Balduccio, Jeroen Buysse, Frederik Ronsse, Guido van Huylenbroeck, and Wolter Prins. 2015. "Cost-Benefit Analysis of Using Biochar to Improve Cereals Agriculture." *GCB Bioenergy* 7 (4): 850–64. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcbb.12180>.

Dumortier, Jerome, Hamze Dokoohaki, Amani Elobeid, Dermot J. Hayes, David Laird, and Fernando E. Miguez. 2020. "Global Land-Use and Carbon Emission Implications from Biochar Application to Cropland in the United States." *Journal of Cleaner Production* 258 (June): 120684. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.120684>.

Enell, Anja, Elias Azzi, Dan Berggren Kleja, Sigrun Dahlin, Alf Ekblad, Peter Flyhammar, Mats Fröberg, et al. 2020. "Biokol - Från Organiskt Avfall till Resurs För Nyttiggörande Av Jordavfall, Syntesrapport." Linköping: Statens geotekniska institut, SGI.

Energimyndigheten. 2022. "Energy in Sweden 2022 - an Overview." Energimyndigheten. <https://energimyndigheten.a-w2m.se/Home.mvc?ResourceId=208766>.

Fajardy, MATHilde, Alexandre Köberle, Niall Mac Dowell, and Alexandra Fantuzzi. 2019. "BECCS Deployment: A Reality Check." Briefing paper No. 28. Grantham Institute. <https://www.imperial.ac.uk/media/imperial-college/grantham-institute/public/publications/briefing-papers/BECCS-deployment---a-reality-check.pdf>.

Fischer, Benjamin M. C., Stefano Manzoni, Laura Morillas, Monica Garcia, Mark S. Johnson, and Steve W. Lyon. 2019. "Improving Agricultural Water Use Efficiency with Biochar – A Synthesis of Biochar Effects on Water Storage and Fluxes across Scales." *Science of The Total Environment* 657 (March): 853–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.11.312>.

Fridahl, Mathias. 2018. *Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage: From Global Potentials to Domestic Realities*. European Liberal Forum.

Fridahl, Mathias, Rob Bellamy, Anders Hansson, and Simon Haikola. 2020. "Mapping Multi-Level Policy Incentives for Bioenergy With Carbon Capture and Storage in Sweden." *Frontiers in Climate* 2 (December): 604787. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fclim.2020.604787>.

Fuss, Sabine, Josep G. Canadell, Glen P. Peters, Massimo Tavoni, Robbie M. Andrew, Philippe Ciais, Robert B. Jackson, et al. 2014. "Betting on Negative Emissions." *Nature Climate Change* 4 (10): 850–53. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2392>.

Gałązka, Anna, Krzysztof Jończyk, Karolina Gawryjółek, and Jarosław Ciepiel. 2019. "The Impact of Biochar Doses on Soil Quality and Microbial Functional Diversity." *BioResources* 14 (4): 7852–68.

Geels, Frank W. 2010. "Ontologies, Socio-Technical Transitions (to Sustainability), and the Multi-Level Perspective." *Research Policy* 39 (4): 495–510. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2010.01.022>.

Genesio, L., F. Miglietta, E. Lugato, S. Baronti, M. Pieri, and F. P. Vaccari. 2012. "Surface Albedo Following Biochar Application in Durum Wheat." *Environmental Research Letters* 7 (1): 014025. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/7/1/014025>.

Godlewska, Paulina, Yong Sik Ok, and Patryk Oleszczuk. 2021. "THE DARK SIDE OF BLACK GOLD: Ecotoxicological Aspects of Biochar and Biochar-Amended Soils." *Journal of Hazardous Materials* 403 (February): 123833. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2020.123833>.

Gruss, Iwona, Jacek P. Twardowski, Agnieszka Latawiec, Agnieszka Medyńska-Juraszek, and Jolanta Królczyk. 2019. "Risk Assessment of Low-Temperature Biochar Used as Soil Amendment on Soil Mesofauna." *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 26 (18): 18230–39. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-019-05153-7>.

Gunnerund, Lasse. 2021. LANDMARC Stakeholder EngagementPhone.

Gustafsson, Kåre. 2017. "Biokol - En Möjlighet Att Reversera Klimatförändringarn." Fortum Värme. <https://start.stockholm/globalassets/start/om-stockholms-stad/utredningar-statistik-och-fakta/utredningar-och-rapporter/klimat-och-miljo/biokol-en-mojlighet-att-reversera-klimatforandringarna-20-nov-2017.pdf>.

Hardy, Brieuc, Steven Sleutel, Joseph E. Dufey, and Jean-Thomas Cornelis. 2019. "The Long-Term Effect of Biochar on Soil Microbial Abundance, Activity and Community Structure Is Overwritten by Land Management." *Frontiers in Environmental Science* 7. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2019.00110>.

Hertsgaard, Martin. 2014. "As Uses of Biochar Expand, Climate Benefits Still Uncertain." *Yale E360* (blog). 2014. https://e360.yale.edu/features/as_uses_of_biochar_expand_climate_benefits_still_uncertain.

Homagain, Krish, Chander Shahi, Nancy Luckai, and Mahadev Sharma. 2016. "Life Cycle Cost and Economic Assessment of Biochar-Based Bioenergy Production and Biochar Land Application in

Northwestern Ontario, Canada.” *Forest Ecosystems* 3 (1): 21. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40663-016-0081-8>.

Jahromi, Nastaran Basiri, Jaehoon Lee, Amy Fulcher, Forbes Walker, Sindhu Jagadamma, and Prakash Arelli. 2020. “Effect of Biochar Application on Quality of Flooded Sandy Soils and Corn Growth under Greenhouse Conditions.” *Agrosystems, Geosciences & Environment* 3 (1): e20028. <https://doi.org/10.1002/agg2.20028>.

Jakobsson, Eric. 2020. “Undersökning Av Möjligheten till Utveckling Av Kommersiellt Tillgänglig Koldioxidlagring i Sverige.” BSc. thesis. Stockholm: KTH Kungliga Tekniska Högskolan.

Jeffery, Simon, Diego Abalos, Marija Prodana, Ana Catarina Bastos, Jan Willem van Groenigen, Bruce A. Hungate, and Frank Verheijen. 2017. “Biochar Boosts Tropical but Not Temperate Crop Yields.” *Environmental Research Letters* 12 (5): 053001. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aa67bd>.

Johansson, Johanna. 2016. “Participation and Deliberation in Swedish Forest Governance: The Process of Initiating a National Forest Program.” *Forest Policy and Economics* 70 (September): 137–46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2016.06.001>.

Jones, D. L., J. Rousk, G. Edwards-Jones, T. H. DeLuca, and D. V. Murphy. 2012. “Biochar-Mediated Changes in Soil Quality and Plant Growth in a Three Year Field Trial.” *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 45 (February): 113–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2011.10.012>.

Karlsson, Åsa-Britt, Monica Daoson, Björn Boström, Eva Jernbäcker, Mattias Lundblad, and David Mjureke. 2020. “Vägen till en klimatpositiv framtid, SOU 2020:4.” SOU. <https://www.regeringen.se/4a9e84/contentassets/1c43bca1d0e74d44af84a0e2387bfbcc/vagen-till-en-klimatpositiv-framtid-sou-20204>.

Klimatpolitiska rådet. 2019. “Årsrapport 2019.” Stockholm. <https://www.klimatpolitiskaradet.se/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/kprrapport190426.pdf>.

Latawiec, Agnieszka E., Bernardo B. N. Strassburg, André B. Junqueira, Ednaldo Araujo, Luiz Fernando D. de Moraes, Helena A. N. Pinto, Ana Castro, et al. 2019. “Biochar Amendment Improves Degraded Pasturelands in Brazil: Environmental and Cost-Benefit Analysis.” *Scientific Reports* 9 (1): 11993. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-47647-x>.

Leviñh, Fabian, Linus Linde, Kåre Gustafsson, and Erik Dahlen. 2019. “Introducing BECCS through HPC to the Research Agenda: The Case of Combined Heat and Power in Stockholm.” *Energy Reports* 5 (November): 1381–89. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egyr.2019.09.018>.

Martelius, Simon. 2022. “Comparative Techno-Economic Analysis of BECCS and Biochar in Sweden.” Uppsala: Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, SLU. <https://stud.epsilon.slu.se/18289/1/martelius-s-2022705.pdf>.

Meyer, Sebastian, Bruno Glaser, and Peter Quicker. 2011. "Technical, Economical, and Climate-Related Aspects of Biochar Production Technologies: A Literature Review." *Environmental Science & Technology* 45 (22): 9473–83. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es201792c>.

Millot, Ariane, Anna Krook-Riekkola, and Nadia Maïzi. 2020. "Guiding the Future Energy Transition to Net-Zero Emissions: Lessons from Exploring the Differences between France and Sweden." *Energy Policy* 139 (April): 111358. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2020.111358>.

Ministry of Infrastructure. 2020. "Sweden's Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan. Reporting under EU Regulation (EU) 2018/1999." Swedish Ministry of Infrastructure.

Ministry of the Environment. 2020. "Sweden's Long-Term Strategy for Reducing Greenhouse Gas Emissions."

Palansooriya, Kumuduni Niroshika, Yong Sik Ok, Yasser Mahmoud Awad, Sang Soo Lee, Jwa-Kyung Sung, Agamemnon Koutsospyros, and Deok Hyun Moon. 2019. "Impacts of Biochar Application on Upland Agriculture: A Review." *Journal of Environmental Management* 234 (March): 52–64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2018.12.085>.

Pratt, Kimberley, and Dominic Moran. 2010. "Evaluating the Cost-Effectiveness of Global Biochar Mitigation Potential." *Biomass and Bioenergy* 34 (8): 1149–58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2010.03.004>.

Reddy, Krishna R., Tao Xie, and Sara Dastgheibi. 2014. "Evaluation of Biochar as a Potential Filter Media for the Removal of Mixed Contaminants from Urban Storm Water Runoff." *Journal of Environmental Engineering* 140 (12): 04014043. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)EE.1943-7870.0000872](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)EE.1943-7870.0000872).

Regeringskansliet. 2017. *Ett Klimatpolitiskt Ramverk För Sverige*.

Riksdag, Sveriges. 1998. *Miljöbalk (1998:808) Svensk Författningssamling 1998:1998:808 t.o.m. SFS 2020:1174 - Riksdagen*.

Rootzén, Johan, Jan Kjärstad, Filip Johnsson, and Henrik Karlsson. 2018. "Deployment of BECCS in Basic Industry-a Swedish Case Study." In . Gothenburg.

Saifullah, Saad Dahlawi, Asif Naeem, Zed Rengel, and Ravi Naidu. 2018. "Biochar Application for the Remediation of Salt-Affected Soils: Challenges and Opportunities." *Science of The Total Environment* 625 (June): 320–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.12.257>.

SCB. 2022. "Marken i Sverige." Statistiska Centralbyrån. October 31, 2022. <https://www.scb.se/hitta-statistik/sverige-i-siffror/miljo/marken-i-sverige/>.

Söderqvist, Helena, Victor Norberg, and Linnea Turnstedt. 2021. "Marknaden För Biokol i Öresundsregionen."

Stockholms Stad. 2020. "Climate Action Plan 2020–2023. For a Fossil-Free and Climate-Positive Stockholm by 2040." City of Stockholm.

Svensson, Josefin. 2018. "Afforestation of Open Land in Sweden: A Case Study of Sjöbo Municipality." Lund: Lund University.

The European Biochar Industry Consortium. 2022. "European Biochar Market Report 2021 / 2022." <https://www.biochar-industry.com/2022/european-biochar-market-report-2021-2022-available-now/>.

Tisserant, Alexandre, and Francesco Cherubini. 2019. "Potentials, Limitations, Co-Benefits, and Trade-Offs of Biochar Applications to Soils for Climate Change Mitigation." *Land* 8 (12): 179. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land8120179>.

Tripathi, Manoj, J. N. Sahu, and P. Ganesan. 2016. "Effect of Process Parameters on Production of Biochar from Biomass Waste through Pyrolysis: A Review." *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 55 (March): 467–81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.10.122>.

Woolf, Dominic, James E. Amonette, F. Alayne Street-Perrott, Johannes Lehmann, and Stephen Joseph. 2010. "Sustainable Biochar to Mitigate Global Climate Change." *Nature Communications* 1 (1): 56. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms1053>.

Woolf, Dominic, Johannes Lehmann, Elizabeth M. Fisher, and Lergus T. Angenent. 2014. "Biofuels from Pyrolysis in Perspective: Trade-Offs between Energy Yields and Soil-Carbon Additions." *Environmental Science & Technology* 48 (11): 6492–99. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es500474q>.

Zhao, Shi-Xiang, Na Ta, and Xu-Dong Wang. 2017. "Effect of Temperature on the Structural and Physicochemical Properties of Biochar with Apple Tree Branches as Feedstock Material." *Energies* 10 (9): 1293. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en10091293>.

LANDMARC

SCALING LAND-BASED MITIGATION SOLUTIONS IN SWITZERLAND

LAND-BASED MITIGATION NARRATIVES

MORITZ LAUB
STATUS: PUBLIC

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1. Introduction

This report includes a description of a generic nation-wide transition scenario for the implementation of land-based mitigation technologies and practices for the AFOLU sector (agriculture, forestry, and other land use sectors) in Switzerland. The report shows outcomes of a series of research steps that have been conducted in this country since the start of the project in June 2020 until the end of 2022:

First, we performed an initial scoping of key LMTs in the case study country. The scoping resulted in a long list of broad LMT portfolios that could be viable within the various case study countries.

Second, following this long list, we developed a short-list LMT portfolio containing key LMTs that would be the most relevant for a given country context. All case study country partners were asked to propose and validate their LMT portfolio through complementary (policy) literature review and with the help of stakeholder interviews (i.e. external validation by relevant country experts and stakeholders). Ex-ante no specific guidance of criteria for LMT portfolio short-listing was provided to allow for a free and open co-design process with stakeholders. The scoping process and results are presented in section 2 of this report (step 1 & 2). In Switzerland, the long-list was derived from key policy documents, while the short-listing for the narratives was done by interviews with key LMT stakeholders from Agroscope, WSL, BAFU and BLW.

Third, after the short-listed LMT portfolios were validated, the LANDMARC case study country partners were asked to develop national scaling narratives or storylines for each LMT included in their portfolio. The assessments focusses on climate risks, vulnerabilities as well as socio-economic co-benefits and trade-offs associated with upscaling LMTs in the case study countries. The analysis is based on a broad range of information/literature sources, and stakeholder consultations conducted. This process is supported through a risk and impact assessment (i.e. an online survey and workshops/seminar/webinars) conducted through the LANDMARC tasks 4.1, 4.2 and 5.2. Several key insights from these risk assessment interviews are explicitly mentioned in the narrative document. The results of this analysis are a set of LMT narratives which are presented in section 3 of this report.

The research steps are designed to enable both an **analysis of the risks and (climate) impacts of scaling up land-based mitigation and negative emission solutions**. As such this report mainly contributes to objectives 2, 3 and 4 of the six LANDMARC key objectives (see Table 1).

Table 1: LANDMARC project objectives.

	Project key objectives
1	Determine the potential and effectiveness of LMTs in GHGs mitigation using Earth Observation (EO)
2	Improve climate resilience of LMT solutions at the local level for large-scale implementation
3	Assess the risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs of scaling up local LMTs nationally
4	Scaling up LMT solutions to the continental and global level to assess effectiveness
5	Improve current methodologies to estimate emissions and removals for LMTs
6	LMT capacity building and develop new tools and services for decision making

While the results shown in this report represent a mostly qualitative storyline describing the context and impact of scaling up LMTs in a country context, they also enable project partners to proceed with the translation of the outcomes in a manner so that they can serve as direct model input.

Furthermore, these national level assessments provide a testing ground and empirical basis for the continental, and global assessment of the realistic scaling potential of land-based mitigation and negative emission solutions implemented in Work Packages 6 and 7 of the LANDMARC project (**Objective 4**).

2. Scoping of land based mitigation and negative emission solutions

2.1 Overview of potential of LMTs in Switzerland

2.1.1 Introduction

In a recent report of September 2020, the Swiss Federal Council provides a list of possible LMTs for Switzerland which is combined with a first assessment of the technical potential, realistic potential as well as the range of cost for different LMTs (Federal Council of Switzerland, 2020). The characterization of LMTs within the report is largely based on a review article by Minx et al. (2018), who categorized the most promising LMTs globally, and the potential of these LMTs is assessed for Switzerland in particular. The overview includes a list of the technical potential and pricing of each of the different LMTs (Table 2) as well as a conservative estimation of the actual realisable potential based on stakeholder estimations. The actual realisable potential is much lower than the technical potential, due to the consideration of cost and due to competing use of available biomass between different LMTs.

Table 2: LMT potential in Switzerland

LMTs	Technical potential (2050)		Additional comments	Costs for achieving negative emissions	
	Mt CO ₂ /y	total		CHF/ton	EUR/ton ^a
BECCS (post-combustion CO₂-capture)	5.1		potential if all available biomass is used	50 - 250	46 - 230
Enhanced weathering (using concrete)	2.5			20 - >1000	18 - >920
Direct Air Carbon Capture (DACC)		2500	total theoretical geological storage potential	40 - 1000	37 - 920
Soil carbon sequestration	2.7		only possible for a few decades	0 - 80	0 - 74
Afforestation, Reforestation and permanent use of wood	3.1		including substitution effects of 1 - 2 Mt CO ₂	1 - 100	1 - 92
Biochar	2.2		potential if almost all available biomass is used	10 - 135	9 - 124
Stakeholder estimated theoretically realistic potential (Portfolio of all LMTs, considering competition between different LMTs)	6				

^aExchange rate of Feb. 05,2021 (1 CHF = 0.92€), rounded to whole numbers

Source: adapted from Federal Council of Switzerland (2020)

2.1.2 Technologies dependent on biomass / photosynthesis

BECCS

The largest potential of all land-based mitigation technologies in Switzerland is attributed to BECCS. The BECCS technology is considered to have a technical potential of storing 5.1 Mt CO₂ per year, which is about double the amount of CO₂ compared to other LMTs. The source of biomass for BECCS may come from oil crops, sugar crops or starch crops, as well as from forestry or organic waste products which could be energetically used and the CO₂ then stored (Beuttler et al., 2019). Options for BECCS are also seen in the combination with other LMTs, such as the capturing of CO₂ from biogas or biochar production. It is important to note that the estimated technical potential in Switzerland for each LMTs (Table 1) is based on the assumption that all currently available biomass of Switzerland is used for that LMTs. Therefore, a direct competition for biomass exists between all biomass based LMTs and maximizing one (e.g. BECCS) means lowering the potential of another (e.g. storage in permanent wooden products). This would mean that other biomass based LMTs, such as a long-term storage in wood products and production of biochar are not possible if the full BECCS potential would be realized. BECCS could also lead to a competition for land with food production (Beuttler et al., 2019), yet since Switzerland is a net importer of food products (Federal Statistical Office of Switzerland, 2020a) the feasibility of such replacements is highly questionable and most likely not wanted by policy makers. About half of the BECCS potential (2.1 Mt CO₂ per year) could be realized relatively easily and without much competition for biomass. This corresponds to the amount of CO₂ that to date is already released from energetic use of biomass, which could be captured by CCS technology, without requiring further biomass than already in use. However, to date there is no policy in Switzerland that supports BECCS and no BECCS plant in Switzerland (Federal Council of Switzerland, 2020).

Biochar

The theoretical potential of biochar to mitigate CO₂ emissions in Switzerland has been estimated to be 2.2 Mt CO₂ per year, based on an estimated market demand of 600.000 t biochar per year, with a maximum national production potential estimated to be 900.000 t per year (Beuttler et al., 2019). This number does, however, not account for the potential competition between the use of biomass for biochar and other uses of biomass, such as BECCS. It was estimated that the total amount of biomass in Switzerland that is sustainably available is 6.3 Mt biomass on dry matter base per year, of which 3.4 Mt are already in use to date (Thees et al., 2017). The actually realizable potential of all LMTs that rely on biomass is therefore lower than the sum of their individual potentials, which are each assuming that all biomass is used for one LMT. Yet, potential synergies exist between biochar production and BECCS. About 38% of the biomass carbon is released as CO₂ during the production of biochar (Beuttler et al., 2019), and this CO₂ could be stored by BECCS technology. Hence, the highest efficiency of biochar production in terms of LMTs would be if biochar production and BECCS would be coupled.

A factor that may interfere with the broadscale adoption of biochar is the lack of knowledge on potential negative side effects of biochar application, such as negative effects on the soil microbiome. Also, there seems to be insufficient knowledge on the long-term stability of biochar in the soil, with the current estimate being that biochar may be stable for decades up to a few centuries in European soils. There seems thus to be a debate between different political actors and stakeholders, whether biochar should be broadly applied. For example, a recent policy paper stressed the potential risks and unwanted negative side effects and warned against large scale applications until the lack of knowledge on the potential risks as well as on the stability are addressed (Federal Council of Switzerland, 2020). On the other hand, a recent policy advisory report by a number of scientist in the field claimed a high potential for biochar, suggesting that biochar application may also slow turnover of soil organic carbon and thus provide more sequestration potential than just the amount of carbon stored in the biochar itself (Beuttler et al., 2019).

2.1.3 Land management practices

Afforestation and enhanced forest management

According to the Swiss Federal Office for the Environment, about a third of Switzerland is already covered by forest (FOEN, 2019). Due to a high pressure on land for other uses and Switzerland being already a net importer of food products (Federal Statistical Office of Switzerland, 2020a), there is simply no available land for a large-scale afforestation in Switzerland. Yet, due to climate change, the tree line is expected to continue to move upwards, which is expected to increase the potential areas for forests (Federal Council of Switzerland, 2020). In their report, the Federal Council of Switzerland (2020) postulates that Swiss forests have been a net sink of CO₂ over the last 30 years, storing about 2.5 Mt CO₂ per year in forest biomass and forest soils. They note, however, that due to already high carbon stocks, the potential of the forests to store more carbon may be limited. The carbon sinks of deadwood in the forest are already high and they have the additional risk of being released due to higher turnover under higher temperatures (Federal Council of Switzerland, 2020). Thus, the largest potentials for forest based LMTs in Switzerland are seen in management practices that make better use of the existing forest and forest products as potential carbon sinks, through enhanced management of forests and of the biomass extracted from forests. An extraction and a more efficient use of forest biomass in products and for energy is therefore suggested. The additionally extracted biomass should, where feasible, be stored in long-lasting wooden products. Additionally, all energetic use of wood biomass, either waste products or wooden products after their lifetime, should be coupled with BECCS to maximize the potential of forests for carbon sequestration.

Agricultural management practices

A range of agricultural management practices could help to increase the amount of carbon stored in agricultural soils in Switzerland. The technical potential of this carbon sequestration is estimated to be about 2.7 Mt CO₂ per year (Federal Council of Switzerland, 2020). This potential is based on a very ambitious soil carbon sequestration, assuming that cropland could sequester 0.63 t of soil organic

carbon per ha and year, which would require a combination of zero tillage, cover crops and leaving all crop residues on the field (Autret et al., 2016). Additionally, it assumes that all grasslands could sequester 0.28 t of soil organic carbon per ha and year and that on arable land, deep tillage is used on up to 5,000 ha per year to sequester additionally 0.21 Mt of carbon per year on 82,500 ha (about 2.5 t of carbon per ha and year; Beuttler et al., 2019). The potential of sequestering additional carbon by improved carbon input into soils (e.g. more cover crops or biogas slurry) is assumed to be very limited, because higher carbon stocks are usually associated with a higher turnover of carbon. Therefore, the mentioned potential of additionally sequestering 2.7 Mt CO₂ per year is assumed to be possible for only a few decades until a new steady state of carbon stocks at higher input rates is reached (Beuttler et al., 2019). Yet, an increase of carbon stocks in agricultural soils has many synergistic benefits, such as increased soil fertility and enhanced water and nutrient holding capacities. Additionally, the measures to increase soil organic carbon, such as improved crop rotations or cover crops, are generally not competing with other LMTs for biomass. In comparison to other LMTs, the implementation of improved agricultural management is also comparatively cheap.

The measures to increase the soil organic carbon content that are available, some of which are already regularly used by many farmers in Switzerland, can basically be split into two categories. One category is to increase the amount of carbon inputs into the soil, as a basis to increase the built-up of soil organic carbon. These include the use of cover crops, (partly) leaving residues on the field, returning organic residues and manures to the field, planting deep rooting crops, applying improved crop rotations including grass-clover leys and the use agroforestry techniques (Beuttler et al., 2019). The other category consists of measures that lower the turnover of carbon which is already present in the soil. Reduced tillage has been suggested to serve this purpose, yet it is debated to which extent tillage actually reduces soil organic carbon by disruption of soil aggregates (Six et al., 1999) and to which extent it just leads to a redistribution of carbon in the soil profile (Luo et al., 2010). Biochar has also been suggested to lower the turnover of soil organic carbon (Beuttler et al., 2019). A special case, combining elements of both categories, would be a one-time deep tillage of soils. Because carbon in deeper soil layers is lost at a slower pace than topsoil carbon, this transition of carbon rich soil material to the subsoil has been suggested as an effective method to increase soil organic carbon stocks (Beuttler et al., 2019). Apart from storing larger amounts of carbon in deeper soil layers, deep tillage moves carbon-poor soil material to the surface, where it can start to accumulate new carbon, which results in an overall carbon sequestration of the soil (Alcántara et al., 2016). However, deep tillage may cause unwanted side effects, such as a reduced topsoil fertility for decades or longer, thus it is questionable whether it would be feasible and whether farmers would be willing to accept it.

Apart from normally managed agricultural soils, there is a high potential to reduce GHG emissions from peatland soils under agricultural use, which are stated to lose around 9.5 t of carbon per ha per year (Beuttler et al., 2019). Therefore, rewetting agriculturally used peatlands would be a very cost-effective measure to reduce GHG emissions by 0.6 Mt CO₂ per year in whole Switzerland (Federal Council of Switzerland, 2020). However, reducing emissions from peatlands does not mean that they are actually sequestering carbon. To achieve this, it would be necessary to reinitiate a growth of the peatlands.

This could mean resettling native vegetation, which is assumed to take at least a few decades, and it is not clear how well this could work. For this reason, no potential for negative emissions is assumed to be associated with rewetting of peatlands until 2050 (Honegger et al., 2020) but they are seen as cheap mitigation options to reduce GHG releases.

Another option to sequester additional carbon in agriculturally used areas, is the implementation of agroforestry systems either in agricultural fields or grassland systems. This double use of the land can lead to higher yields than if either trees or agriculture would be performed separately on different areas. It also allows for additional sequestration of carbon in the woody biomass. While agroforestry systems were classically studied and applied in tropical areas, a new interest in temperate agroforestry systems seems to arise. A recent meta-analysis on agroforestry systems of Europe showed an overall positive effect of agroforestry on biodiversity, soil fertility, nutrient-cycling and erosion control, while no reduction of timber and food production compared to monoculture was found (Torralba et al., 2016). Pilot-studies of agroforestry establishment in Switzerland also found that participating farmers reported mostly positive outcomes of agroforestry (Jäger, 2019), thus agreeing with the results of the meta-analysis. The potential of agroforestry in Switzerland has thus also been recognized by policy makers and the aim to make agroforestry eligible for direct payments has been explicitly stated the Swiss long-term climate strategy (Federal Council of Switzerland, 2021).

2.2 Determining the LMT scope for national level simulation modelling

To reach its aim of net zero emissions in 2050, Switzerland will likely need to offset emissions that are difficult to avoid. Those are estimated to be around 10 Mt CO₂ per year (FOEN, 2020). In this section we discuss which set of LMTs are most promising and will be studied in detail. Table 2 summarises the main LMTs of Switzerland and indicates the inclusion into the short-list of the LMT portfolio. The rationales for inclusion in the national level scaling simulation assessment are presented thereafter.

Table 3: Long-listing of relevant land based LMTs

LMT	Subcategory	Specification	Included in national LANDMARC LMT portfolio
Biomass based LMTs	BECCS	BECCS based on domestic biomass already used today	Y
	Biochar	-	Y
Land management practices	Wetlands	Peat soil management, including rewetting, reverse drainage	N
	Cropland	Reduced tillage, conservation/ organic agriculture	Y
		Deep tillage	N
		Agroforestry and landscape elements (hedgerows etc.)	Y

Grassland	Peat soil management	N
	Agroforestry and landscape elements (hedgerows etc.)	Y
Forest land	Avoided deforestation	N
	Forest maintenance with biomass use (BECCS in cascade)	N

- **BECCS based on domestic biomass**

With the largest potential of all LMTs, the use of BECCS forms an integral part of the portfolio of Swiss strategies for negative emissions and is favoured by Swiss policy. Attractive is that about 40% (2.1 Mt CO₂ per year) of the overall BECCS potential of Switzerland could be achieved by applying CCS techniques to biomass that today is already energetically used, thus BECCS will very likely be used at least to capture these carbon sources. An interesting question would be, to what extent additionally available biomass should be used for BECCS. It is likely a waste of resources to use biomass of higher value for BECCS, e.g. wood that could also be used for construction or biochar. It could be most effective to prioritize the use for permanent wooden products and biochar, but apply BECCS when products get disposed or to capture CO₂ released from biochar production.

- **Biochar**

The application of biochar to agricultural fields could potentially be a cheap option to sequester additional carbon in the soils, if the stability of biochar over several decades to centuries would be verified. In their recent report, the foundation “risk dialogue” prescribed a huge potential to the application of biochar in Switzerland to sequester 2.2 Mt of CO₂ per year (Beuttler et al., 2019). In addition, biochar might reduce the production of other greenhouse gases, mainly N₂O in soils where it is applied and may increase soil fertility (Beuttler et al., 2019). There is also a scepticism of farmers and the government towards a large-scale application of biochar in Swiss soils, mainly due to incomplete understanding of potentially negative side effects such as faster biochar turnover than expected, negative effects on soil microorganisms, and a higher albedo due to darker soils (Federal Council of Switzerland 2020). However, due to only certified biochar being allowed in Switzerland, the risk of soil pollution, for example through heavy metals in the biochar is considered to be low. Through the additional side benefits for soil fertility and reducing GHG emissions, using biomass for biochar may be of added value compared to pure BECCS but a coupling of biochar production to BECCS seems feasible.

- **Reduced tillage, improved crop rotations, organic farming**

Altering agricultural management, for example reduced tillage could potentially lead to higher soil organic carbon stocks, though it is debated in the literature whether this increases carbon stocks or just prevents the redistribution of carbon along the depth profile (Beuttler et al., 2019). Yet, it was shown that with a rigorous use of the “equivalent soil mass approach” higher carbon stocks in reduced tillage systems compared to conventional tillage are detectable (Gauder et al., 2016). Apart from potentially higher carbon stocks, a lower mechanic energy requirement of reduced tillage systems could additionally contribute to lower overall GHG emissions of reduced tillage

systems. Other management options that are considered feasible to increase soil organic carbon stocks in Switzerland are improved crop rotations, including a more intensive use of cover crops and leaving residues on the field (Beuttler et al., 2019). The increase of area under organic farming could be a further suitable measure to increase soil organic carbon stocks. For example, it has been shown that organic farming can lead to lower losses or the maintenance of carbon stocks compared to conventional agriculture (Fließbach et al., 2007), while being more efficient in nitrogen use (Mäder et al., 2007) which could reduce N₂O emissions. All the agricultural management techniques have the advantage that they are not competing for land or biomass with other LMTs and are considered to be relatively cheap. Thus their use fits well into the portfolio with the other selected LMTs.

- **Agroforestry**

While an increase in forest area or wood biomass stocks in Switzerland seems difficult due to no available land and high carbon stocks already present in forests, agroforestry establishment bears the potential to increase the tree coverage in Switzerland without reducing agricultural land. Thus, agroforestry implementation was suggested as a measure to sequester additional carbon in Switzerland (Beuttler et al., 2019). Agroforestry may thus be more suitable than afforestation for reaching the goal of increasing the tree biomass in Switzerland. This and the apparent absence of severe yield depressions in agroforestry systems in Europe (Torralba et al., 2016), may make agroforestry the LMT with the highest potential to intensify the carbon sequestration potential of agricultural systems. The few innovative farmers who have already adopted agroforestry in Switzerland, seem to report mostly beneficial outcomes (Jäger, 2019). Therefore, despite not being broadly adopted at this time, the largest potential for increasing wood biomass in Switzerland may lie in agroforestry, which also offers several potential side benefits. This is also reflected in the stated political interest to support the development of more agroforestry systems in Switzerland by making it eligible to additional subsidies (Federal Council of Switzerland, 2021).

Excluded options from the shortlist

- **Peatland management**

About 2.3% of the Swiss land area are peatland areas but only 9% of these peatlands areas are still natural peatlands (e.g. matching the definition of bog or raised bog; Klaus, 2007), while 82% of functioning peats have vanished in the last 120 years (BAFU, 2017). Due to their high emission potential, it is an integral part of the declared climate action strategy of Switzerland to maintain the carbon stocks in peatland soils (Federal Council of Switzerland, 2021). The only option to remediate disturbed peatlands would be rewetting them, as apparently there is no option to agriculturally use Swiss peat soils while maintaining their carbon stocks (BAFU, 2017; Honegger et al., 2020). A potential danger of rewetting peatlands is that rewetting will lead to increased CH₄ emissions and in formerly agricultural areas also to N₂O emissions, which in the short term might increase radiative forcing by an amount that cannot be offset by the additionally sequestered carbon (Petrescu et al., 2015). Peatlands in Switzerland are estimated to lead to emissions of 0.6

Mt CO₂ per year (Federal Council of Switzerland, 2020), yet it is considered unlikely that they will lead to significant negative emissions until 2050 (Honegger et al., 2020). Due to a scarcity of arable land and a lack of food self-sufficiency of Switzerland, there is a high pressure to keep using Swiss peatlands for agricultural production (personal communication Daniel Bretscher). Thus, despite the strategy to maintain intact peatlands, there is no plan of rewetting disturbed peatlands at the moment and even if they would be rewetted, it would take a long time for disturbed peats to become actual sinks. Therefore, peatland management was excluded from the short list of LMTs.

- **Afforestation/ Forest maintenance with biomass use (BECCS)**

As for now, there is no additional land available for afforestation apart from the tree line moving uphill due to climate change. There seems to be some potential to make more biomass available by a more efficient extraction. This sustainable extraction of wood while maintaining the forest would have the benefit of reducing the risk of a loss of forest carbon stocks due to higher turnover at higher atmospheric temperatures or increased disruptions of the forest systems, as the carbon stocks of Swiss forests already considered to be close to saturation (Federal Council of Switzerland, 2020). However, as afforestation in Switzerland is not an option and thus a tremendous change in forest area and use are not expected. Agroforestry is considered as a more innovative option to increase the availability of wood biomass in Switzerland. Thus, active forest management is excluded from the short-list of LMTs to be studied in detail but could be indirectly included as biomass for biochar or BECCS may likely originate from forests.

- **Deep tillage**

While deep tillage practices have been suggested as an option to sequester carbon by transferring soil material to the surface, that is not yet saturated with carbon (Beuttler et al., 2019), it is a relatively new idea. Hence, the side effects have not been studied intensively. While deep tillage has the advantage of not being in competition for biomass with the other LMTs, it is questionable if farmers would be willing to plough their fertile soil under and reduce their soil fertility for decades or longer, only to sequester carbon. Thus, due to the lack of co-benefits and instead having potential negative side-effects, the potential of deep tillage is considered too uncertain and it is therefore not included in the short list.

2.3 Discussion on short-listing LMTs

2.3.1 Competition for biomass between BECCS & biochar

The competition for biomass of several LMTs that rely on biomass has been identified as a key limitation for the national potential in Switzerland (Federal Council of Switzerland, 2020). Thus, LMTs that create additional biomass to the biomass available now, bear the largest potential. With about a third of Switzerland already covered by forest (UFAM, 2021) and a scarcity of arable land due to being a net importer of food (Federal Statistical Office of Switzerland, 2020a), an increase in forest area

through afforestation is not considered feasible as it would go at the cost of agricultural production area in Switzerland. The two main objectives of Swiss forest policy were therefore specified as, firstly, the conservation of forest area, avoiding deforestation and maintaining healthy forest and, secondly, facilitating an efficient use of forest biomass (FOEN, 2013) so even with business as usual, forest are expected to be maintained and efficiently used. The promotion of agroforestry in contrast, bears the potential to provide additional woody biomass and may help to reduce the pressure on domestic biomass. The LANDMARC project offers the opportunity to not only study and compare the different alternatives which exist for the use of biomass, including use of wood for long-term products, and using forest biomass for biochar and/or BECCS, but also to determine which use is most feasible and how different uses could be efficiently combined in a cascade system.

When comparing the different uses of domestic biomass for suitability as LMTs, the duration of carbon storage and the economic feasibility are two major aspects which should be studied over longer time periods, applying methods such as lifecycle analysis. For high quality wood for example, a material use may be of higher economic value than energy generation. Yet, a cascade use may be feasible with an energetic use at the end of product lifetime. For lower quality biomass, the direct competition between biochar and BECCS raises the question of the cost and storage time for both. Additional logistics might be needed for both, for example to allow for the use of wooden products at the end of their lifetime, yet for BECCS or the combination of biochar production with BECCS there are additional constraints. A carbon capturing and storing as done for in the case of BECCS needs the large-scale facilities to be economically feasible, sufficient storage facilities in the right geological conditions and the infrastructure (trains or pipelines) to transport the compressed CO₂ to the place of storage (Beuttler et al., 2019). To date, neither the transport system nor any certified storing facilities exist in Switzerland (Federal Council of Switzerland, 2020). Thus, despite being ascribed the highest potential of all LMTs, there is tremendous uncertainty surrounding the feasibility of BECCS, which needs to be considered (e.g. with respect to expected consumer behaviour and additional energy cost of making the biomass available and for CCS). Additionally, there is the issue of CCS storage. A high theoretical potential for geologically storing captured carbon in saline aquifers of Switzerland was postulated, estimated to be about 2700 Mt of CO₂ (Swiss Federal Office of Energy, 2010) - 60 times the current yearly CO₂ emissions of Switzerland (Federal Council of Switzerland, 2020). However, this potential is a purely theoretical estimate, based on the geological knowledge about Switzerland. There is to date no practical proof of this theoretical potential. As detailed studies are currently lacking, and the actual realizable potential is at the moment unknown. Switzerland also considers the case of transporting captured CO₂ to storage facilities outside of Switzerland to be a realistic option in case no storage inside Switzerland is possible (Federal Council of Switzerland, 2020).

2.3.2 Limited potential of cropland management but low competition and cost effectiveness

Due to the scarcity of arable land in Switzerland making major changes in land use are unfeasible, Improved management schemes are needed to sequester carbon and reduce GHG emissions while maintaining the current land use. This strategy offers a potential for negative emissions which are mostly not in competition for biomass with BECCS or biochar. Yet, it is explicitly stated that the potential to sequester additional carbon in soils by improved cropland management is limited and only possible until a new steady state of the soil organic carbon is reached, which is expected to be the case within a few decades (Federal Council of Switzerland 2020). Thus, improved management for higher soil carbon could serve as interim solution with the higher soil fertility being an important co-benefit. The extent to which individual measures of conservation agriculture are already adopted and thus, the additional available potential, depends on the exact measure. The current policy of Switzerland already rewards and drives optimized crop rotations. For example, about 81% of the farmers, which are operating year-round, are getting direct subsidies for at least one conservation agriculture measure while measures to reduce soil disturbance (e.g. reduced or zero tillage) are only practiced on 81,933 ha (FOAG, 2020a,b) corresponding to roughly 30 of arable land. A special case of management options is organic farming, which has been shown to bear the potential to increase carbon storage or with at least a better maintenance of carbon stocks compared to conventional agriculture (Fließbach et al., 2007). However, yield reductions in organic farming are observed (e.g. around 14% in wheat; Mäder et al, 2007). This potentially negative side effect could be of high relevance for Switzerland, being a net importer of food. Despite this, a continuous demand for organic products leads to a continued growth of the area of organic agriculture in Switzerland, being now already at 16% (Federal Statistical office of Switzerland, 2021).

Table 4: Agricultural land use in the Switzerland from 1999 to 2019 (in 1000 ha)

Land use category	1999		2009		2019	
Total area of Switzerland	4128.5		4128.5		4128.5	
Agricultural area	1071.9	100%	1055.6	100%	1043.7	100%
Cereals	182.3	17%	152.8	14%	141.4	14%
Potatoes, turnips	34.4	3%	32.4	3%	29.0	3%
Oil seeds	18.9	2%	25.0	2%	30.3	3%
Remaining arable land	58.3	5%	65.1	6%	71.4	7%
Temporary grassland	115.9	11%	129.8	12%	126.7	12%
Natural grassland	626.8	58%	614.6	58%	605.7	58%
Permanent cultures	23.2	2%	23.4	2%	24.0	2%
Remaining agricultural land	12.0	1%	12.4	1%	15.2	1%

Source: Federal Statistical Office of Switzerland 2020b

To get an overview on the realistic potential of additional carbon storage in Swiss soils, one could relate the numbers given in Table 1 to the agricultural area. The increase of carbon stocks by conservation

measures, such as reduced tillage or improved crop rotations, could for example only be achieved in cropland and on temporary grasslands which will be transformed to cropland again. Together they make up 38% of Swiss agricultural area combined (The extent to which individual measures of conservation agriculture are already adopted and thus, the additional available potential, depends on the exact measure. The current policy of Switzerland already rewards and drives optimized crop rotations. For example, about 81% of the farmers, which are operating year-round, are getting direct subsidies for at least one conservation agriculture measure while measures to reduce soil disturbance (e.g. reduced or zero tillage) are only practiced on 81,933 ha (FOAG, 2020a,b) corresponding to roughly 30 of arable land. A special case of management options is organic farming, which has been shown to bear the potential to increase carbon storage or with at least a better maintenance of carbon stocks compared to conventional agriculture (Fließbach et al., 2007). However, yield reductions in organic farming are observed (e.g. around 14% in wheat; Mäder et al, 2007). This potentially negative side effect could be of high relevance for Switzerland, being a net importer of food. Despite this, a continuous demand for organic products leads to a continued growth of the area of organic agriculture in Switzerland, being now already at 16% (Federal Statistical office of Switzerland, 2021).

Table 4: Agricultural land use in the Switzerland from 1999 to 2019 (in 1000 ha)

In contrast, it is unclear if any management options to sequester additional carbon in natural grasslands (58% of agricultural area) exist, and thus the natural potential of grasslands to sequester carbon depends on if their carbon stocks are already at steady state. Swiss croplands and temporary grasslands combined have assumed stocks of 40 Mt of carbon in the top 100 cm of soil. The technical potential of yearly carbon sequestration in agricultural soils was assumed to be 2.7 Mt CO₂, which requires combining the best management practices for sequestering carbon on all agricultural land (e.g. zero tillage, catch crops and no straw removal on agricultural land, best grassland management and deep tillage on up to 5000 ha per year; Beuttler et al., 2019). This amount of 2.7 Mt CO₂ corresponds to 0.74 Mt of carbon. Thus, if the sequestration would be realized in the cropland and temporary grasslands alone, the 0.74 Mt would correspond to an annual growth rate of the estimated carbon stocks by 1.8%. This is almost five times the proposed aim of the 4 per 1000 initiative, whose aim to annually increase current soil carbon stocks by 0.4% (Minasny et al., 2017) is already heavily debated in the scientific community as being too ambitious (e.g. Wiesmeier et al., 2020). If permanent grasslands (including all agricultural and alpine grasslands) are included in the growth of carbon stocks (122 Mt of carbon in the top 100 cm), an increase of 0.6 % per year would be needed to achieve the annual sequestration 2.7 Mt CO₂, which would still be highly ambitious. It is therefore questionable, if this potential could really be achieved with standard practices, if novel practices will be needed or if other LMTs should be used.

Table 5: Calculated soil organic carbon stocks in Switzerland

Depth	Land-use (area)			
	Arable land (2893 km ²)	Temporary grassland (1141 km ²)	Permanent grassland	
Favourable* (5045 km ²)			Unfavourable* (5800 km ²)	
	SOC (t ha ⁻¹)			
0–20 cm	40.6	43.4	50.7	47.7
0–100 cm	90.4	117.4	92.3	62.9
	Soil organic carbon stock (Mt C)			
0–20 cm	11.7 ± 2.6	4.9 ± 1.2	25.6 ± 6.4	27.6 ± 6.6
0–100 cm	26.2 ± 5.8	13.4 ± 3.4	46.6 ± 11.2	36.5 ± 8.8

Source: Adapted from Leifeld et al (2005). *Due to different sources the numbers do not match perfectly to Table 3, but favourable grassland can be considered mostly equivalent to natural grassland in Table 3, whereas unfavourable grassland consists of alpine grasslands not specified in Table 3.

2.3.3 Biochar and Agroforestry as innovative options with potential co-benefits but adoption barriers

While at this stage not largely accepted and applied in Switzerland, both biochar and agroforestry show potential as future LMTs for Switzerland (personal communication Sonja Keel and Daniel Bretscher). Both technologies have co-benefits, such as increased soil fertility (biochar) a higher land-use efficiency (agroforestry) and a long time-frame (permanence) of carbon storage (both). Depending on how the additional woody biomass is used, agroforestry may add the highest carbon sequestration potential, as it allows for an additional long-term sink in the woody biomass, which was previously not present. It is thus a special kind of afforestation that does not compete with arable land. However, for agroforestry on arable land, the shading induced by the trees may cause yield losses. For example, yield losses between 25 and 45% were observed due to shading of wheat Belgium (Artru et al., 2017), mainly due to light competition. Yet, with a proper planning of the systems tree orientation, tree spacing and crops to include significant yield losses can be avoided (Carrier et al., 2019). Especially attractive could be the implementation into permanent grasslands because most forages can tolerate or even benefit from shading (Pang et al., 2019). The potential additional labour requirements or mechanization costs should also be considered when analysing economic feasibility of agroforestry.

While agroforestry mostly increases carbon stocks in biomass, biochar application increases soil carbon stocks. Biochar application can also reduce N₂O emissions (Dong et al., 2020), increase soil fertility by improving nutrient storage capacity and it may even carry the potential to reduce the turnover of carbon already present in the soil (Beuttler et al., 2019). Even if biochar does not slow down the

turnover of the carbon already present in the soil the turnover of biochar itself is very slow and it is estimated to stay in the soil between 270 and 5400 years (Beuttler et al., 2019), thus providing a significant period of sequestration. Yet, due to the slow turnover of biochar in the soil, it is difficult to estimate the exact retention time and a conservative estimate should be used to assess its potential as LMT. An additional adoption barrier for biochar could be the price of the biochar itself, which depends on the origin and quality and due to certification standards in Switzerland may be higher than in other parts of the world. For example, Struhs et al. (2020) reported prices between 200 and 700 US \$ per t of biochar. Yet prices may come down in the future as the technology matures and economies of scale come to play. Overall, biochar and agroforestry may add to the portfolio of Swiss LMTs, offer real long-term potential to use agricultural systems to sequester additional carbon and have both promising additional benefits.

3. Co-design of LMT narratives

3.1 Introduction

We developed the narratives based on the short-listed LMTs that were selected based on Swiss policy documents and a first round of stakeholder interviews. The further trajectory of the selected LMTs was then delineated in a two-step process. First, an in-depth literature research was conducted in 2021 and a first version of the narratives written based on that. Second, further interviews throughout 2022 were conducted within LANDMARC tasks 4.1, 4.2 and 5.2 in which we also included questions that arose from the first version of the narratives and feedback from modelers (i.e. LANDSHIFT). The final version of this report was then enriched with key insights gained through the stakeholder interviews, to complete the picture.

As demonstrated by several official government documents, Switzerland aims to be at the forefront on negative emission technologies. However, the focus of Swiss policy seems to be technical solutions, such as DACCS, BECCS and to a lesser extent, biochar. The interest here seems to be to become and exporter of these technologies in the future once they are applied at large scale. Land-based technologies, such as improved agricultural management and agroforestry, are seen as interim technologies until technical solutions can be deployed, but Swiss policy has concerns about their permanence. An important limitation that LMTs face in Switzerland is the scarcity of available land, hence afforestation projects are for example not feasible, and it is aimed to apply LMTs with minimal land competition.

3.2 BECCS based on domestic biomass

3.2.1 Introduction

The energetic use of available biomass in Switzerland is a common practice, including the use of biogas, burning of organic waste from waste treatment plants and the use of timber for heating. However, estimations are, that to date the amount of biomass available in Switzerland is underutilized by about 30% in wood and by more than 70% in other organic wastes (SFOE, 2017). The CO₂ released during the energetic use of biomass was sourced by plant photosynthesis from the atmosphere. Thus, capturing this CO₂ from the combustion process and storing it thereafter, would be an effective way to achieve negative emissions. While BECCS has never been applied in Switzerland, there is, in the context of the need to compensate remaining emissions by 2050, an increased focus on BECCS as a negative emission technology in the Swiss policy. Yet, there is, to date, no single bioenergy plant in Switzerland that captures the CO₂ from the combustion of biomass and stores it geologically. While the process of CO₂ capturing is not a technical problem, the lack of any BECCS facilities in Switzerland is due to a lack of geological storage. There is a theoretically estimated potential for storing CO₂ in saline aquifers in Switzerland, but this is only based on knowledge about the geological formations and has not been proven. Hence, Switzerland is also looking into the possibility to store captured CO₂ in aquifers abroad.

3.2.2 Policy context

Due to the novelty of the BECCS technique, no policy which addresses BECCS directly has been established to date. However, BECCS has been mentioned as a key LMT in several national policy documents, most recently in the long-term climate strategy of Switzerland (Schweizer Bundesrat 2021). If negative emissions by BECCS could be accounted for, it would be possible to finance BECCS via carbon credits. However, while Switzerland already established a CO₂ price for fossil fuels for private consumers (currently around 90 CHF per ton of CO₂, with 1 CHF roughly equivalent 1 € at the time of writing Oct 2022) and some private sectors, the heavily emitting sectors such as cement industry are currently not included in the CO₂ tax. Yet, while not taxed for emissions those sectors are part of the cap and trade EU emission certificates trading system that also allows for negative emissions such as BECCS to be accounted (Schweizer Bundesrat 2021), which however has a much lower price than the CO₂ tax. Increased prices for CO₂ could therefore favour the deployment of BECCS and be a way to compensate for hard to avoid emissions through market mechanisms. Another development that could benefit the deployment of BECCS is the aim of the Swiss forest policy to exhaust the sustainably extractable harvest potential of tree biomass, which is currently underutilized by about 20 – 30 % (FOEN, 2013). Harvesting this additionally available potential would increase the available biomass and be a driving factor for any biomass-based LMT.

While no actors are currently applying BECCS in Switzerland, many currently existing users of bioenergy could potentially be coupled to CCS. Waste incineration plants, for example have an estimated share of 50% of their emitted CO₂ being of biological origin (Schweizer Bundesrat 2021). Further actors that could potentially be coupled to CCS are biogas plants, which sometimes have already installed CO₂ capturing technology to remove CO₂ from the biogas before feeding it into the gas grid. Also, larger scale central district heating plants applying various forms of bioenergy seem feasible for BECCS. As BECCS, compared to other LMTs, provides no additional benefit apart from removing CO₂ from the atmosphere, the most feasible financing option for BECCS are likely the carbon emission trading systems or direct payments for CO₂ removal. Already now, fossil fuel importers in Switzerland have compensate for a percentage of the emissions from the fuel they import (at the moment only for 10% of emissions but the legal framework foresees that this percentage increased to be up to 90% in the future; Schweizer Bundesrat 2021). These funds are then redistributed to GHG compensation projects through the foundation KLIK ([Home – Foundation for Climate Protection and Carbon Offset \(klik.ch\)](https://www.klik.ch)) and could also become available for BECCS projects.

3.2.3 Current land use and potential land-use competition

The application of BECCS does not directly require land. However, the biomass which is required for BECCS is obviously sourced from land and this land for the generation of biomass for bioenergy is therefore in competition with other land-uses. Due to a scarcity of agricultural land, transforming agricultural land to land that is only used to produce biomass for BECCS is mostly out of the question for Switzerland. This scarcity of agricultural land in Switzerland is further amplified by increases in

organic farming area, and by landscape biodiversity measures, which both reduce the intensity of Swiss agriculture. However, a potential to extract more biomass from Swiss forests than what is used today, has been identified. While not applied yet, the implementation of BECCS is an explicitly stated goal within the Swiss long-term climate strategy. On the other hand, it is recognized that an energetic use is the lowest possible value use of biomass. Applying BECCS is therefore primarily foreseen for the lowest values biomass, for example waste incineration plants that make use of biomass, and for additionally available biomass (e.g. from forest) that is not suitable for a material use. Several important Swiss documents (e.g. Beuttler et al., 2019; Federal Council of Switzerland 2020) state that a material use of wood, for example in construction, is to be preferred. Hence BECCS should be applied within a cascade use system, where an energetic use of biomass coupled to BECCS occurs only at the end of product lifetime, for example when construction wood cannot be recycled anymore. This affects the scalability of BECCS and limits the use to the left-over low value biomass and biomass already energetically used today. On the other hand, in contrast to coniferous trees, the demand for wood from deciduous trees for a material use seems to be lower than the natural supply by Swiss forests and most of it is used as firewood anyway (personal communication with WSL expert). This might favour an energetic use of the additionally available potential or using this wood for biochar with BECCS capturing the generated CO₂ during pyrolysis.

While there is no explicit projection on the extent to which BECCS will be applied in the future in Switzerland, it was estimated that about 5 mln ton CO₂ per year could be removed if all available biomass of Switzerland would be used, whereas applying BECCS to bioenergy already in use today would already remove 2.1 mln ton CO₂ per year (Federal Council of Switzerland 2020). Even if most emissions are avoided by 2050, about 6.8 mln ton CO₂ per year are expected to remain to be compensated, so the potential of BECCS suggests that it will likely be one of the key technologies for compensating remaining emissions (Schweizer Bundesrat 2021), because CCS application in other sectors, such as in the cement industry and for non-biogenic waste treatments are already a fix part of the Swiss plan to reduce CO₂ emissions.

3.2.4 Climate risks & sensitivities

The application of BECCS is not directly sensitive to climate changes. Yet the production of the biomass that is needed for BECCS will obviously be influenced by climate change. However, since almost any biomass could be used for BECCS, it is difficult to tell what the final effect of climate change in Switzerland may be. Diverse effects could cancel each other out. For example, while biomass production Switzerland may be impacted by dryer summers, an increase in temperature in Switzerland could prolong the vegetation period, move up the tree line in the alps. Yet, as for BECCS basically all biomass, even of the lowest quality, could be used, it is likely that BECCS is less sensitive to summer droughts than for example crop yields. It is likely that the climatic risk to BECCS feedstock of the biomass already used today is lower than for newly sourced biomass. Especially forests are expected to suffer from climate change, so the additional feedstock from there may be at higher risk.

3.2.5 *Economic implications*

A main challenge of BECCS may be, that the capturing of CO₂ and the transport infrastructure may only be economically feasible, when applied at sufficiently large scale. Furthermore, since BECCS is not yet applied in Switzerland the estimations of costs are subject to much uncertainty. They depend on the cost for capturing CO₂ from the combustion processes, the scale at which this can be done, the distance and how the captured CO₂ will be transported to its final location (e.g. trains vs. pipelines) and the ease to access the location (e.g. in the north sea vs within Switzerland). All these components are not yet clear, thus the relatively wide price span of 50 – 250 CHF (1 CHF is about 1 € at time of writing) per ton of CO₂ stored was estimated (Federal Council of Switzerland 2020). The competitiveness of BECCS will then strongly depend on the price per ton of CO₂ emissions or the price assigned to negative emissions. At the moment there is a CO₂ tax on fossil fuels in Switzerland equivalent to 90 CHF per ton of CO₂ ([CO₂-Gesetz - UVEK \(admin.ch\)](#)), which depending on how well Switzerland will be on track with its climate goals may rise to 210 CHF in 2030 (Schweizer Bundesrat 2021). However, the current system is a cap and trade system while negative emissions can, at the moment, not be sold. Furthermore, there are several exceptions from the CO₂ tax for heavy emission industries to keep them competitive, so it is mostly a consumer tax. Yet, if the CO₂ price would become generally applicable to all industries and negative emissions could be accounted, it is very likely that BECCS will become feasible, though Switzerland has also stated that negative emissions that are realized in other countries while being paid by the Swiss could be a way to achieve negative emissions in a cheaper fashion.

3.2.6 *Co-benefits and trade-offs*

While, due to a clear prioritization of the Swiss government, BECCS will not be directly in competition for land with food production, there is a competition for the biomass also with other LMTs. For example, straw biomass could either be incorporated into fields, used for biochar, or BECCS. As reduced input of biomass into fields would lower soil carbon stock and thus fertility, there could thus be a very indirect risk to agricultural production. Also, an increased pressure to use biomass for BECCS could change the landscape if a shift towards more intensive fast-growing biomass-plants or trees is favoured. If the production of biomass would be the only goal, it is likely that more intensive production systems would be needed, also threatening biodiversity. However, as biodiversity and landscape conservation are a strong focus of Swiss agricultural policies, including subsidies that are paid for a measured biodiversity, it is unlikely that biomass production for BECCS will be prioritized to have strong effects. It is more likely and already stated, that BECCS should be focused on biomass already used today, or on biomass which is underutilized such as forest biomass (FOEN 2013).

3.2.7 *Risks associated with scaling up*

The main risks associated with scaling up the use of BECCS is likely the competition for biomass with other uses and the fact that Switzerland has no confirmed geological storage capacity. Yet, Switzerland has clearly positioned itself in a way that BECCS shall only be used with lowest quality biomass. However, BECCS can likely only be applied at larger scales, as the infrastructure to enable BECCS (such as pipelines for the CO₂) will probably only make sense at large scales. Hence, there may be a challenge

to transition from small scale utilization of biomass (e.g. firewood) to large scale BECCS plants. Another main risk is likely the lack of practical experience with BECCS up to this point, which is in stark contrast with the clear plan to incorporate CCS technologies into the mitigation technologies portfolio. Thus, it is hard to foresee what kind of unforeseen difficulties could come up when trying to deploy BECCS at national scale.

3.2.8 *Research gaps*

While the long-term climate strategy of Switzerland already plans with CCS technologies storing significant amounts of CO₂, e.g. half of remaining emissions in 2050, in their ZERO-Base emission scenario (Schweizer Bundesrat 2021), there are many open questions. To date, it is not even established, whether there is any storage potential in Switzerland (Federal Council of Switzerland, 2020). The lack of this clear potential assessment is thus the largest research gap. If there is no storage potential within Switzerland, there is the idea to build CO₂ pipelines towards the north-sea, which however could significantly increase the cost. One could thus summarize that the research should mostly focus on delineating the technical feasibility of CCS, especially the storage potential. Estimates on the amount of available biomass are on the other hand much better resolved.

3.3 Biochar

3.3.1 *Introduction*

Biochar is charcoal produced from biomass, such as wood or harvest residues, applying a pyrolysis at high temperatures (400-650°C) in the absence of oxygen (Beuttler et al., 2019), a process that also produces thermal energy that could be used for heating. During biochar production, part of the carbon stored in the biomass is released, and thus the potential exists to combine biochar production facilities with BECCS. As a potential LMT, the biochar is applied to soils with the aim of improving soil properties and to be a long-term storage of carbon. Prior to application, biochar is usually mixed with other organic residues or manure so it soaks up nutrients which it can then slowly release. A growing popularity of biochar application in the recent years has to do with the discovery of highly fertile man-made soils of more than 2000 years of age in recent decades in Brazil, called the “Terra Preta” soils. These are found in areas where soils are commonly degraded and they contain up to 70 times more black carbon than surrounding soils (Glaser et al., 2001). What classifies the application of biochar to the soil as an LMT, is the long turnover times of biochar in the soil, expected to be in the range of many decades to several centuries. Thus, biochar will remain in soils for much longer than normal organic material and constitute a significant sink of carbon. An interesting point, raised by a biochar expert, is that it is the currently the only available LMT that is really considered long-term, and thus favoured on voluntary carbon markets. It is therefore sometimes also referred to as Pyrogenic Carbon Capture and Storage (PyCCS). Adding to the attractiveness of biochar is that the addition of biochar to soils is associated with additional co-benefits, such as increased nutrient or water-holding capacity (Hüppi et al., 2015) thus increasing the fertility of especially lower fertile soils. The application of biochar to soils has also been associated to reduced N₂O emissions in several studies (e.g. Hüppi et al, 2015, 2016).

Different forms of biomass, ranging from forest wood, plantation wood to crop residues, can be used to create biochar, which results in different biochar properties and likely affects biochar stability in soil. While biochar in “Terra Preta” soil of millennial age was found, the stability of biochar in temperate regions is hypothesized to be rather in the range of decades to centuries (Beuttler et al., 2019). Yet, char of old age is also naturally found in many temperate fertile soils such as the steppe soils of Ukraine and Russia (Beuttler et al., 2019).

3.3.2 Policy context

The application of biochar to soils in Switzerland is legal since the year 2013 but each application needs to be approved by the local office of the Swiss Federal Office for Agriculture. The Biochar quality standards in Switzerland are the same as for the European Union and are formulated in the European Biochar Certificate (EBC, 2012). It regulates that biochar is only produced from domestic biomass, free of any additives, and does not contain any organic contaminants. Apart from the regulation, which is assuring the quality of biochar, there is until now, no legal framework that addresses the deployment of biochar, for example through subsidies. Yet such schemes could be developed in the future, as biochar is mentioned in several government reports about LMTs (Federal Council of Switzerland, 2020) and climate change mitigation (Schweizer Bundesrat 2021). Additionally, producing biochar could be one way to make full use of the currently underutilized available biomass of Swiss forests, a declared goal of Swiss forest policy (FOEN 2013). The application of biochar in Switzerland is limited to agricultural soils. Research on biochar is currently conducted by Agroscope ([Pflanzenkohle \(admin.ch\)](#)) and by the Ökozentrum Langenbruck ([CharNet.ch](#)). A large-scale application of biochar is to date not practiced in Switzerland, partly because there are concerns about unwanted side effects, such as introducing toxic substances (though mostly being prejudice, as the biochar quality standards are high in Switzerland), but also due to the current high market prices of biochar (around 800 CHF per ton). Thus, at the moment the application of biochar is mainly done by a few innovative farmers. However, it was postulated that an average annual application of biochar of 0.5 ton ha⁻¹ would lead to many beneficial side effects and that therefore the reasonable demand to achieve these benefits could be up to 600,000 ton per year for whole Switzerland (Beuttler et al., 2019). At the moment, there are no special funds available for biochar in Switzerland, but if biochar application would be classified as a negative emission, it could receive additional funds. Another option is funds through the foundation KLIK ([Home – Foundation for Climate Protection and Carbon Offset \(klik.ch\)](#)), which distributes import taxes for fossil fuel import to GHG mitigation projects could be a source of funds for biochar in the future. However, a stakeholder highlighted, that as an indicator of a high future potential, biochar is among the most requested C sequestration technologies on the voluntary carbon market.

3.3.3 Current land use and potential land-use competition

The application of biochar in Swiss agriculture is currently only a niche, with a use of less than 1,600 ton in 2018, corresponding to less than 10% of the overall Swiss consumption of biochar-like products including uses such as active char or char for barbecue (Beuttler et al., 2019). However, it is projected

that if the interest increases and prejudice barriers are overcome, there is a market potential of 600,000 ton per year (assuming an average input of half a ton per year in all agricultural fields), a quantity which would not exhaust available biomass in Switzerland (Beuttler et al., 2019). Since the application of biochar is to date still a niche and no policies subsidize it, it is difficult to project the development of biochar application in the coming decades. Additionally, there seems to be a common perception among Swiss cantonal soil protection agencies that the application of biochar is connected to risks for soil life, for reduction of pesticide effectiveness and for introduction of pollutants (Federal Council of Switzerland, 2020). However, perceived risks may be greater than actual risks, none of the above stated concern was found a significant concern in recent literature on biochar application. Due to the scarcity of agricultural land in Switzerland, it is highly unlikely that suitable land for food production will be used to produce biomass for biochar. Food production is and will remain a priority in Switzerland, as import dependence is high and maintaining or increasing food self-sufficiency is a declared goal of Swiss policy. It is therefore likely that the competition of biochar for land and biomass, will only be on the land not used for food production. Thus, the competition would be between biochar, BECCS, and the material use of biomass. Such a competition can exist for biomass, which is already used today, including harvest residues, as well as for the currently underutilized biomass (such as underutilized deciduous tree wood from forests). While BECCS and biochar production could be coupled and biochar will likely not be in direct competition with a material use of high-quality wood, there could be a competition between the direct application of harvest residues in the field and the use of those residues to produce biochar (Federal Council of Switzerland, 2020). This could mean that increasing incorporation of harvest residues into soils would be in competition with scaling up the use of biochar. However, since most harvest residues are turned over in a relatively short time of one or a few years, the use of at least some of this biomass for biochar creation could have a higher CO₂ sequestration potential than returning residues.

3.3.4 Climate risks & sensitivities

Due to the long-term stability of biochar even in tropical soils (Glaser et al., 2001), the sensitivity of biochar application as LMT to climate related changes should be relatively low. However, as biochar production depends on biomass availability, the amount of biomass available for biochar production could be negatively influenced by drought, or by a decrease in forest productivity in a changing climate.

3.3.5 Economic implications

The current price of biochar is around 800 CHF per ton (Schmidt et al., 2021). Thus, if 62% of the CO₂ captured within the biochar would be counted as stable and thus a negative emission (the value assumed by Beuttler et al., 2019), the cost would be roughly 350 CHF per ton of CO₂ sequestration (800 x 3.66 tCO₂/t C /.62). Thus, if only the CO₂ sequestration is considered, biochar appears to be a very expensive LMT at the current price level. Yet, other benefits such as reduced N₂O emissions and increased yields have been identified across a broad range of studies in a recent meta-analysis which showed that the strength of the effects also depended on the rate of biochar application and initial soil properties (Zhang et al., 2020). It is, however, recognized that the yield increase due to biochar

application is strongest in unfertile soils with a low pH and that Swiss soils have mostly alkaline pH and are fertile, so large yield increases are not expected in Switzerland (Schmidt et al., 2021). Yet the combination of positive side effects of biochar with a compensation for negative emissions could, depending on the CO₂ price make biochar a competitive negative emission technology and it is expected that the future cost per avoided ton of CO₂ could be between 135 and 10 CHF (Federal Council of Switzerland, 2020).

3.3.6 Co-benefits and trade-offs

While in theory, there could be competition for land of biomass production area with agricultural production, this is not expected to occur in Switzerland (Beuttler et al., 2019) due to a clear priority on producing food and most subsidies being paid for food production only. In general, the application of biochar to soils is associated with benefits to crop production, due to higher nutrient and water storage capacities of biochar amended soils. Yield increases in the range of +20% are commonly reported after biochar application to soils with limited soil fertility (Zhang et al., 2020). While such strong increases are not expected in Switzerland, due to most soils being already high in fertility (Schmidt et al., 2021), the application of biochar is still expected to benefit rather than decrease agricultural production. Also, a stakeholder pointed out that biochar provides several benefits to the soil, such as increasing water holding capacity and it may also be beneficial in capturing and binding soil pollutants, due to its high surface area. As a soil amendment, biochar will likely not have a strong influence on landscape composition or biodiversity, whereas there is a strong potential to reduce N₂O emissions in Switzerland (15-50 %; Hüppi et al. 2015, 2016), which is also in alignment with a recent global meta-analysis (Zhang et al., 2020). An additional risk that has been mentioned is that the application of biochar in larger quantities could increase the albedo of the soil, leading to higher absorbance of sunlight and thus contributing to warming (Federal Council of Switzerland, 2020). However, this effect is only expected if the biochar is not properly incorporated (e.g. ploughed) into the soil (Schmidt et al., 2021) and if the soil is left bare, so with good practice this risk should be negligible. Overall, the summarized literature suggests, that the application of biochar, if done correctly, will be associated with many co-benefits, such as increased soil fertility and reduced N₂O emissions. While there is in theory the risk of creating a competition for biomass with for example harvest residues, it was estimated that the sustainably available biomass in Switzerland is sufficient to satisfy the demand for biochar, even if applied at national level. Yet there seem to be several negative perceptions about biochar, such as that it will negatively impact soil life or introduce pollutants to the soil. As for certified biochar application these risks are found to be negligible in the literature (Schmidt et al., 2021), it seems as if the application of biochar would benefit from campaigns aiming at improving the public perception of biochar.

3.3.7 Risks associated with scaling up

As mentioned before, the main risk for scaling up the use of biochar to the national level is an increased demand and competition for biomass with other LMTs. However, as the expected demand of a maximum of 600,000 ton of biochar annually does not exceed the national availability of biomass (Beuttler et al., 2019), the overall risk seems relatively low. While biomass cannot be simultaneously

used for a material use, biochar and BECCS, there is a clear hierarchy of value and cascade use is possible. Material use is of highest value, but is only feasible for high quality biomass, while the pure energetic use for BECCS is the lowest value use. However, there is the potential to synergistically combine BECCS and biochar production, storing the CO₂ which is emitted during the production of biochar via CCS technologies. Thus, with a solid planning practice it should be possible to manage the risk of scaling up well.

3.3.8 *Research gaps*

One of the largest research gaps about biochar application is the persistence of human introduced biochar in temperate soils. This has to do with the generally long persistence of biochar, and the long-term experiments thus required to analyse the turnover time in detail. However, in a condensation of various studies it was postulated that turnover of biochar in the soil would take at minimum 270 times longer than biomass normally introduced and that biochar could be almost inert at maximum (Beuttler et al., 2019). A similar conclusion was made by the literature analysis of Schmidt et al. (2021), showing that with the most conservative estimate about 0.3% of biochar turnover is possible, corresponding to a half-life in the soil of at least 230 years. Another open question is how the presence of biochar could affect the functionality of pesticides intended to affect the soil, for example nematicides (Schmidt et al., 2021). It could thus be that agricultural systems that highly depend on this special class of pesticides should refrain from applying biochar.

3.4 Reduced tillage, conservation/organic agriculture

3.4.1 *Introduction*

Soils are the largest terrestrial carbon pool in active exchange with the atmosphere and store more than double the amount of carbon than biomass (Lal, 2004). Any soil management options that enhance the amount of carbon in soils are thus effective LMT. Soil carbon is in constant turnover, new carbon formation and turnover of present carbon happen simultaneously, and thus enhancing soil carbon stocks in contrast to other LMTs has an element of impermanence. On the other hand, the increase of soil carbon stocks has also several co-benefits, as it improves water holding- and nutrient storage capacities, soil structure and soil aeration (Bashir et al., 2021). It should thus not come as a surprise that the global increase of soil carbon stocks is a topic of high political interest. For example, it was postulated that increasing global soil carbon stocks by 4 permille annually would compensate all man-made GHG emissions (Minasny et al., 2017). While it needs to be clearly stated that the 4 permille are only a numeric example and in fact not an achievable technical potential, it is still useful to illustrate the importance of global soil carbon stocks. The two ways to alter soil carbon stocks are either slowing down the decomposition of soil carbon or increasing the input of new carbon into the soil. Reduced tillage addresses the first way, as tillage breaks up soil aggregates protecting some of the soil carbon, thereby effectively increasing the speed of carbon cycling in the soil (Six et al., 1999). Other measures such as conservation agriculture, for example using cover crops to produce more biomass, or organic agriculture, often increase the amount of carbon input into the soil. Additionally, through either

reduced application of nitrogen fertilization or improved recycling of nitrogen, nitrogen losses can be reduced. This is especially relevant with regard to the amount of N₂O emitted from soils, which is comprising a large part of agricultural GHG emissions.

3.4.2 Policy context

Swiss agricultural policy has implemented several regulations addressing conservation agriculture. For example, there are subsidies for measures that are stated to increase resource use efficiency, which includes no-till and reduced tillage practices in the Swiss subsidy system ([Ressourceneffizienzbeiträge \(admin.ch\)](#)). For example, there is a subsidy of 150 CHF for mulch seeding and 250 CHF per ha for direct seeding. There are also additional subsidies for practitioners of organic agriculture ([Beitrag für biologische Landwirtschaft \(admin.ch\)](#)). There is no additional subsidy for the application of cover crops in Switzerland, but instead it is mandatory to assure a crop cover in winter months to receive subsidies at all ([Direktzahlungen \(admin.ch\)](#)). Thus, it is very commonly applied as the Swiss agricultural subsidies usually make up a significant share of farm income. Further subsidies are available for practitioners of organic agriculture apart from the price premium. However, there has been concerns the recent past that the increase of food prices in general, following the current Ukraine conflict, have relatively decreased the importance of this price premium. On top of the usual agricultural subsidies, farmers applying organic agriculture in Switzerland get additional yearly subsidies of 200 CHF per ha or up to 1,600 CHF per ha for horticulture. Of the different agricultural management practices discussed as LMT, organic farming is the most widely applied. Currently, 16% of Swiss farmers are already practicing organic farming (Federal Statistical office of Switzerland, 2021) and the number has been constantly growing in the last years. Additionally, according to official statistics, reduced tillage subsidies have been paid for about 82,000 ha in 2019, which is about 7.5 % of agricultural area in Switzerland.

3.4.3 Current land use and potential land-use competition

As priorly stated, about 16% of farmers in Switzerland are currently practicing organic agriculture. The area they cover is in the same magnitude and has been growing from about 120,000 ha in 2010 to about 170,000 ha in 2020 ([biz20_dt_web.pdf \(bio-suisse.ch\)](#)) and is expected to further increase in the future. The current extent of reduced tillage practices is about 7.5 % of Swiss agricultural area, but this is not further differentiated into reduced and no-till in the official statistics. As cover cropping is already a precondition for receiving subsidies, it is likely not in competition with other land uses. For reduced tillage systems and organic cropping systems, it is however likely that they are mutually exclusive. This is because in reduced tillage systems, herbicides such as glyphosate are often applied to reduce the competition for the crop by killing of the established weed cover prior seeding. On the other hand, synthetic herbicides are excluded in organic agriculture and to manage weed pressure, ploughing is usually the best option. An expert stakeholder stated that no-till and organic agriculture can be combined with highly sophisticated crop rotations, but this is difficult and not commonly practiced in no-till. Another critical point when it comes to organic agriculture is the reduced yields per area, compared to conventional agriculture. This could be a relevant factor in Switzerland, as about 40% of

consumed food is imported. For example, compared to conventional agriculture, organic farming requires between 20 (cereals, pulses) and 80% (vegetables, animal products) more land on a per calories basis (Clark and Tilman, 2017). Yet, several stakeholders stated that in tendency, the yields in Swiss conventional agriculture are declining, due to losses of soil fertility, while organic yields due to improvements in management and cultivars increase yield – so in the long-term the yield may become similar. Another point is that GHG emissions of organic agriculture can be significantly lower and the strongest difference is found between plant and animal products, organic agriculture could be applied at larger scales if the consumption of animal products would be reduced at the same time.

3.4.4 Climate risks & sensitivities

While there is no particular vulnerability of increased levels of carbon in the soil to heat waves, it is generally agreed upon that soil organic carbon (SOC) turnover increase with temperature, all else being constant. This leads to the concern that there could be a feedback loop between increased global temperatures and increased SOC turnover (Davidson and Janssens, 2006) which is a strong argument for limiting global warming as much as possible. However, as increased summer temperatures could also be linked to increased drought, which likely reduces SOC turnover due to lack soil microbes becoming dormant, it is not entirely clear how the combination of heat and drought could affect SOC turnover. In general, increased levels of SOC benefit the water storage capacity and could reduce the drought stress that plants are subject to. Also, it improves soil structure which improves water infiltration and thus reduces the erosion potential. Hence, organic fields are generally more resilient to droughts than conventional fields. Reduced tillage and especially no-till could play an important role in mitigating erosion, as they maintain an intact soil cover throughout most of the year, while ploughing leads to open soil cover and destroys the soil cover, leaving the soil more prone to erosion until a new plant cover is established.

3.4.5 Economic implications

In contrast to technical LMTs, such as BECCS, the introduction of conservation agriculture practices such as reduced tillage or organic agriculture is expected to be a relatively cheap LMT (expected costs are in the range of 0 – 80 CHF per ton of CO₂). On the other hand, higher SOC is associated with higher turnover rates (turnover usually proportional to stocks and simulated by 1st order decay). The consequences are twofold. First, after some time of higher inputs, the system reaches a new steady state at a higher SOC stock. Second, this means that practices applied to increase SOC stocks have to be continued indefinitely to maintain the increased SOC stocks at the new steady state. This is probably the reason, why LMT that increase soil carbon stocks are considered as an interim solution available for only a few decades (Federal Council of Switzerland, 2020). It is also worth to note that, as turnover and stocks are proportional, the cost of increasing stocks increases, the more carbon is to be stored in soils. On the other hand, the many co-benefits for agriculture could make increase in SOC attractive, even if there is no direct price paid for it. Also, reduced N₂O emissions due to tighter nutrient cycles, while not being a negative emission, can be seen as a permanent reduction in GHG emissions. To address the impermanence of SOC stock enhancements, Sierra et al. (2021) recently proposed to

compute the economic benefit of carbon sequestration within different pools, calculating the economic benefit as a function of residence time of carbon in a specific pool.

3.4.6 Co-benefits and trade-offs

For reduced tillage practices, there exists the risk of an increased pest pressure from either higher pressure from weeds in the field, or from higher fungal growth on crop residues remaining on the soil surface. This could thus lead to an increased need to apply pesticides, which could both negatively affect biodiversity and water quality. As already mentioned, the main risk for the practicing of organic agriculture is a generally lower yield production on a per area base. This trade-off would be especially relevant if the Swiss food consumption patterns would not change, as the land use for organic animal products is almost double compared to only about 20% increased land need for cereal production (Clark and Tilman, 2017). The higher soil fertility through higher SOC stocks from both organic agriculture and reduced tillage on the other hand could benefit agricultural production especially in dry summers. Especially the use of cover crops to enhance nutrient recycling and carbon inputs into the soils has little to no negative side-effects. On the other hand, as it is a requirement for subsidies most farmers already use cover crops and the potential for it is limited. Several positive side effects are expected at the landscape level for organic farming, for example an improved biodiversity due to more diverse crop rotations used in organic agriculture, and this could be the opposite in reduced tillage systems. Also, a lower load of nutrients, as no synthetic fertilizers are used and livestock units are coupled to land in organic agriculture, would likely lead to reduced N₂O emissions and reduced nitrate leaching, also improving the water quality. As organic agriculture is bound to local animal feed, a larger scale adoption of organic agriculture in Switzerland could also reduce GHG emissions in other parts of the world, such as GHG emissions from land clearing for soy production in Southern America. However, if animal production was coupled to available land area in Switzerland, significantly less animal products would be produced. If this would only be compensated by an increased import, the net effects would probably be negligible, as GHG emissions would just be shifted to other countries. If, however, a dietary shift towards more plant-based nutrition would be possible, shifting to organic agriculture could be an important step to closing local nutrient cycles.

3.4.7 Risks associated with scaling up

The main risk for large scales of organic farming introduction are, as stated before, risks associated with lower yields leading to an import dependence, if not accompanied by a dietary shift of the Swiss population at the same time. For reduced tillage the risk could be that there is an increased need to apply herbicides such as glyphosate to kill of the competition by present weeds at the time of seeding.

3.4.8 Research gaps

The turnover of carbon in the soil, especially in combination with climate change has been subject to controverse discussions for decades. However, this is not likely to be easily resolved. In general, while it is agreed upon, that higher inputs of plant materials into soil lead to an increase accumulation of soil carbon, it has in practice been very difficult to measure the exact increase of SOC stocks, mainly due

to the heterogeneity of soils even at small scales, making changes of carbon difficult to distinguish from natural variation. This is of special relevance if carbon credits shall be substantiated by field measurements and payments are only made based on measured increases. In general, the composition of soils has been identified as one of the main predictors for the storage potential of carbon in the soil, with the amount of fine particle (silt and clay) being correlated to the storage capacity for carbon (Hassink, 1997) and this is also considered in models such as CENTURY where the decomposition of soil carbon decreases with increased soil silt and clay content (Parton et al., 1987). Thus, a main research question would be how to utilize available biomass to bring into the soil most effectively, based on soil properties. A very relevant question would be how subsidies or similar mechanisms may be used to specifically target the most responsive soils and get the highest amount of carbon sequestration with the least amount of biomass.

3.5 Agroforestry and landscape elements

3.5.1 Introduction

Agroforestry is the implementation of trees on agricultural land, leading to a dual use of the land. This includes a large variety of systems, from traditional fruit orchards, Silvopastoral systems, which are meadows with trees that provide shade for the animals, to modern alley cropping systems with trees between agricultural field rows. Many agroforestry systems are established with the general aim of achieving a higher land use efficiency than each system alone, which could be in terms of yield but could also aim at providing other ecosystem services such as increased biodiversity and additional habitat for mammals and insects, erosion control or reduced nitrate leaching through a better recycling of nutrients from deep rooting trees. If trees of significant economic value from timber or fruits are used, agroforestry systems also allow for an economic diversification. Traditional agroforestry systems, such as meadow orchards or forest meadows were very common in Switzerland (Kay et al., 2019b). Also, landscape elements such as shrubs and trees between fields, which were also of smaller patch size in the pasts, comprised a more diverse landscape in the mid-20th century, which has been partly lost in many parts of Europe as a by-product of agricultural intensification. In a way, the establishment of agroforestry systems can thus be seen as a transformation of agricultural systems back to their roots. Despite being much less present than in the pasts, traditional agroforestry systems are still found in many areas of Switzerland. An example are the silvopastoral meadows (“Wytweiden”) in the Swiss Jura. These traditional agroforestry systems are usually used very extensively. Modern agroforestry systems in contrast facilitate a higher intensity and are planned in a way that mechanization is allowed (e.g. alley cropping systems with distances of 20 m or greater between tree rows). Agroforestry systems can directly contribute to climate change mitigation by sequestering additional carbon in the tree biomass, the vegetation below the trees and additionally in the soil. Quantifying the additional carbon stored in the tree biomass is relatively simple at the field level, as it is easy to measure and can be derived from tree density and annual growth rates (Kay et al., 2019c), but due to the diversity of systems may still be difficult at the national level. Belowground carbon, especially soil carbon, are more difficult to access. There is a general understanding that agroforestry systems in tendency enhance soil

carbon compared to sole arable cropping systems (Cardinael et al. 2020) but while in the mean there is soil carbon increase many studies also reported losses of soil carbon, especially when there was a change from high carbon systems such as grassland to agroforestry (Feliciano et al, 2018).

3.5.2 Policy context

While the use of Agroforestry systems as LMT for Switzerland has been briefly mentioned in the official Swiss report about promising LMT, there is no direct policy that supports the deployment of agroforestry as an LMT. However, agroforestry systems are still eligible to agricultural subsidies, and fruit trees are receiving special biodiversity-subsidies. However, timber tree agroforestry on the other hand are not subsidized, which is a disincentive to establish any agroforestry that are not fruit trees: The part of the field that they cover is not eligible to subsidies and their establishment could lead to the risk for farmers of losing subsidies. In some cantons in Switzerland (e.g. Solothurn, [Heckenrichtlinie.pdf \(so.ch\)](#)) there are laws to protect landscape elements such hedges and shrubs. In practice, some farmers report that these laws impede the re-implementation of agroforestry resembling landscape elements, as once planted, their removal will be prohibited by canton law. Employees of the Swiss Federal Office for the Environment and Federal Office for Agriculture reported in personal communication that there is the intent to include Agroforestry into the agricultural legislation, making it explicitly eligible for additional subsidies and maybe carbon credits, not limited to fruit trees. Yet this only in development, and recently the amendment of the law has been postponed until at least the year 2023. Nevertheless, different projects to study and promote agroforestry in Switzerland are going on at the moment, with several innovative farmers already implementing different agroforestry systems. Several networks exist including the Project Agro4esterie ([Projet ressource Agro4esterie – Agroforst](#)) and the AGRIDEA Agroforestry network ([Agroforstsysteme - AGRIDEA \(abacuscity.ch\)](#)). Also, the Swiss Confederation's centre of excellence for agricultural research, Agroscope, is interested in agroforestry and involved in several projects on the topic ([Kontakt – Agroforst & AGROMIX | Coventry University](#)). According to several actors involved in these projects the current interest of farmers in agroforestry is high, and finding enough farmers to implement agroforestry within the projects was easy. On the other hand, there are no research experiments in Switzerland with long-term agroforestry systems.

3.5.3 Current land use and potential land-use competition

Historically, the agricultural landscape was more fragmented than today and landscape elements as well as agroforestry systems were very common. Though there has been a decline due to agricultural intensification, traditional agroforestry systems still are common and make up 12 % of the Swiss farmland (Herzog et al, 2018). Of those systems, the most common systems, covering more than half of the area, are forest pastures, mostly located in the pre-alps and Jura mountains. Hedgerow agroforestry systems cover about a fourth of the agroforestry systems, traditional fruit orchards cover about a fifth of the area, while chestnut selva are a rare form of agroforestry system covering less than two percent of the area (Herzog et al, 2018). Though there is no clear projection how the development

of modern agroforestry systems will change the area under agroforestry, it has been suggested that the adoption of agroforestry on an additional 13 % of the agricultural area could help to reduce simultaneously occurring deficits in the ecosystem service categories of biodiversity, climate change mitigation, air and water quality, as well as soil quality (Kay et al., 2019b). This is in general in alignment with a study across Europe, where 10 % of the area was identified as agroforestry priority area, facing deficits in at least five of the aforementioned ecosystem service categories (Kay et al. 2019c). In general agroforestry does not directly compete with other LMTs for land in Switzerland as, due to high pressure on land, major land-use changes are not feasible in Switzerland and it would only be established on land that is already of agricultural use. However, in some cases agroforestry systems provide lower crop yields on the same land area than arable systems (Kay et al., 2019c), in which case they may partly be in competition with food production. For example, Kay et al. (2018b) found that modelled crop yield of agroforestry systems in Switzerland was about a third less than in arable systems, while many other ecosystem services increased. Yet, the yield reduction is most pronounced in temperate agroforestry systems while in Mediterranean systems, where light and temperature are less limiting and shading may at times benefit the crops, higher yields were observed in agroforestry systems (Kay et al., 2018b). It may thus be, that with the inevitable climate change agroforestry systems may prove the more resilient agricultural systems. Another political question in Switzerland is, that whether agroforestry can be accounted as biodiversity area. At the moment Swiss farmers need to maintain 7% of their area as biodiversity area, and if regulations would be changed to include the tree growing areas from agroforestry into the definition of biodiversity area, the competition with agricultural food production land would be reduced.

3.5.4 Climate risks & sensitivities

Many of the climate risks and sensitivities such as heat waves, drought, heavy rains or forest fires are more pronounced in warmer climates. It is therefore an interesting finding that both in terms of yield and other ecosystems services the benefit of agroforestry systems is usually more pronounced in warmer climates (e.g. Feliciano et al., 2018; Kay et al., 2018b). Many ecosystem services are enhanced in agroforestry systems, with a very clear improvement in erosion control, biodiversity and soil fertility (Torralba et al., 2016). Under increased pressure from climate change these ecosystem services provided by agroforestry may increase in relevance. For example, the trees within the system often have the capacity to buffer heat waves and drought through a better microclimate and tapping into deeper water resources, which is beneficial to animals in grazing systems (Paris et al., 2019.) They also can reduce the effect of heavy rainfall by providing a canopy to protect soils from splash erosion and runoff erosion through root systems. In tropical systems, subject to high amounts of rainfall within short periods of time, for example, agroforestry systems reduce erosion by on average 50% (Muchane et al., 2020). One of the most pronounced benefits of agroforestry in Europe is the provisioning of biodiversity ecosystem services such as habitat for birds and pollinators or providing flowers to pollinators in the case of fruit trees (Kay et al., 2020).

3.5.5 *Economic implications*

The diversity of agroforestry systems is also represented in the economic feasibility. While hedgerows may slightly reduce the area available, with no further side-effects, other agroforestry systems such as alley cropping systems may increase the amount of labour required per land because they require pruning. In tropical agricultural systems, where agroforestry adoption has been studied in more detail, the labour costs are often limiting the adoption of improved agricultural management techniques such as agroforestry (Cavanagh et al., 2017). The same could be the case in Switzerland, where labour costs are very high, making pruning of agroforestry trees a very expensive matter, especially if the trees are only suitable for timber and do not provide any high value fruits. Yet, the Swiss agricultural policy provides many subsidies based on ecosystem services, e.g. for biodiversity areas, which include traditional fruit orchards (bff-spb.ch : Biodiversitätsförderflächen). If modern agroforestry systems such as alley cropping systems would be included in the subsidy schemes, providing payment for the additional ecosystem services that they provide, their implementation could well become profitable. Additional payments for carbon sequestration could further increase the economic feasibility of agroforestry systems. The cost of establishing an agroforestry system with about 50 trees ha⁻¹ was estimated to be in the around 10.000 CHF but could be higher depending on special requirements by the canton (personal communication with Agroscope experts). The yearly sequestration of a typical AF system with 50 trees ha⁻¹ given as 1.6 ton C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Kay et al., 2019b) which is roughly equal to 6 ton CO₂. Thus, with an expected lifetime of 20 years or more, one could estimate the cost per ton CO₂ to be below 100 CHF, not considering additional maintenance cost, but also not considering benefits such as additional fruit yields and ecosystem services. In fact, Kay et al. (2019a) estimated that when also considering the value of other ecosystem services, agroforestry in continental Europe would already become profitable starting at already 10 € ton⁻¹ C (less than 3 € ton CO₂).

3.5.6 *Co-benefits and trade-offs*

In the worst case, the adoption of alley cropping agroforestry in Switzerland could lead to cereal yield reductions of up to 30% (Kay et al., 2018b), but this depends largely on the system, the row spacing and if the trees also provide a harvestable yield. However, it could be a relevant trade-off, especially since Switzerland is scarce in agricultural land and already importing larger portions of its food requirements. On the other hand, it is likely that a larger scale adoption of agroforestry would lead to a more diverse landscape providing many other ecosystem services apart from food production, including erosion control, increased biodiversity, habitat and food for pollinators and birds and enhanced soil fertility (Torralba et al., 2016). In addition, the inclusion of trees often makes landscapes more attractive as recreational areas. There have not been many studies of N₂O emissions in temperate agroforestry systems, but a general tendency of reduced N₂O emissions was reported (Acheamfour et al., 2017). For example, Moore et al. (2017) reported significantly lower cumulative N₂O emissions in agroforestry systems compared to agricultural systems. The same was reported by Wolz et al. (2018) with reductions in the N₂O emissions of alley cropping compared to normal agriculture between 25 and 83%. The trees in the system thus seem to have a very significant impact on the nitrogen cycle, which is even more profound with regard to leaching of nitrogen. For example,

nitrate leaching was reduced between 82 and 91% in the study by Wolz et al. (2018). This is due to the safety net function of tree roots, which reach deeper than crop roots and can take up nutrients lost for the main crop (Allen et al., 2004). It has therefore been suggested to establish agroforestry primarily in areas that are subject to environmental issues such as reduced drinking water quality due to nitrate concentrations (Kay et al., 2019a). Apart from the mentioned risks and benefits, the additional provision of wood from agroforestry systems could be another benefit. If both the tree fruits and the crops are in demand and would alternatively have to be produced on separate areas, the agroforestry can lead to overall efficiency benefit, displaying in a land equivalent ratio (LER) >1 . This seems to be the case in Mediterranean climates. For example, Arenas-Corraliza et al. (2018) reported a LER between 1.3 and 2 for a walnut cereal alley cropping system in central Spain. However, for temperate regions, such as Switzerland it is expected that the LER is rather around 1.2. As the establishment of an agroforestry system can be between 10.000 to 20.000 CHF, the question whether to establish agroforestry systems is mostly an economic one. The consideration includes economic value of the trees (e.g. from fruits), if there are already marketing structures for new tree products, additional labour requirements, and also the expected lifetime of the system compared to for example how long a farmer will still be active. While there are little environmentally negative side effects of agroforestry the trade-offs may rather be economical ones, especially if the length that additional subsidies are available, is unknown.

3.5.7 Risks associated with scaling up

The main risk of large agroforestry application is in the lack of systematic assessments of agroforestry systems in Switzerland. To date all agroforestry trials are established on farms and while they are academically accompanied, no design experiments are established in Switzerland, yet, which will likely start in the coming years. A risk could thus be that if agroforestry is scaled up too fast, there may, due to the lack of regional knowledge, be an establishment of unsuitable trees or systems. In the worst case, the trees of such systems could be removed quite easily, so the risk is mostly an economic risk of capital lost through establishment and clearing.

3.5.8 Research gaps

The largest research gaps in agroforestry in Switzerland is the about the application of modern alley cropping agroforestry systems. So far there have been scientific followings of on-farm establishments of agroforestry systems but controlled scientific design experiments including control treatments without trees yet need to be established. There is a need to better understand field-crop tree interactions to optimize alley-cropping agroforestry to Swiss conditions. Another major uncertainty is how climate change may affect both the modern and traditional Swiss agroforestry systems. The studies from Mediterranean areas suggest that with warmer temperatures and increased summer droughts, the benefits agroforestry systems increase, which make it especially attractive with regard to climate change. Yet, as soils in Switzerland are different from Mediterranean soils, such space-for-time predictions need to be treated with caution.

4. Conclusions

In general, Switzerland takes a pioneer role in negative emission technologies and LMTs. At the same time, land is scarce in Switzerland, so all LMTs are at least to some extent in competition with each other and with food production. The key stakeholders and policy makers in Switzerland seem to be aware of this and already think about how LMT portfolios could be designed to minimize potential trade-offs and apply each LMT where it leads to the least competition. For example, BECCS shall primarily use of waste materials. On the other hand, there is the awareness of the limitations of each LMT. BECCS, for example, which is already planned to play a key role in the Swiss LMT portfolio, lacks CO₂ storage facilities in Switzerland and Swiss policy makers are exploring storage options outside Switzerland. Biochar is identified as the only technology with a high permanence that is already available today, but it is too expensive to be competitive under current CO₂ prices and there are some societal prejudices to overcome for large-scale application. The short-term potential, co-benefits and low cost of agricultural management practices, such as reduced tillage and organic farming, are recognized. At the same time their non-permanence is seen as an issue, especially under future climate change. Finally, modern agroforestry systems are seen to have a significant potential and under a changing climate they may even enhance crop system resilience compared to monocrops. Yet, it is recognized that there is a lack of research on agroforestry in Switzerland and no long-term trials exist. As a result of the strengths and weaknesses of the different LMTs, a sequential adoption seems feasible to the authors of this report: We think that a Swiss LMT portfolio could start with a focus on LMTs that are based on agricultural management practices combined with an experimental implementation of modern agroforestry systems on a smaller scale. If modern agroforestry systems prove successful, they may be scaled up to larger agricultural areas. With time and increasing CO₂ prices, a larger scale application of biochar may then also become feasible and BECCS could come online as the last LMT, once technological readiness is reached and feasible storage facilities are found.

5. References

- Alcántara, V., Don, A., Well, R., Nieder, R., 2016. Deep ploughing increases agricultural soil organic matter stocks. *Global Change Biology* 22, 2939–2956. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13289>
- Allen, S.C., Jose, S., Nair, P.K.R., Brecke, B.J., Nkedi-Kizza, P., Ramsey, C.L., 2004. Safety-net role of tree roots: evidence from a pecan (*Carya illinoensis* K. Koch)–cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.) alley cropping system in the southern United States. *Forest Ecology and Management* 192, 395–407. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2004.02.009>
- Arenas-Corraliza, M.G., López-Díaz, M.L., Moreno, G., 2018. Winter cereal production in a Mediterranean silvoarable walnut system in the face of climate change. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 264, 111–118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2018.05.024>
- Artru, S., Garré, S., Dupraz, C., Hiel, M.-P., Blitz-Frayret, C., Lassois, L., 2017. Impact of spatio-temporal shade dynamics on wheat growth and yield, perspectives for temperate agroforestry. *European Journal of Agronomy* 82, 60–70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2016.10.004>
- Autret, B., Mary, B., Chenu, C., Balabane, M., Girardin, C., Bertrand, M., Grandeau, G., Beaudoin, N., 2016. Alternative arable cropping systems: A key to increase soil organic carbon storage? Results from a 16 year field experiment. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 232, 150–164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2016.07.008>
- Baah-Acheamfour, X. C., W, B., N, C., 2017. The potential of agroforestry to reduce atmospheric greenhouse gases in Canada: Insight from pairwise comparisons with traditional agriculture, data gaps and future research. *The Forestry Chronicle*. <https://doi.org/10.5558/tfc2017-024>
- BAFU (Hrsg.), 2017. Boden in der Schweiz. Zustand und Entwicklung. Stand 2017. (No. 1721), Umwelt-Zustand. Bundesamt für Umwelt, Bern.
- Bashir, O., Ali, T., Baba, Z.A., Rather, G.H., Bangroo, S.A., Mukhtar, S.D., Naik, N., Mohiuddin, R., Bharati, V., Bhat, R.A., 2021. Soil Organic Matter and Its Impact on Soil Properties and Nutrient Status, in: Dar, G.H., Bhat, R.A., Mehmood, M.A., Hakeem, K.R. (Eds.), *Microbiota and Biofertilizers*, Vol 2: Ecofriendly Tools for Reclamation of Degraded Soil Environs. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 129–159. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-61010-4_7
- Beuttler, C., Keel, S.G., Leifeld, J., Schmid, M., Berta, N., Gutknecht, V., Wohlgemuth, N., Brodmann, U., Stadler, Z., Tinibaev, D., Wlodarczak, D., Honegger, M., Stettler, C., 2019. The Role of Atmospheric Carbon Dioxide Removal in Swiss Climate Policy – Fundamentals and Recommended Actions. (Report by Risk Dialogue Foundation). Commissioned by the Federal Office for the Environment, Bern.
- Cardinael, R., Mao, Z., Chenu, C., Hinsinger, P., 2020. Belowground functioning of agroforestry systems: recent advances and perspectives. *Plant Soil* 453, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-020-04633-x>

- Carrier, M., Rhéaume Gonzalez, F.-A., Cogliastro, A., Olivier, A., Vanasse, A., Rivest, D., 2019. Light availability, weed cover and crop yields in second generation of temperate tree-based intercropping systems. *Field Crops Research* 239, 30–37. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2019.05.004>
- Cavanagh, C.J., Chemarum, A.K., Vedeld, P.O., Petursson, J.G., 2017. Old wine, new bottles? Investigating the differential adoption of ‘climate-smart’ agricultural practices in western Kenya. *Journal of Rural Studies* 56, 114–123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2017.09.010>
- Clark, M., Tilman, D., 2017. Comparative analysis of environmental impacts of agricultural production systems, agricultural input efficiency, and food choice. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 12, 064016. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aa6cd5>
- Davidson, E.A., Janssens, I.A., 2006. Temperature sensitivity of soil carbon decomposition and feedbacks to climate change. *Nature* 440, 165–173. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature04514>
- Dong, W., Walkiewicz, A., Bieganski, A., Oenema, O., Nosalewicz, M., He, C., Zhang, Y., Hu, C., 2020. Biochar promotes the reduction of N₂O to N₂ and concurrently suppresses the production of N₂O in calcareous soil. *Geoderma* 362, 114091. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2019.114091>
- EBC, 2012. European Biochar Certificate - Guidelines for a Sustainable Production of Biochar. European Biochar Foundation (EBC), Arbaz, Switzerland. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.4658.7043>
- Federal Council of Switzerland, 2021. Switzerland’s Long-Term Climate Strategy.
- Federal Council of Switzerland, 2020. Von welcher Bedeutung könnten negative CO₂-Emissionen für die künftigen klimapolitischen Massnahmen der Schweiz sein? Bericht des Bundesrates in Erfüllung des Postulates 18.4211 Thorens Goumaz vom 12. Dezember 2018.
- Federal Statistical office of Switzerland, 2021. Farming at a glance [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.bfs.admin.ch/bfs/en/home/statistics/agriculture-forestry/farming.html> (accessed 2.12.21).
- Federal Statistical Office of Switzerland, 2020a. Aussenhandel nach Waren - 1990-2019 | Tabelle [WWW Document]. Bundesamt für Statistik. URL <https://www.bfs.admin.ch/bfs/de/home/statistiken/industrie-dienstleistungen/aussenhandel.assetdetail.13007302.html> (accessed 2.5.21).
- Federal Statistical Office of Switzerland, 2020b. Landwirtschaftliche Nutzfläche - Ohne Alpflächen - Tausend Hektaren - 1996-2019 | Diagram [WWW Document]. Federal Statistical Office. URL <https://www.bfs.admin.ch/bfs/de/home/statistiken/kataloge-datenbanken/grafiken.assetdetail.12867948.html> (accessed 2.12.21).
- Feliciano, D., Ledo, A., Hillier, J., Nayak, D.R., 2018. Which agroforestry options give the greatest soil and above ground carbon benefits in different world regions? *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 254, 117–129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2017.11.032>

- Fließbach, A., Oberholzer, H.-R., Gunst, L., Mäder, P., 2007. Soil organic matter and biological soil quality indicators after 21 years of organic and conventional farming. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 118, 273–284. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2006.05.022>
- FOAG, Federal Office for Agriculture of Switzerland, 2020. Agrarbericht 2020 - Ressourceneffizienzbeiträge [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.agrarbericht.ch/de/politik/direktzahlungen/ressourceneffizienzbeitraege> (accessed 2.19.21).
- FOEN, Federal Office for the Environment of Switzerland, 2020. Hintergrundpapier, Klimaziel 2050: Netto-Null Treibhausgasemissionen.
- FOEN, Federal Office for the Environment of Switzerland, 2019. Waldfläche in der Schweiz [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.bafu.admin.ch/bafu/de/home/themen/thema-wald-und-holz/wald-und-holz--fachinformationen/waldzustand-und-waldfunktionen/waldflaeche-in-der-schweiz.html> (accessed 2.8.21).
- FOEN, Federal Office for the Environment of Switzerland, 2013. Forest Policy 2020. Visions, objectives and measures for the sustainable management of forests in Switzerland. Federal Office for the Environment, Bern.
- Gauder, M., Billen, N., Zikeli, S., Laub, M., Graeff-Hönninger, S., Claupein, W., 2016. Soil carbon stocks in different bioenergy cropping systems including subsoil. *Soil and Tillage Research* 155, 308–317. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2015.09.005>
- Glaser, B., Haumaier, L., Guggenberger, G., Zech, W., 2001. The “Terra Preta” phenomenon: a model for sustainable agriculture in the humid tropics. *Naturwissenschaften* 88, 37–41. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s001140000193>
- Herzog, F., Szerencsits, E., Kay, S., Roces-Diaz, J., Jäger, M., 2018. Agroforestry in Switzerland—a non- CAP European country, in: 4th EURAF Conference. pp. 74–77.
- Honegger, M., Poralla, M., Michaelowa, A., Füssler, J., Kessler, S., 2020. Negative Emissionen und Treibhausgas-Zertifikatehandel. Potenziale, Kosten und mögliche Handlungsoptionen. Grundlagen zur Erarbeitung der langfristigen Klimastrategie des Kantons Zürich und der Netto-Null-Szenarien für die Stadt Zürich. Zürich.
- Hüppi, R., Felber, R., Neftel, A., Six, J., Leifeld, J., 2015. Effect of biochar and liming on soil nitrous oxide emissions from a temperate maize cropping system. *SOIL* 1, 707–717. <https://doi.org/10.5194/soil-1-707-2015>
- Hüppi, R., Neftel, A., Lehmann, M.F., Krauss, M., Six, J., Leifeld, J., 2016. N use efficiencies and N₂O emissions in two contrasting, biochar amended soils under winter wheat—cover crop—sorghum rotation. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 11, 084013. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/11/8/084013>

IOP Full Text PDF, n.d.

Jäger, M., 2019. Agroforst Netzwerk Schweiz 2014 - 2018, Schlussbericht.

Kay, S., Crous-Duran, J., Ferreiro-Domínguez, N., García de Jalón, S., Graves, A., Moreno, G., Mosquera-Losada, M.R., Palma, J.H.N., Roces-Díaz, J.V., Santiago-Freijanes, J.J., Szerencsits, E., Weibel, R., Herzog, F., 2018a. Spatial similarities between European agroforestry systems and ecosystem services at the landscape scale. *Agroforest Syst* 92, 1075–1089. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-017-0132-3>

Kay, S., Crous-Duran, J., García de Jalón, S., Graves, A., Palma, J.H.N., Roces-Díaz, J.V., Szerencsits, E., Weibel, R., Herzog, F., 2018b. Landscape-scale modelling of agroforestry ecosystem services in Swiss orchards: a methodological approach. *Landscape Ecol* 33, 1633–1644. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-018-0691-3>

Kay, S., Graves, A., Palma, J.H.N., Moreno, G., Roces-Díaz, J.V., Aviron, S., Chouvardas, D., Crous-Duran, J., Ferreiro-Domínguez, N., García de Jalón, S., Măciacășan, V., Mosquera-Losada, M.R., Pantera, A., Santiago-Freijanes, J.J., Szerencsits, E., Torralba, M., Burgess, P.J., Herzog, F., 2019a. Agroforestry is paying off – Economic evaluation of ecosystem services in European landscapes with and without agroforestry systems. *Ecosystem Services* 36, 100896. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2019.100896>

Kay, S., Jäger, M., Herzog, F., 2019b. Ressourcenschutz durch Agroforstsysteme – standortangepasste Lösungen. *Agrarforschung Schweiz* 10, 308–315.

Kay, S., Kühn, E., Albrecht, M., Sutter, L., Szerencsits, E., Herzog, F., 2020. Agroforestry can enhance foraging and nesting resources for pollinators with focus on solitary bees at the landscape scale. *Agroforest Syst* 94, 379–387. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-019-00400-9>

Kay, S., Rega, C., Moreno, G., den Herder, M., Palma, J.H.N., Borek, R., Crous-Duran, J., Freese, D., Giannitsopoulos, M., Graves, A., Jäger, M., Lamersdorf, N., Memedemin, D., Mosquera-Losada, R., Pantera, A., Paracchini, M.L., Paris, P., Roces-Díaz, J.V., Rolo, V., Rosati, A., Sandor, M., Smith, J., Szerencsits, E., Varga, A., Viaud, V., Wawer, R., Burgess, P.J., Herzog, F., 2019c. Agroforestry creates carbon sinks whilst enhancing the environment in agricultural landscapes in Europe. *Land Use Policy* 83, 581–593. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2019.02.025>

Klaus G. (Red.), 2007. Zustand und Entwicklung der Moore in der Schweiz. Ergebnisse der Erfolgskontrolle Moorschutz. (Umwelt-Zustand No. 0730). Bundesamt für Umwelt, Bern.

Lal, R., 2004. Soil carbon sequestration to mitigate climate change. *Geoderma* 123, 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2004.01.032>

Leifeld, J., Bassin, S., Fuhrer, J., 2005. Carbon stocks in Swiss agricultural soils predicted by land-use, soil characteristics, and altitude. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 105, 255–266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2004.03.006>

- Luo, Z., Wang, E., Sun, O.J., 2010. Can no-tillage stimulate carbon sequestration in agricultural soils? A meta-analysis of paired experiments. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 139, 224–231. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2010.08.006>
- Mäder, P., Hahn, D., Dubois, D., Gunst, L., Alföldi, T., Bergmann, H., Oehme, M., Amadò, R., Schneider, H., Graf, U., Velimirov, A., Fließbach, A., Niggli, U., 2007. Wheat quality in organic and conventional farming: results of a 21 year field experiment. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture* 87, 1826–1835. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.2866>
- Minasny, B., Malone, B.P., McBratney, A.B., Angers, D.A., Arrouays, D., Chambers, A., Chaplot, V., Chen, Z.-S., Cheng, K., Das, B.S., Field, D.J., Gimona, A., Hedley, C.B., Hong, S.Y., Mandal, B., Marchant, B.P., Martin, M., McConkey, B.G., Mulder, V.L., O'Rourke, S., Richer-de-Forges, A.C., Odeh, I., Padarian, J., Paustian, K., Pan, G., Poggio, L., Savin, I., Stolbovoy, V., Stockmann, U., Sulaeman, Y., Tsui, C.-C., Vågen, T.-G., van Wesemael, B., Winowiecki, L., 2017. Soil carbon 4 per mille. *Geoderma* 292, 59–86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2017.01.002>
- Minx, J.C., Lamb, W.F., Callaghan, M.W., Fuss, S., Hilaire, J., Creutzig, F., Amann, T., Beringer, T., Garcia, W. de O., Hartmann, J., Khanna, T., Lenzi, D., Luderer, G., Nemet, G.F., Rogelj, J., Smith, P., Vicente, J.L.V., Wilcox, J., Dominguez, M. del M.Z., 2018. Negative emissions—Part 1: Research landscape and synthesis. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 13, 063001. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aabf9b>
- Moore, B.D., Kaur, G., Motavalli, P.P., Zurweller, B.A., Svoma, B.M., 2018. Soil greenhouse gas emissions from agroforestry and other land uses under different moisture regimes in lower Missouri River Floodplain soils: a laboratory approach. *Agroforest Syst* 92, 335–348. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-017-0083-8>
- Muchane, M.N., Sileshi, G.W., Gripenberg, S., Jonsson, M., Pumariño, L., Barrios, E., 2020. Agroforestry boosts soil health in the humid and sub-humid tropics: A meta-analysis. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 295, 106899. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2020.106899>
- Pang, K., Van Sambeek, J.W., Navarrete-Tindall, N.E., Lin, C.-H., Jose, S., Garrett, H.E., 2019. Responses of legumes and grasses to non-, moderate, and dense shade in Missouri, USA. I. Forage yield and its species-level plasticity. *Agroforestry Systems* 93, 11–24. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-017-0067-8>
- Paris, P., Camilli, F., Rosati, A., Mantino, A., Mezzalana, G., Dalla Valle, C., Franca, A., Seddaiu, G., Pisanelli, A., Lauteri, M., Brunori, A., Re, G.A., Sanna, F., Ragolini, G., Mele, M., Ferrario, V., Burgess, P.J., 2019. What is the future for agroforestry in Italy? *Agroforest Syst* 93, 2243–2256. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-019-00346-y>
- Petrescu, A.M.R., Lohila, A., Tuovinen, J.-P., Baldocchi, D.D., Desai, A.R., Roulet, N.T., Vesala, T., Dolman, A.J., Oechel, W.C., Marcolla, B., Friborg, T., Rinne, J., Matthes, J.H., Merbold, L., Meijide, A., Kiely, G., Sottocornola, M., Sachs, T., Zona, D., Varlagin, A., Lai, D.Y.F., Veenendaal, E., Parmentier, F.-J.W., Skiba, U., Lund, M., Hensen, A., Huissteden, J. van, Flanagan, L.B., Shurpali, N.J., Grünwald, T., Humphreys, E.R., Jackowicz-Korczyński, M., Aurela, M.A., Laurila, T., Grüning, C., Corradi, C.A.R.,

- Schrier-Uijl, A.P., Christensen, T.R., Tamstorf, M.P., Mastepanov, M., Martikainen, P.J., Verma, S.B., Bernhofer, C., Cescatti, A., 2015. The uncertain climate footprint of wetlands under human pressure. PNAS 112, 4594–4599. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1416267112>
- Schmidt, H.-P., Hagemann, N., Abächerli, F., Leifeld, J., Bucheli, T., 2021. Pflanzenkohle in der Landwirtschaft Hintergründe zur Düngertilgung und Potentialabklärung für die Schaffung von Kohlenstoff-Senken.
- Schweizer Bundesrat, 2021. Langfristige Klimastrategie der Schweiz [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.bafu.admin.ch/bafu/de/home/themen/klima/fachinformationen/emissionsverminderung/verminderungsziele/ziel-2050/klimastrategie-2050.html>
- SFOE, Swiss Federal Office of Energy, 2017. ENERGIE AUS BIOMASSE WEIL IN ORGANISCHEN ABFÄLLEN UND HOLZ VIEL DRIN STECKT [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.bfe.admin.ch/bfe/de/home/versorgung/erneuerbare-energien/energie-aus-biomasse.html> (accessed 2.19.21).
- Sierra, C.A., Crow, S.E., Heimann, M., Metzler, H., Schulze, E.-D., 2021. The climate benefit of carbon sequestration. Biogeosciences 18, 1029–1048. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-18-1029-2021>
- Six, J., Elliott, E.T., Paustian, K., 1999. Aggregate and Soil Organic Matter Dynamics under Conventional and No-Tillage Systems. Soil Science Society of America Journal 63, 1350–1358. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj1999.6351350x>
- Six, J., Feller, C., Denef, K., Ogle, S.M., Sa, J.C. de M., Albrecht, A., 2002. Soil organic matter, biota and aggregation in temperate and tropical soils - Effects of no-tillage. Agronomie 22, 755–775. <https://doi.org/10.1051/agro:2002043>
- Struhs, E., Mirkouei, A., You, Y., Mohajeri, A., 2020. Techno-economic and environmental assessments for nutrient-rich biochar production from cattle manure: A case study in Idaho, USA. Applied Energy 279, 115782. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.115782>
- Swiss Federal Office of Energy, 2010. Studie zur Abschätzung des Potenzials für CO₂-Sequestrierung in der Schweiz.
- Thees, Oliver, Burg, Vanessa, Erni, Matthias, Bowman, Gillianne, Lemm, Renato, 2017. Biomassepotenziale der Schweiz für die energetische Nutzung. Ergebnisse des Schweizerischen Energiekompetenzzentrums SCCER BIOSWEET, WSL Berichte. Eidg. Forschungsanstalt für Wald, Schnee und Landschaft WSL, Birmensdorf.
- Torralba, M., Fagerholm, N., Burgess, P.J., Moreno, G., Plieninger, T., 2016. Do European agroforestry systems enhance biodiversity and ecosystem services? A meta-analysis. Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment 230, 150–161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2016.06.002>

- Wiesmeier, M., Mayer, S., Burmeister, J., Hübner, R., Kögel-Knabner, I., 2020. Feasibility of the 4 per 1000 initiative in Bavaria: A reality check of agricultural soil management and carbon sequestration scenarios. *Geoderma* 369, 114333. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2020.114333>
- Wolz, K.J., Branham, B.E., DeLucia, E.H., 2018. Reduced nitrogen losses after conversion of row crop agriculture to alley cropping with mixed fruit and nut trees. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 258, 172–181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2018.02.024>
- Zhang, Q., Xiao, J., Xue, J., Zhang, L., 2020. Quantifying the Effects of Biochar Application on Greenhouse Gas Emissions from Agricultural Soils: A Global Meta-Analysis. *Sustainability* 12, 3436. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12083436>

SCALING LAND-BASED MITIGATION SOLUTIONS IN BURKINA FASO

LAND-BASED MITIGATION NARRATIVE CO-DESIGN

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2. Introduction

This report includes a description of a generic nation-wide transition scenario for the implementation of land-based mitigation technologies and practices for the AFOLU sector (agriculture, forestry, and other land use sectors) in Burkina Faso. The report shows the outcomes of a series of research steps that have been conducted in this country since the start of the project in June 2020 until the end of 2022:

First, we performed an initial scoping of key LMTs in the case study country. The scoping assessment resulted in a long list of broad portfolios of different LMTs that could be viable within the various case study countries.

Second, following this long list, we developed a short-list LMT portfolio containing key LMTs that would be the most relevant for a given country context. All case study country partners were asked to propose and validate their LMT portfolio through complementary (policy) literature review and with the help of stakeholder interviews (i.e. external validation by relevant country experts and stakeholders). Ex-ante no specific guidance of criteria for LMT portfolio short-listing was provided to allow for a free and open co-design process with stakeholders. The scoping process and results are presented in section 3 of this report (steps 1 & 2). In Burkina Faso, stakeholder engagement activities were not only limited due to the global pandemic and the language barrier but also because of security threats in the country. For that reason, we hired a local consultant who was able to conduct over 25 stakeholder engagements including researchers, farmers, NGOs, and government agencies. We did a few of these stakeholder engagements online at first and then conducted the majority of engagements on-site in french using the help of the local consultant. Stakeholders played a big role in identifying the relevant LMTs for the country and the opportunities and risks associated with applying these techniques at a larger scale across the country. These conversations were enlightening and helped us to set the priority tasks and challenges that matter most for the local farmers.

Third, after the short-listed LMT portfolios were validated, the LANDMARC case study country partners were asked to develop national scaling narratives or storylines for each LMT included in their portfolio. The assessments focus on climate risks, vulnerabilities as well as socio-economic co-benefits, and trade-offs associated with upscaling LMTs in the case study countries. The analysis is based on a broad range of information/literature sources, and stakeholder consultations conducted. This process is supported through a risk and impact assessment (i.e. an online survey and workshops/seminars/webinars) conducted through the LANDMARC tasks 4.1, 4.2, and 5.2. The results of this analysis are a set of LMT narratives which are presented in a section of this report.

The research steps are designed to enable both an **analysis of the risks and (climate) impacts of scaling up land-based mitigation and negative emission solutions**. As such this report mainly contributes to objectives 2, 3, and 4 of the six LANDMARC key objectives (see Table 1).

Table 1: LANDMARC project objectives.

	Project key objectives
1	Determine the potential and effectiveness of LMTs in GHGs mitigation using Earth Observation (EO)
2	Improve climate resilience of LMT solutions at the local level for large-scale implementation
3	Assess the risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs of scaling up local LMTs nationally
4	Scaling up LMT solutions to the continental and global level to assess the effectiveness
5	Improve current methodologies to estimate emissions and removals for LMTs
6	LMT capacity building and develop new tools and services for decision making

While the results shown in this report represent a mostly qualitative storyline describing the context and impact of scaling up LMTs in a country context, they also enable project partners to proceed with the translation of the outcomes in a manner so that they can serve as direct model input.

Furthermore, these national-level assessments provide a testing ground and empirical basis for the continental, and global assessment of the realistic scaling potential of land-based mitigation and negative emission solutions implemented in Work Packages 6 and 7 of the LANDMARC project (**Objective 4**).

3. Scoping of land-based mitigation and negative emission solutions

3.1 Overview of potential of LMTs in Burkina Faso

3.1.1 Introduction

Burkina Faso constitutes 0.05% of the global emissions and ranks in the list of the per capita emission at 175 out of 188 countries. It is also among the 10% most vulnerable countries to climate change according to the Notre Dame Global Adaptation Index.

Burkina Faso ratified the UNFCCC in 1993 and the Kyoto Protocol in 2005. It also ratified the UN Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) and the Convention to Combat Desertification (CCD). Burkina Faso is also part of the Green Great Wall Initiative and the 3 S initiative and is committed to integrated solutions for resilience to climate change.

Burkina Faso has developed a number of policy and strategy documents relating to climate change, including:

- The National Strategy for implementing the Climate Change Convention adopted in 2001;
- The National Action Program for Adaptation to Climate Change (NAPA) in 2007;
- The development of a framework NAMA (2008);
- The National Sustainable Development Policy in 2013;
- Strategic Framework for Investment in Sustainable Land Management (SFI-SLM) in 2014;
- The National Adaptation Plan (NAP, 2014);
- The first Nationally Determined Contributions (NDC, submitted 29 September 2015; rectified on 11 November 2016).

Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs, or CPDN in French) are at the heart of the Paris agreement (COP21, 2015) and describe the countries commitments to reduce their GHG emissions. Prior to COP21 in Paris, Burkina Faso submitted an Intended Nationally Determined Contribution (INDC) to UNFCCC which it later submitted as its first NDC.

Article 4.2 of the Paris Agreement requires Parties to include a mitigation contribution in their NDCs. The Lima Call for Action also invites Parties to consider communicating their undertakings in adaptation planning or including an adaptation component in their INDCs. The NDC of Burkina Faso has both a Mitigation component and an Adaptation component. It highlights the primary interest of Burkina Faso, which is not a large greenhouse gas emitter, as **the improvement of people's capability to adapt** to a significant rise in the average temperature, more severe dry seasons, stronger and less predictable rainy seasons, increased drought, lowering of the groundwater table, and an increased frequency of certain diseases.

In Burkina Faso agriculture (23.94 Mt) and land use change and forestry (8.81 Mt) accounted together for 81 percent of the total emissions (40.25 Mt) in 2017 (Figure 1). Moreover, the ‘rural sector’ consisting of the water-agriculture-forest-land use subsectors provides the livelihood of more than 80% of the population and is the most vulnerable to climate change, hence the relatively large focus on adaptation in Burkina Faso.

Greenhouse Gas Emissions and Emissions Targets in Burkina Faso

Figure 1 Greenhouse gas emissions and emission targets in Burkina Faso

Source: <https://ndcpartnership.org/countries-map/country?iso=BFA>.

Under the adaptation component the objective of Burkina Faso is not principally the reduction of GHG (mainly through carbon sequestration) but the enhancement of environmental services such as food security, water and soil conservation, sustainable agriculture. As a bonus to the mitigation component, these projects result in the medium and long term in considerable reductions of GHG, which even exceed the results of mitigation efforts. This is shown in Table 2 which lists the climate targets of Burkina Faso for unconditional and conditional scenarios as well as for an adaptation scenario. Mitigation scenarios are expected to reduce GHG emissions by 2030 by 18.2% while adaptation scenarios will contribute to a reduction in emissions of 36.95% when compared to the Business As Usual scenario.

Table 2 Climate targets of Burkina Faso: reduction in GHG emissions by 2030 for unconditional and conditional mitigation scenarios as well as for the adaptation scenario as compared to the Business As Usual (BOA) scenario (source: NDC).

Category	Sector	Estimated total emissions (2030) – BAU scenario ¹	Potential reduction under the following scenarios (2030):					
			Unconditional ²		Conditional ³		Adaptation ⁴	
			Gg of CO ₂ eq	%	Gg of CO ₂ eq	%	Gg of CO ₂ eq	%
Emission mitigation reduction	Solid wastes	1841	-		76.3	4 %		
	Transportation	6,925	29.3	0.4 %	2911	42 %		
	Electricity production	4,191	493.04	11.7 %	162.80	4 %		
	Residential	230	49.71	21.65 %	49.35	21 %	6.5	2.83%
	Energy in the manufacturaing industries	363	10.90	3.00 %	7.30	2 %		
	Industrial processes	1,348						
Land management solutions with LMT potential	Agriculture-water	103,424	7,236	7 %	10,560	10 %	5,150	42.25%
	Animal husbandry						21,630	
	Biomass energy						1,220	
	Forests and changes in land use						15,700	
	Total	118,323	7,808	6.60 %	13,766	11,60 %	43,707⁵	36.95 %
	Investment (million US\$)	-	1.25		756		5805	

Table 3 lists the different actions per sector (sustainable land management, forestry, energy, environmental education, and food) identified in the NDC. The focus in Burkina Faso is on land management practices in forest land, cropland, and grassland, and in particular on the dynamics of agricultural land. Agricultural land expansion mainly occurs at the expense of natural areas and forests.

¹ A “trend” scenario (Business as Usual - BAU), which corresponds to continuation of the past under the assumption that economic development continues without interruption. The chosen reference year is 2007.

² What countries could implement without any conditions and based their own resources and capabilities (financing acquired or being acquired)

³ What countries would undertake if international means of support are provided, or other conditions are met (without any acquired financing)

⁴ Not mandatory

⁵ The adaptation scenario aims, among other things, to restore and develop 5,055 million ha of degraded land, corresponding to 55% of the total current area of degraded lands.

The dynamics of agricultural land are expected to be affected by land-demanding mitigation options such as afforestation, avoided deforestation, improved agricultural management and bioenergy crop production (Soest, Elzen, Forsell, Esmeijer, & Vuuren, 2018).

For example, the objective of the Forest Investment Program (FIP) – one of the larger programmes in Burkina Faso with a mitigation and adaptation component - is to reduce the direct and indirect factors of deforestation and degradation of forest and woody areas in order to enhance carbon sequestration and improve the life conditions of rural populations. The approach is communal and participative for the protection of natural resources and taking into account social aspects. The practices are grouped in 3 categories:

- Practices that improve carbon sequestration: reforestation, afforestation, conservation, restauration
- Practices linked to land management and land tenure security
- Practices aimed at decreasing forest degradation and deforestation

Table 3: Sectors identified in the NDC (source: <https://africaadaptationinitiative.org/ndc/countries/burkina-faso/>)

Sustainable Land Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotion of sustainable land management – improving access to climate information • Cultivation of early or drought-resistant varieties • Implementation of water and soil conservation techniques • Practice of integrated soil fertility management • Development of master plans for water management • Development of water reservoirs: construction of modern wells, high-flow boreholes, dams; development of ponds; stream diversion • Development of grazing water sources and points • Delimitation and development of grazing zones • Combatting the silting of water sources • Implementation of water-efficient irrigation techniques • Development of research programmes on the resilience of forest, wildlife and fish species • Rehabilitation and preservation of wet areas
Forestry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of good forestry and agroforestry practices (selective cutting of firewood, assisted natural regeneration, controlled land clearing, etc.) • Protection of water courses and water sources • Practice of agroforestry for sustained management of natural resources • Community and participative management of forest, wildlife and fish resources
Energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diversification of energy sources (solar, wind, biogas) • Promotion of energy-saving technologies in industry and construction
Environmental education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of environmental education in both formal and informal teaching systems
Food	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement of food processing and preservation methods

3.1.2 Land management practices

Tackling deforestation and restoring degraded land are key pillars in Burkina Faso to reduce GHG emissions and the human and environmental vulnerability to climate change. It requires to take a holistic approach as forests, agriculture, pastoralism and water management are strongly intertwined in the country. In that regard, carbon sequestration programs have proposed diverse but integrated LMTs to be implemented in different sectors ranging from sustainable forest management to agricultural development and bioenergy. Through direct or indirect approaches, these various land-based activities aim at decreasing pressure on forests, (re)plant and restore land health while improving the potential for farming and cultivating.

Practices linked to sustainable land management

Sustainable land management practices in drylands increase agricultural productivity and contribute to climate change adaptation and mitigation. Possible integrated crop, soil and water management measures include crop diversification and adoption of shorter-cycle, more drought-resilient crops, reduction of tillage, reduction in the number of herds, adoption of improved irrigation techniques (e.g., drip irrigation) and moisture conservation methods (e.g., rainwater harvesting according to indigenous and local practices) and maintenance of vegetation and mulch (Faye, et al., 2019).

Practices that improve carbon sequestration: reforestation, afforestation and protection

To reach negative CO₂ emissions, afforestation (planting trees where there were previously none) and reforestation (restoring areas where the trees have been cut down or degraded) are commonly used options. The plantation of agroforestry and fruit trees species is an example of practice used for reforestation and afforestation. Planting these species also restores the vegetation and soil biodiversity (The Forests Dialogue, 2011). The establishment of agroforestry parklands (e.g., shea trees) on farmland, fallow land or rangeland is another afforestation practice with high potential for carbon sequestration and return for the farmers (World Bank, 2013). It requires to invest in building tree nursery infrastructure and select the most fitted species. The creation of conservation zones is a third effective option to reduce deforestation and implement restoration measures. The zones are delimited using physical markers and categorized as “Classified”.

The forest sites selected for the (re)plantation, restoration and protection measures are sites that hold a high carbon sequestration potential and are rich in natural resources and biodiversity while having undergone depletion from the following drivers: agricultural and farming area expansion, wood cutting for fuel or for farming practices, overexploitation of non-timber products and bushfires. Other significant co-benefits from these practices include wildlife preservation, watershed and soil conservation, prevention of soil erosion, etc. (World Bank, 2013). In order to make these investments sustainable, the carbon sequestration programmes also focus on improving forest governance, securing the conservation sites and on supporting socio-economic infrastructure for the benefit of neighboring municipalities.

Practices aimed at decreasing forest degradation and deforestation

Between 1992-2002, the deforestation rate in Burkina Faso was estimated at 105 000 ha/year while the degradation rate of woodlands and forests reached 50 000 ha/year. Less information is available since then but these rates are assumed constant during the following years (World Bank, 2013). Creating irrigated spaces, delimitating grazing areas and building modern sylvo-pastoral infrastructure are among the many LMTs proposed to help developing the agro-sylvo-pastoral sector while reducing tremendously the pressure on the nearby forests. For instance, by avoiding wood reliance, infrastructure (e.g., vaccination parks, water holes and pastoral wells) in metal or stone prevent cutting thousands of trees while providing a safer environment for the cattle and the farmers.

In the energy sector, one notable LMT is the promotion of biodigesters and improved cook stoves in rural households close to nature reserves. The adoption of biodigesters holds a climate change mitigation and attenuation effect by: proposing an alternative to the use of fuelwood, charcoal and fossil fuels for lighting and cooking; capturing the methane and carbon emanating from organic waste decomposition and use them as biogas for renewable energy. As an additional advantage of the technology, the compost resulting from the organic matter breakdown can be used as soil fertilizer, which in turn supports agricultural intensification (Fair & Sustainable Consulting , 2019).

3.2 Determining the LMT scope for national level simulation modelling

In Table 4 , we present the short list of national LMTs that are relevant for the scoping analysis. These LMTs were selected from the 2015 mitigation and adaptation actions proposed in the frame of the NDC. Reasons for the selection and expected outcomes are presented below.

Table 4: Long listing of relevant land based LMTs

LMT	Specification	Included in national LANDMARC portfolio
BECCS	-	N
Biochar	-	N
Forest land	Reforestation, afforestation and forests classification	Y
	Sustainable land management practices on forest land (e.g., Assisted Natural Regeneration)	Y
	Reduced deforestation by promoting improved cook stoves and biodigesters	Y
	Degraded stream banks rehabilitation	N
Cropland	Sustainable land management practices on agricultural land (e.g., agroforestry parklands and soil fertility restoration such as stone barriers, zai pits, half moons)	Y
	Agricultural intensification (e.g., organic manure, low lands)	N

- **Reforestation, afforestation and forests classification**

(Re)planting using local species and expanding the classified forest domain are at the heart of Burkina Faso's main plans and programs (e.g., FIP, REDD+) and are expected to have a strong impact on carbon stock. The NDC adaptation scenario aims at creating 900,000 ha of reforested and conservation areas and developing 450,000 ha of classified forests in the forest/change in land use sector, both projects expected to cumulate 14,000 Gg of CO₂eq sequestered per year. It should be noted that in Burkina Faso, forests can be private or public (owned by the state or by decentralized local collectives). Public forests can be themselves categorized as "classified" or "protected". Classified forests are subject to more restrictions regarding their use and exploitation for the purpose of environmental conservation. Despite the ambitious INDC target, land pressure however is currently a limiting factor to the expansion of classified forests in the country.

- **Sustainable land management practices on forest land**

In Burkina Faso, several land management techniques exist to restore degraded forests and woody spaces. Techniques such as fencing, combined or not with Assisted Natural Regeneration (ARN), have shown results as successful as reforestation efforts. Building fences prevents herd animals to graze young trees in their first years of growth. ANR is a low-costs practice aimed at accelerating vegetation regeneration rather than replacing it. It calls for an active participation of the population to recover over-exploited land and manage the regrowth of the field. In forestry, the ANR technique enables land conservation and improvement (increased number of trees and diversity), the maintenance of soil fertility, and livelihood improvements (with the exploitation of non-timber products). Part of the NDC adaptation targets is the establishment of 800,000 ha of ANR (in 200 rural communes) for an estimated amount of 1,600 Gg of CO₂eq saved every year.

- **Reduced deforestation by promoting improved cook stoves and biodigesters**

The vulgarization of improved cook stoves and biodigesters has been at the heart of Burkina Faso's ambitions for several years already. The FIP investments of the African Development Bank resulted for instance in 4282 cookstoves households installation. The ambition under the adaptation plan is to produce and distribute 540,000 improved cook stoves to save 610 Gg of CO₂eq, and to save a similar amount by improving cook stoves for brewers. Regarding biodigesters, the National Biodigester Program (PNB-BF) has supported the construction of 18000 biodigesters across all 13 regions of the country between 2010 and 2018. In 2019, 1500 biodigesters were planned to be built through the PNB-BF – FIP cooperation although reported numbers for this year show that this target wasn't met. In 2017 and 2018, Burkina Faso organized the International Conference of Biodigester Technology (CITBIO) gathering several African countries such as Benin, Ivory Coast, Guinea, Niger, Senegal, Togo and Mali as well as national and international organizations. The objective of the conference being to work towards an African partnership for the promotion and widespread implementation of

biodigesters technology. Under the adaptation scenario, Burkina Faso plans to equip 25,000 households with operating biodigesters that fertilize 750,000 ha of cultivable land, resulting in 1,800 Gg CO₂eq saved. The dissemination of biodigesters and improved stoves is however limited by the related costs and reliability on external financial support.

- **Sustainable land management practices on agricultural land**

Sustainable land management, which includes halting land degradation and restoring soil fertility has been identified in the NAP as top priority measures to mitigate climate change effects while enhancing crop productivity. To do so, the NAP recommends the implementation in Burkina Faso of a set a diverse actions including the diversification of crops (e.g., increase drought-resistant varieties), agro-forestry, assisted natural regeneration, water and soil conservation and restoration techniques (e.g., the establishment of stone barriers, terraces, small dikes, the use of zai pits and half-moons, etc.) but also the use of living hedgerows, sub-soiling and preventing bush fires. In total, the following adaptation measures: restoring and maintaining fertility in 1,575 million ha of cropland through soil and water conservation techniques; restoring 105,000 ha of degraded land for agricultural production through the construction of 10,000 ha of micro-watersheds, should save the equivalent of 5,106 Gg CO₂ per year in 2030.

The rationale for excluding the other LMTs from any further national scenario scaling analysis is provided below:

- **BECCS and biochar**

NETPS in Burkina Faso focus on land management practices. We could not find any implementation of BECCS in the country nor are they described in the NDC. Small-scale biochar application is found in urban vegetable production in the capital Ouagadougou and experimental in other areas, but is not yet part of government strategies.

- **Degraded stream banks rehabilitation**

Stream banks rehabilitation and protection using a hedgerow barrier system are part of the soil and water initiatives recommended by the NAP and the NDC. In the NDC, this LMT obtained however a lower weighted prioritisation score (based on green growth and maintenance of natural resources, generation of wealth, ease of access/adoption of the technology) than the other LMTs listed in Table 3. Given the relatively small-scale (2000 ha) and impact (60 Gg of CO₂ eq) and complexity of relating rehabilitation and protection to its impact on the catchment, we suggest to exclude the degraded stream banks rehabilitation from the analysis.

- **Agricultural intensification**

The intensification of agricultural activities has the primary role of increasing crop production while reducing cropland expansion. Relevant techniques enabling intensification in Burkina

Faso are the application of organic manure and compost to fertilize crops. These techniques that recycle carbon and store it in the soil have shown to be very profitable in the country. Other best practices are the establishment of new irrigation techniques (e.g., pressured drip irrigation) and the development of low lands areas for intensive rice production. The INDC commitments include the development of 15,000 ha of low lands and irrigated areas for intensive rice cultivation, possibly resulting in 44.4 Gg of sequestered CO₂. While these intensification techniques present many advantages, their carbon impact is more indirect and somewhat lower than the ones selected for the scoping analysis and for this reason we propose not to include them in the short list.

3.3 Discussion on short-listing LMTs

3.3.1 Forest and changes in land use sector

According to the World Bank, degraded forest lands and associated restoration efforts hold the highest potential for carbon sequestration in Burkina Faso. It is without surprise that the country has set ambitious NDCs in the forests/change in land use sector in its 2030 adaptation scenario. While the climate benefits of the LMTs listed in Table 3 within that sector would be tremendous, their implementation requires the provision of external support (e.g., capacity building) and fundings (e.g., because of high investment costs or low economic profitability). The requirement for external financial support is indeed often explicitly expressed as a necessary condition for successful NDC implementation. Burkina Faso clearly describes it as a “constraining determinant” with both the mitigation and adaptation actions heavily relying on international financial resources. Furthermore, Burkina Faso’s private sector will contribute almost 50% of the financing. What this amount translates to is not explicitly specified.

While political commitments have been strong in Burkina Faso during the past 30 years, achieving Burkina Faso’s NDCs also heavily relies on political stability and a robust governance structure, which still have to be further established. Frequent terrorist attacks, especially in the northern part of the country have increased the vulnerability of the populations and are an important barrier to the developments of livelihood and environmental improvements in the impacted regions.

Another factor of importance is the further enabling of local community engagement. Building on the results of the FIP will allow us to adopt successful approaches and techniques that improve and decentralize forest and woodland management programs. For instance, protecting investments through land tenure security and providing local actors with the necessary capacity to take ownership of forests and woodlands management are key solutions to focus on.

It is interesting to note that Burkina Faso’s semi-arid forests (tropical dry forests and woodlands) are widespread in the world – we count over 500 million hectares of semi-arid forests over the globe. The

potential for replication and upscaling across the African continent and other countries is therefore significant (World Bank, 2013).

3.3.2 Land management dynamics

Since the 70s, the short-listed LMTs related to soil and water conservation practices have already proven themselves effective in improving forest density, soil structure, biodiversity, and crop productivity in some regions of the country (Clement Nyamekye, 2018). However, one limitation to their extensions is linked to a lack of long-term land ownership and gender issues. In Burkina Faso, parcels of land are loaned or leased to farmers. Because of this, farming approaches usually favor practices that generate fast returns rather than those requiring long-term investments (Clement Nyamekye, 2018). In addition, Burkina Faso has deeply rooted gender norms, preventing most women farmers to own land and to have the same opportunity as men to take part in land restoration activities. These issues are being tackled by NGOs and programs like the FIP. They aim at improving land tenure security but also providing professional training and improved access to financing to women as well as increasing their participation in land use planning and management activities. Strengthening these efforts will therefore enhance the adoption of land conservation and regeneration techniques and their associated carbon sequestration benefits.

4. Co-design of LMT narratives

4.1 Introduction

The LMTs discussed here are the primary land-based techniques and practices implemented in Burkina Faso to reduce GHG emissions and climate change vulnerability. They are considered the most relevant in terms of carbon sequestration potential and co-benefits on the local, national, and regional levels. These LMTs are part of the country's commitments for 2030 and mainly aim at planting trees, restoring degraded land, and reducing pressures on forests:

- Reforestation, afforestation, and forest classification.
- Sustainable land management practices on forest land with a focus on Assisted Natural Regeneration (ARN).
- Reduced deforestation by promoting improved cookstoves and biodigesters.
- Sustainable land management practices on agricultural land with a focus on agroforestry parklands and soil fertility restoration such as stone barriers, Zai pits, and half-moons.

Stakeholder engagements played a key role in identifying the drivers of deforestation and forest degradation in Burkina Faso. It helped us to understand the co-benefits and risks of implementing different LMTs across the country. We found that the degradation of ecosystems in Burkina Faso has been consistent, often explained by climatic deterioration and increasing demographic pressure on natural resources. The sources of deforestation or forest degradation are predominantly anthropogenic, such as agricultural and livestock production, and exploitation of resources for energy and mining. In Burkina Faso, forest loss primarily occurs as a result of uncontrolled bushfires, fuelwood harvest, encroachment into forest areas for agricultural production (i.e. for crops and livestock), and mining expansion. These stressors are exacerbated by population growth, poverty, and urban development, and climate variations. Despite this, Burkina Faso's Initial National Communication to UNFCCC identifies its area of land use, land-use change, and forestry (LULUCF) as a net sink. Overall, the stakeholder engagements opened the gate for us to feel the challenges that the local farmers face and the technical challenges that sometimes prevent them to apply LMTs at a larger scale.

4.2 Reforestation, afforestation, and forests classification

4.2.1 Introduction

In Burkina Faso, deforestation and the exploitation of deforested land are the main emitters of CO₂. As explained in more detail in the Step 1 section of this document, the main drivers of deforestation in Burkina Faso are related to land expansion for agriculture and livestock farming, bushfires, overharvesting for fuelwood and non-timber products as well as gold mining. Since the 1970s Burkina Faso has implemented several initiatives to maintain and increase its forest cover. Among these initiatives, priority is given to reforestation, afforestation, and forest protection. Despite

the effort, the measures taken aren't currently enough for carbon sequestration to equal or surpass CO₂ emissions. According to the Ministry of the Environment, Green Economy, and Climate Change (MEEVCC), the area of planted forests roughly corresponds to 10% of the surface of land deforested each year only. In this section, we will discuss the context of the implementation of reforestation, afforestation, and forest classification in Burkina Faso.

4.2.2 Policy context

Forest governance can be defined as the aggregate of rules, policies, institutions, and practices aimed at ensuring the implementation of the principles of transparency, accountability, and participation within the sector. As such, it concerns how the institutions acquire and exercise their authority in the management of forest resources; with transparently developed policies; a bureaucracy that operates according to a professional ethic; an executive that is aware of their actions, and a strong civil society that participates in the decisions that relate to this sector. In Burkina Faso, the categories of actors with responsibilities for forest governance are state structures, collectivités territoriales, the private sector, rural communities and partner organizations. For the 2020 Global Forest Resources Assessments (FRA), the FAO and Burkina Faso prepared an evaluation on the country's forest resources. The assessment is based on the collection of the country's existing reports and complemented with the use of satellite remote sensing for the identification of land use and land use change. In the 2020 FRA, the main policy and strategy documents guiding the sustainable management of forest resources in Burkina Faso are listed:

- Accelerated Growth and Sustainable Development Strategy (SCADD).
- National Sustainable Development Policy (PNDD).
- National Environmental Policy (PNE).
- National Forest Policy (PFN).
- National Rural Land Security Policy (PNSFMR).
- Decentralized Rural Development Policy Letter (LPDRD).

For the implementation of these policies, the following documents dealing with the preservation of forest resources have been adopted:

- National Rural Sector Program (PNSR).
- Ten-Year Action Plan for the Environment and the Living Framework (PDA / ECV).
- National Action Program to Combat Desertification (PAN / LCD).
- National Forest and Wildlife Resources Management Program (PRONAGREF).
- Burkina Faso's National Strategy and Action Plan on Biological Diversity.
- National Strategy and the Action Plan for the National Strategy for Fire Management in Rural Areas.
- National Plant Production Strategy.
- Environmental Information Management Program.

Forest classification is done at the state level. Reforestation and afforestation efforts are however implemented by the villagers and rural communities. Efforts are led by state and non-state (NGOs) actors. Funding is primarily provided through international projects under programs such as the Forest Investment Program (FIP) under the Strategic Climate Fund (funded by among others the WB's IBRD and AfDB).

4.2.3 Current land use and potential land-use competition

The agro-ecological zones of Burkina Faso reflect the climatic divisions of the country, with the vegetation cover becoming denser from the North to the south. Forest areas in Burkina Faso are made up of land stocked with trees and/or shrubs including agro-forestry parks (Figure 1). The most obvious change in Burkina Faso's land cover over the last decade is the major expansion of croplands (Figure 2). Reforestation programs have started in 1973 in Burkina Faso and have cumulated 52,650 ha of planted surface within the period 1973-1999, although it is not clear whether the plantations have been maintained or converted to another land use since then (Ouedraogo, 2000). According to the FRA's assessment, the extent of the Burkinabe forests has undergone an annual decrease of 0.77% between 2010 and 2020, showing a steeper deforestation rate than during the periods 1990-2000 and 2000-2010 (see

Figure 2: Locations of parks and reserves in Burkina Faso (source: USGS) Natural forests have decreased in extent in the last 20 years due to a conversion to other land uses (woody areas, agricultural land and degraded forests) while planted forests have increased, in a lesser extent, due to sensibilization programs encouraging reforestation and afforestation. The 2020 FRA reports a cumulative planted area of 198,303 ha between 2000 and 2018. Annual details are presented in Figure 3.

It is worth to note that estimates of Burkina Faso's total forest cover vary between sources, many of which use different methods of assessment. For example, the Ministry of the Environment (at that time the Ministry of Environment and Livelihoods) shared that forest formations (i.e. open forest, gallery forest, shrubland, wooded savanna, steppe) covered 13,305,238 ha in 2002, or 48.52% of the national territory. However, FAO statistics in 2020 reported 6,216,000 ha of forest cover in Burkina Faso, accounting for approximately 23% of the total land area, and 'other wooded lands' accounting for about 18%. This mainly consists of acacia bush in the north (Sahelian regions), and savannas, shea (*Vitellaria paradoxa*), néré (*Parkia biglobosa*), tamarind (*Tamarindus indica*), baobab (*Adansonia digitata*), dry forests and gallery forests in the central belt and the south (Sudanian type region). Shrublands represent the most common type of land use, followed by fallow and agroforestry areas, and wooded savannas.

In Burkina Faso, land is used for urban development, agriculture, grazing, mining, forest management and exploitation. Pastoralism is predominant in the north but occurs throughout. Shrublands represent the most common type of land use, followed by fallow and agroforestry areas, and wooded savannas. In terms of legal status, forest types are divided into reserve estates (25%) and protected areas (75%).

Forest reserve estates (Figure 2) cover approximately 3,900,000 ha, or 14% of the country, including national parks (390,000 ha), nature reserves (2,545,500 ha) and forest reserves (880,000 ha)

Table 1: Forest extent in Burkina Faso (FAO, 2020).

Forest area (1 000 ha)				Net annual change					
1990	2000	2010	2020	1990-2000		2000-2010		2010-2020	
				1000ha/yr	%	1000ha/yr	%	1000ha/yr	%
7717	7217	6717	6 216	50.0	-0.67	50.0	-0.72	50.0	-0.77

Figure 1: Different Land cover types in Burkina Faso in 2013 (source: USGS)

Figure 2: Locations of parks and reserves in Burkina Faso (source: USGS)

In Burkina Faso, the rural sector employs around 80% of the active population according to the World Bank and is responsible for 35% of the Gross National Product (Hermann, et al., 2016). Growing and exporting commercial crops is particularly seen as critical for the macroeconomic stability of Burkina Faso. Cotton for instance, is the main cash crop of the country and has an important impact on government’s revenues. As a result, rural agriculture has been developing unsustainably, pushing for land expansion at a rate of 3% per year (World Bank, 2013). In addition, pastoral activities also compete with forest restoration and maintenance. Livestock products are Burkina Faso’s third most profitable export, nationally for dairy products, internationally for meat and hides. As a result, livestock breeding and especially grazing have called for more forest clearing. Illegal grazing by herd cattle can also occur in classified forests in which regulations only recognize the right to harvest fruits, dead wood, and medicinal plants for subsistence, causing land degradation (Hermann, et al., 2016). Finally, gold mining is the last of the main competing land uses posing threat for the state of the Burkinabe forests. Mining for gold makes up 4% of the national GDP and is in expansion with more artisanal sites being created. The mining sector has disastrous consequences for the environment as it leads to deforestation, soil degradation and GHG emissions from excavation and transportation (Hermann, et al., 2016).

Figure 3: MEDD reports on the evolution of the surface of planted forests (FAO, 2020).

4.2.4 Climate risks & sensitivities

Drought, precipitation, and temperature are strong drivers of tree growth and /or mortality in tropical dry forests (Siym, 2020) like in Burkina Faso. Also, forests in Burkina Faso are particularly subject to bushfires. Bushfires occur with very dry herbaceous vegetation and are more common with the increased temperatures and droughts brought with climate change. The analysis of the situation in Burkina confirms that forest and woodland resources are vulnerable to a range of environmental factors including the impact (direct or indirect) of climate variability and change, the pressure from a growing population, the weaknesses and lack of performance of institutions, gaps in the legal and regulatory framework for local forest management as well as a range of social and economic factors.

Direct drivers of deforestation and forest degradation include among others the following: Livestock activities: cattle, goat and sheep husbandry; Agricultural expansion: mostly cotton production and food production; Overharvesting of Firewood due to increasing demand; Overharvesting of Non-timber forest products; Bush fires; and Gold mining. Proximate drivers includes the following: Economic and Demographic factors (growth in impoverished rural populations who depend on forestry products for survival), Land management (delays in implementing land tenure reforms, insufficient tools for sustainable land use planning and management, insufficient enforcement), Technical capacities and Knowledge (lack of capitalizing on good forestry practices, weak control, lack of resource knowledge), Overall capacity weakness of stakeholders (at decentralized and centralized level), Governance (difficulties in enforcing laws and regulations relating to the forestry sector).

Reforestation, afforestation and forest classification are tools to strengthen the resilience of ecosystems and population to climate change by offering protection against landslides and erosion, re-establishing ecosystem functions as well as restoring biodiversity. Most commitments and forest restoration programs have included plans to reduce uncontrolled fires.

4.2.5 Economic implications

In Burkina Faso, the exploitation of forests for non-timber products plays a major role in the alleviation of rural poverty. Forest-based livelihood activities are concentrated in the Sudanian-type ecozones. These include the production of fuelwood and charcoal, the collection and trade of NTFPs such as shea (*Vitellaria paradoxa*), néré (*Parkia biglobosa*), baobab (*Adansonia digitata*) and gum Arabic (*Acacia laeta*, *Acacia senegal*). The extent of fuelwood collection and charcoal production in a given area depends on tree density and population. Higher population densities and higher tree densities both seem to favor increased fuelwood production. Maintaining healthy forested areas is a way to strengthen rural income and GDP development. In terms of implementation costs of the LMT, the investment needed for the creation of 900 000 ha of forest conservation space in the INDC adaptation scenario was estimated at 504,000,000 USD in total (60 USD per beneficiary). The development of 450,000 ha of classified forests is an extra 252,000,000 USD in investment with a ROI of 109% for the national economy by 2030, making it a profitable intervention (see Table).

Table 2: Burkina Faso INDC adaptation actions on reforestation, afforestation and forest classification and estimated cost and effect by 2030 (Burkina Faso, 2015).

INDC adaptation projects	Investment cost [USD]	Tons of CO ₂ saved / year	Cost [USD]/ tons of CO ₂ equ. /ha/year	ROI [%]
Creation of 900 000 ha of forest conservation space	504,000,000	9,360,000	5.98291e ⁻⁵	-
450,000 ha of classified forests	252,000,000	4,680,000	0.000119658	109

4.2.6 Co-benefits and trade-offs

On the environmental side, co-benefits would be related with soil fertility management, erosion control, watershed protection and biological diversity (FIP, 2012). On the economic side, co-benefices are related with employment, revenue increase for the local populations, and boosting the broader local and regional development. On the social side, FIP activities would have a positive impact on gender equity as it will contribute to improving the social and economic status of women: Initiatives should result in time savings from activities, such as fuel wood collection (freeing up time for other tasks, including children’s education) and in revenue generation. The FIP would also have a positive impact on agricultural productivity through providing support to agroforestry, reforestation and the protection of forested areas (FIP, 2012).

The LMT has the main purpose of enhancing carbon stocks in trees however, forests in Burkina Faso also holds direct and indirect economic benefits as well as non-economic ones. The Burkinabe economy relies indeed heavily on forest-based activities (e.g., timber and charcoal sales) but also on the food (e.g., fruits) and medicinal products (e.g., *Vitellaria paradoxa* used for skin diseases and typhoid fever) offered by forests and woodlands. Other important environmental services of forests are biodiversity safety (e.g., pollination) and watershed protection. On the social level, larger forest cover also means higher income for women in rural villages whose responsibilities lies with the exploitation of non-timber products.

As a trade-off, plantations if they are commercial, are usually made of a monoculture. This provides fast and clear economic return and allows to provide biomass fuel without pressuring existing forests. However, the biodiversity is much lower than in natural or regenerated forests (Belem, et al., 2017).

4.2.7 Risks associated with scaling up

The main barrier to the scaling up of the LMT is the lack of interest of the local villagers to maintain and protect collective plantations. Reforestation, afforestation and classification practices are based on top-down approaches and often applied on land that is state owned. The lack of ownership coupled with traditions have brought project failures on the long-term in spite of high financial investments (Langewiesche, 2004). Securing land tenure is necessary to provide long-term benefits to holders and thus incentives to conserve forests. Carbon project should primarily focus on poverty reduction and local development to avoid getting disconnected from the people concerns.

When scaling up to other countries, it should be taken into consideration that while in some country deforestation is mostly caused by the international market, most of the forest degradation in Burkina Faso is linked to local drivers and poverty (FIP, 2012).

4.2.8 Research gaps

There are currently no monitoring procedure of the impacts of degradation and restoration efforts at national level. Data on deforestation rate vary from one source to another and reports on the LMT implementation are inconsistent. For example, based on the FAO data, the annual deforestation rate would be about 75,000 ha/year (from 7.72 million ha to 6.22 million ha over 20 years). However, the government estimates the deforestation rate at 107,626 ha/year – almost double the FAO's estimate. This large discrepancy is an indication of the paucity of forest statistics in Burkina Faso and the difficulty to precisely define the forested land since there is a continuum between forest, wooded savannah and grassy savannah. The deforestation rates for Burkina Faso quoted in the literature are therefore numerous and they vary (Westholm and Kokko, 2011), including estimates of 15,000 ha/year, 65,000 ha/year, 80,000 ha/year, 105,000 ha/year, and 107,626 ha/year.

4.3 Sustainable land management practices on forest land (e.g., Assisted Natural Regeneration)

4.3.1 Introduction

FAO defines the Assisted Natural Regeneration (ARN) as “a biological process that can be assisted and managed to increase forest cover and achieve the recovery of the native ecosystem or some of its functions”. The aim is the recovery of forest ecosystem, structure and biodiversity using natural techniques. The ARN consists of a set of interventions that accelerate the natural process of tree growth by preventing disruptions from bushfire, animal grazing, human activity (e.g., wood harvest) and competition with other plant types (e.g., weeds). ARN has the advantages of being simple, cheap and providing diverse and well-adapted tree species. (FAO, 2019).

4.3.2 Policy context

Burkina Faso has demonstrated significant commitment to various international treaties and conventions. Indeed, the country has ratified several international and regional agreements that reaffirm: (i) their awareness of the important cultural, regulating, and provisioning as well as supporting functions that the forest ecosystem plays in the lives of many people; and (ii) that these resources are under significant pressure. However, the forest management at the local level has evolved over many generations. Community and participatory forest management traditions started many decades ago. Initially, farmers were excluded from the forest management process with the state having the sole authority to make decisions over forest resources. Farmers were eventually incorporated into the management process as a means of drawing on their now considered valuable local knowledge. The management of forest resources at the community level in its different forms has become widespread. There are many other examples of interventions, projects, programs, international organizations and institutions that have adopted similar community or participatory approaches to forestry. Burkina Faso has a great deal of experience in this area, especially in relation to rural forestry, participatory development of natural forests and agroforestry.

Local authorities have the right to decide the most effective method of managing their environmental resources based on local development plans. However, in practice, this transfer of authority, and the necessary financial resources (as pledged in the national legislation), has not yet taken place in Burkina Faso. Instead, the allocation of resources often operates through mechanisms such as tax collection from the exploitation of environmental resources, budget allocation from the state, or through joint and participatory management actions. Indeed, the law allows local authorities to create taxes that increase their income, as the financial resources of local authorities consist of their own revenues, budget allocations from the state and any other contributions (Law No. 055-2004/AN).

ARN is being implemented by farmers, land owners in rural areas. The implementation is often led by NGOs (e.g., newTree, Tiipaalga). Funding is primarily provided through international projects such as the Forest Investment Program (FIP). Half of the restoration initiatives have sourced at least part of their planting materials from the National Tree Seed Center which is a government-run seed conservation and production research center that offers a large range of native species and ensures that collection practices follow best standards.

4.3.3 Current land use and potential land-use competition

NGOs have played an important role in bringing awareness and sensibilisation of rural populations on this LMT in early 2000. In particular, the Swiss NGO newTree and its partner Tiipaalga introduced the ARN to Center and North Burkina Faso in 2003. Since then, the project allowed the creation of 351 ARN zones of around 3 ha each, equalling a total surface of 981 ha and the growth of 800,000 trees. Results of the project are regularly monitored through inventories of biomass and biodiversity. The main competition for ARN is agricultural land use and commercial forestry plantations that provide fast and higher returns than ARN zones.

4.3.4 Climate risks & sensitivities

The dry forests of Burkina Faso are negatively affected by rising temperatures, droughts, extreme rain events and bushfires. ARN spaces allow growing forests to be more resilient to the effects of climate, particularly by protecting them against bushfires.

4.3.5 Economic implications

ARN is cheaper than reforesting/afforesting practices (approximately half of the investment) that require extra costs for seed collection, nursery, planting and irrigating. Labour is the main cost associated with the implementation, see average ARN establishment and maintenance costs in Table . However, when fencing is applied, these financial gains are reduced (Shono, Chazdon, Bodin, Wilson, & Durst, 2020). According to the research of Belem et al. (2017) on the outcomes of the newTree approach in Burkina Faso, 20% of the yearly gross profit of the farmers come from the natural resources of the ARN. Moreover, they uncovered that 70% of the natural products of the ARN were self-consumed. They concluded that ARN played an important role in poverty alleviation in the country.

Table 3: Costs of ARN implementation based on literature review and available data from Americas, Asia and Africa (Shono, Chazdon, Bodin, Wilson, & Durst, 2020).

Cost category	Direct cost [USD]
Establishment cost / ha, year 1	20-579 (average: 257)
Annual maintenance and monitoring cost / ha, year 1-5	31-213
Annual maintenance and monitoring cost / ha, year 5-15	14-17

4.3.6 Co-benefits and trade-offs

Human-induced disturbances (fires, livestock grazing, unsustainable harvesting) are among the risks. The area should not be suitable for land uses that are economically more attractive.

On the long term, co-benefits of the LMT include restoration of soil fertility, increased availability of timber as well as non-timber forest products. Animal (e.g., pollinators) and vegetation biodiversity is also increased allowing the local populations to benefit from diverse indigenous plants and fruits for food and medicinal purposes (Belem, et al., 2017). Other environmental benefits include soil erosion control and improved water quality.

In addition, ARN is less labour-intensive, makes use of local knowledge and is a bottom-up approach that villagers usually apply on their own land. The species selected are these that best fit villagers' needs. This facilitates acceptance and sustainability of the technique.

As a trade-off, ARN zones have lower commercial values than tree plantations regarding timber and the growth is slower (Belem, et al., 2017).

4.3.7 Risks associated with scaling up

According to the FAO, the following factors are critical for the successful completion of an ARN project: clear land tenure, supportive policies, benefits accruing to local stakeholders, and technical expertise.

These apply to reforestation/afforestation projects as well. Moreover, more awareness and attention need to be brought to ARN which is currently still poorly understood, especially among policy makers who usually overlook it and favour tree planting.

As with the other LMTs, the lack of monitoring and mapping is the main research gap. Moreover, ARN fields are usually small and randomly localized and are for this reason challenging to spot. Using satellite imagery, ARN zones are easily confused with other types of tree-based land use which make their identification difficult. Hence, a more advanced monitoring technologies are required.

4.4 Reduced deforestation by promoting improved cook stoves and biodigesters

4.4.1 Introduction

The energy sector in Burkina Faso heavily relies on the use of fuelwood, charcoal and crop residues. The total primary energy supply is made up 80.5% biomass energy (Ruben, 2013). In addition to household's personal use for cooking and lighting, fuelwood contributes to Government's revenues (forest and community taxes related with fuelwood sales) and generates employment. This creates considerable pressure on timber resources and can trigger respiratory diseases to the population inhaling the biomass fuels. Improved Cooking Stoves (ICS) are a low-cost technology that has been promoted in Burkina Faso for more than a decade. It aims at improving biomass combustion efficiency and therefore save fuelwood (around 20-30%) while reducing indoor air pollution and greenhouse gas emissions. Biodigesters are on the other hand a clean technology that is more complex and more expensive. A biodigester converts organic waste into biogas (mixture of several gases, mainly consisting of methane) and fertilizer.

4.4.2 Policy context

The minister of Energy has exposed his vision on the national energy strategy: "By 2023, Burkina's energy sector, relying on endogenous resources and regional cooperation, ensures sustainable access to modern energy services and reinforces its driving role on sustainable development". Among the existing programs that have worked at promoting ICS and biodigesters, we can name:

- **The Foyers Améliorés au Burkina Faso (FAFASO)**
The FAFASO is an ICS project established in 2005 by the Dutch Government and the Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ). The project's objective is to form a sustainable market for domestic and industrial ICS by providing training to whitesmith to produce ICS locally and through promotion campaigns.
- **The National Biodigesters Program (PNB-BF)**
The PNB-BF dates back from 2010 and has since then facilitated the installation of biodigesters in households. In 2018, the program was considered to have saved 311 ha of forest and led to the sequestration of 17500 tons of CO₂ per year.

ICS and biodigesters are being used domestically by rural and urban populations but also industrially (e.g., dolo beer brewers). International funds are available such as ODA funding from the Dutch Government for PNB-BF. The Carbon Initiative for Development (CiDev) will purchase carbon credits generated by the biodigesters installed during the program’s development and these funds will help the project to continue:

- disseminating information on the benefits of biodigesters for clean cooking and agricultural improvement,
- training masons on biodigester construction and conducting quality control measures. (<https://ci-dev.org/programs/west-africa-biodigesters>).

4.4.3 Current land use and potential land-use competition

Before 2005, ICS were poorly exploited in Burkina Faso. A significant adoption of the technology started with the FAFASO project with 107,000 stoves being sold for domestic use between 2005 and 2011 (Ruben, 2013). By 2030, the country’s ambition is to allow the dissemination of another 540,000 ICS (Burkina Faso, 2015). Trends in biodigester use in Burkina Faso have also been increasing in the last decade. Only one biodigester was reported in 2009 against 4013 in 2014, with another 18200 biodigesters distributed between 2014 and 2018 (Burkina Faso, Ministère de l’Energie , 2018). In its national strategy document, Burkina Faso plans for an additional 40 000 biodigesters to be installed in households by 2022. As part of the INDC adaptation plan, Burkina Faso pledges to distribute a total of 75,000 biodigesters by 2030. Biogas adoption has been related to the availability of timber supply. In areas where fuelwood is abundant, biodigester appear less attractive to the local communities.

4.4.4 Climate risks & sensitivities

The climate sensitivity of the LMT is negligible or non-existent.

4.4.5 Economic implications

The LMT has shown to be cost-effective and has direct and indirect financial and economic benefits. For instance, Burkina Faso has estimated in its INDC document that the plan to install ICS in 540,000 households by 2030 will have a ROI of 166% for the national economy and the plan of distributing 75,000 biodigesters will have a ROI of 104%. Indirectly, biodigesters are also economically advantageous through the application of compost allowing smart agriculture, see Table . Similarly, the IOB evaluation of the FAFASO project concluded that buying and using an ICS was profitable for households with the investment being amortised within 2.5 to 4 months thanks to firewood savings (1.42 euros saved monthly).

Table 4: Burkina Faso INDC adaptation actions on the dissemination of ICS and biodigester technology and estimated cost and effect by 2030 (Burkina Faso, 2015).

INDC adaptation projects	Investment cost [USD]	Tons of CO ₂ saved / year	Cost [USD]/ tons of CO ₂ equ. /ha/year	ROI [%]
540,000 ICS	12,096,000	610,200	-	166

75,000 biodigesters for household	136,500,000	300,000	-	104
Compost from the biodigesters is used to fertilise 750,000 ha of cultivable land	52,500,000	1,500,000	4.66667e ⁻⁵	450

The direct economic implication for ICS and biodigester users is related to financial savings (firewood, kerosene, time savings). Looking at the broader picture, avoiding deforestation and land degradation by limiting the overharvesting of firewood allows to sustain the livelihood of the rural populations depending on non-timber forests products for their subsistence and for sale. Women being the main actors in the exploitation of non-timber forest products, this will enable them to maintain and strengthen their income.

4.4.6 Co-benefits and trade-offs

Environmentally speaking, ICS and biodigesters have the advantages of reducing the need to harvest timber and therefore avoid deforestation. In addition to that, biodigesters have several other benefits. A bioproduct of the biodigesters is a digestate which can be used as organic fertilizer and improve soil quality and crop productivity. A study made by the World Bank in Burkina Faso has shown that farmers applying the digestate on their crops increased their maize yield from 0.89 tons/ha to 2.54 tons/ha, their rice yield from 0.78 tons/ha to 4.00 tons/ha, and sorghum yield from 0.81 tons/ha to 1.44 tons/ha (Freeman & Seppala, 2019). Other environmental co-benefits are the decrease in GHG emissions from the incomplete combustion of biomass and from manure (methane).

Biodigesters also holds health benefits and especially women’s health as women are usually the ones to cook. Bio-digesters adopters have reported fewer respiratory and eye problems that non-adopters in several countries of Africa. On the social aspects, both ICS and biodigesters reduce the burden of wood collection for women

An increasingly dry climate, water shortages, and significant soil degradation are core challenges for the agriculture sector. Water shortage is a main barrier for the functionality of biodigesters and thus to their adoption. However, a dry climate and water availability problems do not necessarily lead to a rejection of biodigesters. PNB-BF experience shows that the population in the country’s dry regions (Sahel zone) were among the best clients of the program; due to the digestate, soil water sequestration capacity is improved, leading to higher crop yields (World Bank, 2019).

4.4.7 Risks associated with scaling up

There a several major barriers to the scaling up of this LMT. For the biodigesters, the main ones are the high investment cost of the installation and lack of technical skills required to construct and maintain the machine. Large scale implementation requires as well to have enough supplies of water and feedstock. A minimum of 3-4 cows is required if cow dung is used for instance, which is a limitation for smallholders. Consequently, biodigesters are said to be used in farms with higher income, socio-economic status and educational level. In overall, acceptability of the technology is a main barrier.

Projects that target the promotion and communication around the ICS and biodigesters are critical for their dissemination.

4.4.8 Research gaps

There is no identified research gap associated with this LMT.

4.5 Sustainable land management practices on agricultural land

4.5.1 Introduction

Over-farming, over-grazing and the increasing pressures of climate change are responsible for an important land degradation in the country. In the last decades, smallholders in Burkina Faso have implemented a set of sustainable agricultural techniques to effectively apply soil and water conservation techniques (SWC) on desertic and unfertile land:

Stone barriers, zai pits, half moons

Among the most common SWC practices to restore degraded land in Burkina Faso, we can name: zai pits, half-moons and permeable rock contour barriers (Lenhardt, Glennie, Ali, & Morin, 2014). Contour barriers consist of rocks tightly put next to each other around a field in order to trap water and avoid soil erosion during heavy rain events. Zai are planting pits aimed at rehabilitating soil by increasing termite activity, in turn increasing rainfall infiltration. Half-moons are other structures in semi-circular form that aim at retaining run-off for crop production. These practices are low-cost and can be combined into more complex systems.

Figure 5: Photographs of half-moon (left) and Zai (right) in Burkina Faso (Source: mcc.org).

Agroforestry parklands (AFP)

AFP are a widespread and traditional agroforestry practice in Burkina Faso that help restoring degraded land. They are dynamic systems where indigenous trees are planted and grow under protection on cropped/grazed land. The micro-climate created by the trees allow to increase the productivity of crops around/under the trees.

4.5.2 Policy context

Currently, there is no national policies that promotes SWC agricultural practices in Burkina Faso and no subsidies to support it (Neya, et al., 2020). It is however in the country’s INDC ambitions to implement agroforestry and the SWC techniques listed in this document to reach 2030 mitigation and adaptation goals. The Forest Investment Program is a main framework for planning and implementing the necessary activities to reach success.

Farmers are adopting and applying these SWC and agroforestry techniques on their degraded farmland. Burkina Faso receives support from the AfDB and World Bank through the Forest Investment Program (FIP) and the Forest Carbon Partnership Facility (FCPF) to put in place a national REDD+ strategy to address the drivers of deforestation and forest degradation, including security of land tenure and management of agricultural-sylvicultural-pastoral systems.

4.5.3 Current land use and potential land-use competition

The state of land degradation and desertification in the 1970s and 1980s called for urgent restoration efforts. The Government turned to NGOs to propose a set of relevant SWC techniques and several initiatives were implemented with various success, see Table . SWC adoption increased considerably between 1993 and 2006, as seen in Figure 2. Adoption is more useful and widespread in regions where rainfall events are scarce.

Table 5: Most common SWC techniques in Burkina Faso and their implementation (Nyamekye, Thiel, Schönbrodt-Stitt, Zoungrana, & Amekudzi, 2018)

SWC	Year of implementation	Climatic zone
Half-moon	1958	Sahel and Sudan-Sahel
Zai	1980	Part of Sahel and part of Sudan-Sahel
Rock contour barriers	Late 1970s, early 1980s	Sahel, Sudan-Sahel, and Sudan-Guinea
Agroforestry	1970	Sahel, Sudan-Sahel, and Sudan-Guinea

Today, these techniques still play an important role in the Burkinabe Government to boost CO₂ intake and restore land productivity. NDC land-based adaptation plans include fertility restoration and maintenance for 1,575 million ha of degraded land through various SWC techniques by 2030. This includes among others, the establishment of 225,000 ha of zai, 525,000 of zai combined with stone barriers, 675,000 ha of plant covered stone barriers, 650,000 ha of zai combined with stone barriers and ARN, and finally 150,000 ha of half-moons (Burkina Faso, 2015). The suitable agroforestry area has been estimated to be over 10 million ha representing 38% of the country side (IFN 2, 2015).

Farmers do not always have the incentives to adopt these measures and will instead apply more standard cropping techniques that require less efforts and investments. Moreover, it has been widely reported that trees and crops also may compete for resources above ground (light, heat, water) and below ground (nutrients, water). Selection of the right woody (trees and shrubs) and agricultural crop components is important (Bayala, Sanou, Teklehaimanot, Kalinganire, & Ouedraogo, 2014)

Figure 2: Surface of land that adopted SWC techniques per region of Burkina Faso (Nyamekye, Thiel, Schönbrodt-Stitt, Zoungrana, & Amekudzi, 2018).

4.5.4 Climate risks & sensitivities

AGP are vulnerable to drought and extreme temperatures. Heavy rain may destroy SWC measures such as half moons.

4.5.5 Economic implications

Although agroforestry has benefits for climate mitigation, it is not very profitable at the farm level for smallholders. The carbon price generally is not able to compensate farmers' efforts (the trade-offs). Appropriate incentives are needed to enable farmers to adopt it. The carbon price should be at least 4 US\$ per tCO₂ to enable smallholders to adopt and promote agroforestry parklands (Neya, et al., 2020).

Land tenure plays an important role as often farmers are not the real owners of the land, and the absence of long-term ownership affects the adaptation of SWCM. Table 6 below lists the expected cost, profitability and climatic impact of the SWC techniques included in the INDC adaptation plan.

Table 6: Burkina Faso INDC adaptation actions on the dissemination of SWC practices and estimated cost and effect by 2030 (Burkina Faso, 2015).

INDC adaptation projects	Investment cost [USD]	Tons of CO ₂ saved / year	Cost [USD]/ tons of CO ₂ equ. /ha/year	ROI [%]
225,000 ha of zai	94,500,000	666,000	0.00045045	67
525,000 ha of combined zai and stone barriers	367,500,000	1,554,000	0.000182182	45
675,000 ha of plant covered stone barriers	245,700,000	1,998,000	0.001813063	31
150,000 ha of combined stone barriers, zai and ARN	120,750,000	444,000	0.000945946	39
150,000 ha of half-moons (with addition of manure)	63,000,000	444,000	0.00045045	100

4.5.6 Co-benefits and trade-offs

SWC techniques such as rock barriers have positive impacts on topsoil thickness and nutrient holding capacity by avoiding soil erosion by water. This is linked to improved water infiltration with increased in groundwater levels in many villages (Nyamekye, Thiel, Schönbrodt-Stitt, Zoungrana, & Amekudzi, 2018). On top of the climate benefits through rehabilitated land and related decreased pressure on neighbouring forests, SWC techniques have been shown to increase crop yield and therefore have an impact on food security and rural poverty. In the past, rural poverty was reduced by 50% between 1985 and 1996.

Soil and water conservation measures reduce streamflow and erosion which may dry up wells during the dry season. Also, many SWC initiatives focus on the soil rehabilitation of agricultural lands and pay less attention to the spatial dimensions of soil erosion and the conservation of natural vegetation.

4.5.7 Risks associated with scaling up

As the other LMT listed in this document, sustainable land management practices on cropland succeed when land ownership is ensured. The SWC techniques mentioned here are to be promoted in geographic regions facing water scarcity. In regions with ample rainfall, they are less adapted as they can create waterlogging (Nyamekye, Thiel, Schönbrodt-Stitt, Zoungrana, & Amekudzi, 2018).

4.5.8 Research gaps

The current extent of AFP and other SWC techniques in Burkina Faso is not well documented, and neither is their precise evolution through the years. Bayala et al., (2014) stated that there is a need for a more comprehensive analysis of the multiple benefits and services provided by parkland trees.

5. Conclusions

Burkina Faso is landlocked between 9° and 15° N, and 6° W and 3° E. It has a total landmass of 274,000 km² (FAO 2011) and covers three major climatic zones: Sahelian, Sudanian, and Sudanian-Sahelian. The population growth rate is 3.5%, which is considered one of the highest in Africa. Eighty-five percent of the population is rural and dependent on agriculture and livestock. The center and north of the country have low vegetation cover. Both regions have similar levels of rainfall, soil, and vegetation types. The most wooded areas are in the west and center west of the country. Estimates of Burkina Faso's total forest cover vary between sources, many of which use different methods of assessment. However, recent FAO statistics (FAO 2011) reported 5,649,000 ha of forest cover in Burkina Faso, accounting for 21% of the total land area, and 'other wooded lands' accounting for 18%. Shrublands represent the most common type of land use, followed by fallow and agroforestry areas, and wooded savannas.

In Burkina Faso, the land is used for urban development, agriculture, grazing, mining, forest management, and exploitation. Pastoralism is predominant in the north but occurs throughout. Forest-based livelihood activities are concentrated in the Sudanian-type ecozones. The degradation of ecosystems in Burkina Faso has been consistent, often explained by climatic deterioration and increasing demographic pressure on natural resources. Forest loss primarily occurs as a result of uncontrolled bushfires, fuelwood harvest, encroachment into forest areas for agricultural production (i.e. for crops and livestock), and mining expansion.

We conducted stakeholder engagements in the country with a help of a local consultant. Stakeholders included farmers, researchers, NGOs, and representatives from government agencies. These engagements helped us to select the most relevant LMTs in terms of carbon sequestration potential and co-benefits on the local, national, and regional levels. These LMTs are part of the country's commitments for 2030 and mainly aim at planting trees, restoring degraded land, and reducing pressures on forests: 1) Reforestation, afforestation, and forests classification; 2) Sustainable land management practices on forest land with a focus on Assisted Natural Regeneration (ARN); 3) Reduced deforestation by promoting improved cookstoves and biodigesters; and 4) Sustainable land management practices on agricultural land with focus on agroforestry parklands and soil fertility restoration such as stone barriers, Zai pits, half-moons.

Burkina Faso offers a unique opportunity for a triple win of mitigation, adaptation, and poverty alleviation. Enhancing the management of forest resources will strengthen the adaptation potential against adverse impacts from climate change and will create positive spillover effects for poverty alleviation, such as increased forest production and enhanced agricultural productivity (e.g. agroforestry). However, these multiple co-benefits cannot be achieved without a transformational process toward a landscape approach of integrated natural resource management. Such an approach would analyze the best way to conciliate local development with the limitation of the drivers of deforestation and forest/woodland degradation in different ecosystems.

6. References

Clement Nyamekye, M. T.-S.-B. (2018). Soil and Water Conservation in Burkina Faso, West Africa. Sustainability, 3182.

Fair & Sustainable Consulting. (2019). Africa Biogas Partnership Programme – Phase 2 – Evaluation - Final report.

FAO, Food and Agriculture Organization. 2011. State of the World's Forests 2011. Rome: FAO.

Faye, A., Lejeune, Q., Sylla, M., Neya, O., Theokritoff, E., & D'Haen, S. (2019). Key points for West Africa from the IPCC Special Report on Climate Change and Land. Obtido de https://climateanalytics.org/media/resume_ipcc_wa_v7_translation_final.pdf

Soest, H. v., Elzen, M. d., Forsell, N., Esmeijer, K., & Vuuren, D. v. (2018). Global and regional greenhouse gases emissions neutrality. The Hague: PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency.

The Forests Dialogue. (2011). The Forests of Burkina Faso.

Westholm, L. and Kokko, S. 2011. Prospects for REDD+ - Local forest management and climate change mitigation in Burkina Faso, Focali Report No 2011:01, Gothenburg.

World Bank. (2013). Project Appraisal Document on a Proposed Grant in the Amount of US\$16.5 Million from the Strategic Climate Fund To Burkina Faso for a Forest Investment Program - Decentralized Forest and Woodland Management Project.

LANDMARC

**SCALING LAND-BASED MITIGATION
SOLUTIONS IN KENYA**
LAND-BASED MITIGATION NARRATIVES

MORITZ LAUB
STATUS: PUBLIC

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2. Introduction

This report includes a description of a generic nation-wide transition scenario for the implementation of land-based mitigation technologies and practices for the AFOLU sector (agriculture, forestry, and other land use sectors) in Kenya. The report shows the outcomes of a series of research steps that have been conducted in this country since the start of the project in June 2020 until the end of 2022:

First, we performed an initial scoping of key LMTs in the case study country. The scoping assessment resulted in a long list of broad portfolios of different LMTs that could be viable within this case study country.

Second, following this long list, we developed a short-list LMT portfolio containing key LMTs that would be the most relevant for a given country context. All case study country partners were asked to propose and validate their LMT portfolio through complementary (policy) literature review and with the help of stakeholder interviews (i.e. external validation by relevant country experts and stakeholders). Ex-ante no specific guidance of criteria for LMT portfolio short-listing was provided to allow for a free and open co-design process with stakeholders. The scoping process and results are presented in section 3 of this report (step 1 & 2). In Kenya, the long-list was derived based on a combination of reviewing global literature and local policy documents. Short-lists were derived from Kenya climate and agricultural policy documents and discussion with stakeholders from CGIAR centers based in Nairobi, and with stakeholders from the ministry of agriculture and the Kenya Climate Smart Agriculture Project.

Third, after the short-listed LMT portfolios were validated, the LANDMARC case study country partners were asked to develop national scaling narratives or storylines for each LMT included in their portfolio. The assessments focusses on climate risks, vulnerabilities as well as socio-economic co-benefits and trade-offs associated with upscaling LMTs in the case study countries. The analysis is based on a broad range of information/literature sources, and stakeholder consultations conducted. This process is supported through a risk and impact assessment (i.e. an online survey and workshops/seminar/webinars) conducted through the LANDMARC tasks 4.1, 4.2 and 5.2. The most important insights from these risk assessment interviews were also implemented into the present narrative document. The results of this analysis are a set of LMT narratives which are presented in section 4 of this report.

The research steps are designed to enable both an **analysis of the risks and (climate) impacts of scaling up land-based mitigation and negative emission solutions**. As such this report mainly contributes to objectives 2, 3 and 4 of the six LANDMARC key objectives (see Table 1).

Table 1: LANDMARC project objectives.

Project key objectives	
1	Determine the potential and effectiveness of LMTs in GHGs mitigation using Earth Observation (EO)

2	Improve climate resilience of LMT solutions at the local level for large-scale implementation
3	Assess the risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs of scaling up local LMTs nationally
4	Scaling up LMT solutions to the continental and global level to assess effectiveness
5	Improve current methodologies to estimate emissions and removals for LMTs
6	LMT capacity building and develop new tools and services for decision making

While the results shown in this report represent a mostly qualitative storyline describing the context and impact of scaling up LMTs in a country context, they also enables project partners to proceed with the translation of the outcomes in a manner so that they can serve as direct model input.

Furthermore, these national level assessments provide a testing ground and empirical basis for the continental, and global assessment of the realistic scaling potential of land-based mitigation and negative emission solutions implemented in Work Packages 6 and 7 of the LANDMARC project (**Objective 4**).

3. Scoping of land-based mitigation and negative emission solutions

3.1. Overview of potential of LMTs in Kenya

3.1.1. Introduction

Although Kenya considers itself as a low emitter of greenhouse gases (GHG) that contributed historically less than 0.1% of globally released GHG, it is determined to reduce its GHG emissions (Government of Kenya, 2020). Kenya is a developing country with a growing population and industry. It therefore considers its GHG emission reduction goals against a business as usual (BAU) scenario and not against historical emissions. This BAU scenario is based on projections of population and economic growth and estimates an increase of annual emissions from 96 Mt CO₂ equivalent (CO₂e) in 2020 to 143 Mt CO₂e by the year 2030 (Government of Kenya, 2018a). Kenya's government has committed to a "nationally determined contribution" towards fighting climate change, which has a timeframe until the year 2030. In 2015 Kenya initially committed to reduce GHG emissions by about 30% compared to the BAU scenario. This plan has been updated in 2020 to a reduction of 32% compared to BAU, which would mean that emissions stay roughly at the level of 2020. Kenya requests international financial support for 87% of the project costs (Government of Kenya, 2020). Due to its strong dependency on the primary sector, Kenya expects to be severely impacted by climate change. Therefore, many of the policies aim to increase the resilience of the primary sector, while simultaneously reducing or mitigating GHG emissions (Government of Kenya, 2018a). Compared to the EU, GHG emissions of Kenya are very low (about 5% on a per capita base in 2016; World Bank 2021b). Due to much lower emissions and Kenya being a developing country, GHG emissions are less rigorously monitored than for example in EU states and data availability is scarce. This report tries to identify the most promising LMTs from the available data and predictions, but the lower certainty about the data should be kept in mind. Most of the measures which are intended by the Kenyan government are not primarily targeted towards achieving negative emissions, but instead aim for a reduction of Kenya's GHG emissions. Despite Kenya's focus on reducing identified emissions, a few of the proposed measures carry the technical potential of sequestering additional carbon on top of their mitigation potential. Technologies which could be called LMTs are located in the agricultural and forestry sector (Table 2), which both occupy about 10% of land area in Kenya, each.

Table 2: Estimated GHG emissions and GHG reduction potential in Kenya in 2030

Category	Sector	Estimated total emissions (2030)	Technical potential of emission reduction (2030)	Nationally determined contribution - targeted reduction (2030)	Technical potential relative to estimated emissions
		Mt CO ₂ e/y	Mt CO ₂ e/y	Mt CO ₂ e/y	(%)
Emission mitigation or reduction	Electricity generation	41	18.63	9.32	45.4
	Energy demand	10	12.17	6.09	121.7
	Transportation	21	6.92	3.46	33.0
	Industrial processes	6	1.56	0.78	26.0
	Waste management	4	0.78	0.39	19.5
Land management solutions with LMT potential	Agriculture	39	5.53	2.77	14.2
	Forestry	22	40.2	20.1	182.7
	Total	143	85.8	42.9	60

Source: adapted from Government of Kenya (2018b).

Due to a lower population density of about 80 persons/km² of Kenya compared to European countries (about 100 persons/km²) and much lower per capita emissions (about 1.03 vs 6.9t CO₂ equivalents per year; World Bank, 2021b), LMTs could have a considerable potential for GHG mitigation in Kenya. To get an overview of the overall potential of LMTs, a comparison of the net primary production (NPP) of land in relation to total emissions seems feasible. The average annual NPP of land is between 3 and 5 t of carbon assimilated per ha and year (Foley, 1994; Running et al., 2004). With a land area of 58 mln ha, the NPP of Kenya would be in the range of 174 to 290 Mt of carbon per year, equivalent to capturing about 640 to 1060 Mt of CO₂ per year through photosynthesis. Thus, from a first principles theoretical estimation, between 22 and 13% of the achieved NPP would have to be removed from the land and sustainably stored in order to completely offset the yearly emissions of 143 Mt of CO₂e which were projected in the BAU scenario in 2030. Considering that many natural ecosystems are often at or close to a steady state in terms of carbon stocks and that there is also pressure on the land to satisfy other demands for biomass or food, such a high storage may be difficult to achieve. In the following sections, the most promising options are described.

3.1.2. Technologies of the forestry sector

Forestry-based projects established in many African countries carry a huge potential to sequester carbon (Akinnifesi et al., 2010) and the sector is also targeted by the Kenyan government in order to achieve GHG emission reductions. However, with less than 10% of forest cover, Kenya belongs to the countries with the lowest forest cover rates globally (Government of Kenya, 2018b), but this is largely due to the potential natural vegetation of Kenya being bushlands for the most parts (Lillesø et al., 2015). Yet, Kenya has experienced significant deforestation in recent decades. Forest cover was

diminishing fast in the 90s, changing from a coverage of 8.3% in 1990 to 6.2% in 2000, but through changes in forest policies this trend was reversed (Government of Kenya, 2018b). This led to an increase in forest cover to 7.8% in 2016 (World Bank, 2021c), with the declared aim of forest policy to reach 10% of land covered by forest in 2030 (Government of Kenya, 2014). It is stated that part of Kenya's forest cover is degraded and in poor condition without an exact specification of the proportion (Government of Kenya, 2018b). As a result of the historical loss of forest and of many forests being degraded, the Kenyan administration attributes a huge potential for GHG mitigation to forest projects aiming at the reforestation of areas where forest was lost and at the restoration of degraded forests through protection policies. It is estimated that there is a potential for 1.2 million ha (about 2% of Kenya's land area) of additional forests (Government of Kenya, 2018b), which is in line with the declared goal of 10% forest cover. As can be seen from the estimated technical potentials (Table 2), the forestry sector is the main land-based sector which has an attributed technical potential to achieving net negative emissions. As Kenya has committed to realize half of this technical potential by 2030 (Government of Kenya, 2018b), this would be enough to offset most of the emissions from the forestry sector, but it would not be enough to achieve negative emissions from the forestry sector.

The Government of Kenya (2018b) has stated that the cost for their reforestation programmes until 2030 would amount to 2.7 to 4.1 billion US \$ and the programmes are estimated to decrease CO₂ emissions by 10.4 Mt CO₂ per year in 2022, growing to a yearly decrease in CO₂ emissions of 20.8 Mt CO₂ per year in 2030. Under the assumption of a linear increase of these CO₂ emission offsets between 2022 and 2030, a total of 140 Mt of CO₂ emission would be offset by 2030, which would roughly correspond to a cost of 19 to 29 US \$ per ton of CO₂. This could be considered rather cheap compared to offset costs in other countries (e.g. carbon taxes in Europe range between 10 and 119 US \$ per ton of CO₂ and are expected to rise in the future; World bank, 2020)

The forest management measures in Kenya have been grouped into two categories: restoration of degraded forests and reforestation, both of which have the goal of reaching an intact forest cover. They both are targeted to areas that historically were covered by forest and are thus not termed afforestation. The difference in categorization depends on the action that needs to be taken in order to achieve a tree cover dense enough to meet the definition of forest. The measures of forest management also include management of mangrove ecosystems (often referred to as «blue carbon»), which are counted toward the forestry sector (Government of Kenya, 2018b).

Restoration of degraded forests

The restoration of degraded forests is considered to bear the largest potential (80% of the area). In contrast to reforestation, restoration of forests is defined as a natural regeneration of land where degraded forests can achieve a full tree cover by themselves (Government of Kenya, 2018b). It appears likely that due to pressure on land, this measure requires appropriate laws for the protection of the appointed areas, as well as sufficient law enforcement. A better management of agricultural areas leading to higher yields could indirectly contribute towards restoration of forests, as higher yields of agricultural lands would help to achieve food security and thus reduce the pressure on land.

Reforestation

Reforestation, in contrast to restoration of forests, requires the active planting of new trees on areas that cannot recover to become forests by themselves in a reasonable amount of time. It is considered that this is necessary on 20% of the appointed land area (Government of Kenya, 2018b). For reforestation, both native species and exotic species may be used, even commercial tree plantations are listed amongst the mitigation actions (Government of Kenya, 2018b) and to the understanding of the authors, they will also be counted towards reforestation.

3.1.3. Agricultural management practices

According to the latest data from 2016, about 10% of the land area in Kenya is arable cropland (World Bank, 2021a), which corresponds to a total area of 5.8 mln ha. The expected agricultural GHG emissions of 39 Mt CO₂e per year in 2030, would thus correspond to an emission of about 7 t CO₂e per ha and year, or 1.9 t CO₂-carbon per ha and year, which would have to be avoided to reach net zero emissions in the agricultural sector. Almost half of the emissions are attributed to originate from agricultural soils, whereas the other half comes from livestock enteric fermentation, the latter not being considered for GHG emission reductions (Government of Kenya, 2018b), likely due to food security issues. Due to a growing population and demand for agricultural production, a significant reduction of the emission rates by agriculture will likely not be achieved by agricultural management practices alone, but agroforestry could help to increase the amount of carbon sequestration in Kenya.

Agroforestry

Of all agricultural practices, agroforestry is seen as the technology with the largest potential in Kenya. The technical emission reduction potential estimated was estimated to be about 4 Mt CO₂e per year in 2030, if 281,000 hectares (corresponding to roughly 5% of arable land) would be converted to agroforestry systems with at least 10% of tree cover (Government of Kenya, 2018b). However, there is no data on how much of Kenya's arable land is already under agroforestry (Government of Kenya, 2018b) and how much tree cover these systems usually have. Further information on this baseline adoption rates as well as on the adoption barriers, such as enhanced labour requirements, would be crucial. Apart from sequestering carbon, agroforestry systems can enhance the resilience of agroecosystems by enhancing water use efficiency (Government of Kenya, 2017) or by providing additional nutrients (e.g. by uptake from deeper soil layers or by nitrogen fixation). Thus, agroforestry systems bear the potential to enhance crop yields, for example if leguminous trees (e.g. *Calliandra calothyrsus*) would be used, as they can provide additional nutrients to marginal soils (Chivenge et al., 2009).

Conservation agriculture

Other practices that are attributed to bear the potential of reducing GHG emissions in 2030 by about 1Mt CO₂e annually, are summarized as the adoption of conservation agriculture. This term includes management practices such as conservation tillage, legume planting, incorporating crop residues,

alongside efficient fertilizer use (Government of Kenya, 2018b). If successful in sequestering carbon, these methods naturally increase the amount in soil organic matter, which has the co-benefit of increasing the soil fertility, water holding capacity and nutrient storage capacity. It was shown that conservation agriculture and/or integrated soil fertility management practices in Kenya, such as using farmyard manure, no tillage and leaving crop residues in the field may reduce initial emissions from agriculture (in the range of 0.1 to 0.9 t carbon per ha and year) by up to half, while a net sequestration of carbon could not be achieved (Sommer et al., 2018). A further suggested method to reduce emissions from agriculture is the reduction of fire use in field management (Government of Kenya, 2018b), with the potential of mitigating 0.29 Mt of CO₂e per year in 2030.

3.2. Determining the LMT scope for national level simulation modelling

In this section we discuss which set of LMTs we will study in detail in Kenya. Table 2 summarises the main LMTs and indicates which ones are included in the short-list of the LMT portfolio for Kenya. The main rationales for including the various LMTs in the national level scaling simulation assessment are presented below.

Table 3: Long-listing of relevant land based LMTs

LMT	Specification	Included in national LANDMARC LMT portfolio
BECCS	-	N
Biochar	-	N
Wetlands	Peat soil management	N
Cropland	Conservation tillage	Y
	Integrated soil fertility management (e.g. use of harvest residues, crop rotation, mulching, fertilizer)	Y
	Agroforestry	Y
	Grassland management	N
Forest land	Avoided deforestation	Y
	Afforestation/ reforestation	Y

Conservation tillage

Conservation tillage has been explicitly stated by the Government of Kenya (2018b) as a measure to reduce GHG emissions from agriculture. It has also been found in literature that zero-tillage combined with residue retention can reduce carbon losses from soils in Kenya (Sommer et al., 2018).

Integrated soil fertility management

Integrated soil fertility management is a practice that combines the use of organic manures and chemical fertilizer with good management practices (Yadav and Soni, 2019). It is similar to the kind of management practices which are summarized in the Kenyan official documents as “conservation agriculture” (Government of Kenya, 2018b). It is the goal of such management practices to make best use of several options to make agricultural systems more resilient, increase soil carbon storage and yields. They include a use of available farmyard manure and locally available organic residues, integrating legumes into the crop rotations, incorporating crop residues into the soil, alongside an efficient use of chemical fertilizer where available. Many of the measures are included in the climate smart agriculture strategy (Government of Kenya, 2017).

Agroforestry

The use of agroforestry has been identified as the measure with the highest potential to mitigate GHG emissions in Kenya, but the utility of agroforestry is not limited to GHG. A systematic review of agroforestry system studies across whole sub-Saharan Africa, showed that, in the majority of cases, there was an increase in yield (68%), a better microclimate (61%), enhanced nutrient cycling (60%) and soil fertility (53%) while negative effects, such as lower yields, higher water requirements, or worse microclimatic conditions, were observed only on average in 15% of cases (Kuyah et al., 2016). As it was proposed to increase the amount of agroforestry systems in Kenya by 200,000 ha (Government of Kenya, 2018b), it seems feasible to test the GHG mitigation potential in Kenya. Also, the mentioned benefits could help to make agronomic systems more resilient. The use of agroforestry in Kenya should further be facilitated by the World Agroforestry centre, which has its headquarter located in Nairobi, Kenya.

Afforestation/ reforestation

The Kenyan government has set a focus on afforestation and forest remediation as a cost-effective option for GHG emission mitigation at the national scale (Government of Kenya, 2018b). As stated in detail before, forest-based measures are the only LMTs that have been judged to carry the technical potential of leading to negative emissions. Thus, the strong focus and clear commitment of the Kenyan government make the inclusion of forest-based measurements an imperative.

Despite a possible potential in the future, some of the LMTs seem not yet ready to be applied at large scale in Kenya within the coming decades. Thus, they are excluded from the national simulations. The reasons to exclude these other LMTs from the national analysis are the following:

BECCS

No mentioning of any use of BECCS in Kenya was found in the screened documents.

Biochar

The use of biochar as a potential mitigation measure was not found in the screened documents of the Kenyan government. Yet, initial trials show that biochar use in Kenya may have potential as a soil amendment. It was shown that the addition of biochar facilitated the storage of carbon in the soil: including losses by erosion and vertical translocation, 60% of biochar was still present after one decade while simultaneously crop yields were increased by about 1.2 t per ha for maize and 0.4 t for soybean (Kätterer et al., 2019). However, judging from biochar prices globally, the biochar production in Kenya at larger scales may be too expensive and the technological requirement too high for it being attractive in Kenya at this time. Also, no data could be found on the economic adoption feasibility and willingness at household level. The use of biochar in Kenya is thus excluded in LANDMARC, but there could be potential in the future.

Peatland management

Peatland management was not mentioned in any of the screened documents, nor could the percentage of land covered by peatlands be found. Kenya's interest in peatland management is therefore considered to be low and hence not included in the short list.

Grassland management

Grassland management options were not specified in any of the screened official documents. However, the high share of grassland in Kenya (42%; Kamoni et al., 2007) could make it interesting to use mitigation options connected to grassland managements. For example, a high potential of East African grasslands on a per area base, between 0.1 to 3.1 t of carbon sequestration per ha and year, was found by Tessema et al. (2019) within their systematic review. However, as there is no stated intent to include grassland management in Kenyan GHG mitigation policy, it is at the moment not included in the list of considered options.

3.3. Discussion on short-listing LMTs

3.3.1. *Land use change dynamics*

The Kenyan plan to increase forest cover by up to 2% of the land area, reaching a forest cover of 10%, is quite ambitious. Despite the relatively low forest coverage of Kenya there may be difficulties to achieving this amount of forest cover. This could be due to a lack of law enforcement, but ultimately it is driven by the pressure on land, which again depends on the population dynamics and on the productivity of land. The rapid decrease of forest cover in the 1990s by more than 2% is an indication of the high pressure on land and given the increase of population size in Kenya which is estimated to continue until the year 2100 (United Nations, 2019), the pressure will likely remain high. This pressure is exacerbated by the low increase in cropland productivity in Kenya. Crop yields in Kenya have been stagnating within the past decades (Table 4), whereas a dramatic increase was realized in the rest of the world (e.g. up to a doubling of yields most regions from 1980 to 2010, excluding Africa). Apart from increased climate vulnerability and pest pressure, the stagnating yields in Kenya are mostly due to insufficient nutrient input, thus agriculture mainly depends on nutrient mining (Vanlauwe et al., 2011)

on highly weathered soils. With a growing population leading to a higher demand for agricultural goods, increasing the yields of Kenyan agriculture will not only be important to achieve climate resilience of agricultural systems, but also to reduce the pressure on land.

Sustainable use of forest products

An issue that has not been addressed in the screened government reports but may be crucial for longer timescales, is how the newly established forests are managed after 2030. Considering the relatively short time horizon of only 9 years until 2030, the mitigation of GHG by forest restoration and reforestation until then may be realistic: newly planted trees and recovering forests may not yet be intensively used. However, in the longer term, it is likely that there will be pressure to use the forest biomass and how the biomass will be used will be crucial in determining the GHG mitigation potential. For example, an energetic use of forest biomass without any CCS technology would drastically reduce the potential for negative emissions of forests in the long run, as it would release the biomass-stored carbon and which is more half of the carbon stored in forests in soils and biomass combined (Government of Kenya, 2018b). This is a real risk, given that 87% of the rural population still depends on firewood for cooking (Government of Kenya, 2018b). In contrast, a sustainable extraction and material use may allow high yearly sequestration rates for a long time and increase the carbon sink potential of Kenyan forests.

Table 4: Agricultural land use in Kenya and yields from 1970 to 2016 (% of total land)

Data	1970	1990	2000	2010	2016
Forest share (%)	n.d.	8.3	6.25	7.4	7.8
Agricultural land share (%)	44	47	46.9	48	48.5
Arable land share (%)	6	8.8	8.6	9.7	10.2
Non-arable agricultural land share (%)	38	38.2	38.3	38.3	38.3
Cereal yield (t per ha; 5-year average)	1.25	1.7	1.44	1.56	1.57

Source: World Bank 2021; n.d. = no data.

3.3.2. Land management dynamics

While land management options in Kenya promise the double benefit of reducing GHG emissions and increasing soil fertility, an analysis of adoption barriers seems to be crucial. It is somewhat telling, that there are no official numbers on the actual adoption of agroforestry or conservation agriculture in Kenya (Government of Kenya, 2018b), while the stagnation of cereal yields (Table 4) compared to strong increases in rest of the world shows a strong need to improve the management of land, while simultaneously limiting GHG emissions. The main goal of all climate change mitigation options of the national strategy of Kenya is to achieve food security and make production systems resilient (Government of Kenya, 2018a), but the co-benefit of climate smart agriculture or integrated soil fertility management in reducing GHG emissions is also acknowledged. The need to increase arable land, e.g. from 6% in 1970 to 10% of total land in 2016, (Table 4) could be largely due to the stagnation in yields on a per area base while a higher population needed to be fed. Thus, tackling the yield gap may also be important to assure other measures of GHG reduction, which require land. With only

around 1.5 t ha of cereal yield, the actual yield gap in Kenya may be very high. For example, whereas the actual achievable yield of rainfed maize systems in western Kenya that had a baseline grain yield of 1.7 t per ha, its technical potential was estimated to be 5.4 t per ha, showing a yield gap of 3.7 t per ha (van Ittersum et al., 2013). From the perspective of competition for land, it therefore seems crucial to reduce this yield gap, while simultaneously improving soil fertility.

A key question to resolve is how the adoption of GHG reducing and yield promoting land management techniques can best be achieved, and what barriers exist. It was suggested that characteristics that influence the adoption of climate smart agriculture management practices are partly influenced by the perceived benefits compared to costs (e.g. labour requirement) and partly by access to education about the practices (Ouedraogo et al. 2019). In this regard it may also be important that the poorest farmers seem to be the ones that are least likely to adopt improved management practices (Cavanagh et al., 2017) and may require special extension services. Policies that could facilitate a faster adoption of agroforestry, for example, could be the improved extension services, but also payments to farmers for providing enhanced ecosystem services or for carbon sequestration (Wilson and Lovell, 2016), which could help to cover the initial setup costs of agroforestry systems.

Lack of data on Kenyan soil carbon stocks and their development

Overall, there is a lack of systematic national soil carbon stock assessments in Kenya and thus estimates are only rough and based on models. A modelling study by Kamoni et al. (2007) was assumed that Kenyan soils have lost carbon in the recent decades and will continue to do so (Table 5). However, real measurement data of Kenyan soil carbon stocks were not found. On the other hand, new technologies which might allow for a better estimation of soil carbon stocks in Kenya, at a relatively low price compared to classical soil surveys, were emerging recently. For example, new low-cost portable measurement devices which rely on spectroscopy show potential for a better soil carbon stocks monitoring (Segnini et al, 2019). The data obtained by this could be combined with satellite imagery to achieve monitoring of soil carbon stocks together with land use monitoring in the future.

Table 5: Predicted levels and losses of organic matter in the topsoil of Kenya

Carbon stocks (Mt carbon)	1990	2000	2030
Century	1428	1416	1311
RothC	1611	1522	1308
IPCC	2022	2003	1975
Mean change since 1990 (%)	0.0	-2.4	-9.8

Source: Kamoni et al. (2007)

4. Co-design of LMT narratives

4.1. Introduction

We developed the narratives based on the short-listed LMTs that were selected based on Kenyan policy documents and a first round of stakeholder interviews. The further trajectory of the selected LMTs was then delineated in a two-step process. First, an in-depth literature research was conducted in 2021. The first version of the narratives was written based on this literature review. Second, further one-on-one interviews throughout 2022 were conducted within LANDMARC tasks 4.1, and 5.2 and through a workshop on the upscaling potential on an individual LMT (integrated soil fertility management). The final version of this report was then enriched with key insights gained through the stakeholder interviews, to complete the picture.

All short-listed LMTs for Kenya represent low-tech solutions, that are in alignment with Kenya being in the status of a developing country. As population increase will be a key driver in land-use changes, the LMTs conservation tillage, integrated soil fertility management and agroforestry are all possible on arable land. Additionally, they offer some potential synergies, and could in theory be implemented on the same piece of land. Afforestation, the last LMT was chosen as it is very effective as CO₂ sink and because it is included in Kenyan law to afforest. From the literature reviews and stakeholder engagements, it became clear that an LMT portfolio is needed, because the different land uses are connected. For example, pressure on land, which threatens afforestation, is also related to cropland productivity, which is addressed by the other LMTs. Agroforestry, in that regard is a hybrid, as it integrates agriculture and trees, with potential synergies.

4.2. Conservation tillage

4.2.1. Introduction

While being an effective measure to reduce weed pressure, soil tillage in agricultural fields is disturbing soil structure and soil life, ploughing under soil cover such as plant residues and redistributing soil within the plough layer. From the mechanistic point of view, it has been realized that ploughing amongst other factors increases the turnover of soil aggregates by disrupting them mechanically (Six et al. 1999) which makes intra-aggregate particulate organic carbon available to decomposition and thus is leading to a faster turnover of soil organic carbon (SOC). Thus, conservation tillage aims at either applying tillage practices that less strongly disturb the soil, or at eliminating tillage altogether and applying methods of direct seeding. The advantage of conservation tillage compared to other LMT is that it does not need any additional biomass and that it is relatively simple to implement. While early studies about conservation tillage systems focused mostly on temperate agricultural systems, some more recent studies indicate that the effect of conservation tillage could be more profound in tropical agroecosystems, which is not surprising, given the faster overall turnover of SOC due to higher temperatures. For example, studying several long-term experiments indicated that conservation tillage can reduce losses of SOC compared to standard tillage practices (Sommer et al., 2018). It was also

shown that reduced tillage can slow down nitrogen mineralization, especially when nitrogen rich plant residues are present (Butnan and Vityakon, 2020). Yet, the effect of tillage could be site specific and strongly depending on soil texture. For example, a meta-analysis indicated that conservation tillage lead to increased SOC stocks in only about half of the studies reported (Palm et al., 2014).

4.2.2. *Policy context*

In Kenya reduced tillage is one of the techniques that is promoted under the umbrella term “climate smart agriculture”, a portfolio of strategies aiming at climate change mitigation and simultaneously making systems more resilient against climate change impacts. Increasing the use of reduced tillage systems could have the double benefit of lowering soil erosion, because reduced tillage not only leads to less soil disturbance and therefore better soil structure but also leaves mulching biomass on the surface, decreasing the impact of heavy rains. Therefore, it is one of the government-promoted land management techniques and the application of reduced tillage has been explicitly stated by the government in the Kenya climate smart agriculture strategy as tool to mitigate climate change within their official communication to the UN (Government of Kenya, 2015). As tillage is a standard agricultural practice, reduced tillage can in theory be applied by all farmers cultivating arable land. However, not all cropping systems may be suitable in the same way. A potential side effect in reduced and especially in no-till systems is an increased weed pressure in many cases. The control of such an increased weed pressure might need to be counteracted by the application of herbicides (Palm et al., 2014), so the feasibility of no-till in Kenya could be limited to farmers who have access to pesticides and the capital to invest in this. On the other hand, reduced tillage with shallower ploughing depths may be feasible for a larger share of farmers but could still come at a higher labour requirement for weeding. As it is part of climate smart agricultural practices, the extension of reduced tillage could benefit from the international and national funds which are directed at climate smart agriculture implementation. One of the largest projects dedicated to this is the Kenya Climate Smart Agriculture Project, which is internationally financed with 280 mln US \$ to by the world bank to be spent until 2023 ([Development Projects : Kenya Climate Smart Agriculture Project - P154784 \(worldbank.org\)](https://www.worldbank.org/en/projects-operations/development-projects/kenya-climate-smart-agriculture-project-p154784)).

4.2.3. *Current land use and potential land-use competition*

While there is no clear data on how much farmers practice reduced tillage, it was estimated that at least 25% of farmers use conventional tillage (Government of Kenya, 2018b). It was assumed that over 10 years it would be possible to change 475.000 ha of agricultural land (roughly 8% of 5.8 mln ha of arable land in Kenya) from conventional to reduced tillage and that this would offset significant amount of CO₂. The potential for national yearly emission reductions resulting from this application of conservation tillage was estimated to 0.65 mln ton CO₂ equivalent in 2020 which should increase to 1.09 mln ton CO₂ equivalent in 2025 and then stay at this level, if the additional 475,000 ha would be transformed to conservation tillage (Government of Kenya, 2018b). It should be mentioned, that it was not clearly identifiable where these numbers exactly originate from and what type of conservation tillage (e.g. reduced or no-till) is exactly intended. As the assumptions made were not explicitly stated,

it seems advisable to interpret the stated goal as statement of intent rather than an exact prognosis on the exact amount of CO₂ sequestered and area to be converted to reduced tillage.

An advantage of conservation tillage is that, while having a rather moderate rate of carbon sequestration (for example, less than 0.2 ton C sequestration ha⁻¹ were reported by Prasad et al., 2016), the practice is not in competition with other land use - it is simply and agricultural practice that can be applied in most agricultural fields. However, a constraint could be increased pest pressure leading to higher input costs, either for pesticides or labour for manual removal. Thus, the scaling up of reduced tillage may be mainly affected by the availability of extension to generate the knowledge on how to manage reduced tillage systems and, depending on which system is used by the availability of pesticides needed to implement, for example no-till systems, or the availability of more labour required to do the weeding.

4.2.4. *Climate risks & sensitivities*

As reduced tillage is a land management practice and not a land use, it is not directly affected by climate risks additional to these that affect agriculture. Yet, reduced tillage may have several beneficial effects that make crop production more resilient to climate extremes. For example, reduced or no-till systems in contrast to conventional tillage maintain a higher soil cover. This reduces the direct impact of raindrops and their potential to detach soil particles, thus reducing the potential for erosion during intense rainfall events. Reduced tillage is also associated with a better soil structure which also increases water infiltration and reduces runoff (Palm et al., 2014). This has a double benefit as it increases plant available water while simultaneously reducing erosion potential. Maintaining a higher soil cover through reduced tillage, e.g. higher levels of mulch, can also reduce evaporation in dry periods, thus reducing the amount of unproductive water loss and maintaining higher levels of soil water. One issue that came through in the interviews was that the carbon sequestration potential of reduced tillage may be reduced by droughts, as this reduces plant growth and thus C inputs.

4.2.5. *Economic implications*

In general, there is a scarcity of implementation cost estimates for reduced tillage systems in the sub-Saharan Africa context. Most studies on reduced tillage systems have so far been conducted in temperate regions, where reduced or no-till is usually associated with a high level of mechanization, so it is difficult to judge the costs of reduced tillage systems in the tropics. According to an interviewed specialist, no-till is very common in Brazil where it is favoured because of lower input costs. However, the high level of mechanization and large parcels of Brazil are not comparable to the very small scale low mechanized Agriculture of Kenya. As most agricultural practice being manually implemented, labour costs vary region specific. As labour cost can be one of the strongest barriers that hinder the adoption of new technologies (Hermans et al., 2020), the effect of reduced tillage on labour costs should be investigated in more detail. Additionally, there are several side effects of reduced tillage systems which may impact the economics. While increased soil moisture during dry spells enhances crop yields (Palm et al., 2014) other studies have reported that reduced tillage led to lower yields due to weed competition (Prasad et al., 2016; Okeyo et al., 2016). Thus, in the case that not enough labour

is available for the additional weeding required in reduced-tillage systems, the feasibility of reduced tillage could be doubted.

4.2.6. *Co-benefits and trade-offs*

While any increase of SOC due to the carbon sequestration by reduced tillage offers a better nutrient storage, actually observed increases of SOC due to reduced tillage are only observed in about half of the cases and are often rather small. There is some evidence that no-till is more effective in storing SOC in the tropics compared to temperate regions (Six et al., 2002; Derpsch et al., 2010). Yet, increased SOC will not be the main benefit of reduced tillage systems. According to one expert, no-till has to be seen as a practice in the centre of conservation agriculture, where it assures minimal soil disturbance to limit the loss of C to the soil. Yet, the C input depends on the cropping system, which also has to be carefully designed. An improved water infiltration and reduced evaporation due to improved soil cover in successful no-till are expected to have a beneficial effect on agricultural production in water limited systems. Reduced erosion due to better soil cover and soil structure will also have positive impacts, for example on regional water quality, as less soil material is introduced into streams and less nutrients end up in rivers. On the other hand, increased pest pressure, because mulch provides a habitat for pathogens, and increases weed pressure (Prasad et al., 2016), making the application of herbicides or increased manual weeding frequencies necessary could reduce agricultural production or increase the cost of inputs. The local conditions could thus be an explanation why there have been mixed outcomes from reduced tillage systems with regard to crop yield (Palm et al., 2014). One study in Kenya found lower grain yields under reduced tillage, which they accounted to insufficient surface cover in reduced tillage treatments (Okeyo et al., 2016). Tillage has been shown speed up the nitrogen cycle reducing soil microbes, which can in the long run significantly reduce soil nitrogen (Xiao et al., 2019), but could also lead to higher amounts of plant available nitrogen in the short term, thus explaining observed lower yields in some reduced tillage studies. A clear tendency was also not found for the effect of reduced tillage on N₂O emissions (Palm et al., 2014), which calls for a better understanding on how reduced tillage in tropical agroecosystems affect turnover cycles of residues in the soil and the synchrony between plant demand and nutrient release as well as nitrification and denitrification processes. This understanding is crucial to estimate trade-offs of reduced tillage systems, as different processes are relevant for GHG at the same time. For example, Bayer et al. (2016) found in their study, that there were increased N₂O emissions under reduced tillage, but considering GHG on a CO₂ equivalent, these were more than offset by the overall enhanced CO₂ sequestration under reduced tillage. This is in alignment with a meta-analysis of Six et al. (2004), finding that increased N₂O emissions in no-till are offset by SOC sequestration after about 10 years, when the system starts to become a sink of GHG. As adopting reduced tillage may increase labour cost due to higher weeding frequency, and food security is a major issue in Kenya, it is very important to apply reduced tillage only to suitable soils. Monitoring negative side effects and making region specific decisions should be the priority over blanket recommendations, and thus reduced tillage should only be applied where its benefits are assured.

4.2.7. *Risks associated with scaling up*

As addressed before, there seems to be a strong site specificity in the efficiency of no-till and reduced tillage leads to achieve CO₂ sequestration. At the same time, N₂O emissions could be increased due to increased soil moisture. As a conclusion, no-till systems are only a sink if they are applied long-term. A massive upscaling could thus lead to the risk of increased emissions in the initial years followed by an abandonment of the method, due to policy changes. This is especially relevant for countries that are still in rapid development, such as Kenya. Hence, in scaling, it should be assured to make the transition sustainable, as transitioning to no-till and then back may lead to higher GHG emissions than not transitioning in the first place. While in some areas and with some soils reduced tillage may be highly suitable, in other areas it may lead to increased N₂O emissions, while in the worst case not increasing SOC and reducing yields. The main two risks associated with scaling up reduced tillage are thus that it will be recommended as a blanket solution, not only targeted to the areas where benefits are assured, and that it will not be maintained long enough. Thus, more research is needed on the feasibility of reduced tillage as a function of soil properties, cropping systems and social context.

4.2.8. *Research gaps*

Main research gaps are connected to the main risks. There is a need to better establish how reduced tillage efficiency depends on local soil properties. Also, as reduced tillage reduces aggregate destruction and thus should slow down SOC turnover in theory, it would be important to know how different residue amounts and qualities interact with reduced tillage. As adding residue increases the amount of particulate organic matter, the fraction that is also negatively affected by tillage (Six et al., 1999), it could be that the combination of residue inputs with reduced tillage is most effective in enhancing soil sequestration. Thus, the combination of reduced tillage practices with for example integrated soil fertility management could be synergetic.

4.3. Integrated soil fertility management

4.3.1. *Introduction*

The term of integrated soil fertility management (ISFM) was defined as a measure to enhance crop yield and maintain soil fertility by the combination of several inputs, such as the use of fertilizer, organic residue inputs and improved germplasm, all adopted to local conditions and aiming at maximizing the agronomic use efficiency of nutrients (Vanlauwe et al., 2010). To be attractive to farmers, the focus of ISFM is on increasing agricultural yields but the main method to do so is focusing on the soil fertility and thus also SOC stocks. Higher crop yields are usually associated with higher amounts of crop residues that can be retained in the field, and together with the recommended application of additional organic residue inputs within ISFM, mostly farmyard manure, this leads to a significant increase in carbon inputs into the soil under ISFM practices. Maintaining and increasing SOC in ISFM is more than a co-benefit, it is the basis for long-term sustainability of yields. Another important point is that ISFM aims to increase yields, thus reducing pressure on other land-uses, such as forests, that are effective C sinks and biodiversity hotspots. The use of ISFM therefore offers the potential to

be a double-win strategy, serving as way to enhance agricultural production and food security while simultaneously offering the potential to be an LMT. In that regard, it is important to note that ISFM in most cases may not be a sink of GHG, as in the highly weathered African soils, SOC is almost always lost when they are cultivated (Sommer et al., 2018). Yet, ISFM has to be compared to the baseline condition of farming without inputs, where SOC is lost at 2-4 times higher rates, simultaneously producing having only half the yields. Thus, ISFM can play a very important role in the Kenyan LMT portfolio, as it reduces agricultural emissions and pressure on land for other LMTs (e.g. agroforestry/afforestation). It has been identified that the success of ISFM to enhance yields and SOC stocks depends strongly on the local soil properties, and soils are often categorized into soils that are either responsive or nonresponsive with regards to ISFM (Vanlauwe et al., 2010). Different strategies exist for these soils and while for responsive soils, improved germplasm and fertilizer may already lead to the desired outcome, nonresponsive soils need increased inputs of organic material to achieve higher yields and SOC sequestration (Vanlauwe et al., 2015). ISFM can be seen as a strategy to practice climate-smart agriculture and sustainable intensification.

4.3.2. *Policy context*

The importance of improved agricultural production techniques that address the currently low productivity of maize systems, improve climate resilience and offering to some extent mitigation of GHG has been recognized in Kenya. Thus, the implementation of climate smart agriculture strategies has been a key strategy and is represented in several important documents such as the official communication of Kenya to the UN regarding actions against climate change (Government of Kenya, 2015). Similar as reduced tillage, ISFM is one of the methods summarized under the umbrella term climate smart agriculture. The goal to increase the use of ISFM in the arable land of Kenya has, for example, been stated by the government in the Kenya climate smart agriculture strategy (Government of Kenya, 2017) as tool to mitigate climate change. The intended actions are in the form of regulatory framework development, capacity building by extension services through NGOs, research institutions and development partners. The ISFM strategy is also included as a strategy in the Kenya National Adaption Plan to climate change (Government of Kenya, 2016). The implementation of ISFM can in theory be done by all farmers that practice agriculture on arable land but it depends on access to the required resources, such as fertilizer, germplasm and organic material, most commonly farmyard manure. As ISFM represents a set of practices in combination, there is no national statistics on how much of it is used. However, local studies make it clear that most farmers possess knowledge on individual parts of ISFM, mainly on mineral fertilizer and manure application, while the use of improved germplasm and the combination of the practices (full ISFM adoption) is less common (Mucheru-Muna et al., 2021). At the moment it is not clear, how commonly established ISFM practices are already at the national level, but once they are established, ISFM practices seem to be beneficial and uptake after extension is high. For example, a study by Mugwe et al. (2009) reported adoption levels of ISFM close to 50% after extension services had been successfully implemented. Many of the ISFM practices are part of the common agricultural practices, but are often applied in isolation, so extension services aiming to promote using all ISFM practices combined could lead to further synergies. For example, a

recent study by Wawire et al. (2021), conducted in Meru and Tharaka Nithi counties, reported that adoption rates of different ISFM practices differed and were about 95% for manure and fertilizer application but only around 80% for the application of available residues. While the mentioned studies are not representative for whole Kenya they at least indicate that some ISFM practice are already commonly established and well received. On the other hand, several barriers that hinder the adoption of ISFM on larger scales were identified. The adoption of ISFM seems to be less pronounced under the poorest farmers, as they lack the investment capital necessary to buy fertilizer and germplasm, and there is often the tendency that ISFM is only applied on fields close to the house of farmers, which accumulate a lot of SOC and nutrients, while fields further away are mined for nutrients (Vanlauwe et al., 2015).

In general, funds that are available for the broader umbrella topic of climate smart agriculture should also be available to ISFM. For example, through the Kenya Climate Smart Agriculture Project, 280 mln US \$ from the World Bank are available to be spent until 2023. Furthermore, within the Kenya climate smart agriculture strategy 25 bln Ksh (about 230 mln US \$ at time of writing) have been attributed to foster the deployment of ISFM in Kenya (Government of Kenya, 2017), but it was not fully clear, if these are the same funds as for the Climate Smart Agriculture Project or additionally available resources.

4.3.3. Current land use and potential land-use competition

As discussed above, there is no exact knowledge on the current level of ISFM adoption across the whole Kenya and the identified studies show differences in adoption depending on the region. Summarizing the findings of different studies, the adoption rates may be as high as 90% (Wawire et al. 2021) for individual ISFM practices. The adoption of all techniques at once in combination, also called complete ISFM, seems to be much lower. For example, Adolwa et al. (2017) only found a 36% adoption rate of full ISFM in Kakamega county. However, as ISFM comprises a double-win strategy, tackling both the need to increase yields and to reduce GHG emissions, the use of ISFM has the potential to be adopted at a much broader scale in the future. The extent to which this will happen is not clear, as official documents only state that it shall be promoted, without specifying an explicit target, neither for ISFM nor for climate smart agriculture. Yet, there is little that speaks against a large-scale adoption of at least some of the ISFM techniques and one of the main benefits of ISFM as a LMT is, that it is not directly in competition with other land uses. In fact, the higher yields that ISFM promises compared to current low-input agriculture (about double), would mean that it reduces competition of agriculture with other land uses.

However, as organic input is required for ISFM, there is the potential for a resource competition for available biomass, for example between the use for animal fodder and input into the soils. That the resources are insufficient to apply ISFM in all fields is already visible in fertility gradients of fields in Kenya, where it is often observed that the fertility of soils decreases with increased distance to farmers homes, because the resources such as organic input are mostly allocated to fields close to the home (Vanlauwe et al. 2015). This is also associated with the way of cultivating, as most is still done with

manual labour and many organic inputs, such as farmyard manure are produced close to the home. An even distribution of organic input without mechanization would thus require a lot of additional labour. This could be a barrier for the most efficient utilization of biomass to build up of SOC stocks and increasing nutrients use efficiency, which would probably be highest, if inputs would be evenly distributed on all land used.

4.3.4. *Climate risks & sensitivities*

The practices of ISFM possess the potential to reduce pressure of climate change in several areas. For example, higher SOC usually is accompanied by improvements in soil structure leading to a better infiltration of rain and to a higher water storage capacity which can reduce the susceptibility to drought. Also, while ISFM is not a specific measure against water erosion, improved soil structure through ISFM could reduce erosion. Yet, erosion control by ISFM alone is likely much less effective than additional climate smart agriculture strategies, such as mulching or conservation tillage, which both lead to an increased soil cover. On the other hand, the effects of climate change could decrease the efficiency of ISFM practices compared to nowadays. For example, all other drivers such as moisture being equal, increased temperatures usually speeds up the turnover of SOC in the soil (Davidson and Janssens, 2006), which could negatively influence the overall potential of ISFM techniques to sequester CO₂ compared to lower temperatures. However, such increased temperatures would affect all soils regardless of whether ISFM is applied or not, so even under increased SOC turnover, should the practice of ISFM be beneficial in comparison to agriculture without improved management. Another sensitivity is related to the availability of biomass. If climate change, for example through drought or heat spells, would reduce net primary productivity, it will indirectly affect the feasibility of ISFM, as less biomass would be available as organic amendment and biomass competition with livestock feed could increase.

4.3.5. *Economic implications*

Due to the double-win potential of sequestering CO₂ and increasing yield, ISFM has the strong potential to be applied in a cost-efficient way and could already pay off just by the increased yield. However, as the responsiveness between soils differs (Vanlauwe et al, 2015), the application of ISFM may only be cost-efficient in responsive soils, while unresponsive, typically very weathered soils, may not be worth the additional costs for input and labour. The economics surrounding additional labour requirement are context specific and often depend on opportunity costs. For example, Hörner and Wollni (2021) showed in an Ethiopian case study, that despite leading to higher yields, the adoption of ISFM only lead to higher household incomes compared to non-adoption when it was not in competition for labour with other income generating activities. Also, the prices of fertilizers required may be different in different regions of Kenya. For example, Cedrez et al. (2020) showed that regional fertilizer prices within Kenya varied by about a factor of 1.3, depending mostly on how well the road network was in the area. Due to these region-specific differences, estimating a general cost for the CO₂ sequestration by ISFM is difficult to impossible. In the best cases, ISFM may pay off by increased yields alone, while in the worst case with unresponsive soils, ISFM may under no circumstances sequester any CO₂.

4.3.6. *Co-benefits and trade-offs*

The main aim of ISFM is to increase and sustain yields, so even if its implementation is funded with the aim of mitigating CO₂ emissions, it should lead to higher agricultural production. Thus, compared to other LMT, the application of ISFM is not projected to negatively affect agricultural production in any way. In fact, it rather should increase yields, with positive relieve of pressure on other land. The share of arable land in Kenya has, largely due to increased need for food and due to low national yield levels and population growth, increased from about 6% in 1970 to about 10% in 2016 (World Bank 2021). Hence, yield increases reduce the pressure on other land especially given the expected population doubling in the next 35 years (European-Commission and Joint Research Centre, 2018). Often the land cleared for agriculture produces low yields, as it is mostly mined for available nutrients without a proper replenishment, leading to a rapid decline in yields after the first few years. Thus, it seems that the sparing potential for land when increasing yields by applying ISFM could help to leave more land to other land uses.

There may, however, be a trade-off concerning N₂O emissions. Transforming a subsistence agriculture field to ISFM will increase the level of nitrogen inputs, originating both from chemical fertilizer and from plant residues. The change in nutrient inputs can be very significant as traditional subsistence agriculture may have almost no external nitrogen input, while in ISFM, applications of 50-100 kg nitrogen per ha and season are desired. Such an increase of nitrogen inputs on one hand usually increases N₂O emissions on a per area basis. On the other hand, ISFM N₂O emissions may still be lower on a per yield basis, and in responsive soils can be offset by CO₂ sequestration. For example, Dhandli et al. (2016) found that about double the N₂O emissions of ISFM treatments compared to the control treatment on a per area basis. However, yield was increased by a factor of more than 3, so on a per yield basis ISFM had significantly lower N₂O emissions. Also, Sommer et al. (2016) showed clearly that the higher nitrogen inputs through farmyard manure within ISFM lead to higher N₂O emissions. However, many ISFM trial operate at very high input levels of 200 kg nitrogen and more, while farmers may not have as much capital and apply much lower levels, such as only adding 50 kg nitrogen ha⁻¹ and season. At such low levels N₂O emissions should be less. To reduce the trade-off by increased N₂O emissions, the focus should be put on the nitrogen use efficiency of organic and chemical nitrogen inputs, and on increasing synchrony between soil nitrogen availability and plant demand, which would lead to both lower N₂O emissions and higher cost-efficiency of ISFM. Also, any GHG emissions from ISFM should be scaled to yield, not per area base, to account for lower land-use competition. The increase of nitrogen inputs also bears the potential of increased NO₃⁻ leaching, which could affect the ground water quality, if fertilization is overdone. The central concepts of nutrient use efficiency and synchrony within ISFM have thus to be followed rigorously to reduce the risk of inefficient nitrogen use and of environmental pollution.

One additional risk associated with ISFM could be that the need to use improved germplasm, such as hybrid varieties increases the dependence of farmers external actors to provide seeds. Hybrid seeds are poor material for regrowing crops, so they need to be bought each season, increasing the

dependence of farmers on seeds vendors. Due to different success rates of ISFM in responsive vs unresponsive soils there is also the risk of poor performance of ISFM if its application is not accompanied by sufficient extension and capacity building.

Overall, the application of ISFM presents a strong potential for a double-win strategy, increasing yield while simultaneously mitigating CO₂ emissions. However, as addressed above, there are risks associated with higher rates of nitrogen application, so it is important to do a case sensitive application of ISFM. For example, the addition of nitrogen fertilizer should be distributed across the season, to best match plant demand and the simultaneous application of mineral fertilizer and plant residues with low nitrogen content can temporarily immobilize soil nitrogen, increasing synchrony between plant demand and release (Gentile et al., 2011).

4.3.7. Risks associated with scaling up

The main risk is likely in the need to consider local differences in the efficiency of ISFM and to properly account for them when scaling up to a national level. More knowledge is therefore needed on the interactions between soil properties, climate and ISFM efficiency. In other words, detailed knowledge on the responsiveness under different soils (Vanlauwe et al, 2015) and climates is needed to apply ISFM in the most efficient way and to avoid negative side effects, such as increased nitrate leaching or N₂O emissions. Apart from that, if ISFM is upscaled, the need for organic inputs may create competition for other biomass uses, such as animal feed. Yet, this may be partly circumvented, as animal manure is one of the most efficient organic inputs into ISFM. In fact, stakeholders frequently stated that the recommended application of green manures is not regularly practiced by farmers, so farmyard manure is the most realistic organic resource for ISFM. The demand for residue inputs may be significant, if high rates applied at some ISFM trials of up to 4 ton carbon per ha and year are followed. Yet already smaller amounts of organic amendments, such as 1.2 ton of carbon, have led to positive effects of ISFM on yield (Chivenge et al., 2009). A key insight from our stakeholder workshop was, that the up to 4 ton carbon per ha and year, as implemented in research trials on ISFM are unrealistic rates at scale. Also, the Kenyan stakeholders stated that the most important organic resource is farmyard manure and that green manures are not commonly applied and rather fed to animals. Farmyard manure should thus be the focus of any upscaling exercise. Realistic rates of application are equivalent to 1 or 2 ton carbon per ha and year, at the low and high end.

4.3.8. Research gaps

Several research gaps exist with respect to ISFM in Kenya. First of all, the national level of ISFM application is currently unknown, so national data on ISFM adoption would be important as a starting point. Also, while the benefit of ISFM with regards to yield and GHG mitigation has received attention, the farm level economics of ISFM adaption may be an important barrier (Hörner and Wollni, 2021) but have not been studied in detail in Kenya. The level of market access to fertilizer for smallholder farmers is an important concern, and lack of infrastructure may hinder access to fertilizer or make it more expensive (Cedrez et al., 2020). Another research gap is how ISFM will affect the yields of crops other than maize, which due to its` importance for nutrition has been the focus of research, while for other

crops such as millet only few studies exists (e.g. Dass et al., 2013). Finally, a better understanding of N₂O emissions of ISFM is required to better estimate the emissions on a per yield base and to evaluate the overall GHG sequestration potential of ISFM techniques which may be acting simultaneously as a sink of CO₂ and source of N₂O. This will be crucial to make sure that ISFM will be applied in a form that is most likely to lead to negative emissions and that makes most efficient use of the applied nitrogen.

4.4. Agroforestry

4.4.1. Introduction

Agroforestry is a broad term that addresses the combination of trees or shrubby elements with agricultural production. According to the FAO “Agroforestry can be defined as a dynamic, ecologically based, natural resource management system that, through the integration of trees on farms and in the agricultural landscape, diversifies and sustains production for increased social, economic and environmental benefits for land users at all levels” ([Agroforestry \(fao.org\)](http://agroforestry.fao.org)). In many ways, agroforestry systems are not a new technology - the presence of trees and shrubs in agricultural landscapes was and still is common around the globe. Also, many species which require shading, for example coffee, are commonly grown in agroforestry systems applying shading trees. However, only in recent decades have intentionally designed agroforestry systems with two or multiple strata become more popular as an increased level of research that focuses on the interactions between the different strata. This is important both in terms of nutrient and light competition. The improved agroforestry systems specifically aim at optimizing synergies between different components while reducing competition to be able to harvest more yield from the tree and crop component on a per area basis, than would be possible in a monoculture system. This is also referred to as reaching a land-equivalent ratio (LER) > 1. A special case where agroforestry coincides partly with ISFM is the introduction of legume trees, where nitrogen can be symbiotically fixed by the trees and enters the soil to become crop available through litterfall or pruning, or provide the feedstock for animals to supply manure to the fields. Agroforestry serves as LMT, mainly due to the clearly measurable increase of aboveground carbon stocks in the woody biomass. Belowground root biomass and even SOC are further potential CO₂ sinks, but they are more difficult to measure and they are also less important in terms of magnitude. According to an estimation by the Kenyan government agroforestry has the largest GHG mitigation potential of all agricultural technologies in Kenya (Government of Kenya, 2015).

4.4.2. Policy context

The target to increase the land under agroforestry has been stated in several policy documents such as the Kenya climate smart agriculture strategy (Government of Kenya, 2017), the official communication of the nationally determined contribution to the UN (Government of Kenya, 2015), the Kenya National Adaption Plan (Government of Kenya, 2016) and the National Climate Change Action Plan (Government of Kenya, 2018b). Most recently the government of Kenya committed to planting an additional 350,000 agroforestry trees as part of their updated nationally determined contribution submitted in 2021. The prospect and perception of agroforestry in Kenya are quite positive. Many

farmers in Kenya already apply a simple kind of agroforestry by including trees at the edge of their fields, for example. Furthermore, the World Agroforestry Centre (ICRAF) has its main location in Kenya, and it promotes many projects around agroforestry propagation. However, there are no clear numbers on how much agroforestry is already used in Kenya, which has partly to do with it being a traditional technique in many ways and partly with the difficulty to account for agroforestry systems due to their broad diversity.

In a broader sense, agroforestry could benefit from funds that are expected to be available to target the nationally determined contributions of Kenya. Those are 62 bln US \$ until 2030 of which 44 bln US \$ will be targeted at adaptation and mitigation options which include agroforestry. It is, however, not clearly specified how the funds will be used exactly. Other funds are available through the 280 mln US \$ climate smart agriculture programme ([Development Projects : Kenya Climate Smart Agriculture Project - P154784 \(worldbank.org\)](#)) which includes agroforestry and has assigned 7.4 bln Ksh (about 68 mln US \$) to the promotion of agroforestry (Government of Kenya, 2017).

4.4.3. Current land use and potential land-use competition

While it is an understanding that trees in agricultural systems are common in Kenya, a clearly measured baseline on the exact spatial extent of agroforestry is lacking, and it is thus a goal of the government to develop a baseline understanding of the extent of agroforestry adoption in Kenya (Government of Kenya, 2017). A major challenge for such a project is the diversity of agroforestry systems, as they are often very heterogeneous and therefore difficult measure through satellite imagery but even ground truthing. The combination of trees agricultural production presents unique challenges for classification and exact quantification of carbon stocks, not only because of difficulties to distinguish between forest and agroforestry systems (Rosenstock et al., 2019) but also because of the diversity of species used, and because allometric equations developed for closed tree stands are not suitable for agroforestry systems (i.e. the growth pattern and shape of trees differ). The most up to date estimate, which however only covers about half of Kenya's arable land, classified between 5 and 10% of agricultural production areas within the study area as agroforestry systems (Marshall et al., 2017). Through the strong investment in agroforestry, and as agroforestry may partly count to afforestation programmes which Kenya committed to by national law, an increase in agroforestry is to be expected in the coming decades. A clear projection and baseline are however lacking.

A central goal of the Kenyan environmental and climate change mitigation policy is the increase of forest area to at least 10% of Kenya's land area. One could therefore say that the expansion of forest, as stated by the law and included in the nationally determined contribution, can compete with the expansion and intensification of arable land, as has historically definitely been the case, where forest areas have been cleared to make room for arable land (World-Bank, 2021). Agroforestry in this sense offers a consolidation of the competition between these two land-uses, where trees and agricultural production areas can synergistically be used. More than agricultural area, it may be the labour

requirement that prevents upscaling of agroforestry, as the systems due to the need to prune the trees, for example, are labour intensive.

4.4.4. Climate risks & sensitivities

In many ways, agroforestry systems are less vulnerable to extreme climates than traditional arable monocrop systems. Due to the shade that agroforestry systems provide, the crop component in agroforestry systems is more resilient towards many stresses associated with climate change (Sheppard et al., 2020). The shade helps to buffer extreme heat events and the trees provide a better microclimate. Agroforestry systems can also improve soil water status in several ways, for example by reducing the evaporation of a system, both due to shading and by serving as windbreaks. However, the trees do increase the transpiration of the system, which could overall lead to a stronger competition for water between the tree and arable component (Sheppard et al., 2020) but this may not be the case for deep rooting trees, mostly getting water from areas inaccessible to the crop. The additional canopy provided by the trees also provides protection against heavy rains, reducing soil detachment and runoff. This can increase infiltration and reduce erosion, with an additional runoff reduction if trees or shrubs are planted along the contour line, with the root system protecting against landslides or gully erosion. The trees and stripes on which they are established on also provide additional room for biodiversity (Rosenstock et al. 2019), such as habitat for insects or other plant species in the tree stripes.

4.4.5. Economic implications

As agroforestry provides many benefits apart from GHG mitigation, it may already be feasible to apply it, even if there is no compensation for the carbon sequestration. However, through the need to prune the trees for example, agroforestry increases labour demand, so the additional labour required could be an adoption barrier, especially if other off-farm income generating activities are possible (Hörner and Wollni, 2021). While detailed per ha cost of agroforestry implementation in Kenya was not found, based on cost data reported by the Government of Kenya (2018b), it can be estimated that the cost of CO₂ sequestration of afforestation would be in the range of 19 to 29 US \$ per ton of CO₂. This does not directly translate into agroforestry systems as they require additional labour and provide additional benefits but could give a rough range. Yet, even if the cost is considerably higher (e.g. double that of forests), agroforestry would still be a rather cheap option to mitigate GHG on a global price perspective and would alleviate the inherent competition for land between agricultural production and trees.

4.4.6. Co-benefits and trade-offs

Yield losses compared to monocropping systems have been reported in some instances (Sheppard et al., 2020), but as light is usually not a limiting factor in the tropics, they are not the norm in tropical agroforestry systems. Most often, and especially if tree provide has marketable fruits or high value timber, agroforestry systems have a land equivalent ratio significantly above 1, meaning there is a strong benefit for agricultural production and increased productivity of the land. Several stakeholders also reported on additional benefits, such as a higher biodiversity. Due to the generally positive yields and ecosystem services, increased labour requirements of agroforestry systems could be the main

limiting factor, for example when agroforestry operations are competing with other economic on-farm activities. However, other benefits that agroforestry offers are increased landscape diversity and for the farmer income diversification (Sheppard et al., 2020), so they may be worth the additional labour required. In the special case of implementing legume trees into agroforestry system there exists the possibility that N₂O emissions increase (Rosenstock et al., 2014), yet this may only happen under a strong mismanagement leading to a poor synchrony between crop nitrogen demand and provisioning (Palm et al., 2001). In general agroforestry systems increase nutrient use efficiency, reduce nutrient losses and sometimes even fix additional nutrients (i.e. nitrogen by legume trees). Thus, from a nutrient cycling perspective the benefits largely dominate, and introduction of symbiotic nitrogen fixation is a wanted trait under nitrogen limited systems, common in Kenya. Therefore, with the exception of poorly managed legume tree systems, agroforestry does not lead to increases N₂O emissions but rather improves nutrient cycling (Kim et al., 2016). An additional benefit of agroforestry systems is the more profound depth of tree roots compared to annual crop roots. This presents an efficient safety net to reduce nutrient leaching, as trees can take up nutrients that are leached beyond the root zone of annual crops. This effect can be rather strong, for example Wolz et al. (2018) found that in a maize soybean rotation alley cropping, a modern agroforestry system, reduced nitrate leaching by 90% compared to the monoculture system. Additionally, the permanent root system and vegetation stripes of agroforestry present an effective measure against erosion, which also benefits water quality. As already mentioned, the main trade-off that seems to exist for agroforestry implementation is the increased labour requirement, which is in competition with other income activities and is one of the main adoption barriers for agroforestry (Gosling et al. 2021). Thus, it is worthwhile to understand how this adoption barrier can be overcome. An option would be to provide additional adoption incentives, for example through promoting of high value fruit trees that provide additional income. Also, external payments could be an option, but such incentive systems have to be designed with care and bear the risk of lowering the actual interest in the trees making their implementation only a way gain money. An interesting finding is, that social norms and community pressure play a key role in the adoption of agroforestry (Buyinza et al., 2020) and thus improving the social perception of agroforestry could be a leverage point to enhance agroforestry adoption.

4.4.7. Risks associated with scaling up

If done well, with at suitable selection of trees and crops, there is very little risks associated with scaling up agroforestry to the national level in Kenya. The main barrier could be household economics regarding labour constraints rather than any environmental or food security concerns. It may thus be the best way to provide additional incentives to adopters of agroforestry. Even payments for ecosystem services could be an option but would need to be accompanied by open and suitable communication, so that adopters still feel that they adopt agroforestry due to the additional benefits it provides and do not only do it to get short term access to capital, abandoning it as soon as capital flows stop. This “buy-in” into the technology is especially important for agroforestry as it is a long-term investment and needs some time until it is fully established.

4.4.8. *Research gaps*

Several key research gaps that are yet to be closed include the baseline of how much agroforestry is already adopted in Kenya, but also how to estimate the amount of carbon stored in these highly diverse systems (Rosenstock et al., 2019). As they are not exclusive, it would also be of interest how agroforestry could be coupled with the other discussed LMT, such as reduced tillage or ISFM, as further synergies might be possible. Finally, more attention should be paid to adoption barriers, such as labour requirements. A special focus with regard to social justice agenda should be how poverty affects agroforestry adoption, as it has been indicated that the lack of capital often hinders the economically poorest households to adopt agroforestry, as they are in need for short term economic gains and lack the capital to invest in agroforestry, which does only start to pay off after several years (Cavanagh et al., 2017).

4.4.1. *Introduction*

According to the FAO definition, which is also used in Kenya, forest is defined as land with a tree cover of at least 10% and an area of more than 0.5 ha with trees being at least of 5 m height, once they reach maturity (FAO, 2000), so some agroforestry systems may also count as forest. This section, however deals with forests that only/mainly consist of trees and to not target food production by agriculture. Forests store large amounts of carbon, mostly in the biomass, and regrowing forests can therefore be a strong sink of CO₂. Additionally, as most of the carbon stored in forest is stored aboveground in the trees, it is relatively simple to estimate the amount of carbon stored in homogeneous forests. Thus, reforestation of suitable land, such as areas that were initially forests but have been deforested, represent effective, reliable, and quantifiable sinks of CO₂ and is therefore seen as a highly suitable LMT. In Kenya, due to historical deforestation of major portions of the indigenous forest, starting in colonial period (Government of Kenya, 2014), there is a lot of land that bears the natural potential to accommodate forests, but which is currently not covered by forest. Deforestation was very high towards the end of the 20th century and only roughly 6% of land was covered by forest in the early 2000s (World-Bank, 2021). However, there have been afforestation measures in recent decades leading to an increase of forest cover, which is now around 8%, with an official goal of reaching at least 10% of forest cover by 2030. This aim of achieving 10% of forest cover in Kenya has been implemented into state law (Government of Kenya, 2014). The importance of afforestation in Kenya is also highlighted by the fact that afforestation has been identified as the only technology in the sector of climate change mitigation which can lead to significant negative emissions in Kenya in the official analysis of mitigation potential (Government of Kenya, 2018b).

4.5. Afforestation and forest conservation

4.5.1. *Policy context*

Several official Kenyan policy documents state the clear goal of afforestation to reach 10% of forest cover in Kenya (Government of Kenya, 2014; 2018a). This is derived from the constitution of Kenya, which in article 69(1)b, states explicitly that the “state shall work to achieve and maintain a tree cover

a tree cover of at least ten per cent of the land area of Kenya”. This commitment is not only internal, but the government of Kenya has also committed internationally to reaching the 10% forest cover in within their nationally determined contribution submitted to the UN (Government of Kenya, 2015). Several governmental afforestation programmes are enacted, but it was stated that community and private land need to be included into afforestation efforts to reach the target 10% cover (Government of Kenya, 2020). There are also several important NGOs which promote which strongly promote an afforestation in Kenya. The most famous one is certainly the green belt movement founded by Professor Wangari Maathai in 1977 ([The Green Belt Movement](#)), which combines the planting of trees with communities taking more responsibility for their land and with women empowerment. The importance of afforestation in national policies has also been confirmed by stakeholder interviews. However, they identified a difficulties to implement these policies on the ground level, mainly due to local laws and national laws not being aligned, as well as unwritten “traditional community rules” being opposed to afforestation in some areas.

Large finances are to be made available for the afforestation programmes. Kenya has identified a need of about 4 bln US \$ until 2030 for their reforestation programmes (Government of Kenya, 2018b), which are to come out of the money dedicated to Kenya`s nationally determined contribution (Government of Kenya, 2020b). Additional, private funds are available for the reforestation programmes which can be received for specific project upon application, for example from the reforestation grants of the world wildlife foundation ([Reforestation Grants | Projects | WWF \(worldwildlife.org\)](#)).

4.5.2. *Current land use and potential land-use competition*

From a spatial coverage of forests on about 12% of Kenya`s land area at the time of independence in 1963 (Government of Kenya, 2018a) only half (i.e. 6%) remained in the early 2000s (Government of Kenya, 2018a). However, due to strengthened forest policies and afforestation programmes a recovery to about 7.8% of land area in 2016 (World-Bank, 2021) was achieved. As the stated official objective implemented in the constitution of Kenya is to increase forest cover to at least 10% of Kenya`s surface area in 2030, there is a clear target line which must be met and can be anticipated if policies do not fail. To which extent forest cover will surpass the 10% of land area is open, as much of the land in Kenya is too dry to support forests and is a savanna type of vegetation. While the clear goal of 10% forest cover exists, the main competition to forest is area for agricultural production, especially as low-input agriculture which is still very common in Kenya (total fertilizer consumption ~ 60 kg per ha and year, less than half the world average; World-Bank, 2021). It is also foreseeable that there is an increasing pressure on land in Kenya, the strongest drivers of which are the population growth and the resulting need for food. This trend is not expected to end any time soon, as Kenya is still a strongly developing country, aiming at 6% GDP growth per year and population growth is expected to only level of around the year 2100 and with a population around 120 mln people, which is more double the population compared to today (United Nations, 2019). This development is exacerbated by the relatively low

productivity of agricultural land in Kenya, compared to the global average. This highlights the need to think of LMTs as a portfolio where synergies (e.g. between afforestation, agroforestry and ISFM) must be sought if any land use change shall be sustainable. In that sense, the yield gap presents an opportunity in a synergistic scenario, as an increased productivity from agriculture could make more land available to afforestation. Apart from the threat of forest clearing for agricultural production area, the fact that 87% of the rural population still depend on firewood for cooking, poses additional pressure on the forest biomass (Government of Kenya, 2018b), which could be alleviated with the introduction of alternatives for cooking to reduce the pressure on forest, while also providing health benefits. In this context, also poverty itself has been named as a driver of deforestation (Müller and Mburu, 2009) as people in strong financial need may cut trees as a means to quickly generate money by selling either the wood or charcoal.

4.5.3. Climate risks & sensitivities

Forests are threatened by climate change in several ways. They could suffer severely both from increased heat, and increased frequency and strength of drought events. The change in precipitation distribution was also identified by stakeholders as one of the main risks. The situation is exacerbated in the early stages of afforestation, as small trees do not yet offer much protection against erosion and soil degradation. Also, naturally emerging trees tend to be at lower risk than trees planted as seedlings. The major stress on forests that climate change poses, could reach a degree where forest ecosystems are destabilized and the climate becomes more suitable for savanna than forest ecosystems (Hély et al., 2006). According to stakeholders, the risk of this is higher for afforested areas than for natural forest. Also, forest fires, which occur mainly during dry season, are a major threat to forests in Kenya (Ongeri et al. 2020), and the risk for them could increase with increased severity of droughts due to climate change. Yet, most forest fires in Kenya, to date, are related to human activities, such as land clearing, charcoal production, or hunting, while natural ignition is extremely rare (Poletti et al., 2019). However, even for man-made forest fires could increase severity due to climate change if higher temperatures and drought occur in combination. Apart from forests being under threat from climate change, afforestation can alleviate some risks from climate change. For example, forests are associated with high biodiversity (Muriithi and Kenyon, 2002), so increasing the area of forest could combat the loss of biodiversity, which however strongly depends on forest species decomposition and management.

4.5.4. Economic implications

While exact costs for CO₂ sequestration by forests in Kenya are not clear, it is very likely from other international studies, that afforestation will be one of the most cost-efficient ways to sequester CO₂ in international comparison with many other more technical LMT. For example, Torres et al. (2010) estimated the cost of carbon sequestration through afforestation in Mexico to be somewhere in the range between 10 and 40 US \$ per ton of carbon, which roughly corresponds to 3 to 11 US \$ per ton of CO₂. Even though this is not directly transferrable to Kenya, it gives a hint on how cost-efficient afforestation could be compared to for example technical solutions such as BECCS, which are often

estimated to only start at around 100 US \$ per ton of CO₂. While there is no official statement of cost for GHG sequestration by afforestation, it can be roughly estimated using the estimated project costs and sequestration potential from available data stated by the Government of Kenya (2018b). Using this data, it can be estimated the cost of GHG sequestration by afforestation would be roughly 19 to 29 US \$ per ton of CO₂ sequestered. One point that was raised by a stakeholder, was that the cost of afforestation is often overly optimistic, mainly representing the cost of planting. Yet, many earlier afforestation projects failed as they did not consider the cost of managing the trees, even watering in some case, so that they would survive. The cost of good and sustainable afforestation may thus be higher. It also has to be mentioned in this context, that the storage in the woody biomass of forests is not permanent and may be lost for example due to forest fires. From a sequestration perspective it would probably be best to sustainably extract the wood for a long-term material use, which could also represent an economic activity.

4.5.5. Co-benefits and trade-offs

With the expected population increase in Kenya, the biggest risk of large-scale afforestation projects is most likely the competition for land between agriculture and forests. As stated before, this risk would be exacerbated, if agricultural production remains at the low levels that it is currently at. Yet it also shows how the implementation of productivity enhancing techniques, such as integrated soil fertility management, at the same time as afforestation are needed to partly alleviate this competition. As forests provide many ecosystem services, such as increased biodiversity, provisioning of clean water and landscape diversification, many co-benefits of afforestation are likely. In terms of social justice, it will be very relevant how forest protection will be realized, so that local people are not alienated from their land. Often forest protection policies, especially the establishment of conservation areas bears colonial heritages, remove local people's right to use the land and offers little to them apart from temporary labour to establish the protected area (Pulhin et al., 2010). Also, it has been noted that many large-scale afforestation projects in Africa, such as the Bonn challenge, ignore the initial suitability of afforestation and plan to implement forest or rather tree plantations on originally grassy biomes (Bond et al., 2019). It will therefore be very important take local people's knowledge into account when conducting afforestation programmes and to assure that they directly benefit from the afforestation and implementation. Finally, these large initiatives, according to a stakeholder view, sometimes sell tree plantations as forest, which clearly have much less of the biodiversity and resilience compared to diverse forest. As a result, enabling afforestation through local NGOs such as the green belt movement, could be a better way than top-down implementation mainly by governmental action or, worse, foreign investment that does not consider the local context at all. From a trade-off and social justice perspective it seems to be most relevant to make sure that afforestation is not done in isolation, but instead as part of a portfolio of techniques that enables the provisioning of ecosystem services to local people, including sufficient food production and water availability. It should also be made sure that afforestation is done rather as restoration of degraded forest to be as natural as possible rather than planting tree plantations on originally grassy biomes (Bond et al., 2019). With a high projected population increase, the increase of yield on agricultural areas seems to be key

to reducing the pressure on land in total and to enable any afforestation to be lasting. Additionally, it is important that it is implemented in a local way, that people benefit from it and have a sense of ownership due to the ecosystem services they gain from the forest, and because they maintain the right to use the forest products in a sustainable way, instead of “protecting” the forest by restricting people from any use.

4.5.6. Risks associated with scaling up

As already mentioned above, one of the main risks associated with afforestation is the competition for land with agriculture, especially if agricultural production does not increase at the same time. At areas which are very suitable for agriculture, the establishment of agroforestry may be the most efficient way to allow for a higher tree cover, while offering synergies for agricultural production. Another risk is that afforestation is done with a lack of local biome understanding, mis-specifying grassy biomes as deforested area and implementing, in the worst cases, tree plantations on them (Bond et al., 2019). Even in suitable forest areas there could be a risk for unsuitable choices of tree species, if afforestation is done with a centrally planned blanket approach, only using a few tree species. The local suitability should therefore be a key component in afforestation programmes. Finally, a key risk is that afforestation is understood as only planting trees. From the stakeholder interviews it became clear, that intensive nourishment may be necessary, especially in the first years to establish new forest areas. Additionally, it was highlighted that long-term protection of new afforested sites is crucial. This should best be done by communities reaping benefits from forest areas and allowing them to sustainably use the forest, instead of top-down protection and law enforcement.

4.5.7. Research gaps

The main research gaps to address involve how the need for afforestation and increased agricultural production can be brought together. In this regard, it is also a relevant question how afforestation can be implemented in a way that is sustainable, i.e. that there is an interest to maintain planted trees after the planting project duration. This is especially relevant in Kenya, where firewood is still the most used form of fuel for cooking and thus there is a demand for timber that could be in conflict with the afforestation programmes. With regards to the definition of forests at having at least 10% of tree cover, it is also of interest to better differentiate agroforestry systems from real forests, because 10% cover could also be achieved in agroforestry systems.

5. Conclusions

As indicated by the NDCs and the constitutional 10% forest cover that Kenya pledged to, there is significant interest in LMTs. Kenya is already affected by a changing climate and Kenyan politicians are strongly aware of the fact that the role of Kenya in historic emissions is very low. Hence, there is the (justified) expectation of Kenyans to receive international support in the implementation of LMTs. At the same time, there is a focus on LMTs that do not only store carbon, but also increase ecosystem resilience to a changing climate. The highest potential in Kenya is attributed to afforestation and forest conservation. At the same time, the importance of the agricultural sector is well recognized in two aspects: 1) the storage potential of soil carbon by improved practices itself and 2) the indirect effect of higher crop productivity. The second aspect may well be the most important one, as the need for agricultural production is realized to be a key driver of conversion of natural land, such as forest, to agricultural area. This highlights the importance of a portfolio of several LMTs, including sustainable intensification schemes of lower carbon storage potential, such as ISFM and conservation agriculture, and LMTs of higher carbon storage potential such as afforestation/forest conservation. Agroforestry in that sense represents an interesting combination, as is a sustainable intensification scheme, provides climate resilience and, depending on the tree density, can also be counted as afforestation. For the authors of this report, no clear priority of LMTs in Kenya emerges. Rather, it seems that a successful implementation is only possible if they are implemented simultaneously and with a focus on ecosystem climate resilience.

6. References

- Adolwa, I.S., Schwarze, S., Waswa, B., Buerkert, A., 2019. Understanding system innovation adoption: A comparative analysis of integrated soil fertility management uptake in Tamale (Ghana) and Kakamega (Kenya). *Renewable Agriculture and Food Systems* 34, 313–325. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1742170517000485>
- Akinnifesi, F.K., Ajayi, O.C., Sileshi, G., Chirwa, P.W., Chianu, J., 2010. Fertiliser trees for sustainable food security in the maize-based production systems of East and Southern Africa. A review. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.* 30, 615–629. <https://doi.org/10.1051/agro/2009058>
- Bayer, C., Gomes, J., Zanatta, J.A., Vieira, F.C.B., Dieckow, J., 2016. Mitigating greenhouse gas emissions from a subtropical Ultisol by using long-term no-tillage in combination with legume cover crops. *Soil and Tillage Research* 161, 86–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2016.03.011>
- Bond, W.J., Stevens, N., Midgley, G.F., Lehmann, C.E.R., 2019. The Trouble with Trees: Afforestation Plans for Africa. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 34, 963–965. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2019.08.003>
- Butnan, S., Vityakon, P., 2020. The interactive effects of soil disturbance and residue quality on soil nitrogen mineralisation in a tropical sandy soil. *Soil Res.* 58, 277–288. <https://doi.org/10.1071/SR18350>
- Buyinza, J., Nuberg, I.K., Muthuri, C.W., Denton, M.D., 2020. Assessing smallholder farmers' motivation to adopt agroforestry using a multi-group structural equation modeling approach. *Agroforest Syst* 94, 2199–2211. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-020-00541-2>
- Cavanagh, C.J., Chemarum, A.K., Vedeld, P.O., Petursson, J.G., 2017. Old wine, new bottles? Investigating the differential adoption of 'climate-smart' agricultural practices in western Kenya. *Journal of Rural Studies* 56, 114–123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2017.09.010>
- Cedrez, C.B., Chamberlin, J., Guo, Z., Hijmans, R.J., 2020. Spatial variation in fertilizer prices in Sub-Saharan Africa. *PLOS ONE* 15, e0227764. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0227764>
- Chivenge, P., Vanlauwe, B., Gentile, R., Wangechi, H., Mugendi, D., Kessel, C. van, Six, J., 2009. Organic and Mineral Input Management to Enhance Crop Productivity in Central Kenya. *Agronomy Journal* 101, 1266–1275. <https://doi.org/10.2134/agronj2008.0188x>
- Dass, A., Sudhishri, S., Lenka, N.K., 2013. Integrated Nutrient Management to Improve Finger Millet Productivity and Soil Conditions in Hilly Region of Eastern India. *Journal of Crop Improvement* 27, 528–546. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15427528.2013.800828>
- Davidson, E.A., Janssens, I.A., 2006. Temperature sensitivity of soil carbon decomposition and feedbacks to climate change. *Nature* 440, 165–173. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature04514>

- Derpsch, R., Friedrich, T., Kassam, A., Hongwen, L., 2010. Current status of adoption of no-till farming in the world and some of its main benefits 3, 25.
- Dhadli, H.S., Brar, B.S., Black, T.A., 2016. N₂O emissions in a long-term soil fertility experiment under maize–wheat cropping system in Northern India. *Geoderma Regional* 7, 102–109.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geodrs.2016.02.003>
- European-Commission, Joint Research Centre, 2018. Demographic and human capital scenarios for the 21st century: 2018 assessment for 201 countries. Publications Office of the European Union, LU.
- FAO, 2000. FRA 2000 ON DEFINITIONS OF FOREST AND FOREST CHANGE. Rome.
- Foley, J.A., 1994. Net primary productivity in the terrestrial biosphere: The application of a global model. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 99, 20773–20783.
<https://doi.org/10.1029/94JD01832>
- Gentile, R., Vanlauwe, B., Chivenge, P., Six, J., 2011. Trade-offs between the short- and long-term effects of residue quality on soil C and N dynamics. *Plant Soil* 338, 159–169. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-010-0360-z>
- Gosling, E., Knoke, T., Reith, E., Reyes Cáceres, A., Paul, C., 2021. Which Socio-economic Conditions Drive the Selection of Agroforestry at the Forest Frontier? *Environmental Management* 67, 1119–1136.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-021-01439-0>
- Government of Kenya, 2020a. Re: Submission of Kenya’s updated nationally determined contribution. Ministry of Environment and Forestry, Nairobi.
- Government of Kenya, 2020b. DRAFT NATIONAL FOREST POLICY,. Ministry of Environment, Water and Natural Resources, Nairobi.
- Government of Kenya, 2018a. National Climate Change Action Plan (Kenya) Volume 3: Mitigation Technical Analysis Report. Ministry of Environment and Forestry, Nairobi.
- Government of Kenya, 2018b. National Climate Change Action Plan (Kenya) 2018-2022. Ministry of Environment and Forestry, Nairobi.
- Government of Kenya, 2017. Kenya Climate Smart Agriculture Strategy-2017-2026. Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock and Fisheries, Nairobi.
- Government of Kenya, 2016. Kenya National Adaptation Plan: 2015-2030. National Environment Management Authority, Government of Kenya, Nairobi.
- Government of Kenya, 2015. Second National Communication to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. National Environment Management Authority, Government of Kenya, Nairobi.

- Government of Kenya, 2014. Forest Policy. Ministry of Environment, Water and Natural Resources, Nairobi.
- Hély, C., Bremond, L., Alleaume, S., Smith, B., Sykes, M.T., Guiot, J., 2006. Sensitivity of African biomes to changes in the precipitation regime. *Global Ecology and Biogeography* 15, 258–270. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1466-8238.2006.00235.x>
- Hermans, T.D.G., Whitfield, S., Dougill, A.J., Thierfelder, C., 2021. Why we should rethink ‘adoption’ in agricultural innovation: Empirical insights from Malawi. *Land Degradation & Development* 32, 1809–1820. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.3833>
- Hörner, D., Wollni, M., 2021. Integrated soil fertility management and household welfare in Ethiopia. *Food Policy* 100, 102022. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2020.102022>
- Kamoni, P.T., Gicheru, P.T., Wokabi, S.M., Easter, M., Milne, E., Coleman, K., Falloon, P., Paustian, K., 2007. Predicted soil organic carbon stocks and changes in Kenya between 1990 and 2030. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment, Soil carbon stocks at regional scales* 122, 105–113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2007.01.024>
- Kätterer, T., Roobroeck, D., Andrén, O., Kimutai, G., Karlton, E., Kirchmann, H., Nyberg, G., Vanlauwe, B., Röing de Nowina, K., 2019. Biochar addition persistently increased soil fertility and yields in maize-soybean rotations over 10 years in sub-humid regions of Kenya. *Field Crops Research* 235, 18–26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2019.02.015>
- Kim, D.-G., Kirschbaum, M.U.F., Beedy, T.L., 2016. Carbon sequestration and net emissions of CH₄ and N₂O under agroforestry: Synthesizing available data and suggestions for future studies. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 226, 65–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2016.04.011>
- Kuyah, S., Öborn, I., Jonsson, M., Dahlin, A.S., Barrios, E., Muthuri, C., Malmer, A., Nyaga, J., Magaju, C., Namirembe, S., Nyberg, Y., Sinclair, F.L., 2016. Trees in agricultural landscapes enhance provision of ecosystem services in Sub-Saharan Africa. *International Journal of Biodiversity Science, Ecosystem Services & Management* 12, 255–273. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21513732.2016.1214178>
- Lillesø, J.-P. B., van Breugel, P., Kindt, R., Bingham, M., Sebsebe Demissew, Dudley, C., Friis, I., Gachathi, F., Kalema, J., Mbago, F., Minani, V., Moshi, H.N., Mulumba, J., Namaganda, M., Ndangalasi, H.J., Ruffo, C.K., Jamnadass, R. and Graudal, L., 2011. Potential natural vegetation of eastern Africa. Volume 1: The Atlas. . Forest & Landscape Working Paper 61-2011.
- Marenya, P.P., Barrett, C.B., 2007. Household-level determinants of adoption of improved natural resources management practices among smallholder farmers in western Kenya. *Food Policy* 32, 515–536. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2006.10.002>
- Margenot, A.J., Pulleman, M.M., Sommer, R., Paul, B.K., Parikh, S.J., Jackson, L.E., Fonte, S.J., 2017. Biochemical proxies indicate differences in soil C cycling induced by long-term tillage and residue

management in a tropical agroecosystem. *Plant Soil* 420, 315–329. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-017-3401-z>

- Marshall, M., Norton-Griffiths, M., Herr, H., Lamprey, R., Sheffield, J., Vagen, T., Okotto-Okotto, J., 2017. Continuous and consistent land use/cover change estimates using socio-ecological data. *Earth System Dynamics* 8, 55–73. <https://doi.org/10.5194/esd-8-55-2017>
- Mucheru-Muna, M.W., Ada, M.A., Mugwe, J.N., Mairura, F.S., Mugi-Ngenga, E., Zingore, S., Mutegi, J.K., 2021. Socio-economic predictors, soil fertility knowledge domains and strategies for sustainable maize intensification in Embu County, Kenya. *Heliyon* 7, e06345. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e06345>
- Mugwe, J., Mugendi, D., Mucheru-Muna, M., Merckx, R., Chianu, J., Vanlauwe, B., 2009. DETERMINANTS OF THE DECISION TO ADOPT INTEGRATED SOIL FERTILITY MANAGEMENT PRACTICES BY SMALLHOLDER FARMERS IN THE CENTRAL HIGHLANDS OF KENYA. *Experimental Agriculture* 45, 61–75. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0014479708007072>
- Müller, D., Mburu, J., 2009. Forecasting hotspots of forest clearing in Kakamega Forest, Western Kenya. *Forest Ecology and Management* 257, 968–977. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2008.10.032>
- Muriithi, S., Kenyon, W., 2002. Conservation of biodiversity in the Arabuko Sokoke Forest, Kenya. *Biodiversity and Conservation* 11, 1437–1450. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1016234224819>
- Okeyo, J.M., Norton, J., Koala, S., Waswa, B., Kihara, J., Bationo, A., Okeyo, J.M., Norton, J., Koala, S., Waswa, B., Kihara, J., Bationo, A., 2016. Impact of reduced tillage and crop residue management on soil properties and crop yields in a long-term trial in western Kenya. *Soil Res.* 54, 719–729. <https://doi.org/10.1071/SR15074>
- Ongeri, D., Kenduiwo, B.K., 2020. BURNT AREA DETECTION USING MEDIUM RESOLUTION SENTINEL 2 AND LANDSAT 8 SATELLITES, in: *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*. Presented at the XXIV ISPRS Congress, Commission V and Youth Forum (Volume XLIII-B5-2020) - 2020 edition, Copernicus GmbH, pp. 131–137. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLIII-B5-2020-131-2020>
- Ouédraogo, M., Houessionon, P., Zougmore, R.B., Partey, S.T., 2019. Uptake of Climate-Smart Agricultural Technologies and Practices: Actual and Potential Adoption Rates in the Climate-Smart Village Site of Mali. *Sustainability* 11, 4710. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11174710>
- Palm, C., Blanco-Canqui, H., DeClerck, F., Gatere, L., Grace, P., 2014. Conservation agriculture and ecosystem services: An overview. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment, Evaluating conservation agriculture for small-scale farmers in Sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia* 187, 87–105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2013.10.010>

- Palm, C.A., Giller, K.E., Mafongoya, P.L., Swift, M.J., 2001. Management of organic matter in the tropics: Translating theory into practice. *Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems* 61, 63–75.
<https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1013318210809>
- Poletti, C., Dioszegi, G., Nyongesa, K.W., Vacik, H., Barbujani, M., Kigomo, J.N., 2019. Characterization of Forest Fires to Support Monitoring and Management of Mount Kenya Forest. *mred* 39, R1–R12.
<https://doi.org/10.1659/MRD-JOURNAL-D-18-00104.1>
- Prasad, J.V.N.S., Rao, Ch.S., Srinivas, K., Jyothi, Ch.N., Venkateswarlu, B., Ramachandrapa, B.K., Dhanapal, G.N., Ravichandra, K., Mishra, P.K., 2016. Effect of ten years of reduced tillage and recycling of organic matter on crop yields, soil organic carbon and its fractions in Alfisols of semi arid tropics of southern India. *Soil and Tillage Research* 156, 131–139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2015.10.013>
- Pulhin, J.M., Larson, A.M., Pacheco, P., 2012. Regulations as Barriers to Community Benefits in Tenure Reform, in: *Forests for People: Community Rights and Forest Tenure Reform*. Earthscan, London, UK, pp. 155–175. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781849774765-18>
- Rosenstock, T., Tully, K., Arias-Navarro, C., Neufeldt, H., Butterbach-Bahl, K., Verchot, L., 2014. Agroforestry with N₂-fixing trees: sustainable development’s friend or foe? *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability, Sustainability challenges* 6, 15–21.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2013.09.001>
- Rosenstock, T.S., Dawson, I.K., Aynekulu, E., Chomba, S., Degrande, A., Fornace, K., Jamnadass, R., Kimaro, A., Kindt, R., Lamanna, C., Malesu, M., Mausch, K., McMullin, S., Murage, P., Namoi, N., Njenga, M., Nyoka, I., Paez Valencia, A.M., Sola, P., Shepherd, K., Steward, P., 2019a. A Planetary Health Perspective on Agroforestry in Sub-Saharan Africa. *One Earth* 1, 330–344.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2019.10.017>
- Rosenstock, T.S., Wilkes, A., Jallo, C., Namoi, N., Bulusu, M., Suber, M., Mboi, D., Mulia, R., Simelton, E., Richards, M., Gurwick, N., Wollenberg, E., 2019b. Making trees count: Measurement and reporting of agroforestry in UNFCCC national communications of non-Annex I countries. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 284, 106569. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2019.106569>
- Roser, M., Ritchie, H., Ortiz-Ospina, E., 2013. World Population Growth. *Our World in Data*.
- Running, S.W., Nemani, R.R., Heinsch, F.A., Zhao, M., Reeves, M., Hashimoto, H., 2004. A Continuous Satellite-Derived Measure of Global Terrestrial Primary Production. *BioScience* 54, 547–560.
[https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568\(2004\)054\[0547:ACSMOG\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568(2004)054[0547:ACSMOG]2.0.CO;2)
- Segnini, A., Posadas, A., da Silva, W.T.L., Milori, D.M.B.P., Gavilan, C., Claessens, L., Quiroz, R., 2019. Quantifying soil carbon stocks and humification through spectroscopic methods: A scoping assessment in EMBU-Kenya. *Journal of Environmental Management* 234, 476–483.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2018.12.108>

- Sheppard, J.P., Bohn Reckziegel, R., Borrass, L., Chirwa, P.W., Cuaranhua, C.J., Hassler, S.K., Hoffmeister, S., Kestel, F., Maier, R., Mälicke, M., Morhart, C., Ndlovu, N.P., Veste, M., Funk, R., Lang, F., Seifert, T., du Toit, B., Kahle, H.-P., 2020. Agroforestry: An Appropriate and Sustainable Response to a Changing Climate in Southern Africa? *Sustainability* 12, 6796. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12176796>
- Six, J., Elliott, E.T., Paustian, K., 1999. Aggregate and Soil Organic Matter Dynamics under Conventional and No-Tillage Systems. *Soil Science Society of America Journal* 63, 1350–1358. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj1999.6351350x>
- Six, J., Feller, C., Denef, K., Ogle, S.M., Sa, J.C. de M., Albrecht, A., 2002. Soil organic matter, biota and aggregation in temperate and tropical soils - Effects of no-tillage. *Agronomie* 22, 755–775. <https://doi.org/10.1051/agro:2002043>
- Six, J., Ogle, S.M., Breidt, F.J., Conant, R.T., Mosier, A.R., Paustian, K., 2004. The potential to mitigate global warming with no-tillage management is only realized when practised in the long term. *Global Change Biology* 10, 155–160. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1529-8817.2003.00730.x>
- Sommer, R., Mukalama, J., Kihara, J., Koala, S., Winowiecki, L., Bossio, D., 2016. Nitrogen dynamics and nitrous oxide emissions in a long-term trial on integrated soil fertility management in Western Kenya. *Nutr Cycl Agroecosyst* 105, 229–248. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10705-015-9693-6>
- Sommer, R., Paul, B.K., Mukalama, J., Kihara, J., 2018. Reducing losses but failing to sequester carbon in soils – the case of Conservation Agriculture and Integrated Soil Fertility Management in the humid tropical agro-ecosystem of Western Kenya. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 254, 82–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2017.11.004>
- Tessema, B., Sommer, R., Piikki, K., Söderström, M., Namirembe, S., Notenbaert, A., Tamene, L., Nyawira, S., Paul, B., 2020. Potential for soil organic carbon sequestration in grasslands in East African countries: A review. *Grassland Science* 66, 135–144. <https://doi.org/10.1111/grs.12267>
- Torres, A.B., Marchant, R., Lovett, J.C., Smart, J.C.R., Tipper, R., 2010. Analysis of the carbon sequestration costs of afforestation and reforestation agroforestry practices and the use of cost curves to evaluate their potential for implementation of climate change mitigation. *Ecological Economics* 69, 469–477. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2009.09.007>
- United Nations, 2019. World Population Prospects - Population Division - United Nations [WWW Document]. URL <https://population.un.org/wpp/Graphs/Probabilistic/POP/TOT/404> (accessed 2.16.21).
- van Ittersum, M.K., Cassman, K.G., Grassini, P., Wolf, J., Tittonell, P., Hochman, Z., 2013. Yield gap analysis with local to global relevance—A review. *Field Crops Research, Crop Yield Gap Analysis – Rationale, Methods and Applications* 143, 4–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2012.09.009>
- Vanlauwe, B., Bationo, A., Chianu, J., Giller, K.E., Merckx, R., Mkwunye, U., Ohiokpehai, O., Pypers, P., Tabo, R., Shepherd, K.D., Smaling, E.M.A., Woomer, P.L., Sanginga, N., 2010. Integrated Soil Fertility

Management: Operational Definition and Consequences for Implementation and Dissemination. Outlook Agric 39, 17–24. <https://doi.org/10.5367/000000010791169998>

Vanlauwe, B., Descheemaeker, K., Giller, K.E., Huising, J., Merckx, R., Nziguheba, G., Wendt, J., Zingore, S., 2015. Integrated soil fertility management in sub-Saharan Africa: unravelling local adaptation. SOIL 1, 491–508. <https://doi.org/10.5194/soil-1-491-2015>

Vanlauwe, B., Kihara, J., Chivenge, P., Pypers, P., Coe, R., Six, J., 2011. Agronomic use efficiency of N fertilizer in maize-based systems in sub-Saharan Africa within the context of integrated soil fertility management. Plant Soil 339, 35–50. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-010-0462-7>

Wawire, A.W., Csorba, Á., Kovács, E., Mairura, F.S., Tóth, J.A., Michéli, E., 2021a. Comparing farmers' soil fertility knowledge systems and scientific assessment in Upper Eastern Kenya. Geoderma 396, 115090. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2021.115090>

Wawire, A.W., Csorba, Á., Tóth, J.A., Michéli, E., Szalai, M., Mutuma, E., Kovács, E., 2021b. Soil fertility management among smallholder farmers in Mount Kenya East region. Heliyon 7, e06488. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e06488>

Wilson, M.H., Lovell, S.T., 2016. Agroforestry—The Next Step in Sustainable and Resilient Agriculture. Sustainability 8, 574. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su8060574>

Wolz, K.J., Branham, B.E., DeLucia, E.H., 2018. Reduced nitrogen losses after conversion of row crop agriculture to alley cropping with mixed fruit and nut trees. Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment 258, 172–181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2018.02.024>

World-Bank, 2021a. Prevalence of severe food insecurity in the population (%) - Kenya, World, Sub-Saharan Africa, Malawi | Data [WWW Document]. URL <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SN.ITK.SVFI.ZS?locations=KE-1W-ZG-MW> (accessed 4.21.21).

World-Bank, 2021b. Forest area (% of land area) - Kenya | Data [WWW Document]. URL <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/AG.LND.FRST.ZS?locations=KE> (accessed 2.11.21).

World-Bank, 2021c. Fertilizer consumption (kilograms per hectare of arable land) - Sub-Saharan Africa, World | Data [WWW Document]. URL <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/AG.CON.FERT.ZS?locations=ZG-1W> (accessed 12.17.21).

World-Bank, 2021d. CO2 emissions (metric tons per capita) - Kenya, European Union | Data [WWW Document]. URL <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/EN.ATM.CO2E.PC?locations=KE-EU> (accessed 2.15.21).

World-Bank, 2021e. Cereal yield (kg per hectare) - Kenya | Data [WWW Document]. URL <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/AG.YLD.CREL.KG?locations=KE-1W> (accessed 4.20.21).

World-Bank, 2021f. Arable land (% of land area) - Kenya | Data [WWW Document]. URL <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/AG.LND.ARBL.ZS?locations=KE> (accessed 2.11.21).

World-Bank, 2020. State and Trends of Carbon Pricing 2020. World Bank, Washington, DC.

Xiao, S.-S., Ye, Y.-Y., Xiao, D., Chen, W.-R., Zhang, W., Wang, K.-L., 2019. Effects of tillage on soil N availability, aggregate size, and microbial biomass in a subtropical karst region. *Soil and Tillage Research* 192, 187–195. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2019.05.006>

Yadav, S.K., Soni, R., 2019. Integrated Soil Fertility Management, in: Panpatte, D.G., Jhala, Y.K. (Eds.), *Soil Fertility Management for Sustainable Development*. Springer, Singapore, pp. 71–80. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-5904-0_5

LANDMARC

SCALING LAND-BASED MITIGATION SOLUTIONS IN INDONESIA

NEGATIVE EMISSIONS NARRATIVE AND SCENARIOS

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STATUS: PUBLIC

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2. Introduction

This report describes a generic nation-wide transition scenario for implementing land-based mitigation technologies and practices for the AFOLU sector (agriculture, forestry, and other land use sectors) in Indonesia. The report shows the outcomes of a series of research steps that have been conducted in this country since the start of the project in July 2020 until the end of 2022:

First, we performed an initial scoping of key LMTs in the case study country. The scoping assessment resulted in a long list of broad portfolios of different LMTs that could be viable within the various case study countries.

Second, following this long list, we developed a short-list LMT portfolio containing key LMTs that would be the most relevant for a given country context. All case study country partners were asked to propose and validate their LMT portfolio through complementary (policy) literature review and with the help of stakeholder interviews (i.e. external validation by relevant country experts and stakeholders). Ex-ante, no specific guidance of criteria for LMT portfolio short-listing was provided to allow for a free and open co-design process with stakeholders. The scoping process and results are presented in section 3 of this report (steps 1 & 2). The main outcomes of stakeholder engagement activities for the Indonesia case study in the past 30 months were a validated LMT portfolio, modelling scenario, and case study collaboration and dissemination. The stakeholder engagement contributed significantly to developing LMTs scoping for the Indonesian LMT portfolio through interviews, meetings, surveys, workshops, and discussions.

Third, after the short-listed LMT portfolios were validated, the LANDMARC case study country partners were asked to develop national scaling narratives or storylines for each LMT included in their portfolio. The assessments focus on climate risks, vulnerabilities, socio-economic co-benefits, and trade-offs associated with upscaling LMTs in the case study countries. The analysis is based on a broad range of information/literature sources and stakeholder consultations conducted. This process is supported through a risk and impact assessment (i.e. an online survey, workshops, focus group discussion, meetings, and policy dialogue. The engagement activities also explored the stakeholders' capacity gap in LMT implementation (task 6.5). As a result of our stakeholder engagement, we have several options and enough resources for data collection, project dissemination, case study scenarios, and a national LMT portfolio. The stakeholder engagement improves modelling data collection, project dissemination, land use and carbon research.) conducted through the LANDMARC tasks 4.1, 4.2 and 5.2. The results of this analysis are a set of LMT narratives presented in section 4 of this report.

The research steps are designed to enable an **analysis of the risks and (climate) impacts of scaling up land-based mitigation and negative emission solutions**. This report mainly contributes to objectives 2, 3 and 4 of the six LANDMARC key objectives (see Table 1).

Table 1: LANDMARC project objectives.

	Project key objectives
1	Determine the potential and effectiveness of LMTs in GHGs mitigation using Earth Observation (EO)

2	Improve climate resilience of LMT solutions at the local level for large-scale implementation
3	Assess the risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs of scaling up local LMTs nationally
4	Scaling up LMT solutions to the continental and global level to assess the effectiveness
5	Improve current methodologies to estimate emissions and removals for LMTs
6	LMT capacity building and develop new tools and services for decision making

While the results in this report represent a mostly qualitative storyline describing the context and impact of scaling up LMTs in a country context, they also enable project partners to proceed with the translation of the outcomes in a manner so that they can serve as direct model input.

Furthermore, these national-level assessments provide a testing ground and empirical basis for the continental and global assessment of the realistic scaling potential of land-based mitigation and negative emission solutions implemented in Work Packages 6 and 7 of the LANDMARC project (**Objective 4**).

3. Scoping of land-based mitigation solutions

3.1 Overview of the potential of LMTs in Indonesia

3.1.1 Introduction

Since forests cover 65% of Indonesia's total area, forestry and land use are the main contributors to Indonesia's greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (Ministry of Environment and Forestry, 2016). Peatland Restoration Agency was established in 2016 and engaged all stakeholders and actors (private, local governments, students, and communities) in a national program to control climate change in forests and peatlands.

The Paris Agreement set targets to increase carbon dioxide removal technologies and practices for the countries. These technologies will remove and sequester carbon dioxide (Levin, 2017). Various land-based mitigation technologies (LMTs) exist to capture CO₂ and achieve carbon-neutrality, i.e. afforestation and reforestation, biochar and soil carbon sequestration (SCS), ocean fertilisation, bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS) and utilisation (BECCU), enhanced weathering, and direct air capture (DAC) (Minx et al., 2017). Aside from the technologies, land-based mitigation technologies from the land-use change are divided into land-use types, such as forest, agriculture, wetland, grassland, and other lands. Some technologies and practices are implemented in Indonesia, while others are still at the research stage. In Indonesia, these technologies and practices are planned under The Ministry of National Development Planning (BAPPENAS), in collaboration with Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources (MEMR), the Ministry of Environment and Forestry (MoEF), and the Ministry of Agriculture (MoA).

BAPPENAS has two reports addressing climate change mitigation and adaptation, RAN-API (National Action Plan for Climate Adaptation) and RAN-GRK (National Action Plan for Reducing Greenhouse Gas Emissions). These reports are known as NAMA (Nationally Appropriate Mitigation Action) and NAPA (National Adaptation Programme of Action) of Indonesia. Emissions by sector in Indonesia are divided into six categories: land-use (Land-use Change and Forestry), non-combustion, buildings, transport, industry, and power and heat (Dunne, 2019). Based on the RAN-GRK report, the implementation analysis of LMTs is described in some points, i.e. contribution, implementation target, potential technologies, and emission reduction in Indonesia.

A. Contribution to emission reduction

The main contributor to emission reduction in 2019 was the forestry and peatland sector. More than 80% of emission reductions are achieved through afforestation, forestation, and restoration of forest and peatland.

Table 2 Contribution of LMT to Emission Reduction in Indonesia (2019)

LMT	Contribution to Emission Reduction (%)
BECCS	14.14%
Green Chemistry	
Gasification	
Construction	
Concrete	
Afforestation	81.70%
Forestation	
Restoration	
Land-use (mix of measures)	3.04%
Compost	1.12%

Source: Adapted from (BAPPENAS, 2020).

B. Implementation Target of LMTs in Indonesia

Based on the Medium-Term National Development Plan (RPJMN) 2020-2024 of the Ministry of National Development Planning (BAPPENAS), each LMT has specific targets between 2020 and 2024. LMT focuses on BECCS and gasification. LMT targets afforestation, restoration, sustainable agriculture, and organic waste management.

Table 3 Implementation Target of LMTs in 2020-2024

LMT Category	LMT	Targets	2020	2024
Land-based Mitigation Technologies	BECCS	- Final Energy Intensity (BOE/IDR billion) - Primer Energy Intensity (BOE/IDR billion)	0.9	0.8
	Gasification			
	Green Chemistry			
Land-based Mitigation Practices	Afforestation	National land cover (ha)	366,000	2,143,000
	Restoration	Peatland restoration (ha)	301,800	1,600,000

	Land-use (mix of measures)	Sustainable farm area/farmland requirement (%)	60	100
	Compost	Organic waste management (million tons)	64.8	69.8

Source: Adapted from (BAPPENAS, 2020).

C. Potential LMT in Indonesia in 2030

MEMR has forecasted potential BECCS and Gasification production (PJ) per year and the substitution cost from both business and government perspectives in 2030. Potential gasification production is higher than BECCS since the gasification technology targets the industrial sector. The substitution cost is calculated from the investment cost and energy substituted (IRENA, 2017).

Table 4 Potential LMT in Indonesia by 2030

LMT	Technical Potential (PJ/year)	Substitution Cost - Business Perspective (USD/GJ)	Substitution Cost - Government Perspective (USD/GJ)
BECCS	30	-26.1	-24.5
Gasification	71.1	24.5	23.5

Source: Adapted from (IRENA, 2017).

D. Emission Reduction of LMTs in 2015-2019

Based on the RAN-GRK report, the annual emission reductions are recorded for the last ten years. The primary contributor to annual emission reductions is from LMTs. Those practices include afforestation, restoration, and sustainable farm and organic waste management.

Table 5 Emission Reduction from LMTs in Indonesia from 2015 to 2019

Year	BAU Baseline	land-based mitigation technologies	land-based mitigation practices	Total	Cumulative Baseline	Emission Reduction (per year)	Emission Intensity
	(1000-ton CO ₂ e)					%	(1000-ton CO ₂ e/IDR billion)
2015	1,703,000	40,129.9	100,782.36	140,912.26	9,046,000	8.27	0.516
2016	1,764,000	51,122.2	561,235.40	612,357.64	11,170,000	34.71	0.358
2017	1,860,000	64,833.7	345,091.35	410,053.25	13,030,000	22.05	0.424
2018	1,953,000	81,378.8	829,799.09	911,647.48	14,983,000	46.48	0.295
2019	1,959,000	86,577.3	315,245.21	401,822.53	16,942,000	20.51	0.420

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Source: Adapted from (BAPPENAS, 2020).

The data recorded has some assumptions. Specific assumptions are required for each data. However, in general, the following assumptions are used for the data above (table 1-4):

- a. Emission reduction in Indonesia is divided into seven contributing sectors (forestry, energy, transportation, industry, coastal & ocean, agriculture, and waste) (Low Carbon Development Indonesia (LCDI), 2020).
- b. Indonesia aims to reduce emissions by 29% (baseline) and 41% (with international support) by 2030.
- c. The target of renewable energy and BECCS is 23% of the energy mix by 2025.
- d. Coal and gas are still the primary energy sources in the industry, as it is projected to be until 2050.

3.1.2 *Technologies dependent on biomass/photosynthesis*

BECCS

Indonesia is a coal- and carbon-intensive region. Consequently, low-carbon technologies to reduce and store carbon is needed. BECCS can be an LMT solution to reduce Indonesia's fossil fuel dependency. Besides, BECCS can contribute to waste management since 60% of the waste production in Indonesia is biomass (Tahar, 2018). Biomass is organic material-based fuel, including firewood (wood waste, charcoal, wood) and waste (agriculture, urban solid, and industrial). It converts biomass to energy, storing it in either underground or long-lived products (i.e. concrete) and capturing the embodied carbon (Mulligan, 2018). The energy produced from BECCS can be used for the industrial, power, and transportation sectors. This technology can be a net carbon removal when more carbon is stored and more biomass grows.

In Indonesia, bioenergy without carbon capture storage is implemented through anaerobic digestion (biogas), fermentation (ethanol production), thermal biomethane, hydrogen/ammonia production, top-gas recycling (blast furnaces), industrial processes with high amounts of waste heat, mineral process (cement kilns), bio-CNG (Compressed Natural Gas), co-firing, and power production in CHP mode. However, some technologies cannot be implemented largely due to the high cost and insufficient technological experience (Grönkvist, 2012). The mainstream first pathway to implement BECCS technologies in Indonesia is through biomass, biogas, biofuel, thermal biomethane and co-firing for coal power plants (DEN, 2019). Furthermore, Indonesia is developing bio-CNG to utilise biomass. Some quality standards depend on RDF (Refuse-derived fuel) heating value, especially for biomass fuel.

The Government of Indonesia (GoI) has specific bioenergy targets set to meet the energy mix's target in 2025: 5.5 GW of bioenergy, 13.8 M kL of biofuel, 8.4 M tonnes of biomass and 489.9 million m³ of biogas. By 2050, the target is 54.2 million kL and 30% of the blending target in biodiesel (CIFOR et al., 2018). MEMR initiates some strategies for developing bioenergy, such as implementing waste-to-energy and co-firing, developing biofuel, small-scale biogas, biomass stove, and bio-CNG. Biogas is an energy source which can be utilised for household, Bio-CNG, and power generation. Other co-products from biogas are biomethane from the fuel and gas grid, fertiliser, soil amendments, and livestock bedding. Bio-CNG can be applied to compressors, vehicles, and households (Dililusendi, 2020).

The Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources (MEMR) published press release No 092.Pers/04/SJI/2020 about implementing the co-firing method from biomass as the coal substitution for the coal power plantation. Potential raw materials for the co-firing method are organic waste (agriculture, forestry, and industrial), with the percentage of biomass being 1 - 5%. As one of the potential feedstocks, forestry waste has 20,925 tons/day collected from 15 waste management sites in Java. Also, Indonesia's biomass from potential wood (wood pellets) can generate 1,335 MWe. The State Electricity Company (PLN) initiated corporate action through co-firing. To meet the needs of 1% co-firing for coal power plants in Indonesia, Indonesia needs 17,470 tonnes/day of biomass or 5 million tonnes/year of wood pellets. PLN has implemented co-firing technology in five coal power plants (EBTKE ESDM, 2020). Accordingly, BECCS has not been implemented in Indonesia. Biomass co-firing in the coal-power plant is the first step to initiating BECCS implementation.

BIOCHAR

Biochar is a potential alternative to improve soil quality and restore degraded land. Other advantages include a slower decomposition process and resistance to microorganisms. In agriculture, biochar has functions to reduce soil acidity, increase nutrient availability, and bind nutrients. For example, biochar can be applied on land with high acidity (around 3-5) to increase the pH. Also, biochar can be used for the areas with less water to bind this little water. The Agency for Agricultural Research and Development (Balitbangtan), MoA, introduced the manufacture and application of biochar through technical guidance in several locations. Introducing the technique of making biochar to farmers is easy and inexpensive, particularly when using the Kon tiki model. This model has a cone-shaped hole with an upper diameter of 150 cm and a height of 75 cm. It is simple and suitable for farmers (Bardono, 2018).

In Lampung (a province on Sumatera Island, Indonesia), biochar from rice husks and cocoa pod skins (5-10 tonnes/hectare) is applied to acidic, dry land. After using this technology, stable harvest results for up to three consecutive growing seasons are achieved. In another location of similar conditions, 5-10 tonnes/ha of biochar were used in Kupang, East Nusa Tenggara (eastern region of Indonesia). Results showed increased water availability in the soil, increasing the planting intensity from once to twice per year.

There is an annual trend of gradual drying out during the dry season and long-term flooding during the rainy season in the riparian wetlands. Due to this unpredictable and uncontrollable flooding, the growing season typically occurs only once a year (Kartika et al., 2018). The farmers are used to planting rice seedlings in the anaerobic conditions of floodwater and harvesting in the aerobic conditions of dried-out land. Biochar is applied in transitional anaerobic-aerobic conditions on riparian wetlands to increase yield production and improve grain quality (Lakitan et al., 2018).

The Agency for Agricultural Research and Development (Balitbangtan) suggested giving biochar gradually every season by utilising agricultural waste as the raw materials in the field (Bardono, 2018). Agricultural Research and Development (Balitbangtan) has classified BIOCHAR SP 50, a simple technology from agricultural waste, as an agricultural product (Balitbangtan, 2019). However, this potential LMT is not included yet in the government priority. Hence, biochar implementation in Indonesia is still in the pilot stage.

3.1.3 Land management practices

Based on SNI 7645-2010, the Indonesian government classified land-use types into 22 classes of land cover: 7 classes for forest cover and 15 classes for non-forest cover (Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK), 2017). Then, BAPPENAS grouped the land use into nine categories: forestland, rice field, cropland, coastal and ocean (mangrove), settlements, plantation, grassland, and other lands. Based on RAN-GRK (NAMA) report, the negative emission solution in land use management would refer to group differentiation from BAPPENAS.

REFORESTATION/AFFORESTATION

The government of Indonesia relies on reforestation and afforestation to counterbalance deforestation rates, along with other measures such as fire prevention and the halting of new permit issuance. During one year in both 2017-2018 and 2018-2019, 53.9 thousand ha and 31 thousand ha of forest were recovered due to these reforestation efforts (BAPPENAS, 2020). These have successfully reduced net deforestation (gross deforestation – reforestation) in the last few years (KLHK, 2020).

In the National Forestry Plan 2011-2030, KLHK pledged to rehabilitate 11.55 million ha of degraded forest and land by 2030. The government employs two strategies to achieve this target: intensive and incentive rehabilitation. While intensive rehabilitation is centred on priority areas and relies entirely on government funding (APBN), its counterpart focuses on involving local communities in reward-based rehabilitation activities. The idea of incentive rehabilitation is to provide financial incentives for local communities that promote their commitment to maintaining and rehabilitating adjacent forestlands near their residence. Within 2015-2019, intensive and incentive methods have contributed to forest and land rehabilitation as vast as 308 thousand ha and 873 thousand ha, respectively (KLHK, 2020).

RESTORATION

Indonesian peatland covering approximately 14.3 million ha has been an enormous GHG emissions source (Ritung et al., 2011). The Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK) data reported soaring figures in carbon emissions from peat fires and peat decomposition. Data peaked in 2015 due to extreme warming effects attributed to *El Niño*, wherein Peatland fires and decomposition contributed to 802.87 million TCO₂e and 359.52 million TCO₂e, respectively (KLHK, 2020). Aside from natural phenomena such as *El Niño* that frequently trigger fires and decomposition, human activities such as peatland clearings and conversion contribute to peatland's increased vulnerability. Those activities make forests and peatlands more prone to fires and decomposition. In the last decades, 6 out of 14.4 million ha of peatland has been converted from natural peat forests into agricultural land and industrial plantation (Masripatin et al., 2017).

To address this problem, KLHK established the Peatland Restoration Agency (Badan Restorasi Gambut/BRG) in 2016 to manage and facilitate peatland restoration in seven priority provinces: Riau, Jambi, South Sumatra, West Kalimantan, Central Kalimantan, South Kalimantan, and Papua. According to the Strategic Plan of BRG 2016-2020 (BRG, 2016), BRG mainly relies on three strategic action plans to restore Indonesian peatland: i) rewetting, ii) revegetation, and ii) peatland-based socioeconomic revitalisation for the locals.

2.5 million ha of peatland will be subjected to rewetting by 2020 to restore its hydrologic characteristics by maintaining peatland surface water level and groundwater table, especially during drought. Also, rewetting could minimise the risk of peat fires and restore peatland to its original condition. While rewetting is designed to restore drained peatland, revegetation is designed for degraded peatland (peatland that has lost its full or partial vegetation). The purpose of revegetation is to restore the peatland ecosystem and improve land coverage by planting trees that are endemic to the land. The target of revegetation by 2020 covers 670,000 ha of peatland. The last focused restoration program is a peatland-based socioeconomic revitalisation that aims at encouraging people living in the proximity of the peatland area to participate in taking care of the degraded peatland. The very idea of this strategy is to assist the locals in improving their economy via peatland-based economic activities. By 2020, 185,000 ha of peatland is targeted to be restored for economic purposes.

AGRICULTURAL MANAGEMENT PRACTICES

MoA has reported reducing the emissions in the Agricultural sector from 2010 to 2019 through some strategies. Agricultural cultivation technology is applied through rice intensification (SRI), integrated crop management, and low-emission varieties. Organic fertiliser and biopesticides through fertilisers, organic subsidised and procurement of Organic Fertiliser Processing Unit (UPPO) are utilised. The utilisation of livestock and agricultural waste is conducted. Additional activities are the improvement of animal feed supplements by using reforestation. In 2019, the most significant emission reduction in agricultural cultivation technology activities was achieved. MoA recorded 114.74 million tonnes of CO₂ reduction from 2010-2019 (BAPPENAS, 2020).

The Agency for Agricultural Research and Development (Balitbangtan) under MoA has introduced some activities in agricultural management practices, i.e. Water-efficient rice management, through intermittent planting, maintaining soil moisture, cover crop, land clearing without burning, amelioration, paludiculture, and yield optimisation (Litbang Pertanian, 2020). The production targets are achieved by optimising land use, extensification for low-carbon fields, and livestock and fertiliser management. Activities related to livestock and fertiliser management include livestock management with containment, feed quality, biogas (methane capture and energy source), balanced fertilisation based on soil condition, and organic fertiliser (carbon sequestration) (Dariah, 2020).

3.2 Determining the LMT scope for national-level simulation modelling

This section discusses which set of LMTs we will study in detail in Indonesia. Table 2 summarises the main Indonesian LMTs and indicates which ones are included in the LMT portfolio's short-list. The main rationales for including the various LMTs in the national-level scaling simulation assessment are presented below.

Table 6: Long-listing of relevant land-based LMTs

LMTs	Subcategory	Specification	Included in the national LANDMARC LMT portfolio
Biomass-based LMTs	BECCS	Based on domestic biomass (anaerobic digestion) with CCS	Y
		Biomass fermentation	N
	Biochar	Based on domestic biomass	Y
Land Management Practices	Forestland	Sustainable Forest Management	Y
		Afforestation & reforestation	Y
		Deforestation reduction	Y
	Agriculture	System of Rice Intensification	N
		Land optimisation	Y
		Application of crop cultivation technology	Y
		Utilisation of organic fertilisers and biopesticides	Y
		Development of plantation areas on non-forested land	N
		Livestock management	Y
		Coastal & Ocean	Mangrove & Seagrass restoration
Wetlands	Restoration of peat areas	Y	
	Waste management	Compost & anaerobic digestion	Y

- BECCS

BECCS (bioenergy with carbon capture and storage) has been indicated as a critical potential for emissions reductions in Indonesia (DEN, 2019). Repurposing livestock and agricultural waste can allow for land-based negative emissions, while bioenergy usage can reduce fossil fuel and wood burning. BECCS has been a top priority in Indonesia's renewable energy and negative emission solution through biogas, biofuel, gasification, and biomass co-firing.

- **Biochar**

Biochar technology has been known for a long time in Indonesia through charcoal. Biochar is an abundant resource from agricultural and forestry waste, and MoA includes biochar as one of the sustainable agricultural practices (Balitbangtan, 2019).

- **Forestry management & wetland restoration**

The Low Carbon Development Initiative, initiated by BAPPENAS with various stakeholders, recommends forestry policy changes. The 2045 goal of maintaining 41.1 million hectares of primary forest is among the high priorities, and this priority includes preserving 15 million hectares of peatlands. Furthermore, reforestation, afforestation, and restoration are highlighted, each planning on covering a few hundred thousand hectares a year — 500,000, 325,000 and 300,000, respectively. The potential of GHG emission reduction in these two sectors is estimated at 365,275 tons of CO₂ equivalent for seven years of examination. BAPPENAS will conduct the monitoring and evaluation of forestry and wetland preservation.

- **Agriculture optimisation, fertiliser use, & livestock management**

The agricultural sector is one of the top national priorities, as it is responsible for 13% of Indonesia's total greenhouse gas emissions. Furthermore, it is incredibly vulnerable to climate change. Thus, it has a high potential for emissions reductions and sustainability measures to protect from climate shocks. Rice production is already declining, and BAPPENAS has estimated this trend to increase for all Indonesian provinces in the coming 20 years. Thus, field productivity must increase by implementing sustainable or carbon-negative schemes, such as land optimisation, organic fertilisers, and further related research and technological advancement. Sustainable agriculture is a priority, with policy recommendations increasing agricultural land productivity by 4.4% and expanding sustainable agriculture to 45% of all lands. Top priorities are land optimisation, crop cultivation technology, organic fertilisers, and the utilisation of abandoned or previously degraded land. Furthermore, livestock manure/urine and agricultural waste should be repurposed into biogas to achieve negative emissions and capture all waste.

- **Waste management**

Waste management is another sector identified as a national priority. The government has set a target of reducing waste emissions by 9.4% from 2024 to 2030, which has high potential. Anaerobic digestion processes currently contribute to Indonesia's GHG emissions, but compost and other measures of integrated sustainable waste management systems have enormous potential.

The rationale for excluding the other LMTs from any different national scenario scaling analysis is provided below:

- **Mangrove and Seagrass restoration**

Mangroves, the focus of coastal and ocean landscapes, offer many negative emissions potential. However, the relevant methodology and calculations are still in preparation (BAPPENAS, 2020). Thus, it is not yet ready to be included in these LMT analyses.

- **Biomass Fermentation**

The Bioenergy Division of the Ministry of Mineral and Energy Resources (MEMR) focuses on biofuel or biomass fermentation from agro-industrial waste, such as oil palm, sugar, or cassava. There will be considerable potential negative side effects associated with oil palm waste.

- **System of Rice Intensification (SRI) and non-forested land for agriculture**

These practices are applied as sustainable agricultural management strategies. The regulation and policies include these practices as decarbonisation strategies. The number of negative emissions can be estimated based on agricultural areas.

3.3 Discussion on short-listing LMTs

3.3.1 Land-use change dynamics

The National Forestry Plan 2011-2030 (RKTN, 2019) aims at preserving the forest area of around 112.85 million ha through avoided deforestation, fire control, and forest moratorium while dedicating the other 13.07 to be converted for non-forestry purposes by 2030. To achieve these targets, around 3.96 out of 9.3 million ha of critical (degraded) land need to be rehabilitated at a minimum speed of 396,000 ha per year since 2020. Assuming 1,650 trees take up one hectare of land, the total number of trees that need to be planted by 2030 would be 6.53 billion. Should this target be achieved, this rehabilitated forest area would store 55,000 million tons of carbon in 2030 (Ministry of Environment and Forestry, 2019).

Competing land use

Apart from land claims by the National Forest Plan, the ongoing energy transition in the electricity and transportation sector is also making considerable land use claims up to 2030 and 2050, given the anticipated expansion of solar PV parks and biodiesel utilisation.

To meet the B30 biodiesel mandate, which aims to achieve 30% blending in 2025 (Indonesia Regulation 12/2015), 12.2 billion litres of biodiesel is needed. This requires 11.2 Mton of crude palm oil (CPO), equivalent to 370% of the CPO amount used for biodiesel production in 2014. Consequently, the additional land required for reaching the target blends and increased domestic demand by 2025 reaches up to 6.7 million ha, 64% of the total oil palm plantation area in 2014. Oil palm area, which already occupied 18% of total agricultural land, has increased by more than 10% since 1990, while forest land has decreased steadily by an average of 1.1% annually (Khatiwada et al., 2021).

Furthermore, to meet the 2050 electricity demand that has been projected to reach 2,600 TWh (MEMR, 2019), Indonesia needs a total capacity of 1,500 GW of solar photovoltaic power plants, requiring at least 800,000 ha or about 0.4% of the nation's land area (Silalahi, 2020). While much effort will be made to introduce those solar parks on water and building rooftops, it is expected that the bulk of this expansion will occur at the expense of land currently used for agricultural purposes.

3.3.2 Land management Dynamics

Unlike land-use change, changes in land management do not necessarily involve a conversion of land use. Most land management changes would allow the land to remain used partially or entirely as its original function. Enhancing soil organic carbon (SOC) could be one of the effective negative emission measures. Out of the total agricultural land of around 62.3 million ha, which makes up approximately one-third of the total Indonesian land surface area, about 82% is occupied as cropland, including land for temporary crop cultivation (arable land) and permanent crops (See Table 3).

Table 7: Agricultural land use in Indonesia in 2008 and 2018 (in 1000 ha)

Land use category	2008	2018
Agricultural area, total	54,000	62,300
Arable land	22,700	26,300
Land under permanent crops	20,300	25,000
Land under perm. meadows and pastures	11,000	11,000

Source: (FAOSTAT, 2020)

For instance, adding only 1%-point of the SOC to the agricultural area could provide a significant storage potential. Despite the importance of the organic matter in the soil, data for evaluating SOC change in Indonesia is limited due to the absence of regular SOC stock and change monitoring. However, a study reported SOC levels in Indonesian soil in 2010 (see Table 4). Although SOC change data at the macro-level (nation-wide) is not available, several studies report SOC depletion in Indonesian soils at the micro-level. One study suggested that SOC stock declined by around 30% when a forest was converted to agricultural production (Murty et al., 2002). Another study discovered that the level of organic matter in the 0-15 cm soil of lowland rainforest in Sumatra decreased by 48.1 Mg C ha⁻¹ when the forest was downgraded to grassland (Santoso et al., 1997). Another primary source of soil carbon reduction in Indonesia is the loss of carbon from organic soil (peatland), which covers about 14.9 million ha and contains exceptionally high carbon content ranging from 420 to 820 Mg C ha⁻¹ (FAO and ITPS, 2015).

Table 8: Levels of organic matter in topsoil in Indonesia (the data year 2010)

Total land area (million ha)	SOC stock (Pg C)	SOC level (Mg C ha ⁻¹)
183	20.8	113.4

Source: (Shofiyati et al., 2010)

To reverse this trend, intensive land management systems such as no-till farming, cover crops, nutrient management, manuring and sludge application, improved grazing, etc. and water table level increases would be required to recover soil carbon pool or at least to avoid any further loss of soil carbon (Lal, 2003). For practices that do not involve changing the uses of cropland or grazing land, the extensive primary potentials of soil carbon sequestration have extensively relied on no-till farming and grazing management changes (Searchinger & Ranganathan, 2020). No-till agriculture, where farmers drill seeds into the soil instead of ploughing soils, can reduce soil erosion and prevent carbon releases (Ranganathan et al., 2020). Further, improved grazing management which usually follows practices such as designing proper rest periods between grazing events and adjusting to appropriate stocking

periods (matching the yield potential for the grazing area and weather patterns), tends to lead to increased soil carbon stocks up to 0.28 Mg C ha⁻¹ annually (Conant et al., 2017).

Also, supplementing carbon to soils such as compost, manure, and digester from anaerobic digestion (AD) of organic matter (e.g. manure), harvesting residues, or processed organic fertilisers can be performed to improve organic matter levels in agricultural soils. AD-based bioenergy combined with carbon capture storage (BECCS) could provide massive potential in putting CO₂ emissions into negative territory by converting biomass into bioenergy (biogas) and then sequestering the carbon produced into the soils in the forms of organic fertilisers.

Considering the high livestock population in Indonesia (Table 5), which has steadily increased in the last three years, there is a massive potential in biogas and organic fertiliser production from animal manure via AD-based BECCS. A study has estimated the total biogas production from manure in Indonesia to be of 9595.6 Mm³/year or equal to 1.7 x 10¹⁰ kWh of electricity (Khalil et al., 2019).

Table 9 Indonesia Livestock Population (2018-2020)

Species	2018	2019	2020
Large livestock			
Beef cattle	16,433	16,930	17,467
Dairy cattle	582	565	568
Buffalo	894	1,134	1,179
Horse	378	375	392
Small livestock			
Goat	18,306	18,463	19,096
Sheep	17,611	17,834	17,769
Pig	8,254	8,521	9,070

Source: (Ministry of Agriculture, 2020)

Volume-wise, animal manure is the single largest potential resource of soil organic matter and other macro-and micronutrients to supplement soils. To date, most animal manure is put on soils without any manure processing. However, upgrading animal manure to a high-quality organic fertiliser through anaerobic digestion could better the outcomes and produce energy in the form of biogas by reducing volumes (hence reducing storage problems), exterminating pathogens, and enhancing soil nutrients. On top of that, as an add-on climate change mitigation technology, further animal manure treatments could also significantly reduce CH₄ emissions.

Knowing this potential, the Indonesian Government has set up an ambitious goal to employ biogas in its energy mix as part of the Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC). This plan includes generating 5.5 GW of electricity from biogas by 2025. However, as of 2020, biogas' utilisation for power is only 96.2 MW or 1.33% of the 2025 target (Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources, 2020).

In addition to large-scale biogas, as part of President Regulation No. 22 the Year 2017 on National Energy Planning (RUEN) to improve clean energy access and accelerate the substitution of oil fuel with gas in the household sector, Gol is preparing a roadmap to achieve biogas production at 47.4 mmscf for household uses by 2025. To achieve this target, 1.7 million household-scale biogas digesters need

to be installed (Dewan Energi Nasional, 2019). To date, 47,505 small-scale biogas digesters have been installed across Indonesia, resulting from assorted funding from the national government, foreign aid, and private institutions, producing 26.72 Mm³ annually (Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources, 2020).

4. Co-design of LMT narratives

4.1 Introduction

The Updated NDC submitted in 2021 reflects the progression beyond the existing NDC as well as new elements, including (1) enhanced ambition on adaptation as depicted in Annex 2, (2) enhanced clarity on mitigation by adopting the Paris Agreement Rules Book (Katowice Package), (3) national context that relates the existing condition, milestones, along with national development, from 2020 to 2024, and indicative pathways towards a long-term vision, (4) translating the existing NDC into the language of the Paris Agreement, and (5) translating Indonesia's updated NDC also seeks international cooperation options to help the attainment of the conditional target of up to 41% compared to the business as usual scenario.

Indonesia presents the Long-term plan for Low carbon and Climate Resilience in 2050 following the mandates of Article 4, Paragraph 19 of the Paris Agreement, and Paragraph 35 of the Dec. 1/CP.21 (LTS-LCCR 2050). Considering economic growth, climate resiliency, and impartiality, Indonesia is laying the groundwork for reaching a peak emission level by 2030, with forestry and other land uses as the leading sector and net-sink towards net-zero emission. The LTS-LCCR 2050 paper represents Indonesia's higher 2030 NDC ambitions (Ministry of Environment and Forestry, 2021).

Through LTS-LCCR 2050, Indonesia will increase its ambition on GHG reduction by achieving the peaking of national GHG emissions in 2030 with a net-sink of forest and land-use sector, reaching 540 Mton CO₂e by 2050 and exploring the opportunity to progress toward net-zero emission in 2060 or earlier rapidly. In order to reach this objective, the forestry sector will contribute significantly to the maintenance of the net-increasing sink trend after 2030, as well as to the significant transformation of the energy sector by increasing the proportion of renewable energy in the energy mix, boosting energy efficiency, reducing substantial amounts of coal consumption, and implementing Carbon Capture Storage/Utilisation (CCS/ CCUS) and Bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS).

This ambitious goal necessitates transformational changes in both the energy system and the food- and land-use system, which must account for potential trade-offs among many objectives, including energy security, food security, biodiversity conservation, avoiding deforestation, freshwater use, and competing land use. Indonesia believes adaptation and mitigation play complementary roles in responding to climate change at distinct spatial, temporal, and institutional scales. The LTS-LCCR 2050 establishes the objective of adaptation pathways to reduce the impact of climate change on national GDP loss by 3.45% by 2050 through strengthening resilience in four fundamental necessities (food, water, energy, and environmental health), with three resilience target areas (economy, social and livelihood, ecosystem and landscape) (Indonesian Ministry of Forestry and Environment, 2021).

Based on Operational Plan Indonesia's FOLU Net Sink 2030 published by the Ministry of Environment and Forestry in 2022, in the long-term strategy, the emission level in the LCCP scenario is significantly lower than in the present policy scenario (CPOS), which is an extension of the NDC scenario without conditions. By 2030, the forestry and other land use sector (FOLU), which was previously a net emitter, will become a net sink according to the LCCP (Low Carbon Compatible with Paris Agreement aim). The FOLU sector's net sinks are anticipated to increase until 2050. This sector plays a significant role in

achieving the national NZE target, particularly in offsetting emissions from difficult-to-reduce sectors such as the energy sector. Significant efforts to cut FOLU sector emissions and convert them to net sinks by 2030 (under the LCCP scenario) will depend significantly on the success of the following actions:

- a) reducing emissions from deforestation and forest degradation by expanding protected natural forests, increasing community participation, and strengthening community partnership in forest management;
- b) increasing the carbon sequestration capacity of natural forests by reducing forest degradation and increasing its regeneration through the enrichment or implementation of a sustainable forest management system;
- c) increasing the carbon sequestration of land systems by maximising the use of inefficient or low-carbon land use for the development of forest plantations and other perennials (industrial crops);
- d) reducing emissions from fires and peat decomposition by enhancing peatland management systems;
- e) enforcing the law.

As a baseline for implementing the NDC, the Indonesian government has prepared a mitigation road map. The Road Map guides stakeholders, including the government, local governments, businesses, and the community, to achieve NDC targets by providing information on the planning, timing, and setting of detailed GHG emission reduction targets by subsector, as well as identifying all relevant factors that contribute to achieving targets.

Table 10 Sector emission reduction targets in NDC

No	Sector	2010 Emission (million tonne CO ₂ e)	2030 Emission Level (million tonne CO ₂ e)			2030 Emission Reduction			
			BAU	CM1	CM2	million tonne CO ₂ e		% from BAU	
						CM1	CM2	BaU	CM1
1	Energy ¹	453,2	1.669	1.355	1	Energy ¹	453,2	1.669	1.355
2	Waste	88	296	285	2	Waste	88	296	285
3	Industry	36	70	67	3	Industry	36	70	67
4	Agriculture	111	120	110	4	Agriculture	111	120	110
5	Land & Forestry ²	647	714	217	5	Land & Forestry ²	647	714	217
	Total	1.344	2.869	2.034		Total	1.344	2.869	2.034

Note: ¹ including fugitive emission; ² including peat fire

The literature review and a few interviews with relevant experts provided guidance and information to narrow the long list LMTs to the four selected ones. These four are considered for further analysis (with the help of model simulations) within the LANDMARC project. Before such an assessment can be done, a narrative or storyline for each selected LMTs needs to be developed. The following sections provide the qualitative narratives of the four LMTs for Indonesia.

- Afforestation and Agroforestry (see section 4.2)
- Peatland Management (see section 4.3)
- Agriculture (see section 4.4)
- Soil Carbon Enhancement (Biogas and Compost) (see section 4.5)

4.2 Afforestation and Agroforestry

4.2.1 Introduction

Since forests cover 65% of Indonesia's total area, forestry and land use are the main contributors to Indonesia's greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (Ministry of Environment and Forestry, 2016). Indonesia lost 26.8 million ha of tree cover from 2002 to 2019, where 37% occurred in the humid primary forest. The tree cover lost in the primary forest is equivalent to a 17% reduction in total loss since 2000, contributing to the release of 10.9 Gt of CO₂ emissions in this period (Global Forest Watch, 2021).

A study in 2019 reported three significant deforestation causes in Indonesian forests between 2001 and 2016 (Austin et al., 2019): 1) large-scale oil palm and timber plantations, which together contributed more than two-fifths of nationwide deforestation, 2) conversion of forests to grasslands (pastures), which made up around one-fifth of total deforestation, and 3) small-scale agriculture and plantations, which also comprised one-fifth of national deforestation. Hence, negative emission solutions are implemented to reduce deforestation activities. Based on LMTs, the main contributor to emission reduction in 2019 was the forestry and peatland sector. More than 80% of emission reductions are achieved through afforestation, forestation, and restoration (BAPPENAS, 2020a).

Climate mitigation in forestry refers to all actions that can reduce carbon emissions and sequester carbon into forestry carbon stock through preserving and improving forest area and coverage. This can be achieved by carbon stock preservation and carbon stock enhancement. Carbon stock preservation will include all technologies and practices to prevent deforestation or forest degradation, forest fires, illegal logging and forest clearing/conversion, and land utilisation beyond the concession area by certain groups. Carbon stock enhancement includes forest rehabilitation, i.e. afforestation and reforestation (I. W. S. Dharmawan, personal communication, May 6, 2021). Referring to REDD+ (Reduction Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation), five land-based mitigation actions in the forestry sector are reducing deforestation and forest degradation, forest carbon enhancement, carbon conservation, and sustainable forest management (SFM). SFM includes agroforestry, reducing illegal logging, and forest rehabilitation, and covers 30 million ha of forest. The forestry sector has a potential Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) of 17.2% of dryland and wetland land use. This contribution is large compared to other sectors (Y. Rochmayanto, personal communication, May 5, 2021).

FOLU Sector Mitigation Actions to Achieve Net Sink by 2030 (Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK), 2022):

- a. Conservation of forest resources against deforestation and degradation

The results of the spatial template analysis indicate that 10.48 million hectares of diverse forest functions are at risk of destruction in natural forested regions. The risk is greatest outside the forest area (APL) and lowest within the PBPH-HT. The threat of deforestation is classified as either deliberate or unplanned. Planned deforestation is the legal conversion of natural forest to non-forest, including within the production zone designated for agriculture operations (production directive) and HPK that

may be changed for other purposes. Unplanned deforestation is the conversion of natural forests to non-natural forests due to illicit activity (forest encroachment) or natural calamities like forest fires. According to the LCCP scenario (MoEF, 2021), the total amount of natural forest that can be transformed until 2050 is restricted to 6.8 million hectares. To preserve the goal of zero net emissions, natural forest conversion must be minimised as much as feasible.

b. Prevention of deforestation in concession areas

Included in protecting primary natural forests in concessions are safeguards against both planned and unexpected degradation. Protection against planned degradation entails updating the forest management plan to retain primary natural forests exclusively for NTFP. In contrast, protection against unplanned degradation focuses on the disturbance of primary natural forests maintained inside the concession area. For the 2030 net sink target to be met, the maximum allowable area for primary forest degradation is 2.28 million hectares. In primary forest areas, there is a need for an incentive program for concessions to alter their business plans from timber forest production to non-timber forest products or environmental services.

c. Plantation forest development

To meet emission reduction goals, efforts must be made to expedite the establishment of industrial forest plantations. This will aid in decreasing industrial timber's reliance on domestic and international natural forest supplies. According to the Indonesian National Forestry Plan's (RKTN) forecasts of future wood demand, industrial forest-planted lands are required. It is estimated that 11,2 million hectares of forest have been created. The potential area accessible for forest plantation expansion in the PBHP HT and PIAPS (Indicative Map of Social Forestry Area) areas is only 2.04 million hectares, based on template evaluation. The development of planted forests has reached 5.12 million hectares, leaving a shortfall of 4.07 million hectares. To address this shortfall, plantation forest growth can be implemented in concession lands already occupied by the community to cultivate seasonal and permanent crops under the Forestry Partnership's social forestry initiative. As part of the Rehabilitation with Rotation activity, one method to address the deficiency is establishing agroforestry systems that blend plantation and crops with plantation forests. This is accomplished by expanding social forestry lands in Community Plantation Forests (HTR).

d. Sustainable Forest Management (SFM)

The availability of land to enhance carbon stocks (rehabilitation) is limited, and the increase in carbon uptake can be accomplished by enhancing the capacity of secondary forests to absorb carbon through ENR and RIL. To attain the net sink objective (at least until 2030), the concession area that has implemented a sustainable forest management system through enrichment activities (such as SILIN) and RIL must reach 2,2 million hectares. However, the implementation of SILIN and RIL activities has only reached 0.43 million hectares until 2019. Consequently, the implementation of SFM towards the net sink objective until 2030 must be at least 1.77 million hectares. According to the analysis, the potential area for RIL implementation reaches 1.52 million hectares in the PBPH Natural Wood and PBPH-HT. The ENR implementation covers 0.25 million hectares across many forest functions.

e. Reforestation and land restoration

A component of the carbon stock-increasing mitigation activity is rehabilitation efforts with rotation. To reach the FOLU Net Sink target by 2030, 2.79 million hectares must be rehabilitated using a rotation method. The progress of rotational reforestation through 2019 reached 2.73 million hectares; therefore, the area for rotational reforestation through 2030 is just 0.05 million hectares. To accommodate the plantation expansion (4.07 million hectares), approximately 4.12 million hectares must be rehabilitated and rotated. Most fulfillments are located outside the forest area (APL) in the form of unproductive land (non-forest cover). They are included in the area designated for the development of community forests. 2.51 million hectares of non-rotational restoration are required until 2030 to reach the net sink target. As a result of the implementation's expansion through 2019, the land area only reached 0.62 million hectares. The required land area is, therefore, 1.89 million hectares. The largest areas are in the provinces of Central Kalimantan and Riau. This area contains a portion of the mangrove environment, which comprises around 90,000 hectares. Some of the coastal swamp ecosystems (tidal swamps) have the potential to be converted into mangrove forests.

f. Conservation of biodiversity

As part of the endeavour to minimise greenhouse gas emissions in the forestry and land sector, biodiversity conservation can be regarded from multiple angles, such as the conservation of wild plants and animals, the conservation and protection of habitats, and the participation of local communities. Currently, there are 38 million hectares of high conservation value (HCVF) lands, of which 1.51 million hectares are in high-risk areas that must be safeguarded from conversion. There are more animal deaths outside of protected areas. Therefore, the protection of HCVF outside the conservation area is crucial for ensuring animal protection and preventing animals from leaving the corridor—the distribution of places for executing mitigation efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions based on spatial analysis. Mitigation actions in the FOLU sector are focused on five main mitigation actions, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Action diagram of NDC mitigation road map (Ministry of Environment and Forestry, 2021).

4.2.2 Policy context

Policies and Regulations

To contribute to the REDD+ and Paris Agreement on Climate Change, Indonesia formulated NDC and pledged to reduce 29% of carbon emissions by 2030, which 15% out of 29% had been achieved. The goals are further formulated in Regulation of MOEF SK.679/MENLHK/SETJEN/KUM.1/12/2017 on Monitoring the Implementation of NDC. NDC is further derived into more refined regulations corresponding to each strategic climate mitigation action.

In general, there are two major activities of climate mitigation in forestry. First, the carbon stock preservation activities include preventing deforestation, forest fires, illegal logging/conversion, and prevention of non-forest land expansion into the forested area. Second, the carbon enhancement efforts include afforestation, reforestation (also known as social forestry projects), and rehabilitation of various high conservation value (HCV) and high carbon stock (HCS) ecosystems (van Noordwijk et al., 2014). These projects aim to increase environmental services such as water cycling, carbon sequestration, and nutrient cycling. These activities are funded by the government fund (APBN and regional fund - APBD) and private fund (bilateral or multilateral donations, NGOs, private companies, and initiatives). Besides, the forestry sector is expected to contribute 17.2% or 498Mt CO₂e out of the 29% commitment. However, this also includes peatland as it is considered to be managed under forestry management (Tacconi et al., 2019).

In the National Forestry Plan 2011-2030, MOEF pledged to rehabilitate 11.55 million ha of the degraded and industrial forest by 2030. A series of regulations issued by MOEF, including MOEF's Regulation No. 70/2017 on Implementation Procedures of REDD+, Role of Conservation, Sustainable Management of Forest, and Enhancement of Forest Carbon Stocks, No. 71/2017 on Implementation of National Registration Systems of Climate Change Mitigation³, No. 72/2017 on Implementation Guidelines on Measurement, Reporting, and Verification of Climate Change Mitigation Actions and Resources, and No. 73/2017 on Implementation Guidelines on Inventory Reporting of National Greenhouse Gas Emissions (Ditjen PPI KLHK, 2021).

The Low Carbon Development Initiative (LCDI), initiated by BAPPENAS (Ministry of Development and Planning) with various stakeholders, recommends forestry policy changes. The forestry policy is also included in Presidential Regulation No. 18/2020 on Medium-term National Development Planning 2020-2024 (BAPPENAS, 2020b). The 2045 goal of maintaining 41.1 million hectares of primary forest is among the high priorities. In response to high deforestation, GOI (The Government of Indonesia) relies on reforestation and afforestation to reduce deforestation rates and other measures such as fire prevention and halting new permit issuance. The permit policy is based on President Instruction (INPRES) No. 5/2019 on Termination of New Permit Issuance and Amendment of Primary Forest and Peatland Management). This regulation is a revision from its preceding regulations – INPRES No. 6/2017 and INPRES No. 10/2011 on Halting of New Permit Issuance and Amendment of Primary Forest and Peatland Management. The regulation limits land deforestation and encourages HCV and HCS areas (JDIH BPK RI, 2019). Based on 2009-2019 spatial data, the deforestation trend in Indonesia has been decreasing (Tacconi et al., 2019). On the national level, the One Map Policy aims to harmonise the land-use map and recognise land ownership of the private sector.

On the new FOLU Net sink 2030 document (Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK), 2022), mitigation actions based on priority locations in the forestry sector are:

- 1) Preventing deforestation and forest degradation (FD) Priority locations for adopting this mitigation measure are natural forest areas situated in relatively high IPL and within protection and production zones determined by IJL (Location Priority index). High IPL areas are susceptible to conversion to non-forest or degradation. To ensure the continuance of the forest's provision of environmental services and forest products, the area still covered by natural forest under protection and production must be maintained.
- 2) Preventing Forest Loss in Concessions (Forest Utilisation Business Permit or PBPH). A management approach geared toward using NTFPs (Non-timber Forest Products) is required to prevent the degradation of forested lands in the PBPH under the protection zone, given that part of the areas are still in the form of the primary natural forest.
- 3) PBPH-HT Plantation Forest Development (plantation forest). Priority places for establishing plantation forests in PBPH-HT concession and social forestry areas (PIAPS) are all unproductive lands in the production zone. In the rehabilitation zone, unproductive land is used for a non-rotational rehabilitation program.
- 4) Sustainable Forest Management (PHL). In both PBPH-HA and PBPH-HT concession areas, forest enrichment activities (enhanced natural regeneration, ENR) and low-impact logging methods (RIL) are a priority for implementing PHL activities. ENR initiatives focus on concession areas dominated by natural forests in the conversion and rehabilitation zone and secondary forests in the production zone with a high IPL. SILIN Technique's application is that ENR can raise the production of natural forests by three to four times the current productivity or by 90 to 120 m³/ha/cycle. Meanwhile, RIL activities focus on concession areas where primary forest still covers the land, which is included in the production zone.
- 5) Enhancement of carbon stock in forests (PCK). To increase forest carbon stocks, the land is rehabilitated either inside dryland or wetland (Mangrove and Peatland Forests) by planting trees that can be harvested for wood (rotation) and those that cannot be harvested (non-timber forest products) (non-rotation). Priority places for rehabilitation with rotation are production forest lands with relatively high IPL covered by unproductive lands and agricultural lands within the production zone that is not peatlands. Priority places for rehabilitation without rotation are lands with relatively high IPL in both production and protection forests. The land cover of these areas consists of unproductive, seasonal, and perennial crops located in the protected zone and not on peatlands. Agroforestry refers to rehabilitating degraded land with seasonal and perennial crops.
- 6) Natural Forest Protection The current natural forest, both within forest areas (conservation forest, protection forest, and production forest) and outside forest areas (APL), must be preserved, including through conservation efforts. Natural forest conservation is practised outside the protection zone to preserve places with high conservation value, as identified by IJLH within the protection zone.

For law enforcement to have a continuous and consistent implementation, efforts must be made to establish appropriate policies and procedures. Since 2016, law enforcement has focused mostly on forest fires, forest encroachment, and illegal logging cases, which will be conducted continually.

Based on the earlier criteria for identifying the priority site and considering the emission reduction target for the 2030 net sink, Table 4 depicts the land distribution for implementing mitigation actions in each forest function. It is vital to consider institutional typology to create synergies between the Ministry of Environment and Forestry and other partners in priority areas. It is anticipated that FMUs (Forest Management Units) with Types 1 and 3 will be able to coordinate and establish synergies between programmes from diverse organisations at the site level due to their high institutional capacity. In the meantime, in key regions where the FMU Types are 2 and 4, institutional capacity remains poor, necessitating institutional strengthening efforts.

Table 11 The area of implementing the mitigation action programme according to area stakeholders (Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK), 2022).

Area	Type of Management	Deforestation/ Degradation ³	Degradation in Concession	PFD		SFM ¹		EFCS ⁵		PLM		HCVF ⁶	Total ⁸ (Ha)
				HT/HTR ⁴	ENR	RIL	Rotation	Non Rotation	WM ⁴	Restoration ⁵			
Non Forest area (APL)	Non HGU-PEMDA	3.973.073	-	-	-	-	1.640.824	92.689	-	-	-	1.350.742	5.706.586
HGU-APL	HGU-PEMDA	642.685	-	-	-	-	349.600	34.499	956.682	65.769	440.471	2.049.234	
Conservation Forest	Conservation	915.775	-	-	548	-	-	647.229	-	9.351	-	1.572.902	
Protection Forest	Non SF-Ptn	476.196	-	-	4.597	-	-	126.185	-	-	-	14.128.824	606.978
	SF-Ptn	71.728	-	-	1.060	-	-	39.235	-	-	43.440	1.459.031	155.464
Production Forest	Non Concession-Pdn	942.184	-	-	3.260	-	146.198	231.225	-	-	-	11.095.028	1.322.867
	Pdn-CPF	215.003	-	-	1.882	-	317.243	128.576	-	-	763	840.150	663.467
	PBPH-NATURALLY GROWN TIMBER	613.324	4.398.626	-	110.502	1.460.332	321.205	6.508	-	-	18.772	5.460.254	6.929.270
	PBPH-HT	1.974.995	233.885	1.346.427	118.953	64.122	1.243.630	383.201	718.021	210.408	1.443.708	6.293.643	
	KPHP-SF	324.310	-	697.901	2.627	-	77.730	177.058	-	-	147.428	1.750.410	1.427.053
	PBPH-RE	326.313	58.130	-	2.859	-	22.768	20.596	-	-	9.209	360.930	439.874
Peatland Management by BRGM ⁷		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.382.019	-	1.382.019
TOTAL		10.475.586	4.690.641	2.044.328	246.288	1.524.454	4.119.197	1.887.000	1.674.703	1.887.159	38.329.548	28.549.356	
TARGET of Net Sink 2024¹		3.142.141	1.705.000	9.307.332		1.413.203	1.951.493	1.756.344	785.439	1.996.762			
TARGET of Net Sink 2030¹		4.225.877	2.282.500	11.227.332		2.207.061	2.787.847	2.509.062	946.050	2.724.866			
Progress until 2019²		4.803.000	441.416	5.116.662		436.319	2.734.992	622.269	N.A.	835.288			

Main Actors

Several actors play roles in the forestry mitigation sector, such as MOEF (regulator and planner), local government (at the provincial and city level), NGOs, private actors, and local communities. Some private companies harvest carbon stock and then monetise their carbon stocks through results-based payment or voluntary carbon markets. The private sector has quite high control where nationally, 30-40% of forest land is generally owned by the private sector, which must have mandatory restoration and is proven to undergo sustainable forest management (reduce impact logging). On the other hand, local communities, including indigenous people, hold social forestry in Peatland Care Village/Desa Peduli Gambut. Indigenous people living within the customary forest (Hutan Adat) prevent forest fires and protect the forest. Leaders of customary forests are usually respectable local figures. Forest area provided by the government to be utilised and managed by indigenous people as the customary forest is 4.2 million ha.

The demand for fast-growing plant products from community forests is significant and can even contribute to negative carbon emissions. The community also has a big share, where community activities determine land use, for example, in social forestry or community forests. This activity can be seen in forest management by the community in Kalibiru (a tourism place in Yogyakarta, Java Island), where the forest is cleared for eco-tourism. However, the people's growth of community forests and forest utilisation is still lacking outside of Java, in contrast to Java Island (Y. Rochmayanto, personal communication, May 5, 2021). The use of forests by the community can refer to article 6 of Presidential Regulation No. 88/2017 on Settlement of Land use in Forest Areas. This policy states that parties as owners of TORA (Land the Object of Agrarian Reform) could be defined as individuals, agencies, social/religious bodies, and indigenous peoples.

Funding

The government employs two strategies to achieve this target: intensive and incentive rehabilitation. While intensive rehabilitation is centred on priority areas and relies entirely on national funding (APBN) and government activities, its counterpart focuses on involving local communities in reward-based rehabilitation activities. The idea of incentive rehabilitation is to provide financial incentives for local communities that promote their commitment to maintaining and rehabilitating adjacent forestlands near their residence. This dual-objective forest utilisation by local communities could fall under the agroforestry umbrella (MOEF, 2020b).

Indonesia has generated preliminary financial projections for FOLU Net Sink 2030 based on the standard cost of mitigation activities outlined in the NDC's roadmap for implementation. Estimates indicate that the overall funding for executing mitigation initiatives leading to a net sink might reach 15,379,817,300 USD by 2030. The cost of forest conservation from deforestation is \$7,142,927,700, with the private sector contributing approximately 34% and the public and state budgets covering the remainder.

Forest conservation from deterioration requires a private sector investment of \$3,024,482,900, which must be remunerated with a results-based payment for environmental services. The private sector contributed 94% of the 39,125,225 USD required for enrichment activities, whereas all 49,356,986 USD required for RIL operations came from the private sector. Rehabilitation initiatives using rotation require a total of 514,805,600 USD, with 47% coming from the private sector. Non-rotational rehabilitation efforts require a budget of 257,402,800 USD, with a contribution of 24% from the private sector.

4.2.3 Current Land Use and Potential Land-Use Competition

Indonesia's forests are the third largest, with tropical forests and donations from Kalimantan and Papua's rain forests. According to data from Forest Watch Indonesia (FWI), an independent Indonesian forest monitoring agency, 82 hectares of Indonesia's land area is still covered by forests (KLHK, 2020b). Land-use change in the forestry sector will be the main discussion regarding land-use management and emission production. Once land-use change or forest fires occur in the primary or secondary forests, massive carbon emissions will be produced. Based on its historical utilisation, primary forests are referred to as forests that have not been altered and still contain a natural ecosystem. Secondary forests are forests regrown naturally from previously disturbed primary forests. This disturbance can be intentional, such as through forest clearing to obtain wood or unintentional, such as natural disasters. The regrown forest in the new area used for other land use, such as agriculture, would be planted or industrial if the planting were intended for lumber production (FAO, 2000).

In 2019, there were 17.3 million hectares of forest cover, of which 12.5 million ha were covered by primary forest and 4.7 million ha was secondary forest. Primary and secondary forests are limited in use for the public, in which any activities within primary forests aside from scientific research projects are prohibited from the public. The activities within the secondary forest were also limited, but various indigenous, religious, and social activities were still allowed to a limited extent. A secondary forest would also function as a buffer to the effect of activities carried out of the forest. There are 0.12 million

hectares reserved for wood production utilisation, including Industrial Lumber Forestry and Planted Forest (MOEF, 2019).

Currently, there is a decrease in deforestation (See Table 3). Based on the interview result (Y. Rochmayanto, personal communication, May 5, 2021), forest areas are considered a development resource in developing countries. It will be difficult to stop land-use change in forestry. Therefore, planned deforestation was announced. Oil palm plantations are still the number one driver, followed by land alteration into mixed farming. Population growth did not directly affect forest area for settlement since population growth is concentrated in urban areas, so land expansion is not required. Deforestation was mainly generated by urban consumption, food, fuel, and fibre demand (Deribew, 2020).

Other than that, there is also another land-use antagonism against forests. For example, the lumber production forests can procure threats as they might be transformed into other plantations or competing land use (A. Hani, personal communication, May 4, 2021). These activities lead to partial deforestation in the forest's centre, such as deforestation for the mining and energy sector and infrastructure development, such as road works. Besides, there are some shifts from one type of forest to another, e.g. from a primary forest to a production area. The direct utilisation of HCV and HCS forest areas is expected to be reduced. Other efforts, such as starting social forestry, limiting forest utilisation to assigned areas only, and agroforestry development, are also initiated.

Table 12 Forest, deforestation and reforestation area in Indonesia 2014-2019 (in a million ha)

	2014-2015	2016-2017	2017-2018	2018-2019
Forest area	-	-	125.92	125.91
Gross deforestation	1.29	0.68	0.64	0.65
Reforestation	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.19
Net deforestation	1.09	0.48	0.44	0.46

Source: (BPS, 2021; KLHK, 2020b)

4.2.4 Climate Risk & Sensitivities

The forests are naturally more resistant to disturbance, mainly areas with high reservation value. A forested area tends to stay as a forest unless there is a huge disturbance. Besides that, Indonesia's natural forest has high biodiversity and is resistant to various pests and pathogen attacks (Shroff & Cortés, 2020). Climate mitigation in forestry is vulnerable to all climate hazard risks but most sensitive to drought and desertification, forest fires, floods, and biodiversity loss. As for forest fires, the risks/probability of fire occurrence can be minimised through various fire prevention actions (A. N. Armanto, personal communication, April 22, 2021). However, the forest is not sensitive to heavy rain. When there was heavy rain, trees could hold raindrops on their canopy, so the water did not hit the ground directly, reducing erosion and flowing the rainwater from the higher canopy to the soil slower. One of the problems that were caused by high rainfall is the translocation of the nutrient-rich topsoil. The soil would be acidic and infertile when the water translocated the alkaline layer. The trees can also be utilised as a windbreak and hold back the wind (A. Hani, personal communication, May 4, 2021).

Resistance refers to the ability of the ecosystem to maintain its form under disturbance. In contrast, resilience refers to the ability of the ecosystem to bounce back to its initial form after being disturbed. However, the monoculture wood production area is not as resistant as other forest types or agroforestry land use. Resilience is also risky; for example, if a natural forest is disturbed by a forest fire exaggerated by the heatwave, it might take years to re-establish itself naturally (Cole et al., 2014). Drought and desertification are currently not a national focus. However, due to Indonesia's diversity of ecosystems, there are a few areas with this risk, e.g. East Nusa Tenggara.

Unsuitable methods of forest management could potentially lead to secondary problems; for example, introducing exotic acacia trees (*Acacia* sp.) in Baluran National Park in the 1980s led to biodiversity problems. The acacia was introduced from Africa and has a high resistance to forest fire compared to the native trees. Due to a consecutively occurring forest fire, the introduced acacia thrives better, and the native tree community is threatened (Caesariantika et al., 2011). Therefore, research on local and suitable trees will be required.

In the case of agroforestry with cocoa trees, the main related climate risks are drought and heavy rainfalls, which will affect the longevity of the plants and their production. Heavy rainfalls can also cause flooding, making the fruits rot. Unlike palm tree plantations, forest fires are not a great threat to cocoa tree plantations in Indonesia as plantations are small scale and farmers do not fire the land to clear the land. Also, intercropping is often practised in cocoa plantations in Indonesia, contributing to increasing resilience. Strong winds can have an impact on pollination and fruit harvesting. In the case of coffee plantations, frosts can ruin the harvest (high altitudes), as coffee plants need temperatures between 15-24 C and altitudes between 1000 and 2000 m. The shade tree *Leucaena leucocephala* is planted to protect coffee trees.

The most important improvements are nutrient retention, prevention of soil erosion and carbon sequestration. Landslides are also prevented as the hydric balance is maintained. Cacao agroforestry in buffer areas helps preserve soil macrofauna and biodiversity. Farmers use biopores to retain moisture in dry periods, producing organic fertilisers. This technique increases the quality and quantity of yields in coffee and cacao plantations.

There are also several risks unrelated to climate risk, such as the conflict between stakeholders. The land tenorial and organisational authority between stakeholders must be made clear. Previously, the lack of clarity in tenorial land authority has resulted in illegal forest utilisation by the rural community around the forest. The lack of clarity in the various governance levels has also hindered the growth of community-based climate change action initiatives due to the lengthy funding application or land use permit procedure.

4.2.5 *Economic implications*

Currently, the forest has a different purpose economically. Permanent forests, protected forest areas, and forest reserves (for flora and fauna) are not economically important as they do not function economically. However, they have high economic potential as they provide ecosystem services that are still underappreciated. These services are still unaccounted for due to the insufficient data, method, and in-depth analysis that could be brought to relevant stakeholders to invest in natural

ecosystem maintenance and enhancement projects (A. Wibowo, personal communication, May 6, 2021).

Furthermore, economically, production forests, convertible production forests, and agroforestry are beneficial. The production forest could produce fast-growing woods such as sengon (*Albizia Chinensis*), bamboo (various species, i.e. *Bambusa* sp. or *Gigantochloa* sp.), and high-value wood such as meranti (*Shorea* sp.) and jati (*Tectona* sp.). In 2018, the production of Indonesian timber forest profited as much as 11,815.56 Million USD (World Bank, 2021). Local communities can benefit from direct and indirect incentives for the programmes with community involvement.

Agroforestry provides short-term income through seasonal and annual crops and essential oils. This practice has the potential for long-term income through lumber (Do et al., 2020). In many practices, high-priced wood such as teakwood (*Tectona grandis*) is considered an individual asset that could be utilised for pension (Pramono et al., 2011). In addition, agroforestry helps create various products in one area, such as coffee and cardamom, requiring shade to grow. Another opportunity also arises when the cardamom market demand increases. On one of the pilot projects, we found that the crops not intended as the major commodity of agroforestry would also result in a new opportunity. Besides, another opportunity might also arise from the international market, in which the export of agroforestry products could be beneficial (A. Hani, personal communication, May 4, 2021).

Another economic value is that the forest form of land use requires low to no nutrient input as they rely on local nutrient cycling. The land managers of production forest and agroforestry do not have to put too many inputs, reducing their reliance on added nutrients. Furthermore, non-production forests such as the National Parks area could also be developed into eco-tourism areas, such as the butterfly as the main attraction in Bantimurung (Sulawesi), Bali starling (*Leucopsar rothschildi*) in West Bali, Komodo Island (East Nusa Tenggara), and savanna in Baluran (Java). However, other factors, such as pollution and habitat disturbance, must be accounted for (Hakim, 2017).

Within the climate change mitigation actions, there are monetary and non-monetary incentives under MOEF for stakeholders who want to participate. For example, there is direct monetary support to initiate climate mitigation action with forestry. Besides, there is an incentive for agroforestry initiatives in seedlings and other facilities. The costs of the LMT implementation have been formulated and budgeted by the Fiscal Policy Agency, Ministry of Finance. BAPPENAS now initiates the implementation of investments in forestry within the governmental sector through their green growth investments. The investments would focus on helping to fund green initiatives that focus on environmental sustainability. Through the modelling done under the current EU Emission Trading Scheme on Indonesian forest, the trade of carbon sequestration in forestry would also potentially increase carbon storage by up to 22% under governmental management (Indrajaya et al., 2016).

4.2.6 Co-benefits and trade-offs

Risks

Permanent forests, protected forest areas, and forest reserves provide high environmental services. However, land use is not flexible, and direct utilisation is prohibited. This limitation in use would also result in a lack of direct benefit reaped by the smallholders and the rural community (Wani & Sahoo,

2021). This would lead to the limitation of livelihood strategy by smallholder farmers and the rural community, making them more vulnerable.

When the scale is too large, revegetation and reforestation generally fail. The average size of a WWF (World Wide Fund for Nature) pilot project is 50 to 100 acres (Z. Warta, personal communication, September 27, 2021). The most difficult aspects of this endeavour are sprouting, planting, and caring for the seedlings. Other obstacles include the inability of technology to achieve adaptation/mitigation objectives. During the dry season, peatland initiatives frequently fail because of dryness and fire danger. Therefore, hydrological and season assessments are necessary to prevent failure. This approach includes a component of assisted revegetation to ensure its success. Rarely is mitigation required in regions with poor infrastructure since the land is deemed pristine. In addition, afforestation poses fewer hazards than rewetting peatland in achieving mitigation objectives.

In addition, micro-level regulations, such as technology, are poorly conceived. In addition, it is preferable to decentralise data integration and funding. This gives local governments greater flexibility over the allocation of financing and incentives. If the data between the landowner and national/international governments are connected, incentives can be offered. By decentralising this initiative, local governments can improve the effectiveness of their interventions. Importantly, conservation or restoration programmes must be site- and objective-specific (Harrison et al., 2020).

The Job Creation Act strengthens the one-map policy. However, execution is inconsistent because it depends on the motivation of each government. Numerous specialised policies and objectives exist in the forestry and peatland industries. However, executing these rules and objectives would be difficult due to complex factors (environmental, social, and political issues). Changes in policymakers also impede the implementation of the LMT. After the transition from centralisation to decentralisation in the forestry and peatland sectors, all decision-making will occur at the provincial level. The capability of the stakeholders will be the focal point of this implementation.

On the other hand, community dissemination is required to get community engagement. Without information, it is less likely that the community will be utilised. For example, if the infrastructure developed impedes boat traffic, the community will not hesitate to demolish it. It will take time to introduce and disseminate the technology to the community. As forest and peatland management communities are located in rural locations, they must learn more about new technologies. In addition, there is financial and informational inequality because only some communities can access them. The issue of gender also plays a role. Additionally, technological adaptation is required to ensure the project has no negative effects. Some community members are not receptive to new technology or practices that will cause them to alter their behaviour.

Co-benefits

Forests would benefit from various ecosystem services compared to other land use types such as settlement and agricultural areas. The forest has the potential to sequester more carbon within the woods and soil. The forest could also be beneficial to provide water and nutrient cycling for other land-use types of surroundings (Wani & Sahoo, 2021). The forests also provide other environmental services, such as indirectly housing the hyperparasites that could help control pests in the agricultural area. The diverse forest could provide more niches for higher diversity and further develop a more

stable ecosystem. A more stable ecosystem would have higher resilience towards various climate risks (Meli et al., 2019).

Utilising degraded areas with forestry would also require longer time and more research. Naturally, it would require succession to reforest the field. However, planting fast-growing and resistant trees such as sengon (*Albizia Chinensis*) would make the reforestation process shorter (Prach et al., 2007). The canopy of this tree could create shades to the adjacent seedlings with longer growing times. After the shading facilitation stage, the sengon wood could be harvested and sold later. Ultimately, sengon as the intermediary tree will result in faster economic return while facilitating the forest's growth.

Based on its use, production forests, convertible production forest, and agroforestry could help increase the livelihood of society directly through various activities. In the agroforestry sector, sustainable management practices, i.e. intercropping (*tumpang sari*), can reduce the overall cost of fertilisers, irrigation, labour, etc. These practices could also reduce the risk of weed growth, pest and disease infestation due to the mutual relationship within the crop, resulting in better farm management and increased farmers' income. Agroforestry is considered to have higher economic value for the community. For people with other sources of income, cultivation of the land can be reduced so that the land area is not required to be productive throughout the year. However, seasonal farming is considered more profitable for people who depend heavily on the land because they need income for the seasons (A. N. Armanto, personal communication, April 22, 2021).

Afforestation of agricultural land is supported by agricultural policy to make agriculture more environmentally friendly. Both production forests – aimed at generating wood – and food forests - directed at producing food – can be realised. Promoting agroforestry in Indonesia could increase tree coverage absorbing as much as 30 million tons of carbon (Kahurani and Finestone (2017). Integrating forestry and agriculture, in our case studies are cacao and coffee farms, delivers certain benefits over the conventional way of land use, such as:

- Increase in spatial diversity and biodiversity

Agroforestry allows for a more attractive habitat for insects, birds and other animals. It enhances habitat diversity to support organisms in addition to naturally occurring co-benefits, such as enhanced nutrient cycling, integrated pest management, and increased resistance to diseases.

- Increase in soil structure and health

Planting trees and shrubs into annual cropping systems can protect the exposed land and soil from wind stress and strong precipitation. The transition from agriculture to agroforestry can increase soil organic carbon by 34% on average (Pennsylvania State University., 2018). Additionally, agroforestry increases root diversity that feeds the living organisms within the soil.

- Carbon sequestration and sink

Agroforestry permanently increases the absorption of CO₂ permanently from the atmosphere in soil organic matter and thereby stores it effectively, contributing to climate change mitigation.

- Alternative sources of income

Agroforestry may generate an alternative income source for land users if benefits exceed costs. These benefits may originate from both product revenues and reimbursements for carbon storage.

- Food Security

Agroforestry would work as a carbon sink in Indonesia and could have several other beneficial impacts on agricultural systems and food security. It can help systems adapt to greater climate variability by enhancing the structural and temporal diversity of the production system, promoting resilience to shifts in temperature, precipitation variation, and strong winds producing more favourable crop conditions.

Trade-offs

To encourage farmers to adopt agroforestry, programs should also be executed, as agroforestry is considered not economically beneficial in the local market. Funds and resources would be required to help farmers and initiatives to start these activities. It would require capital to develop agroforestry and require yields, which are economically beneficial commodities. Other than that, products grown in this sector could be sold at a higher price in the international market through agroforestry recognition was environmentally good practice. The product or crop certification can improve the value (Zingrebe et al., 2020). Besides, some risks need to be addressed. In Java Island, for example, the demand for residential and industrial land is still high, and the price of selling land for housing is very high compared to the income obtained from producing food. On the other hand, there is a risk of the so-called emission leaking or emission displacement where local farmers move from protected forest land (due to REDD+) to currently unprotected forest areas. That activity can lead to forest degradation or deforestation as firewood or timber collection (I. W. S. Dharmawan, personal communication, May 6, 2021).

4.2.7 Risks associated with scaling up

Indonesia is a vast country; therefore, applying a method on the national level is often difficult. For example, it is impossible to create just one recommendation on the national level regarding agroforestry, wood standing and crops, as success in one area might fail in other irrelevant areas. Many regions also still have access to the market to be able to sell their produce. On the other hand, while the nutrient efficiency might be higher, as it requires less input, the yield might be lower than the conventionally produced goods. Therefore, there is a lower income if the products have to compete at the same price as conventional goods. While expanding the HCV and HSV areas in the degraded area will be desirable, it might require a long time to develop. Therefore, the expected ecosystem services will not be directly beneficial.

Scaling up can be difficult at the policy level because each government sector has different focus concentrations. Each sector has different priorities regarding what projects each sector will develop. Each forest region has unique characteristics, so scaling up a programme might pose risks unrelated to management. In the agroforestry sector, the practices would differ in each region and be specific to the local geographic and socio-economic aspects. It should always be initiated with a diagnosis stage (land mapping, social mapping on what is preferred by the society, the market access) and design. The

design stage includes what crops to grow, what trees would be able to be sown, and how the crops are to market (A. Hani, personal communication, May 4, 2021).

4.2.8 *Research Gaps*

One of the biggest challenges in climate change mitigation in forestry is to provide useful, accurate and reliable data. This is because the verification ability is insufficient, the effectiveness of the selected method is often doubtful, and the data analysis is not enough. In addition, the data and how we present it should be able to convince stakeholders to be more eager to participate in Indonesia's green investment. Climate change adaptation activities can benefit the environment socially and economically.

On the national level, Indonesia also requires mapping every risk caused by climate change to implement relevant plans in relevant areas. This activity was conducted because Indonesia has a vast territory and diverse natural conditions, so there is no universal solution for implementing climate change adaptation activities. In the future, a clear system will need to be developed to support development towards adaptation and mitigation of climate change. In the future, developing a clear system to support movements towards climate change adaptation and mitigation is also needed.

Furthermore, the competitive business model of LMTs in the forestry sector also needs carbon pricing implementation with clear guidelines. Forestry research has been widely carried out in Indonesia, but forestry research on how the role of the new futuristic forest function has not been explored much. For example, currently, the main view of the forest is wood, habitat or landscape. If wood is lost, environmental services are lost, and environmental services are limited to the loss of woody trees in the forest. In the future, it is hoped that the analysis of biomaterials, alternative microbes, and other resources in the forest can be carried out. The hope is that when the awareness that there is another potential from forests besides food, fibre and fuel, stakeholders will defend the forest to maintain carbon and potential for future civilisation (Y. Rochmayanto, personal communication, May 5, 2021).

Besides, the government must ensure that local communities receive incentives proportionally to what they have done—identifying an appropriate indicator that can show direct relations between what the locals have done to LMT. It is important to address institutional arrangement issues at the local government level. For instance, there is a need to improve the readiness of local government institutions to implement monitoring and evaluation as well as reporting climate mitigation achievement. The percentage of local regions that report their emission reduction through AKSARA (a platform for city and provincial governments to report their emission reduction) is still low (I. W. S. Dharmawan, personal communication, May 6, 2021).

Furthermore, the National Forest Monitoring System must monitor and supervise operations executing FOLU sector mitigation efforts towards the 2030 net sink, following PP23/2021 on Forestry Implementation (NFMS). Norms, Standards, Procedures and Indicators (NSPK) for controlling, monitoring, assessing, and reporting on the execution of mitigation actions for emission reduction from the land and forestry sector would increase the monitoring of mitigation actions in the FOLU sector (FOLU). In addition, it is a component of the Geospatial Information Network (JIG) of the MoEF and is integrated with the National JIG. This activity entails regular institutional monitoring of reporting plans and implementation of emission reduction initiatives and their accomplishments.

On the other hand, Indonesia has a long history of forestry sector capacity-building collaboration. In the past two decades, there has been an increase in forest and climate-related capacity-building programmes, both as stand-alone programmes and as part of a broader scope of collaboration. To support the achievement of the FOLU Net Sink 2030, international support for capacity building under the Paris Agreement (UNFCCC) and forest-related Conventions will continue to be mobilised.

The research will be crucial in supporting the FOLU net sink 2030 implementation. Indonesia will enhance research collaboration between domestic universities and national institutions with overseas partners. Regarding technological advancement, Indonesia will bolster indigenous technology's role while pursuing technological cooperation opportunities within the Paris Agreement and Convention.

4.3 Peatland management

4.3.1 Introduction

Peatland covers 20.6 million ha or 10.8% of the total land area in Indonesia. Peatland and forestry are the main sectors of NAMA and NAPA programs. Data from MOEF reported soaring figures in carbon emissions from peat fires and peat decomposition. Emissions peaked in 2015 due to extreme warming effects attributed to *El Niño*, wherein peatland fires and decomposition contributed to 802.87 million TCO₂e and 359.52 million TCO₂e, respectively (Table 4) (MOEF, 2020). Aside from natural phenomena such as *El Niño* that frequently triggers fires and decomposition, human activities such as peatland clearings and conversion contribute to the increased vulnerability of peatland. Those activities make forests and peatlands more prone to fires and decomposition. Within the last decades, 6 out of 14.4 million ha of peatland has been converted from natural peat forests into agricultural land and industrial plantation (MOEF, 2017).

Control of peatlands, which includes water level management and restoration, is the primary mitigation measure that determines the forest and land sector's performance in becoming a net sink. Through Minister of Environment and Forestry Regulation No. 15 of 2017, PBPH and HGU authorize landowners in peat ecosystems to maintain the water level of peatlands in their territory to no more than 40 centimetres by enhancing the peatlands' water system. Maintaining the water level as a mitigation measure will lower emissions relative to the baseline water level for commercial crop development. It is predicted that 0.95 million hectares will need to install a good water management system by 2030 to meet the net sink goal.

Restoration activities include rebuilding peatlands by blocking or filling canals, followed by revegetation or planting crops adapted to peatlands' natural properties (paludiculture system). Following the successful implementation of restoration works, the risk of emissions from fires and peat decomposition will decrease. To accomplish the aim set for peat restoration, the area must increase by 2.72 million hectares by 2030. The implementation of restoration works has only reached 0.83 million hectares by the end of 2019. (i.e., there are still around 1.887 million hectares that must be restored by 2030). The research suggests that the potential area for carrying out restoration work is dispersed among forest areas and concessions, both inside and outside (Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK), 2022).

Table 13 Changes in peatland area, peatland area impacted by fire, degraded peatland area, and emissions produced

Year	Peatland area (ha)	Peatland area impacted by fire (ha)	Peatland area	Associated emissions (tCO ₂ -eq)	Area of degraded peatland by biological oxidation (ha)	Associated emissions (tCO ₂ -eq)
2001	1,263,637	109,638		33,421,181	85,987	307,128,896
2002	2,250,157	613,303		179,920,945	238,235	308,503,274
2003	2,030,537	249,046		62,299,323	228,510	309,816,441
2004	2,338,964	410,989		97,093,898	284,551	312,987,663
2005	2,167,285	343,905		77,267,691	350,129	316,588,324
2006	2,951,553	796,588		182,619,459	524,131	319,823,569
2007	2,027,415	113,318		22,315,312	262,858	321,767,378
2008	2,073,015	127,648		24,797,451	274,848	324,341,906
2009	2,527,155	483,517		92,761,804	409,098	327,690,706
2010	1,501,311	89,281		14,701,421	202,130	329,794,183
2011	1,635,292	331,484		57,340,566	258,214	332,869,828
2012	1,507,028	352,500		56,689,395	261,759	334,793,736

To address this problem, MOEF established the Peatland Restoration Agency (BRG) in 2016 to manage and facilitate peatland restoration in seven priority provinces, which make up around 40% of the nation's total land area: Riau, Jambi, South Sumatra, West Kalimantan, Central Kalimantan, South Kalimantan, and Papua. Peatland restoration, which includes three main activities, known as 3R – Rewetting, Revegetation, and Revitalisation, plays roles in preserving and enhancing carbon stock in peat biomass (BRG, 2016). The followings are the detailed explanation for each activity (B. Wardhana, personal communication, May 4, 2021):

Rewetting

Rewetting is important to ensure the required standard of water level is constantly maintained. It aims to prevent excessive drainage (droughts), which can ultimately lead to fires; in the worst scenarios where fire occurs at the surface vegetation, as long as the bottom layer is wet, carbon-rich peat in the bottom would not catch fire. By considering its role in preventing peat fires, rewetting contributes to climate change mitigation by preserving carbon-rich peatlands. 2.5 million ha of peatland will be subjected to rewetting by 2020 to restore its hydrologic characteristics by maintaining peatland surface water level and groundwater table, especially during drought periods (BRG, 2016). Also, rewetting could minimise the risk of peat fires and restore peatland to its original condition.

Revegetation

Revegetation is planting or replanting endemic vegetation in a peatland area. Vegetations above the peatland are the source of biomass that form peats. Peat formation is the result of the incomplete decomposition of accumulated vegetation biomass. Therefore, without vegetation, peat would not be formed. This means revegetation is a form of carbon sequestration, starting with plants' natural carbon capture and then carbon storage when peat mass is formed. Hence, revegetation contributed to climate change mitigation by enhancing carbon stock—the target of revegetation by 2020 covers 670,000 ha of peatland (BRG, 2016).

Revitalisation

Revitalisation is a set of actions to ensure that any economic activities performed on or around the peatland area are well-aligned with the peatland preservation. Many local farmers use peatland to plant commodity crops in Indonesia. The problem arises when farmers purposefully convert peatland into dry land (mineral land) to plant crops that can only thrive in mineral land. This conversion would usually lead to fires from overly drained peatland. In order to prevent peatland conversion and unsustainable management, BRG relies on revitalisation programmes that aim to ensure that farmers that plant commodity crops on peatland always maintain the water level. If plants do not grow well under wet conditions, farmers are advised to convert to plants that favour peatland. By 2020, 185,000 ha of peatland is targeted to be restored for economic purposes (revitalisation activities). Planting commodity crops suitable to the wetland is also called Paludiculture (BRG, 2016).

BRG has been helping farmers by introducing alternative crops that thrive in wet soils. Also, under the revitalisation umbrella, BRG aims to increase sustainable peatland governance and management among the locals by introducing Peatland Care Village, a community-based peatland management programme. Initially, there were only 700 villages, but the number surged to 1000s villages. Besides, this programme also contributes to increased local climate adaptation and resilience since farmers can plant various crop commodities instead of single-crop dependence. Also, this programme can contribute to an improved local economy since BRGM also supports and helps local farmers to market the commodities from paludiculture (B. Wardhana, personal communication, May 4, 2021).

The three NDC scenarios for the forestry and land sector (BAU, CM1, and CM2) are based on the same socioeconomic assumptions, such as the rate of national economic development and population growth. The variables that differentiate the three scenarios are the mitigation policy assumptions and the degree of mitigation measures, which impact the land use dynamics in each scenario. The mitigation measures implemented for each NDC scenario are displayed in Table 14.

Table 14 Area targets for implementation of NDC mitigation actions

No	Action	Scenario	Annual Average	Cumulative			
				2013-2019	2013-2024	2013-2029	2013-2030
1	Mineral Land Deforestation Rate (000 hectares)	BAU	802	6,023	9,956	13,692	14,433
		CM1	400	3,183	5,056	6,837	7,193
		CM2	229	2,081	3,072	3,943	4,117
2	Peatland Deforestation Rate (000 hectares)	BAU	61	408	668	1,025	1,104
		CM1	4	32	56	72	75
		CM2	2	19	28	32	33
3	Mineral Land Degradation Rate (000 hectares)	BAU	818	6,114	10,129	13,960	14,721
		CM1	400	3,191	5,065	6,848	7,205
		CM2	233	2,110	3,124	4,022	4,203
4	Peatland Degradation Rate (000 hectares)	BAU	62	410	672	1,030	1,109
		CM1	4	33	56	73	76
		CM2	2	20	29	33	34
5	Sustainable Forest Management (000 hectares)	BAU	23	83	202	369	409
		CM1	170	647	1,542	2,773	3,058
		CM2	321	1,276	2,982	5,265	5,784
6	Rate of Non Rotational Rehabilitation (000 hectares)	BAU	97	680	1,166	1,652	1,749
		CM1	104	727	1,246	1,765	1,869
		CM2	173	1,211	2,076	2,942	3,115
7	Rate of Rotational Rehabilitation (000 hectares)	BAU	110	769	1,318	1,867	1,977
		CM1	173	1,211	2,076	2,942	3,115
		CM2	156	1,090	1,869	2,648	2,803
8	PBPH Development Rate (000 hectares)	BAU	150	1,050	1,800	2,550	2,700
		CM1	320	2,240	3,840	5,440	5,760
		CM2	320	2,240	3,840	5,440	5,760
9	Peatland Restoration (000 hectares)	BAU	-	-	-	-	-
		CM1	70	489	837	1,186	1,256
		CM2	156	1,091	1,871	2,651	2,807
10	Peatland Water System Improvement (000 hectares)	BAU	-	-	-	-	-
		CM1	-	634	864	864	864
		CM2	-	749	864	864	864

Referring to Article 4 of Decision 1/CP.21, Paragraph 2, the NDC is the heart of the Paris Agreement and a promise that must be met by ratifying countries, which must be reaffirmed every five years. In the meantime, the Long Term Strategy (LTS) is a country's long-term vision or aim for achieving the 1.5°C temperature target. In this instance, the achievement of the LTS target (Table 15) considers the national conditions on a national scale and the worldwide context of emissions, which are global externalities (Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK), 2022).

Table 15 Mitigation action targets for NDC-CM1 dan LTS-LCCP (000 ha)

Mitigation action	NDC CMI			LTS-LCCP		
	2013–2020	2021–2024	2025–2030	2013–2020	2021–2024	2025–2030
Deforestation on minela land	3.638	1.418	2.136	2.279	675	1.019
Deforestation on peatland	36	19	20	145	43	65
Degradation of concession forest	NA	NA	NA	1,320	385	578
PHL	798	1.542	3.058	1,010	1.413	2.207
PBPH-HT	2.560	1.280	1.920	2.560	1.280	1.920
Rotational RHL	831	415	623	1,004	502	753
Non rotational RHL	1.384	692	1.038	1.115	558	836
Peatland water management	713	864	864	624	785	946
Peatland restoration	558	279	419	1,140	579	728
Integration of livestock with plantation and forestry	NA	NA	NA	1,280	580	812

4.3.2 Policy context

Climate Agreement, International Treaties, and Peat Plan

In the national context, the primary national policy that regulates peatland restoration is Law No. 32/2009 on Environmental Conservation and Management Law, including peatland conservation and management. There are also UNFCCC agreements and guidelines that the Government of Indonesia has ratified. Another international policy ratified in Indonesia is The Ramsar Convention on Wetlands of International Importance, especially as Waterfowl Habitat, an international treaty for the conservation and sustainable use of wetlands originally aimed to preserve habitats for migratory birds. Ratification of The Convention on Biological Diversity, informally known as the Biodiversity Convention, is also one of the key policies that address peatland restoration (B. Wardhana, personal communication, May 4, 2021).

To reduce emissions from peat decomposition and fires, peatland management operations should be conducted by enhancing water management and restoration (rewetting, revegetation/rehabilitation/revitalisation, and revitalisation). Priority is given to improvements in water management in PBPH and HGU with plantation woods and plantation agriculture, respectively. Priority places for restoration initiatives are peatlands with high IPL in all forest functions. For land with an unproductive land cover, the activities aim to restore the peatland by rewetting the soil, allowing for natural or enhanced forest regeneration. For sites the community has used for seasonal and perennial crops outside of concessions, the activities focus on restoring the land through developing a paludiculture system.

Institutional Foundation

BRGM is the executor of land-based mitigation in the peatland sector. Through Presidential Regulation No. 57/2016 (later amended to Presidential Regulation No. 17/2014), the President of Indonesia mandated the formation of BRG. Besides, its role refers to Presidential Regulation No. 120/2020 on Peatland and Mangrove Restoration Agency (JDIH BPK RI, 2019). This cross-sectoral agency is responsible for implementing programmes to conserve and restore degraded peat ecosystems and facilitate all sectors implementing peatland-friendly activities. In December 2020, BRG was extended

to include mangroves (hence BRGM), another carbon-rich ecosystem. BRGM now works in 13 provinces adding six mangrove-rich provinces of North Sumatra, Riau Islands, Bangka-Belitung, East Kalimantan, North Kalimantan and West Papua (B. Wardhana, personal communication, May 4, 2021).

Peatland Restoration Targets

In the strategic planning of BRG in 2016-2020, there are three restoration targets, i.e. restoration of hydrology and socio-economic capacity of peat ecosystem, protect peat ecosystem for life support and sustainable peat management. BRG targeted to restore a total of 3.35 million ha of degraded peatland by the end of 2020, consisting of 2.5 million ha from rewetting, 670,000 ha from revegetation, and the last 185,000 ha revitalisation programme (BRG, 2016). By the end of 2020, BRG had managed to restore 25% of its target (835,288 ha). With the four-year extension from 2020-2024, BRGM has additional time to hit the target while also rehabilitating 600,000 ha of degraded mangroves (MOEF, 2020).

Main Actors

From the regulator side, besides BRGM and MOEF, another ministry whose sector is highly interrelated with the peatland restoration MPW (Ministry of Public Works). Within MPW, Water Resources Division covers the peatland's water supply for rewetting programmes. Besides, MPW provides irrigation and drainage for peatland utilised for cultivation (paludiculture) (B. Wardhana, personal communication, May 4, 2021).

Landowners are also among the key stakeholders in peatland restoration. Landowners whose land contains peat are mandated to maintain and monitor the peatland water level. The monitoring and enforcement mechanisms are regulated in Perpres No. 16 2016, which mandates landowners to report the water levels to MOEF biweekly. If their water levels are not up to standards three times a row, MOEF will take over their peatland to restore it to its initial condition. Local communities, including indigenous people, also hold social forestry in Peatland Care Village. They are the implementers of LMTs in the peatland sector at the local level. Lastly, private companies also play important roles in restoring peatland within the ecosystem restoration concessions (ERC) area (please see section 4.3.5).

Funding

The main source of funds comes from the government budgets, either from the central government (APBN), provincial government (APBD) or local government (APBDesa). At the local level (village level), an additional budget is dedicated exclusively to peatland restoration called PRORATA, which has allocated 1 billion IDR annually for each peatland-rich village since 2017. In addition to public funds, there is financial support from bilateral/multilateral donors and international aid agencies. Since 2016, a total of 50 million USD has been garnered from international donors. Besides that, non-fiscal funds are the National Government mandate funding initiative under the Ministry of Finance. Lastly, there is also funding for various proposal-based activities, where the funding can be accessed by various parties, including NGOs and the community, with certain proposals and certain targets.

4.3.3 Current land use and potential land-use competition

Historically in the 1980s, peatland was massively converted for agricultural land. This was attributed to the transmigration programme that mass-transfer people from Java island to less-populated islands. Many of these migrants were farmers who demanded vast agricultural land. In the 1980s, a policy

regulating primary forest conversion (non-peatland) to HTI (Industrial Plantation Forest) was issued. However, in the 1990s, due to mineral land being scarce, a new scheme was issued that allowed peatland conversion to HTI. Since 2010, the competition between HTI expansion with peatland conservation was no longer happening due to the low demand for HTI commodities, e.g. timber. The timber market entered stagnancy due to the increased use of artificial woods (wood composites), reducing demands for land (B. Wardhana, personal communication, May 4, 2021).

In addition, current and future land-use competition are also non-existent since 2018 due to the revision of the 2011 Forest Moratorium Law. That regulation previously only halted the issuance of new permits for primary forest and peatland conversion to the complete termination of new permit issuance. The President Instruction now regulates this (Inpres) No. 5/2019 on Termination of New Permit Issuance and Amendment of Primary Forest and Peatland Management, a revision of its preceding policies – Inpres No. 6/2017 and No. 10/2011 on Halting of New Permit Issuance and Amendment of Primary Forest and Peatland Management (Ditjen PPI KLHK, 2021). The main competition of the peatland sector includes agricultural expansion, mainly oil palm plantations. In addition to agriculture, peatland conversion is risky for infrastructure development. However, due to a more collaborative relationship between BRGM and MPW, MPW has always pledged to avoid peatland construction.

Farmers are frequently lured to cultivate palm oil due to market demand. Consequently, peatlands are dried to make room for palm oil plantations. Land use competition occurs, and implementing permission policies or moratoriums might be problematic. Furthermore, human activities such as intense drainage alter the ratios of CO₂ and CH₄ emitted by peatlands (Landry and Rochefort, 2012). Moreover, higher temperatures will result in a greater loss of these two gases (Landry and Rochefort, 2012). Low emission reduction will be a danger in this sector as a result.

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4.3.4 *Climate risks & sensitivities*

Peatland is most sensitive to *El Niño*, which usually causes prolonged drought seasons and extreme temperatures. However, no matter how dry the peatland is, it would not cause fire unless it is intentionally lit. The human factor is much more prevalent than climate-related changes, such as extreme temperature, and human activities have been reported to cause 99% of peat fires in Indonesia. Additionally, sea-level rise impacts peat ecosystems negatively, while impacts from floods could be positive or negative depending on the salinity level of floodwater. Floods that bring water from rivers benefit peat ecosystems as floods can provide favourable conditions for peat formation and maintain water levels. However, when the floods come from the sea, salt-concentrated seawater could decompose peat masses, and as a result, the remains will get flushed off with the water. Storms,

tropical cyclones, increased weather variability, erosions and landslides can destroy peat ecosystems/landscapes (B. Wardhana, personal communication, May 4, 2021).

The government has paid more attention to peatland due to increased fire activity. Peatlands are drained for several reasons, including a stabilising substrate for construction, increasing soil productivity, or supporting heavy machinery for industrial activities (Landry & Rochefort, 2012). To protect Indonesian peatlands, the government released a new policy under Government Regulation no. 57, where peatlands below 3 meters can be used for cultivation. In comparison, peatland above 3 meters is protected. Drought is as important because dried peatland has a higher risk. Also, drought can cause peat fire. Lastly, flood is a huge risk because drained peatland has a reduced ability to absorb water. Consequently, the water level will increase. As a result, surface runoff and flooding occur when precipitation intensity is high (N. Priyono, personal communication, September 15, 2021).

Loss of biodiversity is also one of the biggest threats to peatland since peat is formed from vegetation remains in the first place. When vegetation biodiversity was lost due to monoculture vegetation or overharvesting, there would be less chance of peat formation. Besides, since vegetation in peat ecosystems is also a habitat for migratory birds, and birds can indirectly and directly provide nutrition for peat vegetation, loss of bird biodiversity could significantly impact peatland (Y. Rochmayanto, personal communication, May 5, 2021).

Tropical peatlands are carbon-dense systems suffering from drainage recently, leading to high GHG emissions and a high risk of fires in peat soils. The fire risk can be reduced by re-establishing hydric balance in peat areas. Peatlands can be restored by raising the water level, re-vegetating and implementing paludiculture. Climate risk factors are fire, droughts (increase in the risk of fire and GHG emissions) and floods, as drained peatlands have a limited capacity to absorb water, increasing the water level and risk of surface runoff.

4.3.5 Economic implications

Presently, policies regulating carbon's economic value are not in place yet. Therefore, there is still no valuation of peatland restoration. However, based on REDD+, mitigation activities can reduce emissions while contributing to the local economy (result-based payments). Local communities can participate in restoring peatland and getting payments based on results (A. N. Armanto, personal communication, April 22, 2021). In addition, many companies venture into a profitable carbon farming business from peatland restoration by trading their stored carbon in voluntary carbon markets. PT Rimba Makmur Utama is a private company that runs such a business. In Indonesia, there are 15 ecosystem restoration concessions dedicated to peatland-based carbon farming.

4.3.6 *Co-benefits and trade-offs*

Changes in agricultural production

Peatland restoration has co-benefits with agricultural production in terms of increased variety of commodity crops. Several crops can grow naturally in the wetland. For instance, transmigrated families (Javanese) used to plant mineral-land-grown paddy converted to farming wetland-grown paddy in their peatland-dominated destination regions. Javanese paddy can only grow in mineral land due to the absence of wetlands on Java island (B. Wardhana, personal communication, May 4, 2021).

Landscape changes

Peatland restoration is also beneficial for landscape development since designing the landscape for peatland, e.g. channel construction needs to consider peat hydrologic law. So, all designs need to ensure that water will flow naturally (slope-like landscape) from the dome (upstream) to downstream. When the landscape is poorly designed, causing downstream peatland to dry out, there is a higher risk of fires.

Biodiversity

The risks and co-benefits between peatland and biodiversity are explained in section 4.3.4.

Nitrogen emissions

Peatland restoration will also reduce nitrogen emissions long-term through nitrogen fixation. However, within the first few years (e.g. three years) of peatland formation, nitrogen emissions are usually peaking due to increased fertiliser uses and the outputs of biodigesters. Similar effects also apply to methane emissions.

Water quality/quantity

One peatland's ecological role is to control the water cycle and retain water during drought, especially in the downstream area.

Local economy and social capital

On top of ecological and agricultural co-benefits, peatland management, especially under revitalisation, can contribute positively to the local economy and economic independence through paludiculture and carbon farming. Also, community-based peatland management activities have patched up a close-knitted society among local communities through collaborative programmes such as Peat Care Village. This program will eventually lead to increased entitlement or a sense of ownership among local communities, which will help prevent land-related conflicts.

Other Risks

The greatest threats are infrastructure and technical obstacles. To regulate the water level in peatlands, it is necessary to construct a water gate, canal, or dividers. During the dry season, the gate is closed to provide moisture for the peatland. This technique has a negative effect on the local population, as people will be unable to access water during the dry season. In addition, the greatest risks stem from technical mishaps, scalability, and the failure of LMT to meet mitigation targets, as

there are hazards of drought, peat fire, and flood if the peatland is not rewetted. LMT implementation will depend on regional circumstances.

The government bears a significant percentage of the risk. The first factor is a lack of political support; it has been noted that massive fires occur around election times. It is assumed that this results from landowners receiving concessions to resolve land or land use permission concerns, and the candidate receives more votes. Second, political instability poses a significant threat since different presidents implement different policies. Fortunately, the president comprehends the issue's central and underlying mechanics. In addition, the period between governments (vacuum of power) also adds to political instability. Corruption poses an enormous threat to the adoption of LMTs.

The local government is responsible for protecting and managing peat bogs. Many municipal governments, however, refuse to act because they believe there is no return on investment. Since BRGM is an agency, its jurisdiction over policy execution is limited. BRGM primarily coordinates and facilitates the plan of the ministry. MOEF, for instance, expects BRGM to rehabilitate 83,000 hectares of mangrove. Peat Ecosystem Rehabilitation Plan is the current national policy for peatland restoration.

In contrast to the national policy, the provincial policy is the Peat Ecosystem Protection and Management Plan, which has a different substance. Other hazards include institutional misalignment, difficulties with policy execution, a lack of institutional legitimacy, and competing local and national stakeholder priorities. For instance, the national strategy cannot be applied locally since both levels prioritise conflicting growth objectives.

Furthermore, when revegetation is impractical, rewetting peatlands effectively reduces the risk of wildfire (Sirin et al., 2018). However, there is no connection between peatland rewetting (R1) and BRGM's revitalization (R3). Revitalisation employs peatlands for economic purposes, such as agriculture, cattle management, and paludiculture. BRGM approaches this issue via the lens of community development. The agency offers a programme to give crop cultivation, animal husbandry, and facilitators to the community. The majority of communities are glad to receive R3. However, once they no longer receive wages from pursuing R3, they prefer to abandon R1. This is a regrettable circumstance because R3 was intended to give compensation for declining agricultural yields. Risks include the lack of technology proximity to local populations, resistance to behavioural change, cultural resistance, the influence on daily life, and priority needs. Since communities are solely interested in raising their income through an instantaneous process, they do not wish to exert additional work, modify their behaviour, or alter their priorities to implement LMTs.

The greatest economic danger comes from trade imbalances. This is due to the gap between community business and infrastructure. The primary objective of BRGM is peat restoration, not community economic development. However, to accomplish this objective, community needs must be satisfied. As a result, trade imbalances will be the greatest threat, given that the market and a supporting system will be necessary to facilitate the environment. The second risk is market dominance/oligopoly. Farmers are dependent on middlemen. To eliminate middlemen, BRGM gives entrepreneurial training to farmers, enabling them to collaborate and market their products to cooperatives, Cooperation and Village-owned Enterprise (BUMDES), or Community Groups (POKMAS). However, this organisation has internal issues. In addition, product quantity and quality will positively

affect farmers with enhanced knowledge and the ability to attract more clients. Farmers are also instructed on organising and utilising existing resources, such as social media and the marketplace. These actions will positively affect the peatland region's LMT implementation (N. Priyono, personal communication, September 15, 2021).

4.3.7 Risks associated with scaling up

There is a lack of homogeneity in peat characteristics across regions, e.g. Sumatera peat has different characteristics from Kalimantan counterparts. These differences are attributed to the historical events that led to basin-like area creation, which later provided a favourable microclimate for peat formation. Due to these differences, peatland restoration has to be tailor-made to each region's unique localities and characteristics. Scaling up local restoration actions to the national level will always possess risks associated with characteristic peat incompatibility (B. Wardhana, personal communication, May 4, 2021).

There is a risk of vertically uneven wetting in peatland rewetting, where the peat's top surface is dry while the bottom is wet. This would happen when the water balance in Peat Hydrological Unit (KHG) is not maintained, leading to fires. Besides, rewetting can also increase the risks of floods and groundwater quality around the peatland area is usually negatively impacted (A. N. Armanto, personal communication, April 22, 2021).

Farmers in peatland regions are less inclined to maintain water levels if they are not informed that dry peatlands have a greater risk of catching fire. Due to increasing revenue, farmers are more likely to cultivate seasonal crops than annual crops. Waste issues, technical difficulties, and scalability are possible dangers in the agriculture and agroforestry sectors. Waste segregation has not been fully implemented, and there are insufficient resources to scale up the LMT. In addition, there are possible dangers associated with using LMT to achieve mitigation and adaptation goals, as well as technological lock-in in the community due to a reluctance to implement new technologies/practices (A. Dariah, personal communication, September 15, 2021).

4.3.8 Research Gaps

The research gap in the peatland sector is not about the management practices (in fact, most studies on tropical peatland were conducted in Indonesia) but rather about instrumentations and tools, e.g. remote sensing and satellite imagery. There are very limited uses for those advanced instruments and tools. On the other hand, the government needs to ensure that local actors receive incentives proportionally to what they have implemented and improve the readiness of local governments to implement LMTs.

Tropical peatland is a carbon-dense ecosystem. However, anthropogenic activities such as forest clearance and peatland drainage lead to high GHGs emissions (Landry & Rochefort, 2012; Sirin et al., 2018). As a result, peat fires are more likely to occur (Sirin et al., 2018). The BRGM was initially formed to handle peat fires in Indonesia. One popular method to rehabilitate peatlands is restoring the hydric balance, as dry peatlands are prone to fires. To monitor the water balance in peatlands, BRGM installed 150 units of water balance monitoring sensors.

Although peatlands are wetland ecosystems (Sirin et al., 2018), soil protection techniques are important to protect peatlands. Additionally, the biodiversity and soil in peatlands should be protected as they are usually composed of specialised species. Maintaining the water level, revegetating peatland, and implementing paludiculture will reduce emissions and store carbon. The BRGM team analysed to identify phytodiversity, and they found that the top 10 cm is rich with micro-organisms and decreases with depth. Therefore, accurate peatland management is important to maximise the biodiversity potential of peatlands (Lunt et al., 2010).

4.4 Agriculture

4.4.1 Introduction

The agricultural sector is one of the country's highest priorities because it accounts for 13% of Indonesia's total greenhouse gas emissions. In addition, agricultural activities are extremely vulnerable to climate change. Meanwhile, climate change mitigation through agriculture is not the main focus of agriculture in Indonesia. Agricultural sustainability is important aside from production, and Indonesia's top priority is rice self-sufficiency or food security. All the activities focus on adapting to the ongoing climate change. Rice production is already declining, and BAPPENAS has estimated this trend to increase in the coming 20 years for all Indonesian provinces. Thus, field productivity should increase by implementing sustainable or carbon-negative schemes, such as land optimisation, organic fertilisers, and further related research and technological advancement (BAPPENAS, 2020a).

The adaptation and mitigation activities are executed in the Indonesian agricultural context to maintain and increase food production. However, mitigation activities are counted as co-benefits from adaptation actions in agriculture. The current agricultural activities focus on increasing the yield of important crops such as vegetables and rice through agricultural intensification. Climate change will result in lower soil health, a higher uncertainty in water availability, and erratic weather changes. An effort to be able to tackle these problems has been made. For example, to lower reliance on more water, the farmers are suggested to do intermittent flooding irrigation rather than flood the rice field the whole cropping period.

This adaptation activity would also benefit mitigation efforts, as the field will release less methane. The rice was only irrigated for a few days, which was considered important, such as the first 110 days of the rice development. The dry-wet irrigation method also reduces carbon emissions. The rice irrigation was cut up to 10 cm after each flood and would not be irrigated before the water level reached –15cm below the soil surface; each cycle lasted for 20 days. However, there is no further verification on how much area was assigned for the new novel crop or the alternative practices to know the real impact (Maswar, personal communication, May 3, 2021).

Aside from the intermittent flooding practices, The Agricultural Research and Development Agency (Balitbangtan) under MoA has also introduced other good agricultural management practices related to climate adaptation, i.e., water-efficient rice management through maintaining soil moisture and cover crop. Other activities, such as avoiding using fire for land clearing, using the otherwise burned straw for livestock feed, or increasing soil organic content, are also suggested for mitigation actions (Litbang Pertanian, 2020). Optimising land use, reducing intensification on

vulnerable soil, and better livestock and manure management will benefit adaptation and mitigation. Furthermore, in some ways, Indonesia implements agroforestry as an LMT. First, intercropping or *tumpang sari* for the crop, plantation, and horticulture land. In less populated areas, agroforestry practice is implemented to improve land intensification and optimisation. Second, the complex agroforestry system utilises the forest margin and produces high-economy plantations, such as coffee, cacao, clove, and others (Dariah, 2020). MoA recorded 114.74 million tonnes of CO₂ reduction in 2010-2019 (BAPPENAS, 2020a). Overall data on land-based mitigation practices in the agricultural sector is shown in Table 5:

Table 16 LMTs in the Agricultural Sector

Year	Potential Emission Reduction (ton CO ₂ eq)
2010	12,080,000 ¹
2011	16,000,000 ¹
2012	14,480,000 ¹
2013	13,640,000 ²
2014	16,060,000 ¹
2015	1,880,000 ¹
2016	6,950,000 ²
2017	8,100,000 ³
2018	12,670,000 ³
2019	12,885,000 ³

4.4.2 Policy context

Policies and Regulations

Indonesian agriculture's main framework relies on 20 years of development planning from 2005 to 2025. This long planning term is further segmented into 5-year middle-term planning (RPJMN) of 2020-2024 (BAPPENAS, 2020b). Each RPJMN period has its importance, and for the agriculture sector, the main goal of the 2020-2024 term is to modernise and optimise current agriculture. The efforts include the development of infrastructure to increase productivity (Gregorio et al., 2015). Other than that, the Indonesian government also recognises the agricultural impact on climate change mitigation. Therefore, the effort to participate internationally in the climate change mitigation movements could be found, such as joining the 2017 Koronivia Joint Work on Agriculture (KJWA), Bonn, conference.

In 2007, Indonesia hosted the Conference of Parties (COP) 13 in Bali regarding climate change policy. This conference helped accelerate Indonesian commitment to joining the international effort to tackle climate change. Regardless of how Indonesia shows its commitment to tackling global climate change, Indonesia still has not formulated policies specifically on climate change mitigation in the agricultural

¹ Land Optimisation, Organic fertiliser and biopesticide, biogas from livestock waste

² Sustainable farm practice in degraded land, peatland management for sustainable farm practice, intermittent irrigation

³ Agroforestry, intercropping, biochar

sector. In defining its framework, the government refer to National Action Plan for Climate Change Adaptation (RAN-API) and RAN-GRK (National Action Plan for Reducing Greenhouse Gas Emissions). These reports are known as NAMA (Nationally Appropriate Mitigation Action) and NAPA (National Adaptation Programme of Action) of Indonesia. In 2009, Indonesia voluntarily promised to reduce emissions by 26% by 2020. In 2015, this target was increased to 29% by 2030 (FAO, 2017)

Currently, no established policies, infrastructure, or system allows for tracing the mitigation impact in agriculture. The budget tagging system was introduced by the Ministry of Finance, with the supervision of other relevant ministries. The budget tagging method was initiated to assess how much fund is used to move towards more sustainable development. The Ministry of Agriculture's tagging method covers projects funded by national funding (APBN) or provincial/city funding (APBD) to enhance farm sustainability. Those programs are research, incentives for infrastructure that support sustainable agricultural practices, and knowledge transfer practices to adopt by the farmers through training (Halimatussadiyah, 2020).

However, sustainable agriculture is a priority, with policy recommendations increasing agricultural land productivity by 4.4% and expanding sustainable agriculture to comprise 45% of all lands. Top priorities are land optimisation, crop cultivation technology, organic fertilisers, and utilising abandoned or previously degraded land. Lahan Pertanian Pangan Berkelanjutan or Sustainable Agriculture Land (LP2B) is a policy issued under MoA, limiting the land-use change of rice fields into non-rice field land use. The main issue that LP2B address is the intensive change of rice fields to settlements. The main goal of LP2B is to maintain the current rice field area so any deforestation due to the demand for more rice field areas can be reduced (BAPPENAS, 2020a) while managing the rice reserve to ensure food safety.

While food reserve goals could be easily achieved by importing the commodity, the governments would want to avoid reliance on rice stock from other countries (Timmer, 2019). In terms of climate change mitigation, the shorter chain is desirable as it would reduce the profit spread across the stakeholder within the chain and further reduce the carbon footprint (Canfora, 2016). Other than managing the carbon emission based on land use management, more localised food with lower food miles is preferred as it would have a lower carbon footprint and lower movement of locally cycled nutrients such as nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium between geographical boundaries (Caputo et al., 2013). However, we also acknowledge the risk of food reserve oversupplies, such as price drops, poor supply quality due to incorrect storage, and food waste not being discussed as much (Waarts et al., 2011).

Main Actors

The government and the NGOs are currently some of the actors within the agricultural adaptation and mitigation to climate change; for example, there is an effort to develop social forestry to rehabilitate the soil. The stakeholders involved in the LMT and defining the land use planning are National Government and Local Government. The local government will have a bigger say in planning land use. In contrast, the Central Government will support the plan. Farmers were also important stakeholders. The farmers are the main stakeholders in applying better field practices. However, they do not understand what they are doing to mitigate or adapt to most of their activities. Most farmers were also more interested in their productivity rather than mitigation. Their participation is also mainly

defined by their willingness to change their organic agriculture or agroforestry practices. Besides, the researcher involved in the application of LMT indirectly might be applied and replicated on a larger scale by the farmers due to lab-scale research.

Funding

Not all environmentally sustainable practices are recommended to the farmers. The recommended sustainable practices should be economically beneficial, easy to follow, affordable, and effective in increasing agricultural productivity. Nationally, some LMTs have been planned to be executed at the national level and are given the budget allotted. Most activities in various sectors deemed to be in line with Low Carbon Development (LCD) or low carbon development by the Central Government are given a certain budget, including agriculture practices. However, currently, there is no funding directly budgeted at the national level for LCD activities in agriculture. Most of the funding for agricultural activities is allocated from the Regional Expenditure Budget (APBD), a locally managed budget on the regional level.

LMT in Agriculture has not been given much attention, and there is less donor funding for LMT in agriculture than in other sectors. The donor funding also goes to big agricultural fields such as oil palm plantations. Compared to other sectors, the agricultural sector is more focused on supporting the economic sector. Investments in sustainable development are also given in agriculture within the Green Investment programs under BAPPENAS. However, donors from various parties are rarely found in the sector since most of the funding is given by the government or initiatives to Farmers Group (GAPOKTAN) rather than individual farmers.

4.4.3 Current land use and potential land-use competition

Currently, 47.3 million ha of land use is utilised for Indonesia's agricultural production (Food and Agriculture Statistics (FAOSTAT), 2020). Most of the land use is for the rice field, covering around 10.6 million hectares in 2018. Rice is one of the important crops in Indonesia (MOA, 2021), in which it is responsible for the emission of 71 Gg CO₂eq greenhouse gasses (GHGs) through the intensive cropping system that is currently still adopted (Food and Agriculture Statistics (FAOSTAT), 2020). However, intensification is considered to be important to feed the increasing population. The rice field's productivity will not suffice to feed the growing Indonesian population, and there would be a need to import rice (F. Agus, personal communication, May 6, 2021).

Each year, the satellite data shows that about 96,000 ha of rice fields are transformed into other land-use types. Based on statistical data, about 50,000-60,000 ha of rice fields transformed, in which currently, there is 7,4 million ha of rice fields left out of the initial 8 million ha (Mulyani et al., 2016). These rice fields were mostly being pushed due to urban and infrastructure expansion.

Rice fields are also now under the pressure of land-use change. Indonesia has various types of agricultural land (See Table 6). The demand for settlement areas had been pushing the rice field around the urban area. Other than that, the lack of land-use impact planning left many rice fields unproductive. The land that can no longer generate income is then sold and transformed into other land-use types. Limiting land openings from forests to agricultural fields positively impacts climate change mitigation. However, with this limitation, it is almost impossible to expand the agricultural field.

This activity would lead to reliance on production in a limited area (N. Mustikasari, personal communication, April 21, 2021).

Table 17 Agricultural land use in Indonesia in 2008 and 2018 (in 1000 ha)

Land use category	2008	2018
Agricultural area, total	54,000	62,300
Arable land	22,700	26,300
Land under permanent crops	20,300	25,000
Land under perm. meadows and pastures	11,000	11,000

Source: (Food and Agriculture Statistics (FAOSTAT), 2020)

Moreover, food production should be able to feed an increasing population, and farmers being given the burden of food production are now under pressure due to limited resources. In many cases, the agricultural sector is considered unattractive for the youth who would leave the agricultural area, abandoning their land (Chaudhary et al., 2020). This issue would also increase the possibility for this left-out land to be built into other infrastructures, leaving only limited land to utilise as agricultural areas (Huijsmans et al., 2021).

Land use optimisation should be optimised to utilise the limited agricultural land as a potential LMT. The depleted nutrient taken out of the farm has to be replenished, and adding fertiliser is one way to ensure soil nutrient availability. The addition of nutrition would be needed to avoid soil mining. Therefore, organic fertiliser would be more beneficial in reducing the environmental impact of agricultural activities (Schjoerring et al., 2019). Reducing synthetic pesticide use would also reduce carbon emitted (Skinner et al., 2019). Developing agroforestry or tree-based land use around the agricultural field would also help provide a habitat for the pests' predators as a form of natural pest control (Zewdie et al., 2021). Intercropping would help to optimise land use and reduce pest attacks. It provides more niches for various organisms within the same temporal range, while crop rotation will help cut the life cycle of the pests throughout the seasons (Risch, 1983; Umaerus, 1992).

4.4.4 Climate risks & sensitivities

The current agriculture is very vulnerable to heatwaves, drought, heavy rain, flood, storms, weather variability, erosion, and ocean acidification. For example, heat waves could kill the plants and weather variability could affect the cropping season. Both drought and heavy rain could affect the productivity of the commodities. The heatwave effect of El Niño and the heavy rain effect of La Niña results in drought and flood that result in failed harvest. The temperature change also potentially results in increased pests and weeds. Ocean acidification mainly impacts coastal agriculture, and change in salinity has caused a problem, and many fields have also become infertile due to the sea-level rise. The effort to flush the salt out of the soil could be made by pouring freshwater or rain. Biodiversity loss is not an immediate problem in the agricultural field, and it might be more relevant to forestry. However, in dry areas and areas lacking freshwater availability, soil salt flushing would be hard to do as it would require manual watering. Forest fire could affect agricultural activities in the area with a proximity to the forest (Maswar, personal communication, May 3, 2021).

On the field level, it was also reported that the rice fields' intermittent irrigation would result in a denser weed community around the rice. Then it would take up the nutrient intended for the growth of the rice, resulting in a lower yield (F. Agus, personal communication, May 6, 2021). The application of organic manure on the soil could also be considered a more sustainable effort to increase agricultural soil health. However, manure over-fertilisation increases the sensitivity of the crops to pests (Altieri & Nicholls, 2003). Other practices, such as low to no soil tillage, would also result in a flourishing weed community that would reduce productivity per hectare compared to the conventional method. However, the minimum tillage practice would be more sustainable in the long run (Busari et al., 2015).

As food security is the primary objective of the agriculture industry in Indonesia, productivity is crucial. Nonetheless, variable weather and extreme weather occurrences pose a threat to productivity. In Indonesia, climate-related occurrences include drought, forest fires (typically not driven by climate variables), river and coastal flooding, and high rainfall. In addition, an excess or deficiency of water reduces soil productivity, resulting in lower crop output. In addition, El Nino and La Nina have reduced land production. Therefore, farmers cannot rely on lunar calendars to determine planting and harvesting dates (A. Dariah, personal communication, September 15, 2021).

4.4.5 *Economic implications*

The agricultural sector contributed 861 billion US\$ in GDP (Gross Domestic Product) in 2015. However, the sector also contributes to a big portion of GHG emissions. A rice field mostly emits this emission, contributing to approximately 30% of the emission (Food and Agriculture Statistics (FAOSTAT), 2020). The change of practices would also reduce this emission and increase farmers' income. However, most of the farmers only have limited income in which it was reported that, on average, each farmer has a monthly profit of approximately IDR 750,000 or EUR 45 (BAPPENAS, 2019).

Unlike the global north countries, Indonesian farms' size is generally small and resource-poor. There are also complex socio-economic problems within the agricultural system. One of the efforts to help these smallholder farmers are to increase their resilience resulting in higher income. To help them apply better practice, incentives would be required. These incentives will be essential for adopting adoption practices, as infrastructure and resources are needed. Reducing intensification might also decrease temporary yield (Abraham & Pingali, 2020).

However, Indonesian farmers tend to use the higher profit for consumption rather than reinvest it due to the lower living quality. Giving farmers subsidies or helping them invest in new resources would help them adopt new practices. However, they would continue to rely on these funds if their farm size is small because it will also yield only low economic returns. It would be important to encourage the farmers to continue adopting the practices and ensure their income during the transition period. In the long run, the reduced emission and agriculture's ability to provide food more sustainably would be beneficial economically, socially, and environmentally. Another strategy, such as corporate funding, might also be applicable. However, this would require further study (F. Agus, personal communication, May 6, 2021).

There is still no official calculation of economic loss on the impact of agricultural activities released by the government and adding the price of mitigation required to the food. By calculating how much

money would be required for the current conventional land management in the agricultural sector, we could also compare how much money will eventually be spent in the agricultural sector to revive the natural resources used in food production (Macháč et al., 2021).

4.4.6 *Co-benefits and trade-offs*

Risks

As previously mentioned, currently, there is no policy addressing the mitigation action in agriculture. Climate action in the Indonesian agricultural sector revolves around the adaptation effort, in which the governments focus mainly on production. As a result, many sustainability types of research in Indonesia would result in both environmentally better performing practices. It would have a similar yield with current production, if not more (F. Agus, personal communication, May 6, 2021).

Different technological implementations exist in the forestry and agriculture sectors. In the forestry sector, the government makes decisions, whereas farmers make decisions in the agriculture and agroforestry sectors. To entice farmers into the agriculture industry, technologies must offer co-benefits. Farmers place greater emphasis on productivity than on mitigation. Therefore, a technology designed purely for mitigation will not be implemented. Organic fertilisers are a successful illustration. Farmers recognise that organic fertilisers generate superior harvests to chemical fertilisers and increasingly apply organic fertilisers to their farms voluntarily.

The inability to incorporate new technology is due to a lack of money. In addition, government entities do not prioritise their activities, making integrating new technologies and/or rules challenging. Nevertheless, this is not a significant danger if the private sector provides the funds. The second threat is political unrest. Each government often has its objectives and programs. For instance, the current administration promotes Porang (*Amorphophallus muelleri*) extensively. Consequently, many farmers cultivate this crop on their land. However, neither party realises that other crops can give them greater benefits.

The two greatest economic hazards are trade imbalances and market dominance. Productivity is the primary contributor to the trade imbalance. Since market needs substantially impact commerce, farmers seek to employ highly productive technologies. Similarly, market dominance has both positive and negative consequences. Middlemen collect agricultural products from farmers and distribute them across the supply chain. This is more cost-effective for farmers because the middlemen will distribute the sales. However, many middlemen do not engage in fair trade, thus impacting the revenue of farmers.

On the other hand, the decrease in the budget due to corruption diminishes the benefits for farmers. To win political support, the government will delay or prioritise a program based on the needs of the people during election season. As a result, implementing new policies is likely to be delayed and ineffectual. The final threat is slow policy changes, which may have positive and negative consequences. Quick policy changes may produce long-term problems, but gradual changes may impede positive progress. Nonetheless, policies must mention their implementation features (A. Dariah, personal communication, September 15, 2021).

Co-benefits

Adopting organic practices in horticultural commodities in agriculture would increase manual weeding and labour hour. However, the premium price paid for organic produce would increase the farmers' income, and the farmers must undergo the certification procedure to obtain the premium selling price. Other risks include increased costs, requiring economic capital and energy from the farmers. For example, a physical labour increase would be required to reduce weeds and pests manually as the farmers reduce synthetic fertiliser and pesticide use. This risk would also hinder the farmers from adopting organic practices (N. Mustikasari, personal communication, April 21, 2021).

Trade-offs

To meet the target and demand, food production would still be ensured. For example, the rice of variant "Ciherang" would have lower emissions than other variances (Kinose et al., 2020). However, the discovery of the Ciherang breed was not intended for its lower emission but rather for higher production. Other practices, such as minimal soil tillage, could also help empower the farmers by allowing them more free time, as the method requires lower labour time. The lower labour time would lead to more free time for farmers that could be utilised for other livelihood strategies that could profit more income, such as working off-farm (Chrisendo et al., 2020).

4.4.7 Risks associated with scaling-up

While much intervention in agriculture is promising, several precautions should be considered to scale up the practices. Agriculture is heavily based on its biogeographic condition (Coe et al., 2014). Each region's differences in natural conditions would result in different suitable practices. In the agricultural sector, there is a big tendency for peer learning, and the farmers tend to duplicate other practices that are perceived as successful. This way, unfit practices are selected naturally. If the farmers are mandated to change their practices, unfit practices will not happen. The failed harvest might lower the farmers' trust in other stakeholders (F. Agus, personal communication, May 6, 2021). Therefore, scaling the practice to a similar area might be an alternative rather than scaling up to the national level (Wijeratna, 2018).

Due to the mitigation action from the lower regional level to a national level, losses have not yet been reported. However, with the knowledge of Indonesian natural resources, it is clear that some practices that would suit one region might not be best applied to other regions. For example, increasing Indeks Penanaman or Planting Index (IP) might be feasible in Java. IP shows how many harvests could be done in a year. Knowing that Borneo's soil is not as fertile as Java, the increase of IP would not benefit Borneo, and it might further threaten the farmers with unprofitable yields. Some varieties and breeds of crops should be considered as they might not be sown in other areas. Therefore, pushing the farmers to sow the crop might cause yield loss and economic loss (N. Mustikasari, personal communication, April 21, 2021).

4.4.8 Research gaps

There are a few knowledge gaps in the effort to carbon capture various land use in agriculture. The knowledge of what agricultural practice will be suitable in each area will be beneficial. These recommendations should be beneficial, easy to follow, and clear for the farmers as the main

agricultural land managers. The agricultural land use potential to capture carbon and provide environmental services will also be beneficial in defining the contribution that the agricultural land-use type could make. A deeper analysis of the socio-economic implication of the recommendation should also be executed. The analysis will be important in defining what strategy should be proposed in applying the practices recommended to the farmers.

4.5 Soil Carbon Enhancement (Biogas and Compost)

4.5.1 Introduction

Waste management is another sector identified as a national priority related to soil carbon enhancement (SCE) activities. The government has set a target of reducing waste emissions by 94% from 2024 to 2030, which has high potential. Anaerobic digestion processes currently contribute to Indonesia's GHG emissions, but compost and other measures of integrated sustainable waste management systems have enormous potential. Furthermore, enhancing soil organic carbon (SOC) in the agricultural sector can be an effective negative emission measure. Out of the total agricultural land of around 62.3 million ha, which makes up approximately one-third of the total Indonesian land surface area, about 82% is occupied as cropland, including land for temporary crop cultivation (arable land) and permanent crops (Food and Agriculture Statistics (FAOSTAT), 2020). For instance, adding only 1%-point of the SOC to the agricultural area could provide a significant storage potential.

Despite the importance of the organic matter in the soil, data for evaluating SOC change in Indonesia is limited due to regular SOC stock and changes monitoring. Although SOC change data at the macro-level (nationwide) is not available, several studies report SOC depletion in Indonesian soils at the micro-level. One study suggested that SOC stock declined by around 30% when a forest was converted to agricultural production (Murty et al., 2002). A study discovered that the level of organic matter in the 0-15 cm soil of lowland rainforest in Sumatra decreased by 48.1 Mg C ha⁻¹ when the forest was downgraded to grassland (Santoso et al., 1997). Another primary source of soil carbon reduction in Indonesia is the loss of carbon from organic soil (peatland), which covers about 14.9 million ha and contains exceptionally high carbon content ranging from 420 to 820 Mg C ha⁻¹ (FAO and ITPS, 2015).

Also, supplementing carbon to soils, such as compost, manure, and digester from anaerobic digestion (AD) of organic matter (e.g., manure), harvesting residues, or processed organic fertiliser, can be performed to improve organic matter levels in agricultural soils. AD-based bioenergy can potentially put CO₂ emissions into negative territory by converting biomass into bioenergy (biogas), sequestering the carbon produced into the soils in organic fertilisers. Considering the high livestock population in Indonesia (Table 7), which has steadily increased in the last three years, there is a massive potential in biogas and organic fertiliser (bioslurry).

Bioslurry is a co-product of anaerobic digestion of wet organic waste) production from animal manure via anaerobic digestion processes. Organic matter content in bioslurry can reach up to 27%-weight 29% and 26% for cow dung, poultry manure and buffalo dung, respectively (Islam, 2011). A study has estimated the total biogas production from Indonesia to be 9,595.6 Mm³/year (Khalil et al., 2019). Since bioslurry is produced three times more than biogas of total dry matter of manure, bioslurry has become a promising carbon sequestration agent through SCE.

Table 18 Indonesia Livestock Population, 2018-2020 (unit)

Species	2018	2019	2020
Large livestock			
Beef cattle	16,433	16,930	17,467
Dairy cattle	582	565	568
Buffalo	894	1,134	1,179
Horse	378	375	392
Small livestock			
Goat	18,306	18,463	19,096
Sheep	17,611	17,834	17,769
Pig	8,254	8,521	9,070

Source: (Ministry of Agriculture, 2020)

Volume-wise, animal manure is the single largest potential resource of soil organic matter and other macro- and micronutrients to supplement soils. To date, most animal manure is put on soils without any manure processing. However, upgrading animal manure to a high-quality organic fertiliser through anaerobic digestion could improve the outcomes by producing energy in biogas. This activity can reduce carbon emissions from fossil gas or firewood, reduce volumes (hence reducing storage problems), exterminate pathogens, and enhance soil nutrients. On top of that, as an add-on climate change mitigation technology, animal manure's further treatments could also significantly reduce CH₄ emissions (Ministry of Agriculture, 2020).

Biogas is a viable option for Indonesia to diversify their national energy mix in moving towards sustainable energy (International Energy Agency (IEA), 2019). It can be produced from feedstocks, including organic and agricultural wastes and dedicated energy crops (DEC). Animal waste, such as dairy manure and chicken litter, municipal solid waste, wastewater, sludge and industrial waste, and food processing waste, are all ideal for biogas production (Kulichkova et al., 2020). The demand is also ever-increasing due to the dire need to shift to cleaner energy and increase electricity production within Indonesian regions. However, biogas feedstock utilisation is restricted to specific types, and applications with several renewable possibilities must be prioritised. For instance, biogas can generate electricity and contribute to renewable energy.

4.5.2 Policy context

In 2017, GOI issued a new regulation of national strategy and policy of waste management. Based on this regulation, GOI targets reducing 30% emission reduction, managing 70% of total waste, and developing waste facilities for households. Besides, in the RPJMN of BAPPENAS, the waste management programs will include solid waste and wastewater. Solid waste management will include the domestic and industrial sectors, such as disposal sites, composting (biological treatment), and incineration. For wastewater, the activities are around wastewater treatment plants (aerobic and anaerobic digestion process) and domestic sewage (BAPPENAS, 2020a).

In addition, MoA has reported reducing emissions by applying various agricultural sector strategies from 2010 to 2019. First, agricultural cultivation technology was applied through rice intensification

(SRI), integrated crop management, and low-emission varieties. Second, organic fertiliser and biopesticides through fertilisers, organic subsidised and procurement of Organic Fertiliser Processing Unit (UPPO) are utilised. Third, the utilisation of livestock and agricultural waste is conducted. Additionally, animal feed supplements can be improved by using low-emission products, for example, leguminous plants (*Gliricidia* sp., *Leucaena* sp., and *Calliandra* sp.). The production targets are achieved by land-use optimisation, extensification for low-carbon fields, and livestock and fertiliser management. Activities related to livestock and fertiliser management include livestock management with containment, feed quality, biogas (methane capture and energy source), balanced fertilisation based on soil condition, and organic fertiliser (carbon sequestration) (Dariah, 2020).

Knowing the potential of SCE, the Indonesian Government has set up an ambitious goal to employ biogas in its energy mix as part of the Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) with dual objectives (climate mitigation-wise), fossil fuel substitution and SCE. This plan includes generating 5.5 GW of electricity from biogas by 2025, although as of 2020, biogas' utilisation for power is only 96.2 MW or 1.33% of the 2025 target (23%) (Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources, 2020). Aside from the energy sector, biogas implementation contributes to LMTs in the agricultural sector. Besides President Regulation No. 22/2017 on National Energy Planning (RUEN), GOI is preparing a biogas roadmap. It aims to improve clean energy access and accelerate oil fuel substitution with gas in the household sector. The target is biogas production at 2,203 Nm³/day for household use by 2025.

To achieve this target, 1.7 million household-scale biogas digesters must be installed (Dewan Energi Nasional, 2019). In addition to manure, Indonesia also produces a large amount of organic waste, which is contained in domestic solid waste, also called municipal solid waste (MSW). In 2017, the country's MSW generation reached 65.8 million tonnes, estimated to grow rapidly for the foreseeable future (KLHK, 2020a). Since organic waste makes up around 60% of the total MSW (KLHK, 2020c), composting processes, either aerobic or anaerobic, could become a significant organic fertiliser source, which ultimately can contribute to SCE.

Furthermore, in the Presidential Regulation No. 97/2017 on National Policy & Strategy on Management of Household Waste and Household-like Waste (JAKSTRANAS), GOI sets the target of 30% waste reduction and 70% waste handling (from 67.5 million tonnes of waste handled in baseline 2019 to 339.4 million tonnes) by 2025 (KLHK, 2020a). The waste handling strategy includes the rollout of composting organic waste processes in Integrated Waste Management Sites (TPST) to reduce the volume of waste to be processed in the Final Waste Collection Sites (TPA). GOI aims to increase the number of households covered with composting services in TPST to 494,152 households (MOEF, 2020), about 0.98% of the total population.

Main Actors

The government and the NGOs are currently some of the actors in the agricultural adaptation to climate change; for example, there is an effort to develop social forestry to rehabilitate the soil. As mainland managers, farmers are one of the main stakeholders in agriculture. The farmers possess knowledge of practices such as using palm oil fronds over the soil, which could help mitigate the soil carbon emission. Practices such as applying nitrogen fertiliser would also help increase soil fertility, fertilise the crops, and help the carbon uptake by the crops (F. Agus, personal communication, May 6, 2021).

Funding

Currently, APBN (national funding) is one source to increase the yield in agriculture, covering funding for various programs such as livestock quality improvement and training. 47,505 small-scale biogas digesters have been installed across Indonesia, resulting from assorted funding from the national government, foreign aid, and private institutions, producing 26.72 Mm³ annually (Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources, 2020). Indonesia refers to Koronivia Joint Work on Agriculture (KJWA), Germany, since 2017. LMT in Agriculture has not been given much attention, and there is less donor funding for LMT in agriculture than in other sectors.

The donor funding also goes to big agricultural fields such as oil palm plantations. Funding for organic food farmers is still less and would only cover small-scale agriculture. Other practices, such as biogas and composting stations, are included in the agricultural LMT. Most of the funding available for biogas and composting is for small-scale projects. Funding at the national level does not exist as the previous national-scale biogas project, SIMANTRI/SIPADU (Integrated Agricultural System), has been stopped. The projects include giving farmers livestock of cows and a biogas installation. The funding was stopped as the project was considered successful and had been replicated sufficiently by other farmers (N. Mustikasari, personal communication, April 21, 2021).

The potential for implementing the water management reform activities considerably surpasses the LTS target, with total private sector funding of 19,369,560 USD. The business sector must contribute 16% of the total 772,208,400 USD for peatland restoration initiatives. Currently, the majority of funding for mitigation efforts comes from APBN sources (state budget), which is grossly insufficient (Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK), 2022). Indonesia has adopted various measures that create prospects for greater diversification of national and international, public and private, financial sources. In addition, Indonesia continues to mobilise international financial resources via bilateral, regional, and multilateral channels, including result-based payment for REDD+ under the Paris Agreement, grants, and other relevant sources and procedures.

4.5.3 Current land use and potential land-use competition

Sustainable agricultural land is expected to reduce the land-use change from rice fields to settlements. The main competing land use for agriculture, livestock farms, and the LMTs in agriculture will be the settlement. The key stakeholder that decides whether the agricultural land could be transformed into a settlement is the provincial and city government, as the regional land use planning will be under their jurisdiction. However, the technical side of the land-use change process should be further verified to assess whether there are other stakeholders involved. In Java, most agricultural fields (including husbandry or livestock farms) change to settlement and industry areas. At the same time, out of Java, palm oil plantation was found to overtake many other agricultural fields.

Ideally, with the current land use management based on the existing policy, there should not be a major land-use change in the agricultural sector (including livestock farming). However, many activities are unrelated to real agricultural activities risking the sector. For example, the blockage of irrigation could reduce productivity, disturbing the farmers' livelihood and leading to land abandonment by the farmers. These abandoned lands are further transformed into various land use. In Java Island, the most

common land use transformation is as settlement or industry; meanwhile, outside of Java Island, the land use was changed to palm oil (F. Agus, personal communication, May 6, 2021).

Feedstock plays a crucial role in biogas quality as a renewable energy source (Kulichkova et al., 2020; Zhu et al., 2019). Given the availability of feedstock, there is abundant potential for biogas to utilise municipal solid waste, agricultural residues and animal manure (ASEAN Centre for Energy (ACE), 2020; International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), 2022).

In Indonesia, agricultural waste (e.g., animal manure and crop residues) is the primary feedstock for biogas in the electricity sector. Additionally, crops, municipal solid waste (MSW), and wastewater are other biogas feedstock resources. Most Indonesian regions have at least one potential feedstock available for biogas-to-electricity (Ahmed et al., 2017; Jain, 2019; Kyaw & Greater Mekong Subregion Economic Cooperation Program, 2009; Mojares, 2015; Mustonen et al., 2013; National Environment Agency, 2019; Peace Independence Democracy Unity Prosperity, 2011; Prasertsan & Sajjakulnukit, 2006; Rianawati et al., 2021; Roubík et al., 2018).

Agricultural land covers 62.3 million hectares (ha) of land in Indonesia, making up approximately one-third of Indonesia's land surface area. About 82 percent consists of cropland, including temporary and permanent crop cultivation (Food and Agriculture Statistics (FAOSTAT), 2020). Given the scale of cropland, agricultural waste could serve as feedstock for large-scale biogas plants (Sardiana, 2021).

4.5.4 Climate risks & sensitivities

Erosion and landslide are affected by land use, in which an open agricultural area is more prone to these problems than an agricultural area with cover. Besides that, biodiversity is also at risk and reduced soil quality, as the poor carbon soil would lose its capacity to provide habitat for microbes and microfaunas. Moreover, heavy rain (extreme precipitation) is one of the biggest threats, as it could flood low-lying areas. It also potentially erodes the topsoil layer and leads to soil carbon translocation, reducing the soil quality. River floods and sea-level rise risk the agricultural yield, and sea-level rise could affect soil salinity which can be tackled by freshwater soil flush. In areas with high rainfall, the freshwater could be rain sourced. However, applying underground water to flush the soil in drier areas will only increase farmers' vulnerability (F. Agus, personal communication, May 6, 2021).

Droughts and floods threaten agriculture, and food security is a priority for Indonesia. The emphasis is that farmers will prime higher yields over environmental protection, so they must see how these techniques can benefit them or otherwise, they will probably not apply them. These techniques can improve carbon sequestration and resilience, and Biochar can maintain water retention, prevent landslides, strengthen the soil structure, and store carbon. However, farmers need to be socialised in using these techniques as they can be reluctant to change their practices unless they see short-term benefits (such as improved yields), so it is important to emphasise these advantages.

4.5.5 Economic implications

Integrating livestock into the farm would also be intended for better nutrient cycling by reducing fire for field clearing and increasing farmers' income through livestock products to ensure better economic income rather than addressing climate change directly. If the farmers could make organic fertiliser

within their farms, their fertiliser costs could be reduced. Organic practices will increase the labour required, but they will also produce higher-priced produce (Maswar, personal communication, May 3, 2021).

Another benefit of using organic fertiliser for SCE is micro and macronutrients essential for biomass growth in agriculture and agroforestry, bringing about further decarbonisation. While integrating livestock could also increase the farmers' freedom by reducing their reliance on input and the required amount of fertiliser that should be bought (Uddin et al., 2016), incorrect feed rations will result in higher methane emissions (Jiao et al., 2014). Therefore, knowledge transfer regarding livestock feed will be required. The correct feeding will help increase the quality of livestock products and ultimately reduce methane emissions while empowering the farmers.

Currently, there is no information regarding the cost or the price of emission reduction in agriculture, and there is also no standardised price for carbon sequestration environmental services. However, implementing specific LMT such as Organic Fertiliser Processing Unit (UPPO) or organic fertiliser management facility is worth IDR 200 million for each project according to national funding (APBN), starting from the planning, developing, building, and maintenance. Analysis of regional funding (APBD) has not been done (N. Mustikasari, personal communication, April 21, 2021).

4.5.6 *Co-benefits and trade-offs*

Risks

For chemical fertiliser use, the farmers report lower productivity. The farmers who adopt the practices on the field might see this usage as dangerous. However, the yield would increase over time as the soil health improved. Ideally, this will lead to more sustainable production. This increase in yield would take time, and the farmers might not have the patience to wait for the yield to increase again. Organic fertiliser and biogas slurry to the soil can help increase the soil carbon, sequester more carbon in the soil, reduce carbon emission, reduce nitrogen loss, and increase water quality. The manure processing in the biogas facilities would also help reduce water pollution caused by the manure. As soil health increases, soil biodiversity increases (N. Mustikasari, personal communication, April 21, 2021).

Other risks include the increase in cost, requiring economic capital and energy from the farmers. For example, a physical labour increase would be required to reduce weeds and pests manually as the farmers reduce synthetic fertiliser and pesticide use. This risk would also hinder the farmers from adopting organic practices. Besides, fertilising is required in agriculture; over-fertilising could pollute water and be economically wasteful. High-dosage fertiliser application would lead to greener and fresher-looking produce. However, it will also increase the crop's sensitivity towards pathogen and pest attacks. In rice production, over-fertilising was correlated to a higher empty husk percentage than balanced fertiliser application (F. Agus, personal communication, May 6, 2021).

In addition, institutional mismatch is a danger in this industry. There have been instances where different industries have prioritised distinct characteristics. To ensure Indonesia's food security, the Ministry of Agriculture seeks to enhance agricultural productivity, and the Ministry of Environment and Forestry wishes to reduce emissions and environmental damage. In order to achieve their objectives, the institutes must present a unified face. The third risk is the policy implementation's

scalability. Due to societal and/or cultural factors, the upscaling and downscaling of policies can be problematic.

The greatest threat to society is resistance to behavioural change. Farmers are typically resistant to adopting new technologies or practices. In addition, farmers are hesitant to experiment with new ways when it affects their daily life and the customs of their communities. For instance, they might not wish to invest additional time and resources in implementing LMT. As a result of their long-term investment, farmers with more capital tend to take better care of their land than those with less wealth.

From a business owner's perspective, the four greatest business risks are limited and unclear resources and supply, investment problems, increased capital cost, uncertain income stream, and extended payback period. Frequently, it is difficult for business owners to locate raw materials for the production of fertilisers. In addition, they have limited access to banks and microfinance schemes, relying solely on cooperatives and community organisations. In order to manufacture bio fertiliser and biochar from anaerobic digestion or a waste management method, for instance, upfront costs and resources are required.

In addition, farmers are frequently unaware of or reluctant to implement better farm management. For instance, they refuse to employ intercropping because of the uncertainty that they would reap the benefits of their labour; they need to earn money quickly and therefore choose to use an instant method. This is a common pattern among farmers who migrate to a new location and require food security. The proximity of technology to local companies is the final factor. This can benefit them since they will be better equipped to absorb new farming technology (A. Dariah, personal communication, September 15, 2021).

Co-benefits

The major carbon emitter in agriculture is the rice field due to soil waterlogging and the large land assigned for the rice field. Livestock is in the second position, as there are carbon emissions from ruminants and livestock manure. Accordingly, livestock integration would help cycle the usually burned biomass by processing them as feed, yielding livestock products. Also, processing biomass as an organic fertiliser could help to reduce the carbon emitted due to the burning of straws.

Biogas and livestock waste management are currently the second priority of LMT for carbon emission. Several projects, such as organic-based villages, aim to transform 100 villages into organic-oriented ones with the cropping system and composting. The projects are targeted to be completed by 2024. Other projects such as SIPADU/SIMANTRI have also been done. However, the amount of carbon reduced is still unclear as it has not been assessed previously. LCDI Agriculture uses the calculation based on land use currently used by MOEF. Therefore, a non-land-used carbon emission reduction after the biogas and compost station installation has not been calculated. Moreover, the indigenous practice of integrating livestock, for example, ducks, within the organic rice field results in the mutualism between the livestock and the rice. The livestock would clear up the pest that attacks the rice while yielding higher rice production (Khumairoh et al., 2018).

Trade-offs

In integrated farming or carbon precision farming, the size of the land is also fixed, but with the integration of livestock components, it also increases. However, organic plant residue biomass previously burned in integrated agriculture can be used as compost or animal feed. Thus, carbon emissions can be reduced. However, these new practices would require starting capital, so that the funding source would be needed (Y. Rochmayanto, personal communication, May 5, 2021). In addition, farmers may have the initial capital to add a livestock component to their farm, but the capital to continue and maintain this new component will be difficult. For example, we can provide livestock and biodigester, but it will not be easy to continue the facility if the farmers do not have the ability and capital.

Another aspect of biogas in Indonesia is the relationship between feedstock and the food sector. The key signals for the food sector are the susceptibility of existing crops and livestock to climate change and the loss of croplands to tourism infrastructure. Additionally, concerning transportation, GHG emissions and health implications (particulates) have been highlighted due to a rapid increase in motorcycles, commercial trucks, and car fleets. The infrastructure may be inefficient relative to current and future demand. Hence, human population trajectories, settlement patterns, mean temperature indicators, sea level rise, coastal inundation, tourism person-days (i.e. a tourism activity day and all that is involved in consumption and transport) or potential for livestock manure for biogas can also be assessed.

4.5.7 Risks associated with scaling-up

There is no research on mitigation action to measure the suitability of the action in each region. For example, organic fertiliser (UPPO) and Biogas projects are given as a grant. However, any follow-up sustainability research at all the provinces being executed has not yet been done. Therefore, any risks related to differences in each region have not been assessed in any way. In many cases, the unsuitable practices that might threaten the farmers would be selected on the farmer group level. The farmers would naturally choose the practices that would better suit their needs by learning through their peers, and the unsuitable practices would be selected (N. Mustikasari, personal communication, April 21, 2021).

Socialising farmers to new technologies is equally crucial to ensuring the long-term use of technology. Applying organic fertiliser or adding organic materials (e.g. biochar) will most contribute to carbon sequestration and soil conservation since carbon materials will be stored in the soil. In addition, this LMT will benefit air quality, fire risk reduction, and water balance due to emission reduction. However, farmers are less likely to use these measures if they do not see results. Therefore, the technology supplied to farmers must deliver co-benefits. Increasing farm production is the key benefit that farmers expect. One of the instances of soil carbon augmentation in the agriculture sector is biochar, where corncob has been utilised to raise land productivity in Lampung, Sumatra. Biochar helps sustain water retention, avoid landslides, enhance the soil structure, and store carbon. Furthermore, climate resilience also influences the surrounding ecology, so intermittent irrigation in rice fields assists farmers in adapting and reducing climate change (A. Dariah, personal communication, September 15, 2021).

4.5.8 *Research gaps*

For SCE, a pilot project is important before applying the technologies in the field. Creating an inventory of ongoing pilot projects is also as important. That inventory can monitor, evaluate, verify, and validate the technology and practice. To develop and improve the technology and practice for SCE, BECCS and biochar can be considered. However, there is yet BECCS/U implementation in Indonesia. Bioenergy is implemented through decentralised and non-decentralised biogas, biofuel or biomass without a carbon capture storage system. Various stakeholders, such as MEMR, BAPPENAS, and DEN (National Energy Council), have not set a roadmap and planning for BECCS/U in Indonesia. There is still a lack of research and studies on BECCS/U implementation in Indonesia. Besides, GOI is concerned about this technology's high implementation cost and technology readiness.

In addition, biochar technology has been known for a long time in Indonesia through charcoal. It is used abundant resources from agricultural and forestry waste, and MoA includes it in LMTs on agricultural land. However, BAPPENAS, MoA, and MOEF have not set specific targets and planning for biochar implementation (Balitbangtan, 2019). Biochar or bio charcoal from agricultural or forestry waste is utilised through research or pilot project implementation in Indonesia, and there is no massive-scale biogas implementation.

Conclusion

Existing land-based mitigation technologies (LMTs) include afforestation and reforestation, biochar and soil carbon sequestration (SCS), ocean fertilisation, bioenergy with carbon capture, storage, and utilisation (BECCS) and utilisation (BECCU), increased weathering, and direct air capture (DAC) (Minx et al., 2017). In addition to the technologies, land-based mitigation technologies for land-use change are categorised by land-use type, including forest, farmland, wetland, and grassland. In Indonesia, certain technologies and methods have been applied, while others are still in the study phase.

Bioenergy without carbon capture storage is implemented in Indonesia through anaerobic digestion (biogas), fermentation (ethanol production), thermal biomethane, hydrogen/ammonia production, top-gas recycling (blast furnaces), industrial processes with large amounts of waste heat, mineral processing (cement kilns), bio-CNG (Compressed Natural Gas), co-firing, and combined heat and power (CHP) mode. However, the high cost and lack of technological knowledge prevent using some technologies (Grönkvist, 2012). The conventional initial route to introduce BECCS technology in Indonesia is via biomass, biogas, biofuel, thermal biomethane, and co-firing at coal power plants (DEN, 2019). The State Electricity Company (PLN) launched corporate action using the co-firing approach. Indonesia requires 17,470 tonnes per day of biomass or 5 million tonnes per year of wood pellets to satisfy the co-firing demands of its coal power plants at 1%. PLN has adopted co-firing technology in five coal power facilities (EBTKE ESDM, 2020). BECCS has, therefore, not been adopted in Indonesia. Cofiring biomass in coal-fired power plants is the initial stage in BECCS deployment.

Another potential LMT is biochar. It is a viable approach for restoring damaged land and enhancing soil quality, and a slower disintegration rate and resistance to microbes are additional benefits. In agriculture, biochar lowers soil acidity, enhances nutrient availability, and binds nutrients. For instance, biochar can improve the pH of acidic soil (pH between 3 and 5). In addition, biochar can be utilised in locations with little water to bind this water. In many areas, the Agency for Agricultural Research and Development (Balitbangtan) of the Ministry of Agriculture (MoA) introduced the production and application of biochar via technical supervision. Utilizing the Kon tiki model, introducing the charcoal production process to farmers is simple and economical. This variant features a cone-shaped hole with a 150 cm top diameter and 75 cm height, and it is easy and appropriate for farmers (Bardono, 2018). Nonetheless, this possible LMT is not currently a government priority. Therefore, the adoption of biochar in Indonesia is currently in the pilot stage.

After completing the literature research and a few interviews with relevant specialists, the vast list of LMTs was whittled down to four candidates: 1) Afforestation and Agroforestry; 2) Peatland Management; 3) Agriculture; 4) Soil Carbon Enhancement. These four are under consideration for more investigation (using model simulations) inside the LANDMARC project. Before such an evaluation can be conducted, a narrative or plot must be constructed for each selected LMTs.

For afforestation and agroforestry, since forests cover 65% of Indonesia's area, the forest sector is the main contributor to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Indonesia lost 26.8 million ha of tree cover from 2002 to 2019, contributing to 10.9 Gt of CO₂ emissions. Negative emission solutions are implemented

to reduce deforestation activities. 10.48 million hectares of diverse forest functions are at risk of destruction in natural forested regions. Risk is greatest outside the forest area (APL) and lowest within the PBPH-HT. The total amount of natural forest that can be transformed until 2050 is restricted to 6.8 million hectares. To meet emission reduction goals, efforts must be made to expedite the establishment of industrial forest plantations. It is estimated that 11,2 million hectares of forest have been created, and the development of planted forests has reached 5.12 million hectares, leaving a shortfall of 4.07 million hectares. To reach the FOLU Net Sink target by 2030, 2.79 million hectares must be rehabilitated using a rotation method.

There are 38 million hectares of high conservation value (HCVF) lands, of which 1.51 million hectares are in high-risk areas. Climate change adaptation activities can benefit the environment socially and economically. Forestry research has been widely carried out in Indonesia, but forestry research on how the role of the new futuristic forest function has not been explored much. A clear system to support movements towards climate change adaptation and mitigation is also needed. The government must ensure that local communities receive incentives proportionally to what they have done to LMT. The National Forest Monitoring System must monitor and supervise operations executing FOLU sector mitigation efforts towards the 2030 net sink. Indonesia will bolster indigenous technology's role while pursuing technological cooperation opportunities within the Paris Agreement and Convention. Peatland covers 20.6 million ha or 10.8% of the total land area in Indonesia. Emissions peaked in 2015 due to extreme warming effects attributed to El Niño. To accomplish the aim set for peat restoration, the area must increase by 2.72 million hectares by 2030.

In Indonesia, wetlands include mangrove swamps and in-land wetlands (peatlands). The Ministry of Environment and Forestry (MOEF)'s Peatland Restoration Agency (BRG) was established in 2016 to manage and facilitate peatland restoration in seven priority provinces, which comprise around 40% of the nation's total land area. Three main activities, known as 3R – Rewetting, Revegetation, and Revitalisation, play roles in preserving and enhancing carbon stock. Revitalisation is a set of actions to ensure that any economic activities performed on or around the peatland area are well-aligned with its preservation. Planting commodity crops suitable for the wetland is also called Paludiculture (BRG, 2016). BRG has been helping farmers by introducing alternative crops that thrive in wet soils. Indonesia's government needs to ensure that local actors receive incentives proportionally to what they have implemented and improve the readiness of local governments to implement LMTs. Maintaining the water level, revegetating peatland, and implementing paludiculture will reduce emissions and store carbon.

Moreover, agriculture, as one of the LMTs, accounts for 13% of Indonesia's total greenhouse gas emissions. Agricultural activities are extremely vulnerable to climate change. Climate change will result in lower soil health and uncertainty in water availability. BAPPENAS has made an effort to be able to tackle these problems. MoA recorded 114.74 million tonnes of CO₂ reduction in 2010-2019 (BAPPENAS, 2020a). Overall data on land-based mitigation practices in the agricultural sector is shown in Table 5. There are few knowledge gaps in the effort to carbon capture various land use in agriculture. The Indonesian government has targeted reducing waste emissions by 94% from 2024 to 2030. Anaerobic digestion processes currently contribute to Indonesia's GHG emissions.

Lastly, improving soil organic carbon (SOC) in the agricultural sector can be an effective negative emission measure. Bioslurry is a co-product of the anaerobic digestion of wet organic waste. Organic matter content in bioslurry can reach up to 29%, and 26% for cow dung, poultry manure and buffalo dung. A study has estimated the total biogas production from Indonesia to be 9,595.6 Mm³/year. For SCE, a pilot project is important before applying the technologies in the field. Creating an inventory of ongoing pilot projects is also as important. There is still a lack of research and studies on BECCS/U implementation in Indonesia. GOI is concerned about this technology's high implementation cost and technology readiness.

5. References

- Abraham, M., & Pingali, P. (2020). Transforming Smallholder Agriculture to Achieve the SDGs. In S. Gomez y Paloma, L. Riesgo, & K. Louhichi (Eds.), *The Role of Smallholder Farms in Food and Nutrition Security* (pp. 173–209). Springer International Publishing.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-42148-9_9
- Agus, F. (2021, May 6). *NETP narratives in Agriculture Interview Fahmuddin Agus* [Teams Meeting].
- Ahmed, T., Mekhilef, S., Shah, R., Mithulanathan, N., Seyedmahmoudian, M., & Horan, B. (2017). ASEAN power grid: A secure transmission infrastructure for clean and sustainable energy for South-East Asia. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 67, 1420–1435.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.09.055>
- Altieri, M. A., & Nicholls, C. I. (2003). Soil fertility management and insect pests: Harmonizing soil and plant health in agroecosystems. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 72(2), 203–211.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-1987\(03\)00089-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-1987(03)00089-8)
- Armanto, A. N. (2021, April 22). *LMT Narratives in Forestry and Peatland Sectors* [Zoom].
- ASEAN Centre for Energy (ACE). (2020). *The 6th ASEAN ENERGY OUTLOOK (AEO6)*.
<https://aseanenergy.org/the-6th-asean-energy-outlook/>
- Balitbangtan. (2019). *Biochar SP 50*. Kementerian Pertanian, Badan Litbang Pertanian.
<http://www.litbang.pertanian.go.id/produk/48/>
- BAPPENAS. (2019). *Narasi RPJMN IV 2020*. BAPPENAS.
https://www.bappenas.go.id/files/rpjmn/Narasi%20RPJMN%20IV%202020-2024_Revisi%2014%20Agustus%202019.pdf
- BAPPENAS. (2020a). *Implementasi Perencanaan Pembangunan Rendah Karbon 2018-2019*. Kedeputan Kementerian Perencanaan Pembangunan Nasional/BAPPENAS.
- BAPPENAS. (2020b). *Rencana Jangka Panjang Menengah Nasional 2020-2024*. BAPPENAS.
- Bardono, S. (2018, April 15). *Biochar, Arang Pembengah Tanah untuk Lahan Terdegradasi*. Technology-Indonesia.Com. <http://technology-indonesia.com/pertanian-dan-pangan/inovasi-pertanian/biochar-arang-pembengah-tanah-untuk-lahan-terdegradasi/>
- BRG. (2016). *Rencana Strategis Badan Restorasi Gambut 2016-2020*. Badan Restorasi Gambut (Peatland Restoration Agency). <https://brg.go.id/rencana-strategis-badan-restorasi-gambut-2016-2020/>
- Busari, M. A., Kukal, S. S., Kaur, A., Bhatt, R., & Dulazi, A. A. (2015). Conservation tillage impacts on soil, crop and the environment. *International Soil and Water Conservation Research*, 3(2), 119–129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iswcr.2015.05.002>
- Caesariantika, E., Kondo, T., & Nakagoshi, N. (2011). Impact of *Acacia nilotica* (L.) Willd. Ex Del invasion on plant species diversity in the Bekol Savanna, Baluran National Park, East Java, Indonesia. *Tropics*, 20(2), 45–53. <https://doi.org/10.3759/tropics.20.45>
- Canfora, I. (2016). Is the Short Food Supply Chain an Efficient Solution for Sustainability in Food Market? *Agriculture and Agricultural Science Procedia*, 8, 402–407.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aaspro.2016.02.036>
- Caputo, V., Nayga, R. M., & Scarpa, R. (2013). Food miles or carbon emissions? Exploring labelling preference for food transport footprint with a stated choice study. *Australian Journal of*

- Agricultural and Resource Economics*, 57(4), 465–482. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8489.12014>
- Chaudhary, S., Wang, Y., Dixit, A. M., Khanal, N. R., Xu, P., Fu, B., Yan, K., Liu, Q., Lu, Y., & Li, M. (2020). A Synopsis of Farmland Abandonment and Its Driving Factors in Nepal. *Land*, 9(3), Article 3. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land9030084>
- Chrisendo, D., Krishna, V. V., Siregar, H., & Qaim, M. (2020). Land-use change, nutrition, and gender roles in Indonesian farm households. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 118, 102245. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2020.102245>
- CIFOR, IPB, & CGIAR. (2018). *Pengembangan Bioenergi di Indonesia. Peluang dan Tantangan Kebijakan Industri Biodiesel*.
- Coe, R., Sinclair, F., & Barrios, E. (2014). Scaling up agroforestry requires research ‘in’ rather than ‘for’ development. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 6, 73–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2013.10.013>
- Cole, L. E. S., Bhagwat, S. A., & Willis, K. J. (2014). Recovery and resilience of tropical forests after disturbance. *Nature Communications*, 5(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms4906>
- Conant, R. T., Cerri, C. E. P., Osborne, B. B., & Paustian, K. (2017). Grassland management impacts on soil carbon stocks: A new synthesis. *Ecological Applications*, 27(2), 662–668.
- Dariah, A. (2020, September 24). *Sumber Emisi dan Inovasi Teknologi Rendah Karbon Sektor Pertanian*. LCDI Talk: Inovasi Teknologi Berbasis Rendah Karbon di Bidang Pertanian.
- Dariah, A. (2021, September 15). *LMT Risk Assessment Survey* [Personal communication].
- DEN. (2019). *Indonesia Energy Outlook 2019*.
- Deribew, K. T. (2020). Spatiotemporal analysis of urban growth on forest and agricultural land using geospatial techniques and Shannon entropy method in the satellite town of Ethiopia, the western fringe of Addis Ababa city. *Ecological Processes*, 9(1), 46. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13717-020-00248-3>
- Dewan Energi Nasional. (2019). *National Energy Policy in Indonesia and Its Alignment to Sustainable Development Goals 7 (SDG7) And Paris Agreement (NDC)*. Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources. Secretary General of National Energy Council.
- Dharmawan, I. W. S. (2021, May 6). *LMT Narrative in Forestry and Peatland Sectors* [Zoom].
- Dilisusendi, T. (2020, November 3). *Kerangka Regulasi Biogas dan Bio-CNG di Indonesia*. Web Seminar “Pengembangan Biometana di Indonesia dan Uni Eropa: Peluang, Tantangan serta Lesson Learned dalam Penggunannya sebagai Bio-CNG,” Jakarta, Indonesia.
- Ditjen PPI KLHK. (2021). *Peraturan dan Kebijakan terkait Perubahan Iklim*. <http://ditjenppi.menlhk.go.id/peraturan-perundangan.html>
- Do, H., Luedeling, E., & Whitney, C. (2020). Decision analysis of agroforestry options reveals adoption risks for resource-poor farmers. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, 40(3), 20. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-020-00624-5>
- Dunne, D. (2019, March 27). *The Carbon Brief Profile: Indonesia*. CarbonBrief Clear on Climate. <https://www.carbonbrief.org/the-carbon-brief-profile-indonesia>
- EBTKE ESDM. (2020, February 28). *Menerapkan Metode Co-firing di PLTU, Ini Potensi Biomassa untuk Substitusi Batubara*. Direktorat Jenderal Energi Baru Terbarukan Dan Konservasi Energi (EBTKE). <https://ebtke.esdm.go.id/post/2020/02/28/2490/terapkan.metode.co-firing.di.pltu.ini.potensi.biomassa.untuk.substitusi.batubara?lang=en>

- FAO. (2000). *Definitions Related to Planted Forests—FRA WP 79*.
<http://www.fao.org/3/ae347e/ae347e02.htm>
- FAO. (2017). *Socio-economic context and role of agriculture in Indonesia* (I7696EN/1/08.17; Country Fact Sheet on Food and Agriculture Policy Trends, pp. 1–6). FAO.
- FAO and ITPS. (2015). *Status of the World’s Soil Resources (SWSR) – Main Report. Chapter 10: Regional Assessment of Soil Change in Asia*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations and Intergovernmental Technical Panel on Soils.
- Food and Agriculture Statistics (FAOSTAT). (2020). *FAOSTAT Data*.
<http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/RL>.
- Gregorio, M. D., Nurrochmat, D. R., Fatorelli, L., Pramova, E., Sari, I. M., Locatelli, B., & Brockhaus, M. (2015). *Integrating Mitigation and Adaptation in Climate and Land Use Policies in Indonesia: A Policy Document Analysis* (Working Paper No. 244). The University of Leeds.
<https://agritrop.cirad.fr/578223/1/Di%20Gregorio%202015%20Integrating%20Mitigation%20and%20Adaptation%20in%20Climate%20and%20Land%20Use%20Policies%20in%20Indonesia.pdf>
- Grönkvist, S. (2012, September 21). *BECCS applied in industries*. Bio-energy, CCS, and BECCS: Options for Indonesia, Jakarta, Indonesia.
<https://iea.blob.core.windows.net/assets/imports/events/75/BioenergyCCSandBECCSOptionsforIndonesia.pdf>
- Hakim, L. (2017). *Managing biodiversity for a competitive ecotourism industry in tropical developing countries: New opportunities in biological fields*. 030008. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5012708>
- Halimatussadiyah, A. (2020). *Mainstreaming the Sustainable Development Goals into national planning, budgetary and financing processes: Indonesian experience*. United Nations, ESCAP.
https://www.unescap.org/sites/default/d8files/knowledge-products/WP-20-06_final.pdf
- Hani, A. (2021, May 4). *LMT Narratives in Agroforestry Sector* [Zoom].
- Harrison, M. E., Ottay, J. B., D’Arcy, L. J., Cheyne, S. M., Anggodo, Belcher, C., Cole, L., Dohong, A., Ermiasi, Y., Feldpausch, T., Gallego-Sala, A., Gunawan, A., Höing, A., Husson, S. J., Kulu, I. P., Soebagio, S. M., Mang, S., Mercado, L., Morrogh-Bernard, H. C., ... Veen, F. J. F. van. (2020). Tropical forest and peatland conservation in Indonesia: Challenges and directions. *People and Nature*, 2(1), 4–28. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.10060>
- Huijsmans, R., Ambarwati, A., Chazali, C., & Vijayabaskar, M. (2021). Farming, Gender and Aspirations Across Young People’s Life Course: Attempting to Keep Things Open While Becoming a Farmer. *The European Journal of Development Research*, 33(1), 71–88.
<https://doi.org/10.1057/s41287-020-00302-y>
- Indonesian Ministry of Forestry and Environment. (2021). *Indonesia Long-term Strategy for Low Carbon and Climate Resilience 2050*.
https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/Indonesia_LTS-LCCR_2021.pdf
- Indrajaya, Y., van der Werf, E., Weikard, H.-P., Mohren, F., & van Ierland, E. C. (2016). The potential of REDD+ for carbon sequestration in tropical forests: Supply curves for carbon storage for Kalimantan, Indonesia. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 71, 1–10.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2016.06.032>

- International Energy Agency (IEA). (2019). *Southeast Asia Energy Outlook*.
https://iea.blob.core.windows.net/assets/47552310-d697-498c-b112-d987f36abf34/Southeast_Asia_Energy_Outlook_2019.pdf
- International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA). (2022). *Scaling Up Biomass for the Energy Transition: Untapped Opportunities in Southeast Asia*.
<https://www.irena.org/publications/2022/Feb/Scaling-up-biomass-for-the-energy-transition-Untapped-opportunities-in-Southeast-Asia>
- IRENA. (2017). *Renewable Energy Prospects: Indonesia* (REMap - A Renewable Energy Roadmap). International Energy Agency (IRENA). www.irena.org/remap
- Islam, M. F. (2011). *Linking Bio-energy, Bio-slurry and Composting*. SSNV Netherlands Developments Organization, Bangladesh.
http://www.fao.org/fileadmin/templates/rap/files/meetings/2011/110602_linking_bio-energy.pdf
- Jain, S. (2019). *Market Report Malaysia*, World Biogas Association.
http://www.worldbiogasassociation.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/WBA-malaysia-4ppa4_v1.pdf
- JDIH BPK RI. (2019). *Penghentian Pemberian Izin Baru dan Penyempurnaan Tata Kelola Hutan Alam Primer dan Lahan Gambut*. <https://peraturan.bpk.go.id/Home/Details/116964/inpres-no-5-tahun-2019>
- Jiao, H. P., Dale, A. J., Carson, A. F., Murray, S., Gordon, A. W., & Ferris, C. P. (2014). Effect of concentrate feed level on methane emissions from grazing dairy cows. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 97(11), 7043–7053. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2014-7979>
- Kartika, K., Lakitan, B., Sanjaya, N., Wijaya, A., Kadir, S., Kurnianingsih, A., Widuri, L. I., Siaga, E., & Meihana, M. (2018). Internal-edge row comparison in jajar legowo 4:1 rice planting pattern at different frequency of fertilizer applications. *Agrivita*, 40(2), xx–xx.
- Khalil, M., Berawi, M. A., Heryanto, R., & Rizalie, A. (2019). Waste to energy technology: The potential of sustainable biogas production from animal waste in Indonesia. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 105, 323–331.
- Khatiwada, D., Palmén, C., & Silveira, S. (2021). Evaluating the palm oil demand in Indonesia: Production trends, yields, and emerging issues. *Biofuels*, 12(2).
<https://doi.org/10.1080/17597269.2018.1461520>
- Khumairoh, U., Lantinga, E. A., Schulte, R. P. O., Suprayogo, D., & Groot, J. C. J. (2018). Complex rice systems to improve rice yield and yield stability in the face of variable weather conditions. *Scientific Reports*, 8(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-32915-z>
- Kinose, Y., Masutomi, Y., Shiotsu, F., Hayashi, K., Ogawada, D., Gomez-Garcia, M., Matsumura, A., Takahashi, K., & Fukushi, K. (2020). Impact assessment of climate change on the major rice cultivar Cihorang in Indonesia. *Journal of Agricultural Meteorology*, 76(1), 19–28.
<https://doi.org/10.2480/agrmet.D-19-00045>
- KLHK. (2020a). *National Plastic Waste Reduction Strategic Actions for Indonesia*. Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK); IGES Centre collaborating with UNEP; Sustainable Waste Indonesia (SWI). <https://www.unep.org/ietc/resources/policy-and-strategy/national-plastic-waste-reduction-strategic-actions-indonesia>
- KLHK. (2020b). *Rencana Strategis KLHK 2020-2024*. Ministry of Environment and Forestry.

- KLHK. (2020c). *Vademecum Kehutanan Indonesia*. Kementerian Lingkungan Hidup dan Kehutanan.
- KLHK. (2020d, July 28). Indonesia Melawan Sampah Plastik. *Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK). Pusat Pengendalian Pembangunan Ekoregion Jawa*.
<http://p3ejawa.menlhk.go.id/article17-indonesia-melawan-sampah-plastik.html>
- Kulichkova, G. I., Ivanova, T. S., Köttner, M., Volodko, O. I., Spivak, S. I., Tsygankov, S. P., & Blume, Y. B. (2020). Plant Feedstocks and their Biogas Production Potentials. *The Open Agriculture Journal*, 14(1), 219–234. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1874331502014010219>
- Kyaw, U. H. & Greater Mekong Subregion Economic Cooperation Program. (2009). *Status and potential for the development of biofuels and rural renewable energy: Myanmar*.
<https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/publication/30311/biofuels-myanmar.pdf>
- Lakitan, B., Alberto, A., Lindiana, L., Kartika, K., Herlinda, S., & Kurnianingsih, A. (2018). *The Benefits of Biochar on Rice Growth and Yield in Tropical Riparian Wetland, South Sumatra, Indonesia*.
<http://cmuj.cmu.ac.th/ns/full/2120180410110810.pdf>
- Lal, R. (2003). Soil erosion and the global carbon budget. *Environment International*, 29, 437–450.
- Landry, J., & Rochefort, L. (2012). The drainage of peatlands: Impacts and rewetting techniques. *Peatland Ecology Research Group*.
- Levin, K. (2017, November 6). *Understanding the “Emission Gap” in 5 Charts*. WRI Indonesia.
<https://wri-indonesia.org/en/blog/understanding-%E2%80%9Cemissions-gap%E2%80%9D-5-charts>
- Litbang Pertanian. (2020). *Penerapan Prinsip Teknologi Rendah Karbon*. Agro Inovasi.
www.litbang.pertanian.go.id
- Low Carbon Development Indonesia (LCDI). (2020). *Materi Komunikasi*. Aksara. <https://lcdi-indonesia.id/materi-komunikasi/#>
- Lunt, P., Allott, T., Anderson, P., Buckler, M., Coupar, A., Jones, P., Labadz, J., & Worrall, P. (2010). Peatland Restoration. Report to IUCN UK Peatland Programme. *Report to IUCN UK Peatland Programme*.
- Macháč, J., Trantinová, M., & Zaňková, L. (2021). Externalities in agriculture: How to include their monetary value in decision-making? *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 18(1), 3–20. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13762-020-02752-7>
- Masripatin, N., Rachmawaty, E., Suryanti, Y., Setyawan, H., Farid, M., & Iskandar, N. (2017). *Buku Strategi Implementasi NDC (Nationally Determined Contribution)*. Ministry of Environment and Forestry.
- Maswar. (2021, May 3). *LMT Narratives in Agricultural Sector [Zoom]*.
- Meli, P., Rey-Benayas, J. M., & Brancalion, P. H. S. (2019). Balancing land sharing and sparing approaches to promote forest and landscape restoration in agricultural landscapes: Land approaches for forest landscape restoration. *Perspectives in Ecology and Conservation*, 17(4), 201–205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pecon.2019.09.002>
- MEMR. (2019). *Rencana Umum Ketenagalistrikan Nasional 2019-2038*. Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources. https://gatrik.esdm.go.id/assets/uploads/download_index/files/46a85-ruk-2019-2038.pdf
- Ministry of Agriculture. (2020). *Livestock and animal health statistics 2020*. Direktorat Jendral Peternakan dan Kesehatan Hewan.

- Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources. (2020). *Laporan Kinerja Direktorat Jenderal Energi Baru, Terbarukan dan Konservasi Energi Tahun 2019*. Direktorat Jenderal Energi Baru, Terbarukan and Konservasi Energi.
- Ministry of Environment and Forestry. (2016, April 23). *Indonesia Signs Paris Agreement On Climate Change*.
http://ppid.menlhk.go.id/siaran_pers/browse/299#:~:text=23%20April%202016%2C%20dibaca%2079%20kali.&text=The%20Paris%20Agreement%20will%20enter,the%20world's%20greenhouse%20gas%20emissions.
- Ministry of Environment and Forestry. (2019). *Rencana Kehutanan Tingkat Nasional (RKTN) Tahun 2011-2030*.
http://jdih.menlhk.co.id/uploads/files/P_41_2019_RKTN_2011_2030_menlhk_09022019091329.pdf.
- Ministry of Environment and Forestry. (2021). *Updated Nationally Determined Contribution Republic of Indonesia*.
<https://www4.unfccc.int/sites/ndcstaging/PublishedDocuments/Indonesia%20First/Updated%20NDC%20Indonesia%202021%20-%20corrected%20version.pdf>
- Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK). (2017). *Peta Penutupan Lahan Indonesia*. Peta Penutupan Lahan Indonesia. <http://webgis.menlhk.go.id:8080/pl/pl.htm>
- Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK). (2022). *Operational Plan Indonesia's FOLU Net Sink 2030*. https://www.menlhk.go.id/site/single_post/4705/operational-plan-indonesia-s-folu-net-sink-2030
- Minx, J. C., Callaghan, M., Lamb, W. F., Garard, J., & Edenhofer, O. (2017). *Learning about climate change solutions in the IPCC and beyond*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2017.05.014>
- MOA. (2021). *Kementerian Pertanian Republik Indonesia—Official Data Lima Tahun Terakhir*. Pertanian.Go.Id. <https://www.pertanian.go.id/home/?show=page&act=view&id=61>
- MOEF. (2017). *Buku Strategi Implementasi NDC (Nationally Determined Contribution)*. Ministry of Environment and Forestry (MOEF).
- MOEF. (2019). *Statistik KLHK 2019—Kementerian LHK*.
https://www.menlhk.go.id/site/single_post/3714/statistik-klhk-2019
- Mojares, J. G. (2015). *Implementing Biogas Technology Project in Malvar, Batangas, Philippines*. 3. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341051636_Implementing_Biogas_Technology_Project_in_Malvar_Batangas_Philippines
- Mulligan, J. (2018, September 14). *6 Ways to Remove Carbon Pollution from the Sky*. WRI Indonesia. <https://wri-indonesia.org/en/blog/6-ways-remove-carbon-pollution-sky>
- Mulyani, A., Nursyamsi, D., & Syakir, M. (2016). *Strategies for Utilizing Land Resources to Achieve Sustainable Self Sufficiency on Rice*.
- Murty, D., Kirschbaum, M. U. F., McMurtrie, R. E., & McGilvray, A. (2002). Does conversion of forest to agricultural land change soil carbon and nitrogen? A review of the literature. *Global Change Biology*, 8, 105–203.
- Mustikasari, N. (2021, April 21). *LMT Narratives in Agricultural Sector [Zoom]*.
- Mustonen, S., Raiko, R., & Luukkanen, J. (2013). Bioenergy Consumption and Biogas Potential in Cambodian Households. *Sustainability*, 5(5), 1875–1892. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su5051875>

- National Environment Agency. (2019). *Co-Digestion Of Food Waste And Used Water Sludge Enhances Biogas Production For Greater Energy Generation*.
- Peace Independence Democracy Unity Prosperity. (2011). *Renewable Energy Development Strategy in Lao PDR*. Renewable Energy Development Strategy in Lao PDR
- Prach, K., Marrs, R., Pyšek, P., & Diggelen, R. van. (2007). Manipulation of Succession. In L. R. Walker, J. Walker, & R. J. Hobbs (Eds.), *Linking Restoration and Ecological Succession* (pp. 121–149). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-35303-6_6
- Pramono, A. A., Fauzi, M. A., Widyani, N., Heriansyah, I., & Roshetko, J. M. (2011, April 9). *Managing smallholder teak plantations: Field guide for farmers*. CIFOR; Center for International Forestry Research (CIFOR). <https://doi.org/10.17528/cifor/003493>
- Prasertsan, S., & Sajjakulnukit, B. (2006). Biomass and biogas energy in Thailand: Potential, opportunity and barriers. *Renewable Energy*, 31(5), 599–610. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2005.08.005>
- Priyono, N. (2021, September 15). *LMT Risk Assessment Survey* [Personal communication].
- Ranganathan, J., Waite, R., Searchinger, T., & Zions, J. (2020, May 12). Regenerative Agriculture: Good for Soil Health, but Limited Potential to Mitigate Climate Change. *World Resources Institute*. <https://www.wri.org/blog/2020/05/regenerative-agriculture-climate-change>.
- Rianawati, E., Sagala, S., Hafiz, I., Anhorn, J., Alemu, S., Hilbert, J., Rosslee, D., Mohammed, M., Salie, Y., Rutz, D., Rohrer, M., Sainz, A., Kirchmeyr, F., Zacepins, A., & Hofmann, F. (2021). The potential of Biogas in Energy Transition in Indonesia. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 1143(1), 012031. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/1143/1/012031>
- Risch, S. J. (1983). Intercropping as cultural pest control: Prospects and limitations. *Environmental Management*, 7(1), 9–14. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01867035>
- Ritung, S., Wahyunto, K., Nugroho, Sukarman, Hikmatulloh, Suparto, & C., T. (2011). *Peta Lahan Gambut Indonesia Skala 1:250.000 (Indonesian peatland map at the scale 1:250,000)*. Balai Besar Penelitian dan Pengembangan Sumberdaya Lahan Pertanian.
- Rochmayanto, Y. (2021, May 5). *LMT Narrative in Forestry and Peatland Sectors* [Zoom].
- Roubík, H., Mazancová, J., Le Dinh, P., Dinh Van, D., & Banout, J. (2018). Biogas Quality across Small-Scale Biogas Plants: A Case of Central Vietnam. *Energies*, 11(7), 1794. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en11071794>
- Santoso, D., Adiningsih, S., Mutert, E., Fairhurst, T., & van Noordwijk, M. (1997). Site improvement and soil fertility management for reclamation of Imperata grasslands by smallholder agroforestry. *Grofor. Syst*, 36, 181–202.
- Sardiana, I. K. (2021). Organic vegetable farming system enhancing soil carbon sequestration in Bali, Indonesia. *IOP Conf. Ser.: Earth Environ. Sci.*, 724(012025). <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1755-1315/724/1/012025>
- Schjoerring, J. K., Cakmak, I., & White, P. J. (2019). Plant nutrition and soil fertility: Synergies for acquiring global green growth and sustainable development. *Plant and Soil*, 434(1), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-018-03898-7>
- Searchinger, T., & Ranganathan, J. (2020, August 24). Further Explanation on the Potential Contribution of Soil Carbon Sequestration on Working Agricultural Lands to Climate Change Mitigation. *World Resources Institute*. <https://www.wri.org/blog/2020/08/insider-further-explanation-potential-contribution-soil-carbon-sequestration-working>.

- Shofiyati, R., Las, I., & Agus, F. (2010). Indonesian soil data base and predicted stock of soil carbon. *In Proceedings of an International Workshop on Evaluation and Sustainable Management of Soil Carbon Sequestration in Asian Countries*, 73–83.
- Shroff, R., & Cortés, C. R. (2020). The Biodiversity Paradigm: Building Resilience for Human and Environmental Health. *Development*, 63(2), 172–180. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41301-020-00260-2>
- Silalahi, D. F. (2020, April 22). Why solar energy can help Indonesia attain 100% green electricity by 2050. *The Conversation*. <https://theconversation.com/why-solar-energy-can-help-indonesia-attain-100-green-electricity-by-2050-134807>.
- Sirin, A., Medvedeva, M., Maslov, A., & Vozbrannaya, A. (2018). Assessing the land and vegetation cover of abandoned fire hazardous and rewetted peatlands: Comparing different multispectral satellite data. *Land*, 7(2), 71.
- Skinner, C., Gattinger, A., Krauss, M., Krause, H.-M., Mayer, J., van der Heijden, M. G. A., & Mäder, P. (2019). The impact of long-term organic farming on soil-derived greenhouse gas emissions. *Scientific Reports*, 9(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-38207-w>
- Tacconi, L., Rodrigues, R. J., & Maryudi, A. (2019). Law enforcement and deforestation: Lessons for Indonesia from Brazil. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 108, 101943. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2019.05.029>
- Tahar, N. (2018, October 26). *Solid Waste Management in Indonesia*. Holland Circular Hotspot, Ayana Midplaza. https://ec.europa.eu/environment/international_issues/cem_presentations/Presentatie%20Herman%20EU%20CE%20Missie%20261018%20final.pdf
- Timmer, C. P. (2019). *The Role of Public Grain Stocks in Food Security: The Indonesian Experience* (Working Paper No. 6; Food Reserves, p. 82). CIRAD. <https://europa.eu/capacity4dev/file/90207/download?token=Dsuxyoi9>
- Uddin, M., Khan, M., & Islam, M. (2016). Integrated farming and its impact on farmers' livelihood in Bangladesh. *SAARC Journal of Agriculture*, 13, 61. <https://doi.org/10.3329/sja.v13i2.26569>
- Umaerus, V. (1992). Crop rotation in relation to crop protection. *Netherlands Journal of Plant Pathology*, 98(2), 241–249. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01974491>
- van Noordwijk, M., Agus, F., Dewi, S., & Purnomo, H. (2014). Reducing emissions from land use in Indonesia: Motivation, policy instruments and expected funding streams. *Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies for Global Change*, 19(6), 677–692. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11027-013-9502-y>
- Warts, Y., Eppink, M. M., Oosterkamp, S., Hiller, S., & van der Sluis, A. A. (2011). *Reducing Food Waste: Obstacles Experienced in Legislation and Regulations* [Project Report]. LEI, part of Wageningen UR. <https://edepot.wur.nl/188798>
- Wani, A. M., & Sahoo, G. (2021). Forest Ecosystem Services and Biodiversity. In P. K. Shit, H. R. Pourghasemi, P. Das, & G. S. Bhunia (Eds.), *Spatial Modeling in Forest Resources Management: Rural Livelihood and Sustainable Development* (pp. 529–552). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-56542-8_22
- Wardhana, B. (2021, May 4). *LMT Narratives in Peatland Sector* [Zoom].
- Warta, Z. (2021, September 27). *LMT Risk Assessment Survey* [Personal communication].
- Wibowo, A. (2021, May 6). *LMT Narratives in Forestry Sector* [Zoom].

- Wijeratna, A. (2018). *Agroecology: Scaling-up, scaling-out* (p. 22). Actionaid.
<https://www.actionaid.it/app/uploads/2018/04/Agroecology.pdf>
- World Bank. (2021). *Indonesia Wood Exports by country & region 2018 WITS Data (Drop down column)*.
https://wits.worldbank.org/CountryProfile/en/Country/IDN/Year/2018/TradeFlow/Export/Partner/all/Product/44-49_Wood
- Zewdie, B., Tack, A. J. M., Ayalew, B., Adugna, G., Nemomissa, S., & Hylander, K. (2021). Temporal dynamics and biocontrol potential of a hyperparasite on coffee leaf rust across a landscape in Arabica coffee's native range. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 311, 107297.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2021.107297>
- Zhu, T., Curtis, J., & Clancy, M. (2019). Promoting agricultural biogas and biomethane production: Lessons from cross-country studies. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 114, 109332. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2019.109332>
- Zinngrebe, Y., Borasino, E., Chiputwa, B., Dobie, P., Garcia, E., Gassner, A., Kihumuro, P., Komarudin, H., Liswanti, N., Makui, P., Plieninger, T., Winter, E., & Hauck, J. (2020). Agroforestry governance for operationalising the landscape approach: Connecting conservation and farming actors. *Sustainability Science*, 15(5), 1417–1434. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-020-00840-8>

SCALING LAND-BASED MITIGATION SOLUTIONS IN NEPAL

LMT PORTFOLIO AND NARRATIVE DEVELOPMENT

LOKENDRA KARKI
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1. Introduction

This report sets out a broad nation-wide transition scenario for the implementation of four land-based mitigation technologies and practices (LMTs) for the agriculture, forestry, and other land use sectors (AFOLU) sector in Nepal. This transition scenario is based on a number of pieces of research conducted in Nepal between June 2020 (when LANDMARC started) and the end of 2022:

First, we performed an initial scoping of key LMTs in the case study country, Nepal. The scoping exercise included a literature review and formal and informal meetings with relevant stakeholders. The scoping assessment resulted in a long list of broad portfolios of different LMTs that could be viable within Nepal.

Second, we whittled that long list down to a shortlist that contained only LMTs that would be the most relevant for the Nepalese context. We proposed and validated this LMT portfolio through a complementary (policy) literature review, stakeholder interviews (i.e., external validation by relevant country experts and stakeholders) and a workshop.

The workshop identified rice and forest management as two of the most important components of Nepal's LMT portfolio. It delivered a key message about the need for government policy for landbased mitigation technologies that aim to co-deliver improved environmental outcomes, increased soil fertility and enhanced well-being for farmers.

The interviews focussed on an in-depth understanding of LMTs at the local context. They revealed that Nepal does not yet have mechanism to define and identify peatland and that there is a growing policy concern about organic agriculture development in Nepal. The co-design process allowed insights us to remove peatland management from the portfolio and add organic agriculture. The scoping process and results are presented in section 2 of this report (steps 1 & 2).

Third, after the short-listed LMT portfolios were validated, we developed national scaling narratives or storylines for each LMT included in their portfolio. The assessments focus on climate risks, vulnerabilities as well as socio-economic co-benefits and trade-offs associated with upscaling LMTs in the case study countries. The analysis is based on a broad range of information/literature sources, and stakeholder consultations conducted. This process is supported through a risk and impact assessment (i.e., an online survey and workshops/seminars) conducted through LANDMARC tasks 4.1, 4.2 and 5.2. The results of this analysis are a set of LMT narratives which are presented in section 3 of this report.

The research steps are designed to enable an **analysis of the risks and (climate) impacts of scaling up land-based mitigation and negative emission solutions**. As such this report primarily contributes to objectives 2, 3 and 4 of the six LANDMARC key objectives (see Table 1).

Table 1: LANDMARC project objectives.

	Project key objectives
1	Determine the potential and effectiveness of LMTs in GHGs mitigation using Earth Observation (EO)
2	Improve climate resilience of LMT solutions at the local level for large-scale implementation
3	Assess the risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs of scaling up local LMTs nationally
4	Scaling up LMT solutions to the continental and global level to assess the effectiveness
5	Improve current methodologies to estimate emissions and removals for LMTs
6	LMT capacity building and develop new tools and services for decision making

While the results shown in this report represent a mostly qualitative storyline describing the context and impact of scaling up LMTs in a country context, they also enable project partners to proceed with the translation of the outcomes in a manner so that they can serve as direct model input.

Furthermore, these national-level assessments provide a testing ground and empirical basis for the continental, and global assessment of the realistic scaling potential of land-based mitigation and negative emission solutions implemented in Work Packages 6 and 7 of the LANDMARC project (*Objective 4*).

2. Scoping of land-based mitigation and negative emission solutions

2.1 Overview of the potential of LMTs in Nepal

2.1.1 Introduction

The net greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions of Nepal are estimated to be 31.99 MT Co²-eq per year, equivalent to 0.06% of global emissions (MoPE, 2017). Table 2 shows the mitigation potential of different technologies and practices in Nepal's Agriculture, Forestry, and other Land Use (AFOLU) sectors. The top three potential land-use-based mitigation technologies (LMTs) are reforestation, forest management and rice management. Reliable and consistent data for the analysis of the mitigation potential from the land-use sector in Nepal is lacking. For example, data on upland and lowland rice at the national level are important for estimating the mitigation potential of the rice sector, but such information is not yet available (MoPE, 2017). As such, estimates for realistic potentials, additional costs, biomass impacts, and technology readiness levels (TRL) are not available.

Table 2: Mitigation potential of different technologies and practices in Nepal

LMT Category	LMT	Technical potential, Mt CO _{2e} /y
Negative emission practices-LAND MANAGEMENT	Land-use (mix of measures)	
	Reforestation/afforestation	23.23
	Forest management	2.44
	Rice management	2.43
	Peatland restoration	0.02
Total	Total negative emissions of land management practices in Mton CO₂	28.12

Source: Adapted from Griscom et al. (2017)

2.1.2 Technologies dependent on biomass/photosynthesis

A typical Nepalese farming household relies heavily on traditional biomass, mainly crop and forest residues, for energy resources. which accounts for up to 78% of their total household energy resources (CBS 2011).

Nepal's abundant forest resources and underutilised crop residues give Nepal means that there is a lot of potential for biomass-based negative emission technologies like, for example, Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS) and Biochar. However, these technologies are not addressed in Nepal's existing climate change policies.

BECCS

There is great potential for the use of BECCS feedstock in Nepal, with minimal impact on current residue and waste flows. For example, the abandonment of agricultural land is increasing every year, mainly in hilly and mountainous regions (Chaudhary et al., 2020). Plants grown on this abandoned land could be a good source of feedstock for BECCS. Despite this, there is yet to be any formal assessment of BECCS potential in Nepal.

Biochar

Studies on the application of biochar in Nepal are scant; limited to field trials only. But literature shows that biochar has tremendous potential to improve soil properties and soil productivity (Pandit et al., 2017a), whilst simultaneously addressing climate change mitigation. For example, a study of biochar using different crops in Nepal, Schmidt et al. (2017), found that the application of organic biochar based fertilizers increased crop yield by 123% ($\pm 76.7\%$) when compared with the same amount of organic fertilizer without bio-char. Similarly, another study showed that while there was no significant positive effect of biochar application in the first year, maize and mustard grain yield increased by 93% and 134% respectively in the following year (Pandit et al., 2018).

Biochar is particularly important for areas that have problems with acidic soil, as it increases soil PH (Pandit et al., 2017a). However, there is remains a lack evidence of biochar's effectiveness in the all the various soil types and cropping patterns that are found across the different agroecological regions of Nepal (Dahal et al., 2016). The cost effectiveness of biochar at the household level has also not been studied yet, which is essential for understanding its potential for large-scale implementation.

2.1.3 Land management practices

Forestry (Afforestation/reforestation, avoiding deforestation and forest management)

Historically Nepal has seen plenty of deforestation, for the purposes of converting forests to farmland and for the export of timber. The Nepalese government began trying to clamp down on these practices in 1957, when it nationalised private forests. promulgated stricter laws for forest conservation, and expanded government forest offices to all districts (Gautam et al., 2004). However,

these policies could not stop widespread deforestation, loss of bio-diversity and land degradation (Gautam et al., 2004).

In the 1970s, Nepal recognised the importance of communities in forest management, and initiated a community forestry program as a means of both protecting, and effectively utilizing, forests. Under this program, the government allocates a small area of forest land to the local community. Subsequently, a community forest user group (CFUGs) is responsible for the conservation, sustainable use and management of the forest and its products. The revenues from the community forest are spent on pro-poor activities and community forest development. This community forestry program has made Nepal one of the most successful countries in the world in forest management.

About 45% of farming households in Nepal are already members of a CFUG, covering about 1.8 million hectares of community forests (Nuberg et al., 2019). The community forest initiative successfully restored degraded forests, and has become a source of timber and firewood for the members of the user groups (Basnyat et al., 2020). In addition, studies suggest a substantial increase in the density of trees, biomass and carbon stock of trees in the community forests (CF), showing the important role of CF in carbon sequestration (Anup et al., 2018). Since 2015, Nepalese forest policy has acknowledged the important role of communities in forest management, and classified community-based forest management practices into six different types including: i) community forest; ii) leasehold forest; iii) collaborative forest; iv) buffer zone community forest; v) protected forest, and vi) religious forest.

Agroforestry

Agroforestry can improve the livelihoods of farming households, and simultaneously contributing bio-diversity conservation and removal of atmospheric carbon. Nepalese farmers traditionally practice agroforestry as a source for firewood, fodder, and timber. The type of agroforestry practiced depends on agro-ecological zones and altitudes. A common example of agroforestry practice in Eastern and Central hill regions is *Utis* – Cardamom agroforestry (Amatya et al., 2018). This traditional practice includes on-farm tree plantation, tree intercropping, plantation of fodder trees and an integrated farming system (Aryal et al., 2019). Based on surveys, agroforestry in Nepal can be divided into seven categories: i) Agri silviculture; ii) silvopastoral; iii) Agri-silvopastoral; iv) silvo-fishery; v) home gardens; vi) woodlots, and vi) shifting cultivation (Amatya et al., 2018).

Agriculture

The Agricultural sector in Nepal contributes about 40% of national gross domestic product and employs about two-thirds of the population (MoAD, 2014b). Using traditional knowledge and practices, mountain farmers in Nepal use farmyard manure made from forest litter, crop residues and animal manure, as their main source of fertilizer. However, the organic pools in agricultural soils are decreasing due to a shift to more intensive agriculture, bringing with it chemical fertilizers, soil erosion, excessive tillage and removal of crop residues (Dahal and Bajracharya, 2010; Sitaula et al., 2004).

Nepal has acknowledged climate friendly agriculture in its policies and programs for increasing agricultural production and combating climate change. Nepal’s overarching agricultural policy – the Nepal Agriculture Development Strategy (2015-2035) (ADS) - aims to reduce emissions from agriculture and scale up carbon sequestration. Nepal has recently submitted its second Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), which aims to establish 200 climate-smart villages by 2030 (MoFE 2020). The NDC acknowledges promotion of intercropping, agroforestry, conservation tillage, livestock, and agricultural waste management, which are related to negative emission technologies in agriculture. It has also an ambitious target of increasing soil organic matter in agricultural soils to 3.95% by 2030. Since 1999, Nepal has been implementing a sustainable soil management program in 388 villages. This has been managed through its Agriculture, Forestry and Environment Committee (AFEC) (Shrestha Shiva, 2015; Subedi et al., 2017), which became very effective in participatory planning, resource mobilization, and agriculture service provision (Subedi et al., 2017). The major negative emission technologies in the agricultural sector are tillage and residue management, cover crops, crop rotation and rice management.

2.2 Determining the LMT scope for national-level simulation modelling

This section discusses the set of LMTs that we will study in detail in Nepal. Table 3 summarises the list of possible LMTs in Nepal and indicates those included in the short-list of the LMT portfolio. The main rationales for including the various LMTs in the national-level scaling simulation assessment are presented below.

Table 3: Long-listing of relevant LMTs

LMTs	Specification	Included in the national LANDMARC LMT portfolio
BECCS		N
Biochar		N
Wetlands	Peatland management	N
Cropland	No-tillage and reduced tillage	N
	Rice management (dry-seeded rice with no-till)	Y
	Agroforestry	Y

	Residue retention	N
	Crop rotation	N
	Organic farming	Y
	Cover cropping	N
Grassland	Grassland and range land management	N
Forest land	Avoided deforestation	N
	Afforestation/reforestation	N
	Forest management	Y

After scoping analysis of the LMTs presented for Nepal, we have shortlisted forest management, dry-seeded rice, agroforestry, and peatland management for further scenario scaling analysis in Nepal. The main rationales for this are presented below.

Forest management

Nepal has avoided deforestation and successfully managed forests through ambitious forest sector policies and stricter laws. Nepal is renowned for its success in community-based forest management at the national level. The country's Forest Policy 2015 aims to maintain at least 40% of total land as forests. In Nepal's second NDC this ambition was increased to 45% by 2030 (MoFE 2020).

Agroforestry

Various policies have aimed to develop agroforestry, as it is considered an opportunity for livelihood improvement, employment generation and food security. The forest policy of 2015 recognises the need for research and the extension of various agroforestry systems in Nepal. Similarly, the Forest Sector Strategy (2016-2025) aims to promote agroforestry in existing privately owned farmlands (MOFSC, 2016a) and agroforestry with species of multipurpose trees in the uncultivated agriculture lands (MoFE, 2019). The National Bio-diversity Strategy and Action Plan 2014 also envisaged promotion of agroforestry on public lands for the conservation of biodiversity. Government and several NGOs are promoting small scale private forests as a part of agroforestry systems. Recently, Nepal promulgated the National Agroforestry Policy 2019, which envisages agroforestry as a means of reducing pressure on forests and conserving environmental and biological diversity to develop climate resilience ecosystems.

Dry seeded rice

Rice crop plays a critical role in the food and nutrition security of smallholder farmers. It is a primary source of income and employment for the majority of farmers. It contributes about 20% of Nepal's

agricultural GDP and 7% of national GDP (Joshi et al., 2020). Due to the importance of rice production, the Nepalese government has been formulating policies and programmes on increasing the rice production area, and increasing productivity, since the first five year plan of Nepal (1956-1961) (Bhandari et al., 2017). In terms of climate change mitigation, rice substantially contributes (over 17.%) towards methane emissions from the Nepalese agricultural sector (Joshi, 2016).

Dry seeding rice with no tillage is a climate friendly crop establishment method that can reduce methane emissions from rice fields and enhance carbon sequestration. Rice is dry seeded when primed (or pre-germinated) seeds are sown directly in zero-tillage or reduced tillage conditions. This replaces puddling, transplanting, and maintaining standing water. Although dry seeded rice is important for climate mitigation, this crop establishment method is also widely considered to be a means to increase production, reduce labour costs, and cut water consumption.

The rationale for excluding other LMTs from any further national scenario scaling analysis is provided below:

BECCS and Biochar

There are no policies or programs related to biochar and BECCS. The government has not acknowledged the potential for bio-energy crops to replace cereal crops, as it can threaten the food security of the country.

Reduced tillage, harvest residue management, crop rotation, cover cropping

These LMTs are directed at the enhancement of soil carbon sequestration and the improvement of soil properties. Nepal's second NDC includes these LMTs, however, a clear policy on the application of these LMTs is still lacking.

Peatland management

Nepal has been involved in the conservation of wetlands since the signing of the Ramsar Convention in 1987. Currently, about 5% of the total land is categorised as wetlands, covering 750,000 hectares. This includes nine Ramsar, wetland sites of international importance, covering 60,561 hectares (MoFE, 2018a). The Nepal Wetlands Policy has acknowledged the importance of wetlands in climate change mitigation and has focused on the sustainable conservation of wetlands (MoFSC, 2012). However, Nepal has already lost about 5.4% of its total wetland area due to the conversion to crop cultivation (MoFE, 2018a). Studies on Nepalese wetlands so far are scant, and mostly limited to species diversity and ecosystem services (MoFE, 2018a; Poudel, 2009). Among the wetlands, Nepal has not defined and classified wetlands to the level of peatland.

2.3 Discussion on short-listing of LMTs

2.3.1 Land-use change dynamics

Land-use change in Nepal is presented in Table . Forest dominates Nepalese land cover and is well distributed in the Terai, Siwalik, and Himalayan regions. Area under forest increased from 38% of the total land in late 1978/79 to about 40% in 2010, showing the effective efforts of Nepal on forest management and conservation practices. Handing over government-owned forests to local communities through community forestry started in the late 1970s. The size of the CF area increased from 0.048 million hectares in 1986 to 1.8 million hectares in 2010. Similarly, the area of grasslands decreased from 1.7 million hectares in 1990 to 1.3 million hectares 2010. The area under agriculture increased from 3.8 million hectare in 1990 to 4.0 million hectares in 2010. Rice production area has also risen from 1.4 million hectares in 2009/10 to 1.5 million hectares in 2018/19.

Competing land use

Use of agricultural land for urban growth is becoming a serious problem in Nepal. Currently, the proportion of built up areas to the total land area is very low, however, the rate is steadily increasing. Urban growth averaged 3.3% during 1989-1996, increasing to 12.61% during 2011-2016 period (Rimal et al., 2018). To avoid the rapid loss of cultivated areas, the Nepal Land Use Policy (NLUP) 2015 aims to discourage non-agricultural use of agricultural land, keeping land fallow and restricting widespread land fragmentation (MoLRM, 2015).

Table 4 Land use change in Nepal

SN	Types of land use, units	Historical land use (1960-2009)	Recent land use (2010-2019)
1	Agricultural land, million ha	3.75 (1990)	4.04 (2010)
2	Rice production area, million ha	1.41. (2009/10)	1.49 (2018/19)
3	Area under permanent crops, %	0.7 (1962/63)	6.7 (2011/12)
4	Area under temporary crops, %	92 (1961/62)	84.2 (2011/12)
5	Forest, %	38 (1978/79)	40.36 (2010/11)
6	Shrub, %	4.7 (1978/79)	4.4 (2010/11)
7	Built-up area, %	0.22 (1990)	0.34 (2010)
8	Grassland, million, ha	1.7 (1990)	1.26 (2010)
9	Area under community forest, million ha	0.048 (1986)	1.88 (2018)

10	Area under leasehold forest, million ha	0.007 (1998)	0.043 (2018)
11	Area under partnership forest, million ha	0.0067 (2008)	0.00734 (2018)

Source: Adapted from Nepal et al. (2020), Uddin et al. (2018), and MoAD (2020).

Nepal envisages the use of renewable energy technologies in the near future (MoFE, 2019) which can compete with other land uses. Nepal's second NDC aims to generate around 1500 MW of clean energy by 2030, from micro-hydro, solar, wind and bioenergy (MoFE, 2020). The potential of solar energy and wind energy in Nepal is 2100 MW and 3000MW respectively (Poudyal et al., 2019). However, until now, production from large scale solar, wind and bioenergy are very low. For example, Nepal's largest solar farm, Nuwakot Solar Power Station, produces about 1.5 MWh (as of June 2020), which will be increased to 25 MWh in the next few years. In the biomass sector, policy support is limited to energy from agricultural and forests residues. Nepalese policymakers have not considered bioenergy crops on dedicated cropland yet, due to its possible impact on the country's food security. There is a good opportunity for using abandoned agricultural lands and degraded lands for growing bioenergy crops, which will reduce the likelihood of biomass energy competing with other land uses.

2.3.2 Land management dynamics

In the past, land use planning in Nepal had focussed mainly on increasing agricultural productivity. The 8th Five Year Plan (1992/93-1996/97), became a major milestone in land use planning, as it acknowledged necessity of long-term planning to allocate areas for forestry, agriculture, and pastures. The 9th Five Year Plan (1997/98-2001/02) emphasized the utilisation of ecological variation and biodiversity. The National Land Use Policy (NLUP) 2013 aimed to protect agricultural lands to ensure food security. The NLUP was revised in 2015, with a focus on sustainable socioeconomic and ecological development by optimising the use of available land and land resources (MoLRM, 2015). NLUP 2015 classified 11 land use zones: i) agricultural; ii) residential; iii) commercial; iv) industrial; v) mines and minerals; vi) cultural and archaeological; vii) river and lake reservoir; viii) forest; ix) public use and open spaces; x) building materials (stone, sands, concrete), and xi) other zones as required.

Figure 1 Land-use and land cover pattern in Nepal

Source: Nepal et al. (2020)

Nepal’s climate change policy envisages potential carbon sequestration by forests through: sustainable forest management; agroforestry development in degraded forest areas and riverbeds; and management of forest fires (MoFE, 2019). To implement its ambitious plan of forest conservation, and utilization, Nepal aims to attract funding from global initiatives that seek to reduce emissions from deforestation and degradation (REDD+). This will allow the sustainable management of 50% of Terai (lowland) forests and 25% of mid hills and mountain forests (MoFE 2020). Nepal has increased forest cover in the past decades, through forest conservation policies that promotes the role of local communities for management and optimum utilization of forests.

The total carbon stock in Nepalese forest constitutes 1054.97 megatons (MoFSC, 2015b). In the forest carbon stock, tree components (live, dead standing, dead wood and below ground biomass), forest soil, and litter and debris constitute 61.53%, 37.80%, and 0.67% respectively. The soil organic carbon content was found to be higher with increasing altitude (MoFSC, 2015b). For example, soil organic matter in forests of physiographic units such as Terai, churia, middle mountain and high mountain were 33.66 t/ha, 31.44 t/ha, 54.33t/ha and 114.03 t/ha respectively (MoFSC, 2015b). A rough estimation shows that Nepal could receive between \$20-86 million per year as an incentive from REDD+ initiatives for reducing deforestation and avoiding forest degradation (MoFSC, 2015a).

3. Co-design of LMT narratives

3.1 Introduction

The long and shortlisting were validated by means of both a literature review and stakeholder consultation. Although peatland management was included in the long listing, it was removed from the analysis after discussion with stakeholders, which revealed that it had limited potential in the Nepalese context. Among stakeholders there was a consensus that Nepal lacks a proper classification of wetland to the peatland level, and therefore there are no policies and programs on peatland yet. A workshop highlighted that, instead, organic production has much greater potential in Nepal, due to the possibility of planting export oriented crops including organic non-timber forest products (NTFPs), tea and coffee. As a result of increasing interest from stakeholders,, organic farming has been included in the shortlist of four LMTs that are considered for further analysis within the LANDMARC project. The following sections provide the qualitative narratives of the four LMTs for Nepal.

- Rice management (See section 0)
- Forestry (see section 0)
- Agroforestry (see section 1.4)
- Organic farming (see section 0)

3.2 Rice management: Dry seeded rice

3.2.1 Introduction

Rice is a staple food crop in Nepal. It is cultivated over 1.5 million hectares of land in different agroecological zones, with a production of 5.61 million tonnes per year (FAOSTAT), which is about half (51.6%) of total food grain production (MOAD 2017). Although Nepal has a very small share of global rice production and trade, it plays a significant role in food security and the economy of the country, contributing about one fifth of agricultural GDP (Joshi et al., 2020). Rice is not only a primary source of employment and income but also provides food and nutrition security for the majority of smallholder farmers.

Rice management is considered one of the critical mitigation options in agriculture (IPCC, 2019), which mainly comprise alternate wetting and drying, residue and tillage management, fertiliser management, the system of rice intensification and dry seeded rice. Among them, the dry seeded rice in no-till method is selected for this review, as it is one of the most efficient mitigation options by combining tillage, residue, and water management. No-tillage dry seeding rice involves sowing rice a depth of two to three centimetres directly in untilled soil, using a tractor-drawn seeder. This process replaces the traditional method of raising seedlings in nurseries and manually transplanting them in massively puddled soil. Direct planting of seeds avoids the costs associated with land preparation,

nursery bed preparation and transplanting of the seedlings, and requires less labour and water. This crop establishment method is being promoted in Nepal and other Asian countries. Dry seeded rice could be an option for reducing methane emissions from rice fields, increasing organic content in the soil, and simultaneously increasing rice production.

3.2.2 Policy context

Nepal does not have a specific policy covering rice management. The recently submitted Second Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) mentions that the organic content of agricultural soils will be increased from 2% to 3.5 % by 2030 (GoN 2020). Similarly, Climate Change Policy 2019 also does not mention rice management directly, but it acknowledges the use of climate-friendly technologies in agriculture (MOFE 2020). In the past, the Nepalese Government's National Rice Research Program, and Regional Agriculture Research Centre of National Agriculture Research Council (NARC) conducted on-station and farmer's field trails with dry seeded rice in the Sunsari and Dhanusha districts. Experts from Government and NGOs mentioned that dry seeded rice could be one of the best mitigation options - especially in the Terai (lowland) districts - because of increasing labour costs and water scarcity due to delay in monsoon onset. There is no separate funding for the rice management, however, farmers would be able to get some financial support to buy tractor and zero tiller through the district level agricultural knowledge centres. However, such support is not always available, and are difficult to obtain, in particular by small scale farmers.

3.2.3 Current land use and potential land-use competition

National-level data on the historic and current application of different rice management practices including dry seeded rice is not available. During the discussion, experts projected that despite its potential, very few farmers are currently adopting the dry seeded rice method. Farmers in the major rice-growing districts - including Sunsari, Jhapa and Morang, Bara, Parsa, Rautahat, Dhanusha, Chitwan, Kailali and Kanchanpur - are using the dry seeded rice method. Since the net economic return from rice farming is low, it is likely that other activities with high returns, such as commercial vegetable production and housing development, will increasingly displace rice cultivation in the future.

3.2.4 Climate risks & sensitivities

Unusually early rainfall in the rainy season can limit the use of seed drills in rice fields, restricting the use of this practice. In the wet season, sudden flooding due to high rainfall can decrease crop establishment if it takes place within a few days of seed planting. Farmers mentioned that due to unprecedented high rainfalls in the monsoon season, they prefer to dry seed rice mainly in the spring season rice, when there is very limited rainfall. Similarly, dry seeded rice plants are more vulnerable to damage in high wind conditions than transplanted rice, as the high plant density causes elongation of stems, thinner stem walls and small stem diameters (Wang et al., 2017).

3.2.5 Economic implications

Dry seeded rice can be economically beneficial when compared to transplanted rice. A study in Nepal by Dhakal et al. (2015) showed that the net benefit cost ratio of dry seeded rice was 2.2, compared to 1.6 for transplanted rice. A similar study in India, by Bhullar et al. (2018) found that net return from the dry seeded rice-wheat system was INR 5050 to 8100 per hectare greater than the transplanted rice-wheat system. While many previous studies show similar or greater yield in dry seeded rice methods than conventional rice, yield can vary widely (Kumar and Ladha, 2011) due to a lack of region-specific information on suitable varieties, appropriate soil textures, weed management, no-tillage method and management of residues. Therefore, when compared to conventional rice cultivation, dry seeded rice can be more prone to yield losses due to inappropriate management practices, unsuitable soil, weed infestations and climatic stresses (Xu et al., 2019). Dry seeding also attracts birds immediately after sowing, which may result in poor crop stand and a corresponding loss of yield.

3.2.6 Co-benefits and trade-offs

Co-benefits

Food security: Dry seeded rice increases food availability and nutritional benefit for farmers, and their families. Dry seeded rice requires the timely sowing of rice which increases the possibility of following crops, such as wheat, being planted on time, ensuring production at an optimum level (Kakumanu et al., 2018). Delayed planting of the following crops can, for example, reduce wheat yield by 60 kg per hectare per day (Hussain et al., 2012).

Economics: Dry seeded rice is important for farmers with low resources, as it can provide similar or greater yields as conventional rice with less input (Laing et al., 2018). This is increasingly important, as labour costs for rice production have tripled in recent years (Liu et al., 2014). Dry seeded rice can reduce the total labour required by up to 66%, while crop establishment costs can be reduced by 75%, depending on the season, location and management practices (Kumar and Ladha, 2011). The net return from dry seeded rice could be 1.49 as compared to 1.14 in conventional rice (Rana et al., 2014).

Environment: Dry seeded rice can reduce methane emissions and save freshwater. Methane emission reductions from dry seeded rice fields range from 33% to 37% (Pathak et al., 2013; Singh et al., 2009). Rice crops use about 24 to 30% of the world's freshwater resources, and increasing water scarcity is threatening the sustainability of irrigated rice production (Bouman et al., 2007). Studies show that 17 to 22 million hectares of irrigated rice production area in Asia will face water scarcity by 2025 (Tuong and Bouman, 2003). Dry seeded rice can reduce water consumption by 30 to 55%, which will have a positive impact on hydrology and water use at larger spatial scale levels (Pathak et al., 2011; Tabbal et al., 2002).

Soil quality: Untilled dry seeded rice helps to maintain crop residue on the soil surface, which can improve soil quality through enhanced nutrient recycling and soil organic carbon sequestration. When seed drilling with dry seeded rice, residues of previous crops are retained, adding organic matter that

improves soil pH, soil organic carbon, nutrient content, and microbial activity. A study by Gupta Choudhury et al. (2014) shows that soil in dry seeded rice had a higher capability to hold the organic carbon in the surface (11.57 g Kg per soil aggregates), and increased water-stable macroaggregates by 51.13%.

Trade-offs

Methane and nitrous oxide (N₂O) are potent greenhouse gases and have an inverse relationship to each other when it comes to dry seeded rice. Methane emissions are substantially reduced when dry seeding rice; however, emissions of nitrous oxide can increase. Due to the aerobic condition of the soil, under moderate soil moisture conditions, and especially in the high nitrogenous fertiliser application areas, nitrification and denitrification processes produce nitrous oxide (Kumar and Ladha, 2011).

3.2.7 Risks associated with scaling up

Small farmers need financial support to adopt dry seeded rice techniques. Experts mentioned that the lack of government policy support for dry seeded rice means the pace of adoption by farmers is very slow. For example, farmers were not receiving grants or subsidies from the government, which are often needed for purchasing tractor-drawn seeding machines.

Water management of rice fields is a key aspect to consider as soil drainage and water retention capacity constrain the adoption of dry seeded rice at a large scale. This means dry seeded rice cannot be applied in Nepal's lowland fields, as they have low or no drainage.

Lack of technical support for farmers also constrains dry seeding rice. Ideally, farmers should gain expertise in sowing and weed control techniques, which requires at least two years of continuous technical support. Weed control is more complicated with dry seeded rice than with other conventional methods, which can result in lower yields. Stakeholders reported lower yields of dry seeded rice, but this might be due to the inappropriate weed management. A lack of proper knowledge amongst farmers can result in poor crop establishment and high weed infestation. The resulting yield reduction deters farmers from adopting the technology.

3.2.8 Research gaps

Reliable data on the status of dry seeded rice and other rice management practices is limited, and explicit analysis of the mitigation potential of this technology at the national, regional, and global levels is still lacking. Moreover, dry seeded rice with no tillage can increase soil carbon sequestration. However, the role of no tillage dry seeded rice in carbon sequestration has been, as yet largely overlooked.

The performance of dry seeded rice depends on the set of management practices adopted by farmers, which may vary in different agro-ecological and socio-technological conditions. The development of

complete sets of technological and management solutions, with a focus on the development of rice seeds optimised for dry seeded cultivation and weed management practices, would be crucial in the future. Similarly, the extant literature on dry seeded rice based on field experiments and documentation of farmers' opinions on the challenges of dry seeded rice technology is limited. Future research on understanding farmers' views is critical to guide external interventions to scale up the technology.

In Nepal, women play a vital role in rice cultivation, contributing about half of the required labour. Women are mainly responsible for sowing, transplanting, weeding, fertiliser application, harvesting, and seed storage, while men are responsible for land preparation and irrigation. No tillage dry seeded rice replaces rice nursery, land preparation, and transplanting. This can reduce the heavy drudgery on women, who may work as unpaid labour (Khan et al., 2016). Future research in changing gender dimensions of rice farming due to dry seeded rice would be very valuable.

3.3 Forestry

3.3.1 Introduction

Afforestation/reforestation and forest management are negative emission practices in forestry, which remove carbon from the atmosphere and store it safely above ground (in trees) and below ground (in living biomass, litter, and soil). In Nepal, forests are a source of fuelwood, timber, and fodder for the forest dependant households. This means the forestry sector plays an important role in the Nepalese economy. Existing forests in Nepal are divided into seven types: i) community forests; ii) collaborative forests; iii) leasehold forests; iv) private forests; v) religious forests; vi) protected forests, and vii) protected areas (Table 4). Among them, community-based forests (which includes both community forests and leasehold forests) are popular due to the resource contribution they make to poor households in rural areas.

3.3.2 Policy context

The Nepalese Forest Policy 2019, Nepal Climate Change Policy 2019, Second Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) 2020, Forestry Sector Strategy (2016 -2025), National REDD+ Strategy (2018-2022), and the Community Forestry Development Guideline 2014 are the major national policies aiming to conserve forests and reduce the drivers of deforestation and forest degradation. Forest Policy 2019 aims to promote forest conservation, by securing incentives from global initiatives for reducing deforestation and degradation. Nepal Climate Change Policy 2019 focuses on sustainable forest management to increase forest carbon (MoFE, 2019). To avoid forest degradation and depletion, it also has provisions to reduce drought, wildfire, the spread of invasive alien species, forest pests and diseases. Similarly, Second Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) 2020 aims to maintain 45% of the total area of the country under forest cover by 2030. Forestry Sector Strategy (2016 -2025) aims to enhance forest cover by at least 10% in the 10 years period 2015 to 2025 (MoFSC, 2016b).

Likewise, Community Forestry Development Guideline 2014 aims to conserve forests and improve livelihoods through the active participation of local communities and inclusion of marginalised communities and women. National REDD+ Strategy (2018-2022) aims to enhance the carbon and non-carbon benefits of forest ecosystems to the overall prosperity of the people (MoFE, 2018c). These policies are focused on forest and biodiversity conservation and are not favourable to commercial harvesting and the forest products trade.

At the central level, the Ministry of Forests and Environment (MoFE), formulate policies and plans, and coordinates and monitors forest management activities. The Department of Forests (DoF) plays an important role in drafting forests policy and negotiating with stakeholders. At the grassroots level, Community Forest User Groups (CFUGs) and the Collaborative Forest Management committee are the main sector stakeholders. The Federation of Community Forest Users Nepal (FECOFUN) which represents 22, 266 community forest user groups, the Association of Collaborative Forest Users Nepal (ACOFUN) and the Community-Based Forestry Supporter's Network, Nepal (COFSUN) are the key networks playing a direct role in the implementation of community and scientific forest management in Nepal. These networks of forest user groups have become a strong political force for forest conservation which advocate for protection of forest users' rights in the natural resource governance. Similarly, local governments are responsible for allocating finance at the local level and coordinating forestry programs.

The Nepalese Government provides support for community-based forest programs through its offices at regional and district levels. Attracting international funding for REDD+ programs to reduce emissions from deforestation and forest degradation has been a good opportunity for Nepal. Currently, Nepal has been implementing two REDD+ programs: the Forests for Prosperity Project and Emission Reduction Programme. The Nepalese Government received financial support for the Forests for Prosperity Project from the World Bank, for promoting the private sector in forests and improvement of private sector forests. Similarly, with support from the Forest Carbon Partnership Facility (FCPF) of the World Bank, the Emission Reduction Program aims to protect about 2.4 million hectares in the Terai region.

3.3.3 Current land use and potential land-use competition

Forest cover decreased from 6.40 million hectares in 1964 to 4.26 million hectares in 1994 – meaning Nepal lost 2.14 million hectares of forest to shrubland or other land use (MoFE, 2018b). Recent data shows that today forests cover about 5.96 million hectares, which is 40.36% of the total area of the country (FAO and UNEP, 2020). Most of the forests area are located in the middle mountain region (37.8%) followed by High mountain and High Himal (32.2%), Churia (23%) and Terai (6.9%) regions (DFRS, 2015). The total forest carbon stock in Nepal is around 1.05 million tonnes. Trees, forest soils, and litter and debris constitute 61.53%, 37.8%, and 0.67% of this amount respectively (DFRS, 2015).

The different types of forests, based on management regimes, are presented in Table 4. Altogether 2.90 million farming households in Nepal are already members of 22,266 CFUGs, covering 2.23 million hectares of forest. Similarly, 864,015 households are involved in 30 collaborative forests, covering 76,012 hectares. Leasehold forests are mostly focused on poor households, engaging 71,753 households in 43,317 hectares of forest. Many of the forests are managed by local communities, and the area covered by private forests is very low.

Table 4 Different types of forests in Nepal

SN	Type of forest	Number	Area, ha	Households
1	Community forest	22,266	2,237,670	2,907,871
2	Collaborative forest	30	76,012	864,015
3	Leasehold forest (pro-poor)	7,484	43,317	71,753
	Leasehold forest (commercial)	22	640	
4	Private forest	2458	2,360	
5	Religious forest	36	2,056	
6	Protected forest	10	190,809	
7	Proposed protected forest	6	137,833	
7	Protected areas	10	34,419	

Source (DoF, 2017)

Expansion of agriculture and infrastructure is the main land use developments that cause deforestation and forest degradation in Nepal (MoFSC, 2014). Expansion of infrastructure includes road construction, hydropower, mining, airports, urbanisation, resettlement, industrial area, and transmission lines. Similarly, agricultural activities that affect forest areas are squatter (Sukumbasi) settlements in forests, gradual encroachment of existing cultivators and shifting cultivation.

3.3.4 Climate risks & sensitivities

In general, climate risks factors to forests include drought and fires. Forest fires are becoming more common in Nepal, but do not receive much attention from policymakers, because there are very few human casualties from wildfires. Wildfires mostly occur in government forests, and appear to be the result of deliberate attempts to increase the grass inside the forest, which means there is no long term and pervasive impact of forest fires. Forests are also affected by increasing river floods in the Terai region, and landslides in hills and mountain regions. The increase in river floods and landslides in the future could damage a large forest area in the long-term.

3.3.5 Economic implications

Estimates of the economic benefit from forest management vary widely. A study in Nepal showed that the net economic benefit from community forests ranged from \$ 4,814 to \$7,994 per community user group, which is \$ 152 to \$29 per hectare of forest (Pandit et al., 2017b). Similarly, K C et al. (2015) reported that the benefit-cost ratio of community forests is 3.04. A report on the benefit-cost of different types of forests in different physiographical regions (Table 5) suggests that the income from the collaborative forests is highest, followed by community forests in Terai, Siwaliks and Mid hills. The net annual benefit is lowest in protected forests. Similarly, annual implementation costs of forests are highest in community forests of in mid-hill regions, followed by community forests in Siwalks and Terai regions. Implementation cost is lowest in the protected forest. Annual changes in stored carbon are highest in community forests and lowest in collaborative forests.

Table 5 Annual costs and benefits from forest management and average annual change in carbon

<i>Forest</i>	<i>Annual forest management cost, USD/ha</i>	<i>Net annual benefit, USD/ha</i>	<i>Annual change in tonnes carbon per hectare</i>
<i>Community Forest (Mid hills)</i>	<i>31.56</i>	<i>211.44</i>	<i>1.96</i>
<i>Community Forest (Siwaliks)</i>	<i>26.26</i>	<i>228.74</i>	<i>1.84</i>
<i>Community Forest (Terai)</i>	<i>8.23</i>	<i>504.77</i>	<i>0.18</i>
<i>Collaborative forest management</i>	<i>7.56</i>	<i>1107.44</i>	<i>0.01</i>
<i>Protected forest</i>	<i>6.78</i>	<i>85.22</i>	<i>0.35</i>

Source (Rai et al., 2018)

3.3.6 Co-benefits and trade-offs

Co-benefits

Bio-diversity: Protecting or restoring high carbon forests is directly related to the conservation and promotion of biodiversity (Asbeck et al., 2021). However, some forests with high biodiversity might have low carbon sequestration potential (Buotte et al., 2020). Besides this, forests are important in restoring and conserving unprotected and degraded lands (Soto-Navarro et al., 2020).

Water quality: Forest cover is important in supplying watershed services. Studies suggest that an increase in forest cover is positively related to the quality of freshwater (Ovando and Brouwer, 2019; Price and Heberling, 2018).

Economic: In Nepal, forest management is related to the wellbeing of the local community and the wider society, as the livelihoods of most of Nepal's farmers depend on forests-based resources, including fodder, fuelwood, timber, and leaf litter. However, the benefit communities receive depends on the context of forest management. For example, community forest users can get timber to build new homes, and receive a quota for collecting fodder and fuelwood from dead trees, old trees, and branches. In collaborative forests, on the other hand, members can get much less fodder and fuelwood (25 – 35 %) (Rai et al., 2017), as it covers users from much larger areas. They also create jobs mainly for forest rangers (K C et al., 2015). Collaborative forests are much larger than community forests, which can create additional jobs for unskilled labours, accountants and technicians (GoN, 2016).

Social: Most forest management in Nepal, including the management of community forests, leasehold forests and collaborative forests is based on collective action, where each member contributes to the management of forests, including meetings, forest fencing and thinning. Community forestry is known for reducing gender and social gaps (Giri and Darnhofer, 2010), as they increase participation of marginalised communities - including women, Dalits and Indigenous groups - in decision making.

Trade-offs

Reduced biodiversity: Economic incentives for carbon sequestration through reforestation or afforestation programs can promote a monoculture of high-value trees, leading to negative impacts on biodiversity. Moreover, conflict with biodiversity aims can occur if the forest policies and programs choose trees with high carbon sequestration and high timber values, but with lower biodiversity value (Caparrós and Jacquemont, 2003). In Nepal, the probability of a reduction of biodiversity from forestry programs is low, as current programs mostly focus on forest conservation rather than achieving maximum economic benefits through commercial production and harvesting.

Threat to people's livelihoods: Too much emphasis on carbon sequestration and forest conservation can negatively affect local livelihood practices. In Nepal, the introduction of community forestry and protected forest areas after the 1970s curtailed local and Indigenous peoples' traditional practices of access to and control of the forests. As the access to forest resources were restricted, many transhumance herders could not continue their traditional practices (Banjade and Paudel, 2008).

3.3.7 Risks associated with scaling up

Since the inception of the concept of community forestry in the 1970s, the government is handing over forest areas to the local communities for forest management. Nepal has already promoted different forestry programs at the national level, including programs for community forests, collaborative forests, and leasehold forests. Experts mentioned that there is a high regulatory risk in forest management in Nepal. For example, Nepal's government introduced Forest Regulation 2079, which is being opposed by the Community Forest User Federation. The forest user committees say

that with these new regulation, the Nepal government is centralizing control over the management and utilization of forest resources.

Interview with experts showed that private or family forests have not improved, as the current forest policy is not favourable for the trade of timber from the private forests due to legal and administrative constraints. Private forest owners need to go through a cumbersome process of documentation and contacting district forest offices for validation and verification of forest products and get the harvesting permit for selling forest products. In addition, they also need to pay royalties to the government. All these tedious processes are hindering the commercial trade of harvested woods from the private forests.

3.3.8 Research gaps

The selection of suitable tree species is important for establishing new forest planting areas, for increasing carbon and income from the harvested trees. However, the identification and recommendation of trees based on their suitability at the local micro-climatic level is lacking. Experts mentioned that there is a belief that forests protect against landslides. However, whole forests have been known to be pulled down during landslides as the actual load bearing capacity of Nepal's geographical structure is still unknown. Further research is needed, to understand load bearing capacity of forests in the local contexts.

Another understudied aspect of the Nepalese forest sector is the contribution of forests to carbon storage. Stakeholders pointed out that it is also important to have a local allometric equation to better estimate forest biomass, however, Nepal does not have this yet. There are also limited studies on how local communities can be involved in carbon accounting. Similarly, there are few studies on the value chain of the harvested wood products, and their impact on local livelihoods.

1.4 Agroforestry

3.4.1 Introduction

Agroforestry is a sustainable land management practice in which trees and crops are grown together. Agroforestry is a traditional practice in Nepal, as the planting of fruit and fodder trees in edges of terraces of croplands is commonly practised in the hill and mountain regions. Agroforestry can sequester significant amounts of carbon and simultaneously increase agricultural production, provide fodder and litter for livestock production, and fuelwood for household energy needs. In the Nepalese context, high-value non-timber forest products, mainly medicinal and aromatic plants, are also a component of agroforestry. Therefore, in the hills and mountain regions of Nepal, agroforestry is also considered a way of improving the livelihoods of small farmers.

3.4.2 Policy context

Several policies have acknowledged the contribution of agroforestry in agricultural households and fostered an enabling environment for agroforestry development. The Forest Act 1993 aims to promote agroforestry as a method of forest conservation and development. Similarly, the Forest Sector Strategy (2016-25) aims to promote agroforestry in barren lands and privately owned land. Nepal is the second country in the world to formulate a national agroforestry policy, the Agroforestry Policy (2019). Nepal's 20-year agriculture development plan, the Agriculture Development Strategy (2015-2035) recognises agroforestry as a tool for achieving environmental sustainability, increasing food security, and improving the livelihoods of resource-poor farmers. It envisages a pro-poor approach in agroforestry to restoring degraded lands and increasing productivity of low productive agricultural lands. Likewise, the Climate Change Policy 2019 has a provision for the promotion of agroforestry with multipurpose trees in abandoned agricultural land. Nepal's Second Nationally Determined Contribution 2020 has provision for agroforestry through afforestation or reforestation of public and private lands. Nepal's current 15th Five Year Development Plan (2019 – 2023) aims to promote agroforestry in barren and marginal lands of hill regions with multipurpose trees and high-value products. Recently, the Ministry of Forests and Environment (MoFE) published the Model Agroforestry Program Implementation Procedure 2021, which supports individual farmers or farmer groups to adopt agroforestry practice in plots of land larger than ten hectares. It does this by providing grants, saplings of medicinal plants, fodder trees, non-timber trees and multipurpose tree species in the marginal lands.

3.4.3 Current land use and potential land-use competition

There is no record of current land-use area or future projections for agroforestry. Since the Nepalese government has a strategy of utilising barren and marginalised lands, and degraded forests and land below electricity transmission lines (MoFE, 2021), there will be less competition with the existing forest and agricultural land. In recent years, since land abandonment is increasing in mountain regions (Chaudhary et al., 2018; DFRS, 2015), there is the potential of an increase in agroforestry in abandoned agricultural land.

3.4.4 Climate risks & sensitivities

Fires in the agroforestry plantations is not common in Nepal, since most of the forest fires are deliberate attempt by people living in the areas. However, extreme climatic events including drought, floods and hailstones are important climate risks that affect commercial agroforestry practices in Nepal. These extreme climatic events mainly affect agroforestry crops and small trees rather than large agroforestry trees. Hailstone is mostly common in the mid-hill region, while flooding affects terai (southern plain) region. While there is no reliable data, but stakeholders believe that the frequency and intensity of hailstone is increasing in the mid hills' regions.

3.4.5 Economic implications

The purpose of agroforestry is to maximise economic benefit from both agriculture and forest. Hence, much of the new agroforestry practices are focused on high-value products or medicinal plants. Neupane and Thapa (2001) found that higher benefit from sericulture-based agroforestry (USD 1582/ha) than the non-traditional system (USD 804/ha). The benefit-cost ratio was 2.5 in the agroforestry intervention as compared to 1.8 without intervention. Similarly, a study by Cedamon et al. (2019) found that different agroforestry practices can provide additional revenue. The study showed that if commercial harvesting of trees is allowed, revenue will be increased by EUR1 479 to 2,022 per farmer. Net economic return is focused more on market-oriented agroforestry practices such as tomato (EUR 12,245), cardamom (EUR 1,923), banana (EUR 1,813) , round chilli (EUR 1,201) and ginger (EUR 1,124) (Pandit et al., 2019).

3.4.6 Co-benefits and trade-offs

Co-benefits

Food security: Food security is an important function of agroforestry in Nepal. A study by Cedamon et al. (2019) showed that, among the different agroforestry practices, planting high yielding fodder trees for commercial goat production and market-oriented timber production are agroforestry interventions that increase food security for rural households. A similar study by (Pandit et al., 2019) showed that after the implementation of agroforestry projects the percentage of food sufficient households increased from 52 to 69.

Biodiversity: Agroforestry in farmland can be a solution for biodiversity conservation, providing a reservoir of genetic diversity for tree species. A study of traditional agroforestry practices in Nepal showed that the species diversity index is higher with medium and large landowners (Acharya, 2006). Also, the farmland of upper castes *Brahmin/Chettri* area has large species diversity than those of the lower caste *Dalits* (Pokhrel et al., 2015).

Trade-offs

Financial: Selecting agroforestry systems with high carbon sequestration capacity could provide less return to the farmers (Middendorp et al., 2018; Tschora and Cherubini, 2020). Therefore, it is important to optimize the benefit for farmers and carbon sequestration capacity of agroforestry practices.

¹ 1€ = 131.55 NPR

3.4.7 Risks associated with scaling up

Nepal is globally 2nd in formulating national agroforestry policy for increasing the productivity of agriculture, forestry, and livestock sectors. However, Nepal lacks proper policy and therefore, subnational (provincial level) and local policies for aligning with national agroforestry policy is lacking. Farmer and private sector expect support and subsidies from the government due to the required high initial investments and technical support. But there is no there is no proper political commitment yet forming the main barriers for small farmers. There is also a lack of clear policy in agroforestry, in particular the commercial trade of the harvested wood from agroforestry, which limits the scaling of agroforestry at the national level.

Although Nepal has ample agroforestry policies, there is a lack of proper technical knowledge alongside transfer mechanisms to small farmers. Although there is a consensus that high-value crops or non-timber forest products in agroforestry systems are important in improving the livelihoods of small farmers, there is limited detailed analysis of such products, and without proper market development, they are less likely to be adopted by small farmers.

3.4.8 Research gaps

The size of the return from agroforestry practices is dependent on the type of trees and crops. However, the agro-ecological site-specific suitability of different agroforestry systems has not yet been studied in detail. Traditional or subsistence agroforestry systems, which includes home garden, crop with fodder trees, is widespread in Nepal, mainly in mid-hills and mountain regions. Economic analysis of market-oriented intervention approaches needed to be studied further. Only a few percentages of farmers are engaged in market-oriented agroforestry, including medicinal and high-value crops. Studies on successful cases of agroforestry need to be carried out, to guide and support the further promotion of agroforestry at the national level.

3.5 Organic Farming

3.5.1 Introduction

The development of organic agriculture was a response to the environmental pollution caused by intensive agriculture, which uses an excessive amount of mineral fertilisers and pesticides (Kwiatkowski et al., 2020). Growing consumer demand for organic farming has received attention from researchers, policymakers, environmental NGOs, and farmers in both developing and developed countries. At present, the market for organic produce is around 106 billion Euros, with organic production taking place in 187 countries, by 3.1 million producers over 35.1 million hectares (FiBL, 2021). Nowadays, although the impact of organic farming in climate change mitigation is contested (Leifeld et al., 2013), it is increasingly recognised as a major tool for climate change mitigation due to its huge capacity to store carbon in agricultural soil. Organic soil amendment increases carbon sequestration, enhances long term organic pools, reduces greenhouse gas emissions and improves

the resilience of the agroecosystems (Tautges et al., 2019). In developing countries, including Nepal, organic farming is increasingly popular, as farmers can get premium prices, resulting in an improvement to their livelihoods (Karki et al., 2011).

3.5.2 Policy context

Organic agriculture in Nepal is well embedded in national agricultural policies. Several policies have acknowledged the potential of organic agriculture in the overall development of the agricultural sector in Nepal. The Agriculture Development Strategy (2015-2035) aims to promote organic branding for value addition and targets an increase of organic matter in agricultural soils to 4% by 2035 from a baseline of 1% in 2010 (MoAD, 2014a). Similarly, Nepal's Second Nationally Determined Contribution 2020 has a provision to promote soil organic matter to 3.5% by 2030. The current 15th Five Year Development Plan aims to increase the share of organic farming in agricultural trade by promoting the involvement of farmer groups, cooperatives and the private sector (NPC, 2020). Recently, Nepal's Ministry of Agricultural and Livestock Development (MoALD) formed a high-level committee with multiple stakeholders, including NGOs, the private sector, farmers, to formulate an organic agriculture strategy. The government also formed a high-level task force to develop a proposal for a holistic program to guide the development of organic farming at the national level.

At the regional level, the government of Karnali province recently declared its ambition to become the 'Organic Karnali Province' (GoKP, 2018). The Policy and Programme of the Government of Karnali Province for Fiscal Year 2018/19 states that support for organic food production and marketing will be initially promoted in five mountain districts and five other districts. For this, the Karnali province has a slogan, 'Increased organic farming for prosperous Karnali'. At the district level, the Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock Development (MoALD) provides grants for organic fertiliser, which is operated through Organic Fertiliser Subsidy Program Implementation Procedure 2019 (MoALD, 2019). MoALD is also implementing pilot programmes for organic farming in 12 districts (Gauchan et al., 2020).

3.5.3 Current land use and potential land-use competition

In much of the remote hill and mountain regions, chemical fertiliser and pesticides are not generally used. During a discussion with local experts, it was estimated that around 26% of farmland is organic in Nepal, which can be referred to as organic by default. However, the area under organic certification is very low. Currently, about 9,361 hectares of agricultural land is under certified organic production (FiBL, 2021), which is negligible in comparison to the total cropped area of 2.83 million hectares. Organic certification is mainly applied to export-oriented crops including organic tea, coffee, and high value aromatic and medicinal plant products. Due to the lack of awareness of the need for organic certification, and low technical capacity to certify and the expensive certification system, farmers usually do not opt for organic certification. There are no future projections for organic farming development in Nepal. Due to increased international and national consumer demand, and increased

government interest in the promotion of organic production, organic production will be increased in future. However, the pace of increase in organic production will be low, as current policies favour conventional agriculture by providing subsidies and grants for inputs, including chemical fertilisers.

3.5.4 Climate risks & sensitivities

Similar to conventional farming, flood, drought and hailstones are important climate risks that affect crop production from organic farming. Experts mentioned that crop failure in organic farming due to these extreme climatic events deter farmers from adopting organic farming, as it can incur low returns. Experts mentioned that although it is difficult to highlight type of climate risks in the organic farming is increasing as the level of crop damage by the extreme climatic events such as high rainfall (floods).

3.5.5 Economic implications

Farmers can receive greater economic benefits from the organic farming in comparison to conventional farming; however, benefits vary widely depending on crop type and region. A study on organic tea in Nepal by Karki et al. (2011) found that observed economic benefit is one of the key reasons to switch to organic production. For example, a certified organic farmer can get a price that is 20% higher for fresh coffee and cherry when compared to non-certified smallholders in the conventional market (Kattel, 2017). Similarly, a study of rice farmers in Nepal showed that organic rice production has a benefit-cost ratio of 2.2 in organic rice production, as compared to 1.9 in conventional rice production (Sapkota et al., 2021). A similar study in carrot production found that the benefit-cost ratio was higher (1.52) for organic carrots than the conventional carrot (1.44) (Adhikari, 2009).

3.5.6 Co-benefits and trade-offs

Environmental co-benefits

Organic farming has a lower environmental impact than conventional farming. A meta-analysis of European research by Tuomisto et al. (2012) found that soil organic matter was 7% higher in organic farms than conventional farms. Also, it was found that the rate of nutrient losses including nitrogen leaching, ammonia, and nitrous oxide emission, were lower in organic farms. A similar meta-analysis by Rahmann (2011) showed higher biodiversity in organic farms than conventional farms. Likewise, energy consumption is much lower in organic farms (38%) as compared to conventional farms (Gündoğmuş, 2006; Koesling et al., 2017).

Trade-offs

Yield loss in organic farming is a major trade-off, that can reduce income of farmers. A meta-analysis by (Gong et al., 2022) to quantify the trade-offs between crop yield and biodiversity in conventional and organic farming showed that organic farming increased biodiversity by 23% but also decreased

the yield. Similarly, Seufert et al. (2012) found that organic farming can have similar yields to conventional farming only if they follow good management practices.

3.5.7 Risks associated with scaling up

Despite Nepalese farmers showing increasing interest in organic farming, it is difficult to upscale at the national level due to the challenge of market development and lack of knowledge in soil nutrient management. Certified organic farming is not generally practiced due to the lack of infrastructure and markets. The government continues to provide subsidies for chemical fertilisers, which lowers prices. On the other hand, commercial production and trade of organic fertilisers are also not well developed and organic fertilisers are often expensive and are less reliable in quality. Moreover, internal markets for organic farming are growing, but are not well developed. People tend to buy organic foods by 'trust', as most of the products are not certified. While some farmers are receiving good returns due to direct selling, due to the involvement of several intermediaries, most farmers are not getting an appropriate premium price from the organic production except in export-oriented organic products.

3.5.8 Research gaps

Consultation with stakeholders showed that conventional farmers believe that switching to organic farming means incurring a loss. This is because there is not much local economic analysis of the process of switching to organic farming in different agro-climatic contexts of Nepal. A comparative study exploring the economic profitability of different organic products in different agro-ecological regions, with distinct market features, would be useful. Despite an increase in market demand for the export oriented organic crops including tea, coffee and herbs (Karki et al., 2011), detail studies on international marketing potential of these crops is limited.

4. Conclusions

We identified a portfolio of land-based mitigation technologies and practices (LMTs) in Nepal - forest management, agroforestry, organic farming and rice management. To better understand the realistic future impact of these LMTs on the economy, resource utilization and environment, scaling scenarios for these LMTs need to be optimized. The outcome depends on how Nepal translates these LMTs into policy, and how these policies are implemented in local and sub national levels.

During the interviews and workshop, the stakeholders pointed out that appropriate policy implementation and technical and financial support -- which are crucial for scaling up these technologies -- are lacking. Therefore, further research on better implementation of LMTs is needed to provide appropriate technical support to the farmers. Future strategies should include local capacity building for appropriate research and extension systems. Additionally, a financial incentive mechanism needs to be developed for the farmers and landowners as a reward for mitigation. If implemented sustainably, the LMT portfolio could be a best option for co-delivering improved climate mitigation, increased soil fertility and enhanced well-being of farmers and landowners.

References

- Acharya, Krishna Prasad 2006. Linking Trees on Farms with Biodiversity Conservation in Subsistence Farming Systems in Nepal. *Biodiversity & Conservation* 15: 631-646. doi: 10.1007/s10531-005-2091-7
- Adhikari, Raj Kumar 2009. Economics of organic vs inorganic carrot production in Nepal. *Journal of Agriculture and Environment* 10: 27-33.
- Amatya, S. M., E. Cedamon and I. Nuberg 2018. AGROFORESTRY SYSTEMS AND PRACTICES IN NEPAL- Revised Edition. Rampur, Nepal: Agriculture and Forestry University, 2018.
- Anup, K. C., Roshani Manandhar, Rajeshor Paudel and Sujan Ghimire 2018. Increase of forest carbon biomass due to community forestry management in Nepal. *Journal of Forestry Research* 29: 429-438. doi: 10.1007/s11676-017-0438-z
- Aryal, Kishor, Prakash Singh Thapa and Dhananjaya Lamichhane 2019. Revisiting agroforestry for building climate resilient communities: a case of package-based integrated agroforestry practices in Nepal. *Emerg Sci J* 3: 303-311.
- Asbeck, Thomas, Francesco Sabatini, Andrey L. D. Augustynczyk, Marco Basile, Jan Helbach, Marlotte Jonker, Anna Knuff and Jürgen Bauhus 2021. Biodiversity response to forest management intensity, carbon stocks and net primary production in temperate montane forests. *Scientific Reports* 11: 1625. doi: 10.1038/s41598-020-80499-4
- Banjade, Mani and Naya Paudel 2008. Mobile Pastoralism in Crisis: Challenges, Conflicts and Status of Pasture Tenure in Nepal Mountains. *J.For. Livelihood* 7.
- Basnyat, Bijendra, Thorsten Treue, Ridish Kumar Pokharel, Srijana Baral and Yam Bahadur Rumba 2020. Re-centralisation through fake Scientificness: The case of community forestry in Nepal. *Forest Policy and Economics* 115: 102147. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2020.102147>
- Bhandari, Dila Ram, Prakash Kumar Sanjel and Santosh Adhikari 2017. Policy Review of Paddy Production in Nepal. *Rice Science and Technology in Nepal*: 719-736.
- Bhullar, MS, Sukhpal Singh, Sunny Kumar and Gurjeet Gill 2018. Agronomic and economic impacts of direct seeded rice in Punjab. *Agric. Res. J* 55: 236-242.
- Bouman, B. A. M., E. Humphreys, T. P. Tuong and R. Barker 2007. Rice and Water. In *Advances in Agronomy*, ed. Donald L. Sparks, 187-237: Academic Press.
- Buotte, Polly C., Beverly E. Law, William J. Ripple and Logan T. Berner 2020. Carbon sequestration and biodiversity co-benefits of preserving forests in the western United States. *Ecological Applications* 30: e02039. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/eap.2039>
- Caparrós, Alejandro and Frédéric Jacquemont 2003. Conflicts between biodiversity and carbon sequestration programs: economic and legal implications. *Ecological Economics* 46: 143-157. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0921-8009\(03\)00138-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0921-8009(03)00138-1)
- Cedamon, E. D., I. Nuberg, R. Mulia, B. Lusiana, Y. R. Subedi and K. K. Shrestha 2019. Contribution of integrated forest-farm system on household food security in the mid-hills of Nepal: assessment with EnLiFT model. *Australian Forestry* 82: 32-44. doi: 10.1080/00049158.2019.1610212

Chaudhary, Suresh, Yukuan Wang, Amod Mani Dixit, Narendra Raj Khanal, Pei Xu, Bin Fu, Kun Yan, Qin Liu, Yafeng Lu and Ming Li 2020. A Synopsis of Farmland Abandonment and Its Driving Factors in Nepal. *Land* 9: 84.

Chaudhary, Suresh, Yukuan Wang, Narendra Raj Khanal, Pei Xu, Bin Fu, Amod Mani Dixit, Kun Yan, Qin Liu and Yafeng Lu 2018. Social Impact of Farmland Abandonment and Its Eco-Environmental Vulnerability in the High Mountain Region of Nepal: A Case Study of Dordi River Basin. *Sustainability (Switzerland)* 10: 2331.

Dahal, Ngamindra and Roshan M Bajracharya 2010. Prospects of soil organic carbon sequestration: implications for Nepal's mountain agriculture. *Journal of Forest and Livelihood* 9: 45-56.

Dahal, Ngamindra, Roshan Man Bajracharya and Juerg Merz 2016. Prospects of bicar as soil amendment in Nepal hill farming systems. *Journal of Agriculture and Environment* 17: 92-103.

DFRS 2015. State of Nepal's Forests. Forest Resource Assessment (FRA) Nepal, Department of Forest Research and Survey (DFRS). Kathmandu, Nepal.

Dhakal, M, Shrawan K Sah, Andrew McDonald and Anant P Regmi 2015. Perception and economics of dry direct seeded rice in tarai of Nepal. *Journal of Agriculture and Environment* 16: 103-111.

DoF 2017. Hamro Ban: Annual report 2073/74 BS, Department of Forests, Ministry of Forests and Environment, Kathmandu, Nepal.

FAO and UNEP 2020. The State of the World's Forests 2020. Forests, biodiversity and people. Rome.

FiBL 2021. The World of Organic Agriculture: Statistics and Emerging Trends 2021, Research Institute of Organic Agriculture, FiBL, Frick and IFOAM - Organics International, Bonn

Gauchan, Devendra, Epsha Palikhey, Sajal Sthapit, Bal Joshi, Hira Manandhar and Devra Jarvis 2020. Organic Farming and Marketing of Traditional Crops in Nepal Mountains: Gaps, Issues and Opportunities for Improvement.

Gautam, A. P., G. P. Shivakoti and E. L. Webb 2004. A review of forest policies, institutions, and changes in the resource condition in Nepal. *The International Forestry Review* 6: 136-148.

Giri, Kalpana and Ika Darnhofer 2010. Nepali Women Using Community Forestry as a Platform for Social Change. *Society & Natural Resources* 23: 1216-1229. doi: 10.1080/08941921003620533

GoKP 2018. Policy and Programme of The Government of Karnali Province for Fiscal Year 2018/19, Government of Karnali Province, Office of the Chief Minister and the Council of Ministers, Surkhet

GoN 2016. Sustainable Forest Management in Nepal, Multistakeholder forestry Programme, Government of Nepal, Kathmandu.

Gong, Shanxing, Jenny A. Hodgson, Teja Tschardtke, Yunhui Liu, Wopke van der Werf, Péter Batáry, Johannes M. H. Knops and Yi Zou 2022. Biodiversity and yield trade-offs for organic farming. *Ecology Letters* 25: 1699-1710. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.14017>

Griscom, Bronson W., Justin Adams, Peter W. Ellis, Richard A. Houghton, Guy Lomax, Daniela A. Miteva, William H. Schlesinger, David Shoch, Juha V. Siikamäki, Pete Smith, Peter Woodbury, Chris Zganjar, Allen Blackman, João Campari, Richard T. Conant, Christopher Delgado, Patricia Elias, Trisha Gopalakrishna, Marisa R. Hamsik, Mario Herrero, Joseph Kiesecker, Emily Landis, Lars Laestadius, Sara M. Leavitt, Susan Minnemeyer, Stephen Polasky, Peter Potapov, Francis E. Putz, Jonathan Sanderman,

Marcel Silviu, Eva Wollenberg and Joseph Fargione 2017. Natural climate solutions. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences 114: 11645-11650. doi: 10.1073/pnas.1710465114

Gündoğmuş, Erdemir 2006. Energy use on organic farming: A comparative analysis on organic versus conventional apricot production on small holdings in Turkey. Energy Conversion and Management 47: 3351-3359. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2006.01.001>

Gupta Choudhury, S., S. Srivastava, R. Singh, S. K. Chaudhari, D. K. Sharma, S. K. Singh and D. Sarkar 2014. Tillage and residue management effects on soil aggregation, organic carbon dynamics and yield attribute in rice-wheat cropping system under reclaimed sodic soil. Soil and Tillage Research 136: 76-83. doi: 10.1016/j.still.2013.10.001

Hussain, Mubshar, Muhammad Farooq, Ghulam Shabir, Muhammad Bismillah Khan, Abu Bakar Zia and Dong-Jin Lee 2012. Delay in Planting Decreases Wheat Productivity. International Journal of Agriculture & Biology 14: 533-539.

IPCC 2019. Climate Change and Land: an IPCC special report on climate change, desertification, land degradation, sustainable land management, food security, and greenhouse gas fluxes in terrestrial ecosystems [P.R. Shukla, J. Skea, E. Calvo Buendia, V. Masson-Delmotte, H.-O. Pörtner, D. C. Roberts, P. Zhai, R. Slade, S. Connors, R. van Diemen, M. Ferrat, E. Haughey, S. Luz, S. Neogi, M. Pathak, J. Petzold, J. Portugal Pereira, P. Vyas, E. Huntley, K. Kissick, M. Belkacemi, J. Malley, (eds.)].

Joshi, Krishna Dev, Santosh Upadhyay, Pashupati Chaudhary, Suchit Shrestha, Kamal Bhattarai, Aashif Iqbal Khan and Bhava Prasad Tripathi 2020. The Rice Processing Industry in Nepal: Constraints and Opportunities. Agricultural Sciences 11: 1060-1080.

Joshi, Madhab 2016. Status of Methane Gas Emission from Paddy Fields in Nepal. Agronomy Journal of Nepal 4: 142-148.

K C, Anup, Indra Koirala and Naveen Adhikari 2015. Cost-Benefit Analysis of a Community Forest in Nepal. Journal of Sustainable Forestry 34: 199-213. doi: 10.1080/10549811.2014.1003074

Kakumanu, Krishna Reddy, Gurava Reddy Kotapati, Udaya Sekhar Nagothu, Palanisami Kuppanan and Suresh Reddy Kallam 2018. Adaptation to climate change and variability: a case of direct seeded rice in Andhra Pradesh, India. Journal of Water and Climate Change 10: 419-430. doi: 10.2166/wcc.2018.141

Karki, Lokendra, Rosa Schleenbecker and Ulrich Hamm 2011. Factors influencing a conversion to organic farming in Nepalese tea farms. Journal of Agriculture and Rural Development in the Tropics and Subtropics (JARTS) 112: 113-123.

Kattel, RR 2017. Impacts of group organic certification of coffee on socio-economic and environmental sustainability in Nepal. Journal of Agriculture and Forestry University 1: 49-60.

Khan, Md, Avinash Kishore and Pramod Kumar Joshi 2016. Gender dimensions on farmers' preferences for direct-seeded rice with drum seeder in India: International Food Policy Research Institute.

Koesling, Matthias, Sissel Hansen and Maximilian Schueler 2017. Variations of energy intensities and potential for improvements in energy utilisation on conventional and organic Norwegian dairy farms. Journal of Cleaner Production 164: 301-314. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.06.124>

Kumar, Virender and Jagdish K. Ladha 2011. Chapter Six - Direct Seeding of Rice: Recent Developments and Future Research Needs. In Advances in Agronomy, ed. Donald L. Sparks, 297-413: Academic Press.

Kwiatkowski, Cezary A., Elżbieta Harasim, Beata Feledyn-Szewczyk and Jacek Antonkiewicz 2020. Enzymatic Activity of Loess Soil in Organic and Conventional Farming Systems. *Agriculture* 10: 135.

Laing, A. M., C. H. Roth, L. Chialue, D. S. Gaydon, C. M. Grünbühel, T. Inthavong, V. Phengvichith, J. Schiller, Sipaseuth, K. Thiravong and L. J. Williams 2018. Mechanised dry seeding is an adaptation strategy for managing climate risks and reducing labour costs in rainfed rice production in lowland Lao PDR. *Field Crops Research* 225: 32-46. doi: 10.1016/j.fcr.2018.05.020

Leifeld, Jens, Denis A. Angers, Claire Chenu, Jürg Fuhrer, Thomas Kätterer and David S. Powlson 2013. Organic farming gives no climate change benefit through soil carbon sequestration. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 110: E984-E984. doi: 10.1073/pnas.1220724110

Liu, Hongyan, S Hussain, Manman Zheng, Liming Sun, S Fahad, Jianliang Huang, Kehui Cui and Lixiao Nie 2014. Progress and constraints of dry direct-seeded rice in China. *J. Food Agric. Environ* 12: 465-472.

Middendorp, Romaike S., Veerle Vanacker and Eric F. Lambin 2018. Impacts of shaded agroforestry management on carbon sequestration, biodiversity and farmers income in cocoa production landscapes. *Landscape Ecology* 33: 1953-1974. doi: 10.1007/s10980-018-0714-0

MoAD 2014a. Agriculture Development Strategy (ADS) 2014, Ministry of Agricultural Development, Kathmandu.

MoAD 2020. Statistical Information on Nepalese Agriculture. In *Statistical Information on Nepalese Agriculture*. Singha Durbar, Kathmandu, Nepal: Agri-Business Promotion and Statistics Division, Government of Nepal, Ministry of Agricultural Development.

MoAD 2014b. Statistical Information on Nepalese Agriculture. In *Statistical Information on Nepalese Agriculture*. Singha Durbar, Kathmandu, Nepal: Agri-Business Promotion and Statistics Division, Government of Nepal, Ministry of Agricultural Development.

MoALD 2019. Organic Fertilizer Grant Program Implementation Procedure 2019, Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock Development, Kathmandu.

MoFE 2021. Model Agroforestry Programme Implementation Procedure 2021, Ministry of Forests and Environment, Kathmandu, Nepal.

MoFE 2019. National Climate Change Policy, 2076 (2019), Ministry of Forests and Environment, Kathmandu, Nepal.

MoFE 2018a. National Ramsar Strategy and Action Plan, Nepal (2018-2024), Government of Nepal, Ministry of Forests and Environment, Kathmandu, Nepal.

MoFE 2018b. Nepal National REDD+ Strategy (2018-2022), Ministry of Forests and Environment, Government of Nepal.

MoFE 2018c. Nepal National REDD+ Strategy (2018-2022), Ministry of Forests and Environment, Government of Nepal.

MOFSC 2016a. Forest Sector Strategy (2016-2025), Government of Nepal, Ministry of Forests and Soil Conservation, Kathmandu, Nepal.

MoFSC 2016b. Forest Sector Strategy (2016-2025), Ministry of Forests and Soil Conservation, Kathmandu.

MoFSC 2012. National Wetlands Policy 2012, Ministry of Forests and Soil Conservation, Kathmandu, Nepal.

MoFSC 2015a. Nepal REDD+ Strategy Part I: Operational Summary, Government of Nepal, Ministry of Forests and Soil Conservation, REDD Implementation Centre, Kathmandu, Nepal.

MoFSC 2015b. State of Nepal's Forests, Government of Nepal, Ministry of Forests and Soil Conservation, Department of Forest Research and Survey, Kathmandu, Nepal.

MoFSC 2014. Understanding drivers and causes of deforestation and forest degradation in Nepal: potential policies and measures for REDD+ , Discussion Paper February 2014, Ministry of Forests and Soil Conservation, REDD Forestry and Climate Change Cell.

MoLRM 2015. National land use policy 2015, Ministry of Land Reform and Management, Government of Nepal, . Kathmandu, Nepal.

MoPE 2017. Nepal's GHG Inventory For Third National Communication to the UNFCCC, Ministry of Population and Environment, Government of Nepal, Singh Durbar, Kathmandu.

.

Nepal, Pashupati, Narendra R. Khanal, Yili Zhang, Basanta Paudel and Linshan Liu 2020. Land use policies in Nepal: An overview. Land Degradation & Development 31: 2203-2212. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.3621>

Neupane, Ramji P. and Gopal B. Thapa 2001. Impact of agroforestry intervention on soil fertility and farm income under the subsistence farming system of the middle hills, Nepal. Agriculture, ecosystems & environment 84: 157-167. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-8809\(00\)00203-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-8809(00)00203-6)

NPC 2020. The Fifteenth Plan (Fiscal Year 2019/20 – 2023/24), Government of Nepal, National Planning Commission, Kathmandu.

Nuberg, I. K., K. K. Shrestha and A. G. Bartlett 2019. Pathways to forest wealth in Nepal. Australian Forestry 82: 106-120. doi: 10.1080/00049158.2019.1614805

Ovando, Paola and Roy Brouwer 2019. A review of economic approaches modeling the complex interactions between forest management and watershed services. Forest Policy and Economics 100: 164-176. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2018.12.007>

Pandit, Bishnu Hari, Ian Nuberg, Krishna K. Shrestha, Edwin Cedamon, Swoyambhu Man Amatya, Bishow Dhakal and Ramji Prasad Neupane 2019. Impacts of market-oriented agroforestry on farm income and food security: insights from Kavre and Lamjung districts of Nepal. Agroforestry Systems 93: 1593-1604. doi: 10.1007/s10457-018-0273-z

Pandit, N. R., J. Mulder, S. E. Hale, H. P. Schmidt and G. Cornelissen 2017a. Biochar from "Kon Tiki" flame curtain and other kilns: Effects of nutrient enrichment and kiln type on crop yield and soil chemistry. PLoS ONE 12: e0176378. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0176378

Pandit, N. R., J. Mulder, S. E. Hale, A. R. Zimmerman, B. H. Pandit and G. Cornelissen 2018. Multi-year double cropping biochar field trials in Nepal: Finding the optimal biochar dose through agronomic trials and cost-benefit analysis. Science of the Total Environment 637-638: 1333-1341. doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.05.107

Pandit, Ram, Prem Raj Neupane and Bishnu Hari Wagle 2017b. Economics of carbon sequestration in community forests: Evidence from REDD+ piloting in Nepal. *Journal of Forest Economics* 26: 9-29. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfe.2016.11.002>

Pathak, H, AN Tewari, S Sankhyan, DS Dubey, U Mina, Virender K Singh, N Jain and A Bhatia 2011. Direct-seeded rice: potential, performance and problems—A review. *Current Advances in Agricultural Sciences* 3: 77-88.

Pathak, H., S. Sankhyan, D. S. Dubey, A. Bhatia and N. Jain 2013. Dry direct-seeding of rice for mitigating greenhouse gas emission: field experimentation and simulation. *Paddy and Water Environment* 11: 593-601. doi: 10.1007/s10333-012-0352-0

Pokhrel, Chandra P, Arbindra Timilsina, Rajib Khanal, Kazuo Ando and Ram Kailash P Yadav 2015. Biodiversity in agroforestry systems: A case study in homegardens of Gulmi and Palpa districts, Western Nepal. *Journal of Institute of Science and Technology* 20: 87-96.

Poudel, BS 2009. Wetland conservation in Nepal: policies, practices, problems and possibilities. *Banko Janakari*: 5-9.

Poudyal, Ramhari, Pavel Loskot, Rabindra Nepal, Ranjan Parajuli and Shree Krishna Khadka 2019. Mitigating the current energy crisis in Nepal with renewable energy sources. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 116: 109388. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2019.109388>

Price, James I and Matthew T Heberling 2018. The effects of source water quality on drinking water treatment costs: a review and synthesis of empirical literature. *Ecological Economics* 151: 195-209.

Rahmann, Gerold 2011. Biodiversity and Organic farming: What do we know? *Landbauforschung Volkenrode* 61: 189-208.

Rai, Rajesh Kumar, Arun Dhakal, Madan S. Khadayat and Sunita Ranabhat 2017. Is collaborative forest management in Nepal able to provide benefits to distantly located users? *Forest Policy and Economics* 83: 156-161. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2017.08.004>

Rai, Rajesh, Basant Pant and Mani Nepal 2018. REDD+ in Nepal: Experiences from the REDD readiness phase. In *REDD+ in Nepal: Experiences from the REDD readiness phase*, eds. Sindhu Dhungana, Mohan Poudel and Trishna Signg Bhandari. Kathmandu: . REDD Implementation Centre, Ministry of Forests and Environment, Government of Nepal.

Rana, Md. Masud, Md. Abdullah Al Mamun, Afruz Zahan, Md. Nayeem Ahmed and Md. Abdul Jalil Mridha 2014. Effect of Planting Methods on the Yield and Yield Attributes of Short Duration & Aman Rice. *American Journal of Plant Sciences* Vol.05No.03: 5. doi: 10.4236/ajps.2014.53033

Rimal, Bhagawat, Lifu Zhang, Nigel Stork, Sean Sloan and Sushila Rijal 2018. Urban Expansion Occurred at the Expense of Agricultural Lands in the Tarai Region of Nepal from 1989 to 2016. *Sustainability* 10: 1341.

Sapkota, Bidya, Ananta Subedi, Kalyani Tripathi and Shiva Chandra Dhakal 2021. Economics of Organic vs Inorganic Rice Production: A Case of Chitwan District of Nepal. *Journal of Nepal Agricultural Research Council* 7: 109-121. doi: 10.3126/jnarc.v7i1.36933

Schmidt, Hans-Peter, Bishnu Hari Pandit, Gerard Cornelissen and Claudia I. Kammann 2017. Biochar-Based Fertilization with Liquid Nutrient Enrichment: 21 Field Trials Covering 13 Crop Species in Nepal. *Land Degradation & Development* 28: 2324-2342. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.2761>

Seufert, Verena, Navin Ramankutty and Jonathan A. Foley 2012. Comparing the yields of organic and conventional agriculture. *Nature* 485: 229-232. doi: 10.1038/nature11069

Shrestha Shiva, Kumar 2015. Sustainable soil management practices: A key to combat soil desertification in the hills of Nepal. *World Journal of Science, Technology and Sustainable Development* 12: 13-24. doi: 10.1108/WJSTSD-07-2014-0015

Singh, S. K., Venkatesh Bharadwaj, T. C. Thakur, S. P. Pachauri, P. P. Singh and A. K. Mishra 2009. Influence of crop establishment methods on methane emission from rice fields. *Current Science* 97: 84-89.

Sitaula, B. K., R. M. Bajracharya, B. R. Singh and B. Solberg 2004. Factors affecting organic carbon dynamics in soils of Nepal/Himalayan region – a review and analysis. *Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems* 70: 215-229. doi: 10.1023/B:FRES.0000048474.85331.7d

Soto-Navarro, C., C. Ravilious, A. Arnell, X. de Lamo, M. Harfoot, S. L. L. Hill, O. R. Wear, M. Santoro, A. Bouvet, S. Mermoz, T. Le Toan, J. Xia, S. Liu, W. Yuan, S. A. Spawn, H. K. Gibbs, S. Ferrier, T. Harwood, R. Alkemade, A. M. Schipper, G. Schmidt-Traub, B. Strassburg, L. Miles, N. D. Burgess and V. Kapos 2020. Mapping co-benefits for carbon storage and biodiversity to inform conservation policy and action. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 375: 20190128. doi:10.1098/rstb.2019.0128

Subedi, Rosan, Jay Dutta, Rishi Kattel and Ankit Koirala 2017. Effectiveness of Agriculture forestry and environment committee in adoption of Sustainable Soil Management Practices (SSMP) technology in Ramechhap and Dolakha, Nepal. *Alanya Akademik Bakış* 1: 27-35. doi: 10.29023/alanyaakademik.311059

Tabbal, D. F., B. A. M. Bouman, S. I. Bhuiyan, E. B. Sibayan and M. A. Sattar 2002. On-farm strategies for reducing water input in irrigated rice; case studies in the Philippines. *Agricultural Water Management* 56: 93-112. doi: 10.1016/S0378-3774(02)00007-0

Tautges, Nicole E., Jessica L. Chiartas, Amélie C. M. Gaudin, Anthony T. O'Geen, Israel Herrera and Kate M. Scow 2019. Deep soil inventories reveal that impacts of cover crops and compost on soil carbon sequestration differ in surface and subsurface soils. *Global Change Biology* 25: 3753-3766. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14762>

Tschora, Héloïse and Francesco Cherubini 2020. Co-benefits and trade-offs of agroforestry for climate change mitigation and other sustainability goals in West Africa. *Global Ecology and Conservation* 22: e00919. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2020.e00919>

Tuomisto, H. L., I. D. Hodge, P. Riordan and D. W. Macdonald 2012. Does organic farming reduce environmental impacts? – A meta-analysis of European research. *Journal of Environmental Management* 112: 309-320. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2012.08.018>

Tuong, TP and BAM Bouman 2003. Rice production in water-scarce environments, Water productivity in agriculture: Limits and opportunities for improvement, In Kijne, J.W., Barker, R., Molden, D., Eds.; CABI Publishing: Wallingford, UK. 1: 13-42.

Uddin, Kabir, Mir Abdul Matin and Sajana Maharjan 2018. Assessment of Land Cover Change and Its Impact on Changes in Soil Erosion Risk in Nepal. *Sustainability* 10: 4715.

Wang, W., S. Peng, H. Liu, Y. Tao, J. Huang, K. Cui and L. Nie 2017. The possibility of replacing puddled transplanted flooded rice with dry seeded rice in central China: A review. *Field Crops Research* 214: 310-320. doi: 10.1016/j.fcr.2017.09.028

Xu, Le, Xiaoxiao Li, Xinyu Wang, Dongliang Xiong and Fei Wang 2019. Comparing the Grain Yields of Direct-Seeded and Transplanted Rice: A Meta-Analysis. *Agronomy* 9: 767.

LANDMARC

**SCALING LAND-BASED MITIGATION
SOLUTIONS IN VIETNAM
LAND-BASED MITIGATION NARRATIVE CO-DESIGN**

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STATUS: CONFIDENTIAL

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2. Introduction

This report includes a description of a generic nation-wide transition scenario for the implementation of land-based mitigation technologies and practices for the AFOLU sector (agriculture, forestry, and other land use sectors) in Vietnam. The report shows the outcomes of a series of research steps that have been conducted in this country since the start of the project in June 2020 until the end of 2022:

First, we performed an initial scoping of key LMTs in the case study country. The scoping assessment resulted in a long list of broad portfolios of different LMTs that could be viable within Vietnam.

Second, following this long list, we developed a short-list LMT portfolio containing key LMTs that would be the most relevant for the Vietnamese context. The LMT portfolio were validated through complementary (policy) literature review and with the help of stakeholder interviews (i.e., external validation by relevant experts and stakeholders in Vietnam). Ex-ante no specific guidance of criteria for LMT portfolio short-listing was provided to allow for a free and open co-design process with stakeholders. The scoping process and results are presented in section 3 of this report (step 1 & 2).

Third, after the short-listed LMT portfolios were validated, national scaling narratives or storylines for each LMT included in their portfolio were developed. The assessments focus on climate risks, vulnerabilities as well as socio-economic co-benefits and trade-offs associated with upscaling LMTs in Vietnam. The analysis is based on a broad range of information/literature sources, and stakeholder consultations conducted. This process is supported through a risk and impact assessment (i.e. an online survey and workshops/seminar/webinars) conducted through the LANDMARC tasks 4.1, 4.2 and 5.2. The results of this analysis are a set of LMT narratives which are presented in section 4 of this report.

The research steps are designed to enable both an **analysis of the risks and (climate) impacts of scaling up land-based mitigation and negative emission solutions**. As such this report mainly contributes to objectives 2, 3 and 4 of the six LANDMARC key objectives (see Table 1).

Table 1: LANDMARC project objectives.

	Project key objectives
1	Determine the potential and effectiveness of LMTs in GHGs mitigation using Earth Observation (EO)
2	Improve climate resilience of LMT solutions at the local level for large-scale implementation
3	Assess the risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs of scaling up local LMTs nationally
4	Scaling up LMT solutions to the continental and global level to assess effectiveness
5	Improve current methodologies to estimate emissions and removals for LMTs
6	LMT capacity building and develop new tools and services for decision making

While the results shown in this report represent a mostly qualitative storyline describing the context and impact of scaling up LMTs in the Vietnamese context, they also enable project partners to proceed with the translation of the outcomes in a manner so that they can serve as direct model input.

Furthermore, this national level assessment provides a testing ground and empirical basis for the continental, and global assessment of the realistic scaling potential of land-based mitigation and negative emission solutions implemented in Work Packages 6 and 7 of the LANDMARC project (*Objective 4*).

3. Scoping of land based mitigation and negative emission solutions

3.1 Overview of potential of LMTs in Vietnam

3.1.1 Introduction

In order to inform the process of revising the Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) under the UNFCCC's Paris Agreement, Escobar et al. (2019) reviewed the mitigation pledges of Vietnam in the AFOLU sector using a marginal abatement cost approach. This study provides a good overview of different LMTs and their importance at national scale. In September 2020, Vietnam submitted the revised NDC now including agroforestry and added additional land management practices. Mulia et al. (2020) estimated the technical and economic mitigation potential of different agroforestry systems, which will inform agroforestry-related activities and targets for the NDC action plan. The table adapted by Escobar provides a good overview of the main LMTs in Vietnam. In the following sections, we will expand on the set of available Vietnamese LMTs in the context of LANDMARC in order to conclude with a long-list of options. As a consecutive step, we discuss which LMTs seem promising for the Vietnamese scenario development. This set of LMTs is referred to as 'short list' (see Table).

Table 2 LMT potential in Vietnam

LMT Category	LMT	Mitigation potential	Total costs	Cost effectiveness
		Mt CO ₂ eq	M USD	USD/tCO ₂ eq
LMTs-LAND MANAGEMENT	Coffee & avocado	0.22	-118.51	-529.4
	Coffee & durian	0.13	-30.78	-234.7
	Rubber in bare land	5.27	-135.53	-25.7
	Compost from pigs	7.31	-14.41	-2.0
	Acacia in bare land	8.81	-8.12	-0.9
	Rainforest protection	59.41	9.75	0.2
	Biogas from pigs	22.32	7.11	0.3
	Rainforest restoration	8.03	11.63	1.4
	Forest restoration	6.57	11.63	1.8
	Low tillage	1.52	2.87	1.9
	Bamboo restoration	5.22	26.83	5.1
	Coffee & cassia	5.9	88.94	15.1
	Mangrove protection	47.75	1102.63	23.1

	Bamboo protection	6.37	333.20	52.3
	Maize compost	1.69	219.13	129.8
	Sugarcane compost	0.52	97.99	187.1
	Biochar	0.17	124.23	749.7
Total		187.21	1728.59	-

Note that each LMT was considered for a defined scenario in relation to Vietnam’s NDC representing a fraction of total commitments. Negative marginal cost is when a proposed option costs less than the current business as usual practice. See Escobar et al. (2019) for details. Source: Adapted from Escobar et al. (2019).

3.1.2 Technologies dependent on biomass / photosynthesis

BECCS

BECCS are currently not an option in Vietnam and are therefore not discussed.

Biochar

Biochar is already part of local knowledge and produced artisanal on small scale. Biochar is also produced on a larger scale using modern machinery. The main feedstock is rice, maize and coffee husks; however, it is unclear to what degree biochar is applied to soil and there is a lack of research on the benefits for agricultural production and soil carbon sequestration. Within the coffee sector, coffee husks have been used as feedstock with pyrolysis technology at the farmer cooperative level (Flammini et al. 2020), using the produced heat for drying coffee cherries. This is done as an alternative to currently used burners for coffee drying which are not only inefficient but also cause heavy smoke emissions with negative effects both on the health of the local population and the quality of the coffee beans. One of the key challenges of scaling biochar use is related to the application rate (i.e., amount per ha) required to improve the soil to the level of interest (e.g. pH level). A study by Scheifele & Gattinger 2017, suggested that a rate of 20 t/ha is required to raise the soil pH to an ideal range. Due to the problem of soil acidification, this is a primary concern for soil health in Robusta coffee growing areas. However, this study was conducted in laboratory only and field designs are currently under way to assess whether lower rates might be sufficient. If the required rate is too high, this could make the technology either too costly or logistically unfeasible. Depending on the carbon price on the carbon market, using biochar as soil amendment could potentially be at least partially subsidized. Given that coffee in Vietnam is planted on 650,000 ha with globally the highest yields, there is a lot of biomass (i.e., coffee husks) that is not properly returned to soils.

3.1.3 Land management practices

Afforestation

In the late 1980s, the government of Vietnam initiated major policy reforms and ambitious forest and replanting programs. By 2017, total forest cover reached again 14.4 million ha, covering 42 percent of the country, supporting economic growth, job creation, and poverty alleviation. While the overall forest area has been increasing, the quality of the forest continues to deteriorate. Today two-thirds of

Vietnam's natural forests are considered in poor condition or regenerating, while rich and closed-canopy forests constitute only 5 percent. As a result of competing land uses, pockets of deforestation are still found in the country. Agriculture continues to be the main direct cause of forest loss in Vietnam, its expansion being facilitated by the extension of rural infrastructure, particularly roads. Several initiatives are dedicated to reach zero deforestation commitments (e.g. Initiative for Sustainable Landscape Approach – jurisdictional approach).

Agroforestry

Mulia et al. (2020) have identified eight key agroforestry systems in Vietnam with a total area covering 820,000 hectares, which is 92% of the total area with agroforestry systems. These eight systems are i) Melaleuca (*Melaleuca cajuputi*)-based (245.5×10^3 ha), ii) Robusta coffee (*Coffea canephora*)-based (245.3×10^3 ha), iii) Rhizophora (*Rhizophora* spp.)-based (149×10^3 ha), iv) Acacia-based (129.5×10^3 ha), v) Rubber (*Hevea brasiliensis*)-based (20.5×10^3 ha), vi) Arabica coffee (*Coffea arabica*)-based (10.5×10^3 ha), vii) Cashew (*Anacardium occidentale*)-based (10.4×10^3 ha), viii) Tea (*Camellia sinensis*)-based (9.5×10^3 ha).

Existing areas with these eight agroforestry systems in Vietnam sequester a total of 1346 ± 92 mil tCO₂e. both above-ground, below-ground and soil organic carbon. The two systems in wetlands, namely Rhizophora- (617 ± 22 mil tCO₂e) and Melaleuca-based (482 ± 19 mil tCO₂e), contribute about 82%, thanks to their high carbon storage per hectare. Robusta coffee contributes (137 ± 30 mil tCO₂e). Soil organic carbon accounts for about 52%. Most of the coffee is currently monocropped, although intercropping systems in agroforestry with fruit trees (avocado, durian), black pepper and nitrogen-fixing *Cassia siamea* and *Leucaena* sp. (often used as living poles for pepper vines) is on the rise. Current assumption regarding the area with coffee monocropping systems range between 66% to 80%, hence there is high potential for expanding agroforestry within the existing coffee growing area. A monocropping coffee system has around 5.4 t ha^{-1} aboveground carbon (AGC) while current coffee agroforestry systems in Vietnam have around 13 t ha^{-1} AGC. Given that there are 650,000 ha of coffee, the potential increase in AGC by converting monocropping systems to agroforestry is considerable. Further increases in soil organic carbon are expected with improved agricultural management that improve soil health.

Agricultural management practices

Organic fertilizers, integrated soil fertility management, low-tillage, mulch, cover crops, intercropping, etc. can have positive co-benefits on soil carbon sequestration, particularly when several of these practices are combined. However, there is little evidence under what conditions these practices reduce soil carbon loss or increase soil carbon. Due to the long reaction time of soil carbon sequestration, modelling is often required to assess the potential benefit. Only few studies have been identified in the context of Vietnam.

Organic fertilizers derived from biogas production using animal manure (mainly piggery) has a high potential as a by-product to replace the current unsustainable energy source of wood for cooking

and lightning purposes of the rural population. The Vietnam Biogas Programme led by Dutch NGO SNV started to push biogas using pig manure back in 2003 to replace wood burning stoves in rural areas. Smallholder farmers account for 80% of pig production and the use of small-scale biogas plants is one of the options to treat the manure through anaerobic digestion (AD) to provide a clean, efficient, and low-cost renewable source of energy, while the digested matter is a high quality fertilizer for crops. Roubík et al. (2018) found that the biogas potential is two times higher than current biogas generation.

3.2 Determining the LMT scope for national level simulation modelling

Priority should be given to LMTs that also contribute to improving farmers livelihoods and climate change adaptation. The Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (MARD) clearly emphasized that profitability and food security are prioritized before GHG reduction and carbon sequestration.

Table 3: Summary of relevant land based LMTs

LMT	Specification	Included in national LANDMARC LMT portfolio
Biochar		Yes
Feedstock from coffee, rice or maize		
Wetlands	Mangrove protection and restoration	No
Cropland	Reduced tillage	No
	Harvest residues, crop rotation	No
	AD residue based on organic fertilizers / digestates	No
	Composting based on agricultural residues	No
	Integrated crop management in upland crop cultivation and rice cultivation	Yes
	Agroforestry	Yes
Forest land	Avoided deforestation	Yes
	Afforestation / reforestation	Yes
	Agroforestry	Yes

- **Biochar**

Biochar at small and large scale has been identified as a priority technology by the Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment of Vietnam recommending early deployment based on 17 indicators (MONRE 2018). For the coffee sector with 650,000 ha of land and a total of more than 10 million tonnes of coffee produced in 2018, significant waste is currently either lost or inefficiently used and biochar could provide heating for coffee drying, improve soil health and

sequester carbon in soils. Ongoing projects with Sofies and Unido are exploring the scaling potential of early pilots and align nicely with LANDMARC's objective.

- **Agroforestry**

Agroforestry has been included in the updated NDC of September 2020 as part of the measures for the LULUCF sector. Agroforestry-related activities and targets will likely be elaborated in the NDC action plan that is still under development by the government (Mulia et al. 2020). Vietnam has also committed to the UNFCCC's Koronivia Joint Work on Agriculture (KJWA) to promote and enhance investment in climate-smart agriculture such as agroforestry. Enhancing terrestrial and soil carbon is among the priorities of the KJWA, along with improved nutrient and water management for food security and resilience to climate change, for which agroforestry can also generate relevant benefits.

- **Soil health improving agricultural practices**

Investments in soil health improving agricultural practices, with co-benefits of increasing soil carbon sequestration are of high priority. Soil degradation due to erosion (75% of agricultural soils are sloping) and soil acidification is a major issue which requires high investments in order to sustain crop production. Changing demands from international markets regarding product quality and environmental costs of production have been putting pressure on the agricultural export capacity of Vietnam. Big investments from government, World Bank and private sector are changing the mode of production to comply with these new market demands.

- **Afforestation/ reforestation and avoided deforestation**

In the last 5 years, REDD+ programs and projects have been focusing on improving institutional frameworks and policies, capacity building, developing technical guidelines and investing in the implementation of REDD+ activities. A policy on carbon payments for forest ecosystem services has been institutionalized in 2010 to generate funds for avoided deforestation and afforestation. However, afforestation is mostly based on non-native species such as *Acacia mangium* Willd, *Eucalyptus*, and *Manglietia conifer* Dandy with an average rotation of about six to seven years, therefore not contributing to biodiversity conservation and related ecosystem services. Avoided deforestation of primary forest is therefore most critical. Jurisdictional landscape approaches to sustainable sourcing of agricultural products have been set up to enable zero-deforestation pledges from public and private sector.

Not all MTs can be selected given the resource constraints of the project. Therefore, we prioritized four MTs based on their cost effectiveness and potential to align with already ongoing initiatives where Landmarc can best complement.

3.3 Discussion on short-listing LMTs

3.3.1 Land use change dynamics

Vietnam defines forest as an area with perennial timber trees, bamboos and palms of all kinds of a minimum height of 5 m, minimum tree cover of 10%, and a minimum plot area of 0.5 hectares or forest tree strips of at least 20 m in width and of at least three tree lines (MARD 2016). Forests are classified into three types according to management purposes: i) production forests that are designated for timber supply, ii) protection forests that are designated for protection functions, such as watershed and coastal areas, and iii) special use forests which are for biodiversity conservation such as national parks, protected area, biosphere etc. As can be seen in table 4, the total forest area has increased since 2005, however, the increase is mainly due to the expansion of production forest and a decrease of protection forest. Localized deforestation is still an issue, especially in the Central Highlands (World Bank 2019).

Table 4 Forest area dynamics

Year	National area (ha)	forest	Types of forest (% of total)		
			Special use forest	Protection forest	Production forest
2005	12,616,700		15.52%	48.92%	35.56%
2012	13,862,043		14.59%	33.73%	50.24%
2018	14,491,295		14.87%	31.66%	53.47%

Source: <http://www.kieclam.org.vn/Desktop.aspx/List/So-lieu-dien-bien-rung-hang-nam/>.

Competing land use

Vietnam is one of the world's largest exporters of rice, rubber, coffee, pepper, cashew nuts, wood products, and shrimps which compete to some extent with forests. Large-scale conversion of natural forests have occurred over the past 30 years due to commodity booms in the 1990s and early 2000s, most notably in the coffee and shrimp sectors. Between 1990 and 2017, the area of coffee plantations increased from 50,000 ha to 645,400 ha, by 2011, sea and brackish water aquaculture had expanded to cover an area of 730,000 ha, causing a major loss of mangroves. While the production of these and other commodities continues to rise, the expansion into natural forest areas has diminished since the 1990/2000s peak (World Bank 2019). Coffee expansion is expected to pose the highest risk to continued direct and indirect deforestation, as long as international demand for coffee remains strong. However, various private and public partnership projects have been set up to minimize this risk. Timber plantations are also expected to grow due to increasing demand of paper and pulp and other wood-based products (World Bank 2019).

3.3.2 Land management dynamics

Changes in land management practices are a crucial part of sustaining future agricultural production, rural livelihoods and climate change mitigation. Vietnam's agriculture is highly intensive with overuse of mineral fertilizers and irrigation, which has led to degrading soils and high pollution. Due to

decreasing productivity and high demand of international markets for cleaner production, a large investment by public and private sector is being made to identify and scale management practices that restore soils and decrease pollution. There is limited research evidence on soil organic carbon dynamics of different agricultural land use systems in Vietnam, but taking into account that current management is highly intensive and unbalanced, the trajectory of soil organic carbon is expected to be negative. Given that 40% of the total area is dedicated to agricultural production and yields of several crops are above average globally (e.g. rice, coffee), there is considerable plant residue produced which is still underutilized. Livestock manure, particularly pig manure, is widely available and provide substantial organic matter input to soils, but again it is too often not managed properly and returned to soils.

Table 5 Agricultural land use in Vietnam in 2018 (in 1000 ha)

Land use category	2018
Agricultural area, total	11,498
Annual crop land	6952.1
- Rice paddy	4120.5
- Other annual crop land	2831.6
Perennial crop land	4546.4

Source: General Statistics Office of Vietnam.

4. Co-design of LMT narratives

4.1.1 Introduction

The main LMTs identified as having high potential are i) agroforestry, ii) reforestation, afforestation and avoided deforestation and iii) biochar. Agroforestry seems to have the highest potential as it is highly cost-efficient, does not necessarily lead to land use competition and can contribute to climate change adaptation and farmer livelihood diversification. Vietnam has achieved an impressive scale of reforestation and afforestation, however, this was primarily done using low quality monocropping Acacia and Eucalyptus plantations. There is high potential to improve the quality of these plantations through more sustainable mixed species management, while expansion of forested areas will be more challenging due to land use competition. Finally, biochar could potentially become a promising LMT at national level, however, there are still knowledge gaps on how different feedstocks and pyrolysis protocols affect soil health, crop yields and farmer profitability. Considerable uncertainties exist regarding the required supply chain from biomass collection to production and biochar application as soil amendment to enable a viable business for biochar production and economic use at farmer level.

4.2 Agroforestry

4.2.1 Introduction

Agroforestry is a traditional agricultural practice in many countries, including Vietnam. Examples of traditional agroforestry practices in Vietnam are the forest–garden–fishpond–livestock systems in the lowlands and the home gardens with fruit, timber, or commercial tree-based systems in the uplands. In the past decades forests and agroforestry areas have been significantly reduced and replaced by intensive mono-cropping systems, driven by rapid population growth and increasing demands for food production and economic development. However, across the country, many farmers still adopt and maintain agroforestry as subsistence farming and more intensive commodity cropping systems (Mulia & Nguyen, 2021).

Nowadays, agroforestry has been recognized as an integrated sustainable land-use practice not only for soil conservation and improved resource-use efficiency, but also to adapt to and mitigate climate change thanks to its potentials for carbon sequestration and regulating microclimate. Agroforestry also helps farmers to mitigate market risks, including the price fluctuation and the situation such as Covid-19 pandemic, via diversifying farmer’s income and enhancing food security.

There is an estimated >0.83 million ha of existing agroforestry systems in Vietnam storing a total of 1346 ± 92 million ton CO₂ equivalent including above-, belowground, and soil carbon. Over the period of 2021 – 2030, estimates of the potential area agroforestry systems could be expanded to vary from 0.93 to 2.4 million ha. About 10% of this expansion area are highly suitable for production with a sequestration potential of 2.3–44 million ton CO₂ equivalent (Mulia et al. 2020).

4.2.2 Policy context

National policies addressing this LMT

Mainstreaming agroforestry will support Vietnam in implementing and achieving its targets of several national policies.

In 2020, Vietnam updated its NDC for the period of 2010 - 2030, including the aims of “developing agroforestry models to enhance carbon stocks and conserve land” (section 2.4.3) as one of the measures under LULUCF sector. Moreover, agroforestry-related targets and activities will likely be incorporated in the national NDC Action Plan which is still under development by the government. However, it is recommended to include agroforestry as a part of the agricultural sector in order to effectively offset sectoral emissions (Mulia et al. 2020). Moreover, Vietnam has committed to the UNFCCC’s Koronivia Joint Work on Agriculture (KJWA) to promote and enhance investments for the sectoral adaptation and mitigation measures such as climate-smart agriculture and agroforestry. The National Action Plan of the 2030 Sustainable Development Agenda clearly emphasizes the need for developing a more sustainable agriculture in upland areas, to which agroforestry can provide multiple relevant benefits.

In 2021, the government of Vietnam has issued [Decision No. 523/QĐ-TTg \(2021\)](#) on approving the Vietnam Forestry Development Strategy in 2021-2030 with a vision to 2050. In which, agroforestry is included as recommended production models for most of the regions across the country, including the northern midland & mountainous regions, north central region, south central region, central highlands, and southeast region.

Several studies mentioned agroforestry as potential direct or indirect targets for carbon finance. However, Vietnam’s sectoral forestry policies and related mechanism for carbon credits such as the national REDD+ vision to 2030 have not elaborated agroforestry. In April 2021, the Prime Minister released the Decision No 524/QĐ-TTg approving the national project "Planting one billion trees in the period of 2021 - 2025", which will be coordinated by the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development in collaboration with the Ministry of Environment and Natural Resources and the Ministry of Construction. Likewise, the project focuses on forest plantation and have not included agroforestry.

Actors currently applying the LMT

Agroforestry has been traditionally and widely adopted by rural smallholder farmers in Vietnam. Shade management has been promoted in key agricultural commodities, for example in coffee in the Central Highlands and tea in the North of Vietnam. In the Central Highlands, due to the unfavourable market prices of coffee in recent years, farmers have increasingly intercropped high-value fruit trees such as durian and avocado in their coffee farms. One of the important adoption constraints has been the lack of guidelines for agroforestry development, thus the selection of associated trees relies on farmers’ preference and is highly influenced by expectations of economic benefits (Nguyen MP et al. 2020). An ACIAR (Australian Center for International Agricultural Research) funded project led by the World

Agroforestry Centre (ICRAF) in collaboration with the Centre for International Tropical Agriculture (CIAT) and other international and national partners, will contribute to this knowledge gap.

Which funds are available for the LMT implementation

[Resolution No. 84/NQ-CP \(2021\)](#) on Approving the investment policy for the Program on sustainable forestry development for the 2021-2025 period; and the Sustainable Forest management program (Decision No. 809/QD-TTg (2022)) for the period 2021-2025: 78,585 billion VND (3,2 million USD).

4.2.3 Current land use and potential land-use competition

The Spatially Characterized Agroforestry (SCAF) database (<http://scafs.worldagroforestry.org/>) provides information on distribution, biophysical and socio-economic characteristics of 48 existing agroforestry practices across 42 provinces in Vietnam during 2013–2014. Based on SCAF database, the total area and the potential for carbon sequestration were estimated (Table 6).

Table 6: Total area, carbon sequestration amount and investment cost for expansion of existing agroforestry systems in Vietnam (*adapted from Mulia et al. 2020*)

Agroforestry system	Area (10 ³ ha)	Main regions	Total sequestered carbon (mil tCO ₂ e)	Investment cost (USD ha ⁻¹ year ⁻¹)
Melaleuca (<i>Melaleuca cajuputi</i>)-based	245.5	Mekong River Delta	482 ± 18.8	
Robusta coffee (<i>Coffea canephora</i>)-based	245.3	Central Highlands, South East	137±29.5	2124 ± 574
Rhizophora (<i>Rhizophora</i> spp.)-based	149	Mekong River Delta	617±22.4	
Acacia-based	129.5	North East, Red River Delta, South Central Coast, Mekong River Delta	76.1±15.6	173 ± 4.6
Rubber (<i>Hevea brasiliensis</i>)-based	20.5	North West, North Central Coast, Central Highlands	12.0±2.4	
Arabica (<i>Coffea arabica</i>)-based	10.5	North West	5.9±1.3	2587
Cashew (<i>Anacardium occidentale</i>)-based	10.4	Central Highlands, South East	7.4±1.25	213
Tea (<i>Camellia sinensis</i>)-based	9.5	North East, North Central Coast	5.4±1.17	2806
Other systems (*)	79.8	Spread across regions	-	
All systems	900		1343±92.4 (**)	

(*) Other systems: Various fruit- or timber tree-based systems with relatively small areas

(**) Estimates of all eight main agroforestry system; TOC of Other systems were not taken into account

Existing agroforestry systems could be expanded to a total of 0.93–2.4 million hectare, of which approximately 10% is considered highly suitable for production, with a potential to sequester 2.3–44 million ton CO₂ equivalent over the period 2021–2030. For commercial crops, Vietnam’s Master Plan on Agricultural Production Development to 2020 with a vision to 2030 prioritizes improvements in in the processing industry rather than area expansion. Agroforestry could be expanded into existing producing regions via gradual conversion of sole crop plantations. There is not sufficient information available for assessing potential land-use competition. Depending on the agroforestry design and management, yields of the main crops might be negatively affected, hence potentially requiring more land than current monocropping systems to maintain total production and increasing demand. By replacing old coffee trees with new high yielding varieties (e.g., TRS1, TR4, TR9 and TR11) off-set potential yield losses (D’haeze 2022). Furthermore, the long-term sustainability of current monocropping systems is questioned (climate and market risks, soil degradation, etc.) and land equivalent ratios (assessing yields of all associated crops) needs to be accounted for. Indirect land-use competition effects have been reported where the expansion of commodity crops have displaced subsistence farming systems of ethnic minorities into forest margins leading to deforestation (Meyfroidt et al. 2013).

No other land use developments are known that compete with the expansion of agroforestry. However, continued low prices of coffee, for example, can lead farmers to abandon coffee and therefore coffee agroforestry switching to other land uses. But, this is more common in coffee monocropping systems, as coffee agroforestry are more profitable and rely less on the coffee price alone due to the diversified income streams from other crops such as pepper, avocado and durian.

4.2.4 *Climate risks & sensitivities*

Under impacts of climate change, suitable areas for perennial crops such as coffee and tea are projected to be reduced. Mulia et al. (2020) estimated the potential expansion area and impacts of climate change on five major agroforestry systems (robusta-, arabica-, acacia-, tea- and cashew-based) in Vietnam under different climate change scenarios. On average, highly suitable areas for agroforestry expansion are potentially reduced by 34% under RCP 4.5 and 48% under RCP 8.5 by 2050. Arabica and Robusta coffee-agroforestry systems are most affected by impacts of higher temperature with up to 89% and 83% reduction of highly suitable planting areas compared to the baseline under RCP 8.5 in 2050. This value is 30% for tea, while acacia is the most resilient with a projected decrease of 7%.

However, the estimation excluded co-benefits of associated trees in agroforestry systems which can help modify the microclimate within the system thanks to the shade- or ground cover layer keeping the system temperature lower and soil moisture higher. Therefore, prioritizing agroforestry for commodity production is clearly needed to mitigate the strong risks of climate change on such perennial crops, especially coffee.

Currently, drought and water shortages are an increasing challenge for people of the Central Highlands. For example, the 2016 drought reduced the discharge of main rivers by 20-90% (NCHMF

2016, cited in CGAR 2016) with 70% of the cultivation area experiencing severe drought (MARD 2016). Nearly 170,000 ha of crops were affected by the drought, of which 7,100 ha were left fallow and more than 95,00 ha were deficient in irrigation (CGIAR 2016)

4.2.5 Economic implications

According to Escobar et al. (2019), coffee agroforestry systems with fruit trees such as Durian and Avocado are the most cost-effective land use based mitigation measures among the analysed practices, being more profitable compared to monocropping systems. However, investment costs are higher (e.g. 2 times higher) for agroforestry compared to monocropping and profits of agroforestry are higher only once all the trees are mature and bear fruits. In a timber system, returns can take even longer compared to fruit trees. Initial finance mechanisms for transitioning to agroforestry systems might therefore be required.

Mulia et al. (2020) estimated the investment cost for agroforestry expansion in highly suitable areas to range between USD 28 to 2790 million, depending on the agroforestry system. Cashew-based agroforestry and tea-based agroforestry systems have the lowest and highest investments costs, respectively. In terms of carbon sequestration, agroforestry is 1.3–17 times more cost-efficient than sole crop plantations. For example, robusta-based agroforestry can potentially remove 45 mil tCO₂e, equivalent to 41% of total GHG emission of Vietnam's agriculture sector by 2030. It requires an investment cost of USD 6.3 billion for agroforestry expansion, compared to an additional cost of about USD 41 billion for sole plantation to removing the same amount of emissions. Moreover, crop diversification can increase and help farmers reach break-even points earlier, therefore stabilizing their income.

4.2.6 Co-benefits and trade-offs

Through our qualitative risk assessments, co-benefits related to soil (soil protection, nutrients retention, etc) are perceived as most important by researchers and local experts. Stakeholders from the private sector highlighted income diversification and carbon sequestration as most important co-benefits. The improved regulation of the water balance was also mentioned.

- a) **Agricultural production:** High level of shade and resource competition could limit productivity. Meanwhile, some crops such as coffee benefit from shade trees at their early establishment. The replacement of old varieties with new improved varieties could mitigate potential negative effects of shade on coffee yield. Both public and private stakeholders are interested in compiling information on trees and crops that grow well together.
- b) **Landscape:** During drought conditions, there is potential for competition between different water uses, e.g., between water use for electricity and domestic use and the use of irrigation. However, agroforestry can reduce nutrient and sediment loss, thereby reducing the risks of water pollution.

- c) **Biodiversity:** Soil biodiversity is expected to improve in agroforestry systems, but there is a lack of scientific studies in the Vietnam agroforestry context. Improved forest quality and increased tree density and diversity in agricultural systems improves biodiversity habitat.
- d) **Nitrogen emissions?:** *No studies have been found that evidence lower nitrogen emission in agroforestry systems. Although incorporating additional trees is expected to increase nitrogen uptake and thereby potentially reduce nitrogen loss, leguminous trees also add additional nitrogen to the soil through leaf litter. Nitrogen emissions will be more strongly affected by the source, rate, timing and place of application.*
- e) **Water quality:** Depending on the design of agroforestry systems (tree species and their arrangement), the risk of water pollution by agrochemicals and sediments is reduced.

The main benefit of agroforestry to farmers are the associated products derived in addition to the main crop, such as timber, fruits, fuel wood, etc. Agroforestry systems tend to increase management efficiency, however, implementation costs and time required until benefits (e.g., timber, fruits) are available can be high and limiting the potential uptake.

Trade-offs of the LMT

Risks

Being highly driven by economic benefits, selection of species in agroforestry systems that will enhance ecological benefits is not well considered. Additionally, big timber and native trees are less likely to be selected due to its slow growth rate. Timber-based agroforestry and afforestation, in general, are mostly based on non-native species such as *Acacia mangium* Willd and *Eucalyptus* with an average rotation of about six to seven years, therefore not contributing to biodiversity conservation and related ecosystem services. Fruit-based or commodity-based (coffee, tea) agroforestry are mostly semi-shaded as commercial polyculture or shaded monoculture.

Co-benefits

Besides being a cost-effective practice for carbon sequestration and GHG removal, agroforestry provides multiple co-benefits for agriculture production, soil conservation, improving food security and farmers' income.

Agricultural production

Although competition of resources might affect productivity of each plant component, total production and income generated from the whole system could be higher compared to the sole crop plantations. In addition, thanks to crop diversification, less inputs are required and thus enhancing resource-use efficiency and reducing costs. On the other hand, some studies showed that in several agroforestry systems, interactions among species facilitate common resources and result in higher productivity of each plant component than in sole crop plantations. Agroforestry can also regulate micro-climate and help to mitigate climate risks on crop production.

Soil conservation

Agroforestry reduces water and chemical inputs, so as their impacts on soil, compared to sole crop plantations. Trees, in general, improve soil health thanks to its increasing litters and deep rooting systems which enhance soil organic matter, soil pores, infiltration, water retention and activities of soil organisms. On sloping land, soil erosion and sedimentation can be reduced by arranging agroforestry as crop trips and contour planting.

Biodiversity

Combination of trees, especially with different vegetation layers, regulates micro-climate and conducts favourable conditions on farms for both sun-loving and shade-tolerant species. In addition, trees can increase biodiversity of a system, including through providing a temporary or permanent habitat for wildlife. Agroforestry can reduce the risk of forest encroachment and degradation through providing ‘forest products’, such as timber and fuelwood as alternative livelihoods and thus help conserve forests and their ecosystem services. Vietnamese agroforestry systems are currently not favouring native tree species within their systems due to a lack of economic incentives. However, if agroforestry can contribute to protect remaining biodiversity, then it can have a positive impact.

Trade-offs

Converting mono-cropping to agroforestry system requires high initial investment and is a long-term process, which can create a huge burden to farmers if sustainable financing mechanisms for the transitioning process are lacking. Some timber and fruit trees also take few years before being able to generate yield and income, thus without any compensation, farmers will lose a part of their income in the first years. Lack of related policies, technical guidelines, extension services and incentives for agroforestry might hinder farmer’s motivation to adopt agroforestry.

4.2.7 Risks associated with scaling up

Although the benefits and potentials of agroforestry are well-acknowledged, scaling agroforestry adoption in Vietnam remains challenging. Major constraints including the lack of specific policies needed to enhance institutional support, lack of technical guidelines, quality planting materials, and financial incentives to attract farmers interest and investment efforts. There are different understandings of “agroforestry” from stakeholders of different domains, e.g., forestry and agriculture. A common understanding of definitions, risks and benefits is required for successful scaling. Farmer decision on removing/intercropping some crops is driven by market price. When the market price is too low, farmer will revert to a monocropping system.

4.2.8 Research gaps

A lack of technical guidelines to design and manage locally adapted agroforestry systems have been highlighted as a key constraint for wide scale adoption. Research on the agronomy, ecology and economics of agroforestry is therefore required. The ACIAR funded project running in parallel to Landmarc will contribute to filling this gap, but more resources will be needed.

Agroforestry can vary substantially in the level of complexity. System ages and complexity (simple to complex agroforestry) are critical to be considered for carbon benefits of the system. There is a need to characterize several agroforestry typologies and get baseline data of their benefits as well as trade-off to reach mutual understanding of “agroforestry” by different stakeholders/ decision-makers. The potential of sustainable finance for initial investments to incentivize transitioning to agroforestry.

4.3 Biochar

4.3.1 Introduction

Many soils in Vietnam show declining soil organic carbon content due to intensive long-term monoculture with insufficient supply of organic fertilizers and soil protection. This comes at the cost of long-term sustainability related to negative environmental externalities such as N₂O emissions due to overuse of nitrogen and reducing crop yields due to unbalanced plant nutrition, reducing soil water holding capacity and increased pest and disease pressure (e.g. Pham et al. 2020, Häring et al. 2014). There is considerable scope for improved soil organic matter management techniques. More than two thirds of the country’s territory is classified as upland soils. Although some studies found higher SOC in agricultural lands than in forested lands (Pham et al. (2018) it is important to note that the latter study did not compare SOC taking into account equivalent soil masses (Wendt & Hauser 2013), therefore questioning the comparability between soils.

There is a lack of field experiments measuring SOC as a function of land management practices in Vietnam in general, and for biochar in particular. Again, the few studies comparing SOC between soils of different management practices did not base their comparisons on equivalent soil masses. Other soil quality aspects such as changes in soil fertility and soil water holding capacity are equally important, yet very scarce.

Policy context

Vietnam has committed to the UNFCCC’s Koronivia Joint Work on Agriculture (KJWA) to promote and enhance investment in climate-smart agriculture (UNFCC 2018). This includes improving soil carbon, soil health, and soil fertility in integrated systems is one of the priorities identified by Vietnam. Soil carbon sequestration is considered within the Vietnamese National Adaptation Strategy to Climate Change. Practices that improve food security with a co-benefit of soil carbon sequestration are prioritized. Therefore, there is a need to clarify soil and plant health benefits of using biochar as a soil amendment.

In 2021, the Vietnamese Government issued Decision 1658/QĐ-TTg (2021) on approving the National Green Growth Strategy 2021-2030, with a vision to 2050, aiming to contribute to Vietnam’s economic restructuring to achieve economic prosperity, environmental sustainability, and social justice. The goal of the strategy is a green and carbon-neutral economy that positively contributes to limiting global warming. Key Ministries were assigned to formulate and implement specific tasks for an efficient,

sustainable, and low-emission agricultural sector towards a circular economy and climate smart agriculture.

In addition, Decision No. 687/QĐ-TTg (2022) on approving the scheme for circular economy development in Vietnam allocated specific tasks to MARD for developing policies in order to create a legal corridor for the formation and development of a circular economy in agriculture & rural development. MARD was requested to conduct research and propose implementation of one circular economy model (OCOC) in one commune.

A recent workshop (16 September 2022) between MARD and UNIDO revealed a high need for including biochar as a climate resilient solution in the national policy framework to maximize its potential and efficiency.

Actors currently applying the LMT

There is no report that provides a good overview of who applies what type and amount of biochar. However, there was a three-year project called ‘Biochar for Sustainable Soils’ led by the UN Environment and Global Environment Facility with assistance by the Thai Nguyen University of Sciences. A technology transfer program (www.repic.ch) between Swiss partners and a Vietnamese coffee processing equipment manufacturer (Viet Hien Ltd.), designed a new Pyrolysis Technology to suit the Vietnamese coffee industry. The new technology which uses coffee husks as a feedstock is very efficient, does not produce smoke and meets strict EU emissions standards. In addition to producing biochar, the pyrolysis machine also generates heat, which is used by a coffee cooperative to dry the coffee beans. This technology is managed at the farmer cooperative level.

Next to this highly standardized example, low quality rice husk ash is also produced from rudimentary combustion systems and marketed as biochar with inconsistent quality and lower impact on soil health and yields compared to high quality biochar. This is one of the factors that is distorting the market.

Funds available for the LMT implementation

No good overview of available funds for biochar has been identified. Government investment would likely require clear evidence on soil health, crop yields and farmer benefits before they support the technology at scale. International funding has already been directed to the technology particularly by UNIDO, SECO, GEF and now by ACIAR. Coffee private sector actors are interested to co-invest in the technology and carbon markets could play an important role in ‘subsidizing’ the technology to overcome the cost restrictions by smallholder farmers. However, the current carbon price is likely still too low.

4.3.2 Current land use and potential land-use competition

There is no information available on how much of the land is treated with biochar. However, the use of biochar does not lead to land use competition if waste products are used as feedstock. Rather, there might be a competition for i) biomass used for producing biochar and ii) use of the produced biochar

(e.g. charcoal, active carbon). Competition for biomass is currently not an issue, as there is an increasing amount of bio-wastes that are inefficiently used. Biochar could solve this inefficient use of bio-wastes. For example, coffee and rice husks are often burned for drying the coffee beans and rice, respectively. Due to the intensive agriculture use and resulting high yields there is a high availability of biomass that is available. Agricultural area is not expected to decrease in the coming decades, in the contrary, while soil degradation is increasing, soil amendments such as biochar are increasing in importance.

4.3.3 *Climate risks & sensitivities*

The climate sensitivities are related to the available area of agricultural land where biochar can potentially be applied and the availability of specific crop waste products used as feedstock. Depending on the specific agroecological zones and specific crops, climate risks and sensitivities will change. For example, coffee in the Central Highlands is expected to be increasingly affected by climate variability and change such as increasing temperatures, more severe and frequent droughts and more frequent flooding. High temperatures and insufficient rainfall during vegetative growth and bean filling can substantially affect crop yield and quality. Salt intrusion due to sea level rise is a problem in the Mekong Delta and can put agricultural production at risk. The Mekong Delta plays a key role in ensuring national food security. In the northern mountainous area, heavy rainfall can increase erosion.

4.3.4 *Economic implications*

Currently, one of the main concerns and uncertainties of biochar is the potential high costs. Based on a pilot study at a coffee farmer cooperative, two main aspects were identified to be key for the profitability of the system: the price of biochar and the positive impact on the coffee quality. The biochar is used as soil amendment for coffee as well as durian and pepper plantations or it is sold to the local market. The cost for one tonne of biochar on the Vietnamese market, produced with the small-pyrolysis system (the PPV300), is approximately USD 350 to 400 if the capital and operating expenses are entirely accounted to the biochar (Flammini et al. 2020). An average coffee farmer, however, has a monthly income of USD 250-500 and an area of three hectares. On the other hand, the improved drying system using the excess heat from the pyrolysis system can improve the quality of coffee and thereby the received price, which is estimated to be around 10% higher because of fewer price deductions for coffee quality defects. Taking these aspects into account, the payback period for the investment (around 33,000US\$) and a production size of at least 36 ha is less than 2 years and becomes very interesting for bigger farmer groups. Current investigations for further improvement on the efficiency and the management of the technology are likely to make the business case even more prominent. On the other hand, the evolution of the market price for biochar is uncertain and must be further evaluated (Zellweger et al. 2018).

The cost of biochar production and market value of biochar has been assessed by Zellweger et al. (2018), however, no information is available on costs of applying biochar and the respective benefits in terms of soil health and related crop yield and final profitability. This information will be collected

in parallel to the Landmarc project within the ACIAR funded project led by ICRAF in collaboration with CIAT and other partners.

With the pyrolysis system used for coffee drying, approximately 50% of the heat values of the input are stored in biochar and 50% is turned into a climate positive energy resource. Due to the carbon sequestration, the energy output has a “negative carbon footprint”, without any additional negative effects such as N₂O emissions. Based on the carbon content of one tonne of biochar / coffee husk, there is a potential of 2.45 / 0.73 tonnes of CO₂ that can be sequestered.

4.3.5 Co-benefits and trade-offs

Agricultural production:

Biochar can adsorb nutrients making them unavailable to plants. This can lead to temporary nutrient deficiency. This can be avoided by mixing biochar with another fertilizer. Also, if the pH level becomes too high, nutrient deficiency can occur. However, this would require a huge amount of biochar that is not economically feasible. Furthermore, some of the soil health related benefits have been shown to provide only short-term benefits (e.g., raise in soil pH), and require frequent application of biochar to maintain the required benefits.

Landscape:

Biochar has the potential to increase soil erosion control.

Biodiversity:

Biochar has been found to increase biological activity and biodiversity in the soil. However, this requires further research for the local conditions in Vietnam.

Nitrogen emissions:

Potentially reduced nitrogen emissions due to reduced requirement of nitrogen fertilizers. There is also evidence that biochar can act as a nitrification inhibitor.

Water quality:

Biochar has been identified to reduce soil erosion and nitrate leaching, thereby contributing to improved water quality.

Other risks / co-benefits as part of the LMT implementation:

Heat production, which is currently used for drying coffee beans.

Trade-offs of the LMT

Biochar could also be used as charcoal or active filters, which could lead to increased prices if demand is high. However, this is currently not the case and rather unlikely in the near future. Other trade-offs could result due to negative effects on plant nutrient availability, but this research is still pending.

4.3.6 *Risks associated with scaling up*

Developing a market and supply chain for biochar is still in its infancy. Hence, creating a market for biochar demand and identifying the right size of biochar production (e.g. cooperative level or industrial level) for competitive prices and carbon markets to facilitate affordability as a soil amendment.

4.3.7 *Research gaps*

Effect of different feedstocks on biochar quality and soil health, crop yields, GHG reductions (e.g. from reduced need of chemical fertilizers, nitrification inhibition) and overall economic benefit to the farmer (Scheifele & Gattinger 2017). On what soil types and soil constraints biochar can benefit farmers most. Another open question is how long the potential benefit last (e.g. frequency of biochar application needed to maintain specific soil pH level) and an improved understanding of the trade-offs.

4.4 Afforestation/Reforestation

4.4.1 *Introduction*

Vietnam is one of the few tropical countries where forest areas have been increasing in the last 30 years (Traedal & Angelsen 2020). Tree planting and restoration programs have expanded the country's forest cover from a low point of 9.4 million hectares of forest in 1990 to an estimated 14.8 million ha in 2015 (Keenan et al. 2015). However, the quality of its natural forests has suffered (World Bank 2019). This is a result of major policy reforms and ambitious forest and replanting programs. Total forest cover was 14,415,381 ha in 2017, constituting 41.6 percent of the country and it seems on track to reach the targets set out in the 2016-20 Target Program on Sustainable Forest Development. Nonetheless, deforestation and forest degradation still continue in parts of the country, such as the Central Highlands, and the overall quality of the natural forest continues to decrease. Two thirds of the natural forests are in poor conditions or regenerating, only five percent are rich and closed canopy forests. Most replanted forests are non-native Acacia and Eucalyptus plantations. Climate change further becomes an increasing thread, particularly to the mangroves.

4.4.2 *Policy context*

Vietnam's commitment to the forest sector is enshrined in the national constitution and has the full support of the Communist Party and the Prime Minister. It has been mainstreamed in national development plans and is manifested through multiple action plans, decisions, and policies of key ministries. Within the updated NDC, Vietnam included managing and developing sustainable forests, enhancing carbon sequestration and environmental services, conservation of biodiversity associated with economic development and increasing income for forest-dependent communities and people as a key measure. The mitigation-related legal documents include the Forestry Law (2017) and as mitigation-related strategies the Vietnam Forestry Development Strategy 2007-2020 (2007).

In the LULUCF sector, Vietnam has actively implemented mitigation measures, especially under the REDD+ programme. In the period 2015-2020, REDD+ programmes and projects have been focusing on

improving institutional frameworks and policies, capacity building, developing technical guidelines (reference emission level for REDD+, MRV, benefit sharing mechanism, etc.) and investing in the implementation of REDD+ activities. Several REDD+ programmes have calculated the potential GHG reduction and enhancement of forest carbon stock under specific REDD+ activities. The emission reduction programme in North Central Vietnam is expected to cut 25 million tonnes of CO₂eq in the 2018-2025 period.

The national forestry development strategy (period 2021-2023) also highlights a strong focus on promoting afforestation and mobilising state fund for this effort. Some of the specific objectives of this strategy include planting production forest (about 340,000 ha/year in 2030), planting special-use forest using indigenous, precious and rare tree species (on average 4.000-6.000 ha/year), and restoration of production forest, special use forest (on average 15.000 ha/year).

Actors currently applying the LMT

Public and private sector (paper and timber sector), and smallholder farmers.

Fund available for the LMT

Vietnam is one of the world's leading countries in operationalizing a payment for forest environmental services (PFES= system). The PFES program has generated nearly \$400 million since 2008. More recent reforestation efforts are led by conservation NGOs such as WWF-Vietnam and PanNature and push mixed plantations rather than monocropped Acacia and Eucalyptus plantations working with small-scale farmers. State budget from the National Forestry Development Strategy (2021-2030) is 78,585 billion VND (3,2 billion USD).

4.4.3 Current land use and potential land-use competition

Main challenges are competing land uses, overexploitation of resources, mounting risks of supply shortages, and insufficient capacity for forest governance and management. The National 5 Million Hectare Reforestation Program 5 (MHRP) that ran from 1998-2010 failed because there was simply not enough land to plant trees. The main driver of deforestation and forest degradation is from competing land uses, particularly agricultural commodities such as rubber and coffee. The area for future plantation expansion is limited; however, there is considerable potential to increase the productivity and economic value of existing plantations. In the future, the available areas for forest are at increasing risks, due to i) direct effects on forest species composition and survival, ii) loss of area due to sea level rise (i.e., mangrove forest ecosystems) and iii) indirect effects due to increased land use competition related to decreased availability of agricultural land area related to sea level rise and shifts in crop suitability. Nevertheless, Vietnam continues to aim at restoring and improving quality of the current 16.2 million hectares of forests.

4.4.4 Climate risks & sensitivities

Increasing temperatures will affect the carbon sink strength of forests. It is difficult to identify a temperature threshold that regulates carbon uptake. Duffy et al. (2021) combined Eddy-covariance flux measurements with applied macromolecular rate theory to identify temperature thresholds where respiration is higher than photosynthesis on a global scale. Changes in temperature and rainfall but as well atmospheric carbon dioxide concentration can change species composition of forests and thereby their carbon storage potential. Natural forests make up only 5% of forested areas and are mainly located in the Central Highlands. Vietnam has a 2,900 km of coastline with the majority facing the East Sea. Sea level rise will directly affect mangrove forest ecosystems. The number of strong to very strong tropical storms and typhoons are expected to increase which could damage forest ecosystems.

4.4.5 Economic implications

Plantation forests can be applied in a competitive way, however, these forest would only provide limited ecosystem services and not contribute to biodiversity conservation. Diverse forests with high percentage of native species can provide positive effects to local communities, particularly ethnic minorities that traditionally rely on non-timber forest resources for their livelihoods. However, this would require substantial public funding and adequate policies and land tenure systems in place.

4.4.6 Co-benefits and trade-offs

Forests play a particular critical role in watershed and coastal protection given the topography of the country. Past reforestation has mainly been achieved by monocropped Acacia and Eucalyptus plantations with low ecosystem value and no biodiversity conservation benefits. Recent developments, however, aim at improving forest quality through mixed species approaches that are adapted to local conditions.

4.4.7 Risks associated with scaling up

There remain highly relevant questions regarding legitimacy of different stakeholders entitled to govern and manage forests. Ethnic minorities are often excluded and negatively impacted by the government's forest protection and development policies.

4.4.8 Research gaps

An improved understanding of how forest governance affects forest dependent ethnic minorities and how their relationship has changed with respect to forest resources for their livelihoods over time.

5. Conclusions

Vietnam has considerable potential and political will for scaling different LMTs. Agricultural productivity is considerably higher compared to other South East Asian countries. On the one hand, this provides a lot of biomass with potential for valorisation and carbon storage (e.g., biochar), while integrated agricultural farming practices can significantly contribute to lowering greenhouse gas emissions. Agroforestry seems to be the most cost-effective LMT that is more easily scaled. There remain, however, various challenges that need to be addressed to close relevant knowledge gaps, enable access to finance and provide other essential enabling conditions. Relevant risks, such as permanence due to changes in crop prices and due to climate change impacts need to be carefully considered and requires that LMT practices increase overall resiliency. Importantly, any incentive for LMTs in the Vietnam context should primarily focus on improving the livelihoods of often vulnerable smallholder farmers and aim for improving biodiversity benefits, which carbon sequestration and reduction of greenhouse gas emissions as co-benefits.

6. References

CGIAR Research Program on Climate Change, Agriculture and Food Security – Southeast Asia (CCAFS SEA) 2016. Assessment Report: The drought crisis in the Central Highlands of Vietnam. Hanoi, Vietnam: CGIAR Research Program on Climate Change, Agriculture and Food Security (CCAFS).

D'haeze D. (2022) Optimizing water use in the central highlands of Viet Nam. Focus on the Robusta coffee sector. Hanoi, Viet Nam: IUCN and Gland, Switzerland.

Duffy K., Schwalm C., Arcus V., Koch G., Liang L., Schipper L. (2021) How close are we to the temperature tipping point of the terrestrial biosphere? *Science Advances* 7: Doi.10.1126/sciadv.aay1052.

Escobar Carbonari D., Grosjean G., Läderach P., Nghia Tran D., Sander B., McKinley J., Sebastian L., Tapasco J. (2019) Reviewing Vietnam's nationally determined contribution: a new perspective using the marginal cost of abatement. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems* 3:14. doi:10.3389/fsufs.2019.00014

Flammini A., Brundin E., Grill R., Zellweger H. (2020) Supply chain uncertainties of small-scale coffee husk-biochar production for activated carbon in Vietnam. *Sustainability* 12, 8069; doi:10.3390/su12198069.

Häring V., Fischer H., Stahr K. (2014) Erosion of bulk soil and soil organic carbon after land use change in northwest Vietnam. *Catena* 122:111-119; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2014.06.015>

Keenan R., Reams G., Achard F., Freitas J., Grainger A., Lindquist E. (2015) Dynamics of global forest area: Results from the FAO Global Forest Resources Assessment 2015. *Forest Ecology and Management* 352:9-20.

MARD (2016) Vietnam's modified submission on reference levels for REDD+ results based payments under UNFCCC. URL: https://redd.unfccc.int/files/vietnam_frl_modified_submission_final_for_posting.pdf

Meyfroidt P., Tan Phuong V., Viet Anh H. (2013) Trajectories of deforestation, coffee expansion and displacement of shifting cultivation in the Central Highlands of Vietnam. *Global Environmental Change* 23:1187-1198.

MONRE (2018) Low carbon technology assessment contributing to implementation of Viet Nam's NDC – Volume 2: Multi-criteria assessment to identify prioritized technologies and essential steps to build consensus among key stakeholders.

Mulia R., Nguyen D. D., Nguyen M.P., Steward P., Pham V.T., Le H.A., Rosenstock T., Simelton E. (2020) Enhancing Vietnam's nationally determined contribution with mitigation targets for agroforestry: a technical and economic estimate. *Land* 9, 528; doi:10.3390/land9120528.

Mulia R., Nguyen M.P., eds. (2021) Diversity of agroforestry practices in Viet Nam. Ha Noi, Viet Nam: World Agroforestry (ICRAF).

Roubík H., Mazancová J., Phung L.D., Banout J. (2018) Current approach to manure management for small-scale Southeast Asian farmers – Using Vietnamese biogas and non-biogas farms as an example. *Renewable Energy* 115:362-370.

Scheifele M. & Gattinger A. (2017) Recommendations for application of coffee pulp biochar in Vietnamese coffee plantations. Final Report. URL: http://www.repic.ch/files/6815/4944/9365/Biochar_Application_Report-FiBL.pdf

Traedal L. & Angelsen A. (2020) Policies drive sub-national forest transitions in Vietnam. *Forests* 2020 (11):1038; doi:10.3390/f11101038.

UNFCCC (2018) Submission from the Socialist Republic of Vietnam in Response to Decision 4/CP.23; New York, USA.

Wendt J. & Hauser S. (2013) An equivalent soil mass procedure for monitoring soil organic carbon in multiple soil layers.

World Bank (2019) Forest Country Note – Vietnam. World Bank, Washington, DC.

Zellweger H., Viet Vinh L. & D’Haeze D. (2018) Pyrolysis technology for better coffee quality: Vietnamese farmers pioneer climate smart agro-processing practices. URL: https://www.hrnstiftung.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/policy_brief_pyrolysis.pdf

SCALING LAND-BASED MITIGATION SOLUTIONS IN CANADA

LAND-BASED MITIGATION NARRATIVES

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2. Introduction

Reinforcing its commitment in the Paris Agreement, Canada has recently announced the increase of its emission reduction targets by 2030 and its intention to achieve net-zero emissions by 2050 (Canada Energy Regulator, 2020). From Canada's *mid-century long-term low-greenhouse gas development strategy* report to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) in 2016, LMTs are considered of importance to meet Canada's climate targets but are perceived as long-term high uncertainty technology alternatives (Environment and Climate Change Canada, 2016a).

In recent reports, the Canadian Institute for Climate Choices and Navius Research Inc. explored a variety of net-zero pathways for Canada (Dion et al., 2021; Riehl and Peters, 2021). These pathways considered a cap of emissions by 2050 as the only policy in place and contemplated uncertainties around availability and price of low-carbon technologies and negative emissions technologies, policies in other jurisdictions and commodity prices. The reported results indicated that Canada has several pathways to achieve net-zero by 2050 but LMTs are essential to meet this goal. Also, the Canadian Oil and Gas sector is susceptible to changing international oil demand and policies implemented today will have a big impact on the future pathways as argued by Riehl and Peters (2021). This research separated technologies in commercially available technologies today (safe bets) and technologies under development with higher uncertainty for their implementation (wild cards). The modelling projections found that 2/3 of the expected emission reduction by 2030 could be achieved by "safe bets". However, achieving net-zero by 2050 would require 2/3 of contributions from "wild card" technologies. Special attention was brought in this study to engineered negative emission technologies such as Direct air capture (DAC) and Bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS) due to its potential and lower uncertainty concerning nature-based solutions. LMTs are considered part of "wild cards since" most of them are immature and require further investment to become available at the required scale (Dion et al., 2021).

This description presents of a general nation-wide transition scenario for the implementation of land-based mitigation technologies and practices (LMTs) for the AFOLU sector (agriculture, forestry, and other land use sectors) in Canada. The report shows a summary of the different narratives and relevant elements built from literature and stakeholder engagement. The information included on this document reflect the outcomes of a series of research steps that have been conducted in this country since the start of the project in June 2020 until the end of 2022.

The first section of this report introduces the different LMTs considered relevant in the Canadian context and presents the rationale for scoping a national LMT portfolio. In the second section, we expand more on relevant elements of the LMT narratives including policy contexts, implementation and consequential risks, and economic implications. The presented narratives were mainly developed from scientific and grey literature. Stakeholder feedback from interviews and bilateral meetings were incorporated to refine the perspectives in the narratives. These narratives are use for scenario

assessment both with stakeholder and in models to understand their potential implications at national and regional levels.

3. Scoping of land-based mitigation solutions in Canada

A summary of LMTs and estimated potential for Canada is shown in Table 1. About half of the technical potential can be considered as constrained by biodiversity and food security safeguards (Roe et al., 2019).

Table 1: Estimated LMT potential in Canada.

LMT Category	Sector	LMT	Technical potential ^(a)	Constrained potential ^(b)
			Mt CO ₂ /y	Mt CO ₂ /y
Nature-based	Forest	Natural forest management	127.86	
		Reforestation	54.58	
		Afforestation	12 ^(c)	
	Agriculture	Enteric fermentation	6.4	
		Grazing: legumes in pastures	5.32	
		Synthetic fertilizer	4.95	1.1
		Manure management	4.26	0.25-1.36
		Cropland management	4.23	2.7
		Soil carbon	11.4	3.6-6.1
	Peat-lands	Peatland restoration	1	
Reduced conversion of peatlands		0.2		
Engineered and hybrid		Biochar	52-86.5 ^(b)	7-9
		BECCS (post-combustion CO ₂ -capture)	218	
		Direct Air Capture (DAC)	426	
		Mineralization / Enhanced Weathering	80 ^(d)	25
TOTAL			1008.2	

sources: (a) (Roe et al., 2019), (b) (Haugen-Kozyra et al., 2010), (c) (Natural Resources Canada, 2020a), (d) (Beerling et al., 2020).

Canada has vast expanses of forested and agricultural landscapes with substantial land-based negative emissions potential in the form of biomass production (afforestation), soil carbon sequestration (climate smart agriculture), and organic carbon fixing (biochar). The federal government acknowledges the negative emissions potential of land-based carbon sequestration approaches (Environment and Climate Change Canada, 2020a) and yet these strategies have been excluded from national GHG emission reduction strategies (Riehl and Peters, 2021). This is likely due to the technical and logistical challenges associated with measuring, validating, and modelling net carbon emissions linked to dynamic carbon cycling processes across that vary broadly across temporal and spatial scales and land use types. However, land-based mitigation strategies should be an essential part of Canadian

mitigation strategies considering the vast land extension available in the country, the scale of the agricultural sector, and decreasing of vulnerability of portfolios only focused on engineered solutions alone.

Today, there is no specific roadmap or policy to develop and deploy LMTs or achieving net-zero emissions in Canada. In September 2020, the Canadian government introduced the *Canadian Net-Zero Emissions Accountability Act* - Bill C-12 which requires the government to develop a plan for emission reduction but does not establish a specific action plan (Minister of Environment and Climate Change, n.d.). In February 2021, an independent advisory committee - Net-Zero Advisory Body – has been announced and will be tasked to provide advice on the most likely pathways to achieve net-zero by 2050 (Environment and Climate Change Canada, 2021a).

In this scoping report, we will review the status and potential of different LMTs in Canada. Also, we will discuss the scope of the case study and its position within the context of current efforts to reduce carbon emissions in the country.

3.1 Relevant nature-based solutions for Canada.

3.1.1 Afforestation

Out of all terrestrial ecosystems, forests have the greatest capacity for negative carbon emissions and approximately 9% (over 347 million ha) of the world's forests are located in Canada (Natural Resources Canada, 2020b). Afforestation and reforestation of Canada's landscapes deforested by agriculture, industrial development, resource extraction and urban expansion since the 1800s is an effective climate change mitigation strategy because it increases both soil and vegetative carbon stocks and provides a sustainable feedstock for bioenergy (Amichev et al., 2012; Rowe et al., 2009). Within the boreal forest region alone over 10.9 Mha of land have been converted to agricultural use (Environment Canada, 2013) since early European settlement during the mid-1800s (Boucher et al., 2014; Hobson et al., 2002).

Forest ecosystems can act as both carbon emission sources and sinks depending on their health and how they are managed (Metsaranta, 2019; Seddon et al., 2019; White and Kurz, 2005, p. 200). Globally, forests represent up to 80% of above ground and 70% of below-ground biomass carbon stores (Ameray et al., 2021). Therefore, sustainable forest management and afforestation practices and policies provide valuable opportunities for supporting Canada's climate change mitigation initiatives. Afforestation is defined as the conversion of non-forested land (land that has not been forested within the previous 50 years), to forested land through planting and seeding (IPCC, 2006). While reforestation is defined as direct human-induced conversion of non-forested land to forested land through planting and seeding (IPCC, 2006). Forests provide carbon sink/sequestration ecosystem services by transforming atmospheric carbon dioxide into biomass via photosynthesis. Afforestation and reforestation increase landscape carbon stocks through production of above-ground (i.e., branches and foliage) and belowground (i.e., roots) biomass (IPCC, 2006). Conversely, forests can become carbon emission sources from deforestation and soil disturbance, fire, disease, and decomposition (Kurz and Apps, 2006). Because of the dynamic nature of carbon stocks within forests and the vast

expanses of forested land across Canada, forest carbon modelling is becoming an increasingly important land-use planning tool (Laganière et al., 2010).

Fortunately, deforestation rates in Canada have steadily decreased over the last three decades, from approximately 64,000 hectares in 1990 to 34,300 in 2018 hectares per year and is expected to continue decreasing over time (Natural Resources Canada, 2020b). Currently, afforestation rates in Canada are approximately 9,000 hectares of new forests planted per year which is estimated to sequester approximately 1 million tonnes of carbon dioxide capture each year (Natural Resources Canada, 2020b). In 2020, Canada announced it will be planting two billion trees over 10 years to support nature-based solutions and it is expected the initiative to sequester 12 MtCO₂ per year by 2050 (Natural Resources Canada, 2020a).

Figure 1 indicates that Canadian forests sequestered approximately 47 million tonnes of carbon per year between 1990 and 2008. This diagram presents the typical annual rates of carbon cycling through the atmosphere, biosphere, and pedosphere in Canada and demonstrates how the rates of atmospheric carbon fixing and emissions are driven by dynamic biological (photosynthesis and heterotrophic respiration) and abiotic (fire and soil chemistry) processes. Negative carbon emissions (carbon capture and sequestration) occurs when the rates of carbon fixing into biomass and soil chemical compounds are faster than the rates of carbon release into the atmosphere from fire and respiration. As long as the soil carbon is maintained, harvesting from managed forests can contribute to net negative emissions when the harvested wood products are put into long term use such as furniture.

Figure 1. Estimated carbon balance of Canada's managed forest for 1990-2008, Tg (Mt)C/y. The number show the annual mean +/- one std. deviation based on 2019 annual values. Reproduced from "A Blueprint for Forest Carbon Science in Canada: 2012-2020", Canadian Forest Service (Natural Resources Canada, 2012).

The soil carbon sequestration potential and economic opportunities associated with afforesting marginal agricultural lands with short rotation woody crops like willow (*Salix* spp.) has been gaining attention in recent decades. Amichev et al. (Amichev et al., 2012) estimates that afforesting 0.4 Mha of agriculturally marginal land in the Saskatchewan Boreal Plains using short-rotation coppice willow (*Salix* spp.) could sequester as much as 1.1 t CO₂/ha/year of soil carbon and generate enough biomass to offset 16.9 t CO₂/ha/year worth of bioenergy over a 44-year period (LemprièreT.C et al., 2013).

Further research is required to fully understand the total life cycle costs and benefits of implementing afforestation systems designed to maximize climate change mitigation benefits taking into account biophysical conditions and potential carbon leakage (LemprièreT.C et al., 2013).

Both Canada Federal and Alberta Provincial Government has started investing in the investigation of co-benefits of afforestation abandoned areas of coal mines with willows as a means to sequester soil carbon, reclaim disturbed lands, generate biofuel feedstock and create new jobs for rural communities once reliant on the coal industry. In 2019 Alberta Innovates in partnership with several industry and NGO organizations invested over \$14 million dollars into the BIOSALIX project : a mine reclamation program using fabricated soils and organic residuals to augment soil quality and underpin a cleantech economy through short rotation willow feedstock production and sequestering carbon into the developing soils (Government of Canada, 2020a) . The BIOSALIX project will be the first of its type and size, providing a path for clean energy growth through the transition of prairie coal mines to biomass production while providing mining communities with economical stability through the development of a cleantech economy. By using municipal organic residuals to overcome mine reclamation challenges BIOSALIX integrates societal challenges to achieve a highest, best end use and outcome – achieving carbon sequestration, closing the nutrient cycle, building long-term soil productivity, and kickstarting a new economic opportunity through a large-scale demonstration. The result: sequestration of thousands of tonnes of carbon in both the soils and biomass, and new opportunities for communities on the threshold of coal mine closure (Government of Canada, 2020a). In 2020, the Federal government announced \$2M in funding for Calgary's willow tree plantation farm to pursue reduction of about 200,000 tonnes of greenhouse gas emissions.

3.1.2 Soil carbon

Soils play a major role in the global carbon cycle. With an estimated total of 2000-2500 Gt of soil carbon within the top 1 m, soils hold four times more carbon than the biotic pool (vegetation and organisms) and three times more carbon than the atmospheric pool (Sommer and Bossio, 2014). Therefore, even small changes in global soil carbon pools can measurably influence total atmospheric carbon concentrations (Lal, 2016; Tian et al., 2009; Wijesekara et al., 2017). Kirschbaum (2000), estimated that a 10% increase in the global SOC pool would equate to capturing 30 years' worth of anthropogenic emissions. Figure 2 shows the key drivers for GHG emissions from soils .

Figure 2. Key drivers of GHG emissions from soils. Reproduced from (Oertel et al., 2016).

Soil carbon sequestration (SCS) increases the organic carbon content of the soil which results in a net removal of CO₂ from the atmosphere (Fuss et al., 2018). Soil has the capacity to hold four times more carbon than above ground biomass, and its global potential is estimated to 2-5 GtCO₂e/yr (Fuss et al., 2018). Increasing soil carbon can be achieved through various strategies. For this report, soil carbon sequestration includes non-till agriculture, grassland management, cover crops, Silvopasture and tree intercropping (Drever et al., 2021; Griscom et al., 2017).

The climate change mitigation potential of SOC sequestration received global attention during the 2015 COP21 United Nations Climate Change Conference when the “4 per Thousand” target was proposed. This target aims to increase the upper 40 cm of the world’s topsoil soil organic carbon (SOC) concentrations by 0.4% each year by adopting the conference’s recommended climate smart agricultural practices (Wijesekara et al., 2017).

Agriculture’s Role in Climate Change and Climate Change Mitigation

The agricultural industry is one of the top contributors to anthropogenic climate change (Environment and Climate Change Canada, 2020b). By converting approximately 40% the earth’s ice-free land surface from natural ecosystems to arable lands agriculture has been the second largest generator (25%) of total GHG emissions after fossil fuel combustion (75%) (IPCC, 2014; Lal, 2016). Agriculture generates GHG emissions by intensifying soil carbon losses through soil disturbance and utilizing fossil-fuel based inputs for machinery and fertilizers (West and Marland, 2002). North American prairie soils alone have lost between 25% and 50% (~0.46 Gigatons (Pg)) of their original carbon content due to deforestation and cultivation (Lemus and Lal, 2005; Post and Kwon, 2000). The total soil carbon losses resulting from converting natural ecosystems to agriculture lands worldwide is estimated at ≥350 CO₂e Pg (Oertel et al., 2016). Agricultural practices deplete soil carbon pools in three ways (1) enhancing oxidation and mineralization of SOC compounds (2) leaching and translocating dissolved organic carbon compounds,

and (3) accelerating soil erosion (Lal, 2002). Additionally, annual fossil-fuel based agriculture inputs generate approximately 10-12% of total annual anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions (IPCC, 2014).

By implementing climate smart agricultural practises promoted by COP21 such as no-till cultivation, organic amendments application and agroforestry much of these agricultural-based carbon emissions can be reversed through soil re-carbonization (Lal, 2016; Paustian et al., 2016). Lal (2005, 2016) estimates that through applying SOC sequestration land management practices carbon-depleted agricultural soils have the potential to re-carbonize up to 60-70% (62 Mg C ha⁻¹, 227 Mg CO₂e/ha) of their native ecosystem SOC levels within 50-75 years. While the IPCC (2014) estimates that with the right combination of Agriculture, Forestry, and Other Land Use (AFOLU) practices, SOC sequestration could contribute between 20% and 60% of the total cumulative GHG offsets within 15 years.

As of 2006, the total area of cropland in Canada was almost 36 million hectares equating to roughly 53.1% of all land (Statistics Canada, 2006). In Alberta government efforts have been made to mitigate the climate change impacts of agriculture by developing agriculture carbon offset quantification protocols such as conservation cropping (no-till agriculture) and biofuel production and usage to incentivise climate smart agricultural practices. Although the carbon offset potential for SOC sequestration is considerable, because soils have a maximum carbon holding capacity and land management or climate pattern changes can release soil carbon, the long term climate change mitigation impact of this strategy is finite and reversible (Goglio et al., 2015; Lal, 2016). Therefore, instead of viewing SOC sequestration as a climate change mitigation solution, it should be considered an effective initial stop-gap measure and used in tandem with other land based (e.g. biochar) and technological negative emissions approaches (e.g. bioenergy production) that do not have upper limits to their negative emissions potential.

3.1.3 Wetlands

Wetland ecosystems have a vital importance in the socio-economic and ecological health of Canada. They account for about 14% of the total land area of Canada, which accounts for about 25% of the world's total wetlands (Kennedy and Mayer, 2002). Wetlands play an important role in the environment as an intermediary between aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems. According to Mitch and Gosselink (2007), they could be called "nature's kidneys" for the natural water quality improvements they provide. They are also crucial for mitigating GHG in a national and international context. Canadian soil store approximately 384±214Pg of organic carbon in the first meter of soil, which is about 25% of the world's total soil carbon storage. Peatlands account for 24% of this carbon stored in the soil of Canada (Sothe et al., 2022). Wetland reclamation, or the creation of wetlands in areas where they do not exist, is thus an important process for regenerative agriculture and carbon sequestration.

A Local Indigenous Perspective of Wetlands in the Athabasca Region

Wetlands are integral to the ecosystems and their significance has been traditionally recognized by the Indigenous peoples of Canada. Boreal peatlands and bogs are called *Muskeg* by the Cree. The Cree are one of the largest Indigenous groups in Canada, living across the provinces from Alberta to Quebec

and in parts of the Northwest Territories. Cecilia Fitzpatrick, a Cree Elder in Fort McKay, Alberta, shares stories her father shared with her about the Muskeg: *“ My father would tell me that our body is like the Earth...that the Muskeg is your heart and that the mountains are your brain, and the creeks and rivers are blood vessels...Muskeg is very important to rivers and creeks, and everything in them – with that comes our spiritual values and how we are connected to and respect the Earth. When you take from the Earth, you always put something back. The Muskeg is why the Earth breathes...We treat the Earth with respect- it is like treating your own body with respect. We take care of ourselves to live a life of longevity, to maintain a life of health and happiness. We need to treat our Earth the same way. Caring for our future, for our children”*. This narrative of the Muskeg emphasizes the need to protect wetlands, which are not only integral to the health of the wider ecosystem and represent a strong spiritual connection and respect for the land.

3.1.4 Biochar

Biochar is produced through thermal degradation of biomass in the absence of oxygen. This method sequesters carbon by transforming it to its elemental form so it cannot be degraded into carbon emissions through soil bacteria respiration processes. When biochar is added to the soil, this stabilized form of carbon can permanently increase soil carbon content and improve soil quality by increasing soil water retention. The net benefit of using biochar as a negative emissions strategy has been debated because of uncertainties associated with the sustainability of some biomass sources. In some cases, biochar has been produced from biomass of unsustainably harvested forests resulting in carbon emissions from degraded soils and thereby negating some of the net negative carbon emissions effects of this carbon fixing process (Woolf et al 2010). More transparency around best practises for sourcing biomass feedstocks (i.e. using organic waste products such as lumber industry offcuts and woodchips instead of intact forests as feedstock) are required for this negative emissions strategy to build momentum in Canada. In Alberta programs such as Bio-Resource Information Management System (<https://www.brimis.ca>) have emerged to advertise sources of sustainable biomass waste resources for biochar production and other carbon management uses. According to (Woolf et al., 2010), sustainable biochar implementation could offset up to 12% of annual anthropogenic GHG emissions Globally and (Haugen-Kozyra et al., 2010) reports that biochar production from agricultural surplus wastes could generate approximately 3.4 Mt CO₂ e y⁻¹ in Alberta, Canada. Figure 3 highlights the potential net carbon sequestration and emissions outcomes associated with the system lifecycle of converting agriculture-base organic waste into biochar. In addition to storing carbon in an inert form, the process of generating biochar can offset additional carbon emissions when paired with coproduction of heat and bioenergy (Homagain et al., 2016).

Figure 3. Overview of the sustainable biochar process. Reproduced with permission from (Woolf et al., 2010).

Biochar technology shows promise in mitigating climate change and improving soil quality, as well as reducing waste and producing energy as a by-product (Spears, 2018). Biochar is a charcoal-like substance produced by burning organic material from agricultural and forestry wastes (also called biomass) in a controlled process called pyrolysis. Although it looks a lot like common charcoal, biochar is produced using a specific process to reduce contamination and safely store carbon. During pyrolysis organic materials, such as wood chips, leaf litter or dead plants, are burned in a container with very little oxygen. As the materials burn, they release little to no contaminating fumes. During the pyrolysis process, the organic material is converted into biochar, a stable form of carbon that can't easily escape into the atmosphere. The energy or heat created during pyrolysis can be captured and used as a form of clean energy. Biochar is by far more efficient at converting carbon into a stable form and is cleaner than other forms of charcoal (Spears, 2018).

Biomass pyrolysis is a type of bioenergy production in which biomass is exposed to high temperatures for short periods, with little or no oxygen. Besides biochar, this produces syngas and bio-oil, both of which can be used for heat and power or be further refined into road transport or possibly aviation fuel. Pyrolysis can be done in large plants and small kilns or stoves (Paul et al., 2009).

Although biochar technology is considered a more recent strategy for carbon sequestration, the practice of adding charred biomass to improve soil quality is not new. This process is modelled after a 2,000-year-old practice in the Amazonian basin, where Indigenous people created areas of rich, fertile soils called terra preta (meaning "dark earth") (Spears, 2018). By heating the feedstocks and

transforming their carbon content into a stable structure that does not react to oxygen, biochar technology ultimately reduces carbon dioxide in the atmosphere (Spears, 2018).

Biochar also contributes to the mitigation of climate change by enriching the soils and reducing the need for chemical fertilizers, which in turn lowers greenhouse gas emissions. The improved soil fertility also stimulates the growth of plants, which consume carbon dioxide. The many benefits of biochar for both climate and agricultural systems make it a promising tool for regenerative agriculture (Spears, 2018).

3.1.5 BECCS

BECCS, also challenged to change to biomass carbon removal and storage (BiCRS), consists of a series of technologies (a process) where biomass systems remove CO₂ from the atmosphere and oceans, people harvest the energy through conversion, and the carbon is stored under the ground (geosphere)(FRIEDMANN et al., 2020) – Figure 4. BECCS represents a pivotal technology in most pathways for limiting global warming by 1.5 C (Masson-Delmotte et al., 2019). Globally, it is expected for BECCS to have a LMT potential of 0.5-5 GtCO₂/yr, 3-8% of total energy consumption (Canadell and Schulze, 2014), with a cost of 100-200 USD/tCO₂ (Fuss et al., 2018). However, significant overestimation of the capacity of BECCS deployment by Integrated Assessment Models (AIMs) has led to broad debate about appropriate scale-up of this technology and large uncertainties remain around technical feasibility and governance (e.g. transform traditional governance structures and policy-making models) issues (Sandalow et al., 2021).

Figure 4. Bioenergy with carbon capture and storage process. Reprinted with permission from Canadell et al. Nature (2014).

Today, only five facilities are actively using BECCS technologies reaching ~1.5 million tonnes per year (Mtpa) of CO₂ removal mostly dedicated to enhanced oil recovery (EOR) (Consoli, 2019). In Canada, there are two BECCS projects deployed: (i) Husky Energy Lashburn and Tangleflags CO₂ Injection in

Heavy Oil with a capacity of 90,000 Mtpa, and (ii) Saint-Felicien Pulp Mill and Greenhouse Carbon Capture Project with a capacity of 90,000 Mtpa. No other projects have been announced to date.

Canada considers BECCS as a key long-term opportunity to achieve net-zero by 2050. However, there are no policies in place to further develop the sector. A recent report by Navius research (Riehl and Peters, 2021) estimated that negative emission CCS could contribute up to a 218 MtCO₂e emission reduction with respect to 2020 levels by 2050. This estimate contemplates emission reduction from combustion emissions from sectors like hydrogen, cement, and coal plants, not only BECCS, and is sensitive to the dynamic with different other scenarios.

Further studies are necessary to more precisely estimate the potential risks and rewards for BECCS in Canada. The full carbon cycle of BECCS is not comprehensively studied and the LMT potential benefits could be overstated. The effectiveness of BECCS heavily relies on the type of biomass, geographic location, total final consumption of energy, ways and efficiency of energy consumption, and other relevant factors. Therefore, the carbon removed from the atmosphere can be off-set by emissions related to land-use and energy-use changes (Harper et al., 2018), and it may only remain as LMTs if residues are used from currently managed forest lands (Withey et al., 2019).

3.1.6 Direct Air Capture with storage (DACs)

Technologies for air purification and carbon removal from the atmosphere have existed since the 1940s for use in submarines, spacecrafts, and fuel production. However, DACs was first introduced for climate change mitigation in 1999 (Lackner, K. et al., 1999). DACs removes CO₂ directly out of the atmosphere and delivers a pure compressed gas stream for storage under the ground or reuse (Riehl and Peters, 2021). Although removing low concentrations of CO₂ in air (~400 ppm) is challenging and costly, DACs in concept is presented as an alternative for distributed emission sources, low water and land footprint, and potential to locate near storage sites eliminating the need for transport. Carbon removal from air can be achieved using liquid or solid sorbents as well as chemical looping with oxides, electrochemistry, photocatalysis, membranes, and biological routes (Sanz-Pérez et al., 2016).

There are currently 15 DACs plants operating capturing more than 9,000 tCO₂/y and 1 MtCO₂/y in advanced development in the US (International Energy Agency, 2020). Globally, it is expected for DACs to have a LMT potential of 0.5-5 GtCO₂/yr with a cost of 100-300 USD/tCO₂ (Fuss et al., 2018). Canada is home of Carbon Engineering Ltd., one of the few companies trying to commercialize DACs currently at pilot scale with a capacity of 1 t/d (National Academies of Sciences, 2019). Major support is growing for DACs locally with international and national partnerships developing to accelerate the scale up of DACs. For Canada, it is projected that DACs could be adopted at a very large scale with a potential capacity up to 426 MtCO₂e by 2050 (Riehl and Peters, 2021).

3.1.7 Carbon mineralization of CO₂ / Enhanced Weathering

Carbon mineralization is a natural process where CO₂ is sequestered by an exothermic reaction of alkaline silicates and hydroxides forming a stable carbonate mineral (Power et al., 2013). In the 1990s it was first proposed as a climate mitigation strategy and promising natural materials, such as ultrabasic/ultramafic rocks, through the engineering of a process to maximize this effect via pulverization and maximizing solid-gas contact (Lackner et al., 1995; Seifritz, 1990). In the past decades, other routes for mineralization using synthetic materials, industrial wastes, and integration with cropland have been developed increasing the potential for this LMT. Challenges in energy use and reaction kinetics remain as barriers for this technology, as well as political and social inertia for policy development (Beerling et al., 2020).

Enhanced Weathering remains a very early technology. However, it is expected for enhanced weathering to have a LMT potential globally of 2-4 GtCO₂/yr with an approximate cost of 50-200 USD/tCO₂ (Fuss et al., 2018). In Canada, there has been significant research in the identification of appropriate geological storage areas and the first major field trials looking at site weathering of mining waste are underway. However, no comprehensive study of national potential or specific policies for enhanced weathering has been found.

3.2 Determining the LMT scope for national level simulation modelling

In this section we discuss which set of LMTs we will study in detail for Alberta, Canada. Table 2 summarises the main LMTs and indicates which ones are included in the short-list of the LMT portfolio for Canada. The main rationales for including the various LMTs in the national level scaling simulation assessment are presented below.

Table 2: Long-listing of relevant land based LMTs

LMT Category	LMT	Included in national LANDMARC LMT portfolio
Nature-based	Afforestation	Y
	Soil carbon	Y
	Wetlands	Y
Engineered and hybrid	Biochar	Y
	BECCS (post-combustion CO ₂ -capture)	Y
	Direct Air Capture (DAC)	N
	Mineralization / Enhanced Weathering	N

Risks and uncertainties around LMTs raise criticisms around the likelihood for deployment, especially about overestimation of IAMs, necessary land extensions to meet the projections, climate vulnerability, and potential social inequities resulting from development in remote/rural communities (Anderson and Peters, 2016). Although the negative emission potential of land-based negative emission approaches is widely understood, including them as part of international emissions reduction commitment strategies is challenging because both it is difficult and costly to accurately measure and predict the complex biogeochemical and climatic systems that control soil carbon sequestration and biomass production and the economic markets that incentivise land-based negative emissions projects (LemprièreT.C et al., 2013; Oertel et al., 2016; Saiz and Albrecht, 2016).

In Canada, significant negative emissions can be gained through re-carbonizing Canadian landscapes that have been depleted by extensive deforestation and till-based agricultural practices since the 1800s. However, the landscape's total biomass production and soil carbon sequestration potential is finite, and rates of negative emissions decrease over time as forest and soil systems approach their carbon holding capacity. Therefore, it could be argued to broaden the scope to other carbon emissions offset strategies like Biochar and BECCS biogenic approaches because their performance and potential are easier to accurately measure, verify, and forecast and they have theoretically limitless carbon negative and carbon neutral offset potential.

However, through consultation with local communities it was highlighted that from a stakeholder perspective, the local ecosystem play a vital role in the livelihoods of those communities. Beyond their climate change mitigation potential, issues associated with land and how to better use it connect more with culture, religion, health, and identity. A shift on perspective with regards to LMTs is needed to better understand the human dimension and incorporate it on policies to better support a just transition.

Considering the critical role of the local context in the feasibility and scalability of LMTs, our case study aims to explore the climate change mitigation potential of restoration of damaged landscapes, particularly of boreal forests. This approach will evaluate the synergies and barriers for various LMTs interacting:

- Afforestation – reclamation and afforestation of damaged land using energy crops
- Soil Carbon – increasing soil carbon content through land reclamation
- Wetlands – restoration and protection of wetlands and peatlands in the Canadian north
- BECCS – use of energy crops and long-term storage of carbon
- Biochar – use of biochar by-products to replenish soil carbon content

Our study will focus on the LMT potential benefits of restoring and protecting boreal ecosystems, how to develop a sustainable enterprise, and its role as a green economic alternative for communities largely affected by extractive industries and traditionally left out of energy transition strategies such as rural and indigenous communities.

4. Co-design of LMT narratives

Nature-based solutions provide Canada with valuable opportunities to support national carbon offsets greenhouse gas emissions reduction target commitments. The following five LMTs have been shortlisted for their value to local communities, technical potential, and supportive federal and provincial policies.

Further details of these LMTs will be presented in this section to highlight current policy frameworks, risks, co-benefits, and trade-offs. Effects of avoided disturbances, though significant on the overall emission reduction, will not be addressed on this section since LMTs are focused on implemented strategies to reduce carbon emissions.

4.1 Wetland protection and restoration

4.1.1 Policy Context

Federal Level

The Pan Canadian Framework (Environment and Climate Change Canada, 2016b) lays out a detailed plan of how Canada wants to achieve GHG reduction targets. The key components of their plan entails ecosystem conservation and restoration. A particular focus is laid on converting Canada to a low-carbon economy (Alcock, 2017). The national Green Infrastructure Fund was introduced in 2017 to provide financial support for investments in green infrastructure, i.e, constructed wetlands and urban forests, as wetlands and trees are effective carbon sinks that also provide ecological benefits.

The Agricultural Policy Framework of 2022 (APF) is a five-year funding program that aims to provide funding for agricultural investments across Canada until 2028. The APF, along with the Canadian Agricultural Partnership, have previously focused solely on environment-beneficial management practices (BMPs), but according to Farmers for Climate Solution (FCS), which is a farmer-led task force of experts who aim to implement the most cost-effective climate change measures, a more system-wide approach is required. FCS recommends standard cost-share programs as well as reverse auctions and collective bonus payments (Farmers for climate solutions, 2022a)

Canada has committed to a number of UN Aichi Biodiversity Targets to improve biodiversity by 2020. One target was described as follows: *“By 2020, at least 17% of terrestrial areas and inland water, and 10% of marine and coastal areas of Canada are conserved through networks of protected areas and other effective area-based measures.”* As of August 2019, there was still 492,981 km² of land left to achieve the 17% target (Wark, 2019).

Provincial Level

Alberta’s unique scientific research capabilities and biomass availability has led to it being a key region for improvements in wetland and forest management (Government of Alberta, 2016). The creation of the Indigenous Protected and Conserved Areas (IPCAs), which are “lands where Indigenous

governments have the primary role in protecting and conserving ecosystems through Indigenous laws, governance and knowledge systems.” Is also a significant step in this direction since wetlands in the oil sands regions are linked to the traditional way of life of the indigenous Metis communities.

The Alberta Water act (1999) and the Alberta Environmental Protection and Enhancement Act (EPEA) (2022) are the most important legislations for the reclamation of wetlands. The objective of EPEA is to return disturbed landscapes to “equivalent land capability”. The Provincial Land Use Framework (LUF) of the Alberta Land Stewardship Act (ALSA) (Government of Alberta, 2022b), is also an important framework whose key objectives are to enable healthy ecosystems and people-friendly communities by restoring wetlands and grasslands. However, in 2013 a specific policy was developed - the “The Alberta Wetland Policy” which came into full effect in 2016 across the province (Government of Alberta, 2013). The policy aims to conserve and restore wetlands while allowing economic growth. In this policy, wetlands are managed by avoiding, minimizing, and replacing lost wetland value by restoration or payment. However, some of the directives were just in place since 2018, and their implementation is undergoing review.

One of the major concerns with this policy is that it has been stated that it does not apply to projects approved before July 4, 2016, which are most of the Oil Sands mining projects in Northern Alberta (Huynh, 2018). Therefore, there is uncertainty about the capacity of this policy to restore the function of the damaged areas in the green areas (mostly public land, forested and less settled).

4.1.2 Current land use

Wetlands in Canada account for 24% of the global wetlands. The Boreal region is the largest biome in Canada, accounting for 58% of the land base (Anielski and Wilson, 2009). Within Canada, 119 million ha consists of wetlands. Alberta’s unique geography sets 70% of the land base within the boreal region which largely consists of wetlands (Alcock, 2017). This makes Alberta especially rich in soil carbon storage. Approximately 15,000 ha of wetlands are converted to crop land every year in Canada (Farmers for climate solutions, 2022b). Careful management is required for the proper management and reclamation of these lands to limit the destruction of peatland ecosystems.

4.1.3 Potential climate risk sensitivities

The destruction of wetlands and conversion to cropland results in an estimated GHG emissions of over 1.2 Mt of CO₂e per year but Canada’s National Inventory Report does not account for these emissions. The draining of wetlands leads to the release of the carbon stored under as CO₂ over a period of years or decades. Evidence points to an increased rate of conversion of wetlands to croplands in recent years due to the rising prices of commodities. Creating or restoring wetlands is less effective than preventing conversions in the context of mitigation of GHG, but it is still beneficial as it could provide a mitigation of 22,000 tons of CO₂ e per year (Farmers for climate solutions, 2022b).

Other risks to wetlands associated with climate change involve the dry up and disappearance of small wetlands, seasonal water levels of larger wetlands, wetlands over permafrost may shrink or disappear,

impaired water retention, burnt due to increase wildfire risks, and greenhouse gas emissions associated with decomposition and brunt of wetlands and peatlands (Aquality Environmental Consulting Ltd., n.d.; Wilkinson et al., 2021).

4.1.4 Economic implications

Wetland management is costly to farmers as they would rather use the land for cropping. Wetland restoration is expensive, with the cost in the Prairies at the rate of \$5,200/ha and around \$31,000/ha in the rest of Canada. Drever et al. (2021) estimated wetland restoration costs ranging between 3500-400 USD/ha. FCS estimates an annual expenditure of per year for the mitigation of 1.4 Mt CO₂e in the year 2028 at \$50 Million per year (Farmers for climate solutions, 2022b). The cost for carbon sequestration and CO₂e reduction is also calculated in detail by in the FCS in their Economic Analysis report of March 2022 (Table 1).

Table 3.6.3: Program spending, emissions reduction, carbon sequestration, and program abatement cost for 2023-2024.

Management Practice	Incentive Cost in 2023 (\$)	Emissions Reduction in 2023 (t CO ₂ e)	Carbon Sequestration in 2023 (t CO ₂ e)	Abatement Cost in 2023 (\$/t Co ₂ e)
Nitrogen	35,952,942	760,843	0	47.25
Manure	12,373,402	479,589	0	25.80
Livestock	13,031,887	405,121	455,034	15.15
Soil	68,260,290	152,306	700,373	80.05
Trees/Wetlands	55,828,069	200,917	85,600	194.85
Total	185,446,591	1,998,775	1,241,007	57.24

Table 1. Emissions reduction, carbon sequestration and program abatement costs for 2023-2024 (Farmers for climate solutions, 2022b).

4.1.5 Co-benefits and trade offs

Wetlands are valuable carbon sinks that also provide numerous ecological benefits. Successful avoidance of the conversion of wetlands into croplands can result in significant reduction in emissions while restoration of wetlands can increase soil C to a large extent. Natural Boreal Wetlands are also natural habitats of a large number of important Canadian wildlife species such as moose, muskrats, beavers and woodland caribou. Wetlands are also deeply connected to the Aboriginal way of life due to the cultural significance of the presence of the flora and fauna of wetlands. Wetlands also provide ecological benefits such as water storage, groundwater regeneration, storm runoff generation and shoreline stabilization (Government of Alberta, 2018a). However, it is uncertain if the soil in a reclaimed wetland that has been previously mined will retain soil permeability, as some evidence suggests an increased permeability that could impact groundwater recharge and water input to wetlands (Devito et al., 2005).

4.1.6 Risk of scaling up

Expansion of wetlands via reclamation may interfere with pre-existing ecosystems and the natural habitats of wildlife species. As the interactions between wildlife may be complex and as of now indeterminable, a specific focus must be laid on studying the neighbouring ecosystem before scaling up. Wetlands also require a water supply to support hydrophytic plants which produce saturated soil, hence it is necessary to study how water moves through reclaimed soil before large scale implementation. Vegetation design and trees on upland hill-slopes must also be considered as forests on upland hill slopes will reduce surface runoff (Government of Alberta, 2018a). Physical, biological and chemical monitoring methods must be incorporated to ensure long term feasibility of reclaimed wetlands and ecosystems.

Local stakeholders have expressed their concern about the success of wetland restoration efforts. Some have indicated that seedlings and trees being brought from outside areas are not successfully growing. As well as reclamation efforts substituting wetlands with high-lands due to lower costs. In addition, local stakeholders indicate that the spiritual value of the wetlands are lost and can't be recovered by restoration efforts that do not take into consideration Traditional Environmental Knowledge. To our knowledge, there are no known examples of successful constructed peatlands which pose a great challenge in Alberta particularly in the peatland zone in the north that overlaps with the oil sands (Locky, 2011; Nwaishi et al., 2015). Therefore, major technical and economic challenges need to be overcome if the ecosystem is to be restored.

4.1.7 Research and Implementation Gaps

The uncertainties with peatland restoration mainly concern the lack of proper understanding of chemical and nutrient interactions in groundwater from reclaimed landscapes along with changes in the long-term permeability of the soil. The interaction of old and new animal species flocking to reclaimed wetland is also unpredictable (Alberta Environment 2008)(Nwaishi et al., 2015).

The wetlands of Alberta were also traditionally maintained effectively by indigenous communities living in the area. However, the current policy aims and regulations create an unfavourable position for the respectful application of traditional ecological knowledge from the communities. This disconnect between policy aims and inclusion of communities must be addressed to enable successful implementation of climate mitigation technologies.

4.2 Forest Management and Afforestation

4.2.1 Policy context

International level

Afforestation was initially introduced during the 2002 United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) Subsidiary Body on Scientific, Technical and Technological Advice (SBTSA) 19 when discussions were initiated to define and scope afforestation and reforestation project activities under the Clean Development Mechanism (CDM) (UNFCCC, 2021). Since then, afforestation

and reforestation have been mentioned several times at Conference of the Parties (COP) and SBSTA meetings. Most recently, the UNFCCC COP has adopted special rules to ensure that accounting for GHG emissions removals from afforestation projects comply with Kyoto Protocol objectives and do not cause negative impacts within the regions they are implemented (UNFCCC, 2021).

Federal level

In 2016, Environment and Climate Change Canada adopted the Pan-Canadian Framework on Clean Growth and Climate Change plan. The objective of this plan is to grow the domestic economy while reducing emissions and building resilience to adapt to a changing climate (Environment and Climate Change Canada, 2016b). As part of the Pan-Canadian Framework on Clean Growth and Climate Change, the federal, provincial, and territorial governments committed to collaborate through Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment (CCME) on a pan-Canadian greenhouse gas (GHG) offsets framework. Pan-Canadian Greenhouse Gas offset framework was adopted by CCME in 2019, and it supports federal, provincial and territorial governments in developing and implementing their offset systems. The Framework also offers several means of managing carbon emissions including best practices on carbon offset program design and implementation to support future offset fungibility (CCME, 2019).

The Forestry, Agriculture and Waste subsection of the Pan-Canadian GHG offset report highlights the role of forests, wetlands and agricultural lands in carbon emissions reduction (CCME, 2019). Although afforestation is not specifically named in the report, it is noted that advancement of forestry and agricultural management practices that help reduce emissions is one of the federal and provincial objectives (CCME, 2019).

On July 2, 2020, the Government of Canada released a discussion paper on the proposed Federal Greenhouse Gas Offset System (the “Federal GHG Offset System”) that clarifies how the protocols for offset credits will be developed for specific project types (Richardson and Williams, 2020). The federal government shortlisted eight project types for the development of offset protocols of which afforestation/restoration, improved forest management, and soil organic carbon are included (Richardson and Williams, 2020).

Provincial level

Afforestation is recognized by the provincial Government of Alberta as one of several effective GHG offset solutions. In September 2007, the Government of Alberta published Quantification Protocol for Afforestation Projects that includes guidance on afforestation projects in Alberta (Alberta Environment, 2007) and in 2020 the Government of Alberta released Specified Gas Reporting Regulation (Alberta Regulation 251/2004), which provides the legal basis for afforestation practices in Alberta (Alberta Queen’s Printer, 2020).

The afforestation project protocol notes that carbon offsets are primarily generated by carbon sequestration occurring from planting trees on non-traditionally forested lands i.e. agricultural land, urban land, agro-forestry operations, and reclamation of industrial sites (Alberta Environment, 2007).

Projects and Actors in Canada

Forest management and Afforestation projects Canada involved several actors where the Federal and Provincial Governments have important participation:

- Growing Canada's Forests program (Government of Canada, 2021a)
This program applies where trees can be planted: "on public and private lands across the country in remote, rural, suburban and urban areas via afforestation, which is the creation of new forest cover on lands that currently do not have trees (e.g abandoned fields), and via reforestation, which is the regeneration of forests that have temporarily lost their tree cover through natural disturbances (e.g. wildland fire) or in areas where commercial disturbances (e.g. forestry roads and landings, mining or seismic lines) have occurred, but for which there is no current legal requirement to plant trees. To restore forest habitat, including under recovery strategies for species at risk, conservation agreements and related planning processes (e.g. range plans)"
- The Prairie Farm Rehabilitation Administration Shelterbelt Centre in Indian Head, Saskatchewan, part of Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada (AAFC), is currently the only federal organization that has a national agro- forestry mandate. A national strategy is being developed with the goal of improving the competitive position of the agricultural sector by incorporating agroforestry systems for the sustainable management of the agricultural land base (Policy Options, 2008)
- In Alberta, all projects listed on the AEOR must meet system requirements as outlined in the Standard for Greenhouse Gas Emission Offset Project Developers (Government of Alberta, 2019).
- Forest resource improvement association of Alberta (Forest Resource Association of Alberta, 2021)

Allowing regulated facilities to use market-based compliance tools such as emission offsets creates incentive for Albertans from all areas of the economy to innovate and invest in activities that will reduce greenhouse gas emissions - from farmers to municipalities to small renewable energy industry developers (CSA Group, 2019).

In Alberta, the conservative ideology mostly favours business-oriented projects (Biggs, 2009). One can expect that afforestation generated carbon offset projects would conform to the conservative values including low permanence, explicit inclusion of carbon offsets as fungible with emissions reductions, standards not compliant with those relevant to the Kyoto Protocol, and operated as profit-generated businesses (Biggs, 2009).

- TreeCanada - Since 1992, we've planted more than 83 million trees and sequestered millions of tons of carbon pollution in the process. Every year we deliver mass plantings in each of Canada's five major regions; Atlantic & North, Québec, Ontario, the Prairies and British Columbia (Tree Canada, n.d.).

- The National Greening Program is mass seedling plantings across Canada, where there is a need for reforestation or afforestation (Tree Canada, n.d.).
- For private Land owners (Government of Ontario, 2021) This program, funded by the Ministry of Natural Resources and Forestry and administered by Forests Ontario and other partners, provides funding and information for landowners willing to plant trees on their property.

Within the 2021 federal budget, the government of Canada has committed to investing over the next two years \$54.8 million CAD to foster new forest-based economic opportunities, \$28.7 million CAD to map wildfires risks, \$67.2 million CAD to deploy Clean Fuel Standards, and \$15 million CAD to plant 2 billion trees (Government of Canada, 2021b). Locally, Alberta has dedicated more than \$100 million CAD a year to support the forestry sector through infrastructure development and wildfire mitigation. Also, an annual budget of \$30 million CAD to mitigate the effects of mountain pine beetle infestation. However, no direct mention to afforestation has been proposed in Alberta.

4.2.2 Current land use and potential land-use competition

Canada has 348 million hectares (ha) of forest and accounts for approximately 7% of global forest cover. Forest land is subdivided into managed (226 million ha) and unmanaged (122 million ha) and it is mostly under provincial or federal jurisdiction. Deforestation rates have been on decline in Canada since 1990. In 2018 Canada had 35,000 ha deforested mostly due to oil and gas, agriculture, and urban development, but the deforestation rate has been ~1% in the period. Hydroelectric developments have shown significant peaks in deforestation during the deployment of specific projects (Natural Resources Canada, 2020b).

To fully evaluate forestry potential as an LMT, Drever et al. (2021) identified a potential area of 139 million ha for improved forest management with an expected mitigation potential of approximately 8 MtCO₂e/y and 4.34 million ha for afforestation with an expected mitigation potential of approximately 0.05 MtCO₂e/y. This potential has not considered areas already considered for food production or urban development, as well as already burnt areas since new forest are growing or will grow on it.

4.2.3 Climate risks & sensitivities

As Canada's territory is expected to warm up more than the world average, the effects of climate change on Canada's forests are already evident in the form of increased frequency and severity of fires, droughts, severe storms, damaging insects and disease attacks. Forest fire season has become more frequent and destructive with an estimate of 74-118% of projected increase of burned areas by the end of the century (Williamson et al., 2009). Extreme weather events will also include floods and droughts that are expected to have major economic impacts in the region, such as the 2013 Flood in Southern Alberta or the Fort McMurray Fire from 2016 (Sauchyn et al., 2020). Out of the 20 most costly weather events in Canada since 1983, 13 happened in the Prairie provinces demonstrating a major vulnerability in the Canadian North and the Central Prairies.

On the other hand, climate change will result in more frequent, extended, intense and longer outbreaks of pests. Insect species with the potential for increased economic impacts under climate change include the mountain pine beetle, the larch sawfly, the spruce bark beetle, the jack pine budworm, the spruce budworm, the gypsy moth, the forest tent caterpillar, and the large aspen tortrix. Also, climate change will likely increase the risks for diseases to become more established in the Canadian forests (Meyer, 2018; Natural Resources Canada, 2013; Prairie Climate Centre, 2021).

With regards to biodiversity, a northward movement of climate envelopes is expected to boost productivity and species diversities. However, not all species will be able to adapt so quickly, tending to disappear. Also, the genotypes will evolve in response to climate making some forest areas disappear. For example, over parts of the boreal forest will convert to aspen parkland and what is today aspen parkland will convert to prairie grassland type ecosystems. Considering these risks adaptation and mitigation measures need to be in place to maintain current levels of harvesting (Boucher et al., 2018).

4.2.4 Economic implications

Forest pathways can provide ~11.9 MtCO₂e per year by 2030 in a cost-effective and readily available manner with more than 40% of it is estimated achievable at less than \$50 CAD/tCO₂e. For improved forest management, almost all the projected capacity 2021-2030 could be covered below \$80 CAD/tCO₂e, while for afforestation costs are estimated below \$1000 CAD/tCO₂e during the first years and below \$200 CAD/tCO₂e 2021-2050. These differences were explain as the afforestation costs take place on the initial years while the benefits of the LMT were observed in the long term (Drever et al., 2021).

4.2.5 Co-benefits and trade-offs

Utilizing forestry practices and increasing forest coverage as an LMT could bring benefits on ozone abatement and air filtration, avoided air quality impacts as a result of slash burning, contribute to the restoration of habitat for other dependent species, create wildlife corridors and buffer areas, reduce soil erosion and nitrogen loss, improve availability of water for irrigation increase employment opportunities and socio-economic benefits for local communities (Drever et al., 2021; Government of Canada, 2020b). Also, the incorporation of trees into predominantly agricultural landscapes has environmental benefits including enhanced soil conservation, nutrient management, and water quality. However, maximizing the short-term emissions reduction can reduce the forest's ability to contribute to longer term objectives such as reduce C stocks and increasing the sustainable rate of harvesting (Smyth et al., 2014).

4.2.6 Risks associated with scaling up

When considering scaling up forestry LMTs, it is important to highlight that these practices require large amounts of land (up to 1.10 Mha) leading to competition with agricultural land (IPCC, 2014). Strong afforestation policies could drive to lock-in in other sectors reducing incentives to invest in other

in those that are more expensive to decarbonize, such as the energy sector. In addition, forest LMTs could be susceptible to reversibility due to severe climate conditions, storms, wildfires, and extended diseases (Doelman et al., 2020). Lastly, grow rates in colder climates is slower therefore it takes a long time for benefits to be realized increasing potential back-lash from groups advocating for other climate change mitigation strategies.

- “Most current and potential CDR measures could have significant impacts on land, energy, water or nutrients if deployed at large scale (high confidence). Afforestation and bioenergy may compete with other land uses and may have significant impacts on agricultural and food systems, biodiversity, and other ecosystem functions and services (high confidence). Effective governance is needed to limit such trade-offs and ensure permanence of carbon removal in terrestrial, geological and ocean reservoirs (high confidence). Feasibility and sustainability of CDR use could be enhanced by a portfolio of options deployed at substantial, but lesser scales, rather than a single option at very large scale (high confidence). (Masson-Delmotte et al., 2019)

4.2.7 *Research gaps*

During this review, here are some of the research gaps identified (Crossley, 1980):

- Forest inventory requires more certainty. There are many forest areas that are inaccessible and will impact the real potential for managed forest areas
- Proper monitoring of forest residues and residue handling during harvesting activities
- Lack of unified framework for mitigation assessment (Smyth et al., 2014) and the impact of the specific local context
- The intersectionalities of forestry and other sectors, as well as how this LMT impacts food security in Canada.
- Proper analysis of ecosystem vulnerability due to climate change impacts
- Verification of estimated potential with in-situ measures to confirm the projected capacity (Drever et al., 2021)

4.3 Soil Carbon

4.3.1 *Policy context*

Federal level

Along with afforestation, soil organic carbon was also included into discussion paper on the proposed Federal Greenhouse Gas Offset System (released in July 2020) (the “Federal GHG Offset System”) that clarifies how the protocols for offset credits will be developed for specific project types (Richardson and Williams, 2020).

According to the Government of Canada (Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada, 2021), soil carbon levels performance in eastern and western provinces is very distinct. On the Prairies, farm soil carbon levels have stabilized or increased over the past few decades, largely from adoption of no-till cropping, which

avoids disturbing the soil while growing crops (Lynch, 2019). In Eastern Canada, however, most estimates suggest that the intensity of crop production (especially reduced use of forage crops) is causing soil carbon levels to decline. This situation is made more challenging by the fact that in higher moisture regions such as Eastern Canada and British Columbia no-till cropping does not enhance soil carbon (Lynch, 2019). According to the Western Producer, Canadian east versus west politics likely factors into why the federal government isn't talking about the sequestration of carbon in prairie soil (Booker, 2018). If specific farming sectors are rewarded or punished for the amount of greenhouse gases, including carbon, that is emitted into the atmosphere, then it's feasible the farming practices used by western Canadian grain growers would provide dividends (Booker, 2018). However, there is little indication from the federal government that it's interested in considering the actual balance of greenhouse gases emitted or sequestered by specific farming regions, practices or sectors. Due to the East-West divide, the federal government does not want to take risks by paying more dividends to western farmers. "That's a political nuclear bomb. That's why we aren't hearing much about carbon sequestration at a national level." (Booker, 2018).

Provincial level

The Conservation Cropping Protocol provides opportunities for farmers to earn carbon offsets by increasing soil carbon levels through no-till management (Government of Alberta, 2021a). The Conservation Cropping Protocol is nearing the end of its life. Fields in existing projects can continue to generate credits for 2021, but the protocol ends on December 31, 2021 (Government of Alberta, 2021a).

"Since the year 2000, Alberta soils have sequestered more carbon than emitted," the Team Alberta release stated (Tateson et al., 2021). The Conservation Cropping Protocol recognizes those efforts by setting up a price (which is shared with a carbon aggregation company) on carbon captured in the soil by specific practices. For example, in the Parkland area, it says 0.279 Mg/ha can be sequestered using no till. The no-till specs allow one pass of an opener with up to 46 per cent soil contact or two passes with up to 38 per cent soil contact (Cheater, 2021).

Through long-lasting policies, Canadian farms have implemented many soil carbon strategies since 1981. The main actors involved in the implementation of agricultural practices correspond to large farming companies, small farmers, farming associations, as well as large scale investors who have recently increase their involvement in the agricultural sector. For example, Farmers in Canada and the US, so called "Soil Carbon Cowboys" (Carbon Nation, 2021) are changing the way they graze cattle. By moving herds between small temporary pens, they allow other areas to regenerate, mimicking the grazing patterns of wild bison herds (GALLANT, 2018). In addition, local, provincial and federal government have an important role when it comes to regulation and deployment of incentives for these practices.

In the Federal budget, the agricultural sector will receive mainly support on innovation of clean technologies to address sustainability challenges allocating ~\$34 million CAD/y. In the provincial

budget, Alberta has set to invest \$245 million CAD to improve the irrigation infrastructure and support the diversification of the crops produced. Other smaller funding available until 2021 includes conservation agriculture protocol which provides a \$23/Mg offset to farmers to be able to reduce carbon emissions (Government of Alberta, 2021a) .

4.3.2 Current land use and potential land-use competition

It is estimated that the total 55.2 million hectares (Mha), currently in agricultural production, should contain about 4,140 Mt of C in the top 30 cm of soil and 5,500 Mt to a depth of 100 cm (Minasny et al., 2017). Agricultural land in Canada, could sequester 22 MtCO₂e/y equivalent to 11% of Canada's total emissions (Smulker, 2019). Much of this potential would materialize in the Prairie provinces which account for 80% of Canada's agricultural land.

In Canada, the soil organic carbon index has shown an increased trend from 1981 to 2011, with carbon sequestration of ~11.9 MtCO₂e/y (Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada, 2021). The main reason for this increase had to do with the incorporation of conservation tillage (no mechanical soil intervention) in the Prairies. However, in eastern Canada, soil carbon content has decreased due to a switch from perennial crops, such as pasture and forage, to annual crops such as cereals and oil seeds as a result of the decreased of Canada's cattle industry.

Since the federation, the number of farms in Canada has decreased while the size of the farms has increased. Today, ~53% of all Canadian territory. Competing land-uses include urban development, recreational uses, aggregate extraction, and transport corridors (Walton, 2013). As the population in Canada grows, more competition of urban development will be put on agricultural land and it may hinder potential expansion. Also, in many provinces the best quality land is located near urban centres which poses more challenges to expand soil carbon sequestration.

4.3.3 Climate risks & sensitivities

Numerous projections expect Canada to warm over the next 60 years. The changing climate is expected to have both positive and negative impacts in agriculture. Warmer temperatures will extend the growing season and allow the incorporation of new crops that are more efficient for warmer climates. However, increases in draughts and severe storms are expected to increase affecting crop yields and increasing climate vulnerability of farmers (Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada, 2020; Chung, 2020).

4.3.4 Economic implications

Drever et al. (2021) evaluated the implementation of soil carbon sequestration in about half of the total arable land in Canada (~20.5 Mha) and identified no negative impact on crop economics. The estimation on this study indicated that 1.4, 4.5 and 8.3 MtCO₂e/y by 2030 could be possible at \$10, \$50 and \$100 CAD/tCO₂e, respectively. These estimates align with international estimates reported by Fuss et al. (2018) and Roe et al. (2019).

4.3.5 *Co-benefits and trade-offs*

Agricultural practices that might promote soil C sequestration, such as the application of fertilizers and manures to improve yields or the reduction of tillage, can also lead to increased nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions. These emissions can in turn, offset any climate mitigation benefits (Smulker, 2019). Today, Canadian agriculture had net emissions of ~70 MtCO₂e/y in 2016 accounting sectors specific emissions as well as the emissions associated with the energy consumed in fertilizer production and farm activities (Environment and Climate Change Canada, 2021b).

Increasing cropland leads to loss of C-stored due to loss of woody biomass through extending croplands as well as negative impacts on biodiversity. Also, it could lead to an increase of use for fertilizers and pesticides which has a negative impact on the environment. When using alternatives to increase crop yields, the use of manure and mineral fertilizers has also increased the losses of phosphorous into the environment. Another impact of using animal manure as fertilizers involves the contamination of ground water with pathogens such as viruses, bacteria, and protozoa. In Canada, specific buffer strips and manure fraction separations have been implemented to allow farmers to utilize nutrients more efficiently. Further impacts of increasing cropland is associated with higher risks for soil erosion, reduced wildlife habitats.

Smulker et al. (2019) evaluated the trade-offs of agri-environment indicators such as GHG, pesticides, Nitrogen, Phosphorus, Coliforms, Cover and Wildlife. The study found that when evaluating these indicators with the increasing intensification of agricultural practices, GHG emissions have not been significantly addressed by current policies resulting on a marginal reduction of carbon emissions in the sector.

4.3.6 *Risks associated with scaling up*

Similar to forestry, some actors consider that too many resources on climate policies for the agricultural sector could deviate much needed resources necessary to decarbonize more expensive sectors. To maximize sequestration potential of the Canadian agricultural sector, efforts are needed to address emissions associated with livestock production, manure fertilizer use and energy consumption in the agricultural processes. Also, the soil theoretical capacity and local dynamics on each province difficulties the application of a unique strategy while maintaining the response to evolving markets.

4.3.7 *Research gaps*

For Soil Carbon Sequestration, we have fund gaps in specific ways of accounting for GHG emissions, establish the stability of the carbon sequestered, clear understanding of the interconnections of the agricultural sector with other carbon intensive sectors.

The East-West divide between Western Canada when Western farmers contribute more into carbon offsets is not quite addressed at the federal level. This is a gap in federal legislation. Another gap refers to Carbon Cowboys voluntary project, in which farmers use grazing rotation technologies that help to generate more soil carbon on their lands (The List Show TV, 2020)

4.4 BECCS

4.4.1 Policy context

International level

ISO Technical Committee (TC) 238 was established in 2007 to develop International Standards on solid biofuels. Many of these Standards are based on existing CEN (European Committee for Standardization) TC335 Standards, while others are entirely new ones, all of which intended to reflect current needs and priorities of the solid biofuels industry (Melin et al., 2016). The Standards specify and classify all types of biomass such as woody, herbaceous, fruity and aquatic. The Standards also provide specifications for graded solid biofuels traded in the market, including wood pellets, wood briquettes, wood chips, firewood, as well as non-woody pellets and briquette (Melin et al., 2016).

Federal level

Despite Canada having the greatest quantity of solid biomass per capita in the world, the country, outside of the pulp and paper sector, has been relatively slow to adopt modern solid biomass fuel technologies (Stephen and Wood-Bohm, 2016). The reasons for this include a lack of recognition by policy makers of the important role of solid biomass in decarbonization, erroneous beliefs on the air pollutant emissions performance of modern biomass technologies, and the low cost of the primary competitive fuels – natural gas and coal. However, a variety of successful policy measures have been used by other countries and could serve as examples for Canada’s federal policy development (Stephen and Wood-Bohm, 2016).

Since the inception of ISO/TC238, Canada has taken on a leadership role to ensure that these standards are technically sound, do not discriminate against Canadian markets, and that the Canadian solid biofuels industry is well positioned to compete effectively in the global marketplace (Melin et al., 2016).

Canada, largely through work conducted at WPAC and UBC has made significant contributions towards international safety regulations, including:

- Development of MSDS (Materials Safety Data Sheets) for wood pellets around the world and more recently an upgrade to the new Safety Data Sheet (SDS) format;
- Development of the International classification of wood pellets under the International Maritime Organization (IMO) Code for safe transportation of wood pellets;
- Currently developing “Best Practices Guidelines for the Wood Pellet Industry” with participation with the ISO/TC 238 working group on safety; and
- Development of methodologies for determination of self-heating, off-gassing and oxygen depletion (Melin et al., 2016).

The Pan-Canadian Framework for Clean Growth and Climate Change (PFC) mentions that Clean technology, such as lower-carbon bioenergy, and bioproducts that use feedstock from agriculture and forestry waste and dedicated crops to replace higher-carbon fuels can also reduce emissions

(Environment and Climate Change Canada, 2016b). The Government of Canada promotes the use of landfill biomass to create sustainable energy sources, such as renewable natural gas or advanced biofuels, or to create other bioproducts (such as bioplastics and biocomposites) that can also generate new economic opportunities for Canadians (Environment and Climate Change Canada, 2016). The PCF was developed to establish a path forward to meet Canada's commitments under the Paris Agreement (Government of Canada, 2021c).

According to the PFC, Prince Edward Island is home to Canada's longest running, biomass-fired district heating system. Operating since the 1980's, the system has expanded to serve over 125 buildings in the downtown core of Charlottetown, including the University of Prince Edward Island and the Queen Elizabeth Hospital, and cleanly burns 66 000 Mg of waste materials annually (Environment and Climate Change Canada, 2016b).

The proposed Clean Fuel Regulations would require liquid fossil fuel primary suppliers (i.e. producers and importers) to reduce the carbon intensity (CI) of the liquid fossil fuels they produce in and import into Canada from 2016 CI levels by 2.4 gCO₂e/MJ in 2022, increasing to 12 gCO₂e/MJ in 2030 (Government of Canada, 2021c). The proposed Regulations would allow the creation of credits from the production of low CI fuels produced from biomass-based feedstocks. To prevent adverse impacts on land use and biodiversity stemming from the increased harvest and cultivation of these feedstocks, the proposed Regulations would establish land-use and biodiversity (LUB) criteria. Only biofuels made from biomass feedstock that adhere to the LUB criteria would be eligible for compliance credit creation. These criteria apply to feedstock regardless of geographic origin. The criteria do not apply to feedstock that is not biomass (e.g. fuel made from direct air capture) or that is designated "low-concern biomass feedstock" (e.g. municipal solid waste) (Government of Canada, 2021c).

Provincial level

Alberta is one of five provinces that have renewable fuel requirements equal to or higher than the current federal requirements set in the RFR (Government of Canada, 2021c). The Alberta RFS pertains to fuels produced from renewable materials in the form of renewable fuel alcohols, such as ethanol, used in gasoline and bio-based diesel, used in diesel. These products may be produced using traditional technologies or emerging technologies based on advanced chemical and biological processes (Government of Alberta, 2021b).

According to Welling & Shaw (2007), there are several challenges that the province should overcome in order to develop a better policy framework on biomass use in Alberta. The potential of wood-based bioenergy has not been fully explored in rural Alberta yet.

Welling & Shaw (Welling and Shaw, 2007) suggest the following solutions for the use of wood biomass in Alberta:

- Wood biomass must become a profitable business for energy companies, subcontractors, and forest owners to see any sustained success. This is unlikely to develop rapidly or on any sizable

scale without the direct involvement of the government. The climate needed to produce economic success is missing many of the positive factors cited in the barriers and recommendations sections.

- The environmental value of using wood heating – GHG neutral status – is not at all understood by consumers and amazingly, also by a large proportion of government employees and officials involved in shaping alternative heating choices.
- Education and training should play a central role in mobilizing the wood-energy resources. Government, academic institutions, and professional bodies should address education, training, and the need for the sensitization of all wood producing stakeholders and energy consumers with regard to wood-energy skills and entrepreneurship. Wood-energy issues should be introduced into forestry training curricula (Welling and Shaw, 2007).

Currently, there are only two examples that have implemented BECCS in Canada at pilot scale. One was related to oil and gas production and the other to Pulp and paper manufacturing. However, many projects around Bioenergy are being deployed and supported country-wide and in Alberta, though not yet incorporating carbon capture. Most actors implementing bioenergy right now belong to the power sector and heavy industry. However, in 2018 the government of Canada created the “Clean Energy for Rural and Remote Communities program” which provides support for communities to deploy their own clean energy projects. Today, there are more than 70 biomass generating power plants with a total installed capacity of 2,408 MW. Wood biomass must become a profitable business for energy companies, subcontractors, and forest owners to see any sustained success (Welling and Shaw, 2007).

To further deploy BECCS, different funding alternatives can arise by the combination of programs supporting growth in bioenergy use and carbon capture and storage. Within the Pan-Canadian Framework for Clean Growth and Climate change, the government of Canada pledged to provide support for the Forestry, Agriculture and Waste sector on the development of advanced bioproducts and bioenergy (Environment and Climate Change Canada, 2016b). As for the 2021 Federal budget, the government of Canada proposed to provide \$54.8 million CAD over two years for the forest-based bioeconomy and \$67.2 million for seven years on the deployment of a Clean Fuel Standard to increase the use of biofuels. In addition, the government proposed to provide \$319 million CAD over seven years to promote the commercial viability of carbon capture, utilization and storage projects, \$35 million CAD to support innovation on CCS, plus a tax incentive for CCS whose costs have not been yet determined (Government of Canada, 2021b). At the provincial level, Alberta provides \$63 million CAD to support liquid biofuel and bio-power production for 2.5 years (Government of Alberta, 2018b). Also, Alberta is providing \$80 million CAD through the “Industrial Energy Efficiency and Carbon Capture Utilization and Storage program (IEE CCUS)” to support industrial energy efficiency and carbon capture, utilization and storage projects and \$1.24 billion through 2025 to support two commercial-scale CCS projects, Shell-Quest and Alberta Carbon Trunk Link (ACTL) to reduce GHG from oil sands and fertilizer sectors by 2.76 million Mg per year. This infrastructure could support deployment of BECCS in the area.

4.4.2 *Current land use and potential land-use competition*

Currently only two projects on BECCS for Canada have been completed: (i) Husky Energy Lashburn and Tangleflaps CO₂ Injection in Heavy Oil with a capacity of 90,000 Mtpa, and (ii) Saint-Felicien Pulp Mill and Greenhouse Carbon Capture Project with a capacity of 90,000 Mtpa. BECCS only negative emissions if used with residues from currently managed forest land and no un-managed land (Withey et al., 2019). Under this scenario, BECCS implementation would be possible on 200 million ha of long-term managed forest which accounts for 57% of total forest land in Canada (Natural Resources Canada, 2020b). However, today only 0.2% of the total forest managed area is harvested.

In Canada, land-use competition for BECCS is associated with those that present risks of deforestation such as Oil and gas exploitation, Agriculture, Hydroelectricity, Urban development. However, Canada's deforestation rate is 0.02% of total forest area, which is relatively low and represents low risks for BECCS. On the other hand, scaling capacity for BECCS depends heavily on the availability of biomass and adequate underground storage space. BECCS sector depends heavily on forestry sector demand and capacity unless other resources are tapped. Within this context, western provinces, such as Saskatchewan, Alberta and British Columbia have better possibilities for large-scale deployment of BECCS (Natural Resources Canada, 2021).

4.4.3 *Climate risks & sensitivities*

As BECCS in Canada relies mainly on the availability of forestry and agricultural residues, the climate risks for this LMT are linked to its biomass sources as discussed on previously for Forestry and the Agricultural sectors (see sections 3.3 and 3.4). On the other hand, the carbon capture portion of BECCS is an engineered solution. Therefore, its exposure to climate risks may be associated more with potential damages due to wildfires and severe storms. However, the engineered infrastructure would be designed to endure a certain level of stressors, resulting in a lower/more controlled risk exposure.

4.4.4 *Economic implications*

BECCS could be applied in a competitive way given ideally located hubs/clusters are deployed combining bioenergy with CCS. The provinces of Alberta and Saskatchewan are the best situated since their combination of high bioenergy potential and vast underground storage capacity. With carbon prices above \$65 USD, the value of carbon removal from biomass exceeds the energy value of oil. With a carbon price of \$170 USD by 2030 as proposed by the federal government, revenue from atmospheric carbon removal would ensure competitive electricity costs (International CCS Knowledge Centre, 2021). If BECCS is deployed, revenues from biomass trade are projected to become a significant share of GDP reaching 6-10% in Canada (Muratori et al., 2016).

Abatement costs for BECCS are estimated between \$20-200 USD depending on the energy carrier and sector (Melton et al., 2020) when abatement potential of both bioenergy and CCS are accounted for.

4.4.5 *Co-benefits and trade-offs*

Assessing the impacts of BECCS requires looking into complex intersectionalities across different sectors. Stoy et al. (Stoy et al., 2018) proposed food, water, energy, biodiversity, and social systems (FWEBS) framework that can be implemented to evaluate the expected impacts of BECCS on different regions. The full implementation of the FWEBS framing will be done during the execution of LANDMARC. However, some insights of the different elements are discussed below.

BECCS could impact food production if specific cropland is developed for bioenergy. For Canada, BECCS is expected to be deployed using forestry and agricultural residue only. Therefore, not major impacts on food production are foreseen though it should be taken into consideration when developing new policies. Despite of the lower land-use of BECCS with respect to afforestation, this LMT could displace land for other uses such as recreation and urban development. On the other hand, diversification of crops, pulse crop, crop coverage, could bring additional economic benefits for farmers (Stoy et al., 2018).

With regards to water, BECCS would compete with other industrial and agricultural activities in the area. Though Canada has vast water resources, it is important to assess the effect of BECCS activities in water demand and water quality since will interact with other uses. Also, pollution from neighbouring industrial activities may impact BECCS efficiency. When considering potential opportunities and trade-offs of BECCS on the energy spectrum, it is expected that the major impact could be seen at the Prairie provinces. On one side, these provinces have a strong reliability on fossil-fuel based energy sources while the potential of bioenergy requires further public investment. However, the long history of the region with large-scale energy projects could facilitate the deployment of CCS due to better understanding of communities of the implications. Also, these provinces have more developed regulatory frameworks for the energy sector, forestry and agriculture that share many similarities with BECCS. Improved consultation approaches and incentives to level the playing field for BECCS will be required.

Expanded industrial activity in the region could compromise biodiversity through loss of habitats. Also, the impacts of BECCS deployment should be balanced with the loss of native grasslands and wetlands which are important carbon sinks for the region. Appropriately managed, cropland could foster wildlife habitat but could also decrease biodiversity due to the elimination of native species. In the social aspects, BECCS could bring new economic sources to local communities but could also favour certain stakeholders leading to more inequalities. All the aspects of the FWEBS framework require further study to establish the local context.

4.4.6 *Risks associated with scaling up*

For scaling up BECCS in Canada, it is important to identify the different potential across regions and the LMT portfolio that is more suitable to the local context. For higher efficiency, BECCS requires appropriate access to biomass feedstocks as well as neighbouring underground storage facilities. So far, the most suitable landscape for this deployment is found mostly at the Prairie provinces. This

implies that BECCS potential is restricted to some areas and requires other provinces to utilize different LMT portfolios. In addition, Canada's energy mix is rather mature so BECCS could find some resistance due to the necessary investment in regions that are heavily reliant on carbon intensive energy sources.

4.4.7 *Research gaps*

From the review of BECCS for Canada, we found knowledge gaps that are important to address to better understand the LMT potential and implications of its deployment. First, considering Canada to be a country with a large extension of land the context on each region can significantly vary. Therefore, it is important to assess the spatial-explicit optimization of BECCS and its real potential per region. Further understanding the opportunities and trade-off of BECCS in the different provinces since each region has their own geographical and socioeconomic dynamics that would be influenced by BECCS.

BECCS will need to be fully integrated with the electricity grid in the case of power generation. That requires proper alignment of different actors and institutions which was not found on during this review. As biomass residue harvesting does not generate visible profit for farmers, it has less interest from farmers than other LMTs. Therefore, there is a need to frame these projects in terms of their economic capacity to generate profits.

All the aspects mentioned above, highlight the need for clear coherent policies at the local, provincial, and federal level to materialize BECCS' potential. Therefore, further studies on socio-economic impacts and policy recommendations are needed and not abundant for the Canadian context.

4.5 Biochar

4.5.1 *Policy context*

International level

Fourteen governments as well as the United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD) are formally calling for 'biochar' to play a significant role in a post-2012 climate change agreement and in carbon trading (Paul et al., 2009). They have signed up to claims by the International Biochar Initiative (IBI), a lobby organisation made up largely of biochar entrepreneurs as well as scientists, many of them with close industry links. However, the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) has warned that biochar is a 'a new and poorly understood technology', that feedstock for large-scale biomass is likely to come from 'biofuels' (agrofuels), i.e. dedicated tree and crop plantations which "should be approached with great caution" and that the impacts on biodiversity and long-term agricultural sustainability are unknown (Paul et al., 2009). When the IPCC finalised its Fourth Assessment Report, it did not find sufficient evidence to reach any conclusion about biochar. UNCCD's claims about IPCC support for biochar, contained in their recent submissions to UNFCCC are therefore incorrect. The IBI argues that applying charcoal to soil creates a reliable and permanent 'carbon sink' and mitigates climate change. It also argues that biochar makes soils more fertile and better able to hold water, thus helping farmers adapt to climate change (Paul et al., 2009). Proposals for 'climate change mitigation' with biochar involve such large quantities of biomass that at least 500 million

hectares of dedicated plantations would be required, as well as agricultural land and forests being stripped of so-called ‘residues’. As the experience with agrofuels shows, the creation of a large new market for biomass can be expected to move the ‘agricultural frontier’ (including tree plantations) further into forests and other ecosystems, causing agricultural intensification leading to more nitrous oxide emissions, as well as displacing communities and food production (Paul et al., 2009).

Federal level

Similar to soil carbon and biomass, the Pan-Canadian Framework on Clean Growth and Climate Change mentions biochar in general terms, stating that clean technology, such as lower-carbon bioenergy, and bioproducts that use feedstock from agriculture and forestry waste and dedicated crops to replace higher-carbon fuels can also reduce emissions (Environment and Climate Change Canada, 2016b).

The Canadian Government through its regulating agency, Canadian Food & Inspection Agency (CFIA), has approved the use of biochar in soil. This development is the result of two years of concerted work from organizations such as the Alberta Biochar Initiative (ABI), AirTerra, and other provincial biochar proponents to gain CFIA approval (International Biochar Initiative, 2018).

“Regulatory approval is something ABI has pursued since 2012,” said Don Harfield, who has conducted biochar research and development at Alberta Innovates – Technology Futures for over ten years and serves as ABI’s technical lead (International Biochar Initiative, 2018). “It gives ABI partners the opportunity to pursue a wide range of potential commercial applications for biochar in Alberta and other markets.” (International Biochar Initiative, 2018).

The Canadian Food Inspection Agency (CFIA) requires, by law, that all biochar sold as soil supplement in agriculture and horticulture be certified. To obtain this registration, one must demonstrate that the biochar is harmless for the environment through analyses of carbon, nitrogen and ash contents as well as some toxicological analyses are required such as metal, dioxin and furan contents (Bertrand and Lange, 2019). No Canadian regulation covers the use of biochar pellets as a combustible. However, producers tend to follow technical specifications set by the industry, such as the ISO/TS 17225-8 standard (ISO, 2016), to ensure consistency and to classify their products in compliance with international standards for pellets. These ISO standards refer to several properties that must be declared, namely the origin and source of the organic material, moisture, metal, ash and fines contents, calorific value and density. By respecting these specifications, producers can more easily offer their biochar pellets on the international market (Bertrand and Lange, 2019).

The Canadian Food Inspection Agency (CFIA) requires, by law, that all biochar sold as soil supplement in agriculture and horticulture be certified. The CFIA is responsible for this certification under the Federal Fertilizer Act as a level II soil supplement (CFIA 2017, cited in Bertrand and Lange, 2019). This is applicable for imported and local biochar (Bertrand and Lange, 2019).

Biochar is registered under the list of approved soil supplement materials as part of the Guidance Document repository from the Canadian Food Inspection Agency (CFIA) (Canadian Food Inspection Agency, 2021).

Provincial level

In 2002, Alberta Environment released Standards and Guidelines of the Use of Wood Ash as a Liming Material for Agricultural Soils (Government of Alberta, 2002). This document presents general information on wood ash as well as the regulatory requirements for generators and recommended practices for land managers (Government of Alberta, 2002).

Lakeland College and Alberta Innovates Technology Futures (AITF) with assistance from Western Economic Diversification Canada and industry support have developed the Alberta Biochar Initiative. The ABI is intended to develop and demonstrate technologies that will enable the large-scale commercial deployment of biochar products and biochar applications for the benefit of Albertans (International Biochar Initiative, 2018).

Established in Dec 2011, the ABI consists of small-to-medium sized enterprises (SMEs), industry, academia and government sharing information and producing and generating biochar for end-use applications including soil amendments, reclamation, remediation, horticultural growth media and conducting biochar lifecycle analysis for potential carbon sequestration applications (International Biochar Initiative, 2018). As of 2010, Alberta Innovates Technology Futures pyrolyzers were the only Biochar facility in the province (Anyia, 2010). As of 2016, two ABI demonstration scale pyrolysis units located in Vegreville (commissioned in 2013) (Harfield, 2016). In December 2015, the Canadian federal government approved commercialization of biochar in Alberta, based on a request by the Alberta Biochar Initiative (Davey, 2016). No specific mentioned of biochar on the federal or provincial budget of Alberta.

4.5.2 Current land use and potential land-use competition

Biochar was only allowed for commercialization in recent years. Several applications are being explored including soil amendment, agriculture support, energy use and air and water filtration. However, no clear statistics are available about the country-wide use of biochar. D. Matovic (Matovic, 2011) estimated that there is enough biomass available in Canada to off-set total Canadian GHG emissions when considering both forestry and agricultural residues produced. However, the main limitation is the amount of land on which biochar can be deployed. Considering potential competition of forestry residue for bioenergy generation, Drever et al. 2021 (Drever et al., 2021) considered biochar only from agricultural residues and estimated a mitigation potential of 6.9 MtCO₂e/y spread throughout one fifth of the total arable land of Canada (~67 Mha) where the biomass was harvested. Though there are evidence of growth in the market and interest from the private sector there are no projections for biochar deployment as a carbon sequestration strategy. For biochar, the main competition would be those land uses that compete with agriculture as described on section 3.3.

In Alberta, the Alberta Biochar Initiative, had proposed a desired pathway where 2010-2015 5 MtCO₂e reduced by applying 1.4 Mt of biochar to 280,000 ha of farmland annually. Then, implement a scale-up phase to achieve 10 MtCO₂e reduced by applying 2.8 Mt of biochar to 560,000 ha of farmland annually followed by a full commercial scale aiming for 30 MtCO₂e reduction annually by applying ~8.3 Mt of biochar over 1.6 million ha a year (Anyia, 2010). However, today there is no information about the continuity of the biochar initiative and or continuing support for this initiative.

4.5.3 Climate risks & sensitivities

Climate risks for biochar in Canada are well aligned with those described for agriculture on section 3.3. In addition, the impact of biochar sequestration can also be look from the perspective of soils emissions, soil albedo, and native soil organic carbon (Tisserant and Cherubini, 2019). Climate risks for biochar are not well studied yet and understanding the impacts of changes in soil albedo, transpiration and other short-lived climate forcers (i.e. methane and black carbon) requires coupling of land-climate models. Precipitation, latent heat, surface radiation and clouds could have a complex interaction with soil response. For example, some research as indicated that soil albedo can be reduced offsetting partially or all mitigation potential of biochar for biofuels. Also, evapotranspiration changes from substitution of annual to perennial crops could offset 0.5 °C of warming. In addition, mitigation potential has shown to be very sensitive to the modelling assumptions and study scope taken during life-cycle analysis of biochar (Tisserant and Cherubini, 2019).

4.5.4 Economic implications

Economic viability of biochar depends on feedstock, conversion process, and its connection with carbon sequestration and availability of credits locally (Homagain et al., 2016). Cost analysis for biochar deployment as mitigation practice in Canada showed no possible alternative under \$100 CAD/tCO₂e and it costs were impacted by residue availability and collection efficiency (Drever et al., 2021).

4.5.5 Co-benefits and trade-offs

As a form of carbon, biochar is considered stable, and its carbon storage capacity can be quantifiable serving as a potential offset mechanism. However, once incorporated into the soil biochar decomposes, therefore its permanency is question since it varies on soil type and environmental conditions. Analyses in Canada indicated that assuming stability for 100 years is acceptable since decomposition rates are low in this period. However, further studies are necessary to identify the decomposition of biochar under different soil types and weather conditions which vary significantly across Canada (de Ruiter et al., 2014).

A trade-off of biochar involves the energy use and combustion during its production. Smokeless processes are needed to abate emissions and particles emanated from pyrolysis. Also, measures are needed to abate other potential harmful air pollutants. Also, harvesting forestry residue for biochar may affect ecosystem biodiversity and increase erosion on exposed soil surfaces. Biochar components

and heavy metals should be carefully assessed to guaranteed low-toxicity to the remediated environments.

Further studies are being develop which show the potential of biochar to absorber harmful metals, reclaim damaged mine sites and purification of polluted water from heavy industry. The development of a supply chain for biochar could also provide materials to mitigate other environmental issues besides carbon emissions.

Today, uncertainty remains about mitigation potential of biochar. Studies conducted in Canada are not conclusive around the actual capacity for biochar to increase soil carbon in agricultural land or decrease emissions from manure when provided as a feed supplement to cattle. This evidences the susceptibility of biochar to local environmental conditions which proves to be challenging for Canada with a wide variety of climatic zones and soil types (Betkowski, 2021; Briere, 2017; Willis, 2019).

4.5.6 Risks associated with scaling up

As discussed on previous sections, the major risks associated with scaling up involve the wide variety of contexts across regions in Canada. Soil quality varies significantly within and across regions, which impacts the biochar decomposition and efficiency. Also, assumptions of land availability rely on type of crops and farming activities. Also, so far biochar deployment costs are higher than other potential mitigation practices. Therefore, lowering the costs for implementation could provide better opportunities for biochar. Currently, there is no specific federal or provincial polices for biochar for carbon sequestration. Therefore, for scaling up it is required that Canada develops specific policies with regards to Air quality and soil applications.

4.5.7 Research gaps

There is definitely a lack of biochar's recognition as potential technology for carbon emissions' reduction. Pyrolysis process is facilitated by using sophisticated technology that is only located in a few towns in Alberta. At the federal level, biochar is mostly perceived as fertilizer, at the provincial level, the Alberta Biochar Initiative's efforts are not enough to push the government to adopt specific regulations on biochar production that could focus on the role of biochar in land-based mitigation initiatives. Biochar has been commercialized in Alberta since 2015.

Another gap with biochar in Canada involves Quality and Standards definition. Though international and European standards are available, Canadian regulations are needed for carbon sequestration and other energy uses. Also, large scale agronomic field trials needed across climatic zones and soil types to assess stability and large-scale impact.

Lastly, there a big knowledge gaps with regards risks and sensitivities of climate change on biochar as well as comprehensive understanding of the social risks and impacts associated with local implementation.

5. Conclusion

The five LMTs shortlisted for Canada, afforestation/reforestation, soil carbon, wetlands, BECCS and biochar, are commonly related to management of forest areas and agricultural land. Canadian forest expands to 348 Mha of forest which are divided by 226 Mha of managed land and 122 Mha of unmanaged land. Most of the LMTs deployment is expected to occur within managed forest land. On the other hand, Canada has 67 Mha of agricultural land (Matovic 2011) which is considered at least half to be apt for LMT implementation. In addition, wetlands cover ~119 million ha in Canada. Combined, this LMTs could be potentially implemented in ~400 Mha across the country.

Currently the deployment of LMTs in Canada is on very early stage. Significant research efforts and pilot projects have been implemented. However, specific policies are not available though discussions have been taken across different provinces and the federal level. Considering this stage, land use competition is mainly related with the land-use changed around the forestry and agricultural sectors.

For all the shortlisted LMTs, there was consensus that there is enough technical certainty for deployment. Most of this LMTs have been implemented for years, but not with a climate mitigation focus. Therefore, the lack of direct policy to align the different economic sectors with the climate goals represents a barrier. Also, all LMTs were deemed very susceptible to climate risks. That is, the risks of wildfires, floods, draughts, pests, and a changing environment, it is considered to add uncertainty in the potential success of the LMTs. Finally, one of the major barriers identified was associated with the uncertainty around impact monitoring and permanency. When compared to BECCS or DAC, some LMTs are graded very high risks of looking the mitigation capacity due to an unexpected natural disaster. Also, potential biological degradation above- and underground. As a result, LMT mitigation capacity are valued below engineered solutions represented more barrier to access more financing.

As LMTs are deployment, it is expected that the different alternatives compete for land. Despite of a theoretical mitigation potential, the development of different LMTs portfolios at the local level will determine the actual mitigation capacity. Each LMT has its own opportunities and trade-off that are connected with other potential LMTs. Therefore, policies need to be carefully design in order to achieve carbon reduction goals while supporting other sustainability factors such as food, water, energy, biodiversity and socio-economic priorities. Based on its geography, deployment of LMTs will change significantly on the target location. In addition, due to its federal structure, the policies around land-use changes depend of each province which represents a barrier for streamlining efforts to scale LMTs nationally.

The implementation of the shortlisted LMTs is not expected to significantly change the land management framework already in place. In Canada, land management plans are in place at the federal and provincial levels to monitor and regulate the use of the natural resources as well as mitigate the impacts of industrial activities within these areas. Also, federal jurisdiction for applies to support indigenous communities on development land management plans for reserves.

For Afforestation and BECCS, sustainable land management policies – already in place in Canada – require forest to be regenerated and are certified by third-party international organization to review its transparency. Guidelines supporting climate adapted replenish species and implementation of new technologies. Current regulations and guidelines could be adapted to incorporate responsible harvesting of forestry residue as well as location of conversion facilities to mitigate negative impacts on the environment. Canada’s forests are an important economic sector and 70% of indigenous peoples live on forest lands or near forest lands. Therefore, all management efforts should consider local communities at the forefront of the decision making since they will be heavily impacted by changes in the sector. The Canadian Forest Service (CFS) is the governmental entity in charge of ensuring forest are sustainable and healthy and oversees the policies to implement management plans. Equivalent institutions are also established across each province to bring the regional perspective.

For Soil carbon and biochar, policies for agricultural land management are under the oversight of Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada (AAFC). This entity keeps monitoring data and establish best practices for managing agricultural land and associated resources. To further implement LMTs within the agricultural sector, clear policies will have to be created to incorporate climate targets in agricultural activities. Currently, an Agricultural Climate Solutions (ACS) program has been created with the support of \$185 million CAD for 10 years to support the development and implementation of farming practices that address climate change. However, further details are needed to create the necessary incentives to achieve the LMTs full potential. For wetlands, new policies are coming online associated with wetlands protection and restoration, which gives an initial framework to start.

The identification of the narratives for the main Canadian LMTs seeks to enable the analysis of the risks and (climate) impacts of LMTs, as well as support the scenario development for modelling and assessment with stakeholders the potential impacts of scaling up LMTs at national and regional scale, which are key objectives of the LANDMARC project.

One of the main challenges with informing these narratives with stakeholder perspectives lies on the disconnection of local perspectives with national/regional perspectives. LMTs have a tangible local impact, that when looking from a regional lens, loses resolution and create risks of national portfolios missing the priorities of the local communities. LANDMARC is looking to address these challenges by evaluating the integration of local, national, and regional perspectives in portfolio design and alignment with global sustainability commitments. Further research necessary to ensure the co-development of portfolios, strategies and policies, relevant at different scales, is being considered within LANDMARC’s scope.

6. References

- Adolwa, I.S., Schwarze, S., Waswa, B., Buerkert, A., 2019. Understanding system innovation adoption: A comparative analysis of integrated soil fertility management uptake in Tamale (Ghana) and Kakamega (Kenya). *Renewable Agriculture and Food Systems* 34, 313–325. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1742170517000485>
- Akinnifesi, F.K., Ajayi, O.C., Sileshi, G., Chirwa, P.W., Chianu, J., 2010. Fertiliser trees for sustainable food security in the maize-based production systems of East and Southern Africa. A review. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.* 30, 615–629. <https://doi.org/10.1051/agro/2009058>
- Bayer, C., Gomes, J., Zanatta, J.A., Vieira, F.C.B., Dieckow, J., 2016. Mitigating greenhouse gas emissions from a subtropical Ultisol by using long-term no-tillage in combination with legume cover crops. *Soil and Tillage Research* 161, 86–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2016.03.011>
- Bond, W.J., Stevens, N., Midgley, G.F., Lehmann, C.E.R., 2019. The Trouble with Trees: Afforestation Plans for Africa. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 34, 963–965. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2019.08.003>
- Butnan, S., Vityakon, P., 2020. The interactive effects of soil disturbance and residue quality on soil nitrogen mineralisation in a tropical sandy soil. *Soil Res.* 58, 277–288. <https://doi.org/10.1071/SR18350>
- Buyinza, J., Nuberg, I.K., Muthuri, C.W., Denton, M.D., 2020. Assessing smallholder farmers' motivation to adopt agroforestry using a multi-group structural equation modeling approach. *Agroforest Syst* 94, 2199–2211. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-020-00541-2>
- Cavanagh, C.J., Chemarum, A.K., Vedeld, P.O., Petursson, J.G., 2017. Old wine, new bottles? Investigating the differential adoption of 'climate-smart' agricultural practices in western Kenya. *Journal of Rural Studies* 56, 114–123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2017.09.010>
- Cedrez, C.B., Chamberlin, J., Guo, Z., Hijmans, R.J., 2020. Spatial variation in fertilizer prices in Sub-Saharan Africa. *PLOS ONE* 15, e0227764. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0227764>
- Chivenge, P., Vanlauwe, B., Gentile, R., Wangechi, H., Mugendi, D., Kessel, C. van, Six, J., 2009. Organic and Mineral Input Management to Enhance Crop Productivity in Central Kenya. *Agronomy Journal* 101, 1266–1275. <https://doi.org/10.2134/agronj2008.0188x>
- Dass, A., Sudhishri, S., Lenka, N.K., 2013. Integrated Nutrient Management to Improve Finger Millet Productivity and Soil Conditions in Hilly Region of Eastern India. *Journal of Crop Improvement* 27, 528–546. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15427528.2013.800828>
- Davidson, E.A., Janssens, I.A., 2006. Temperature sensitivity of soil carbon decomposition and feedbacks to climate change. *Nature* 440, 165–173. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature04514>
- Derpsch, R., Friedrich, T., Kassam, A., Hongwen, L., 2010. Current status of adoption of no-till farming in the world and some of its main benefits 3, 25.

- Dhadli, H.S., Brar, B.S., Black, T.A., 2016. N₂O emissions in a long-term soil fertility experiment under maize–wheat cropping system in Northern India. *Geoderma Regional* 7, 102–109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geodrs.2016.02.003>
- European-Commission, Joint Research Centre, 2018. Demographic and human capital scenarios for the 21st century: 2018 assessment for 201 countries. Publications Office of the European Union, LU.
- FAO, 2000. FRA 2000 ON DEFINITIONS OF FOREST AND FOREST CHANGE. Rome.
- Foley, J.A., 1994. Net primary productivity in the terrestrial biosphere: The application of a global model. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 99, 20773–20783. <https://doi.org/10.1029/94JD01832>
- Gentile, R., Vanlauwe, B., Chivenge, P., Six, J., 2011. Trade-offs between the short- and long-term effects of residue quality on soil C and N dynamics. *Plant Soil* 338, 159–169. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-010-0360-z>
- Gosling, E., Knoke, T., Reith, E., Reyes Cáceres, A., Paul, C., 2021. Which Socio-economic Conditions Drive the Selection of Agroforestry at the Forest Frontier? *Environmental Management* 67, 1119–1136. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-021-01439-0>
- Government of Kenya, 2020a. Re: Submission of Kenya’s updated nationally determined contribution. Ministry of Environment and Forestry, Nairobi.
- Government of Kenya, 2020b. DRAFT NATIONAL FOREST POLICY,. Ministry of Environment, Water and Natural Resources, Nairobi.
- Government of Kenya, 2018a. National Climate Change Action Plan (Kenya) Volume 3: Mitigation Technical Analysis Report. Ministry of Environment and Forestry, Nairobi.
- Government of Kenya, 2018b. National Climate Change Action Plan (Kenya) 2018-2022. Ministry of Environment and Forestry, Nairobi.
- Government of Kenya, 2017. Kenya Climate Smart Agriculture Strategy-2017-2026. Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock and Fisheries, Nairobi.
- Government of Kenya, 2016. Kenya National Adaptation Plan: 2015-2030. National Environment Management Authority, Government of Kenya, Nairobi.
- Government of Kenya, 2015. Second National Communication to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. National Environment Management Authority, Government of Kenya, Nairobi.
- Government of Kenya, 2014. Forest Policy. Ministry of Environment, Water and Natural Resources, Nairobi.
- Hély, C., Bremond, L., Alleaume, S., Smith, B., Sykes, M.T., Guiot, J., 2006. Sensitivity of African biomes to changes in the precipitation regime. *Global Ecology and Biogeography* 15, 258–270. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1466-8238.2006.00235.x>

- Hermans, T.D.G., Whitfield, S., Dougill, A.J., Thierfelder, C., 2021. Why we should rethink ‘adoption’ in agricultural innovation: Empirical insights from Malawi. *Land Degradation & Development* 32, 1809–1820. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.3833>
- Hörner, D., Wollni, M., 2021. Integrated soil fertility management and household welfare in Ethiopia. *Food Policy* 100, 102022. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2020.102022>
- Kamoni, P.T., Gicheru, P.T., Wokabi, S.M., Easter, M., Milne, E., Coleman, K., Falloon, P., Paustian, K., 2007. Predicted soil organic carbon stocks and changes in Kenya between 1990 and 2030. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment, Soil carbon stocks at regional scales* 122, 105–113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2007.01.024>
- Kätterer, T., Roobroeck, D., Andrén, O., Kimutai, G., Karltun, E., Kirchmann, H., Nyberg, G., Vanlauwe, B., Röing de Nowina, K., 2019. Biochar addition persistently increased soil fertility and yields in maize-soybean rotations over 10 years in sub-humid regions of Kenya. *Field Crops Research* 235, 18–26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2019.02.015>
- Kim, D.-G., Kirschbaum, M.U.F., Beedy, T.L., 2016. Carbon sequestration and net emissions of CH₄ and N₂O under agroforestry: Synthesizing available data and suggestions for future studies. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 226, 65–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2016.04.011>
- Kuyah, S., Öborn, I., Jonsson, M., Dahlin, A.S., Barrios, E., Muthuri, C., Malmer, A., Nyaga, J., Magaju, C., Namirembe, S., Nyberg, Y., Sinclair, F.L., 2016. Trees in agricultural landscapes enhance provision of ecosystem services in Sub-Saharan Africa. *International Journal of Biodiversity Science, Ecosystem Services & Management* 12, 255–273. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21513732.2016.1214178>
- Lillesø, J.-P. B., van Breugel, P., Kindt, R., Bingham, M., Sebsebe Demissew, Dudley, C., Friis, I., Gachathi, F., Kalema, J., Mbago, F., Minani, V., Moshi, H.N., Mulumba, J., Namaganda, M., Ndangalasi, H.J., Ruffo, C.K., Jamnadass, R. and Graudal, L., 2011. Potential natural vegetation of eastern Africa. Volume 1: The Atlas. . Forest & Landscape Working Paper 61-2011.
- Marenya, P.P., Barrett, C.B., 2007. Household-level determinants of adoption of improved natural resources management practices among smallholder farmers in western Kenya. *Food Policy* 32, 515–536. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2006.10.002>
- Margenot, A.J., Pulleman, M.M., Sommer, R., Paul, B.K., Parikh, S.J., Jackson, L.E., Fonte, S.J., 2017. Biochemical proxies indicate differences in soil C cycling induced by long-term tillage and residue management in a tropical agroecosystem. *Plant Soil* 420, 315–329. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-017-3401-z>
- Marshall, M., Norton-Griffiths, M., Herr, H., Lamprey, R., Sheffield, J., Vagen, T., Okotto-Okotto, J., 2017. Continuous and consistent land use/cover change estimates using socio-ecological data. *Earth System Dynamics* 8, 55–73. <https://doi.org/10.5194/esd-8-55-2017>

- Mucheru-Muna, M.W., Ada, M.A., Mugwe, J.N., Mairura, F.S., Mugi-Ngenga, E., Zingore, S., Mutegi, J.K., 2021. Socio-economic predictors, soil fertility knowledge domains and strategies for sustainable maize intensification in Embu County, Kenya. *Heliyon* 7, e06345. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e06345>
- Mugwe, J., Mugendi, D., Mucheru-Muna, M., Merckx, R., Chianu, J., Vanlauwe, B., 2009. DETERMINANTS OF THE DECISION TO ADOPT INTEGRATED SOIL FERTILITY MANAGEMENT PRACTICES BY SMALLHOLDER FARMERS IN THE CENTRAL HIGHLANDS OF KENYA. *Experimental Agriculture* 45, 61–75. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0014479708007072>
- Müller, D., Mburu, J., 2009. Forecasting hotspots of forest clearing in Kakamega Forest, Western Kenya. *Forest Ecology and Management* 257, 968–977. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2008.10.032>
- Muriithi, S., Kenyon, W., 2002. Conservation of biodiversity in the Arabuko Sokoke Forest, Kenya. *Biodiversity and Conservation* 11, 1437–1450. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1016234224819>
- Okeyo, J.M., Norton, J., Koala, S., Waswa, B., Kihara, J., Bationo, A., Okeyo, J.M., Norton, J., Koala, S., Waswa, B., Kihara, J., Bationo, A., 2016. Impact of reduced tillage and crop residue management on soil properties and crop yields in a long-term trial in western Kenya. *Soil Res.* 54, 719–729. <https://doi.org/10.1071/SR15074>
- Ongeri, D., Kenduiywo, B.K., 2020. BURNT AREA DETECTION USING MEDIUM RESOLUTION SENTINEL 2 AND LANDSAT 8 SATELLITES, in: *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*. Presented at the XXIV ISPRS Congress, Commission V and Youth Forum (Volume XLIII-B5-2020) - 2020 edition, Copernicus GmbH, pp. 131–137. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLIII-B5-2020-131-2020>
- Ouédraogo, M., Houessionon, P., Zougmore, R.B., Partey, S.T., 2019. Uptake of Climate-Smart Agricultural Technologies and Practices: Actual and Potential Adoption Rates in the Climate-Smart Village Site of Mali. *Sustainability* 11, 4710. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11174710>
- Palm, C., Blanco-Canqui, H., DeClerck, F., Gatere, L., Grace, P., 2014. Conservation agriculture and ecosystem services: An overview. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment, Evaluating conservation agriculture for small-scale farmers in Sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia* 187, 87–105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2013.10.010>
- Palm, C.A., Giller, K.E., Mafongoya, P.L., Swift, M.J., 2001. Management of organic matter in the tropics: Translating theory into practice. *Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems* 61, 63–75. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1013318210809>
- Poletti, C., Dioszegi, G., Nyongesa, K.W., Vacik, H., Barbujani, M., Kigomo, J.N., 2019. Characterization of Forest Fires to Support Monitoring and Management of Mount Kenya Forest. *mred* 39, R1–R12. <https://doi.org/10.1659/MRD-JOURNAL-D-18-00104.1>

- Prasad, J.V.N.S., Rao, Ch.S., Srinivas, K., Jyothi, Ch.N., Venkateswarlu, B., Ramachandrapa, B.K., Dhanapal, G.N., Ravichandra, K., Mishra, P.K., 2016. Effect of ten years of reduced tillage and recycling of organic matter on crop yields, soil organic carbon and its fractions in Alfisols of semi arid tropics of southern India. *Soil and Tillage Research* 156, 131–139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2015.10.013>
- Pulhin, J.M., Larson, A.M., Pacheco, P., 2012. Regulations as Barriers to Community Benefits in Tenure Reform, in: *Forests for People: Community Rights and Forest Tenure Reform*. Earthscan, London, UK, pp. 155–175. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781849774765-18>
- Rosenstock, T., Tully, K., Arias-Navarro, C., Neufeldt, H., Butterbach-Bahl, K., Verchot, L., 2014. Agroforestry with N₂-fixing trees: sustainable development's friend or foe? *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability, Sustainability challenges* 6, 15–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2013.09.001>
- Rosenstock, T.S., Dawson, I.K., Aynekulu, E., Chomba, S., Degrande, A., Fornace, K., Jamnadass, R., Kimaro, A., Kindt, R., Lamanna, C., Malesu, M., Mausch, K., McMullin, S., Murage, P., Namoi, N., Njenga, M., Nyoka, I., Paez Valencia, A.M., Sola, P., Shepherd, K., Steward, P., 2019a. A Planetary Health Perspective on Agroforestry in Sub-Saharan Africa. *One Earth* 1, 330–344. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2019.10.017>
- Rosenstock, T.S., Wilkes, A., Jallo, C., Namoi, N., Bulusu, M., Suber, M., Mboi, D., Mulia, R., Simelton, E., Richards, M., Gurwick, N., Wollenberg, E., 2019b. Making trees count: Measurement and reporting of agroforestry in UNFCCC national communications of non-Annex I countries. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 284, 106569. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2019.106569>
- Roser, M., Ritchie, H., Ortiz-Ospina, E., 2013. World Population Growth. *Our World in Data*.
- Running, S.W., Nemani, R.R., Heinsch, F.A., Zhao, M., Reeves, M., Hashimoto, H., 2004. A Continuous Satellite-Derived Measure of Global Terrestrial Primary Production. *BioScience* 54, 547–560. [https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568\(2004\)054\[0547:ACSMOG\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568(2004)054[0547:ACSMOG]2.0.CO;2)
- Segnini, A., Posadas, A., da Silva, W.T.L., Milori, D.M.B.P., Gavilan, C., Claessens, L., Quiroz, R., 2019. Quantifying soil carbon stocks and humification through spectroscopic methods: A scoping assessment in EMBU-Kenya. *Journal of Environmental Management* 234, 476–483. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2018.12.108>
- Sheppard, J.P., Bohn Reckziegel, R., Borrass, L., Chirwa, P.W., Cuaranhua, C.J., Hassler, S.K., Hoffmeister, S., Kestel, F., Maier, R., Mälicke, M., Morhart, C., Ndlovu, N.P., Veste, M., Funk, R., Lang, F., Seifert, T., du Toit, B., Kahle, H.-P., 2020. Agroforestry: An Appropriate and Sustainable Response to a Changing Climate in Southern Africa? *Sustainability* 12, 6796. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12176796>
- Six, J., Elliott, E.T., Paustian, K., 1999. Aggregate and Soil Organic Matter Dynamics under Conventional and No-Tillage Systems. *Soil Science Society of America Journal* 63, 1350–1358. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj1999.6351350x>

- Six, J., Feller, C., Denef, K., Ogle, S.M., Sa, J.C. de M., Albrecht, A., 2002. Soil organic matter, biota and aggregation in temperate and tropical soils - Effects of no-tillage. *Agronomie* 22, 755–775. <https://doi.org/10.1051/agro:2002043>
- Six, J., Ogle, S.M., Breidt, F.J., Conant, R.T., Mosier, A.R., Paustian, K., 2004. The potential to mitigate global warming with no-tillage management is only realized when practised in the long term. *Global Change Biology* 10, 155–160. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1529-8817.2003.00730.x>
- Sommer, R., Mukalama, J., Kihara, J., Koala, S., Winowiecki, L., Bossio, D., 2016. Nitrogen dynamics and nitrous oxide emissions in a long-term trial on integrated soil fertility management in Western Kenya. *Nutr Cycl Agroecosyst* 105, 229–248. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10705-015-9693-6>
- Sommer, R., Paul, B.K., Mukalama, J., Kihara, J., 2018. Reducing losses but failing to sequester carbon in soils – the case of Conservation Agriculture and Integrated Soil Fertility Management in the humid tropical agro-ecosystem of Western Kenya. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 254, 82–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2017.11.004>
- Tessema, B., Sommer, R., Piikki, K., Söderström, M., Namirembe, S., Notenbaert, A., Tamene, L., Nyawira, S., Paul, B., 2020. Potential for soil organic carbon sequestration in grasslands in East African countries: A review. *Grassland Science* 66, 135–144. <https://doi.org/10.1111/grs.12267>
- Torres, A.B., Marchant, R., Lovett, J.C., Smart, J.C.R., Tipper, R., 2010. Analysis of the carbon sequestration costs of afforestation and reforestation agroforestry practices and the use of cost curves to evaluate their potential for implementation of climate change mitigation. *Ecological Economics* 69, 469–477. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2009.09.007>
- United Nations, 2019. World Population Prospects - Population Division - United Nations [WWW Document]. URL <https://population.un.org/wpp/Graphs/Probabilistic/POP/TOT/404> (accessed 2.16.21).
- van Ittersum, M.K., Cassman, K.G., Grassini, P., Wolf, J., Tittonell, P., Hochman, Z., 2013. Yield gap analysis with local to global relevance—A review. *Field Crops Research, Crop Yield Gap Analysis – Rationale, Methods and Applications* 143, 4–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2012.09.009>
- Vanlauwe, B., Bationo, A., Chianu, J., Giller, K.E., Merckx, R., Mokwunye, U., Ohiokpehai, O., Pypers, P., Tabo, R., Shepherd, K.D., Smaling, E.M.A., Woomer, P.L., Sanginga, N., 2010. Integrated Soil Fertility Management: Operational Definition and Consequences for Implementation and Dissemination. *Outlook Agric* 39, 17–24. <https://doi.org/10.5367/000000010791169998>
- Vanlauwe, B., Descheemaeker, K., Giller, K.E., Huising, J., Merckx, R., Nziguheba, G., Wendt, J., Zingore, S., 2015. Integrated soil fertility management in sub-Saharan Africa: unravelling local adaptation. *SOIL* 1, 491–508. <https://doi.org/10.5194/soil-1-491-2015>

- Vanlauwe, B., Kihara, J., Chivenge, P., Pypers, P., Coe, R., Six, J., 2011. Agronomic use efficiency of N fertilizer in maize-based systems in sub-Saharan Africa within the context of integrated soil fertility management. *Plant Soil* 339, 35–50. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-010-0462-7>
- Wawire, A.W., Csorba, Á., Kovács, E., Mairura, F.S., Tóth, J.A., Michéli, E., 2021a. Comparing farmers' soil fertility knowledge systems and scientific assessment in Upper Eastern Kenya. *Geoderma* 396, 115090. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2021.115090>
- Wawire, A.W., Csorba, Á., Tóth, J.A., Michéli, E., Szalai, M., Mutuma, E., Kovács, E., 2021b. Soil fertility management among smallholder farmers in Mount Kenya East region. *Heliyon* 7, e06488. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e06488>
- Wilson, M.H., Lovell, S.T., 2016. Agroforestry—The Next Step in Sustainable and Resilient Agriculture. *Sustainability* 8, 574. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su8060574>
- Wolz, K.J., Branham, B.E., DeLucia, E.H., 2018. Reduced nitrogen losses after conversion of row crop agriculture to alley cropping with mixed fruit and nut trees. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 258, 172–181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2018.02.024>
- World-Bank, 2021a. Prevalence of severe food insecurity in the population (%) - Kenya, World, Sub-Saharan Africa, Malawi | Data [WWW Document]. URL <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SN.ITK.SVFI.ZS?locations=KE-1W-ZG-MW> (accessed 4.21.21).
- World-Bank, 2021b. Forest area (% of land area) - Kenya | Data [WWW Document]. URL <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/AG.LND.FRST.ZS?locations=KE> (accessed 2.11.21).
- World-Bank, 2021c. Fertilizer consumption (kilograms per hectare of arable land) - Sub-Saharan Africa, World | Data [WWW Document]. URL <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/AG.CON.FERT.ZS?locations=ZG-1W> (accessed 12.17.21).
- World-Bank, 2021d. CO2 emissions (metric tons per capita) - Kenya, European Union | Data [WWW Document]. URL <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/EN.ATM.CO2E.PC?locations=KE-EU> (accessed 2.15.21).
- World-Bank, 2021e. Cereal yield (kg per hectare) - Kenya | Data [WWW Document]. URL <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/AG.YLD.CREL.KG?locations=KE-1W> (accessed 4.20.21).
- World-Bank, 2021f. Arable land (% of land area) - Kenya | Data [WWW Document]. URL <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/AG.LND.ARBL.ZS?locations=KE> (accessed 2.11.21).
- World-Bank, 2020. State and Trends of Carbon Pricing 2020. World Bank, Washington, DC.
- Xiao, S.-S., Ye, Y.-Y., Xiao, D., Chen, W.-R., Zhang, W., Wang, K.-L., 2019. Effects of tillage on soil N availability, aggregate size, and microbial biomass in a subtropical karst region. *Soil and Tillage Research* 192, 187–195. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2019.05.006>

Yadav, S.K., Soni, R., 2019. Integrated Soil Fertility Management, in: Panpatte, D.G., Jhala, Y.K. (Eds.), Soil Fertility Management for Sustainable Development. Springer, Singapore, pp. 71–80.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-5904-0_5

LANDMARC

SCALING LAND-BASED MITIGATION SOLUTIONS IN VENEZUELA

LAND-BASED MITIGATION NARRATIVES

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2. Introduction

Venezuela is one of 17 megadiverse countries worldwide. It comprises four biogeographic regions: Amazonian, Andean, Caribbean, and Guiana (Figure 1), and it ranks fourth in amphibian diversity, sixth in bird diversity, eighth in mammal and vascular plant diversity, and ninth in reptile diversity. The number of dicotyledonous plant species is estimated to be half the world total, with 14,292 species of angiosperms and an estimated 100,000 species of Coleoptera. Levels of endemism are high, particularly in plants, birds, mammals, and invertebrates (INPARQUES, 2007; FAO, 2020).

This variety of bioregions also involves a high diversity of ecosystems, which present a great variety of warm tropical climates in lowland areas, to temperate and cold in altitudinal floors that reach 5000 m, with very high to very low average annual rainfall (350 mm to > 6000 mm), diverse geological types (from the oldest >3000 million years in the Guiana region to active sedimentary plains such as the Llanos western) and topographies, with mountain ranges (Andean Cordillera and Cordillera de la Costa), with sea fronts (Caribbean Sea), and proximity to Ecuador (Amazon Basin). Among the dominant vegetation types, Venezuela possesses 46.2 million hectares of forest (51% of total country land cover), with tropical rainforests having the highest coverage (> 25,000,000 ha).

Figure 1. Vegetation map of Venezuela (adapted from Huber and Alarcón, 1988).

In this sense, climate change mitigation policies in the country have focused on the conservation and sustainable management of forests to protect carbon sinks and increase their capture of CO₂ (Bolivarian Republic of Venezuela, 2017a; FAO, 2020). However, various threats and uses expose these

ecosystems to deforestation. It is important to mention that in Venezuela, protected areas are inhabited, so it represents a real challenge to develop policies that guarantee the sustainability of local communities and, at the same time, the conservation of natural ecosystems.

In this report, we will address the analysis of LMTs in three of the most relevant bioregions of the country:

- 1) Integrated fire management in the tropical humid forest of Amazon Basin (see section 3.2)
- 2) Agroforestry of arid and semiarid lands (very dry and xerophytic forests) (see section 3.3)
- 3) Agroforestry in dry forest lands (see section 3.4)

The first LMT corresponds to integrated fire management with an intercultural vision, in the tropical humid forest of Amazon basin. This LMT is based on Indigenous traditional knowledge of fire, as a promising LMT as a strategy for mitigating GHG emissions and the effective reduction of wildfires both in these ecosystems, as well as the challenges and advances to bring this experience to the national level. It is based on the extensive experience of the working group and addresses the analysis of fire management strategies based mainly on ancient Indigenous knowledge and traditional practices north of the Amazon region, in the heart of the Guianese shield. The initial experiences were focused on Canaima National Park, but within the framework of the LANDMARC Project, a national escalation is being carried out to implement policies that are based on fire prevention and fire management, rather than on the suppression and fighting of fires, which have been the dominant policies historically in the country and at the regional level in Latin America. The effective implementation of this LMT acquires great particular relevance due to the growing number of fires that occur and affect the natural areas of the country (Fire Management Report, 2020; Luziola et al., 2020; Finner and Mamani, 2022), degrading and reducing the carbon stock of natural systems (especially the most vulnerable such as tropical rainforests) with a strong impact on local populations, their productive activities, as well as the conservation and management of protected areas.

The second case we addressed is agroforestry in arid and semiarid lands. Although this region, which is located along the northern Caribbean coastline and islands (Figure 1), covers an area significantly smaller than that of tropical humid forests (4,102,300 ha that represents 4.5% of the national territory; Matteucci, 1986), it concentrates a third of Venezuela's population and are under high urbanization, agricultural, and industrial pressures. Additionally, erosion of these lands is a serious environmental problem and is considered the most determining factor in the degradation of productive soils. According to future scenarios of seasonal dryness (Medina et al., 2016), by 2050 semiarid lands will expand about 106,000 Km² into regions that currently belong to subhumid provinces, representing 10.08% of the national territory. Considering this situation, in this report we present and analyse the potential of LMT, of several projects of mixed agroforestry systems that mimic natural ecosystems and have been developed by public agencies, academics, and NGO's working closely with local farmers, goat peasants and aloe or agave (i.e., cocuy, a tequila – like beverage) producers, with very promising results (Díaz, 2001; Miriam Díaz, pers. comm.).

Finally, we included the analysis of agroforestry in dry forest lands. Dry forest is the second most important ecosystem in the country with respect to extension and carbon accumulation capacity (Table 1). They are mainly localised in the Eastern, Central and Western Region of the "Llanos Venezolanos" (figure 1). The progress of physical and biological environmental degradation is highly dangerous, even leading to the disappearance of almost 70 % of the dry tropical forests.

Table 1. Forest biomass and potential of C capture (Source: prepared by the authors)

No.	Forest type	Area (ha)	Aboveground biomass (Tn/ha) ⁽¹⁾	Carbon Stock Tn C/ha ⁽¹⁾	Potential of C capture (Tn CO ₂ /ha) ⁽²⁾
1	Tropical xerophytic forest	933,300 ^(2,3)	24	12	44.0 ^(2,3)
2	Very dry tropical forest	2,663,000 ^(2,3)	75	37.5	137.6 ^(2,3)
3	Tropical dry forest	15,860,600	162	81	297.3
4	Humid tropical forest (evergreen)	25,058,000	277.2	138.6	508.7
5	Premontane Humid Forest	1,202,000	240	120	440.4
6	Lower montane humid forest	369,000	180	90	330.3
7	Montane Cloud Forest	18,000	180	90	330.3
8	Subalpine Forest	127,000	30	15	55.1

¹ FAO, 2020; ² Veillon, 1985; ³ Díaz, 2021

Dry forests have been disappearing rapidly due to logging associated with encroachment, burning and destruction for agricultural and livestock purposes. It is estimated that laminar erosion has caused the loss of more than 40% of the region's arable soils and the extinction of tree and wildlife species (Pacheco-Angulo and Silva, 2020). Agroforestry systems (AFS), which include silvopastoral systems (SPS), are considered as key alternatives in the current trend to promote the transformation of conventional agriculture into "climate-smart agriculture". This concept integrates the three dimensions of sustainable development (economic, social and environmental), jointly addressing food security and climate challenges (Montagnini 2015). In this report we present interesting initiatives with a great potential for scaling this LMT to other areas characterized by dry forests.

In summary this report will provide new information obtained from the literature review and testimonies gathering in interviews with relevant experts from a selected and representative LMTs of these three selected Venezuelan systems, considering the criteria and rationale used in the previous report (see D2.1 report). This report's present aim was to provide NETP quality narrative of these selected LMT's and analyse the techniques for further studies (through the help of model simulations)

to scale up at local, regional, national, and global levels and meet the objectives of the LANDMARC project.

2.1. Integrated fire management

2.1.1. Introduction

Fire occurs naturally on terrestrial ecosystems from all continents of our planet, except on areas which lack vegetation such as deserts or those permanently covered by snow in Polar Regions (Bowman *et al.*, 2011; Bilbao *et al.* 2020; FIRMS, 2021). The area affected by fires annually ranges between 300 and 450 Mha with maximums of 600 Mha (GFMC, 2019; IUFRO, 2018), with an average of 341 Mha (1997-2011), equivalent to 2.6 of the entire global land area (Chatenoux & Peduzzi, 2013; van Lierop *et al.*, 2015; Giglio *et al.*, 2018). Fire is a landscape modelling agent that promotes fire-dependent ecosystems such as savannas and pine forests with fire-adapted plant species, while fire-sensitive vegetation such as tropical humid forests, have evolved in the absence of fire.

According to the recent IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (IPCC, 2021) many regions of the planet show, with a high level of confidence, a significant rise of "fire-prone weather" conditions: such as higher temperatures, extended dry seasons and increased heat waves, all of which favor wildfire occurrence and propagation, and greenhouse gas emissions. All fires, especially large wildfires (defined as uncontrolled fire in combustible vegetation that occurs in the countryside), have a significant impact on the production of carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gases (CH₄ and N₂O) that contribute to climate change (Randerson *et al.*, 2012). From 1997 to 2016, biomass burning from different ecosystems produced CO₂ e emissions (2.2 10¹⁵ g C y⁻¹), equivalent to 23% of global fossil-fuel_{CO₂} e emissions in 2014 (FAO, 2014; Boden *et al.*, 2015; Van der Werf *et al.*, 2017). Approximately 84% of global carbon emissions originate in the tropics, while 62% originate from tropical savannas, underlining the importance of fire as a driver of biogeochemical cycles and ecosystem processes in tropical ecosystems, particularly in savanna areas (Van der Werf *et al.*, 2017). NASA (2010) predicts that wildfire could increase by as much as 35% by 2100 and that most of these increases will take place in these fire dependent landscapes. Put the UNEP.

At present and according to Venezuela's second national communication (República Bolivariana de Venezuela, 2017a), wildfires and biomass burning during the year 2010 represented a critical factor in the C sink conversion of the AFOLU (acronym for Agriculture, Forestry and Land Use) sector to a source of emissions (Figure 1). Thus, the aggregate sources of CO₂ emissions and sources of emissions other than CO₂ on land emitted 0.5 Mt CO₂, 0.3 Mt CH₄ and 0.035 Mt N₂O, reaching an equivalent of 18 Mt CO₂eq. The burning of biomass contributed just over half of this emission (54%), either by burning forests (89%), savannas (9%) or crops (2%). Furthermore, considering that Venezuela has registered the highest historical fire incidence record during the last decade (Bilbao *et al.* 2020; Lizundia-Loiola *et al.* 2020; Finner and Manuni, 2022; Figure 2 and Figure 3), implementing a new paradigm concerning fire management as a mitigation strategy in Venezuela is needed.

Figure 2. Emissions from the sub-sector aggregate sources of CO₂ emissions and AFOLU-sources of non-CO₂ emissions (adapted from República Bolivariana de Venezuela, 2017a).

Figure 3. Area affected by fire (ha) estimated by remote sensors nationwide during the periods of drought (January-May) of the years 2018-2020 in Venezuela.

Historically, wildfire control around the world relies heavily on reactive practices of suppression and fire-fighting expert techniques such as fire brigades, the use of especial technical aerial and terrestrial support (e.g., helicopters and trucks), besides satellite monitoring. For instance, USA invest five billion dollars annually in fire-fighting control activities, equipment, and tools. However, wildfires and mega-fires incidence keeps on rising, as the mega-fire event in California during 2020 demonstrated. Besides their high costs, major criticisms of fire suppression policies indicate that they are not effective at reducing area burnt statistics, and that they do not consider the ecological and cultural role of fire in many ecosystems of the world (Eloy *et al.*, 2019, Mistry *et al.*, 2019, Ponce *et al.*, 2020; Bilbao *et al.*, 2020; Durigan, 2020). Despite these criticisms, most countries still rely on 'zero-fire' policies to ban and control virtually any fire type. These policies stigmatize all kinds of fire, promote ecological

imbalances in zones with fire-adapted vegetation and create social conflicts with Indigenous peoples and local communities that depend on controlled burnings for their subsistence activities.

On the contrary, evidence has been provided on the benefits of Indigenous fire usage practices, not only for daily livelihood of Indigenous peoples, but also in reducing the risk of large fires, maintaining the reservoirs of carbon in soil and vegetation, and increasing the diversity of ecosystems (Crisostomo et al., 2015; Walter et al., 2021). There are positive experiences, such as the one presented in this report, that have tried to incorporate Indigenous fire management practices and knowledge in their territory in a new paradigm of fire management, called Integral Fire Management (IFM), which incorporates and recognizes the positive aspects of fire, as well as the knowledge of fire ecology and the cultural practices of local populations.

There are several definitions of the concept of integrated fire management, and especially of its application. The origin of the definition, Integrated Fire Management policy, comes from Myers (2006) who points out the importance of promoting inter-institutional coordination to reduce damages caused by wildfires and restoring the importance of fire as an ecological and cultural agent. This approach includes the three components of fire management: prevention, control, use of fire; along with its ecological character, as well as the socioeconomic and cultural needs of its use and integration of knowledge and capacities of institutions and fire managers, scientists, and local communities. His book "Living with fire" presents integrated fire management (IFM) as a management approach that links ecological, socio-economic, and technical aspects of fire in a holistic manner to address social and conservation problems and issues resulting from burning of to achieve goals of ecosystem sustainability as well as human livelihoods in fire-prone environments by integrating multiple scales - from local needs to global pacts on gas emissions, for example. However, usually researchers, the communities and environmental technicians are often using the term IFM, to refer exclusively to the implementation of prescribed burns. Thus, Barradas and Ribeiro (2021) consider the importance to be aware the intercultural approach, as suggested by Bilbao et al. (2019), for the integrated fire management, avoiding the regress to a technocratic understanding of fire management, disconnected from the ecological and social components.

In this sense, integrated fire management (MIF) with an intercultural vision, presents an important potential as LMT, which will be discussed and updated in this section, including the experiences at the local level in the Canaima National Park (CNP) in Venezuela, and the escalation process at the national level, which occurred in recent years.

Controlled application of fire by Indigenous people takes into account the place, time of the year, atmospheric conditions, as well as frequency, extension, duration and intensity of the burnings, for social, cultural and economic reasons (i.e. agricultural and cattle raising, ashes and charcoal application to improve soil fertility, boost grasses and pasture re-sprout, among others) (Mistry et al., 2005; Bilbao et al., 2010; Ziegler et al., 2011; Huffman, 2013; Welch, 2014; Trauernicht et al., 2015, Archibald, 2016; Eloy et al., 2018; Nikolakis & Roberts, 2020).

Integrated Fire Management based on Indigenous fire management practices as a LMT has the potential to reduce overall emissions from massive wildfires. Since controlled burnings used by Indigenous people in their territories are of low intensity and limited extension, and consider local ecological conditions, they prevent the occurrence of large wildfires. Alike Indigenous burnings, *prescribed burnings* are also controlled fire treatments applied by firefighters under the IFM policies, for the reduction of fuel material to prevent the occurrence and reduce the severity and extension of wildfires.

Fire also has been used from prehistorical times by South American Indigenous communities. The main uses are as fertilising agents for agricultural purposes and the protection of forests by reducing combustible accumulation material and thus preventing the spread of fire and its conversion into a wildfire. Thus, fire has a vital role in soil preparation before crop planting in shifting cultivation practices in small patches inside forests. The burning of plant material is required to release nutrients contained in the biomass. It increases soil fertility, reducing soil acidity (pH) and aluminium toxicity of the characteristic ancient and impoverished and washed tropical soils. These are very controlled burns that the Indigenous do against the wind (backfires) in the early morning hours, preventing the fire from spreading. Very different from uncontrolled and damaging wildfires that spread without control.

These Indigenous traditional practices were disrupted after Europeans arrived in South America. Indigenous acculturation processes and implementation of fire suppression policies lead to changes in fire practices, which currently are mainly used for deforestation, waste burning or without a functional purpose. This situation, combined with increasing drought periods promoted by climate change, has prompted mega-fires (defined as wildfires of great severity impossible to control with existing firefighting mechanisms) across the region.

2.1.2. *Experiences of the CNP*

In 1999 a long-term fire experiment was established to study the meteorological and fuel drivers of fire behaviour and its impact on vegetation, soil and atmosphere in a savanna – tropical humid forest gradient in Gran Sabana, Canaima National Park (CNP, 30.000 km²) (Fig. 2, Bilbao et al. 2009, Bilbao et al. 2010). Canaima National Park (CNP) is a region of great value due both to its biological and cultural uniqueness and its strategic importance, both politically and economically. The Park is a protected area located in the south-east of the country, in northern Amazonia, declared a World Heritage Site in 1994 by UNESCO because of its high biodiversity and endemism. Although humid tropical forest represents the dominant ecosystem in the CNP, it also contains a region characterised by a mosaic of savanna and forest ecosystems (Fig. 3) called the Gran Sabana (Huber 1990; Huber and Febres 2000; Huber 2006; Delgado et al. 2009). It also represents a strategic area because it includes the upper basin of the Caroní River. This hydrological source provides more than 70% of the country's energy.

Figure 4. Gran Sabana and Canaima National Park location.

The use of fire by the Pemón Indigenous communities, natural inhabitants of the park, has been the hydroelectric company's concern because it could reduce the forest cover and affect the region's hydrological regime. Park administrators (INPARQUES) have been shared this concern, as the presence of "fire" was incompatible with the Park's conservation practices. In consequence, the institutional response was the creation, in 1981, of the Control of Wildfire Programme (PCIV), implemented by the Initial Attack Brigade Carlos Todd of CORPOELEC (the regional hydroelectricity company) to prevent, detect and fight wildfires in order to protect the headwaters of the Caroní. 21 000 km² of this highly protected area is located in the Gran Sabana and includes the eastern sector of Canaima National Park (Gómez et al. 2000, Fig. 2). However, despite carrying out expensive and enormous fire suppression efforts, on average, only 13% of total fires are combated owing to the high number of fires over a large area (EDELCA-CORPOELEC. 2008).

Under this context, the results of the long-term fire experiment were critical to providing information and knowledge not only about fire ecology but also tools to inform the park administrators to make decisions about more appropriate policies.

The main discovery of this study was the characterisation of the ecological basis of the PMB (patch-mosaic burning technique). This technique, used by the Pemón for millennia, produces a savanna landscape in different stages of succession, which acts as natural firebreaks when wildfires reach the border of a previous burned patch (Bilbao et al., 2010). This strategy promotes the reduction of catastrophic wildfires, particularly in the most vulnerable areas of ecotones and tropical humid forest edges (Fig. 2). At the same time, fire exclusion resulted in the risky accumulation of dead combustible material that can promote wildfires of considerable magnitude and extension (Bilbao et al., 2009; Bilbao et al., 2010). The significance of this last result is that it promoted the reviewing of fire policies based only on fire suppression by firefighter bodies implemented in the CNP for decades.

Figure 5. Experimental burns initiated by Indigenous Pemón firefighters (Photography by Bibiana Bilbao); b) Aerial view of the long-term fire collaborative long-term experiment plots (Photography by Rafael Salas); c) and d) Different views of Indigenous Patch mosaic burnings (PMB) (Photography by Ruth Salazar-Gascón).

Several initiatives, which evolved as a result of several participatory action-research projects coordinated by academics, and supported by firefighters, public officials (park administrators) and the inclusion of Pemón Indigenous communities, a paradigm change was finally enhanced to a more integrated fire management in CNP where Indigenous traditional practices of fire management were included (Bilbao et al. 2019; Mistry et al. 2019; Bilbao et al. 2020, Bilbao et al. 2021, Bilbao et al. 2022).

This experience was considered the case study (CS6) of the LANDMARC project to explore the LMT as NETP and to encompass the scaling up at the national level.

3. Policy context

In Venezuela, the Environmental Criminal Law enacted in 1992 and reformed in 2012 contains measures that prohibit fire and punish those who use fire in protected areas and limit the management by or inclusion of traditional practices of local populations (Government of Venezuela 2012). This Environmental Law respond to the fact that historically, Venezuela has had a national fire suppression policy based on the control and combat of all types of fires. This type of action has been extended to all national territory despite the great diversity of vegetation and climates along with the country. In 2013, the Forest National Law was enacted, creating the National System of Protection against Forest Wildfires (Chapter III), which operates under the Ministry's supervision with competence in environmental matters. It guides or regulates the creation of "unified commands" that operate at the national, regional, and local levels. Fires, in general, are considered in the forestry law as environmental risks or threats that must be addressed in terms of prevention, extinction and control of forest fires and the evaluation and recovery of areas affected by these events.

Likewise, within the framework of the same law, Chapter IV of Article 62 is dedicated to conserving the forest heritage by creating areas under a special administration regime (ABRAE). Thus, ABRAE is defined as those areas subject to special regulations destined for the conservation of ecosystems and the integral protection of natural resources according to their characteristics or location. Example of that is protective areas (PA), national parks, natural monuments, and biosphere reserves. Thus, particular legislation has been applied to protect natural areas (ABRAE zones) under the jurisdiction of INPARQUES (acronym in Spanish for Instituto Nacional de Parques) the highest administrative authority in charge of their management and conservation. INPARQUES, created in 1978, is an autonomous body ascribed to the Ministry of Power of the People for Eco-socialism (formerly Ministry of Power of the People for the Environment). In 1978, a Programme for Prevention and Protection Against Forests Fires was created to impart knowledge, experience, and skills for training forest rangers. In 2001, the Law of Fire-Fighters and Civil Emergency Management was enacted, promoting, some years later, the graduation of the first professional forest firefighters in the country. This law also gave rise to the Unified National Command against Forest Fires to coordinate the different entities—MINEA, INPARQUES, the Bolivarian National Guard and Civil Protection, regional and local bodies—during the dry season and mitigate fires in the country. Thus, the environmental authorities oversee the prevention and control of fires.

On the other hand, Venezuela has one of the most progressive Indigenous rights regimes in South America. For example, it officially recognizes, within its constitution, Indigenous peoples' rights to maintain their own production practices and protects the collective intellectual property of knowledge, technologies, and innovations (Constitución de la República Bolivariana de Venezuela, 1999). In addition, specific legislation focusing on Indigenous communities, such as the Organic Law of Indigenous Peoples and Communities (República Bolivariana de Venezuela, 2005), has also strengthened Indigenous rights to genetic resources and ancestral knowledge. However, despite the

progressive constitution and regulations and the relative protection of Indigenous rights in national parks, the use of fire, in legal terms, has been heavily restricted and combated (Art. 65, Ley Penal del Ambiente, República Bolivariana de Venezuela. 2012).

Mainly within the framework of this body of laws protecting Indigenous rights and autonomy granted by the Forest National Law to INPARQUES, which was able to advance with initiatives coordinated by the Simón Bolívar University, financed by the Ministry of Science and Technology and supported by national and regional public development institutions, to the adoption of integrated and participatory fire management principles by the INPARQUES forest fire firefighters. Thus, the inclusion of Pemón Indigenous communities, firefighters, public officials, government institutional actors and academics in field research and joint experimentation on fire behaviour, as well as the debate and dialogue on socio-ecological issues of the CNP, led to the development of articulated knowledge and actions resulting in the foundation of a new paradigm of integrated fire management (IFM) and strategies for climate change mitigation and adaptation.

Since 2015, with the support and collaboration of the British Academy, Royal Holloway University and COBRA Collective, these activities and experiences were consolidated and spread to Brazil and Guyana north Amazonian countries. These activities resulted in the creation of the "Intercultural and Participatory Fire Management Network", whose fundamental principle is that "Indigenous fire management should be included in the management of territories in which Indigenous peoples live and develop their way of life, using ancestral, traditional and adaptive Indigenous knowledge of fire in conjunction with scientific/academic knowledge and the capacities of the institutions" (Bilbao et al., 2019).

In 2018, as a result of the agreements reached, implementation began of an intercultural mechanism for IFM in the east of the park (Gran Sabana). These pioneering activities involved two-way training, with the Pemón providing training in patch mosaic burning and other Indigenous fire prevention techniques to park authorities and forest firefighters, while also receiving technical training.

In 2019, following a presidential initiative, forest fire brigades throughout the country were expanded to 10,000 personnel, with training for 3,400 male and female firefighters; 1,800 of them are currently progressing toward university degrees as higher technicians and graduates in fire science and fire safety. This in-service education and training include elements of IFM in a new operational philosophy for firefighters. They do not just intervene in fire control, but also work as local managers who facilitate intercultural dialogue and replace the fire exclusion model with community fire management.

In the framework of LANDMARC project, a permanent working group for integrated fire management in Venezuela was formed in 2021, including researchers and academics, and officials from environmental, territorial management, public safety and emergency response agencies. They are committed to promoting the methodological development of IFM with an intercultural vision and disseminating this approach at the national level through webinars and workshops. The park's forest

fire firefighters have now incorporated lessons learned throughout this process in their training programmes, applying IFM techniques in protected areas throughout the country and exchanging experiences in integrated and participatory fire management with national and international experts.

These experiences are now being included in a new national system of IFM that seeks to define the terms of reference and search for financing for a new integrated fire management policy at the national level. The objective is to replace the existing one (previously mentioned on wildfire risk reduction in the current Forest Law). It is promoted by an intersectoral team that includes public officials representing the INPARQUES forest fire firefighters, the Forest Fire Protection Directorate of the Ministry of Eco-socialism, the Vice-Chair of IPCC Working Group II on impacts, adaptation and vulnerability, and academics who have promoted these actions (see Bilbao et al. 2022, for details).

3.1.1. Current land use and potential land-use competition

The burning of biomass associated with land deforestation and degradation as a mechanism for the expansion of the agricultural and livestock frontier, the burning of crop residues and the elimination of weeds have become a trigger for large wildfires and important sources of GHG emissions in Venezuela (ACFIMAN-SACC, 2018; República Bolivariana de Venezuela, 2017a). Furthermore, under current climate change scenarios, the impact of these activities is promoting the turning of AFOLU sinking capacity (due to CO₂ fixation) to a net GHG source considering aggregate sources and non-CO₂ land emissions sources (República Bolivariana de Venezuela, 2017a, see Sections 3.2 and 3.3 for details). Although the forest policy and legislation plan in Venezuela envisage reducing forest wildfires by 50% for 2030 throughout the territory, (República Bolivariana de Venezuela, 2017a; República Bolivariana de Venezuela, 2019), new paradigms regarding the formulation of more effective fire policies based on the prevention instead of the suppression and combat of fire are necessary (Figure 5). The CS6 case of LANDMARC includes a fire management proposal based on 20 years of ecological studies and joint work with the Pemón Indigenous communities about fire management practices for agriculture and forest protection in Canaima National Park. The integration of scientific, Indigenous, and technical knowledge gained in this experience provided the basis for an integrated fire management in Canaima National Park, and other implementations at national level.

Figure 5. Conceptual framework of CS6 describing the transition states of CNP ecosystems affected by wildfires (under policies of fire suppression) and their interaction with climate change, as well as the effect of LMT's measures and comprehensive IFM policies based on Indigenous land management.

IFM-LMT actions in Canaima National Park (CNP)

Despite the limitations imposed by COVID-19 and the deep economic crisis in the country, important progress could be made in the realization of an intercultural articulation mechanism for Integral Fire Management in the Eastern Sector of Canaima National Park, in the Gran Sabana sector (ca. 18,000 km², figure 4) through the organization, comprehensive training and equipping of Community Forest Brigades, made up of members of the Indigenous people in the Pemón communities: Kavanayén (Arekuna), Paraitepuy del Roraima (Taurepan) and Mapauri_(Taurepan) (Figure 4). These pioneering activities involved two-way training, with the Pemón providing training in patch mosaic burning and other Indigenous fire prevention techniques to park authorities and forest firefighters, while also receiving technical training.

In collaboration with other LANDMARC team members, diverse studies are being developed through EO and ALCES and DayCENT simulation models, to estimate the impact of the implementation of the LMT: Integrated fire management with an intercultural vision (based on Indigenous fire management techniques) and fire exclusion practices (based on fire suppression policies historically used by the Park's fire departments) (Figure 5). The EO studies are in the phase of data collection and identifying best places that describe the different types of management in the park and in the case of ALCES and DayCENT, are in the final stage of the definition of the landscape and carbon systems to be modelled (see Figure 6).

Figure 6. An overview of the landscape and carbon system that is being modelled by ALCES.

The abatement capacity of IFM-LMT in the CNP has not yet been estimated, but according to the revised literature, Indigenous fire management practices and prescribed burnings (based on effective EDS fire management) under the Integrated Fire Management could serve as a powerful natural climate solution to address climate change mitigation challenges facing countries within fire-prone savannas. The literature shows some evidence about the mitigation potential of this LMT in ecosystems similar to those of the Gran Sabana, in the CNP, particularly in the savannas of Australia and Brazil and several countries in Africa. These programmes have begun to be implemented at the local and regional levels during the last decades. The achievable abatement through savanna burning projects (based on Indigenous practices) reported in local experiences oscillates in the range of 0.12 Mt CO₂e y⁻¹ (37%) in Western Arnhem Land (3 million hectares) and 1.38 Mt CO₂e y⁻¹ across almost 40 million hectares of the savannas of northern Australia, to 0.29 Mt CO₂e y⁻¹ (130 T CO₂e y⁻¹ ha⁻¹) in Indigenous territories of the Cerrado Brazil.

National level

As part of the policies outlined in the plan for economic and social development at national level, Venezuela intends to implement a National Mitigation Plan to reduce its emissions by at least 20% by 2030 with respect to the baseline scenario (República Bolivariana de Venezuela, 2017a; República Bolivariana de Venezuela, 2019). From the mitigation options analysed for land-use change, it was established that the forest sector has a considerable potential for reducing CO₂ emissions (avoid or remove; Table 1) through the adoption of sustainable forest practices, especially by slowing the rate of forest loss and degradation. Due to the important extent of forest and other natural areas under different levels of protection (national parks, natural reserves), the maintenance of already existing biomass in natural forests should be the first priority to reduce the amount of carbon released to the

atmosphere and potentially has the lowest carbon unit cost (Table 2, Figure 1). A good proportion of this Venezuelan forest heritage consists of Areas under Special Administration Regime (ABRAE, Spanish acronym), which represent 47% of the total country area. Over 37% of the ABRAE are devoted to the protection and conservation of biological diversity; 18%, to forestry production; and the remaining 19% are dedicated to multiple forestry uses (MPPEHV, 2014). However, in 2017, the Venezuelan national government changed El Caura Forest Reserve's figure to El Caura National Park (República Bolivariana de Venezuela, 2017b). This produced an increase in the forest areas destined for conservation (from 24.3 to 29.3 million hectares) and a reduction of the forest areas destined for sustainable forest resources management (from 16.3 to 11.18 million hectares). These data reveal that Venezuela is among the ten top nations with greatest extension of forests conserved for soil and water protection (República Bolivariana de Venezuela, 2017a; FAO, 2020).

Considering the potentiality of the total area under ABRAE system and the Forest Fire Brigade of INPARQUES has extended the IFM training process and the experience acquired in Gran Sabana, Canaima National Park, to Waraira Repano National Park (La Costa Mountain Range, Capital Region, 81,800 ha), Mochima National Park (Northeast coastal Region, 94,769 ha), El Guácharo National Park (La Costa Mountain Range, Eastern Chain, 62,700 ha). The bases of this intercultural strategy include rural communities as central characters in the formulation and development of Local Fire Management Plans in the whole country.

These plans comprehend the inclusion of community members, their traditional knowledge and practices about fire management, and scientific criteria, as to achieve an effective reduction of the area affected by fires. This strategy involved the promotion, organisation, training and equipment of Community Forest Brigades that integrate voluntarily to the National Risk Management System. This strategy has focused on the reduction of the forest area affected by fire while contributing to strengthening the culture of self-protection in remote rural communities.

There are no data on estimates of the abatement capacity of IFM-LMT techniques being implemented at the national level. However, estimates of the potential technical abatement capacity at a regional level in Brazil and at more global level, showed very promising values that ranged between 2.96 Mt CO₂ e y⁻¹ (148 T CO₂ e y⁻¹ ha⁻¹) for the entire area of the Cerrado Brazil (2,000,000 km²) (Steil, 2020) and 89.3 Mt CO₂ e y⁻¹ at a more global level, considering 37 countries, including Africa, South America and Australia (Lipsett-Moore et al., 2018). If results similar to those of Brazil are obtained, the abatement capacity of this MFI-LMT could contribute to offset the emissions corresponding to the loss of 32,140 ha/year of humid forests with a long dry season (emission of 3.82 Mt of CO₂eq). Not to mention, the conservation of the capacity of carbon sequestration that occurs mainly in the unburnt very humid and short dry season moist forests, with an annual aboveground biomass growth rate of 5-7 m³/ha (FAO, 2016; FAO, 2020).

Governmental authorities responsible for the creation and implementation of IFM showed a firm commitment to support this IFM-LMT initiatives. Return of fire suppression policies and impediments of the implementation of fire uses by Indigenous communities in CNP and other protected areas, due

to changes in authorities or policies at governmental level, could represent, although unlikely, a significant limitation in the expansion of this LMT. However, in the case of this scenario, individual actions related to the IFM can still be implemented that would partially achieve similar objectives. Namely: implementation of prescribed and controlled burns, construction of firebreaks, participation of traditional communities' dwellers of protected areas and their surroundings in fire prevention activities, promotion, and compilation of Indigenous traditional knowledge of the use and management of fire, among others.

On a local and national scale, IFM could be replaced by other management practices for the implementation of crops at a more industrial scale (for example machinery for the elimination of plant cover, soil management and cleaning agricultural areas, fertilisers to increase the level of nutrients in the soil) instead of fire). However, these activities require high economic investments. Due to the country's current economic situation, it would not be possible to sustain and support these initiatives at the national level. Moreover, besides the socio-environmental benefits described above about IFM, its implementation is much less costly than intensive agriculture.

3.1.2. *Climate risks & sensitivities*

The LMT (IFM) is sensitive to the following climate-related changes:

Increase in the severity of "Fire-weather" conditions: including the increase of heatwaves frequency and air temperature, as well as the extension, duration, and intensity of dry seasons (IPCC, 2021). Heatwaves and intense droughts increase the flammability of fuel material, limiting the conduct of controlled burns. Drying fuel material, especially in savanna-forest edge areas, favours combustion and spreads fire into the forests.

Increased risk of accidents of occurrence of wildfires during controlled burning, preventing stopping the dangerous spread of fire to unwanted areas.

The alternation of extreme events of rainfall and drought stimulates the production of biomass of the fuel material during wet years, with the subsequent accumulation of dead and dry material during extreme drought periods favouring the spread of fires of greater severity and intensity.

Forest fires reduce carbon pools and the CO₂ assimilation capacity of the remaining vegetation. Likewise, recurrent and severe wildfires limit the regeneration capacity of vegetation, especially forests, and it prevents the implementation of cultivation practices in forest areas. On the other hand, PMB (patch mosaic burning) practices in savanna areas are hindered by reducing the fuel material that resprouts after fires.

Increased or generally changed weather variability affects the burning regime (specific to each period of the year) and the timing of cropping practices that require particular conditions for planting and harvesting.

For most interviewees, the loss of diversity is one of the most worrying factors, which would make implementing this LMT more difficult. Species diversity allows greater resilience of ecosystems to climate change and wildfire occurrence and severity. Forests and savannas diversity maintain the supply of essential environmental services, such as water quality and availability, soil maintenance, and supply of natural resources, among others.

3.1.3. *Economic implications*

The introduction of the new paradigm of Integrated Fire Management (IFM) instead of fire exclusion policies, conveys important advantages in terms of costs reduction (and costs avoided) and economic benefits. IFM represents a viable alternative to the prohibitive costs and low efficiency of fire exclusion, especially for low-income countries (Mistry et al., 2019; Eloy et al. 2019). Fire prohibition and firefighting or extinction activities in the face of climate change scenarios, demand growing human, technical and financial resources that may surpass local and national capabilities and budgets as it occurs in many countries of Latin America and Africa (for example the US Forest Service employs US\$ 5,000,000 annually to combat wildfires in the country).

The Federal Brigades Program implemented by Prevfogo/ Ibama in Brazil, is one successful example of how the implementation of IFM policies together with the involvement of Indigenous communities may become an efficient way to reduce wildfires and GHG emissions at low and affordable costs. Since 2016, fire brigades established in different settlements (Indigenous, rural communities, *quilombolas*) provided support to apply prescribed burnings to protect more than 600,000 km² located in federal, regional, and local public and private conservation areas (RPPNs), including settlement projects, Indigenous and *quilombolas* lands, with a public investment of R\$ 1.5 (US\$ 0.26) ha⁻¹ (Ibama, 2020; Falleiro et al. 2021).

The low costs of the Federal Brigades Program were associated to the significant reduction of wildfire occurrence as well as the hiring of local and Indigenous peoples to handle prescribed burnings in those communities that manage fire in an autonomous way, instead of using external human resources. However, according to Brazilian technicians, this initiative should include funds to recognize the environmental services provided by local and Indigenous peoples, such as CO₂ sequestration, water resources and socio-biodiversity protection.

Indigenous Fire Management Programs may actually provide economic benefits, as it was the case of the Emissions Reduction Fund (ERF), established in 2014 by the Australian government, after the official approval of the use of savanna fire management to generate Australian Carbon Credit Units (ACCUs; Commonwealth of Australia 2015). The ERF offers a long-term public contract to landowners and managers for storing carbon or reducing GHG emissions. By 2018, a total of 75 savanna burning projects were registered under the ERF and 52 of these projects had secured contracts with the Australian Government to abate 13.8 MtCO₂e over an average of 8.5 years. Savanna burning projects account for 7.2% (191.7 MtCO₂e yr⁻¹) of Australia's ERF contract portfolio, and 23 Indigenous projects account for 74% of the total potential savanna burning abatement. Considering the average ERF

Auction price of \$11.97 (in June 2018), as a conservative value, the sales of 2 668 848 ACCUs reached by one of the most successful programs implemented in Australia (ALFA program) equates to well over AUD \$31 million (Commonwealth of Australia, 2018). This is expected to provide significant incomes to Indigenous landowners over the next 7–10 year (Ansell et al. 2020).

Based on the Australian experience, Lipsett-Moore et al. (2018) made a global estimate for the least developed countries that have suitable environmental conditions to implement early fire management. These countries are eligible to receive the \$5 USD t CO₂e results-based payments offered by the GCF2, since they could effectively deliver early savanna burning (EDS) in order to remove all late undesirable wildfires (LDS) in their territories. According to the authors estimations the fire managers that fit into these conditions could benefit of a total global market valued in USD \$321 million per year.

3.1.4. *Co-benefits and trade-offs*

Integrated fire management is not only a possibility but an effective environmental management tool. It has been shown to have the potential to contribute to a range of positive environmental outcomes (as explained above), including biodiversity conservation. It also can enhance the capacity to support the sustainable livelihoods and pirobioculturality of savannas and tropical forest-based peoples (Ponce et al., 2022).

- a) Among the main environmental benefits resulting from the application of the LMT are
- b) the reduction in the number of forest fires and the absence of large fires (megafires),
- c) reduction in GHG emissions increased carbon capture and storage,
- d) improved air and water quality and other ecosystem services,

enhanced maintenance of ecosystems (savanna-forest mosaics), increased landscape diversity, enhanced landscape ecology (plants dependent on fire for their permanence), and increased plant and fauna diversity.

At the same time as mitigating climate change, supporting climate adaptation, and enhancing biodiversity conservation, the IFM-LMT approaches that are community-led and implemented can generate social, economic, and other benefits for local communities in these settings. Some of these benefits are: efficient management and conservation of forests and other ecosystems for conservation and/or support resources for subsistence activities, protecting public health (forest wildfires cause cardiovascular problems, respiratory failure and pneumonia), promote cultural heritage and aesthetic values. Other benefits point to the visibility and consolidation of local culture and practices.

Between the risks from applying the LMT, some actions contemplated in the MIF, such as prescribed or controlled burning, can cause forest fires due to the neglect or lack of human talent (forest firefighters and experimented members of local communities, among others), equipment and

materials during their execution. Likewise, implementing prescribed or controlled burning techniques without adequate knowledge of how, where, when and for what can bring more significant inconveniences, which is to be solved in terms of damage to vegetation and soil and the respective GHG emissions. Another risk is the lack of adequate inclusion of all local, institutional, and academic stakeholders. Although the IFM in Venezuela merged from the interaction between academics, Indigenous people, and firefighting officials, it is essential to involve the private sector and rural companies that confront serious problems to cope with wildfires and their impacts.

It is also essential not to stop investing in previous programs of forest fire suppression, especially the big ones, while an effective IFM-LMT is implemented. Some of the stakeholders interviewed recommend the coexistence between the two policies.

3.1.5. Risks associated with scaling up

Scaling up the IFM-LMT from the sub-national level to the national level implies significant risks and new challenges that are important to address. Some of them are listed:

- 1) The consolidation of the LMT-IFM in Canaima National Park was possible thanks to research studies and actions to involve stakeholders systematically over several years. The socioeconomic realities of the local communities and the heterogeneity of actors involved require generating trust environments and stakeholder engagement activities, so it would be essential to cover the technical capacity of human resources to coordinate these activities, considering these complexities. It is also necessary to have facilitators that allow the integration of scientific, operational, and local community knowledge about IFM on a sustained basis.
- 2) Difficulties to adopt the new IFM-LMT paradigm and submit to the dominant historical discourse of the park administrators, firefighting institutions, some private landowners, the media, and other authorities, about the perception of the urgent and necessary implementation of fire exclusion strategies and continue criminalising local people as the starter of wildfires.
- 3) For practical reasons, diverse initiatives of IFM at regional and global levels are focused on prescribed burnings and not involving local communities' participation. Consequently, there is an increasing risk of losing operativity or even increasing wildfire risks for selecting erroneous conditions for prescribed burnings implementation.
- 4) Venezuela is a vast country with a high diversity of ecosystems, topographies, geographical accidents, and remote areas of difficult access. Implementing this LMT extensively and simultaneously in diverse regions will be a significant challenge. It would be advisable to reduce risks by starting with pilot studies, in which progress and learning are monitored on an ongoing basis to strengthen these IFM-LMT initiatives.

3.1.6. *Research gaps*

- There is not enough information and scientific research to properly understand the specific fire regimes and fire ecology from different vegetation types in order to design suitable and sustainable fire management programs (Bilbao et al., 2020).
- Currently, there is non-existent legislation on Integrated Fire Management.
- Limited or unavailable statistical data on the socio-environmental realities at the local level of Canaima National Park and the national level (vegetation maps, population distribution and density, land use types, and meteorological data, among others).
- Limited or absent information on different types of land use and their impacts on productivity, environmental aspects, cost-benefits and economic value.
- Need to update emission inventories and national communications (the last one was done in 2017, with data from 2010).
- Implementing remote sensing technologies for systematic and sustained fire occurrence monitoring over the country is necessary.
- Creation of national and international cooperation networks to exchange experiences and learn land-use strategies for climate change mitigation.
- Addressing IFM-LMT with an intercultural approach must recognise the relationship between fire and society and consider the complex interplay between the actors, factors, and fire.
- Addressing strategies for the co-production of knowledge and mechanisms promotes participatory platforms to reduce the intercultural deficit of institutions and close the gap between academics, local communities and the responsible of politics.

4. Agroforestry of arid and semiarid lands (very dry and xerophytic forests)

4.1.1. Introduction

The development of sustainable agro-silvopastoral systems together with the conservation of natural resources in the fragile arid and semiarid ecosystems in the north-west of Venezuela have been addressed in the past 50 years by several research institutions and development agencies, always focused on the improvement of living conditions and wellbeing of the poor rural inhabitants of these areas. The efforts have brought about the development of a solid corpus of knowledge and experiences on sustainable practices and technologies that have been slowly adopted in the region to reduce deforestation, forest resources extraction and extensive goat raising. Altogether, they appear as complement and compatible LMTs that take into account key socio-economic and environmental interconnections proper of arid and semiarid lands.

Looking at these experiences from an integral perspective, allowed us to present a coherent array of LMTs that jointly contribute to counterbalance land degradation caused by continuous extraction and overexploitation of resources. The alternative technological proposal includes:

- a) Agroforestry systems that associate: (a) native legume tree species (to provide shadow, enhance local water balance, fix soil nitrogen, and serve as a protein source for human and animal consumption); (b) CAM local traditional crops of low-water demand, such as aloe, agave or cacti, planted under the trees cover (to avoid deforestation and soil degradation, reduce the irrigation requirements, and provide regular medium-term incomes to the farmers); (c) short-cycle vegetable crops planted in association with trees semi-shade (to provide food for family consumption and rapid economic returns from the sale of production exceeds); (d) establishment of plant nurseries and reforestation programs with native species.
- b) Agro-silvopastoral goat and/or sheep systems based on semi-tabulated management (to replace extensive herd management). Grazing paddocks are established with grasses, maize, beans, moringa, and other native or naturalized fodder plant species to supplement food requirements. This involves the suppression or drastic reduction and strict control of animal charges on common foraging forested lands. Maintenance and protection of natural nearby forests.
- c) Conservation, protection, and enhancement of forested areas remnants.
- d) Afforestation and water surface runoff technologies to control soil erosion and promote vegetation recovery.

The application of water harvest techniques, the use of organic fertilization, and the adoption of sustainable energy sources and saving cooking devices are key for the success of the LMT.

Here, we will describe some of the alternative solutions developed by academic and institutional stakeholders jointly with communities from the arid and semiarid regions of Venezuela that have been adopted in this highly vulnerable region. Special attention will be paid to the experiences recorded in Falcón state and which have potential as LMTs.

Characteristics of Venezuelan arid and semi-arid lands

Venezuelan arid and semiarid lands cover 41,023 km² and represent 4.5% of the country. They are located along with the northern islands, the Caribbean Sea mainland coastland, the Falcón-Lara depression in the central-western area of the country, and in some slopes and valleys of the Andean west mountain range, below 600 (-800) masl (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Location of arid, semiarid, and dry lands in Venezuela. Left: Map showing the current distribution of arid and semiarid lands in the country; at the bottom, the hydric climate balance of selected locations is presented (Medina et al. 1985). Right: Map of Venezuelan dry lands (MINEA, 2020). The areas shown in light yellow are at risk of desertification under climate change future scenarios.

Historically, these territories have been the location of important human settlements due to their vicinity to the coast and favourable conditions to establish land and sea communication and exchange routes. Archaeological evidence indicates that these areas have been inhabited since 14200 – 12980 years before the present, as Taima-Taima and many other archaeological sites excavated by Josep Cruxent in Falcón since 1960’s demonstrate (Darvill 2002). At the present, these areas concentrate nearly a third of Venezuela’s population and are under high urbanization, agricultural, and industrial pressures.

This region shows a mega-thermic regime, with annual mean temperatures of 27° to 30° C, and mean annual rains of 250 to 500 (-800) mm. Precipitation tends to be erratic but usually concentrates in short periods of time causing torrential runoff, loss of soil and fast accumulation of sediments downstream, as well as the release of carbon to the atmosphere. Episodic brief rain events (5-10 mm)

occur almost every month in some localities. High evapotranspiration rates (1600-2300 mm), constant wind currents (speeds of 4 to 8 m.s-1), and high daily radiation values (up to 6500 Kwatt) are stressful conditions for the local vegetation and fauna (Díaz 2001; Ewel & Madriz 1968, cited by Matteucci 1986). Soils are mostly alkaline and often with an argillic horizon between 40-60 cm deep, which explains the abundance of superficial tree roots (Díaz 2001).

High levels of hydric stress, together with soil characteristics shape the natural ecosystems found in these regions. Different types of vegetation are found in these lands, ranging from littoral herbaceous formations, thorny shrubby vegetation dominated by emergent cacti (<5 m tall), thorny shrubby vegetation dominated by legume *Prosopis* trees cover, and tall deciduous forest or a mixture of them (Matteucci 1986, Oliveira et al. 2010). Oliveira-Miranda et al. (2010) estimated that 25,172 Km² of Venezuelan arid and semiarid lands were covered by thorny bush vegetation, while Díaz (in press) estimated that around 32,350 Km² of this region have some degree of xerophytic vegetation coverage.

Arid and semiarid ecosystems provide many resources exploited by rural inhabitants, such as firewood; wood for handcraft, furniture, and construction purposes; pastures and forages for goat raising; agave plants used for alcoholic beverage production, and as a source of food and fibre; and fruits for local consumption. Rabbits, iguanas, wild pigs (*Tajassus* sp.), and white-tailed deer (*Odocoileus* sp.) are appreciated hunts. Birds such as parrots, trupials, and cardinals (*Carduellis cucullata*), giant spiders (blue tarantula), as well as ornamental plants (i.e. bromeliads and orchids) are also extracted and sold illegally (Ángela Martino, pers. comm. 2021). The forest cover is usually removed in order to establish aloe plantations of various sizes as well as conucos where local families cultivate maize, legume grains, and pumpkins, among other short-lived crops. Intensive irrigated agriculture (onion, tomato, melon, maize, sugarcane, pineapple, sisal), cattle and goat, sheeps raising, and shrimp farming have been associated with vegetation degradation and soil loss.

Starting in the second half of the 20th century intensive exploitation of underground water's reservoirs for irrigation purposes has caused salinization of soils located in the vicinity of the seaside in sites such as El Cebollal, Paraguaná and Tocópero in Falcón state (Barros 2006, Torres et al. 2006).

Some authors (Torres et al. 2006) indicate that a continuous land degradation process has been observed in the semiarid zone of Falcón state, due to the prevalence of inappropriate conventional agricultural systems (i.e. honey dew melon or short cycle vegetable crops intensive production), under low rainfall and high evapotranspiration climatic conditions. Here, soil degradation has been accelerated by the application of high frequency localized irrigation systems that contribute to medium and long term soil salinization.

The intense human activity is responsible for a high degree of disturbance and loss of vegetation cover. Goat free ranging, wood extraction, urban wastes inadequate disposal, and sand mining have been reported also as some of the most degrading activities affecting these ecosystems (Matteucci 1986, Oliveira-Miranda 2010). On the coast, many touristic developments have been also established.

Oliveira-Miranda et al. (2010) reported a change of -19.37% (1988-2010), of shrubby thorny vegetation cover, while Díaz (2021) found a loss of -13.75% (1986-2019) of the total xerophytic forest vegetation (Table 2). Attending to the degree of disturbance and the risks of loss of their ecological functions, these ecosystems are included in the IUCN Endangered category (Oliveira-Miranda et al. 2010).

Table 2. Changes in xerophytic forest cover in some states of Venezuela were estimated from satellite analyses (Modified from Díaz, 2021).

Xerophytic forest cover in Venezuela				
State	Forest cover area (Km ²) in 2019	Forest cover area (Km ²) in 1986 ¹	Forest cover change (Km ²)	Forest cover change (%)
Falcón	8.939,42	10.000,04	-1.060,62	-10,61
Lara	6.668,83	10.710,70	-4.041,87	-37,74
Mérida ²	13.540,83	13.540,83		
Zulia	2.679,72	2.661,70	18,02	0,68
TOTAL	32.348,98	37.506,86	-5.157,88	-13,75

Source: Díaz, Miriam. Manual de restauración del bosque xerofítico. FAO. In press.

¹ Zulia state cover estimated from 2001 data

Inadequate management of these lands increases the vulnerability of desertification, as shown by Mogollón et al. (2016) in Paraguaná region. Shrubby and herbaceous thorny vegetation types that cover the 3% of this peninsula are the most vulnerable ones to degradation processes. Bush vegetation covers 11.4% of this territory and is the least vulnerable vegetation type thanks to the presence of plant species adapted to dryness. The remaining 85.6% of the lands have a moderate vegetation cover but are vulnerable to desertification caused by free or extensive goat cattle raising, and the application of intensive conventional horticultural practices leading to soil salinization and erosion.

CO₂ fixation potential of Venezuelan arid and semiarid lands

Semiarid tropical lands can be highly productive under adequate management, and efficient soil and water use (Díaz, 2001). In Falcón state, natural undisturbed xerophytic forest ecosystems show a significant diversity and stratification, including trees, shrubs, erect cacti, vines, epiphytes and dense mats of succulent CAM species growing in the forest undercover, such as *Bromelia humilis*, *Agave* spp., several cacti species, and the naturalized *Aloe vera* plants. Under adequate conservation and management conditions, these systems have a significant biomass CO₂ fixation potential of up to 8.236,39 Kg ha⁻¹ year (including photorespiration and respiration losses) as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. CO₂ fixation potential of evergreen and deciduous tree species from Paraguaná, Falcón state, estimated from instant photosynthetic rate measures.

Estimated CO ₂ fixation potential of a xerophytic forest from Paraguaná Peninsula, Falcón state, Venezuela											
Tree species	Instant photosynthetic rate						CO ₂ weight	CO ₂ annual exchange rate per tree	Tree mean density (1)	CO ₂ fixation potential (2)	
	$\mu\text{m}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{sec}^{-1}$	$\mu\text{m}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{hour}^{-1}$	$\mu\text{m}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$	$\mu\text{m}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{year}^{-1}$	$\text{mm}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{year}^{-1}$	$\text{m}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{year}^{-1}$					$\text{g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$
Evergreens	150	540.000	4.320.000	1.576.800.000	1.576.800	1.577	44	69.379	69	82	5.654,47
Deciduos & semi-deciduos	250	900.000	7.200.000	720.000.000	720.000	720	44	31.680	32	82	2.581,92
										TOTAL	8.236,39

(1) A ratio of 1:1 evergreen to deciduos trees was estimated of a total count of 164 trees per ha
(2) Results include photorespiration and respiration values
Sources: a) Díaz M. 1988. Las zonas áridas al norte de Venezuela: Hacia el aprovechamiento racional de sus recursos naturales renovables. En: Caliman A. & Paredes L. Zonas áridas. Fundacite Zulia, Maracaibo. pp 33-54. b) Díaz M. 1994. Caracterización ecofisiológica de las especies arbóreas predominantes en las zonas áridas y semiáridas. Trabajo de ascenso para optar a la categoría de Profesor Asociado. UNEFM, Coro. 105 pp. c) Díaz M. & Granadillo E. 2005. The significance of episodic rains for reproductive phenology and productivity in trees in semiarid regions of northwestern Venezuela. Trees 19: 336- 348.

According to Mogollón et al. (2015), soil organic carbon (SOC) reserves in Paraguaná arid areas are highly variable, due to differences in soil, climate, and vegetation along altitudinal gradients. The SOC reserves increase with altitude (7.8 t ha⁻¹ at 1 masl vs. 101.5 t ha⁻¹ at 400 masl) and mean annual precipitation while decreasing at higher average annual temperatures conditions. Soil carbon content levels are also higher under dry and deciduous forest cover (63-92 ton C.ha⁻¹), in comparison to cacti or thorny-shrubby vegetation (36.7-47 ton C.ha⁻¹), and herbaceous or sparse shrubby vegetation types (10.3-21.9 ton.ha⁻¹). The highest values of SOC in Paraguaná correspond to the understory of forest vegetation in Cerro Santa Ana Natural Monument (Mogollón et al. 2015). In contrast to conventional agricultural systems, in situ analyses performed in lands with similar climatic conditions but under aloe organic farming cultivation showed that soil carbon content and ion exchange capacity were similar to those of surrounding secondary forests and much higher than the values obtained from lands with conventional agricultural systems (Torres 2006, Mogollón 2015).

Mitigation and adaptation measures in Venezuelan arid and semiarid lands

Traditional farmers from the arid and semiarid regions of Falcón state have small subsistence production units based on free-ranging goats (to obtain meat and its derivatives, as well as milk, cheese, cream and traditional sweets), aloe or sábila plantations (to obtain aloe latex, sold to national intermediaries of a long international commercial chain), and maize and frijol rainfed plantations. Some of them also produce artisan liquors. These units provide food for family consumption and income from the sale of exceeds. Usually, trees are removed to establish the plantations. Farmers also extract wood for cooking and artisan fabrication of furniture and handcrafts.

Several mixed alternative agroforestry systems that mimic local ecosystems compartmentalization have been tested in Falcón state by academics and researchers from the Research Center in Ecology and Arid Zones of Francisco de Miranda University (Centro de Investigaciones en Ecología y Zonas Áridas - Universidad Nacional Experimental Francisco de Miranda, CIEZA-UNEFM).

Over more than four decades, CIEZA professionals have led research on ecological and physiological adaptive features of potential alternative crops, adapted to the harsh conditions that prevail in Falcón state, in order to offer local communities sustainable alternative agricultural solutions to their needs.

The results of their studies and practical experiences allowed the definition of an agroforestry semiarid system depicted as a combination of natural resources investments that include a) a tree coverage of legume and other woody species used by the farmers (analogous to a trust fund), b) succulent CAM crops production in forest understory (analogous to a saving account), and c) short-cycle crops (analogous to a current account). The farming potentiality of some local fauna resources such as rabbits, iguanas, or wild pigs, have also been assessed.

These systems are intended to provide local rural families alternatives to the extractive traditional land management practices that contribute to deforestation and land degradation while being economically attractive.

Aloe vera - Prosopis juliflora agroforestry systems

Prosopis juliflora, known locally as “cují”, is a native legume tree species that contribute to soil nitrogen fixation while protecting the soil from erosion; its nutritive fruits are used to feed goats. Under the partial shade of cují trees, bromeliads plants such as teco (*Bromelia humilis*) and maya (*Bromelia karatas*, *B. pinguin*), as well as agave grow spontaneously forming dense mats. These species have a distinct CAM photosynthesis metabolism, proper of succulent plants adapted to dry and desert conditions. This observation gave insights to test the behaviour and productivity of sábila (*Aloe vera*), a local traditional rainfed crop introduced at least 400 years ago in the region when planted under cují trees partial shade. The results from various assays showed that sábila plants actually grow healthy and vigorous under partial shade conditions, increasing the gel production volume since they avoid the excess loss of water from their tissues. Similar results were obtained with agave plants (Díaz 2001), showing that carbohydrate accumulation is higher under partial tree shade. These findings suggest that tree coverage reduces crop irrigation requirements and protect plants from excess radiation levels. Similar effects have been observed with other tree species. In short, the incorporation of sábila CAM crops that grow well under partial tree shading, in association to mature legume trees and short cycle crops, are sustainable agricultural practices that prevent deforestation, reduce soil loss, and help in the restoration of already degraded dry lands (Figure 8 and 9).

Figure 8. Left: Cultivated Aloe vera plant. Right: Aloe vera plantation under the partial shade of Bursera sp. tree in Paraguaná. (Photos: Herbario Coro & Rosalba Gómez Martínez).

Agave cocui agroforestry systems. Towards the domestication of a traditionally multipurpose plant.

In the Falcón-Lara semiarid mountain range, there is a long tradition of harvesting *Agave cocui* plants for several purposes. This native species grows abundantly on dry calcareous soils and is tolerant to harsh climate conditions. Local inhabitants cook and eat the highly nutritive and tasty growing apex as well as the flowers during scarcity periods. The plant is used to treat several ailments (i.e., joint pains, menstrual and fertility disorders in women). They obtain soft fibres from the leaves to make hammocks, sandals, and handcrafts. The leaves and the inflorescence stalks are used as building materials. Finally, they prepare a traditional and highly appreciated alcoholic distilled beverage, the “cocuy”, which is similar to the Mexican mescal and tequila. All these products are harvested from wild populations. Traditionally, cocuy spirit production, together with goat extensive production and aloe and maize cultivation has been a source of income for poor local farmers in the dry mountain range area of Falcón and Lara states. However, due to the influence of industrial competitors, the cocuy artisan spirit was banned and excluded from the Alcoholic Beverages National Law during the ‘70s of the past century, leading to persecution of local producers.

Figure 9. Agave cocui plants growing in natural conditions in Falcón state. Photographs: Miriam Díaz.

Attending the request of cocuy artisans and Falcón Government, Fundacite Falcón (Fundación para el Desarrollo de la Ciencia y la Tecnología del estado Falcón), a public institution affiliated to the Science and Technology Minister in charge of the promotion and support of research and innovation in the region, started in 1995 the research and innovation *Agave cocui* program, involving academics from UNEFM, NGOs and local farmers from Pecaya parish (Sucre municipality, Falcón state), in order to study the biological, environmental, sociological and technological implications of cocuy traditional production (Díaz 2002). A multidisciplinary team gathered information about the ecology, physiology, reproduction, propagation, and biochemistry of the plant; the analysis of the quality of the cocuy spirit as well as fermentation and distilling process; historical and sociological studies of the people from Pecaya parish were also undertaken. The productivity and benefits of several agroforestry systems based on promising genotypes of *Agave cocui*, Aloe vera, and short cycle vegetable crops (i.e., beans, coriander, tomato) planted under cují (*Prosopis juliflora*) trees shadow, were evaluated in the field. *Agave* plants and native tree species nurseries were established and promoted among local producers

in order to reforest the areas and assure long-term supplies of agave and wood to sustain cocuy beverages production.

Semi-tabulated goat management

Degradation of the vegetation and desertification have been associated with extensive goat farming in the arid and semi-arid regions of Venezuela, similarly to what has been described in other countries of the world (Matteucci 1986, Matteucci & Colma 1997, Mogollón 2016). These processes usually occur when high occupation animal rates are maintained in a limited area during drought periods, resulting in overgrazing of vulnerable plants under hydric stress.

Extensive goat farming is one of the traditional subsistence activities that has been developed over the past 400 years in the arid and semiarid of Falcón – Lara states (Armas et al. 2006). Although the importance of goat farming has been underestimated in the rest of the country, it has great socio-productive relevance in this area, since this is the most important source of proteins for the inhabitants of these lands (Delgado et al. 2010).

These animal systems have been thoroughly studied by academics and researchers from Universidad Centro Occidental Lisandro Alvarado (UCLA-Lara), Universidad Nacional Experimental Francisco de Miranda (UNEFM-Falcón), Universidad Politécnica Territorial Alonso Gamero (UPTAG), and Instituto Nacional de Investigaciones Agrícolas (INIA-Lara and INIA-Falcón), among others.

Several initiatives have been implemented in this region in order to improve the technologies applied for goat production, reduce the environmental impact of the activity, and offer socio-economic assistance to the poor families that depend on this resource (Table 4). Semi-tabulated systems based on paddocks and protein banks that include native and naturalized herbaceous, shrubby and tree plant species as fodder resources, together with water harvest techniques, as well as reproductive control and sanitation herd management, help to lower the pressure over the xerophytic forests and promote the environmental and socio-economic sustainability of this activity. The many promotion efforts have contributed so far to an increase of awareness in relation to natural resources conservation and protection among some segments of the producers, although these practices have not been generally adopted yet (CIARA, 2014).

Table 4: Research and development public initiatives promoted to improve the sustainability of goat farming in the arid and semi-arid region of Venezuela.

NATIONAL RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMS FOR THE SUSTAINABILITY OF GOAT CATTLE PRODUCTION				
Initiative	Date	Aim	Stakeholders involved	Funding
PIDZAR Project of Research & Development on Arid and semi-arid zones in central-western Venezuelan region (Proyecto de Investigación-Desarrollo de Zonas Áridas y Semiáridas en la Región Centro Occidental de Venezuela)	1980's	Design, implementation and evaluation of initiatives for the rational use of the natural resources of this zone, in harmony with the environmental conditions and the integral development of the area (Improvement of goat traditional farming and optimization of water and energy)	FONAIAP (currently INIA), UCLA, UNEFM, CORPOCCIDENTE& FUDECO. Pilot communities in Lara and Falcón states.	France International Technical Cooperation Program. Institutional participants contributions.
National Research Agenda on Goat Cattle	2000's	Research to advance national goat productive capabilities	MCTI, Fundacite Falcón, Fundacite Lara, Fundacite Zulia, UNEFM, UCLA, LUZ, UDO	FONACIT
Project for the sustainable rural development of the SemiArid zones of Lara and Falcón estates (PROSALAF, by its Spanish acronym). PROSALAF I, II & III	1993-2004 / 2006-2013 / 2014-	Capacitation and technology transfer to diminish the levels of extreme poverty and poverty of the rural communities of the semiarid region of Lara and Falcón states	CIARA Foundation	International Fund for Agricultural Development of the United Nations and the Corporación Andina de Fomento (CAF)
Program: Networks of Productive Innovation ("Redes de Innovación Productiva" or RIP)	2000-2016	Technology transfer program to increase capabilities of rural productive organizations	MCTI, Fundacite Falcón, Fundacite Lara, Fundacite Zulia, Rural productive organizations	FONACIT, LOCTI Funds & Misión Ciencia
<p>Referenc es: CIARA 2014, Fundacite Falcón et al. 20009, IICA 1983, Matteucci & Colma 1997.</p> <p>CIARA: Fundación para la Capacitación y la Innovación para el Desarrollo Rural (Development)</p> <p>CORPOCCIDENTE Corporación para el Desarrollo del Occidente de Venezuela</p> <p>FONAIAP: Fondo Nacional de Investigación Agrícola y Pecuaria</p> <p>FONACIT: Fondo Nacional de Ciencia y Tecnología</p> <p>FUDECO: Fundación para el Desarrollo del Centro Occidente de Venezuela</p> <p>Fundacite Falcón: Fundación para el Desarrollo de la Ciencia y la Tecnología del Edo. Falcón</p> <p>Fundacite Lara: Fundación para el Desarrollo de la Ciencia y la Tecnología del Edo. Lara</p> <p>Fundacite Zulia: Fundación para el Desarrollo de la Ciencia y la Tecnología del Edo. Zulia</p> <p>INA Instituto Nacional de Investigaciones Agrícolas</p> <p>MCTI: Ministerio de Ciencia y Tecnología</p> <p>UCLA Universidad Centro Occidental Lisandro Alvarado</p> <p>UNEFM: Universidad Nacional Experimental Francisco de Miranda</p>				

Conservation of forested lands. The experience of Montecano communal lands in Paraganá.

According to Jongwon et al. (2011) "traditional rural forests exist within the area of influence of village communities, having historical and cultural significance, and for this reason, they are forests that play a special role in clan communities or village communities." This concept can be applied to Montecano forests, located on communal Indigenous lands legally recognized as such since the XVII century. The members of the San José de Cocodite community have long used these lands mainly as shared foraging places for their goats. However, they started to have concerns about the sustainability of the forest decades ago when neighbouring communities pressed also for the use of these foraging lands, and new private urbanisms started to appear in their surroundings, among other threats.

In order to protect Montecano, a long cooperative effort was established in 1985 between the Community of San José de Cocodite from Paraganá (Pueblo Nuevo Parish, Falcón municipality), Universidad Nacional Experimental Francisco de Miranda (UNEFM), and the private NGO BIOMA Foundation. After BIOMA's closure in 1996, INFALCOSTA NGO got into the cooperative agreement. In spite of various threats and external pressures over Montecano, this joint effort allowed to conserve this forested area and to develop research, conservation and educational programs, including the

establishment of eco-touristic routes, about the value and importance of its natural resources and biodiversity (Infalcosta, n/d, Martino 2012).

Montecano is a low range of irregular topography that captures the air humidity carried by the northeastern-southeastern trade winds. During late-night hours when air temperatures drop, water condensates over the plant leaves enhancing plant productivity, especially of CAM species such as epiphytic and terrestrial bromeliads, orchids and cacti (i.e., pitahaya), and trees such as *Pereskia guamacho* (Edwards & Díaz 2006, Martino 2012). Recent studies have shown that some tree species present in Monte Cano (i.e., *Quadrella odoratissima*) can absorb water through the leaves and depend on atmospheric humidity rather than on direct precipitation; for that reason, they survive in these areas (Losada et al. 2021).

Attending the request of San José de Cocodite Community and its allies, Montecano was declared as a Natural Monument on April 22, 2019, by Presidential Decree N° 3825 published in the Gaceta Oficial de la República Bolivariana de Venezuela n° 41.617 and was officially included in the list of National Protected Areas administered by INPARQUES. The biological and ecological evidence to support this decree was gathered by CIEZA-UNEFM (Martino, 2012). Montecano Natural Monument covers 2,599 ha of xerophytic forest and shrubby vegetation and serves as a refuge for many animal and plant species that are not found in the rest of Paraguaná. It is an important CO₂ reservoir in this largely environmentally disturbed region (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Montecano Natural Monument covers 2995 ha of hills located in the northeast of Paraguaná Peninsula, Falcón state, in the Venezuelan arid and semi-arid region. Upper row, from left to right: a) the epiphyte *Tillandsia usneoides* captures air humidity and grows abundantly in the understory; b) hill landscape covered by bush and shrubby vegetation; c) San José de Cocodite community together with UNEFM and INFALCOSTA have guarded Montecano for almost 40 years. Lower row: d) Montecano faces eastward to the Caribbean Sea, so the hills trap humidity brought by north trade wind; e) Members of the San José de Cocodite community listen to the presentation of the proposal to declare Monte Cano as a National Monument in August 2016; f) columnar cacti and terrestrial bromeliads are common in Montecano.

Afforestation and water surface runoff technologies to control soil erosion and promote vegetation recovery.

Soils are a major CO₂ reservoir in arid and semi-arid lands in Venezuela. However, inadequate vegetable agricultural and irrigation practices, extensive goat farming, cattle raising introduction, native tree species overexploitation (to obtain firewood and handcrafts), and deforestation lead to loss of the reserves of soil organic carbon and microbial biomass carbon (Mogollón et al. 2015). Dry environmental conditions, high wind speeds, torrential rains in short spans of time, and wildfire occurrence, increase the risks of salinization, soil loss and desertification. The Paraguaná peninsula, El Cebollal, and Matícora river basin, are some of the areas that show evidence of degradation and loss of soil caused by inadequate agricultural and goat raising management in Falcón state.

Some local producers apply traditional “*torobas*” technologies in order to avoid soil loss during rainy season and manage rain overflow. *Torobas* are trappings made from stones or logs that are set on the terrain in a perpendicular way to the slopes, in order to conduct and slow down the speed of superficial runoff. *Torobas* function as sediment traps while increasing local soil water infiltration. These processes enhance the establishment of new plants that, in turn, attract herbivores which release their urine and feces in these feeding sites and contribute to enrich soil nutrients availability, thus creating a positive vegetation recovery cycle. *Torobas* are also used to improve irrigation water distribution in plantations.

In the past decade, Venezuela’s national environmental authority (MINEC) promoted several projects and actions in Falcón state to mitigate and recover the severely degraded basin of Matícora river including its tributaries sub-basins. Due to the severe erosion degree, native trees used in reforestation campaigns showed low rates of survival. In contrast, according to Falcón state MINEC environmental technicians the establishment of rural ditches undertaken by the local communities of Tupurito, in Dabajuro municipality was a successful experience (Josefa Morles, personal communication, 2022). Starting in 2014, the national environmental authorities from MINEC (Ministerio del Poder Popular para el Ecosocialismo) initiated a project based on a formal agreement with members of the local community organized as the “Consejo Comunal of Tupurito”, by which MINEC technicians offered a basic preparation on local hydrology control principles and field advisory and supervision on how to build rural ditches using materials locally available (i.e., stones and logs). MINEC national officers transferred financial resources to the Consejo Comunal to hire members of the community to build several rural ditches. The community selected the area to establish the

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ditches, considering the recurrence of torrential floods that carried large amounts of sediments and debris that tended to interrupt an important rural road during the short rainy season. A battery of 6 rural ditches built by the community members under the supervision of MINEC technicians was ready before the next rainy

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season. The results were evident: no flood occurred and the transit on the road was open during the whole rainy season. The ditches trapped large sized sediments and allowed the passage of smaller ones carried by the slowly flowing water. One of the local producers took advantage of the sediments trapped in the ditches to establish forages to feed their cattle. Runoff water remained in ponds for weeks after the end of the rainy season offering the cattle a source of drinking water. A group of women from Tupurito village that took part of this experience, decided to implement by themselves new rural ditches in their own lands to take advantage of this technology for their agricultural and cattle raising activities. They also shared their knowledge and helped other producers from nearby localities to build their own ditches. This is an example of how local communities can adopt sustainable technologies when the benefits are evident and compatible with their socio-economic rationale.

Figure 11: National Environmental authorities from MINEC provided technical and financial support to rural communities to develop artisanal ditches in Tupure river basin, one of the tributaries of Maticora river, in north-western Venezuelan Falcón state, in order to stop erosion and promote soil and vegetation recovery.

4.1.2. Which national policies exist that address the LMT?

In general, Venezuela has a comprehensive law system in the environmental area that provides support to agroforestry and conservation LMTs. Starting with the Constitución de la República Bolivariana de Venezuela approved in 1999, a varied set of organic laws and general laws have been approved such as: Ley Orgánica de Planificación y Ordenamiento Territorial; Ley Orgánica del Ambiente; Ley Orgánica para la Conservación Ambiental; Ley Penal del Ambiente; Ley de Meteorología e Hidrología; Ley sobre Manejo Integral de Riesgos; Ley de Áreas Naturales Protegidas, Ley de Seguridad y Soberanía Alimentaria. A thorough review of the legal instruments related to arid and semi-arid land management and development has been recently produced by Durán (2018)

United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification and mitigate the effects of drought (UNCCD)

Venezuela presented in 2004 a national report indicating its commitment to implement prevention and mitigation, or compensation actions related to the effects of desertification and drought in the country, according to national environmental policies and environmental agreements already signed.

In 2019, Venezuelan authorities officially informed the UNCCD about the national voluntary goals fixed by the country to accomplish Neutrality in Land Degradation (NLD) by 2030 (República Bolivariana de Venezuela 2019). The more relevant goals for arid and semiarid land sustainable management are the following ones:

- Goal n° 1: By 2030, to increase 262,361 ha (0.53%) of forest lands based on year 2010. This goal explicitly includes the reforestation of Hueque, Mitare and Matícora river basins, all of them located in Falcón state, as well as Tocuyo river in Lara state.
- Goal n° 3: By 2030, to recover and maintain an agricultural cultivated surface of 100,000 ha per year. This goal refers to the contribution of the Lands and Agriculture Ministry to the NLD that will be implemented in arid and semiarid zones of Lara and Falcón states, through (a) the Integral Crops and Goats Management strategies based on environmental sanitation and education in 3000 production units covering around 15000 ha; (b) Irrigation water-saving techniques implementation (sprinkler and drip irrigation); (c) tabulated and semi-tabulated goat herds management, with genetic improvement, fodder banks, multi-family rural cisterns, and comprehensive management of crops and vegetables, with technical and financial support. All these actions are oriented towards the establishment of a sustainable production quality certification program.
- Goal n° 6: By 2030 integration of Neutrality in Land Degradation (NLD) into territorial planning has been promoted, especially in those zones with critical levels of land degradation. This goal includes the obligation to produce and put into action the Management and Conservation Plans of the river basins Hueque, Mitare and Matícora in Falcón state, and of the Tocuyo river in Lara. It also refers to the consolidation of the territorial management of Coastal Zones to prioritize present and future actions to promote the sustainable development of these spaces.

These goals provide key orientations to all stakeholders involved in arid and semiarid sustainable development in Venezuela for immediate action. The experiences and models here presented may now find an opportunity to be extended, improved, and adapted under this official scheme of Neutrality in Land Degradation (NLD).

Forest National Law

Agroforestry systems are acknowledged in the Venezuelan Law corpus. The “Ley de Bosques” (Forest National Law), officially enforced in 2013, declares that one of its purposes is the promotion of agroforestry systems along multiple-use forest plantations as one way of assuring sustainable forest management and use (Article 7). The law acknowledges organizations, and Indigenous peoples and communities, the right of being consulted and of participating in the promotion and development of diverse initiatives oriented towards the conservation, and management of forests and forest patrimony including the conformation and management of socio-productive forms integrated into the productive forestry chain (Article 27). This legal instrument clearly points that is the duty of the State

(at national, regional and local levels) to promote and encourage the increase of forest cover with responsibilities through programs, plans and actions aimed at the afforestation of lands devoid of vegetation for protective or productive purposes, and the promotion and conservation of forests as carbon sinks, among other initiatives.

Policies related to exploitation of local fauna species

According to Venezuelan Law of Protection of Wild Local Fauna (Gaceta Oficial 29.289, August 11, 1970), local fauna conservation and rational exploitation are considered activities of public interest under the direct supervision of the environmental authority. This legal instrument does not explicitly support fauna domestication programs; therefore, the establishment of private initiatives to exploit fauna species faces many restrictions. Starting in the '70s through the beginning of XXI century, some emblematic research programs promoted by Universidad Central de Venezuela and Universidad de Los Llanos Ezequiel Zamora, with the support of Ministerio del Ambiente, produced information on raising activities of some endangered fauna species (i.e., caiman del Orinoco, Arrau turtles) and some hunting preys (i.e. capybara), in order to improve the status of their natural populations. However, these initiatives have not been exploited at a commercial level. The establishment of commercial fauna species production systems could improve agroforestry systems economic impact and provide a sustainable source of food for the rural communities in semi-arid zones. An updated legal frame to promote sustainable fauna species domestication and exploitation is required.

Policies that regulate sustainable artisan beverages manufacturing and its impact on the environment

The results of the Program on Agave cocui, described in a previous section, supported the official acknowledgement of Agave cocui and its traditional usages as a natural and cultural Indigenous heritage in 2000, together with the approval of a quality standard (COVENIN) to produce the beverage, and the granting of a national appellation of origin to artisan cocuy pecayero spirit in 2001. This experience provided evidence to change the Alcoholic National Beverage Law in 2005, and to approve a special providence by the national tax authority (SENIAT) in 2008. These legal instruments set limits to the maximum volume of cocuy each artisan can produce per year, limiting thereof the number of plants that can be harvested to obtain this spirit. They also set the obligation of the artisans to establish agave nurseries for reforestation.

Starting from the request of Pecaya communities, followed by the involvement of academics and regional institutions, this bottom-up process led to the approval and modification of national legal instruments that finally allowed the artisans to produce and sell cocuy, improve their living conditions, and receive the recognition they deserve while setting sustainability environmental standards (Miriam Díaz pers. comm., Sánchez et al. 2008).

Cocuy artisans are allowed to produce up to a limited amount of cocuy spirit per year (2.000 litres per year); they also have the obligation to establish agave and tree species nurseries and are legally

enforced to plant agave and trees (used as a source of wood for fuel) in the exploited areas. In 2022, a new law project intended to protect and promote Agave cocui production has been proposed and is currently under public consultation and discussion.

Figure 12: National laws that regulate artisan cocuy alcoholic beverages production remark the obligation of producers to develop sustainable agave plantations.

Which actors are currently applying the LMT (e.g., land users, forest owners, farmers)?

In the past 20 years, several research-innovation projects have been developed by public organisms in Falcón and Lara states (i.e. Fundacite Falcón, Fundacite Lara, CIARA-PROSALAFSA, Instituto Nacional de Investigaciones Agrícolas –INIA–), academics from Universidad Nacional Experimental Francisco de Miranda –UNEFM–, Universidad Politécnica Alonso Gamero –UPTAG–, Universidad Centro Occidental Lisandro Alvarado –UCLA–, NGO’s such as INFALCOSTA, working closely with local goat farmers, peasants and cocuy beverage producers, with varying results. Funds for this kind of projects used to come from grants provided by Ministerio de Ciencia y Tecnología including funds obtained by the Ley Orgánica de Ciencia y Tecnología (LOCTI, but they are not currently operative).

Some private initiatives of small and medium producers and local entrepreneurs are already incorporating sustainable practices of goat herds management (i.e., Granja Agroecológica Virgen de la Guadalupe and others in Guzmán Guillermo Parish close to Coro), as well as pilot projects to raise local fauna species.

Figure 13: Semi-tabulated goat raising systems offer a sustainable alternative to extensive or free ranging environmental degrading practices, increasing the quality of the products obtained as well as the economic returns of small producers in semi-arid lands. Credits: Photos from Granja Agroecológica Virgen de la Guadalupe Instagram account @gvguadalupe.

Recently, a new generation of entrepreneurs have begun to implement agave beverages production projects in other localities of Falcón state, based on sustainable management of natural populations, as well as the establishment of their own nurseries for the propagation of promising agave clones to start large scale plantations (@cocuypecayero Instagram account, Figure 14). One promising private enterprise, Magno label, has recently been distinguished with two silver and one bronze medals in the International 2021 Liquor Contest in New York (<https://observadorlatino.com/noticias/el-cocuy-venezolano-es-premiado-en-nueva-york/>) (Figure 14). Artisans from Lara state have followed this example and recently received a medal in the London Spirits Competition 2022 for the quality of Cocuy 7 Primos Gota a Gota (<https://elestimulo.com/gastronomia/2022-04-18/cocuy-7-primos-gana-medalla-en-london-spirits-competition/>) (Figure 14).

Figure 14: Artisan and young entrepreneurs are adopting sustainable practices to produce cocuy alcoholic beverages in Pecaya and other semi-arid Venezuelan regions. A) Establishment of agave

plantations under native trees shadow avoid deforestation. B & C) These new trademarks of cocuy have received international recognition in 2021 (Magno cocuy from Falcón state) and 2022 (Cocuy 7 Primos - Gota a gota from Lara state).

Which funds are available for the LMT?

Currently, financial sources to promote or support the adoption of agroforestry LMT in Venezuela, are very limited. During the past seven years due to the drop in Venezuela's national income, the hyper-inflation economic cycle, and the international sanctions that affect country's economy, public investment in this sector has stopped. Restrictions associated to the COVID19 pandemic during 2019-2020, brought about additional financial restrictions. Public and private banks that used to offer credits to producers and entrepreneurs, reduced drastically or even closed their credit offer in the past years due to the constant loss of value of the national currency.

However, small and medium established enterprises have managed to resist through these hard times, and continue to offer their production to national or even international markets (i.e.: BIOALOE, Barunú, Naturaven, Granja Agroecológica Virgen de la Guadalupe, among others)

Some private entrepreneurs are already evaluating and investing in the future development of environmentally friendly and sustainable agro-productive projects, such as intelligent or precise crop farming in Paraguaná (*Finca Ictiotecnológica El Chuchuve*), establishment of cocuy organic plantations in Lara and Falcón states (Chumaceiro Liquors company), and aloe farm agroforestry plantations in western areas of Falcón (CORPRISMA), to supply national and international markets demands of specific products.

International cooperation funds provided through FAO and the PNUD as well as some private international foundations, have granted some financial resources to rural communities and NGOs to develop technology transfer and family enterprises projects, and to support scientific research.

With the support of the Small Donations Program of PNUD in Venezuela, INFALCOSTA, a local NGO, develops a project (2021-2022) working closely with local communities from Monte Cano in Paraguaná, north of Falcón state. The project aims to transfer appropriate technologies (improved artisan ovens, solar dehydrators, capture of rainwater, establishment of family orchards and local trees nurseries, food processing techniques), offering poor rural family's new opportunities and means to improve their ways of living based on locally sustainable practices. One of the expected results of this project is to produce plants to implement a reforestation program in degraded areas of Monte Cano Natural Monument.

PNUD and Impact Hub Caracas NGO are sponsoring the program "Innovation Eco" aimed at community and private enterprises that promote sustainable productive projects in Venezuela. In 2022, the project "Eco-desarrollo del Agave cocui y sus derivados" was one out of 10 selected projects to receive technical and financial advisory to escalate their family business in Falcón (Instagram account @impacthubcaracas).

With the support of FAO and the participation of the Ministry of Ecosocialism, Dr Miriam Díaz and INFALCOSTA produced a Manual for the restoration of the xerophytic forest in Venezuela that was published in 2022.

Misión Árbol is a national reforestation program established by the Venezuelan national environmental authority (MINEC). This program has managed to establish nurseries of native tree species, adapted to arid conditions, to supply trees at low cost for reforestation campaigns and for private reforestation initiatives.

Figure 15: Innovation Eco Program was started in 2021 by Impact Hub Caracas to provide support to Venezuelan small entrepreneurs' initiatives, oriented toward sustainability production.

4.1.3. *Current land use and potential land-use competition*

Agroforestry as a way to conserve xerophytic lands and biodiversity has been used in the region for the past 30-40 years. It started as isolated initiatives undertaken by a few private landowners as a way to improve crop and goat farming results, while making efficient use of scarce local resources, such as water and plant fodder for cattle raising.

Unfortunately, under the current socioeconomic circumstances, mitigation through forest conservation or reforestation in the arid zones does not seem to be very effective at the present time. One particular difficulty is related to gas and oil scarcity conditions that affect the population in rural and urban contexts all over the country, the extraction of forest wood has increased. In the arid zones, people are extracting wood as a source of fuel to cook food and also as a way of living (i.e., sell of wood).

In spite of these circumstances, the recent establishment of the 2030 NDG national goals and the approval of tax incentives might help revert this scenario. Future expansion of these sustainable initiatives seems to be closely tied to private investment.

Due to local soil fertility conditions, the productivity, and economic returns of short cycle vegetable crops such as onion, chives, coriander, pepper, chilli, tomato, and melon are very attractive for farmers in semiarid lands. In the short term, these vegetable crops are more profitable than agroforestry systems, despite the implicit risks of underground water over-exploitation for irrigation with the subsequent soil salinization and aridisation effects.

It is important to assess if currently the incentives granted by the government to plant and export specific food crops are competing with this LMT. This should be assessed by agronomic professionals, considering the carbon balance of each crop.

Economic incentive schemes to promote agroforestry sustainable food production systems while discouraging traditional vegetable agriculture should be designed and carefully implemented.

4.1.4. Climate risks & sensitivities

Studies based on the analysis of precipitation and evaporation ratios have concluded that dry territories all over the world have extended in the past 60 years and they will continue to do so under a high greenhouse gas emissions scenario during the XXI century. This global dry land expansion will increase the population affected by water scarcity and land degradation. At present time, dry lands cover 41% of land world surface and are home to 1/3 of its population (Feng & Fu, 2013). South America will be one of the regions with the highest expansion of semiarid lands.

According to previous studies (Martelo 2012, Ovalles et al. 2008), the most plausible future climate scenarios for Venezuela in 2060 will be dryer and warmer than the current conditions. Some expected impacts include increased risk of drought and wildfires, an increase in the frequencies and impacts of ENSO events in its warm and cold phases (El Niño and La Niña), and an 8% increase of areas under desertification risk (from 39% to near 47%), among others. Since in Venezuela drought periods are usually modulated by a complex interaction system between atmospheric-oceanic ENSO and superficial water temperatures in the North Tropical Atlantic Ocean, it is expected that climate change increases the frequency, severity, and extension of drought events in the country (Paredes-Trejo & Olivares, 2018). In 2015, Medina et al. explored future tendencies of seasonal dryness in Venezuela. Their results showed a clear expansion of areas with a negative hydric balance in 2050. Accordingly, arid areas will expand in 7,904 Km², and the greatest increase will occur in Falcón, Zulia and Lara states which are already the largest states in terms of aridity. These authors also found that semiarid lands will expand about 106,000 Km² into regions that currently belong to subhumid provinces (Medina et al. 2015).

In spite of hydric resources abundance in Venezuela, barely 5.7% of agricultural lands have irrigation systems (Ovalles et al., 2008, cited by Paredes-Trejo & Olivares, 2018); therefore agricultural production is very vulnerable to extreme drought events, with negative socio-economic consequences (i.e. food scarcity, health problems, economic losses) that affect rural communities and small producers with limited recovery capacities (Olivares et al., 2016a, 2016b, 2017, 2018; Hernández, 2008; Paredes et al. 2014; all cited by Paredes-Trejo & Olivares, 2018).

The future expected climate scenarios of increased dryness will affect plants and the associated fauna species in different ways. Some dry-tolerant bird or bat species may experience an expansion of their niches and geographical distribution while others with very specific niche requirements will be totally excluded or severely restricted in their distribution, hence affecting the survival and distribution patterns of those plants species that depend on them for their pollination or dispersal (Angela Martino, pers. comm).

Stakeholders agreed that the agroforestry LMT practices are sensitive to climate change, in particular to extreme drought and high temperatures. They also mentioned that although in these dry areas the occurrence of wildfires is not so frequent, certain specific localities may be sensitive to forest fires increase. Biodiversity loss, diminishing soil fertility, and increased soil salinization and desertification were the major foreseen negative effects. The loss of insects, birds, bats and small mammals' populations that act as pollinators or fruit dispersal agents, as well as natural pest control agents, was a major concern pointed out by stakeholders, since these animals provide essential ecosystem services in semi-arid regions of the country. Soil degradation and loss due to inappropriate agricultural management, cattle introduction and deforestation are expected to worsen under climate change scenarios.

Increased weather variability is perhaps the most negative climate change effect on agroforestry LMT in arid and semiarid territories in the country. The effect and consequences of the El Niño-La Niña cycles are evident on Venezuelan arid and semi-arid lands. For instance, the heavy rains that occurred during the La Niña phase in 2010-2011 affected Aloe vera crops and many cultivated lands were lost due to fungi and bacterial diseases; goat herds also suffered serious diseases. Floods in the lowlands affected urban and rural infrastructure, causing the loss of many roads and homes. The 2011 rainy year was followed by an intense three-year drought period that limited water availability for agricultural, industrial, and urban uses. Currently in 2022, an extended La Niña phase has increased the intensity and frequency of rainy events leading to the proliferation of African snails' populations, an invader species that affects crops and bring about health risks to rural communities.

In order to increase the success and resilience of the proposed LMTs in arid and semi-arid lands, special efforts must be done to apply efficient technologies to store excess rain during La Niña ENSO phase, increase water percolation rates to recharge underground reservoirs, reduce drainage speed and soil loss, and protect the degraded river basins to diminish the risks of lowland flooding. These activities contribute to a better endurance of rural communities during the inevitable drought periods that will follow during El Niño ENSO phase.

4.1.5. Economic implications

Careful planning and implementation of agroforestry systems may bring along more benefits than risks, in terms of economic, social, and environmental impacts. The appearance of new private entrepreneurs that are incorporating sustainability concepts and LMT in their businesses is a favourable sign in this regard. Some interviewed stakeholders expressed their concerns in relation to

larger initial investment costs and longer periods of time to start receiving economic returns. To overcome in part this handicap, early financial support and incentives are needed. However, these concerns only apply when establishing productive units in previously deforested or severely degraded lands. In those cases where there is a vegetation cover, a careful analysis of the land and soil conditions prior to the intervention will allow the design and implementation of a sustainable and diversified agro-productive plan that takes into account the local reality. This means that a new approach and economic rationale is required to assure the success of the LMT.

Stakeholders also pointed out that loan schemes applied to agricultural projects by national funding agencies and banks should be revised to incorporate agroforestry LMT budget items instead of those applied in intensive traditional non-sustainable agricultural activities (i.e. deforestation, agro-chemicals application, and soil cover removal). This means that there is a gap to be overcome between the financial institutions and producers who are willing to adopt sustainable agroforestry LMT.

Information on actual costs of implementing agroforestry at different scales is not readily available. Field assessment of the costs and on the GHG emissions reductions are still pending.

4.1.6. Co-benefits and trade-offs

Agroforestry systems contribute to preserving the landscape since these systems mimic natural conditions and maintain the continuity of the vegetation cover. They improve the percolation of rainwater and reduce water surface runoffs, therefore avoiding soil erosion and contributing to improve surface and underground water quality. Biodiversity could also be enhanced as long as a careful selection of plant species is assured. In this sense, the incorporation of legume tree species could also contribute to improving soil nitrogen fixation.

The success of agroforestry LMT solutions in arid and semiarid lands will highly depend on their capacity to provide food and useful resources to the farmers and the inhabitants of rural areas.

Therefore, the species selected to establish a particular agroforestry system are a key factor. Plant species should be tolerant and resilient to harsh climate conditions (i.e., increasing temperatures and water stress), and provide resources for the local population (i.e., fodder for goats and sheep, wood as fuel and building materials source, nutritive food and beverage sources, products demanded by local agroindustry with economic competitive value). These combined criteria have been used to design systems including *cují* legume trees (*Prosopis juliflora*), aloe and/or agave perennial herbs

According to some consulted experts, economic value and ecological criteria should be both taken into account for the design and implementation of these agroforestry systems. Selected plant species should also offer resources to support animal biodiversity. For instance, cardones (a type of columnar cacti) should be included in agroforestry systems in Falcón semiarid regions (as living fences, for instance), to assure the continuity of bat species corridors and migratory routes that feed on them and contribute, in turn, to the reproduction of these cacti species and other important groups of plants. So, plant species associations in the agroforestry systems are key for the success of this

mitigation strategy. It is important to mimic natural vegetation composition when designing and establishing new agroforestry systems.

Beyond the economic value, other biological and ecological considerations must be considered. Slow-growing plant species, such as cardones (columnar cacti), might not be such an attractive candidate for an economically sustainable agroforestry system when compared to aloe vera crop, for instance, but aloe cannot provide the same ecological services and support to the trophic web that cacti do. In brief, ecological, and economic benefits should be carefully assessed when designing and implementing agroforestry systems in semiarid lands.

Are there any other risks / co-benefits as part of the LMT implementation?

- 1) At small scales of development, agroforestry systems may not represent high-income levels, but they can provide food and resources to farmers and rural populations. The dynamics of human migrations could be improved, helping to keep the population in their original lands and offering them the adequate sustainable quality of living conditions, while reducing rural migration into impoverished urban centres, and preserving the continuity of rural systems.
- 2) Adoption of agroforestry systems by isolated small producers may not be successful nor generate the expected benefits when neighbouring production units still rely on conventional unsustainable agricultural practices. Under these circumstances conflicts of interest among producers in a region are prone to occur (i.e., organic aloe or watermelon cultivation may be affected by agro-chemicals application in surrounding areas; careless fire management in adjacent production units may affect forest barriers). Therefore, it is important to create conditions by offering incentives and/or imposing certain legal restrictions to producers located in larger areas (i.e., a complete river basin), so they feel akin to adopt agroforestry LMT practices.
- 3) The inclusion of foreign species in the agroforestry systems should be avoided.

Maintaining the original natural landscape conditions should be preferred instead of promoting drastic changes in the vegetation type and landscape, which could lead to unforeseen consequences.

Under climate change scenarios, agroforestry LMT can be considered as a promising option of preserving biodiversity and ecosystem services in a very fragile territory, such as the arid and semiarid lands of Venezuela. Agroforestry practices offers alternative and sustainable ways of living to local rural communities; besides, they are also novel agri-business opportunities to provide national and international markets interested in innovative products (i.e., nutraceuticals, cosmetics, food and beverages, and natural products economic sectors). Although traditional agricultural short-cycle vegetable products, such as onions, peppers, or tomatoes offer high and fast economic returns, the increasing temperatures, drought intensification and climate variability represent growing risks for producers and therefore more resilient and water-efficient crops will be needed in the near future. At the same time, it is urgent to adopt environment-friendly practices to slow down and revert desertification processes in the rural areas, as a way of providing sustainable and dignified ways of living to rural inhabitants, while maintaining the environmental services required by urban populations (i.e., water for human consumption, extreme weather events mitigation, among others).

Decisive action and incentives from the government together with communication and education programs can provide the needed impulse for a wider adoption of agroforestry LMT.

4.1.7. Risks associated with scaling up

Although establishing agroforestry systems similar to those that have been previously promoted in Falcón state in other Venezuelan zones is a feasible LMT solution, a successful scaling up depends on the understanding, support and acceptance of the local communities, landowners and land managers.

Previous analyses and thorough studies of the local socio-economic and environmental conditions must be performed in advance to adapt and adequate previously identified agroforestry solutions or design new ones.

The possible impacts of establishing these systems (escalate) should be previously assessed, in particular, the impacts over the local biota must be considered.

4.1.8. Research gaps

- a) The systematization, evaluation, and diffusion of results of previous experiences are necessary.
- b) Detailed long term assessment and quantification of environmental impacts/benefits of agroforestry models at different scales could provide deep insights for the scaling up of this LMT.
- c) Long term studies of economic flows and carbon balance of proposed agroforestry systems are lacking. Special efforts should be devoted to fulfilling these gaps.

5. Agroforestry in dry forest lands

5.1.1. Introduction

The contribution of the Bolivarian Republic of Venezuela to the global emission of 2010 was 0.49%, which places it within the category of low emission countries, both globally and regionally (Second National Communication on Climate Change, 2017). According to this communication, total GHG emissions reached 243,380 gigagrams of carbon dioxide equivalent (Gg CO₂eq), shared as 124,979 Gg of CO₂, 5,011 Gg of methane (CH₄) and 43 Gg of nitrous oxide (N₂O) (52%, 43% and 5% respectively if estimated as CO₂eq). The contributions per economic sector to the total national emissions were: 84% (203,399 Gg CO₂eq) in the Energy sector; 12% (26,921 Gg CO₂eq) in the Industrial sector; 2% (6,664 Gg CO₂eq) in the Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use sector, and finally, 2% (6,395 Gg CO₂eq) in the Waste sector.

However, as part of the policies established in the country's economic and social development plan, Venezuela intends to implement a National Mitigation Plan in conjunction with a National Adaptation Plan. In this sense and on a voluntary basis since 1995, the DANAC Foundation has been implementing and operationally validating four of the seven strategies and/or practices (NETPS) that make up the LANDMARC mitigation activities matrix.

Agroforestry systems (AFS), which include silvopastoral systems (SPS), can be defined as dynamic and ecological systems of natural resource management, based on the spatial integration of trees with agricultural crops and/or pastures, in order to diversify and maintain a sustained production, providing social, economic and environmental benefits. They are viable forms of land use that are governed by the principle of sustained yield and at the same time allow production to increase progressively through the integration of forestry activities with agricultural and/or livestock activities Macdicken and Vergara (1990); Montagnini (1992); Nair (1993); (Couto and Pasos, 1995).

These kinds of productive systems are considered as key alternatives in the current trend to promote the transformation of conventional agriculture into "climate-smart agriculture". This concept integrates the three dimensions of sustainable development (economic, social, and environmental), jointly addressing food security and climate challenges. It is based on three fundamental pillars: a) sustainably increase agricultural productivity and income; b) adapt and build resilience to climate change; c) reduce and/or eliminate greenhouse gas emissions where possible (Montagnini 2015).

Agroforestry systems (AFSs) are nature-based technologies and good land-use practices that contribute to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions through carbon capture and sequestration in, above, and below-ground biomass. Contreras (2019) using Emergy Analysis proved the ecological sustainability, financial viability, and higher energy efficiency of PBSs in the use of natural resources when compared to other forms of land use.

The most widespread agroforestry system in tropical regions is the "Taungya" system, a term that translates as "hill cultivation," in which annual agricultural crops were established in teak (*Tectona*

grandis) forest plantations with the objective of providing food for the workers by using available space during the first two to four years of the development of the plantation. It was developed at the end of the 19th century in Burma, introduced in South Africa in 1887 and taken to India in 1890, expanding later to other regions of Asia, Africa, and Latin America (Mac-Dicken and Vergara 1990, Nair 1993).

In 1996, DANAC Foundation established the Agroforestry System Program. The project: “Establishment and Evaluation of a Multispecific Agroforestry Forest”, undertaken from 1996 to 2006, helped to consolidate this Program through the development and study of agroforestry production systems applying a sustainable development approach (DANAC, 2021). The LMT is the Taungya Agroforestry System and SSP is known in DANAC as Multispecific agroforestry forests or MAF (Bosques Agroforestales Multiespecíficos or BAM), being its main objective of the project was the establishment of 100 ha of valuable timber trees, bamboo (*Bambusa vulgaris*) and guadua (*Guadua angustifolia*), in association with short-cycle crops.

DANAC is located in the San Javier sector, via Guarataro, San Felipe, Yaracuy State, 15 km from San Felipe, the state capital, at coordinates 10°41'45" North and 68°49'00" West. It is part of the Tropical Dry Forest (BST) life zone of the central-western region of Venezuela (Figure 16), however, Torres and Madero (1999, cited by Messa, 2009), consider that it belongs to a transition zone between the Tropical Dry Forest and the Tropical Humid Forest.

Figure 16. Location of the LMT, DANAC Foundation, San Javier, Estado Yaracuy, Venezuela.

San Javier is located at an altitude of 100 masl; it has a clear rainy season between May and November, that concentrates 76% of the waterfall, that reaches an average annual rainfall of approximately 1370 mm, with an average monthly temperature of 26° C, with annual maximum and minimum averages

of 31 and 22°C, respectively. evapotranspiration of 14 mm, maximum relative humidity of 90% and minimum relative humidity of 60%. The average annual evaporation is approximately 2070 mm, while the average annual relative humidity is 83% with a monthly variation of + 1.6%.

The LMT is located in the Cordillera de la Costa physiographic province in west-northern Venezuela, specifically in the natural region of the Yaracuy depression, which forms an elongated and dissymmetrical tectonic valley that presents relief in the form of a large, inclined plane or *glacís de explayamiento*, oriented towards the Yaracuy River, with a predominance of two types of landscapes (Messa, 2009).

The biogeographic context of the LMT is devoid of natural vegetation, except for some relicts and gallery forests in the Yaracuy River meadows, which were formerly exploited for banana cultivation. The vegetation in the upper and middle reaches of the Yaracuy depression consists of the natural vegetation of semi-deciduous and deciduous forests, while the lower reaches are dominated by natural vegetation of semi-deciduous and evergreen forests, alternating with deciduous forests (Messa 2009). Most of the depression's surface has been deforested to establish pastures, annual crops and irrigated semi-permanent crops (Messa 2009).

Tree species more frequently found are: Bambú (*Bambusa vulgaris*), Bucare (*Erythrina glauca*), Caña Brava (*Gynerium sagittatum*), Caoba (*Swietenia macrophylla*), Ceiba (*Ceiba pentandra*), Jabillo (*Hura crepitans*), Guácimo (*Guazuma ulmifolia*), Mata ratón (*Gliricidia sepium*), Yagrumo (*Cecropia sp*), Roble (*Platymiscium diadelphum*), Samán (*Samanea saman*), Mijao (*Anacardium exelsum*), Cedro (*Cedrela odorata*), Jobo (*Spondias mombin*), among others.

The DANAC Foundation for Agricultural Research (formerly known as Desarrollos Agrícolas Naranja Asociación Civil), is a non-governmental non-profit organization (NGO), supported by Polar Enterprises Foundation (FEP). Since 1986, the DANAC Foundation has contributed to scientific and technological agricultural knowledge, food production, rural communities support and environmental protection in Venezuela (DANAC Foundation 2021). It has been mainly dedicated to research and development of technologies for the genetic improvement of rice, corn, and soy, building alliances with farmers, universities and public and private institutions related to the national science, technology, and innovation system of Venezuela.

With the agroforestry system known in DANAC as the Multispecies Agroforestry Forest (MAF, Figure 9, it was possible to optimize the spatial diversification of land use through the adoption of good agricultural, forestry and livestock management practices, with the permanent participation of the rural communities neighbouring its productive environment and in strict compliance with current legislation regarding the environment and natural resources, labour rights and sustainable human and rural development.

Figure 17. Image of the “sistema agroforestal multiestratificado”, Fundación DANAC. San Javier, Yaracuy State, Venezuela (GoogleEarth, 2005).

According to the results reported by Messa (2009) for different types of land use, total soil organic carbon (COS) fluctuated between 39.04 and 79.24 Mg ha⁻¹. ha, with the highest values corresponding to primary forest and grasslands with scattered trees. The first 20 cm of soil depth concentrated 44% to 63% of the soil organic carbon. The total C stored varied between 63.79 and 233.20 Mg ha⁻¹. The C fixation rate of the agroforestry systems (wooded pasture and forage bank) was 3.90 and 2.56 T ha⁻¹ respectively, these amounts represented three times the amount of carbon fixed by the sugarcane crop with 1.15 T ha⁻¹.

The total C stock varied between 63.79 and 233.20 Mg ha⁻¹, being 3.2 times greater in the Primary Forest than the average value of intervened units. Pasture in alleys, fodder banks and sugar cane units stored between 27 to 29% of total C observed in the primary forest, whereas it reached 43% in the improved pasture with scattered trees unit. The rate of C fixation was 0.96; 2.56; 1.15 and 3.90 Mg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ for PAL, FB, SCC and PST units. The removals of CO₂ from the studied units varied between 3.52 and 14.30 Mg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, corresponding the highest values to the pasture with scattered trees and primary forest units. These results show the potential of improved pastures with scattered trees in carbon storage in livestock systems. The overall GHG balance was influenced by the distribution and management of LUTs in the livestock production system. In this sense, the Grassland with Sparse Trees and Forage Storage units showed a net positive balance, which shows the importance of silvopastoral systems in their contribution to the removal of carbon from the atmosphere.

These results show that AFSs play an important role in mitigating CC by reducing the pressure on forests, which are the largest reservoir of C, in addition to contributing to the uptake of C in the tree component, in crops and soils (Montagnini and Nair 2004, cited by Montagnini 2015). The potential for the capture of C by the SAF is highly variable, depending on the site, type of SAF, species involved, age and management (Montagnini 2015).

In general, AFSs with perennials accumulate more C than AFSs with annuals due to the additional contribution of the trees or shrubs of the perennial crop. In conclusion, it can be said that AFSs with perennial crops can be important in the storage of C, while AFSs with annual crops and intensive management are more similar to conventional agriculture (Montagnini 2015).

According to Guerra & Messa-Arboleda (2017), the most relevant results obtained between 1997 and 2015, were: consolidation of the BAM as a biophysical unit of environmental conservation, experimental and demonstrative agroforestry production; increase of soil organic matter and reduction of losses of arable layer due to water erosion; increase of soil moisture retention and decrease of sediment and agrochemical loads in runoff waters; improved habitats and food supply for more than 114 species of fauna; protection of the natural forest and in situ conservation of 19 agroforestry genetic resources in seedling stands, arboretums, etc.; CO₂ capture, improvement of the microclimate and rural landscape; 140,000 trees planted on farms and in communities; 16 graduate and postgraduate projects supported; transfer of products and results to 4,000 users through workshops, courses, guided tours, consulting, etc.; 20 presentations at technical-scientific meetings; and 100 publications in print, digital and audiovisual media.

5.1.2. Policy context

The planning system in force in Venezuela, applicable to the national, state, metropolitan and municipal levels, comprises two categories of processes: those oriented to territorial planning and management (long term) and those oriented to a specific management period (medium and short term). The first category, i.e., long-term processes or plans (20 years or more) are generated from the articles of the organic laws for Land Management (1983), Urban Planning (1987), Environment (2007), Municipal Public Power (2010), Water Law (2007), Biodiversity Management (2008), and the Law of Forests and Forest Management.

Thus, for example, in 1983 the Organic Law for Land Management was enacted, allowing the integration of the land management process with development strategies, i.e., regulating and locating socioeconomic activities with respect to the physical-spatial conditions for the exploitation and "rational" use of natural resources, incorporating the protection-valuation of the "environment", its self-regulation capacities, specific conditions and ecological limitations (LOOT, 1983).

The regulatory framework at the national and international levels has taken important steps to encourage the strengthening of inclusive governance for environmental conservation and management. Two important processes have opened opportunities for addressing the effects of climate change in rural and urban areas. First, changes in national regulations as a result of the 1999 constitution; and second, the approval and ratification of international agreements.

International agreements become important for the development of national and local regulations and instruments for environmental conservation, addressing the effects of climate change and guaranteeing the right to enjoy a healthy environment. Their importance lies in providing guidelines for the establishment of inclusive environmental governance by not limiting themselves to

government action commitments, but rather in raising the importance and need for private, community and all stakeholders' participation as a mechanism for the management and solution of socio-environmental conflicts. The main international agreements approved by law that are related to climate change and its effects are presented in Annex 1.

In the Venezuelan legal context, in accordance with the Constitution and the International Legal Framework on Environment, Conservation and Climate Change subscribed by the country, a series of laws have been developed to address the existing conditions of vulnerability, such as Law of Coastal Zones, Law of Forests, Law of Integral Management of Socio-Natural and Technological Risks and Law of Management of Biological Diversity; as well as different laws have been promoted and approved that somehow face the issue of the affectation derived from Climate Change: Organic Law of the Environment, Criminal Law of the Environment, Law of Waters, Law of Integral Management of Garbage and Law of Rational and Efficient Use of Energy, among others.

The "Bosques Agroforestales Multiespecíficos" (BAM) of the DANAC Foundation, since its creation, has received the unconditional support of the Fundación Empresas Polar (FEP); this foundation has promoted and supported DANAC institutionally and financially through the Sustainable Tropical Agriculture Program. FEP is a non-profit social organization that is part of "Empresas Polar", a conglomerate of large and small private industries in the food production sector for human consumption. In Venezuela, Empresas Polar has established itself as a diversified, solid industry committed to the socio-economic development of the country. Products such as POLAR beer, PAN precooked corn flour, MAZEITE edible oil, PRIMOR rice and pasta, EFE ice cream, a subsidiary of Pepsi-Cola and other emblematic food and beverage brands make up the list of products consumed in the world food market.

Together, the two Foundations (DANAC and POLAR) have implemented research and extension programs in agroforestry and environmental matters to consolidate the LMT - "Multispecies Agroforestry Forests" in which the efficiency of the good use of natural resources and the contribution to climate change mitigation and compliance with the Sustainable Development Goals of the 2030 Agenda has been proven.

In addition, there has been technical and scientific support from another very important institutional actor, the Faculty of Agronomy (FAGRO) of the Central University of Venezuela (UCV), Messa (2009).

In the context of sustainable rurality, other actors have been incorporated as protagonists in the agro-productive processes. These actors and users of the LMT total 118 people who have the benefit of being directly employed. In addition, another 354 people benefit indirectly from the socio-productive relationships generated by the LMT.

The most important, both in terms of extension and of contributions or benefits generated, was the system of legume species intercropped in the plantations of timber trees. These crops were selected to improve degraded Class III soils according to the FAO classification, due to the presence of a conglomerate and rock horizon, salinisation, and frequent periods of waterlogging. In the period

between 1997 and 2004, 150.5 ha of legume species, including 109.3 ha of quinchoncho and 41.2 ha of crotalaria were established. Cover crops remained in the field for a couple of years until they were incorporated into the soil with a harrow pass, after harvesting the grain to ensure the seed for the establishment of new areas the following year. This was particularly the case of the quinchoncho, which was harvested by hand by members of neighbouring communities for 5 years. In the period 1999 – 2004, a total of 7,322 kg of quinchoncho were harvested. The product obtained was distributed in three parts for the communities and one for DANAC Foundation as seeds for the next plantations.

The management of the LMT and the benefits it generates have strengthened the strategic alliances with the families of small farmers who live in harmony and solidarity with the Foundation in the vicinity of Hacienda El Naranjal in the San Javier sector in the State of Yaracuy. The aforementioned producers make up rural communities near the foundation, occupying an area of approximately 272 hectares, of which 67 are gallery forests and environmental protection areas or forest areas of the "Tropical Dry Forest" biome.

Which funds are available for the LMT?

Fundación Danac is a non-governmental, non-profit organization that develops projects and programs focused on research and technology transfer related to food security and sovereignty, good land use and sustainable agricultural development. The funds for its operation come from self-management, the contribution of capital from Empresas Polar and the competition in national and international calls for research, development, and technological innovation projects.

5.1.3. Current land use and potential land-use competition

For 24 years, the DANAC Foundation, through its organizational policy, has implemented specific actions to mitigate greenhouse gases using nature-based strategies. Since 1995 and at all levels of the organization, a corporate commitment was established to carry out activities in all contexts that, today, are aimed at meeting the Sustainable Development Goals. For the next decades 2030 - 2050, it is projected to be one of the main organizations of technological innovation for the development of agricultural production and agroforestry systems in the country, whose carbon balance tends to neutrality (Guerra, 2021). In order to achieve these goals, there is already a platform for the mitigation of emissions based on the good use of land, which is the LMT or "Multispecific Agroforestry Forests". Likewise, in the medium term, corporate actions will be undertaken to quantify emissions, including avoided emissions from the program to eradicate the use of fire and from agroindustrial decarbonization actions and strategies within the framework of Empresas Polar's environmental policies. These actions are carried out in order to contribute to the Nationally Determined Contributions (NDC's) of the agri-food sector, meeting the criteria of the Kyoto Protocol and the guidelines of the Paris Agreement and the Sustainable Development Goals.

Approximately 50% of Venezuelan territory is covered by forests, 90% of which are concentrated south of the Orinoco River in the Guayana Region. Most of these forests are located in the lowlands.

Based on satellite images, the country's forest cover was estimated at 427,000 km² in 1996 (Bevilacqua and Miranda 2002). However, in the lands north of the Orinoco, which concentrate 85% of the national population, the forests have been subjected to strong pressures as a consequence of the development of different economic activities (MARN-UNDP-GEF 2005).

In Venezuela, agricultural lands are severely degraded due to excessive use of machinery and chemical inputs, among other aspects. Likewise, the growing need for land for urban and industrial development has often been covered at the cost of loss of land with high agricultural capacity, generating significant soil degradation problems (Guerra, 2021). According to the same author, for the year 1978, it was established that the areas that did not present limitations in soil characteristics for good agricultural development in Venezuela occupied barely 2 % of the territory, most of these areas have relief limitations (44 %) and low fertility (32 %), poor drainage (18 %) and aridity or scarcity of rainfall (4 %). Precisely, this general condition of the country means that agricultural activity, if not well managed under the precepts of sustainability, can generate or intensify soil degradation processes.

In the mid-2000s, as a result of socio-economic changes and government policies, there was a growing interest on the part of agricultural producers and landowners in adopting forestry and agroforestry systems. Although this meant an increase in the area occupied with FFS, it was determined that the maintenance and management of most of these systems are deficient, since producers have little knowledge on the subject, often do not have clear objectives of the forestry component in the production unit and do not use technical advice (Guerra, 2021).

In this context, Fundación Danac consolidated the LMT the "Multi-species Agroforestry Forest", which is a biophysical unit of environmental conservation and agroforestry production designed to recover agricultural soils with severe limitations, major restrictions for crops and conservation needs. In addition, the production unit socializes the knowledge generated on the management of small and medium agroforestry systems applying economic, environmental, and social criteria. Currently, the Multi-species Agroforestry Forest has 73 Agroforestry Validation and Productive Demonstration Plots and 10 Conservation Plots for soil, water, and agroforestry phylogenetic resources (Guerra, 2021).

Are there other land use developments that compete with the expansion of the LMT, and if so, how do those affect the scaling-up of the LMTs?

The region where the LMT is located in a rural territory designated for agricultural production in the national land-use plan. There is currently no population pressure or competition from other productive activities. According to Guerra, (2021) the LMT does not have and should not have problems maintaining its continuity in the short, medium, and long term. Consequently, the scaling up of LMT within the LANDMARC context is positive and without limitations, as long as balanced governance is maintained, and the bioethical and eco-sociological precepts of Sustainable Rural Development are preserved.

5.1.4. Climate risks & sensitivities

In the First National Communication on Climate Change in Venezuela, climate type patterns were estimated according to Thornthwaite for the temperature and precipitation variables. According to the estimates suggested by the models, it is predicted that the LMT will be most affected by the following climatic events: heat waves, pronounced droughts, forest fires and an increase, or change in climate variability. It is estimated that the most likely future climate for Venezuela will be drier and hotter than the current climate, although precipitation could increase locally. Figure 5 shows the territorial distribution of climate types in the future, according to the two models run for the Intermediate Climate Scenario. It can be observed that at present, practically all the northern area of the country (with some exceptions) presents the three dry climate types (arid, semi-arid and dry sub-humid), which the United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification and Drought considers as critical climates. Consequently, the future climate in the medium and long term will be drier; therefore, it is necessary to optimize food production strategies based on the intensive use of open field lands, being agroforestry systems the ones that will provide greater resilience to climate variability and change.

Figure 18. Territorial distribution of climate types in the future, according to the two models run for the Intermediate Climate Scenario

5.1.5. Economic implications

Venezuela's national accounts do not consider the environmental goods and services provided by nature. The sylvopastoral LMT *per se* is already economically competitive because it incorporates the environmental sustainability component in all activities. It is estimated that it will be even more competitive when the value of ecosystem benefits is included in the financial and/or economic analysis compared to other forms of land use. Nevertheless, the DANAC Foundation has been implementing technologies based on nature and good land use, such as agroforestry systems and agriculture, for more than twenty years.

In this context, in 2015, Escalante and Guerra presented a review of the successful agroforestry Taungya systems in DANAC Foundation Venezuela that include those in which short-cycle and semi-annual crops such as plantain (*Musa* spp.), quinchoncho (*Cajanus cajan*), and other species have been interspersed within high commercial value timber plantations during the first two years, in order to improve soil fertility, control weeds, produce food for the communities involved, and provide an additional income that makes up for the initial investment in forest plantations. Taungya systems significantly reduce the costs of establishing plantations in the first years and improve the financial performance of the investment in wood, since several years must pass before obtaining economic benefits. These avoided costs at the beginning of the forest plantation are very important for the financial performance of the system.

5.1.6. Co-benefits and trade-offs

What are the risks (negative side-effects) or co-benefits (positive side-effects) of the LMT:

Aspect	Negative effect	Positive effect
Agricultural production	In some cases, there will be a reduction in production and annual financial profit from monoculture.	Sustainable: Natural elements are maintained in the long term for future harvests (water, soil, biodiversity, soil carbon, soil macro and microbiota).
Landscape	None	With agroforestry diversification, the landscape will be more protected, more attractive and more pleasing to the eye.
Biodiversity	None	Increased plant biodiversity, resulting in a greater number of niches, livelihoods and refuges for wildlife.
Nitrogen emissions	Reduced	Very low or almost nil because there is no enteric fermentation or discharge of the livestock component.
Water quality	None	Water quality will be improved by substantially reducing erosion and eliminating leaching from polluting discharges.

Are there any other risks /co-benefits as part of the LMT implementation?

No other risks are foreseen for the moment, but there are many co-benefits associated with the sustainability of the productive systems due to the addition of carbon. Likewise, there will be new income from the commercialization of timber, as the trees will be reaching the cutting age.

Could you discuss the trade-offs of the LMT?

As the plantations are dedicated to carbon storage, the opportunity cost increases. As a consequence, as the decision is made to have less aggressive strategies for fuelwood production and, at the same time, the forest or plantation is maintained for carbon storage, a greater amount of income from the commercial timber activity is foregone and a greater amount of carbon storage is obtained, due to the tradeoff that exists between harvesting for carbon storage or fuelwood production (Merchán & De Freitas 2006).

The LMT will be prepared to exchange technical and scientific information, goods and services such as the sale of seeds and other inputs, consultancy, technologies and, in the medium term, it is expected to obtain income from the exchange of CO₂ credits or bonuses as soon as the Venezuelan government incorporates into the national environmental policy the entry into the global carbon offset market.

5.1.7. Risks associated with scaling up

The main risks are socioeconomic, associated with changes in government public policies that may affect the operation of the DANAC Foundation. At the local level, there are no problems of scale due to the solid governance relationships of the LMT with the local actors, directly and indirectly, involved with it (since the beginning of its foundation), which has materialized in an excellent and harmonious community relationship - business.

5.1.8. Research gaps

This LMT has been a pioneer in setting the standard for the generation of the administrative, technological and methodological instruments necessary to be drafted to contribute to the design of a private enterprise approach to Agroforestry LMT in Venezuela. Comparative studies are required with other regions of the country to accomplish this goal.

6. Conclusions

Venezuela offers a rich range of opportunities for developing and implementing LMTs within the framework of NETP. Some of the major key points to achieve progress in the LMTs application in Venezuela are: a) the diversity of ecosystems, b) its status as a tropical country that favours the development of forests with a high capacity for carbon fixation and storage, c) the value of the traditional practices of local populations and human resources of the technical and academic sector. Additionally, the Venezuelan legal frame, starting with the National Constitution, indicates the state's obligation to promote public participation and consult the citizens regarding public policies. In spite of these good intentions, in most cases, these processes have historically, confronted significant barriers that limited relevant knowledge shared co-creation and solutions implementation. The analysis of several experiences revealed that top-down initiatives are prone to fail when public institutions lack efficient organisational mechanisms or continuity in their policies to lead and execute these processes until its completion. In contrast, bottom-up experiences or intercultural approaches conducted by local communities, supported by academics, collective organisations and official or private sectors showed promissory capabilities and positive results. This strategy provides more opportunities to build up safe spaces for the coproduction of knowledge by enhancing the inter-sectorial interactions required for the successful adoption of sustainable LMTs.

7. References

ACFIMAN-SACC, 2018: “Primer Reporte Académico de Cambio Climático 2018: Contribución de los Grupos de Trabajo I, II y III al Primer Reporte Académico de Cambio Climático (PRACC) de la Secretaría Académica de Cambio Climático (SACC) de la Academia de Ciencias Físicas, Matemáticas y Naturales (ACFIMAN) de Venezuela”. [Villamizar, A., E. Buroz Castillo, R. Lairer Centeno, & J. A. Gómez (Eds.)]. EDICIONES ACFIMAN – CITECI, CARACAS.

Armas W, Arvelo M, Delgado A & Aubettere R. 2006. El circuito caprino en los estados Lara y Falcón (Venezuela), 2001-2003: Una visión estratégica. *Agroalimentaria* 11 (23):

Asamblea Constituyente. 1999. Constitución de la República Bolivariana de Venezuela. Gaceta Oficial Extraordinaria No. 5.453. Abril 24, 2000. Caracas, Venezuela.

Barradas AC & Ribeiro KT. 2021. Integrated Fire Management: Serra Geral do Tocantins Ecological Station’s Journey (2001 to 2020). *Biodiversidade Brasileira*, 11(2): 139-152,

DOI: 10.37002/biobrasil.v11i2.1739

Barros H. 2006. Evaluación de la posible intrusión marina y salinización de pozos costeros en áreas piloto al norte de Tocópero y Puerto Cumarebo, estado Falcón. Informe final de proyecto. Fundacite Falcón. Mimeografiado. 63 pp.

Bevilacqua M & Miranda M. 2002. Cobertura y protección de los bosques. In Situación de los bosques en Venezuela. La región Guayana como caso de estudio. Informe del Observatorio Mundial de Bosques Observatorio Mundial de Bosques (OMB - Venezuela). Instituto de Recursos Mundiales (WRI) - Fundación Polar. Caracas, VE, ImagenColor S.A. 133 p.

Bilbao BA, Leal AV & Méndez CL. Indigenous Use of Fire and Forest Loss in Canaima National Park, Venezuela. Assessment of and Tools for Alternative Strategies of Fire Management in Pemón Indigenous Lands. *Human Ecology*, 38(5): 663–673, 2010. doi:10.1007/s10745-010-9344-0.

Bilbao B, Mistry J, Millán A & Berardi, A. Sharing Multiple Perspectives on Burning: Towards a Participatory and Intercultural Fire Management Policy in Venezuela, Brazil, and Guyana. *Fire*, 2(3), 39, 2019.

Bilbao BA, *et al.* 2020. Wildfire, p. 459-524. In: Moreno JM, Laguna-Defior C, Barros V, Calvo Buendía E, Marengo JA, Oswald Spring U (orgs.). *Adaptation to Climate Change Risks in Ibero-American Countries — RIOCCADAPT Report*. McGraw-Hill, Madrid, España (ISBN: 9788448621643), p. 716.

Bilbao BA, Millán A, Vessuri H, Salazar-Gascón R, Gómez-Martínez R. 2021. To burn or not to burn? The history behind the construction of a new paradigm of fire management in Venezuela through interculturality. Local actions of national and regional impact. *Biodiversidade Brasileira BioBrasil. Vol. International Wildland Fire Conference, (2)*: 99-127. DOI: 10.37002/biobrasil.v11i2.1878

Briceño Méndez M. 2005. Estudio de tendencias y perspectivas del Sector Forestal en América Latina Documento de Trabajo. Estudio Nacional Venezuela. Ministerio del Ambiente y de los Recursos Naturales & Organización de las Naciones Unidas para la Agricultura y la Alimentación, Roma. 115 pp.

CIEZA. <http://cieza-unefm.blogspot.com>

CIARA. 2014. Proyecto de Desarrollo Rural Sostenible para las zonas semiáridas de los estados Falcón y Lara, Segunda fase (PROSALAFa II). Informe de Terminación. MAT-CIARA, Barquisimeto. 124 pp. <https://es.calameo.com/read/001625975c56e86ec5a60>

Congreso Nacional de Venezuela. 1983. Ley orgánica para la ordenación del territorio del 26JUL1983. Gaceta oficial extraordinaria N° 3.238 del 11AGO1983. Caracas.

Couto L, & Passos C. 1995. O estado da arte e do conhecimento do uso de eucaliptos em sistemas agroflorestais em Minas Gerais, Brasil. In *Eucalipto uma visão global*. AMDA. EMBRAPA Florestas, SIF. Belo Horizonte, Brasil.

Corona V. 2015. Desarrollo de actividades agroforestales y evaluación de un sistema silvopastoril multiestrato en la Fundación para la Investigación Agrícola DANAC, San Javier, Municipio San Felipe, estado Yaracuy, Venezuela. Trabajo Especial de Grado. Universidad de Los Andes, Facultad de Ciencias Forestales y Ambientales. Mérida. 66 pp.

Contreras C. 2019 Evaluación de la Sostenibilidad de Sistemas Agroforestales por medio de la Metodología Emergética. Tesis Doctoral en Desarrollo Sostenible Universidad Simón Bolívar, Caracas. Venezuela, 167p.

Darvill T. 2002. Taima-Taima. In: The concise Oxford dictionary of archaeology.

Delgado A, Armas W, D'Aubeterre R, Hernández C & Araque C. 2010. Sostenibilidad del sistema de producción *Capra hircus-Aloe vera* en el semiárido de Cauderales (estado Lara, Venezuela). *Agroalimentaria* 16(31)

Díaz M. 1988. Las zonas áridas al norte de Venezuela: Hacia el aprovechamiento racional de sus recursos naturales renovables. En: Caliman A. & Paredes L. Zonas áridas. Fundacite Zulia, Maracaibo. pp 33-54.

Díaz M. 1994. Caracterización ecofisiológica de las especies arbóreas predominantes en las zonas áridas y semiáridas. Trabajo de ascenso para optar a la categoría de Profesor Asociado. UNEFM, Coro. 105 pp.

Díaz M. 2001. Ecología experimental y ecofisiología: Bases para el uso sostenible de los recursos naturales de las zonas áridas neo-tropicales. *Interciencia* 26 (10). http://ve.scielo.org/scielo.php?pid=S0378-18442001001000009&script=sci_abstract

Díaz M. 2002. Programa *Agave cocui*: Ciencia y Tecnología al servicio del hombre de las zonas áridas. Fundacite Falcón, Coro. 31 pp.

Díaz M. In press. Manual de restauración del bosque xerofítico en Venezuela. FAO. 110 pp.

Díaz M. & Granadillo E. 2005. The significance of episodic rains for reproductive phenology and productivity in trees in semiarid regions of northwestern Venezuela. *Trees* 19: 336- 348.

Díaz M, Yépez L. & Gotopo E. 2018. *Agave cocui*: un noble de las zonas áridas de Venezuela. Desde el Herbario CICY 10: 137–143. Centro de Investigación Científica de Yucatán, A.C. http://www.cicy.mx/sitios/desde_herbario/

Durán N. 2018. Estrategia Nacional Neutralidad en la Degradación de Tierras (NDT) hacia el 2030. Informe final. Ministerio del Poder Popular para el Ecosocialismo (MINEC), Caracas. 51 pp.

Edwards E & Díaz M. 2006. Ecophysiology of *Pereskia guamacho*: a cactus with leaves. *Plant, Cell & Environment* 29 (2): 247-256.

EDELCA-CORPOELEC. 2008. La Cuenca del río Caroní. Una visión en cifras. Corporación Eléctrica Nacional/EDELCA, Puerto Ordaz, Venezuela.

Eloy L, Schmidt IB, Borges SL, Ferreira MC & Dos Santos AT. 2018. Seasonal fire management by traditional cattle ranchers prevents the spread of wildfire in the Brazilian Cerrado. *Ambio* 2018.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-018-1118-8>

Escalante E. & Á Guerra. 2015. Sistemas Taungya en plantaciones de especies forestales de alto valor comercial en Venezuela. In: Montagnini, F; Somarriba, E; Murgueitio, E; Fassola, H; Eibl, B. 2015. *Sistemas Agroforestales. Funciones Productivas, Socioeconómicas y Ambientales*. Serie técnica. Informe técnico 402. CATIE, Turrialba, Costa Rica. Editorial CIPAV, Cali, Colombia. 454pp.

Ewel J, Madriz A & Tosi J. 1976. Zonas de vida de Venezuela. (2da. Ed.). Caracas. FONAIAP-Ministerio de Agricultura y Cría. 265 pp.

Finer M, Mamani N (2022) Deforestation Hotspots in the Venezuelan Amazon. MAAP: 155.

Fundación DANAC. 2021. Programa de Sistemas Agroforestales. <https://danac.org.ve/press/agroforestal>

Feng S. & Q. Fu. 2013. Expansion of global drylands under warming climate. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* 13 (19). DOI: 10.5194/acp-13-10081-2013.

Gómez E, Picón G, Bilbao BA. 2000 Los incendios forestales en Iberoamérica. Caso Venezuela. In: R Vélez-Muñoz, ed. *La defensa contra incendios forestales. Fundamentos y experiencias*, pp. 800–830. Madrid, Spain: McGraw-Hill.

Guerra A & Messa–Arboleda H. 2017. Conservación ambiental y socialización del conocimiento en la gestión del bosque agroforestal multiespecífico de Fundación Danac. *Gestión y gerencia* 11(3): septiembre-diciembre 2017.

Guerra A. 2021 Comunicación personal

Fundacite Falcón, Fundacite Lara, Fundacite Trujillo & Fundacite Zulia. 2009. Propuesta conjunta sobre ovinos y caprinos. Mimeografiado. 19 pp.

Huffman, MR. The many elements of traditional fire knowledge: synthesis, classification, and aids to cross-cultural problem solving in fire dependent systems around the world. 2013. *Ecol. Soc.* 18 doi:10.5751/ES-05843-180403

INFALCOSTA. n/d. Reserva Biológica de Montecano. <http://infalcosta.blogspot.com/p/montecano.html>

Instituto Interamericano de Cooperación para la Agricultura (IICA). 1983. 1er. Seminario Nacional sobre Agroenergía en Venezuela. 674 pp.

<https://repositorio.iica.int/handle/11324/15610>

Lizundia-Loiola, J., M.L. Pettinari y E. Chuvieco, 2020: Temporal anomalies in burned area trends: satellite estimations of the Amazonian 2019 fire crisis (Letter). *Remote Sensing*, 12, 151.

Le Queré, C et al. Global carbon budget 2015. *Earth System Science Data*, 6(1): 235-263, 2014.

Macdicken KG & Vergara. 1990. *Agroforestry: classification and management*. John Wiley, ed. New York. 382 pp.

MARN-PNUD-GEF (Ministerio del Ambiente y de los Recursos Naturales, Programa de las Naciones Unidas para el Desarrollo y Fondo Mundial para el Medio Ambiente). 2005. *Primera Comunicación Nacional de Cambio Climático de Venezuela*. Caracas, VE, MARN. 141 p.

Martelo M T. 2012. Impacto del cambio climático en la agricultura de Venezuela. *Revista de la Facultad de Agronomía de la UCV*

Martino AM & Díaz M. 2012. Características físico naturales de la fila de Montecano, Península de Paraguaná: bases para la propuesta de un área natural protegida. Universidad Nacional Experimental Francisco de Miranda, Centro de Investigaciones en Ecología y Zonas Áridas, Coro. Mimeografiado. 71 pp.

Matteucci S. 1986. Las zonas áridas y semiáridas de Venezuela. *Zonas áridas* (4): 39-48. Centro de Investigaciones en Zonas Áridas, Universidad Agraria La Molina, Lima.

Matteucci S & Colma A. 1997. Agricultura sostenible y ecosistemas áridos y semiáridos de Venezuela. *Interciencia* 22(3): 123-130.

Medina E, Velásquez G & Hernández Valencia I. 2016. Impacto del calentamiento global y enriquecimiento atmosférico de CO₂ sobre cultivos tropicales: la perspectiva para Venezuela. *Rev. Fac. Agron. (UCV)* 42 (1): 25-37.

Messa-Arboleda H F. 2009. Balance de gases de efecto invernadero en un modelo de producción de ganadería doble propósito con alternativas silvopastoriles en Yaracuy, Venezuela. Tesis de *Magister Scientiae* en Agroforestería Tropical. CATIE, Turrialba, Costa Rica. 225 pp.

Mistry J, Berardi A, Andrade V & Leonardos O. Indigenous fire management in the Cerrado of Brazil: The case of the Krah of Tocantins. *Hum Ecol.* 2005. 33, 365–386. doi:10.1007/s10745-005-4143-8

Montagnini, F. 1992 *Sistemas agroforestales. Principios y aplicaciones en los trópicos*. Organización para Estudios Tropicales. San José. Costa Rica. Editorial CATIE, 95 p

Montagnini F. 2015. Función de los sistemas agroforestales en la adaptación y mitigación del cambio climático. Cap. 12. pp. 269-297. En: *Montagnini F, Somarriba E, Murgueitio E, Fassola H & Eibl B. Sistemas Agroforestales. Funciones Productivas, Socioeconómicas y Ambientales. Serie técnica. Informe técnico 402*. CATIE, Turrialba, Costa Rica. Editorial CIPAV, Cali, Colombia. 454p.

Mogollón J, Rivas W, Martínez A, Campos Y & Márquez E. 2015. Carbono orgánico del suelo en un gradiente altitudinal en la Península de Paraguaná, Venezuela. *Multiciencias* 15(3): 271 – 280.

Mogollón J, Martínez A, Rivas W, Maseda C, Muñoz B, Márquez E, Lemus L, Colmenares M & Campos Y. 2015 a. Carbono orgánico como indicador del proceso de desertificación en suelos agrícolas al norte de Venezuela. *Suelos Ecuatoriales* 45(1):24-30.

Mogollón J, Rivas W, Alvizu P, Marquez E, Colmenares M, Lemus L, Hernández S & Martínez A. 2016. Calidad de la vegetación como indicador de desertificación en la Península de Paraguaná, Venezuela. *Ágora de heterodoxias* 2(2): 72-97.

Myers R. 2006. *Living with fire: sustaining ecosystems and livelihoods through Integrated Fire Management*. Tallahassee, USA, The Nature Conservancy Global Fire Initiative.

Nair PKR. 1993. *An introduction to agroforestry*. Dordrecht, Países Bajos, Kluwer Academic publishers.

Nikolakis WD & Roberts E. Indigenous fire management: a conceptual model from literature. *Ecology and Society* 25(4): 11, 2020. <<https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-11945-250411>>.

Oliveira-Miranda M A, Huber O, Rodríguez JP, Rojas-Suárez F, De Oliveira-Miranda R, Hernández-Montilla M & Zambrano-Martínez S. 2010. Riesgo de eliminación de los ecosistemas terrestres de Venezuela. Libro Rojo de los ecosistemas terrestres de Venezuela.

Ovalles FA, Cortéz A, Rodríguez MF, Rey JC & Cabrera-Bisbal E. 2008. Variación geográfica en el impacto del cambio climático en el sector agrícola en Venezuela. *Agronomía Trop.* 58(1): 37-40.

Paredes-Trejo F & Olivares Ba. 2018. Venezuela. In: Centro de Zonas Áridas y Semiáridas de América Latina y el Caribe (CAZALAC) & Programa Hidrológico Internacional de la UNESCO (PHI). *Atlas de Sequías de América Latina y el Caribe*. UNESCO & CAZALAC, eds. 203 pp.

Randerson JT, Chen Y, van der Werf GR, Rogers BM & Morton DC. 2012. Global burned area and biomass burning emissions from small fires. *Journal of Geophysical Research* 117, G04012. doi:10.1029/2012JG002128.

República Bolivariana de Venezuela. 2013. Gaceta Oficial 40.222 del 06-08-2013. Ley de Bosques.

República Bolivariana de Venezuela. 2017a. Segunda Comunicación Nacional ante la Convención Marco de las Naciones Unidas sobre Cambio Climático. Centro Simón Bolívar, Caracas-Venezuela.

República Bolivariana de Venezuela. 2017b. República Bolivariana de Venezuela. Gaceta Oficial 41.118 del 21-03-2017. Creación del Parque Nacional El Caura.

República Bolivariana de Venezuela. 2019. Estrategia Nacional Neutralidad en la Degradación de las Tierras (NDT) hacia el 2030. Informe Final Programa de Neutralidad en la Degradación de Tierras (NDT). Centro Simón Bolívar, MINEC, Caracas. 51 pp.

República Bolivariana de Venezuela. 2019. Oficio N° 00898 del 12 de agosto de 2019 del Despacho del Ministro de Ecosocialismo, dirigido al Secretario Ejecutivo de la Convención de Lucha contra la Desertificación, manifestando la voluntad del país en tomar acción para evitar, reducir y revertir la degradación de las tierras mediante la aprobación de las Metas y Medida Nacionales de Neutralidad de la Degradación de las Tierras (NDT).

República Bolivariana de Venezuela. 2005. Ley Orgánica de Pueblos y Comunidades Indígenas.

Gaceta Oficial No. 38.344. Diciembre 27, 2005. Caracas.

República Bolivariana de Venezuela. 2012. Ley Penal del Ambiente. Gaceta Oficial No. 39.913 del 02 de mayo de 2012. Caracas.

Russell-Smith J., Monagle C., Jacobsohn M., Beatty R.L., Bilbao, B. Millán A., Vessuri H. & Sánchez-Rose I. 2013. Can savanna burning projects deliver measurable greenhouse emissions reductions and sustainable livelihood opportunities in fire-prone settings? *Climatic Change* DOI 10.1007/s10584-013-0910-5

Sánchez I, Vessuri H, Barreto M & Gómez R. 2008. Red de Innovación Productiva de *Agave cocui* de Pecaya como espacio local de conocimiento, Venezuela. ALTEC, Caracas. 14 noviembre 2008.

Trauernicht C, Brook BW, Murphy BP, Williamson GJ & Bowman DMJS. 2015. Local and global pyrogeographic evidence that Indigenous fire management creates pyrodiversity. *Ecol. Evol.* 5(9), 1908–1918. doi:10.1002/ece3.1494.

Torres D, Rodríguez N, Yendis H, Florentino A & Zamora F. 2006. Cambios en algunas propiedades químicas del suelo según el uso de la tierra en el sector el Cebollal, estado Falcón, Venezuela. *Bioagro* 18(2). Disponible en http://ve.scielo.org/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S1316-33612006000200007

Van der Werf GR et al. Global fire emissions estimates during 1997–2016. *Earth System Science Data.* 9:697-720, 2017. <<https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-9-697-2017>

Welch, J.R. Xavante Ritual Hunting: Anthropogenic Fire, Reciprocity, and Collective Landscape Management in the Brazilian Cerrado. *Hum. Ecol.* 2014, 42, 47–59. doi:10.1007/s10745-013-9637-1

8. ANNEX 1

INTERNATIONAL AGREEMENTS LEGALLY APPROVED IN VENEZUELA ON CLIMATE CHANGE

INSTRUMENTO JURÍDICO	OBJETIVO	FECHA Y LUGAR DE LA FIRMA	GACETA OFICIAL
Acuerdo de París Proyecto de resolución remitido a la cumbre de las Naciones Unidas para la aprobación de la agenda para el desarrollo después de 2015 por la Asamblea General en su sexagésimo noveno período de sesiones	Transformar nuestro mundo: la Agenda 2030 para el Desarrollo Sostenible Erradicar la pobreza Mantener el aumento de la temperatura media mundial muy por debajo de 2°C con respecto a los niveles preindustriales	París 2015	30/12/2015 N° 40.819
Convenio de Estocolmo sobre Contaminantes Orgánicos Persistentes	Proteger integralmente la salud humana y el medio ambiente frente a los contaminantes orgánicos persistentes, de conformidad con el principio de precautoriedad estipulado en el principio 15 de la Declaración de Río	Estocolmo 23-05-2001	03-01-2005 N° 38.098 (Véase N° 5.754 Ext. misma fecha)
Ley Aprobatoria del Protocolo de Kyoto de la Convención Marco de las Naciones Unidas sobre el Cambio Climático	Comprometer a los Estados a implementar medidas tendientes a limitar y reducir las emisiones de Dióxido de Carbono y de gases de efecto invernadero a un nivel inferior al 5% del total de emisiones de esos gases para 1990, para el período comprendido entre el 2008-2012	Kyoto, Japón. 1997 del 22 JUL 2004	Asamblea Nacional 07-12-2004 N° 38.081
Convenio sobre el Procedimiento de Consentimiento Fundamentado Previo aplicable a ciertos Plaguicidas y Productos Químicos Peligrosos objeto de Comercio Internacional (Convenio de Rotterdam)	Promover la responsabilidad compartida y los esfuerzos conjuntos de las Partes Contratantes en la esfera del comercio internacional de ciertos productos químicos peligrosos, facilitando el intercambio de información acerca de sus características, estableciendo un proceso nacional de adopción de decisiones sobre su importación y exportación y difundiendo esas decisiones a las Partes		22-12-2004 N° 38.092
Enmienda de Montreal del Protocolo de Montreal	Establece la obligación de crear un sistema de licencias dirigido a reducir el tráfico ilegal de las sustancias que permita controlar el ingreso y egreso; así como el origen y destino de las mismas	Montreal 17-09-1997	12-06-2001 N° 32.217
Convención Internacional de Lucha contra la Desertificación	Prevención o reducción de la degradación de las tierras, rehabilitación y recuperación de las tierras degradadas.		N° 5.239 23-06-98
Enmienda de Copenhague del Protocolo de Montreal	Establece la ampliación de la lista de sustancias controladas y un nuevo calendario de eliminación para los países desarrollados y en vías de desarrollo	Copenhague 25-11-1992	04-11-1997 N° 5.180
Protocolo relativo a las áreas de flora y fauna silvestre especialmente protegidas (SPAW)	Conservación y preservación de especies raras, endémicas y en peligro de extinción		N° 36.110 18-12-1996
Convenio Marco de las Naciones Unidas sobre el Cambio Climático	Lograr la estabilización de las concentraciones de gases de efecto invernadero en la atmósfera a un nivel que impida la interferencia antropogénica peligrosa con el clima	Río de Janeiro 13-06-1992	27-12-1994 N° 4.825
Convenio Internacional de las Maderas Tropicales	Construir un marco eficaz de cooperación y consulta entre los países productores y consumidores de maderas tropicales; así como estimular la investigación y alentar el desarrollo de políticas de protección sostenible y conservación de los bosques tropicales y sus recursos genéticos	Ginebra 18-11-1983 Nueva York 26-01-1994	01-02-1994 N° 4.686 Ext. 05-12-1997 N° 5.187.
Convenio sobre la Diversidad Biológica	Conservar y preservar el máximo posible de diversidad biológica en beneficio de las generaciones presentes y futuras	Río de Janeiro 12-06-1992	12-09-1994 N° 4.780
Enmienda de Londres del Protocolo de Montreal	Establece el calendario de eliminación y crea el Fondo Multilateral del Protocolo de Montreal para cooperar con los países en desarrollo en la reconversión industrial y tecnológica	Londres 29-06-1990	21-05-1993 N° 4.580
Convención sobre la Protección del Patrimonio Mundial, Cultural y Natural de la UNESCO	Establecer un sistema eficaz de protección colectiva del patrimonio cultural y natural de valor excepcional organizado de una manera permanente y según sentido científico moderno	París 23-11-1972	06-07-1990 N° 4.191

INTERNATIONAL AGREEMENTS LEGALLY APPROVED IN VENEZUELA ON CLIMATE CHANGE

INSTRUMENTO JURÍDICO	OBJETIVO	FECHA Y LUGAR DE LA FIRMA	GACETA OFICIAL
Protocolo de Montreal relativo a las Sustancias Agotadoras de la Capa de Ozono	Proteger la capa de ozono adoptando medidas preventivas para controlar las emisiones mundiales de las sustancias que la agotan	Montreal 16-09-1987 Ajustes Londres 26-09-1990 07-03-1991	11-01-1989 N° 34.134
Convenio sobre el Comercio Internacional de Especies Amenazadas de la Fauna y Flora Silvestres (CITES)	Proteger ciertas especies de animales y vegetales que se encuentran en Peligro de Extinción Acordar medidas para proteger las especies mediante el control del comercio internacional	Washington 03-03-1973	29-06-1977 N° 2.053
Convención para la Protección de la Flora, la Fauna y de las Bellezas Escénicas Naturales de los Países de América	Establecer un sistema de protección en los países de América para la flora, fauna y medio ambiente de sus entornos	Washington 12-10-1940	13-11-1941 N° 20.643

ANNEX 2

LIST OF STAKEHOLDERS INTERVIEWED BY LANDMARC-VENEZUELA			
NAME	POSITION	INSTITUTION	CONTACT INFORMATION
Lic. Efrain Enrique León Cornivell	Director de Fiscalización y Control de Impactos Ambientales	Ministerio de Ecosocialismo (MINEC), Caracas, Venezuela	Phone: +58 424 2994667 eelcguitar6@gmail.com
Dr. Carlos Méndez	Jefe del Centro de Ecología y Ciencias Ambientales (IVIC) Jefe del Laboratorio de Ecosistema y Cambio Global (IVIC) Vice-Presidente del Grupo de Trabajo II del IPCC sobre Impactos, Adaptación, Vulnerabilidad Miembro del Advisory Board del Proyecto LANDMARC Coordinador General del Capítulo II: Inventario Nacional de Gases Efecto Invernadero, de la II Comunicación Nacional de Venezuela ante la Convención Marco de las Naciones Unidas sobre Cambio Climático, Venezuela	Instituto Venezolano de Investigaciones Científicas (IVIC), Caracas, Venezuela	Phone: +58 416 2079763 / +58 212 504 1246 carlos.menvall@gmail.com
Dr. Roberto Rivera-Lombardi	Docente e Investigador activo del Instituto de Geografía de la UCV. Ex Director de Protección y Control de Incendios Forestales (2014-2015). Colabora desde el 2019 con el Núcleo de Investigación y Monitoreo de PREVFOGO Brazil. 20 años de experiencia en teledetección del fuego y estimación de las emisiones resultantes.	Universidad Central de Venezuela (UCV), Caracas, Venezuela Ministerio de Ecosocialismo (MINEC), Caracas, Venezuela Centro Nacional de Combate y Prevención de Incendios Forestales, Brasilia, Brazil	Phone: +55 84 9833 5441 robertoriveralombardi@gmail.com
Cnel (B) Miguel Matany Luque	Primer Comandante del Cuerpo de Bomberos Forestales (INPARQUES).	Instituto Nacional de Parques (INPARQUES)/ Ministerio de	

		Ecosocialismo (MINEC), Caracas, Venezuela	+58 424 1356063 / 426 mmatanyl172@gmail.com	+58 3110496
Dra. Mirian Díaz de Arends	Presidenta de la ONG INFALCOSTA. Profesora Titular jubilada de la UNEFM.	ONG INFALCOSTA, Coro, Edo. Falcón, Venezuela Universidad Experimental Francisco de Miranda (UNEFM), Coro, Edo. Falcón, Venezuela	mdiaz541@gmail.com	
Dra. Ángela Martino	Profesora Asociada activa de la UNEFM, Investigadora activa del CIEZA	Universidad Experimental Francisco de Miranda (UNEFM), Coro, Edo. Falcón, Venezuela Centro de Investigaciones en Ecología y Zonas Áridas (Cieza), Coro, Edo. Falcón, Venezuela	amg.martino@gmail.com	
Ing. Alvaro Guerra	Analista de procesos. Coordinador de sistemas de Gestión de calidad y sistemas Agroforestales de DANAC	Fundación DANAC, San Felipe, Edo. Yaracuy, Venezuela	alvaro.guerra@danac.org.ve	

LANDMARC

ANNEX III

OVERVIEW OF INPUT TABLES FOR SIMULATION MODELLING PER COUNTRY

This project has received funding from the European Unions' Horizon2020 Grant Agreement No 869367

1. Germany

1.1. Qualitative storylines by identifying measures and actions from interviews for each LMT scenario

LMT 1: Forest Management

	1. Wishes of the future for the LMT: include timing	2. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Who pays? Who implements? 	3. Target/Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policies, strategies, projects
Scenario 1: "Reference" Stakeholder representations: Forest owners, forest administration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regenerate damaged forest areas with adapted species (including neophytes) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Existing support schemes for forest regeneration and forest conversion Private forest owners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continue existing support schemes
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maintain managed forest area for wood supply (about 97%) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Revenues from wood supply Private and state forest owners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> None
Scenario 2: "Achieve existing targets" Stakeholder representations: Forest owners, climate policymakers, government officials, forest administration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regenerate damaged forest areas with adapted species (limited share of neophytes) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased funding for natural regeneration and planting of natural species Private forest owners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adapt and extend existing support schemes for forest regeneration and forest conversion
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Take 10% of national forest area out of production (at least for 20 years) Implement national and EU targets on protected areas Increase forest carbon stocks in adapted forest 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support schemes for extensification of wood harvest, especially in broadleaved forests as an alternative to revenues from wood supply 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New support scheme Involve voluntary (carbon) markets? Guarantee of financial resources

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	<p>stands (broadleaved and mixed stands)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase biodiversity in forests 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce demand for fire wood • Private and state forest owners 	
<p>Scenario 3: “Green supreme” Stakeholder representations: NGOs, climate policymakers, government officials</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regenerate damaged forest areas with adapted species (exclude neophytes) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased funding for natural regeneration and planting of natural species • Private forest owners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adapt and extend existing support schemes for forest regeneration and forest conversion
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take 10% of national forest area permanently out of production • Take additional 10% of national forest area out of production (at least for 20 years) • Increase forest carbon stocks in adapted forest stands (broadleaved and mixed stands) • Increase biodiversity in forests 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support schemes for intensification of wood harvest, especially in broadleaved forests as an alternative to revenues from wood supply • Reduce demand for fire wood • Private and state forest owners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New support scheme • Involve voluntary (carbon) markets? • Guarantee of financial resources

LMT 2: Afforestation

	1. What are the wishes of the future for the LMT <ul style="list-style-type: none"> include timing 	2. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How much does it cost? Who pays for the cost? Who implements? 	3. Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> policies, strategies, projects
Scenario 1: “Reference” Stakeholder representations: farmers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maintain forest area 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduce loss of forests due to land conversion Deforested areas need to be compensated for Compensation areas bought by state 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> None
Scenario 2: “Achieve existing targets” Stakeholder representations: climate policymakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increase forest area 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduce loss of forest area Increase revenues from forests compared to agricultural land Farmers/land owners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incentive schemes for establishing forests on grasslands and croplands
Scenario 3: “Green supreme” Stakeholder representations: NGOs, climate policymakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increase forest area substantially 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduce loss of forest area Increase revenues from forests compared to agricultural land Lower demand for (agricultural) land Farmers/land owners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incentive schemes for establishing forests on grasslands and croplands Reduce meat /livestock production to free land

LMT 3: Organic soils

	4. What are the wishes of the future for the LMT <ul style="list-style-type: none"> include timing 	5. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How much does it cost? Who pays for the cost? Who implements? 	6. Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> policies, strategies, projects
Scenario 1: “Reference” Stakeholder representations:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> maintain agricultural area on organic soils 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> continued management on organic soils 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> none
Scenario 2: “Achieve existing targets” Stakeholder representations:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduce emissions from organic soils under forests, cropland and grassland 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Take organic soils out of production through rewetting Paludiculture Farmers/land owners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incentive schemes, including voluntary carbon market? State buying land from farmers
Scenario 3: “Green supreme” Stakeholder representations:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduce emissions from organic soils under forests, cropland and grassland 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Take organic soils out of production through rewetting Paludiculture Farmers/land owners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incentive schemes, including voluntary carbon market? State buying land from farmers

1.2. Quantitative storylines: pace of implementation for each LMT

Table 1: Quantitative trends/pace of implementation of LMT options

Year	Current situation (baseline)	Scenario 1: “Reference” Stakeholder representations: Forest owners, forest administration		Scenario 2: “Achieve existing targets” Stakeholder representations: Forest owners, climate policymakers, government officials, forest administration		Scenario 3: “Green supreme” Stakeholder representations: NGOs, climate policymakers, government officials	
	Now	2030	2050	2030	2050	2030	2050

	(provide sources)	(change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	(change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	(change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	(change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	(change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	(change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)
LMT 1: Forest management	3 % of forests not available for wood supply (NFI 2012)	3 % of forests not available for wood supply	3 % of forests not available for wood supply	7 % of forests not available for wood supply	10 % of forests not available for wood supply	10 % of forests not available for wood supply	20 % of forests not available for wood supply
LMT 2: Afforestation	Forest area 11,4 Mha in 2012 (NFI 2012)	Maintain forest area (compensate deforestation of ca. 5,000 ha per year, NIR Germany (2022))	Maintain forest area (compensate deforestation of ca. 5,000 ha per year, NIR Germany (2022))	Linear increase to 2050 value	425,000 ha	Linear increase to 2050 value	850,000 ha (BMEL 2016)
LMT 3: Soil carbon	Difficult to assess						
LMT 4: Organic soils	Area of drained organic soils 1,58 Mha (NIR 2022)	No change	No change	Linear increase to 2050 value	325,000 ha	278,000 ha (20% of drained organic soils, Prognos et al. 2020)	650,000 ha (50% of drained organic soils, Prognos et al. 2020)

References

NFI (2012): <https://bwi.info/>

NIR Germany (2022): <https://unfccc.int/documents/461716>

BMEL (2016): Klimaschutz in der Land- und Forstwirtschaft sowie den nachgelagerten Bereichen Ernährung und Holzverwendung. Bundesministerium für Ernährung und Landwirtschaft

Prognos; Öko-Institut; Wuppertal-Institut (2020): Klimaneutrales Deutschland. Studie im Auftrag von Agora Energiewende, Agora Verkehrswende und Stiftung Klimaneutralität.

2. Netherlands

2.1. Qualitative storylines by identifying measures and actions from interviews for each LMT scenario

The Netherlands: Full LMT portfolio including BECCS, rewetting, agroforestry and afforestation

	1. Wishes of the future for the LMT: include timing	2. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Who pays? Who implements? 	3. Target/Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policies, strategies, projects
Scenario 1: "Business as Usual"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continuation of existing (intensive) livestock farming practices, with associated land use, economic benefits, and social-environmental costs (0 to -5% decline can be assumed). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social-environmental costs are born by society and ecosystems. Complex system agro-food production (consumers, farmers, supermarkets, agro-food companies, guided by policy frameworks) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scenario incompatible with a range of air quality, biodiversity, water, climate policies and strategies
Scenario 2: "Scaling nature based solutions"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduction of cattle (& pig) herd size by 30-50% (range) to reduce environmental impacts and free up land for other uses. To achieve targets, this should already be achieved by 2030 or 2035. Expansion of rewetting organic / peat(y) soils in Northern and Western (coastal) provinces to keep carbon in soils, limit (damage of) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Livestock farmers and linked agro-food sector will see significant decline in revenue/profits. Compensation for these losses (or finance for buy-out schemes for farmers) will come from the public budget. Rewetting can be implemented by farmers / landowners (parcel level), but also at subregional level (for 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 30-50% reduction of livestock sector (question of balance between poultry, pig, cattle) to meet 2030-2035 - NH3 emission reduction target. Rewetting target = -1 MtCO₂-eq. emissions from peat soils by 2030 (current level at 4-7 MtCO₂-eq. per year.

	<p>soil subsidence and preserve / improve biodiversity. This could technically be scaled up rather fast by 2030-2035, simply by limiting draining the country via existing water infrastructure.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expansion of agroforestry and afforestation in Southern and Eastern part of country on sandy/clay soils to increase carbon storage in trees (and materials) while improving biodiversity. Agroforestry may scale up a bit faster as hedgerows and planting of productive trees, fiber crops can be done faster. Full scale implementation by 2050 according to a linear trajectory should be feasible. Afforestation target by 2050 could be achieved, but phase-in will likely start slower as massive amounts of seedlings need to be planted, land needs to be purchased (legal procedures). 	<p>each catchment area ‘polder’ by regional water boards). This is done by increasing water levels. In case farmers execute this, funding may come from private sector or EU agricultural funds. When done by water boards, extra water management costs may be charged to society (to fund rewetting and/or compensate farmers). This may be funded through avoided future damage costs.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agroforestry likely implemented by farmers in collaboration with expert third parties. In most cases no land acquisition needed as farmland is already owned. Farmers will need to invest, which can be funded by the market (new other market products or carbon market), or public funds (EU CAP/forestry funds). • Afforestation likely implemented by semi-public nature conservation / forestry agencies. Will entail costs for land acquisition / buy outs. Other costs involve cultivating, buying, and planting seedlings/trees. Land acquisition costs likely to come from public sources (although there are some 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agroforestry expansion set at range of 7.000-25.000 ha by 2030. <i>Dutch Forest Strategy, the total climate impact of agroforestry is quantified as part of the sector goal “trees, forest and nature” with 0.4 Mton CO₂ and 0.8 Mton CO₂ (‘ambitious goal’) in 2030. However, it is not clear yet how much of the aimed GHG emissions are assigned to non-agroforestry in this sector such as landscape elements. According to (Lesschen et al., 2021), agroforestry could contribute to 0.1 Mton CO₂, however, assuming a more ambitious target of 25,000 ha in 2030 compared to 7,000 ha mentioned in the Dutch Forest Strategy.</i> • Forest expansion outside Natura2000 (NNN) zones target for 2030 set at 19.000 ha. <i>Overall forest sector target includes increase (18,000 ha) to be realized in the so-called Nature Network the Netherlands (NNN), which includes all Dutch Natura 2000 sites, and partly (19,000 ha) outside this network in forests that are private property.</i>
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		<p>private funds also buying land). Funds for planting trees to be funded through a mix of public and private schemes (e.g., CAP/forest funds + carbon market)</p>	
<p>Scenario 3: “Scaling engineered solutions”</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction of cattle (& pig) herd size by 5-29% (range) to reduce environmental impacts and free up land for other uses. To achieve targets, this should already be achieved by 2030 or 2035. • Significant expansion of manure treatment facilities (farm-level and industrial scale plants) for production of biogas (biomethane / bio-LNG, organic fertilizers (RENURE) and captured liquid/compressed CO₂. Could theoretically be deployed to all liquid cattle/pig manure captured in stable systems (54,1 mln ton cattle manure, 8,9 mln ton pig manure (link)). Currently, about 5-10% of all animal manure is undergoing some form of manure treatment. Biogas sector has seen slow down (link) of new production coming online (0,23 BCM in 2022, 4% growth rel. to 2021). Large-scale (pig manure) plants could scale up more rapidly, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Livestock farmers and linked agro-food sector will see significant decline in revenue/profits. Compensation for these losses (or finance for buy-out schemes for farmers) will come from the public budget. • Farming sector, energy and fertilizer sector will be most involved in implementation. Energy component can be funded through a range of renewable energy subsidy schemes (e.g., feed-in premium, co-firing under EU ETS, renewable transport fuel tradable certificates) for biogas and even a green gas blending target (link) may be implemented. Also, several market-based schemes for using organic fertilizers, carbon market may apply. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5-29% reduction of livestock sector (question of balance between poultry, pig, cattle) to meet 2030-2035 - NH₃ emission reduction target. • Domestic policy target for biogas/green gas production is 2 BCM by 2030 (link). Also EU has specific strategy to increase production of biomethane (link). • No quantified target for circular agriculture, but nutrient (N, P, K and SOC) recycling can be improved significantly by enabling manure treatment to produce organic fertilizers. However, use of organic fertilizers from animal origin has been capped by EU-law. More recently Dutch farming has lost rights (link) to use 230-250 Kg animal manure N per ha. By 2026 it will be limited to 170 Kg N per ha, current derogation will be gradually phased out until 2026. This is expected to increase the use of chemical fertilizers to maintain

	relative to development of farm-scale biogas systems or biogas hubs.		productivity. RENURE (link) fertilizers are becoming more important with increasing prices for gas and chemical fertilizers.
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3. Portugal

3.1. Qualitative storylines by identifying measures and actions from interviews for each LMT scenario

Country PORTUGAL and SPAIN LMT 3: Forests and Agroforestry (Montado (Portugal) and Dehesas (Spain))

	1. Wishes of the future for the LMT: include timing	2. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Who pays? Who implements? 	3. Target/Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policies, strategies, projects
Scenario 1: “High Natural Value System” Stakeholder representations: farmers, forest and agroforestry producers, forestry associations, industry, polluting companies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Valuing the natural capital of agro-forestry companies by creating good practices in: i) carbon balance; ii) biodiversity; iii) landscape; iv) resilient territories (fire risk reduction); and v) social value, by 2050 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Polluting companies, industry pay by purchasing CO₂ credits from farmers/forestry producers Implemented by companies like AgroInsider and government based on the decree-law that creates and promotes the development of a nationwide voluntary carbon/biodiversity market CO₂ credits 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Actions start now with pilot projects Regulations on voluntary carbon market in order to create trust Montado/dehesa carbon credits certification Fire risk reduction
Scenario 2: “No change or loss” Stakeholder representations: farmers, forest and agroforestry producers, forestry associations, industry, polluting companies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accelerated natural capital degradation due to production systems intensification and climate change pressure on natural resources by 2050 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The degradation will be paid by European tax payers After degradation, natural capital are difficult and sometimes impossible to completely recover 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Changes in legislation risks, for example eliminating the need for environmental and social companies compensations (e.g., ESG) Not promoting the enhancement of the

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Less resilient territories by means of high fire risks and social territory abandoned and desertification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Government funds subsidies will be used to replace and monetize losses putting more pressure on prices of goods 	territory through the preservation and protection of biodiversity and natural capital
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Country Portugal LMT 1: Cropland

	1. What are the wishes of the future for the LMT	2. How to achieve the wishes	3. Actions
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> include timing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How much does it cost? Who pays for the cost? Who implements? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> policies, strategies, projects
<p>Scenario 1: “Sustainable agricultural practices” Stakeholder representations: Farmers, consumers, food retailers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil and water conservation by means of precision agriculture practices to reduce carbon emissions and enhance carbon sequestration reducing the use of synthetic fertilizers particularly urea nitrogen type direct seedling and cover crops to improve water conservation by 2030 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Supporting financially farmers to do good practices Precision agriculture consultancy to monitor and inspect the production systems to optimize CO2-biodiversity-Soil-Plant-Water processes Farmers being trained on how to implement the sustainable agricultural practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Actions started due to the Green deal and Farm to fork European objectives Climate change is driving the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices for the efficient use of water, especially in drier regions (e.g., South of Portugal).

Country Portugal LMT 2: Grassland

	<p>4. What are the wishes of the future for the LMT</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> include timing 	<p>5. How to achieve the wishes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How much does it cost? Who pays for the cost? Who implements? 	<p>6. Actions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> policies, strategies, projects
<p>Scenario 1: “Biodiverse grasslands” Stakeholder representations:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Swon biodiverse pastures rich in legumes and grasses can increase three times more the organic matter that can rapidly grow in the soil and hence to increase carbon sequestration and promote floristic biodiversity to pollinators by 2050 Soil pH correction to promote biomass yield (e.g., in Montado/Dehesa) by 2050 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Supporting financially farmers to sow biodiverse pastures rich in legumes and grasses and to correct soil pH Farmers are the ones who implement these practice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> According to the trajectories for carbon neutrality of the Portuguese economy and Circular Economy by 2050 To reduce the use of nitrogen fertilizers and its environmental impact, increase the production of biomass and soil fertility and contribute to an increase in the volume and quality of dairy/meat production To reduce production costs and consumption of concentrated feed and raw materials needed for its manufacture

3.2. Quantitative storylines: pace of implementation for each LMT

Year	Current situation (baseline)	SCEN-“ High Natural Value System” SH perspective:		SCEN-“No change or loss” SH perspective:	
	Now (provide sources)	2030 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2050 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2030 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2050 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)
LMT 3: Forest and Agroforestry (Montado & Dehesa)	In decline, high animal load (Pinto-Correia et al. 2013); Loss of 1 tree ha/year in the Iberian Peninsula due to climate change (3 M trees in the Iberian Peninsula), ≈9 M ton/year of CO ₂ .	Achieve maintaining the current state by reducing the rate of degradation	Recover the stock of CO ₂ by the densification carried out 40 years ago in an annual growth of 9 M ton/year of CO ₂ . Burned area of 50 thousand ha per year Creation of new forest in non-forested areas per plantation of 410 thousand ha of new plantations by 2050	If climatic pressure increase and production systems intensification are kept, degradation can be doubled reaching 18 M ton/year of CO ₂ .	If climatic pressure increase and production systems intensification are kept, degradation can be triple reaching 27 M ton/year of CO ₂ . Plant trees that are more adapted to climate change.
LMT 2: Grassland	Poor grasslands predominate – i.e., natural/spontaneous grasslands not fertilized or sown –	20% of farmers plant biodiverse pastures	an increase, by 2050, of biodiverse pasture areas corresponding to 50% of the areas		

	representing, on average, 73% of the total surface of meadows and permanent grasslands.		occupied by meadows and permanent pastures improved and sown on clean land Net sequestration of 0.76 Mt in 2050		
LMT 3: Cropland	Some PA front runners in Portugal implemented sustainable practices and exploitation of resources considering the European Policies (e.g., Green Deal and Farm to Fork) GHG agriculture emissions to total national emissions of 9.8 % in 2017; Organic farming area represents 6% of the agricultural area*	Increase in productivity and a more efficient use of resources Increase carbon sinks with low GHG emissions from agriculture of 6.8 MtCO ₂ eq in 2015 (83% of animal sector and 17% of mineral fertilisers, lime correctors and crop residues not removed from agricultural lands)	emissions from agriculture will have a weight in national emissions between 29% and 34% by 2050 an increase, by 2050, of direct sowing areas corresponding to 50% of the areas occupied by rainfed cereals and maize -1.5%/year of consumption per hectare of synthetic nitrogen fertilizers		

* Organic farming has low impact per unit area but is limited in nitrogen.

Organic farming needs agroecological and circular economy improvements to be feasible globally.
(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0959378021000923>)

References

Pinto-Correia, Teresa, and José Mira Potes. "Livro verde dos montados." (2013).

4. Spain

4.1. Qualitative storylines by identifying measures and actions from interviews for each LMT scenario

Spain LMT 1: Dehesas management, Extremadura and Western Andalucía, Spain

	1. Wishes of the future for the LMT: include timing	2. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Who pays? Who implements? 	3. Target/Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policies, strategies, projects
<p>Scenario 1 (Go all Green): “Increase of investments and improvement of the dehesa” Stakeholder representations: Public administrations, scientific community, dehesa landowners, farming associations, nature conservation associations</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recognition of dehesas as agro-ecosystems that provide ecosystem services (biodiversity, landscape, carbon sink, soil protection, public and recreational use...) and receive economic income for it (2040). Improved management practices by landowners following investments in training and regeneration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ecosystem services are monetised. The profitability of traditional uses (pasture, cork, firewood...) is improved. Added value is invested in the regeneration of dehesas (tree planting and grassland improvement). CAP Fruitful investments in research to slow down the mortality rate of oak trees. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pilot projects from 2023 Spanish legislation promotes investments in conservation and regeneration of the dehesa Dehesa finds the right place and is recognised with its specific value in the CAP in 2030 Promotion of carbon credits for best management practices Job creation in rural areas
<p>Scenario 2 (Halfway is enough): “Natural and social evolution of the current situation in the dehesa” Stakeholder representations: Public administrations, scientific</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dehesas are maintained with public support for regeneration and landowner investment from the direct 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public aid for regeneration and drought control Investments by landowners from traditional use benefits 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pilot projects from 2030 Progress in the legislation of the dehesa but this agro-ecosystem is still not

community, dehesa landowners, farming associations, nature conservation associations	benefits of agro-silvo-pastoral resources (2035).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical and scientific advances against the dryness of kermes oak trees • CAP 	recognised with its specific value in the CAP in 2030.
Scenario 3 (The population crisis in rural areas worsens): "Progress of desertification and the drying up of the Iberian quercine trees (oaks)" Stakeholder representations: Public administrations, scientific community, dehesa landowners, farming associations, nature conservation associations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dehesas are in progressive degradation, aggravated by drought and the advance of desertification (2050). • No solutions are found and the abandonment of dehesas is increasing due to lack of profitability (2040). • Public aid for regeneration and investments by landowners are insufficient to halt the degradation of the agro-ecosystems of the dehesa. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public support for regeneration and drought control is very low • Little investment by landowners due to the low profitability of the systems. • Quercus plantations and pasture improvements only in very specific areas. • Quercus mortality does not find solutions in agroforestry science. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilot projects from 2030 • Progress in the legislation of the dehesa but this agro-ecosystem is still not recognised with its specific value in the CAP in 2040. • Administrative bureaucracy is not simplified

Spain LMT 2: Grasslands management for soil regeneration and carbon storage, Spain

	1. Wishes of the future for the LMT: include timing	2. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who pays? • Who implements? 	3. Target/Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policies, strategies, projects
Scenario 1 (Go all Green): "Valorisation of grasslands with new uses such as carbon sequestration and storage,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Livestock management of extensive pastures is carried out with greater sustainability criteria. It increases activity based on 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecosystem services are monetised and rents are obtained on carbon markets. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilot projects from 2023 • EIP AGRI invests in operational groups related to good practices, grassland

<p>improved agro-livestock practices, etc.” Stakeholder representations: Public administrations, scientific community specialised in soils and grasslands, owners of large grasslands, agricultural and livestock associations, nature conservation associations.</p>	<p>organic fertilisation and good soil and grassland practices.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extensive grazing increases its added value to the traditional use of livestock pastures, and provides ecosystem services (biodiversity, landscape, carbon sink, soil protection, hydrological regulation and green filter...) that are recognised and receive economic income for it (2040). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved profitability of traditional uses (pastures, regulation of the hydrological cycle, organic agriculture, etc.). • Added value is invested in grassland regeneration, sowing of more biodiverse grassland species. • Fruitful research investments to curb grassland degradation • Better management practices by landowners who also invest in soil regeneration and holistic management. 	<p>management and carbon grazing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CAP distinguishes more types of grassland, including irrigated grassland, and recognises their agrarian and holistic value by 2030 • Job creation in rural areas
<p>Scenario 2 (Halfway is enough): “Maintenance of the current grassland situation, extensive livestock farming, best farming practices” Stakeholder representations: Public administrations, scientific community specialised in soils and grasslands, owners of large grasslands, agricultural and livestock associations, nature conservation associations.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Livestock management of extensive pastures is carried out with greater sustainability criteria. • It increases activity based on organic fertilisation and good soil and pasture practices (2040). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improves the profitability of traditional uses (pastures, regulation of the hydrological cycle, organic farming, etc.). • Added value is invested in grassland regeneration, sowing of more biodiverse grassland species. • Fruitful research investments to curb grassland degradation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilot projects from 2023 • EIP AGRI invests in operational groups related to good practice and grassland management • CAP distinguishes different types of grassland and recognises their agricultural value in 2030

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Better management practices by landowners who also invest in soil regeneration 	
<p>Scenario 3 (<i>The population crisis in rural areas worsens</i>): "Degradation of grasslands and gradual abandonment of traditional uses"</p> <p>Stakeholder representations: Public administrations, scientific community specialised in soils and grasslands, owners of large grasslands, agricultural and livestock associations, nature conservation associations.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Grasslands are in progressive deterioration aggravated by drought and advancing desertification (2050). No solutions are found and the abandonment and degradation of soils and grasslands increases due to lack of profitability (2040). Public aid for regeneration and investments by landowners are insufficient to halt the degradation of livestock pastures. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public support for regeneration and drought control is very low Little investment by landowners due to the low profitability of the systems. Sowing of grass legumes and pasture improvements only in very specific areas. Desertification is causing increasing problems and no solutions to soil erosion and degradation are being found. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pilot projects for pasture improvement and soil regeneration from 2030 onwards Administrative bureaucracy is not simplified and aid for pasture improvement is becoming more complicated The CAP does not make a clear commitment to extensive grazing land.

Spain LMT 3: Forest planning and management in Spain

	1. Wishes of the future for the LMT: include timing	2. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Who pays? Who implements? 	3. Target/Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policies, strategies, projects
<p>Scenario 1 (<i>Go all Green</i>): "Simplification of legal forest planning and management and increased forestry investments"</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Digitalisation, applied innovation, simplification of forest management and increased forestry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public administrations and forest owners. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pilot projects on forest management at different scales.

<p>Stakeholder representations: Public administrations, technical and scientific forestry community, forest owners, forestry companies, forestry associations, nature conservation associations</p>	<p>investments from integrated and multi-scale perspectives.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The inventory of natural resources and forest management at different territorial scales is optimised and technical and administrative procedures are facilitated. 2035 • Commitment to innovation and forestry digitalisation. 2030 • Forests increase their added value to the traditional use of woody and non-woody forest uses, and provide ecosystem services (biodiversity, landscape, carbon sink, soil protection, hydrological regulation and green filter...) that are recognised and receive economic income for it (2040). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecosystem services are monetised, rents are obtained in carbon markets. • Improved profitability of traditional uses (timber and non-timber, hunting and fishing, recreational use, regulation of the hydrological cycle, ...). • Added value is invested in forest restoration and preventive forestry to fight forest fires. • Successful research investments to curb desertification, biodiversity loss and forest fires • Better forestry practices by landowners who also invest in protection and defence of the forest system. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investments in forestry works increase in the general state budgets • Pilot projects on forests as a carbon sink. • EIP AGRI invests in operational groups related to more sustainable forestry practices and carbon sinks (2023). • The balance between timber and non-timber forest productivity and forest ecosystem services are the pillars of forest policy and management. • Decarbonisation strategy in Spain 2050. • Carbon sequestration and storage by forests is contemplated in the economic exploitation plan. • Job creation in rural areas
<p>Scenario 2 (Halfway is enough): “Simplification of legal forest planning and management and increased forestry investments” Stakeholder representations: Public administrations, technical and</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The inventory of natural resources and forest management at different territorial scales is optimised and technical and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public administrations and forest owners. • It improves the profitability of traditional uses (timber and non-timber, hunting and fishing, recreational 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilot projects on forest management at different scales. • Pilot projects on forests as a carbon sink.

<p>scientific forestry community, forest owners, forestry companies, forestry associations, nature conservation associations</p>	<p>administrative procedures are facilitated. 2045</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Commitment to innovation and digitalisation of forestry. 2040 • Carbon sequestration and storage by forests is included in the economic exploitation plan. 	<p>use, regulation of the hydrological cycle, ...).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Added value is invested in forest restoration and preventive silviculture to fight forest fires. • Better forestry practices by landowners who also invest in protection and defence of the forest system. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EIP AGRI invests in operational groups related to more sustainable forestry practices and carbon sinks. • The balance between timber and non-timber forest productivity and forest ecosystem services.
<p>Scenario 3 (The population crisis in rural areas worsens): "Abandonment of rural areas, increase in forest fires" Stakeholder representations: Public administrations, technical and scientific forestry community, forest owners, forestry companies, forestry associations, nature conservation associations</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical and administrative procedures are not facilitated. 2035 • Investment in forest innovation stagnates. • Traditional forestry is not profitable and there is a progressive abandonment of rural areas and forests (2040). • Large forest fires are devastating abandoned forests, biodiversity and carbon stocks in trees and soil. • Erosion is increasing and desertification is advancing on the Iberian Peninsula. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public administrations and forest owners. • Payments for ecosystem services are non-existent or very low. • Reduced profitability of traditional forest uses and increased operating costs. • Insufficient investment in forest restoration and preventive silviculture to fight forest fires. • Mediterranean forestry is practised only on forest land where it is profitable. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forest management does not overcome bureaucratic burdens and is maintained under complex conditions that make it difficult. • Forestry policy does not take fair account of the demography of rural areas. • The general state budgets do not provide for sufficient investment to make life and welfare attractive in rural areas.

Spain LMT 4: Afforestation/reforestation of agriculture degraded areas, Spain

	1. Wishes of the future for the LMT: include timing	2. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Who pays? Who implements? 	3. Target/Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policies, strategies, projects
<p>Scenario 1 (Go all Green): “Increased investment in afforestation of agricultural degraded land” Stakeholder representations: Public administrations, technical and scientific farming and forestry community, owners of degraded agricultural land, forestry companies, agricultural associations, nature conservation associations</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Degraded land condemned to desertification is transformed into new forests in 2050 with a promising horizon for 2075. Agro-ecosystems providing ecosystem services (biodiversity, landscape, carbon sink, soil protection...) and receiving economic rent for it (2040) Investments are made in reforestation and maintenance of reforestations. Job creation in rural areas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public administrations and landowners. Ecosystem services are monetised, rents are obtained in carbon markets. Investments are made in reforestation and maintenance of reforestations. Job creation in rural areas Fruitful research investments to curb desertification and biodiversity loss. Better management practices by landowners following investments in training and regeneration. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reforestation programmes for degraded agricultural land from the 1990s and early 2000s are being revived. Reforestation pilot projects for carbon sinks. EIP AGRI invests in operational groups related to reforestation of agricultural land and monitoring of results. Decarbonisation strategy in Spain 2050.
<p>Scenario 2 (Halfway is enough): ”Maintaining the status quo” Stakeholder representations: Public administrations, technical and scientific farming and forestry community, owners of degraded agricultural land, forestry companies, agricultural</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Existing reforestations are maintained, but there is no significant investment in new reforestation of degraded land. Investments are made in reforestation and maintenance of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public administrations and landowners. Ecosystem services are monetised, but revenues are not sufficient. Very limited rents are obtained in carbon markets. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reforestation programmes for degraded agricultural land are very specific and insufficient for the territory. Reforestation pilot projects for carbon sinks. Decarbonisation strategy in Spain 2050.

<p>associations, nature conservation associations</p>	<p>reforestations, but they are not sufficient to improve the employment structure in rural areas.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research investments to curb desertification predominate over implementation investments for reforestation, leading to mismatches between science, technique and real solutions. • Better management practices by landowners following investments in training and regeneration. 	
<p>Scenario 3 (<i>The population crisis in rural areas worsens</i>): "No significant investment in afforestation of agricultural land" Stakeholder representations: Public administrations, technical and scientific farming and forestry community, owners of degraded agricultural land, forestry companies, agricultural associations, nature conservation associations</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Abandoned agricultural land is progressively deteriorating, aggravated by drought and the advance of desertification (2050). • Erosion increases and desertification advances in the Iberian Peninsula. • No solutions are found and the abandonment of agricultural land increases due to the lack of profitability (2040). • The problems of rural depopulation worsen. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public administrations and forest owners. • CAP • Payments for ecosystem services are non-existent or very low. • Public aid for reforestation of agricultural land and investments by landowners are insufficient to halt land degradation. • Quercus plantations and pasture improvements only in very specific areas. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administrative bureaucracy is not simplified. • Forestry policy does not take into account the demography of rural areas. • State budgets do not provide for sufficient investment to make life and welfare attractive in rural areas.

4.2. Quantitative storylines: pace of implementation for each LMT

	Current situation (baseline)	Scenario 1 (Go all Green): SH perspective: Public administrations, technical and scientific community, landowners, agricultural associations, private sector, nature conservation associations		Scenario 2 (Halfway is enough): SH perspective: Public administrations, technical and scientific community, landowners, agricultural associations, private sector, nature conservation associations		Scenario 3 (The population crisis in rural areas worsens): SH perspective: Public administrations, technical and scientific community, landowners, agricultural associations, private sector, nature conservation associations	
Year	Now (provide sources)	2030 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2050 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2030 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2050 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2030	2050
LMT 1: Dehesas management	Area: 2 million hectares of dehesa in Spain in need of efficient management (Extremadura and Andalucía Regional Government).	15% of the territory with improved management (Extremadura and Andalucía Regional Government)	40% of the territory with improved management (Extremadura and Andalucía Regional Government)	10% of the territory with improved management (Extremadura and Andalucía Regional Government)	20% of the territory with improved management (Extremadura and Andalucía Regional Government)	10% of the territory is degraded (Extremadura and Andalucía Regional Government)	25% of the territory is degraded (Extremadura and Andalucía Regional Government)
LMT 2: Grasslands management for soil regeneration and carbon storage	1,27 million hectares of permanent pasture in organic farming in Spain (Government of Spain)	0.25% annual extensive grasslands in organic farming area increase. 35% Sustainable management practices in grasslands (Government of Spain)	1% annual extensive grasslands in organic farming area increase. 70% Sustainable management practices in grasslands (Government of Spain)	0.10% annual extensive grasslands in organic farming area increase. 15% Sustainable management practices in grasslands (Government of Spain)	0.25% annual extensive grasslands in organic farming area increase. 25% Sustainable management practices in grasslands (Government of Spain)	0.15% annual extensive grasslands in organic farming area decline. 10% Sustainable management practices in grasslands (Government of Spain)	0.35% annual extensive grasslands in organic farming area decline. 20% Sustainable management practices in grasslands (Government of Spain)
LMT 3: Forest planning and management	Forest area: 27 million hectares of forest in Spain (Juntos por los bosques)	0.6% annual forest area increase.	0.7% annual forest area increase.	0.25% annual forest area increase.	0.35% annual forest area increase.	0.25% annual forest area decline.	0.35% annual forest area decline.

		50% Sustainable maintenance of the forest area (Juntos por los bosques)	70% Sustainable maintenance of the forest area (Juntos por los bosques)	30% Sustainable maintenance of the forest area (Juntos por los bosques)	50% Sustainable maintenance of the forest area (Juntos por los bosques)	20% Sustainable maintenance of the forest area (Juntos por los bosques)	30% Sustainable maintenance of the forest area (Juntos por los bosques)
LMT 4: Afforestation/reforestation of agriculture degraded areas	Baseline: 730,000 ha of degraded agricultural land reforested (Iglesias Ranz et al 2021)	2% annual increase in reforestation of agricultural land and maintenance programmes (Government of Spain)	4% annual increase in reforestation of agricultural land and maintenance programmes (Government of Spain)	0.5% annual increase in reforestation of agricultural land and maintenance programmes (Government of Spain)	1.5% annual increase in reforestation of agricultural land and maintenance programmes (Government of Spain)	No annual increase in agricultural land reforestation and maintenance programmes. 0.5% annual increase in agricultural land degradation. (Government of Spain)	No annual increase in agricultural land reforestation and maintenance programmes. 2% annual increase in agricultural land degradation. (Government of Spain)

References

- EIP-AGRI, 2018. Focus Group Grazing for Carbon.
- Fernández Nogueira, D., Corbelle Rico, E., 2017. Cambios en los usos de suelo en la Península Ibérica: un meta-análisis para el período 1985-2015. Rev. Bibliográfica Geogr. y Ciencias Soc. 22.
- Fuentes Pazos, M., Zamora Rojas, E., Gallardo Cobos, R., Lara Vélez, P., 2018. Servicios ecosistémicos de la dehesa. Proyecto LIFE BioDehesa.
- Government of Spain, 2021a. Proyecto de Ley de cambio climático y transición energética. (621/000020). Senate, Madrid, Spain.
- Government of Spain, 2021b. Registro de huella de carbono, compensación y proyectos de absorción de dióxido de carbono [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/cambioclimatico/temas/mitigacion-politicas-y-medidas/registro-huella.aspx> (accessed 5.21.21).

- Government of Spain, 2021c. Bosques españoles y su evolución [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/desarrollo-rural/temas/politica-forestal/inventariocartografia/inventario-forestal-nacional/index.aspx> (accessed 5.21.21).
- Government of Spain, 2020a. Plan Nacional de Adaptación al Cambio Climático 2021-2030. Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico, Madrid.
- Government of Spain, 2020b. Informe final sobre las acciones del sector del uso de la tierra, del cambio de uso de la tierra y de la silvicultura de España [WWW Document]. URL https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/cambio-climatico/temas/mitigacion-politicas-y-medidas/informeaccioneslulucfart10decision529diciembre2020_tcm30-520352.pdf (accessed 4.8.21).
- Government of Spain, 2020c. Estrategia de descarbonización a largo plazo 2050. Madrid, Spain.
- Government of Spain, 2015. Información sobre acciones en el sector del uso del suelo, cambio de uso del suelo y silvicultura de España.
- Government of Spain, 2003. Ley 43/2003, de 21 de noviembre, de Montes. Madrid, Spain.
- Government of Spain, 2002. Plan Forestal Español. Madrid, Spain.
- Horrillo, A., Gaspar, P., Escribano, M., 2020. Organic farming as a strategy to reduce carbon footprint in dehesa agroecosystems: A case study comparing different livestock products. *Animals* 10, 162. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10010162>
- Howlett, D.S., Moreno, G., Mosquera Losada, M.R., Nair, P.K.R., Nair, V.D., 2011. Soil carbon storage as influenced by tree cover in the Dehesa cork oak silvopasture of central-western Spain. *J. Environ. Monit.* 13, 1897–1904. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c1em10059a>
- Iglesias Ranz, Á., Ceballos Aranda, J., Jovellar Lacambra, L.C., Sánchez Martín, Á., 2021. Programa de forestación de tierras agrarias en Castilla y León. Desarrollo y avance de resultados. *Montes* #143 14–22.
- in+dehesa, 2020. Convenio interadministrativo de colaboración entre la Consejería de Medio Ambiente y Rural, Políticas Agrarias y Territorio de la Junta de Extremadura para el desarrollo de acciones de desarrollo sostenible y adaptación al cambio climático de la dehesa.
- J.M.H., Hooper, D.U., Butterfield, B.J., Cardinale, B.J., 2017. The economic value of grassland species for carbon storage. *Sci. Adv.* 3, e1601880. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.1601880>
- Juutinen, A., Ahtikoski, A., Lehtonen, M., Mäkipää, R., Ollikainen, M., 2018. The impact of a shortterm carbon payment scheme on forest management. *For. Policy Econ.* 90, 115–127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2018.02.005>
- Kay, S., Graves, A., Palma, J.H.N., Moreno, G., Roces-Díaz, J. V., Aviron, S., Chouvardas, D., Crous-Duran, J., Ferreiro-Domínguez, N., García de Jalón, S., Măcișan, V., Mosquera-Losada, M.R., Pantera, A., Santiago-Freijanes, J.J., Szerencsits, E., Torralba, M., Burgess, P.J., Herzog, F., 2019a. Agroforestry is paying off – Economic evaluation of ecosystem services in European landscapes with and without agroforestry systems. *Ecosyst. Serv.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2019.100896>

5. Sweden

5.1. Qualitative storylines by identifying measures and actions from interviews for each LMT scenario

Sweden LMT 1: BECCS

	1. Wishes of the future for the LMT: include timing	2. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Who pays? Who implements? 	3. Target/Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policies, strategies, projects
Scenario 1: “Favourable” Stakeholder representations: big Private stakeholders, small participants, government	By 2045: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low investment and operating costs Low energy prices combined with high CO2 prices No or few issues when deployed in practice (technology maturity) CO2 underground storage is secured Small scale BECCS becomes viable Broad investment support nationally and from the EU Ambitious climate policy framework requiring negative emissions for net zero targets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Payment: established voluntary CO2 markets Payment: government investment Implementation: private actors including power generators and pulp and paper industry, shipping industry and international underground storage providers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lifting of Regulatory barriers Stable and predictable economic conditions International cooperation Ambitious carbon pricing

<p>Scenario 2: "Unfavourable" Stakeholder representations: Big Private stakeholders, government</p>	<p>By 2045:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investment and operating costs are higher than anticipated • Infrastructure investment cost too high • High energy and feedstock prices, and low CO2 prices • Failure to establish CO2 storage outside of Sweden • Negative shift in public opinion on biomass or negative emissions • Competing uses for biomass are more attractive • Lack of investment support nationally and from the EU 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Payment: government and EU investment • Implementation: private actor in power generation sector, local underground storage providers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policies in place are half way to include demand pull measures for the technology • Still on-going plans to involve the public in policymaking • More rigorous sustainability demands on forestry and agriculture
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Sweden LMT 2: Biochar

	Wishes of the future for the <ul style="list-style-type: none"> include timing 	1. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How much does it cost? Who pays for the cost? Who implements? 	2. Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> policies, strategies, projects
Scenario 1: “Favourable” Stakeholder representations: Agricultural stakeholders (farmers), carbon market intermediaries, industrial participants	By 2045 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low investment and operating costs Low energy prices combined with high CO2 and biochar prices Additional values of biochar are found to be highly useful Medium to large scale biochar plants are viable Ambitious carbon and biochar pricing Heating providers switch to biochar Knowledge sharing among cities promotes use of biochar for urban gardening projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Several large markets for biochar are established and for their carbon credits Payment: voluntary markets Implementation: municipalities (use) and private operators (production) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Established voluntary CO2 markets Stakeholder initiatives in bio-coal and biochar pave the way for more deployment
Scenario 2: “Unfavourable” Stakeholder representations: small producers, local producers, policymakers	By 2045 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investment and operating costs are higher than anticipated 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementation: Small pilots Dependent on private investment decisions and/or municipal funding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of markets for biochar NET incompatible uses for biochar are prioritised

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High energy and feedstock prices, and low CO₂ prices • Negative shift in public opinion on biomass or negative emissions • Usefulness of biochar found to be low • Competing uses for biomass are more attractive • Lack of interest from municipalities to implement biochar initiatives. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More rigorous sustainability demands on forestry and agriculture
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5.2. Quantitative storylines: pace of implementation for each LMT

	Current situation (baseline)	SCEN-“ Favourable ” SH perspective: Stakeholder initiatives in CCS and BECCS pave the way for more		SCEN-“ Unfavourable ” SH perspective: Negative shift in public opinion on biomass or negative emissions	
Year	Now (Karlsson et al. 2020)	2030 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2050 -> 2045 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2030 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2050 -> 2045 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)
LMT 1: BECCS	0 CO ₂ emissions captured and stored ¹	Deployment rate would be 0.535 Mton CO ₂ /y: 2 Mtonnes CO ₂ -eq per year ¹ are captured and stored	Deployment rate would be 0.535 Mton CO ₂ /y: By 2045	Deployment rate would be 0.08 Mton CO ₂ /y: 0.5 Mtonnes CO ₂ -eq per year ¹ are captured and stored	Deployment rate would be 0.08 Mton CO ₂ /y: By 2045

¹ <https://www.regeringen.se/rattsliga-dokument/statens-offentliga-utredningar/2020/01/sou-20204/>

			10 Mtonnes CO ₂ -eq per year ¹ are captured and stored		around 2 Mtonnes CO ₂ -eq per year ¹ are captured and stored
LMT 2: Biochar	0.001 Mtonne CO ₂ -eq per year mitigated ²	Deployment rate would be 0.078 Mton CO ₂ /y: 0.7 Mtonne CO ₂ -eq per year are mitigated ²	Deployment rate would be 0.078 Mton CO ₂ /y: By 2045 1.8 Mtonne CO ₂ -eq per year ¹ are mitigated	Deployment rate would be 0.0078 Mton CO ₂ /y: 0.07 Mtonne CO ₂ -eq per year are mitigated ²	Deployment rate would be 0.0078 Mton CO ₂ /y: By 2045 0.18 Mtonne CO ₂ -eq per year are mitigated ²

² <https://stud.epsilon.slu.se/18289/1/martelius-s-2022705.pdf> and <https://www.biochar-industry.com/2022/european-biochar-market-report-2021-2022-available-now/> and <https://bitrix24.tbm.tudelft.nl/~DlvW7>

6. Switzerland

6.1. Qualitative storylines by identifying measures and actions from interviews for each LMT scenario

Switzerland Organic Agriculture:

	1. Wishes of the future for the LMT: include timing	2. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Who pays? Who implements? 	3. Target/Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policies, strategies, projects
Scenario 1: "Max growth" Stakeholder representations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - FiBL - BioSuisse - IP-Suisse - TerraABC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 30, 35 and 40% of arable land under organic agriculture by 2030,40 and 50 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Paying for pollution (polluter pays principle). Currently indirectly subsidized (e.g. Interview TerraABC) Increase awareness for positive effects of OA increasing the demand for OA products in public canteens (e.g. Interview Regenerative CH) Implementation by farmers to satisfy the demand by policy and society 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Higher subsidies for OA, financed via increasing CO2 prices. Full payments for companies in transition. Loosening strictness of permanence for CO2 certification --> each t CO2 sequestered is positive (e.g. SH workshop J. Leifeld) Reducing animal numbers in conventional livestock, consumption of animal products --> less area needed for livestock (summary of SH of various interviews)
Scenario 2: "Delayed growth" Stakeholder representations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - IP-Suisse 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 20, 25 and 30% of arable land under organic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consumer-only driven increase of OA (increased 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Awareness campaigns of environmental co-benefits (and health concerns)

- BioSuisse	agriculture by 2030,40 and 50	awareness) (e.g. Interview IP-Suisse; demand-driven)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local actions are main driver (e.g. "Community-supported agriculture)
Scenario 3: "Stagnating at current area "	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Area remains at about 20% of arable land 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No new resources directed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No additional policies (e.g. SH workshop SBV, no additional money, not attractive to farmers)

Switzerland Reduced/ No-Tillage:

	1. What are the wishes of the future for the LMT: include timing	2. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How much does it cost? Who pays for the cost? Who implements? 	3. Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> policies, strategies, projects
Scenario 1: "Focus on RT and NT expansion" Stakeholder representations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Swiss NT Regenerativ CH T. Friedrich SBV (see highest potential) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> By 2050, almost no areas with normal tillage remain. 60% of area is RT, 20% NT by 2050 (relative % of NT increases), only 20% conventional tillage remain as exception areas RT/NT in %: 2030, 40,6; 2040, 50, 12; 2050, 60, 20 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Subsidized through "Ressourceneffizienzbeiträge (up to 250 CHF ha-1 yr-1)" Implemented by farmers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Subsidies further increased More awareness campaigns on co-benefits of NT/RT (e.g., SNT-guides, paid by BAFU https://no-till.ch/publikationen/)
Scenario 2: "RT increase but little NT " Stakeholder representations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> SBV (want fair compensation) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RT and NT are scaled slower, NT remains at niche (10% of NT and RT area combined, as current, <u>Agrarbericht 2022 - Ressourceneffizienzbeiträge</u>) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Subsidized through "Ressourceneffizienzbeiträge (up to 250 CHF ha-1 yr-1)" Implemented by farmers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No further increase in subsidies A little additional money through CO2 market Awareness raising only by private initiatives

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RT/NT in 2030, 36/4%, 2040, 41/4.5%, 2050, 45/5% of arable land 		
Scenario 3: “No change”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RT remains at about 30% of arable land, also no increase in NT 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No new resources directed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No additional policies (e.g. SH workshop SBV, no additional money, not attractive to farmers)

Switzerland Agroforestry:

	4. What are the wishes of the future for the LMT <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • include timing 	5. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How much does it cost? • Who pays for the cost? • Who implements? 	6. Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • policies, strategies, projects
Scenario 1: “Silvoarable and silvopasture” Stakeholder representations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Agroscope interview (AF has highest additionality) - First climate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Half of permanent grassland becomes silvopasture land. 2030: 10%, 2040, 25% 2050, 50% • Experimental application of silvoarable on 10% of arable land. 2030: 2%, 2040, 4% 2050, 10% 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Paid through Swiss government: <u>Biodiversitätsbeiträge (admin.ch)</u> • Implemented by farmers and owners of land • Additional payments through CO2 certificates for trees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subsidies for silvopasture and silvoarable • Subsidies further increased • Awareness campaigns of agroforestry co-benefits • Additional research for most suitable silvoarable systems in Switzerland
Scenario 2: “Only silvopasture” Stakeholder representations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Agroscope interview (AF has highest additionality) - SBV interview (limited potential) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 30% of permanent grassland becomes silvopasture land. 2030: 5%, 2040, 15% 2050, 30% 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Paid through Swiss government: <u>Biodiversitätsbeiträge (admin.ch)</u> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subsidies only for silvopasture • Awareness campaigns of agroforestry co-benefits

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No expansion to arable land due to land pressure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implemented by farmers and owners of land Additional payments through CO2 certificates for trees 	
Scenario 3: “No agroforestry “ -	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No relevant increase in agroforestry area (stagnates at ~2% of agriculture area (arable + pasture land)). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No new resources directed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No additional policies (e.g. SH workshop SBV, no additional money, not attractive to farmers)

6.2. Quantitative storylines: pace of implementation for each LMT

	Current situation (baseline)	SCEN-“Max out all” SH perspective:		SCEN-“Medium ambition” SH perspective:		SCEN-“ Low hanging fruits” SH perspective	
Year	Now (provide sources)	2030 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2050 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2030 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2050 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2030 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2050 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)
LMT 1: OA	18% <u>Agrarbericht 2022 - Produktionssystembeiträge</u>	24% of area is organic	30% of area is organic (area is limited by RT/NT)	20% of area is organic	25% of area is organic	20% of area is organic	22% of area is organic
LMT 2: RT/NT	RT~18% of arable land NT~2% <u>Agrarbericht 2022 - Ressourceneffizienzbeiträge</u>	30% RT 6% NT	50% RT 20% NT	25% RT 4% NT	40% RT 10% NT	25% RT 3% NT	40% RT 4% NT
LMT 3: Agroforestry	~2% <u>Biodiversitätsbeiträge (admin.ch)</u>	10% silvopasture 2% silvoarable	50% silvopasture 10% silvoarable	5% silvopasture 1% silvoarable	35% silvopasture 5% silvoarable	5% silvopasture 0% silvoarable	20% silvopasture 0% silvoarable

7. Ukraine

7.1. Qualitative storylines by identifying measures and actions from interviews for each LMT scenario

Ukraine Organic Farming / RT-NT / Agroforestry (shelterbelts) / Bioenergy:

	1. Wishes of the future for the LMT: include timing	2. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Who pays? Who implements? 	3. Target/Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policies, strategies, projects
Scenario 1: “Balanced mix” Stakeholder representations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Agroecology - UTC (Ukrainian technological company) - ISSAR - Yuzefo-Mykolayivska Biogas Company LLC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 20, 35 and 40% of arable land under organic agriculture by 2030,40 and 50; by 2050, almost no areas with normal tillage remain; returning 10% by 2030, and 15% by 2050 of cultivated agricultural lands to natural landscapes by taking them out of cultivation, turning them into pastures, hayfields, fallows, and buffer strips, creating field-protective forest strips in the form of ecological corridors connecting biodiversity habitats; the total production of biogas and biomethane by 2050 may reach 6.0 billion m³ of CH₄ per year. 25% of the total amount (1.5 billion m³/year) is predicted to be used as raw biogas for combined heat and power generation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> paying for pollution (polluter pays principle) <u>GOVUA</u>; Increase awareness for positive effects of organic food production, increasing the demand for organic products; implementation by farmers to satisfy the demand by policy and society; the European Union through the implementation of programs on the adaptation of farming in accordance with the legislation of Ukraine to the legislation of the European Union in the agro-industrial complex <u>MinAgro</u> paid through European Investment Bank <u>UBN</u>, <u>GOVUA</u> to technological companies and UA government (<u>UTC</u>). State Budget, international loans and the EU donor aid. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> higher subsidies for OA, financed via increasing CO₂ prices; additional money through CO₂ market; Subsidies for the creation of forest protection strips; Development of new approaches to improve the investment attractiveness of land resources in order to expand biodiversity and expand the list of export commodity items; <u>2050 LOW EMISSION DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY</u>; subsidies only for the creation of shelterbelts; soil protection and restoration strategies; strategy for the development of biogas complexes paid through European Investment Bank, private companies;

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • German-Ukrainian cooperation in the field of organic agriculture; • <u>state environmental policy of Ukraine to 2030, UA environmental policy</u>
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7.2. Quantitative storylines: pace of implementation for each LMT

	Current situation (baseline)	SCEN-“Max” SH perspective:		SCEN-“Medium” SH perspective:		SCEN-“ Low” SH perspective	
Year	Now (provide sources)	2030 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2050 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2030 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2050 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2030 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2050 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)
LMT 1: Organic Farming	5% <u>GOVUA</u>	20% of area is organic	40% of area is organic	15% of area is organic	35% of area is organic	10% of area is organic	20% of area is organic
LMT 2: RT-NT/Agroforestry (shelterbelts)	RT~10% of arable land NT~3% A(S) - 5% <u>GOVUA</u>	RT - 20% NT - 10% A(S) - 10%	RT - 30% NT - 20% A(S) - 15%	RT - 15% NT - 8% A(S) - 8%	RT - 25% NT - 15% A(S) - 11%	RT - 12% NT - 4% A(S) - 8%	RT - 15% NT - 10% A(S) - 10%
LMT 3: Bioenergy	0,5 billion m3 <u>ECOET</u>	1,6 billion m3	3,5 billion m3	1,2 billion m3	2,0 billion m3	1,0 billion m3	1,5 billion m3

References

Are ATM given in the tables. The interviews, SH comments where I got the idea from. Furthermore, the websites for baselines etc.

8. Burkina Faso

8.1. Qualitative storylines by identifying measures and actions from interviews for each LMT scenario

Burkina Faso LMT 1: Agroforestry

	1. Wishes of the future for the LMT: include timing	2. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Who pays? Who implements? 	3. Target/Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policies, strategies, projects
Scenario 1: “Max growth” Stakeholder representations:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agroforestry increased by 70% by 2030 (1.9 million hectares) and by 150% by 2050 (4 million hectares) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> it can involve a combination of government, international donors, private sector actors, community-based organizations, farmers, extension agents, non-governmental organizations, and other stakeholders. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop and implement policy and institutional frameworks that support agroforestry. Provide financing mechanisms such as grants, subsidies, loans, and insurance to enable stakeholders to invest in agroforestry practices. Loosening strictness of permanence for CO2 certification --> each t CO2 sequestered is positive Provide technical assistance, capacity building, and research and development to enhance the knowledge

			<p>and skills of stakeholders in agroforestry practices.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involve local communities in the design, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation of agroforestry practices to ensure their ownership, sustainability, and effectiveness.
<p>Scenario 2: “Slow growth” Stakeholder representations:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agroforestry increased by 20% by 2030 (0.5 million hectares) and by 80% by 2050 (2 million hectares) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • it can involve a combination of government, international donors, private sector actors, community-based organizations, farmers, extension agents, non-governmental organizations, and other stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide financing mechanisms such as grants, subsidies, loans, and insurance to enable stakeholders to invest in agroforestry • Support implementations led by farmers, extension agents, NGOs, and other stakeholders, with support from the government and other partners.
<p>Scenario 3: “Stay as current”</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agroforestry stays at 13% (2.7 million hectares of Burkina Faso’s land area) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No new resources directed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No additional policies (e.g. SH workshop SBV, no additional money, not attractive to farmers)

Burkina Faso LMT 2: Cropland Management

	1. What are the wishes of the future for the LMT: include timing	2. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How much does it cost? Who pays for the cost? Who implements? 	3. Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> policies, strategies, projects
Scenario 1: “Max growth” Stakeholder representations:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> By 2050, almost all farm areas are following best practices in managing their land. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> significant investment from the government, private sector, and development partners. The specific cost of these interventions would depend on the technologies and practices used, but they would likely require long-term investment and sustained commitment to achieving sustainable results. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National Agricultural Investment Plan (NAIP) National Rural Land Use Plan (PNFDR) Agricultural Value Chains Development Project (AVCDP) Sustainable Land Management Project (PROGRES)
Scenario 2: “Slow growth” Stakeholder representations:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> By 2050, 40% of the arable land under organic agriculture 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Farmers and NGO’s only driven project at local scale 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Awareness campaigns of environmental co-benefits (and health concerns) Building resilience to climate change: To achieve that, farmers would need access to drought-resistant crop varieties, soil conservation practices, and agroforestry systems.

Scenario 3: “ Stay as current”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By 2050, 15% of the arable land under organic agriculture 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No new resources directed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No additional policies (e.g. SH workshop, no additional money, not attractive to farmers)
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Burkina Faso LMT 3: Forest Management

	4. What are the wishes of the future for the LMT: include timing	5. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How much does it cost? • Who pays for the cost? • Who implements? 	6. Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • policies, strategies, projects
Scenario 1: “Max growth” Stakeholder representations:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By 2050, all forest areas are protected and managed in a sustainable way. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding could come from a variety of sources, including domestic and international sources. Domestically, the government of Burkina Faso could allocate funds from its national budget for forest management activities. Internationally, funding could come from bilateral and multilateral development partners, as well as private sector investment. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This could involve developing policies and regulations to promote sustainable forest management practices, as well as engaging with the private sector to encourage sustainable supply chains and investments in sustainable forest management. • Expansion of protected areas: This could involve the creation of new national parks and reserves, as well as the expansion of existing protected areas. • Strengthening law enforcement: This could

			<p>include training and equipping forest rangers and other law enforcement personnel, as well as improving monitoring and enforcement activities to combat illegal logging.</p>
<p>Scenario 2: “Slow growth” Stakeholder representations:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By 2050, 50% of the forest areas are protected and managed in a sustainable way. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding could come from similar sources as the Max Implementation Scenario, including domestic and international sources but with much lower capacity and scale. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incremental strengthening of law enforcement: This could involve a phased approach to training and equipping forest rangers and other law enforcement personnel, as well as improving monitoring and enforcement activities. • Gradual promotion of sustainable forest management: This could involve a phased approach to developing policies and regulations to promote sustainable forest management practices, as well as engaging with the private sector to encourage sustainable supply chains and investments in sustainable forest management.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gradual promotion of sustainable forest management: This could involve a phased approach to developing policies and regulations to promote sustainable forest management practices, as well as engaging with the private sector to encourage sustainable supply chains and investments in sustainable forest management.
<p>Scenario 3: “ Stay as current”</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By 2050, 12% of the forest areas are protected and managed in a sustainable way. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No new resources directed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintaining current protected areas: This would involve continuing to manage existing national parks and reserves without expanding them. • Maintaining current law enforcement efforts: This would involve continuing current monitoring and enforcement activities without strengthening them. • Maintaining current forest management practices: This would involve continuing to manage forests according to

			current policies and regulations without promoting sustainable forest management practices.
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Burkina Faso LMT 4: Afforestation and Reforestation

	7. What are the wishes of the future for the LMT: include timing	8. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How much does it cost? Who pays for the cost? Who implements? 	9. Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> policies, strategies, projects
Scenario 1: "Max growth" Stakeholder representations:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> By 2030, the forest cover in Burkina Faso would increase by approximately 5%. By 2050, the forest cover in Burkina Faso would increase by approximately 15%. The country would have restored 5 million hectares of degraded land by 2030. The country would have planted over 1 billion trees by 2050. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The cost of implementing this scenario would depend on various factors, including the extent of afforestation and reforestation efforts, the types of interventions used, and the level of community engagement. According to the World Bank, the cost of restoring one hectare of degraded land in Burkina Faso ranges from \$250 to \$1,500, depending on the level of intervention. Therefore, restoring 5 million hectares of degraded land by 2030 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developing and implementing policies that support afforestation and reforestation, such as forest restoration programs, sustainable land management practices, and community-based forest management initiatives. Mobilizing resources and funding from both national and international sources to support afforestation and reforestation efforts. Strengthening institutional capacity and coordination among relevant government

		<p>could cost between \$1.25 billion and \$7.5 billion.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The cost of implementing this scenario could be paid for by a combination of sources, including the government, international donors, and the private sector. The government could allocate resources from the national budget to support afforestation and reforestation efforts, while international donors could provide funding through programs such as the Green Climate Fund or the World Bank's Forest Carbon Partnership Facility. The private sector could also contribute through corporate social responsibility initiatives or investments in sustainable forest management. 	<p>agencies, civil society organizations, and local communities.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promoting awareness and education on the importance of afforestation and reforestation for ecosystem services and livelihoods.
<p>Scenario 2: “Slow growth” Stakeholder representations:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> By 2030, the forest cover in Burkina Faso would increase by approximately 2%. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The cost of implementing this scenario would be lower than Scenario 1. For example, restoring 2 million hectares of degraded land 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prioritizing afforestation and reforestation efforts in areas where the benefits are highest, such as areas with high biodiversity, ecosystem

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By 2050, the forest cover in Burkina Faso would increase by approximately 10%. • The country would have restored 2 million hectares of degraded land by 2030. • The country would have planted over 100 million trees by 2050. 	<p>by 2030 could cost between \$0.5 billion and \$3 billion</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The cost could be shared among various stakeholders, including the government, international donors, private sector partners, and local communities. 	<p>services, and/or high vulnerability to climate change.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fostering partnerships between the government, private sector partners, civil society organizations, and local communities to mobilize resources and expertise for forest restoration efforts. • Providing incentives for sustainable land use practices that promote both food security and forest restoration. • Strengthening institutional capacity and governance for effective forest management.
<p>Scenario 3: “Stay as current”</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By 2030, the forest cover in Burkina Faso would remain at approximately 14%. • By 2050, the forest cover in Burkina Faso would remain at approximately 14%. • The country would not have restored any degraded land by 2030. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No new resources directed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The country would not implement any new efforts towards afforestation and reforestation. • The country would not have restored any degraded land by 2030. • The country would not have planted any new trees by 2050.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The country would not have planted any new trees by 2050. 		
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8.2. Quantitative storylines: pace of implementation for each LMT

Table 2: Quantitative trends/pace of implementation of LMT options

Year	Current situation (baseline) (provide sources)	SCEN-“ Max growth ” SH perspective:		SCEN-“ Slow growth” SH perspective:		SCEN-“ stay as current” SH perspective	
		2030 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2050 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2030 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2050 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2030 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2050 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)
LMT 1: Agroforestry	13%	70% increase	150% increase	20% increase	70% increase	0%	0%
LMT 2: Cropland management	15%	50% of arable land	100% arable land	20% of arable land	40% of arable land	0%	0%
LMT 3: Forest Management	12%	30% of forest areas	100% of forest areas	20% of forest areas	50% of forest areas	0%	0%
LMT 4: Afforestation and Reforestation	14%	Increase by 5%	Increase by 15%	Increase by 2%	Increase by 10%	0%	0%

9. Indonesia

9.1. Qualitative storylines by identifying measures and actions from interviews for each LMT scenario

Indonesia LMT 1: Reforestation

	1. Wishes of the future for the LMT: include timing	2. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Who pays? Who implements? 	3. Target/Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policies, strategies, projects
Scenario 1: “HIGH” Stakeholder representations: DKLH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] Bali government initiates restoration on the significant area of the degraded land by 2030 (Stakeholder Interview, 2023). [LANDSHIFT] The Indonesian government put the 20 year-target (2011 – 2030) of the significant forest area for reforestation (KLHK document). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] International Donors fund projects while DKLH (Bali forestry agency) and local stakeholders (KPH) implements and maintains. [LANDSHIFT] International donors will fund projects in different scale (local/pilot, city, and province). [LANDSHIFT] All monitoring will be done by DKLH (provincial forest agency) and the database is submitted nationally to KLHK (Ministry of Environment and Forestry - MOEF). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] Reforestation of 2,000 Ha / year from DKLH (Bali forestry agency). [LANDSHIFT] The Indonesian government published the National Forestry Plan 2011-2030. [LANDSHIFT] Intensive rehabilitation is centred on priority areas and relies entirely on government funding (APBN), its counterpart focuses on involving local communities

			<p><i>in reward-based rehabilitation activities.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> [LANDSHIFT] Within 2015-2019, intensive and incentive methods have contributed to forest and land rehabilitation as vast as 308 thousand ha and 873 thousand ha.
<p>Scenario 2: "LOW" Stakeholder representations:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] Bali government keeps the initial effort in restoration (20%) on the degraded land without any improvement. [LANDSHIFT] The Indonesian government keeps the initial effort in reforestation (25%) on the forest area without any improvement. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] Only depend on the National Budget (APBN). [LANDSHIFT] Only depend on the national budget (APBN). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] Achieve 50% of the restoration on the degraded land in Bali. The Indonesian government keeps the incentive method only for big players in reforestation (big companies and organisations), and not improve the incentive method for smallholders.

Indonesia LMT 2: Peatland Restoration

	<p>1. What are the wishes of the future for the LMT</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> include timing 	<p>2. How to achieve the wishes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How much does it cost? Who pays for the cost? Who implements? 	<p>3. Actions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> policies, strategies, projects
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<p>Scenario 1: "HIGH" Stakeholder representations:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [LANDSHIFT] Indonesia aims to keep emissions from peatlands constant to the 2010 level (the draft National REDD+ Strategy). • [LANDSHIFT] The Indonesian government will reduce emissions from peat decomposition and fires through peatland restoration (revegetation/rehabilitation) in the significant area of degraded peatland. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [LANDSHIFT] MOEF established the Peatland Restoration Agency (BRG) to manage and facilitate peatland restoration in seven priority provinces, which make up around 40% of the nation's total land area: Riau, Jambi, South Sumatra, West Kalimantan, Central Kalimantan, South Kalimantan, and Papua. • [LANDSHIFT] International funds under REDD+ will have some projects for peatland restoration in Indonesia 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [LANDSHIFT] The amended regulation increases protections for the peat ecosystem, by permanently stopping the issuance of new license on selected areas of peatland in 2019 through the Permanent Moratorium Policy.
<p>Scenario 2: "LOW" Stakeholder representations:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [LANDSHIFT] The Indonesian government keeps the initial effort in peatland restoration (38%) without any improvemet. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [LANDSHIFT] Only depend on the national budget (APBN). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No improvement in monitoring the peatland moratorium.

Indonesia LMT 3: Agroforestry

	<p>4. What are the wishes of the future for the LMT</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> include timing 	<p>5. How to achieve the wishes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How much does it cost? Who pays for the cost? Who implements? 	<p>6. Actions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> policies, strategies, projects
<p>Scenario 1: “HIGH” Stakeholder representations:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] Bali government will fulfill the target to implement agroforestry in all potential areas (Stakeholders Interview). [LANDSHIFT] The government set a target of accelerating agroforestry in 2023-2030. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] Bali government will increase the area of the social forest. [ALCES] International donors will fund more agroforestry projects. [LANDSHIFT] Aspects of agroforestry management access are spread across 33 provinces, 380 districts, 2,315 sub-districts, and 4,294 villages in Indonesia. Beneficiaries are 1.2 million families or equivalent to 5 million people. [LANDSHIFT] The development of Social Forestry Business Groups (KUPS) until 2022 has formed 10,068 KUPS. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] North-east Bali projects. [ALCES] Award Program for CSR contribution by DKLH (Bali Forest Agency). [LANDSHIFT] Agroforestry is the program priority of the current president and ministry. [LANDSHIFT] To strengthen collaboration among facilitators, a Social Forestry Facilitator Communication Forum has been established in five regions.

<p>Scenario 2: "LOW" Stakeholder representations:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [ALCES] Bali government keeps the initial effort in agroforestry (20%) without any improvement. • [LANDSHIFT] The Indonesian government keeps the initial effort in agroforestry implementation (19.5%) without any improvement (KLHK doc). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [ALCES] Depend only on the National Budget (APBN). • [LANDSHIFT] Only depend on national budget (APBN). • [LANDSHIFT] There is no acceleration on legal access/permission for the agroforestry implementation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [ALCES] Engage with current communities (ALCES). • [LANDSHIFT] Less additional members for facilitators. • [LANDSHIFT] Less additional members for Agroforestry Business Group in the community scale.
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Indonesia LMT 4: Soil Carbon (Biogas and Bioenergy)

	<p>7. What are the wishes of the future for the LMT</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • include timing 	<p>8. How to achieve the wishes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How much does it cost? • Who pays for the cost? • Who implements? 	<p>9. Actions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • policies, strategies, projects
<p>Scenario 1: "HIGH" Stakeholder representations:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [E3ME] The Indonesian government will focus on the clean energy transition, including the increase of bioenergy installation (IESR doc). • [E3ME] The GHG production will increase till 2030, then 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [E3ME] Indonesia will implement a carbon tax for coal-fired power plants starting April 1, 2022. The tax will be based on an emission cap and will apply a rate of Rp30.00 per kilogram of CO₂e. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [E3ME] Potential feedstock for bioenergy Indonesia are varied from palm oil waste, sugarcane, tapioca, paddy, and other agriculture and agroforestry waste. The total potential electricity from all feedstock are 56.97 GW.

	<p>decrease gradually till 2050 (IESR doc).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [E3ME] Indonesia will be predicted to have the booming commodity export in 2030 and 2050. 		
<p>Scenario 2: "LOW" Stakeholder representations:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [E3ME] The Indonesian government will use current and low scenario where there is no significant improvement in renewable energy and coal power retirement (IESR doc). • [E3ME] There is no significant change in the increase trend of the GHG production (IESR doc). • [E3ME] The Indonesia government use the current condition where there is no improvement in the commodity export in 2030 and 2050. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [E3ME] Only depend on current key players in the renewable energy plantation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [E3ME] There is no prohibition for new coal power plant.

Indonesia LMT 5: Cropland Management

	10. What are the wishes of the future for the LMT <ul style="list-style-type: none"> include timing 	11. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How much does it cost? Who pays for the cost? Who implements? 	12. Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> policies, strategies, projects
Scenario 1: “HIGH” Stakeholder representations:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] 0.79% of the rice field area will decrease annually due to the land use change. [ALCES] The Bali government targets 7,132 ha/year of organic rice field increasing. [LANDSHIFT] The Indonesia government targets all rice farming practices to be rice intensification process (SRI). [LANDSHIFT] The Indonesian government targets 1.9% of rice production increasing annually. [LANDSHIFT] The Indonesian government targets to have 100% organic farm of the total agriculture farm in 2050. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] The Bali government through the Agricultural agency and Center of Agricultural Technology Assessment take in charge in monitoring the rice field area. [LANDSHIFT] The Indonesia government will collaborate with local farmer groups through the agricultural agency at the city level to access the national (APBN) and donor funds. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] The subak system will manage the sustainable water and field management in the sub-village level. [ALCES] The regional regulation No 08 Year 2020 about organic farming. [LANDSHIF] The first rice intensification implementation was introduced in 1999. [LANDSHIFT] The National Regulation No 41 Year 2009 about the protection of sustainable food land.

Scenario 2: "LOW" Stakeholder representations:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] 2.05% of the rice field area will decrease annually due to the land use change. [ALCES] The Bali government targets 5,000 ha/year of organic rice field increasing. [LANDSHIFT] The Indonesian government targets 0.61% of rice production increasing annually. [LANDSHIFT] The Indonesian government targets to have 50% organic farm of the total agriculture farm in 2050. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] Bali government only depend on DAK (Special Allocation Budget) from each village. [LANDSHIFT] The Indonesia government only depends on the national budget and there is no improvement in the number of projects. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] Some subak systems are not working well. [LANDSHIFT] The sustainable farming practices are not applied in all regions well.
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9.2. Quantitative storylines: pace of implementation for each LMT

	Current situation (baseline)	SCEN-"HIGH" SH perspective: DKLH Bali		SCEN-"LOW" SH perspective:	
Year	Now (provide sources)	2030 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2050 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2030 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2050 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)
LMT 1: Reforestation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] 43,000 Ha of Degraded land in Bali 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] 20,000 Ha of degraded land are restored 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] All degraded land are already 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] 50% or 10,000 ha of degraded land with annual 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] restoration on 50% or 21,500

	<p>(Stakeholder Interview, 2023).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> [LANDSHIFT] 800,000 ha per year nationally with survival rates of 90 percent (BAPPENAS, 2022). 	<p>through annual restoration of 2,000 Ha (Stakeholder Interview, 2023).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> [LANDSHIFT] 11.55 million ha of reforestation in 2030 (KLHK, 2018). [LANDSHIFT] Reach an emission level at minus 140 Mt CO₂e by 2030 (MOEF, 2022b). 	<p>reforested / afforested (Stakeholder Interview, 2023).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> [LANDSHIFT] 24 million ha of reforestation in 2050 [LANDSHIFT] Reach an emission level at minus 304 Mt CO₂e by 2050 (MOEF, 2022a). 	<p>restoration 1,000 ha.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> [LANDSHIFT] 2 million ha of reforestation in 2030 with 200,000 ha per year nationally (KLHK, 2020). 	<p>ha of degraded land.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> [LANDSHIFT] 6 million ha of reforestation in 2030 with 200,000 ha per year nationally.
LMT 2: Peatland Restoration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [LANDSHIFT] 301,800 ha of peatland restoration in 2020 and 272,000 ha annually (BAPPENAS, 2022). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [LANDSHIFT] the area for peat restoration until 2030 should reach 2.72 million hectares (KLHK, 2021). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [LANDSHIFT] 8.16 million ha achieved for peat restoration by 2050. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [LANDSHIFT] 1.04 million ha of peatland restoration by 2030 with 104,000 ha per year (38% of the target) (KLHK, 2021). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [LANDSHIFT] 3.12 million ha of peatland restoration achieved by 2050.
LMT 3: Agroforestry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] 23,000 Ha of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] More farmers are 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] All agroforestry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] 5,000 ha of potential 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] 15,000 ha of potential

	<p>agroforestry exists in Bali with another 55,000 Ha of potential agroforestry land (Stakeholder Interview, 2023).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [LANDSHIFT] 5 million ha agroforestry in 2020. 770,000 ha of agroforestry annually (MOEF, 2021). 	<p>more open to implementing agroforestry in social forests. 15,000 ha of potential agroforestry implemented with annual implementation 1,500 ha (Stakeholder Interview, 2023).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [LANDSHIFT] 12.7 million ha of agroforestry with legal access and the addition of 25,000 facilitators. 	<p>potential has been fulfilled (Stakeholder Interview, 2023).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [LANDSHIFT] 22.7 million ha of agroforestry by 2050. 	<p>agroforestry are implemented with annual potential agroforestry implementation 500 ha.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [LANDSHIFT] 6.5 million ha of agroforestry with 150,000 ha (19.5%) annually. 	<p>agroforestry can be implemented with annual potential agroforestry implementation 500 ha.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [LANDSHIFT] 9.5 million ha of agroforestry achieved by 2050.
<p>LMT 4: Soil Carbon (Biogas and Bioenergy)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [E3ME] 0.01 MW of bioenergy installed (biomass, biogas, biofuel and waste-to-energy) in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [E3ME] 0.59 GW of bioenergy (biomass, biogas, biofuel and waste-to-energy) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [E3ME] Bioenergy in the energy mix is 23 GW by 2050. • [E3ME] Reducing coal power 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [E3ME] 50% of coal plantation in the energy mix [ESDM doc]. • [E3ME] 3% of bioenergy installation in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [E3ME] 60% of coal plantation in the energy mix. • [E3ME] 2% of bioenergy installation in the energy mix.

	2020 (MEMR, 2023).	<p>installed by 2030.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [E3ME] Reducing coal power generation by 11% by 2030. • [E3ME] National Electricity Company (PLN) plans to retire 2-3 coal-fired power plants with a combined capacity of about 1 gigawatt by 2030. • [E3ME] GOI aims to reduce CO2 emissions by 17.2% in the energy sector. • [E3ME] GOI aims to increase the share of renewable energy in the 	<p>generation by 11% by 2030.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [E3ME] National Electricity Company (PLN) plans to 43 gigawatt of coal power plant by 2050. • [E3ME] GOI aims to reduce CO2 emissions by 100% in the energy sector by 2050. • [E3ME] GOI aims to increase the share of renewable energy in the national energy mix to 100% by 2050. • [E3ME] GDP Indonesia will be \$ 10.502 	<p>the energy mix [ESDM doc].</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [E3ME] 100% generation capacity for coal. • [E3ME] the emissions from the energy sector are to around 947 million to CO2eq (IESR doc). • [E3ME] GDP Indonesia will be \$ 28.4 billion by 2030 (Cabinet secretary, 2021). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [E3ME] 50% generation capacity for coal. • [E3ME] the emissions from the energy system are to around 950 Mton CO2eq (IESR doc). • [E3ME] GDP Indonesia will be \$ 9.12 trillion by 2030 (Cabinet secretary, 2021).
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		<p>national energy mix to 31% by 2030.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> [E3ME] GDP Indonesia will be \$ 5.424 trillion by 2030 (WEF, 2017). 	trillion by 2050 (WEF, 2050).		
LMT 5: Cropland Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] Rice 112,000 ha of rice field exist in Bali in 2020 with 1,568 ha decreasing annually (interview with local stakeholders). [ALCES] 25,000 ha of organic rice field in Bali by 2020. [LANDSHIFT] 54 million tonnes of rice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] 96,320 ha of rice field in Bali by 2030. [ALCES] 100% of rice field will be 100% organic with 7,132 ha increasing annually by 2030. [LANDSHIFT] 64.26 million tonnes of rice field by 2030 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] 64,960 ha of rice field in Bali by 2050. [ALCES] 100% of rice field will be organic by 2050 [LANDSHIFT] 84.78 million rice of rice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] 89,000 ha of rice field in Bali by 2030 with 2,300 ha decreasing annually (interview with local stakeholders). [ALCES] 75,000 ha of rice field will be organic by 2030 with 5,000 ha increasing annually. [LANDSHIFT] 57.3 million tonnes of rice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ALCES] 43,000 ha of rice field in Bali by 2050. [ALCES] 100% of rice field will be organic by 2050. [LANDSHIFT] 64.6 million tonnes of rice field production with 0.61% of

	<p>field production in 2020 (MOA, 2021).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> [LANDSHIFT] There are 75,793 ha of organic rice field in 2020 at the national level (AOI, 2016). 	<p>with 1.9% (1.026 million tonnes) increasing annually (MOA, 2021).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> [LANDSHIFT] 50% of the total rice field will be organic by 2030 (BAPPENAS, 2014). 	<p>field production by 2050 with 1.9% (1.026 million tonnes) increasing annually.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> [LANDSHIFT] 100% of the total rice field will be organic by 2050. 	<p>field production with 0.61% (0.33 million) of rice field increasing annually by 2030 (BPS, 2023b).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> [LANDSHIFT] 20% of the total rice field will be organic by 2030 (MOA, 2021). 	<p>rice field increasing annually by 2050 (BPS, 2023a).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> [LANDSHIFT] 50% of the total rice field will be organic by 2030 (MOA, 2021).
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References

AOI. (2016). Statistik pertanian organik indonesia.

BAPPENAS. (2014). Potret Rencana Aksi Daerah Penurunan Emisi Gas Rumah Kaca (RAD-GRK). Bappenas.

http://ranradgrk.bappenas.go.id/rangrk/admincms/downloads/publications/Potret_RAD-GRK.pdf

BAPPENAS. (2022). Peta Jalan SDGs Indonesia Menuju 2030. https://sdgs.bappenas.go.id/website/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Roadmap_Bahasa-Indonesia_File-Upload.pdf

BPS. (2023a). Luas Panen dan Produksi Padi di Indonesia 2022.

BPS. (2023b). Luas Panen, Produksi, dan Produktivitas Padi Menurut Provinsi 2020-2022. <https://www.bps.go.id/indicator/53/1498/1/luas-panen-produksi-dan-produktivitas-padi-menurut-provinsi.html>

Cabinet secretary. (2021). Trade Minister: Indonesian Digital Economy to Grow Eightfold by 2030 [Interview]. <https://setkab.go.id/en/trade-minister-indonesian-digital-economy-to-grow-eightfold-by-2030/>

Ditjen PPI KLHK. (2021). Peraturan dan Kebijakan terkait Perubahan Iklim. <http://ditjenppi.menlhk.go.id/peraturan-perundangan.html>

KLHK. (2018). Status Hutan dan Kehutanan Indonesia. Kementerian Lingkungan Hidup dan Kehutanan.

KLHK. (2020). Vademecum Kehutanan Indonesia. Kementerian Lingkungan Hidup dan Kehutanan.

KLHK. (2020a). National Plastic Waste Reduction Strategic Actions for Indonesia. Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK); IGES Centre collaborating with UNEP; Sustainable Waste Indonesia (SWI). <https://www.unep.org/ietc/resources/policy-and-strategy/national-plastic-waste-reduction-strategic-actions-indonesia>

KLHK. (2020b). Rencana Strategis KLHK 2020-2024. Ministry of Environment and Forestry.

KLHK. (2020d, July 28). Indonesia Melawan Sampah Plastik. Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK). Pusat Pengendalian Pembangunan Ekoregion Jawa.

KLHK. (2021). Updated Nationally Determined Contribution Republic of Indonesia. <https://www4.unfccc.int/sites/ndcstaging/PublishedDocuments/Indonesia%20First/Updated%20NDC%20Indonesia%202021%20-%20corrected%20version.pdf>

MEMR. (2019). Rencana Umum Ketenagalistrikan Nasional 2019-2038. Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources. https://gatrik.esdm.go.id/assets/uploads/download_index/files/46a85-rukkn-2019-2038.pdf.

MEMR. (2020). Laporan Kinerja Direktorat Jenderal Energi Baru, Terbarukan dan Konservasi Energi Tahun 2019. Direktorat Jenderal Energi Baru, Terbarukan and Konservasi Energi.

MEMR. (2023). Arah dan kebijakan pemanfaatan biogas dalam transisi energi Indonesia.

MOA. (2021). Renstra Pertanian.

MOEF. (2016, April 23). Indonesia Signs Paris Agreement On Climate Change.

http://ppid.menlhk.go.id/siaran_pers/browse/299#:~:text=23%20April%202016%2C%20dibaca%2079%20kali.&text=The%20Paris%20Agreement%20will%20center,the%20world's%20greenhouse%20gas%20emissions.

MOEF. (2017). Buku Strategi Implementasi NDC (Nationally Determined Contribution). Ministry of Environment and Forestry (MOEF).

MOEF. (2017). Peta Penutupan Lahan Indonesia. Peta Penutupan Lahan Indonesia. <http://webgis.menlhk.go.id:8080/pl/pl.htm>

MOEF. (2019). Statistik KLHK 2019—Kementerian LHK. https://www.menlhk.go.id/site/single_post/3714/statistik-klhk-2019

MOEF. (2019). Rencana Kehutanan Tingkat Nasional (RKTN) Tahun 2011-2030.

http://jdih.menlhk.co.id/uploads/files/P_41_2019_RKTN_2011_2030_menlhk_09022019091329.pdf.

MOEF. (2021). Updated Nationally Determined Contribution Republic of Indonesia.

<https://www4.unfccc.int/sites/ndcstaging/PublishedDocuments/Indonesia%20First/Updated%20NDC%20Indonesia%202021%20-%20corrected%20version.pdf>

MOEF. (2021). INDONESIA Long-Term Strategy for Low Carbon and Climate Resilience 2050. https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/Indonesia_LTS-LCCR_2021.pdf

MOEF. (2022a). FOLU Net Sink: Indonesia's Climate Action Towards 2030. <https://www.menlhk.go.id/uploads/site/post/1681109460.pdf>

MOEF. (2022b). Indonesia's FOLU Net Sink 2030. https://gakkum.menlhk.go.id/assets/filepublikasi/Buku_RENOPS_Indonesia_s_FOLU_NETSINK_2030.pdf

WEF. (2017). A prediction: The world's most powerful economies in 2030. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2017/02/a-prediction-the-worlds-most-powerful-economies-in-2030>

WEF. (2050). These will be the most powerful economies in the world by 2050.

10.Nepal

10.1. Qualitative storylines by identifying measures and actions from interviews for each LMT scenario

Nepal LMT 1: Afforestation/reforestation and forest management

	1. Wishes of the future for the LMT: include timing	2. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Who pays? Who implements? 	3. Target/Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policies, strategies, projects
Scenario 1: "Fully green forests" (Ideal scenario) Stakeholder representations: Federal and provincial government, Indigenous and local community, NGOs, (provincial/national)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All degraded forests reforested, full afforestation capacity achieved, completely avoid deforestation by 2050 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Government supports to restore and manage forests Local communities manages forests International carbon markets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New forest policies by 2030 that promotes forest management and new forest development Reducing ambiguity in national and federal government policies Prevent forest encroachment and land use change Strengthen institutional capacity
Scenario 2:"Midway ambition" Stakeholder representations: Provincial government, NGOs, communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Only half of degraded forest restored, half of the afforestation capacity achieved, but complete avoidance of deforestation by 2050 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Government grants Local communities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National campaign - One household one tree, one village one forest, one town one park New regulation by 2030

<p>Scenario 3: “ Prosperity through forests” Stakeholder representations: Federal government, private companies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing in government revenue from forests • Policy shift from forest conservation to commercialisation of forest , that creating friction with the interests of local communities. • Only 25% of the target achieved by 2050 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Companies pay and implement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review of current forest policy started to lease large forests for private sector. • New regulation by 2030
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Nepal LMT 2: Organic farming

	<p>1. What are the wishes of the future for the LMT</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • include timing 	<p>2. How to achieve the wishes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How much does it cost? • Who pays for the cost? • Who implements? 	<p>3. Actions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • policies, strategies, projects
<p>Scenario 1: “Fully Organic Nepal” Stakeholder representations: Local farmer cooperatives, environmental NGOs, National and provincial governments</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complete organic production by 2050 • Import substitution of inorganic fertilizers • Reduce extensive use of chemical fertilizers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Government grants and subsidies • Contract farming from companies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilot projects • New regulations by 2030 to promote organic farming and development of organic certification • Promote participatory guarantee system

Scenario 2: "Midway ambition" Stakeholder representations: Provincial government, industry,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Convert most croplands to allow new business opportunities and protect environment by 2050 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Government subsidies Voluntary carbon markets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pilot projects Regulations by 2030
Scenario 3: "Fully Organic Karnali Province" Stakeholder representation Provincial and local governments, farmer cooperatives, industries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fully organic Karnali province 25% of other provinces organic by 2040 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Government subsidy Farmer cooperatives implement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Karnali province bill of Organic agriculture bill 2018 One local government one model organic farm One cooperative one model agriculture, livestock and fisheries farm

Nepal LMT 3: Agroforestry

	4. What are the wishes of the future for the LMT <ul style="list-style-type: none"> include timing 	5. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How much does it cost? Who pays for the cost? Who implements? 	6. Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> policies, strategies, projects
Scenario 1: "Fully agroforestry" Stakeholder representations: Local community, environmental NGOs, green party (provincial/national)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Full scale market based agroforestry in all hill and mountain districts by 2050 Community based agroforestry in restored bare forests and abandoned croplands Export promotion for high value non-timber products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Government grants and subsidies Contract from companies Voluntary carbon markets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regulations on agroforestry by 2030 Amendment on existing agroforestry policy (2019), to encourage involvement of farmers in agroforestry by 2030 Simplify private forestry registration system

Scenario 2: "Midway ambition" Stakeholder representations: Provincial government, industry,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least 50% of agroforestry in hill and mountain districts by 2050 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Government grants and subsidies Voluntary carbon markets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regulations on agroforestry by 2030
Scenario 3: "Partial agroforestry" Stakeholder representation: Provincial government, local government, farmer cooperatives.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Around 25% of agroforestry in hill and mountain districts by 2050 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Government grants and subsidies Voluntary carbon markets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regulations on agroforestry by 2030

Nepal LMT 4: Improved rice management

	7. What are the wishes of the future for the LMT	8. How to achieve the wishes	9. Actions
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> include timing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How much does it cost? Who pays for the cost? Who implements? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> policies, strategies, projects
Scenario 1: "Complete climate friendly rice" Stakeholder representations: Local community, NGOs, provincial and national government)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved rice management In all rice production by 2050 Efficient fertilizer and water management in rice Better water quality in rivers and aquifers Reduced cost of production 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Government grants and subsidies for inputs (machinery and organic fertilizer and market development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regulation by 2030 New environment friendly rice labeling Research and knowledge transfer to manage problems related to improved rice management
Scenario 2: "Midway ambition" Stakeholder representations: Central and Provincial government, industry,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 50% of total rice production new improved y management by 2050 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Government grants and subsidises Farmer cooperatives and rice processors implement. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New regulation by 2030 Promotion of technology

Scenario 3: “Partial improved rice production” Stakeholder representation Provincial government, local government, farmer cooperatives.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Only 25% of total rice production in new improved management by 2050 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Government grants and subsidises Individual farmers and rice processors implement. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New regulation by 2030
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10.2. Quantitative storylines: pace of implementation for each LMT

Year	Current situation (baseline)	SCEN-“ High ambition ”		SCEN-“ Midway ambition ”		SCEN-“ Low ambition ”	
		SH perspective:		SH perspective:		SH perspective	
	Now (provide sources)	2030 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2050 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2030 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2050 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2030	2050
LMT 1: Forestry (AF/RF and FM)	40.36% of total area of the country covered by forests (DFRS 2015).						
LMT 2: Organic farming	9,361 ha certified organic (FIBL,2021) But organic by default (non certified organic) could be upto 25% of the total production (interview)						
LMT 3:Agroforestry	Data not available						
LMT 4: Improved rice management	Data not available						

11. Vietnam

11.1. Qualitative storylines by identifying measures and actions from interviews for each LMT scenario

Country Vietnam LMT 1: Agroforestry, Central Highlands

	1. Wishes of the future for the LMT: include timing	2. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Who pays? Who implements? 	3. Target/Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policies, strategies, projects
Scenario 1: "All in for agroforestry" Stakeholder representations:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nearly all monocropping systems are converted into agroforestry/intercropping systems which include at least two woody perennial species 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Value chains and government pay and scale through farmer network. Farmers implement based on recommendations from extension system. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Company net zero / sustainability commitments NDC action plan
Scenario 2: "Half-way through: Area of agroforestry doubled" Stakeholder representations:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Half of current monocropping systems are converted to agroforestry/intercropping systems which include at least two woody perennial species. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Value chain and government pay and scale through farmer network. Farmers implement based on recommendations from extension system. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Company net zero / sustainability commitment NDC action plan

Country Vietnam LMT 2: Biochar from coffee husks

	1. What are the wishes of the future for the LMT <ul style="list-style-type: none"> include timing 	2. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How much does it cost? Who pays for the cost? Who implements? 	3. Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> policies, strategies, projects

<p>Scenario 1: “All coffee wastes are converted to biochar and applied back to the soil” Stakeholder representations: Farmer cooperatives, local governments, value chain (coffee buyers, traders, processors), NGOs (DSS), UNIDO</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Convert all coffee wastes (coffee husks) to biochar instead of burning (i.e., avoided GHG emissions). • Apply the biochar back to the soil as soil amendment (improve soil health and sequester carbon in soils and potential N₂O inhibition effect). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public and private incentive mechanisms to scale biochar production and carbon credits (voluntary) to incentivize farmers applying biochar back to the soil. • Intermediary or hybrid between farmer and coffee processor would produce the biochar. • Farmers apply the biochar as soil amendment. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National Green Growth Strategy 2021-2030 • Coffee private sector commitments (i.e., net zero; regenerative agriculture) • UNIDO, DSS, ACIAR
<p>Scenario 2: “All coffee wastes are converted to activated carbon and sold on the market” Stakeholder representations:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Convert all coffee wastes (coffee husks) to biochar instead of burning (i.e., avoided GHG emissions). • Biochar is sold on the market as activated carbon. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public and private incentive mechanisms to scale biochar production. • Intermediary or hybrid between farmer and coffee processor would produce the biochar. • Activated carbon industry buyers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National Green Growth Strategy 2021-2030 • Coffee private sector commitments (i.e., net zero; regenerative agriculture) • UNIDO, DSS, ACIAR
<p>Scenario 3: “Half of the biochar is converted to biochar and applied to the soil”</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Convert half of the coffee wastes (coffee husks) to biochar instead of burning (i.e., avoided GHG emissions) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public and private incentive mechanisms to scale biochar production and carbon credits (voluntary) to incentive farmers applying biochar back to the soil. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National Green Growth Strategy 2021-2030 • Coffee private sector commitments (i.e., net zero; regenerative agriculture) • UNIDO, DSS, ACIAR

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply the biochar back to the soil as soil amendment (improve soil health and sequester carbon in soils and potential N2O inhibition effect) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Intermediary or hybrid between farmer and coffee processor would produce the biochar. Farmers apply the biochar as amendment. 	
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11.2. Quantitative storylines: pace of implementation for each LMT

	Current situation (baseline)	SCEN-“All in...” SH perspective:		SCEN-“Half-way through...” SH perspective:		SCEN-“Half-way through v2 ” SH perspective	
Year	Now (provide sources)	2030 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2050 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2030 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2050 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2030 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2050 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)
LMT 1: Agroforestry in Central Highlands	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 66-80% of coffee is currently monocropped 	33-40% coffee monocropping	10% coffee monocropping	50-60% coffee monocropping	33-40% coffee monocropping	-	-
LMT 2: Biochar use in Central Highlands	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Very little production of biochar and use as soil amendment 	460k -560k tonnes of coffee husks are converted to biochar	1.4 million tonnes of coffee husks are converted to biochar	460k -560k tonnes of coffee husks are converted to biochar	1.4 million tonnes of coffee husks are converted to biochar	300k -400k tonnes of coffee husks are converted to biochar	700k tonnes of coffee husks are converted to biochar

12.Canada

12.1. Qualitative storylines by identifying measures and actions from interviews for each LMT scenario

Canada LMT 1: Afforestation, Alberta Canada

	1. Wishes of the future for the LMT: include timing	2. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Who pays? Who implements? 	3. Target/Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policies, strategies, projects
Scenario 1: “Go all green” Stakeholder representations: Local community, environmental NGOs, green party (provincial/national), oil industry, private sector (forestry services)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nearly all cutlines restored by 2050 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Company pays for parts of the restoration Government to provide part of the funding. Implemented by local communities for economic diversification CO2 credits – access to regulated or voluntary markets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Actions start now with pilot projects Regulations by 2030 Tax credits for restoration for industry Monitoring in place to control progress and CO2 offset credits
Scenario 2:”Halfway is enough” Stakeholder representations: Provincial gov’t, oil industry, private sector (forestry services)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Only half of the cutlines need to be restored because nature will take over by 2050 Some cutlines became transportation infrastructure and communities want to keep them 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Company pays for some Gov’t grants for rest 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tax credits for reclamation Regulations to be modified by 2030
Scenario 3: ”Reclaim my way” Stakeholder representations: Provincial gov’t, oil industry, Local community, environmental NGOs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regulation requires “reclamation” not “restoration” Industry wants to reclaim the way it is easiest and lower costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Company pays for parts of it Gov’t incentives for the rest 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tax credits for reclamation Regulations to be modified by 2030 to allow other forms of reclamation industry wants

Canada LMT 2: Wetland restoration

	1. What are the wishes of the future for the LMT <ul style="list-style-type: none"> include timing 	2. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How much does it cost? Who pays for the cost? Who implements? 	3. Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> policies, strategies, projects
Scenario 1: “Go all green” Stakeholder representations: Local community, environmental NGOs, green party (provincial/national), oil industry, private sector (forestry services)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Protect all current wetlands and do not allow for new resource development in wetland areas Restore all degraded wetlands for biodiversity and ecosystems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Company pays for degraded sites Gov’t pays for protection CO2 credits – access to regulated or voluntary markets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Actions start now with pilot projects Regulations by 2030 Existing accreditation scheme Carbon tax
Scenario 2: “Halfway is enough” Stakeholder representations: Provincial gov’t, oil industry, private sector (forestry services)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Protect most wetlands allow for some new resource development Restore some degraded wetlands for biodiversity and ecosystems Convert other wetlands into forest ecosystem 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Company pays for some Gov’t grants for rest CO2 credits 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tax credits for reclamation Regulations by 2050
Scenario 3: “Reclaim my way” Stakeholder representations: Provincial gov’t, oil industry, Local community, environmental NGOs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Industry wants to reclaim (not restore) by forestry or just flooding with water (pit lakes) Looking for opportunities to use “constructed wetlands” to manage polluted water, not to restore the biological function of the wetlands 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Company pays for some Gov’t expected to provide incentives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tax credits for reclamation Regulations to be modified by 2030 to allow other forms of reclamation industry wants

12.2. Quantitative storylines: pace of implementation for each LMT

Table 3: Quantitative trends/pace of implementation of LMT options

	Current situation (baseline)	Scenario 1: “Go all green” Stakeholders: Local community, environmental NGOs, green party (provincial/national), oil industry, private sector (forestry services)		Scenario 2: “Halfway is enough” Stakeholders: Provincial gov’t, oil industry, private sector (forestry services)		Scenario 3: “Reclaim my way” Stakeholders: Provincial gov’t, oil industry, Local community, environmental NGOs	
Year	Now (provide sources)	2030 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2050 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2030 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2050 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2030 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)	2050 (change relative to the current situation) (provide sources)
LMT 1: Afforestation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1599 km² of Northern AB boreal forests leased for oil development [1] • 738.6 km² disturbed by mines and plants footprints [1] • 64% of the leased land supports wetland vegetation, 23% supports upland vegetation. • Seismic lines (cutlines) disturbed at least 1,900 km² of peatlands in Alberta [3] 	15% restoration of damaged areas [4]	80% restoration of damage areas [5]	15% restoration of damaged areas [4]	50% restoration of damage areas [6]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0% restoration of damaged areas. • 15% of area reclaimed but with no carbon uptake function [1] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0% restoration of damaged areas. • 30% of area reclaimed but with no (or very little) carbon uptake function [6]

LMT 2: Wetlands	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (see above) 	15% restoration of damaged areas [4]	80% restoration of damage areas [5]	15% restoration of damaged areas [4]	50% restoration of damage areas [6]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0% restoration of damaged areas. 1% of area reclaimed but with no carbon uptake function [1] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0% restoration of damaged areas. 5% of area reclaimed but with no (or very little) carbon uptake function [6]
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References:

[1] <http://osip.alberta.ca/library/Dataset/Details/27#>

[2] R.C. Rooney, S. E. Bayley, and D.W. Schindler, PNAS, March 27, 2012, vol. 10, no. 13, 4933–4937

[3] M. Strack, Sh. Hayne, J. Lovitt, G.J. McDermid, M. Mustafizur Rahman , S. Saraswati & Bin Xu. NATURE COMMUNICATIONS (2019) 10:2804

[4] TU Delft / Ambienta estimate on potential scale-up of pilot project in the region. LANDMARC consortium. 2022

[5] Interview with elder from local community

[6] TU Delft team. Assumptions based on limitations in policy and as a result of interview with experts.

13. Venezuela

13.1. Qualitative storylines by identifying measures and actions from interviews for each LMT scenario

Venezuela LMT 1: Integrated fire management (IFM) with an Intercultural vision (which considers local knowledge and participation of Indigenous populations and local communities).

	1. Wishes of the future for the LMT: include timing	2. How to achieve the wishes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Who pays? Who implements? 	3. Target/Actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policies, strategies, projects
<p>Scenario 1: "IFM Policies at the National Level with an intercultural vision" (more optimistic)</p> <p>Stakeholder representations: Indigenous peoples, Local communities, Academia, environmental NGOs, INPARQUES (Acronym in Spanish for National Institute of Parks), Forest Fire Department, Ministry of Eco-socialism, Hydroelectric Company, private sector (forestry services)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Development of a plan and a new law about IFM Policies at the National Level with an intercultural vision by 2030 that replace the actual Fire Suppression Policies. Training of new brigades from Forest Fire Department with and holistic formation integrating academic, technical, and local knowledge - cultural heritage, and considering human and ecological dimensions of fire in socio-ecological systems (SES). Include indigenous local communities at all hierarchical levels of decision-making and implementation of these 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> International funds for (1) and (2) (e.g., Green Fund), and the government pays for implementation (3). Bottom-up IFM implementation (including Indigenous peoples and Local communities at all stages of the process) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Permanent National Working Group on Integrated Fire Management in Venezuela (Grupo de Trabajo MIF-VEN, created under the LANDMARC project) conformed by academics, INPARQUES, Forest Fire Department Coordinators, the Director of Forest Fires of the Ministry of Ecosocialism, National Coordinator of Fire Specialties, National General Directorate of Firefighters (DGNB), Ministry of Interior Affairs, Justice and Peace. Design and proposal development of a new plan and law about about IFM Policies at the National Level with an

	<p>policies. Promote local governance.</p>		<p>intercultural vision (together with IP and LC) by 2030 that replace the actual Fire Suppression Policies.</p>
<p>Scenario 2: "IFM ghost policies" Stakeholder representations: Indigenous peoples, Local communities, Academia, environmental NGOs, INPARQUES (Acronym in Spanish for National Institute of Parks), Forest Fire Department, Ministry of Eco-socialism, Hydroelectric Company, private sector (forestry services)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Development of a plan and a new law about IFM Policies at the National Level with an intercultural vision by 2030 that replace the actual Fire Suppression Policies. 2. There are no implementation actions, nor monitoring of IFM plans. Weak relationship between IPs, LCs and government and academic members. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International funds for (1) and (2) (e.g., Green Fund), but the government does not invest for implementation for the new policies (3). • Limited IFM implementation and participation of Indigenous peoples and Local communities at all stages of the process. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efforts of the National Working Group on Integrated Fire Management in Venezuela (MIF-VEN) unsuccessful for the acceptance of the proposal and implementation of the IFM law.
<p>Scenario 3: "Exclusion - as usual - policies" Stakeholder representations: Indigenous peoples, Local communities, Academia, environmental NGOs, INPARQUES (Acronym in Spanish for National Institute of Parks), Forest Fire Department, Ministry of Eco-socialism, Hydroelectric Company, private sector (forestry services)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The design of new IFM policies is not achieved and fire suppression policies continue as yore. 2. The traditional practices of the use of fire by IP and LC continue to be prohibited (excluded), and large fires of great magnitude occur due to climate change (fire climate due to great drought, high temperatures and heat waves). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is no investment of international funds, and governments maintain fire exclusion policies (although without funds for combat or the implementation of new IFM programs), or • Government asks for loans to equip with high and expensive fire suppression technologies (and increases state indebtedness), or • Government diverts international funds granted to MFIs with local 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dissolution of the National Working Group on Integrated Fire Management in Venezuela (MIF-VEN). • No formulations of new MFI policies are made. • Restrictions and implementation by the use of fire by IP and CL are accentuated.

		participation, for other programs (or the funds disappear).	
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13.2. Quantitative storylines: pace of implementation for each LMT

	Current situation (baseline)	SCENE- 1"IFM Policies at the National Level with an intercultural vision" SH perspective: Indigenous peoples, Local communities, Academia. environmental NGOs, INPARQUES (Acronym in Spanish for National Institute of Parks), Forest Fire Department, Ministry of Eco-socialism, Hydroelectric Company, private sector (forestry services)		SCEN- 2"IFM ghost policies" SH perspective: Indigenous peoples, Local communities, Academia. environmental NGOs, INPARQUES (Acronym in Spanish for National Institute of Parks), Forest Fire Department, Ministry of Eco-socialism, Hydroelectric Company, private sector (forestry services)		SCEN- 3": "Exclusion - as usual - policies" SH perspective: Indigenous peoples, Local communities, Academia. environmental NGOs, INPARQUES (Acronym in Spanish for National Institute of Parks), Forest Fire Department, Ministry of Eco-socialism, Hydroelectric Company, private sector (forestry services)	
Year	Now (Provide sources)	2030 (Change relative to the current situation) (Provide sources)	2050 (Change relative to the current situation) (Provide sources)	2030 (Change relative to the current situation) (Provide sources)	2050 (Change relative to the current situation) (Provide sources)	2030 (Change relative to the current situation) (Provide sources)	2050 (Change relative to the current situation) (Provide sources)
LMT 1: Integrated fire management (IFM) with an Intercultural	Excluding Protected areas (PA) and Indigenous territories (IT) or areas where local	50% of wildfires [5]. The implementation of IFM programme, in savanna areas of Brazil, achieved	Lipsett-Moore et al. [10] estimated a 74% emission	Similar to the current situation, with increases in the trend of	Similar to the current situation, with higher increases in the	Increase of wildfire occurrence with respect to the current situation	Increase of wildfire occurrence with respect to the 2030 situation

<p>vision (which considers local knowledge and participation of Indigenous populations and local communities).</p>	<p>management is allowed, Venezuela shows an increase in its trends of wildfire incidence due to the initial implementation of IFM policies, land use changes and an increase of fire weather (due to climate change). [1],[2], [3], [4]</p>	<p>a 17% reduction in total burned area (from 13766 km² to 11449 km²), during 2013-2018, in comparison to the previous 5 years (2007-2012), and an estimated abatement potential of 1.71 MtCO₂e of non-CO₂ GHG over six years (0.29 MtCO₂e y⁻¹) [6],[7]. According to Australian experience, shifting the fire regime from an average of 7.6% of area burned early and 32% of area burned late to an average of 20.9% burned early and 10.9% burned late, the fire managers achieved a mean annual emissions reduction of 37.7% (116,968 tCO₂e), relative to the baseline, over the first 7 years of operations [8],[9].</p>	<p>potential, 89.3 Mt CO₂e y⁻¹ global emissions reductions of the late dry season uncontrolled wildfires through early dry season burning considering 37 countries, including Africa, South America and Australia.</p>	<p>wildfires, but with more reduced wildfire incidence in IT and PA, where local fire management is allowed) [1] [2] [3], [4]</p>	<p>trend of wildfires, but with more reduced wildfire incidence in IT and PA, where local fire management is allowed [1] [2] [3], [4].</p>	<p>(globally by a factor of 1.08 to 1.4 in the year 2030 [11]), promoted by more intense “fire weather” (under more severe climate change conditions than present), and suppression policies (that promotes fuel accumulation and limit or prohibit use local fire management, and loss of traditional local fire knowledge) [1] [3], [11], [12].</p>	<p>(globally by a factor of 1.21 to 1.27 in the year 2050, and by a factor of 1.3 to 1.57 in the year 2100 [11]), promoted by more intense “fire hazard weather” (under more severe climate change conditions than 2030*), and suppression policies (that promotes fuel accumulation, limit or prohibit use local fire management and loss of traditional local fire knowledge) [1] [3], [11], [12].</p>
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References

- [1] Bilbao, B.A.; Steil, L.; Urbieto, I.R.; Anderson, L.; Pinto, C.; González, M.E.; Millán, A.; Falleiro, R.M.; Morici, E.; Ibarnegaray, V.; Pérez-Salicrup, D.R.; Pereira, J.M.; Moreno, J.M. 2020. 'Wildfires'. In: Adaptation to Climate Change Risks in Ibero-American Countries — RIOCCADAPT Report (pp. 435–496). Madrid: McGraw-Hill.
- [2] Lizundia-Loiola, J., M.L. Pettinari & E. Chuvieco, 2020: Temporal anomalies in burned area trends: satellite estimations of the Amazonian 2019 fire crisis (Letter). *Remote Sensing*, 12, 151.
- [3] Bilbao BA, Millán A, Vessuri H, Salazar-Gascón R, Gómez-Martínez R. 2021. To burn or not to burn? The history behind constructing a new fire management paradigm in Venezuela through interculturality. Local actions of national and regional impact. *Biodiversidade Brasileira BioBrasil* Vol. International Wildland Fire Conference, (2): 99-127. DOI: 10.37002/biobrasil.v11i2.1878
- [4] Bilbao, B.; Mistry, J.; Millán, A.; Berardi, A. 2019. 'Sharing Multiple Perspectives on Burning: Towards a Participatory and Intercultural Fire Management Policy in Venezuela, Brazil, and Guyana'. In: *Fire*, 2(3), 39. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fire2030039>
- [5] República Bolivariana de Venezuela. 2019. Oficio N° 00898 del 12 de agosto de 2019 del Despacho del Ministro de Ecosocialismo, dirigido al Secretario Ejecutivo de la Convención de Lucha contra la Desertificación, manifestando la voluntad del país en tomar acción para evitar, reducir y revertir la degradación de las tierras mediante la aprobación de las Metas y Medida Nacionales de Neutralidad de la Degradación de las Tierras (NDT).
- [6] Mistry, J.; Schmidt, I.B.; Eloy, L.; Bilbao, B. 2019. 'New perspectives in fire management in South American savannas: The importance of intercultural governance'. In: *Ambio*, 48(2), 172–179. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-018-1054-7>
- [7] Falleiro, Rodrigo de Moraes, Lara Steil, Marcelo Siqueira de Oliveira, Isolde Lando, Luciana de Oliveira Rosa Machado, Ana Maria Canut Cunha and Gabriel Constantino Zacharias 2021. Histórico, Avaliação, Oportunidades e Desafios do Manejo Integrado do Fogo nas Terras Indígenas Brasileiras. *Biodiversidade Brasileira-BioBrasil*: 75-98.
- [8] Russell-Smith J, Whitehead PJ, Cooke PM (Eds). 2009. Culture, ecology and economy of savanna fire management in northern Australia: rekindling the Wurrk tradition CSIRO Publications, Melbourne.

- [9] Russell-Smith, J.; Monagle, C.; Jacobsohn, M.; Beatty, R.L.; Bilbao, B.; Millán, A.; Vessuri, H.; Sánchez-Rose, I. 2017. 'Can savanna burning projects deliver measurable greenhouse emissions reductions and sustainable livelihood opportunities in fire-prone settings?' In: *Climatic Change*, 140(1), 47–61. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-013-0910-5>.
- [10] Lipsett-Moore, G.J., Wolff, N. & Game, E. 2018. Emissions mitigation opportunities for savanna countries from early dry season fire management. *Nat Commun* 9, 2247. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-04687-7>
- [11] UNEP, 2022. *Spreading like wildfire: The rising threat of extraordinary landscape fires. A UNEP Rapid Response Assessment*.
- [12] Bedia, J., S. Herrera, J.M. Gutierrez, A. Benali, S. Brands, B. Mota & J.M. Moreno, 2015: Global patterns in the sensitivity of burned area to fire-weather: implications for climate change. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, 214, 369-379.